

**17th Conference on
Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries**

COMPIT'18

Pavone, 14-16 May 2018

**17th International Conference on
Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries**

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Edited by Volker Bertram

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Virtual Reality for Maritime Training – A Survey

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Abstract

This paper reviews literature on using Virtual Reality (VR) technology for maritime training purposes. Most applications are 3D in modelling, but not 3D in viewing. The field of published VR applications for maritime training is still small enough to be reviewed in such a paper, with few applications in commercial shipping with the notable exception of the well-established nautical simulators. The high costs for VR based training limit applications. Business cases usually appear when large assets or human health/life is at risk in real-world training.

1. “Virtual Reality” – Reality

The term 'Virtual reality' (VR) was initially coined by the artist Jaron Lanier who envisioned the user fully immersed in an artificial world completely generated by a computer. Despite significant progress in the last 20 years, we are far from this vision. While Virtual Reality has progressed from vision to industry reality, it has fallen short of expectations, compare e.g. *Rosenblum's (2000)* vision for Virtual Reality in 2020 with current state of the art and industry adaptation. The state of the art in VR applications can be summarized as follows:

1. Navigation in 3D space with look-around, walk-around, and fly-through capabilities in virtual environments. Control devices allow manipulation, operation, and control of virtual worlds. This is the minimum capability to qualify for a “Virtual reality” denotation. VR models thus always require an underlying 3D CAD model of the “world” modelled, typically enhanced by surface structure, mapped images, etc.
2. Stereoscopic viewing enhances the perception of depth and sense of space. This is a nice-to-have gadget for most training applications. Experience shows that trainees may encounter discomfort, sometimes resembling motion sickness, after 5-20 minutes of immersion in stereoscopic worlds, which has not been observed in “poor-man’s” VR on screens with trainees perceiving the normal training room environment.
3. The virtual world is presented in full scale and relates properly to human size. While important for many training applications, this aspect might be omitted on purpose in some applications (having an overview from a giant perspective or shrinking to go e.g. inside blood vessels in medical training).
4. The convincing illusion of being fully immersed in an artificial world can be enhanced by auditory, tactile and other non-visual technologies. Sound effects are common in video games; data gloves are used in some applications but interfere with the immersive feeling, *Rosenblum (2000)*.
5. Networked applications allow shared virtual environments: users at different locations (anywhere in the world) can meet in the same virtual world, see each other, communicate, and interact. Shared virtual environments appear in some cases, *Nordby et al. (2016)*, but there seems to be more the “thrill of the new” than convincing applications in an industry work context. The more people participate in shared virtual environments, the more difficult speech communication becomes. The “cocktail party effect” is amplified by the limited frequency bandwidth in electronic voice transmission.

Virtual Reality applications often use “immersive” as a marketing distinction. Stereoscopic vision using e.g. Oculus Rift glasses is then hailed as more immersive than plain PC screens (without stereoscopic vision). However, the degree of immersion depends largely on the willingness of the viewer to accept the immersion (same as with any movie).

Increased reality (level of detail, stereoscopic view, lighting effects) and model size come at a price. Pragmatic applications have just the necessary level of detail. The main cost factor is the creation of a tailored Virtual World. Many 3D models can be found for free on the internet, but specific models and elements require (sometimes prohibitively expensive) work to create. Model reuse from other applications, e.g. finite-element or CFD models, is not straightforward, Fig.1, *Lindenau and Bertram (2003)*.

Creating a VR model for a given ship is likely to take man-months. In most maritime cases, the business case does not exist (personal communication with David Thomson (AVEVA); Denis Morais (SSI): “Virtual Reality (VR) technology is still around a decade away from providing consumers with a good VR experience”, Mark Zuckerberg (CEO Facebook)).

Fig.1: Original CFD model (left) and post-processed VR model with much fewer edges (left)

Fig.2: Gartner hype cycle for emerging technologies

Still, there is reason for moderate optimism. With more and more maritime 3D models, we have more starting points to create VR models reducing the current cost. In the specific case of DNV GL, such models come typically from 3D ship modelers such as POSEIDON and NAUTICUS.

Fig.2 illustrates the mildly optimistic view on VR in the manic-depressive technology cycle, where hype is followed by disillusion, taken from Denis Morais' (SSI) blog waveform <http://blogs.ssi-corporate.com/waveform/2017/technology/industry-will-drive-enhancements-in-vr/>.

2. Virtual Reality in maritime training

2.1. Nautical Simulators

Nautical simulators are akin to Virtual Reality. Here a view of the world outside a nautical bridge is projected with other ships and waterways. The simulators generate increasingly realistic visual effects of environment (night/day, fog/rain/etc., waves) and mimic the maneuvering physics of own ship and encountered ships. Simulators range from small desktop to large full-mission solutions.

A typical solution is Simflex4 of FORCE Technology, <https://forcetechnology.com/en/maritime-industry/cargo-vessels/simulation-studies-for-maritime-operations>. The brochure mentions visual effects in 3D, but all images shown reflect standard practice of 2D displays and are far less photorealistic than state-of-the-art video games, compare Fig.3 and Fig.4. A very realistic portrait of the outside world is apparently not required to meet the training needs. FORCE Technology mentions four vital ingredients for their simulation-based training:

1. models of ships and shipping areas (= 3D worlds and maneuvering models for each ship),
2. the simulator (the display and interaction option),
3. experienced instructors (!),
4. pedagogical training methods and insights (!).

Developing such simulators is an interdisciplinary task. A video game playing a captain is much simpler than having a simulation-based training facility.

A simulator facility charges ~4000 € per day (8 h) in the simulator. Setting up a specific ship and specific environment and training crews may then cost 70000 – 110000 €. More recent entries focus more on visual effects, e.g. <https://unigine.com/en/industries/simulation/maritime>, <http://osc.no/#solutions>.

Fig.3: Nautical simulator (FORCE Technology)

Fig.4: Video game shipsim.com

2.2. Navy/military simulators

Navies employ simulators to train military staff for combat situations. The Italian provider IBR Sistemi offers a solution employing Virtual Reality technology, the “Joint Tactical Theatre Simulator”, <http://www.naval-technology.com/contractors/simulators/ibr-sistemi/>. “The scenario can be displayed on unlimited multiple screens/360[°] projections or through special stereoscopic displays and head mounted displays (HMD).” The photorealistic visuals rival state-of-the-art video games, Fig.5.

The solution is rather sophisticated, with many ships, equipment systems, geographical areas, etc. in the database.

The Bremen-based software provider Szenaris (www.szenaris.com) has developed VR based training and e-learning solutions for underwater vehicle operations, Fig.6, and submarine operation, Fig.7, Katzky (2014). The latter was for one specific submarine (U 212) and served to familiarize new crews with the submarine in a risk-free training environment. The involved effort seems too high to create a business case outside the specific naval applications.

Fig.5: High degree of photorealism in IBR Sistemi simulator

Fig.6: PC-based VR training for underwater vehicle handling

Fig.7: VR model of U212 (control room)

2.3. Ship survey simulator

DNV GL has developed SuSi (Survey Simulator), a Virtual Reality based training solution for ship inspections, www.dnvgl.com/Images/ShipManager-Survey-Simulator-flier_tcm8-58658.pdf, Wardell (2010), Kubiak (2011), see also the Appendix. SuSi provides realistic and cost-efficient 3D training software for survey inspections, using Virtual Reality technology and detailed models of ships and offshore structures, Fig.6. The virtual inspection gets trainees exposed to deficiencies that would take years for a surveyor to experience in real life. An inspection run can be recorded and discussed in a debriefing with an experienced supervisor/trainer, pointing out oversights and errors by the trainee. If trainees navigate themselves in the virtual worlds, we observed occasional problems with some train-

ees struggling with navigation or task, while others went ahead and started to get sidetracked. Alternatively, courses can be run with solely the trainer in command ensuring a common vision on a projected screen. This form of teaching, while not immersive at all, has been very well received.

The experience so far is based on blended learning, where classical classroom training alternates with SuSi-based elements. The classroom training focuses e.g. on regulations, inspection techniques or frequently found deficiencies on ships, before a virtual ship inspection starts.

Fig.8: Level of detail in SuSi (Virtual Reality based survey simulator)

In addition to the blended teaching form, SuSi combines Virtual Reality scenarios with a knowledge base of thousands of photos of actual surveyor findings linked to the deficiencies incorporated in the VR model. Trainees can then use a virtual smartphone to retrieve photos of associated real-world defects with attached text information adding to the training effect, Fig.9.

The initial vision was that SuSi would revolutionize the way we conduct (surveyor) training, *Wardell (2010)*. Eight years later it still seems to be a great training solution ahead of state of the art in maritime training, but adoption has been slower than originally envisioned. The combination of hardware requirements, surveyor competence, trainer competence, course content competence and SuSi operating competence makes global roll-out difficult, for the same reasons that potential new entries offering comparable solutions face significant hurdles. The combination of software, sophisticated scenarios, pedagogical solution and trainer competence would require significant effort to copy.

Fig.9: Virtual reality finding and corresponding real-world finding

Korean Register of Shipping (KRS) has developed its own VR-based ship survey simulator to train ship surveyors on classification rules and inspection procedures, *Kil et al. (2018)*. The 3d stereoscopic images are combined with physics engines to recreate scenarios such as drops or collisions. The player has elementary functions such as ladder climbing, photographing and hand lighting.

Fig.10: KRS ship survey simulator

2.4. Ship familiarization

The NRL (National Research Laboratory) has developed InterShip, a VR tool to familiarize personnel with the layout of a ship, Fig.11, *Wauchope et al. (2003)*, *Wauchope and Bertram (2004)*. InterShip combines VR techniques with a knowledge-based route planner (shows how to get from one compartment to another) and speech control (user can e.g. open door by command; user can query system for information, e.g. invoking route planner.) Using the head-mounted display and a hand-held joystick, users could walk through portions of a ship and ask questions about compartment names, numbers and locations. (“What compartment is this?”, “Which deck is the communications center on?”)

Fig.11: VR tool InterShip to explore a ship with glove avatar opening door

Newell and Luck (2017) describe a 3D walkthrough training system for the Queen Elizabeth Class (QEC) aircraft carriers for the Royal Navy, Fig.12. BMT used its in-house VR training solution EN-GAGE as a platform. For this new class of warships, support personnel must be safe to work onboard, requiring training. A needs analysis determined that such training would be best delivered employing a 3D walkthrough with interactive functionality based on a game-based simulation engine (augmenting classroom training). This approach provides a through-life solution, is electronically distributable and has wider possible applications. Technical information behind equipment or systems within the model can be reviewed in the virtual environment. Despite the high-quality graphics, the system is pedagogy driven and not technology driven: “[The] training system is designed around the needs of the trainee and the desired outcome, rather than just developing the highest fidelity system for the sake of it,” *Newell and Luck (2017)*. Consequently, only the QEC bridge was developed for 3D viewing with HTC Vive VR hardware, for use at public-relations and outreach events.

Fig.12: BMT’s training solution ENGAGE for aircraft carrier familiarization, *Newell and Luck (2017)*

Besides ship familiarization, further possible applications are mentioned: safety training including emergency response, escape routes, and maintenance options such as on-board transport routes for the removal/replacement of large equipment.

2.5. Marine fire-fighting

The National Research Laboratory (NRL) of the USA has investigated employing virtual reality to improve the performance of firefighters, Fig.13, *Tate et al. (1997)*. Using a mixture of physically based modeling and fractal techniques, the fire changed color and transparency levels to simulate the appearance of real flames.

Fig.13: VR fire-fighting training environment of NRL

The density of simulated smoke varied with distance to the simulated fire and could be changed by operator control. There was a measurable improvement in the performance of firefighters that used VR training over firefighters without such training. VR trained firefighters made fewer wrong turns and reached the fire faster than untrained firefighters.

The Dutch company VSTEP (www.vstepsimulation.com) offers VR based training for emergency response, e.g. fire-fighting, both for land-based applications and for ships (three different ships were modelled), vstepsimulation.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/RescueSim_Brochure_V3.5_Online.pdf. The training is designed to be part of STCW, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/STCW_Convention, requirements with blended learning combining classroom elements and supervised simulations.

2.6. Maritime safety training

Venter and Juricic (2014) describe a VR-based training using elements of video gaming to familiarize the crew of an offshore oil & gas platform with the platform and safety procedures, Fig.14. Fig.15 gives an idea of the effort involved in creating the 3D world for an oil platform with sufficient level of detail. Here a CAD vendor (Intergraph, supplying the 3d world for the platform) and a gaming specialist (Samahnzi) cooperated to create a tailored training solution. “Players” (=trainees) embraced this solution, but most likely the project received subsidies to match development costs and price expectations of the customer.

MacKinnon et al. (2016) report that such VR-based training results in faster evacuation of platforms (as measured in mock-ups with groups that were just instructed and groups that could explore the platform in VR). As in the application of *Venter and Juricic (2014)*, the improved training result is probably due to stronger involvement and interest in the offered information. As VR technology has been largely driven by the gaming industry, we can often tap into the gaming features and experience to improve training solutions.

Fig.14: Gamification of training – Scenario to train correct behavior in emergency situations, *Venter and Juricic (2014)*

Fig.15: Small part of the 3d model to create the training environment in *Venter and Juricic (2014)*

The Institute of Technical Education (ITE) in Singapore uses advanced Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality for maritime and offshore training. EON Reality and ITE partnered to create several such applications to increase the engagement of today’s digital learners, www.eonreality.com/portfolio-items/virtual-technology-training/. For example, trainees can work virtually on an oil rig, Fig.16(left). Trainees can familiarize themselves with the complex structure and various equipment used, but also

perform important safety operations in various weather conditions. The hardware park at ITE seems to be impressive, as they offer group training using holograms and CAVE-like environments with data gloves, motion tracking, etc. Apparently, ITE also uses the VR environment to create interactive learning sequences, Fig.16(right). The focus is on safety related (high-risk) training for crews on board ships and offshore platforms.

Fig.16: ITE training offers involving Virtual Reality

Lloyd’s Register announced plans for VR based training on safety issues for the oil & gas market in 2017. No further conference or journal paper is available yet. Demo versions on fairs show relatively simple scenarios, but with stereoscopic viewing via head-mounted devices.

Kil et al. (2018) present a multi-user VR-based crew training application for on-board emergency situations required by the International Safety Management (ISM) Code, Fig.17.

Fig.17: Emergency response training for crew following ISM, *Kil et al. (2018)*

2.7. Assorted other applications

The University of Sao Paulo in Brazil has developed a virtual model basin for offshore technology applications, *Gaspar et al. (2009)*, <http://tpn.usp.br/sala-de-visualizacao-4d/>. Besides high-performance computing for CFD (computational fluid dynamics), there is also a “4D visualization” hall,

Fig.18. Here an instructor guides the audience (wearing 3D glasses) through a 3D world changing in time (the fourth Dimension), while the platform moves simulating the motions of a ship. It is unclear how extensively the facility is used.

The EU-project SLIM-VRT (Self-Learning Integrated Methodology - Virtual Reality Tool), *Lambrou et al. (2006)*, <http://cordis.europa.eu/pub/ist/docs/ka3/eat/SLIM-VRT.pdf>, describes rather vaguely how VR might be embedded in maritime training, but apparently did not result in any concrete tool, despite 3 years and 2.2 M€ funding. There may be a general lesson in this, namely that significant resources are needed to develop workable and sustainable VR solutions and 3 years and 2.2 M€ may not be enough in many cases.

Fig.18: “4D visualization” hall

Fig.19: 3D scanner and view of VR view with avatar on bridge

Fig.20: Virtual Kjetil Nordby avatar appearing on a virtual nautical bridge

Nordby et al. (2016) [involving my ex-DNV GL colleague Etienne Gernez] report a rather advanced application of “mixed reality” to design ship bridges. The system enables real-time scanning of human avatars for use in VR supported design processes. The system uses off-the-shelf 3D sensors to generate high-density 3D meshes and high-resolution textures of human beings in real-time, Figs.19 and 20. Designers can insert real time avatars in virtual scenes using a game engine. One motivation of the research is enabling human-to-human communication in a virtual environment – in essence, such a vision could be used to have a teacher appearing virtually on stage anywhere. The system reaches its limits when the real person turns and the avatar appears with zig-zag lines where the body scanning is lost. In addition, issues with sound must be expected if multiple speakers are involved.

MacGregor opened a VR based training center in Arendal/Norway, Fig.21. Using stereoscopic vision, trainees operate cargo-handling equipment. The intention is to reduce the likelihood of causing injury to personnel or damage to equipment because operators have already tried and tested it in the virtual world. The training room uses an authentic operating chair for offshore crane simulations and a displayed virtual world, like nautical bridge simulators.

Fig.21: MacGregor cargo handling simulator (source: MacGregor)

Raal Harris (Videotel) in personal communication (20.3.2017): Videotel has started working with VR but so far just “[exploring] the technology and testing it on the maritime audience.” The first applications reported are for an engine room and maintenance tasks.

3. Take-home lessons

Creating 3D models as a starting point for Virtual Reality applications is costly and beyond the capabilities of a training department. Instead, training scenarios are usually opportunistic and employ existing (in-house or downloadable) 3D models.

The high costs for VR based training limit applications. Business cases can usually be made only when large assets or human health/life is at risk in real-world training.

Stereoscopic vision and high-res photorealism are nice to have, but for most training purposes not vital. The more trainees immerse in a virtual world, the more they leave the real world. Trainees may then no longer be aware of trainers or fellow trainees with detrimental effects for pedagogy. Full immersion may also create health and safety problems.

VR “cinemas” with special rooms mean that trainees must come to a specific location, reducing the potential customer group and making convincing business cases difficult.

References

GASPAR, H.M.; TANIGUCHI, D.; RUOCCO, P.; NISHIMOTO, K. (2009), *A real-time 3d post-processor for a numerical model-basin simulator*, 8th COMPIT Conf., Budapest, pp.512-524, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2009_budapest.pdf

KATZKY, U. (2014), *Virtual reality simulation training for underwater operations*, 13th COMPIT Conf., Redworth, pp.504-511, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2014_redworth.pdf

KIL, W.S.; SON, M.J.; LEE, J.Y. (2018), *Development of multi-purpose VR simulator for a ship from 3D CAD model*, 17th COMPIT Conf., Pavone, pp.250-258, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2018_pavone.pdf

KUBIAK, M. (2011), *Virtual training – a way to improve operational performance*, Bulk Carrier Update 3, DNV, Høvik, pp.28-31

LAMBROU, M.A.; POLYDOROPOULOU, A.; NIKITAKOS, N.; LITINAS, N. (2006), *Personalized, virtual maritime self-learning in the SLIM-VRT environment*, 5th European Conf. on e-Learning, Winchester

LINDENAU, O.; BERTRAM, V. (2003), *The making of a VRML model for an SES with streamlines and pressure distribution*, 2nd COMPIT Conf., Hamburg, pp.5-14, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2003_hamburg.pdf

MacKINNON, S.N.; BRADBURY-SQUIRES, D.; BUTTON, D. (2016), *Virtual reality based training improves mustering performance*, 15th COMPIT Conf., Lecce, pp.75-83, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2016_lecce.pdf

NEWELL, J.; LUCK, S. (2017), *Testing the boundaries of virtual reality within ship support*, Engine as a Weapon Int. Symp. VII (EAAW VII), Bristol

NORDBY, K.; BØRRESEN, S.; GERNEZ, E. (2016), *Efficient Use of Virtual and Mixed Reality in Conceptual Design of Maritime Work Places*, 15th COMPIT Conf., Lecce, pp.392-400, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2016_lecce.pdf

ROSENBLUM, L. (2000), *Virtual and Augmented Reality 2020*, IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications 20/1, pp.38-39, www.nrl.navy.mil/itd/imda/sites/www.nrl.navy.mil.itd.imda/files/pdfs/2000_CGA_VRAR2020.pdf

TATE, D.L.; SIBERT, L.; KING, T. (1997), *Virtual environments for shipboard firefighting training*, Virtual Reality Annual Int. Symp., Albuquerque, https://www.nrl.navy.mil/itd/imda/sites/www.nrl.navy.mil.itd.imda/files/pdfs/cp_VRAIS97.pdf

VENTER, A.; JURICIC, I. (2014), *Virtual Reality for crew education in on-board operational and emergency conditions*, 13th COMPIT Conf., Redworth, pp.437-446, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2014_redworth.pdf

WARDELL, A. (2010), *DNV's survey simulator: A ship in every classroom*, Bulk Carrier Update 2, DNV, pp.14-16

WAUCHOPE, K.; EVERETT, S.; TATE, D.; MANEY, T. (2003), *Speech-interactive virtual environments for ship familiarization*, 2nd COMPIT Conf., Hamburg, pp.70-83, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2003_hamburg.pdf

WAUCHOPE, K., BERTRAM, V. (2004), *Ship familiarization in virtual reality using speech interaction*, Schiff+Hafen 56/6, pp.53-56

Appendix – Features of DNV GL’s Survey Simulator (SuSi)

The Survey Simulator offers elements of four maritime vessels: Bulk Carrier, Tanker, Containership, Mobile Offshore Unit. Each vessel has several disconnected survey areas, such as cargo hold, deck, double bottom, etc. The vessels and their areas were modelled after real ships or structures, with high-level of detail.

Thousands of deficiencies were placed in the inspection areas, both safety-related and of technical nature. These deficiencies are based on DNV GL’s global inspection experience.

The Survey Simulator offers four training modes:

1. Ship knowledge mode - Covers maritime naming convention, parts naming and certificate requirements
2. Areas of attention mode - Highlights areas where hull structural deficiencies are likely to occur
3. Survey requirements mode - Visualization of class and statutory survey requirements (based on DNV GL rules)
4. Findings mode - Display of built in deficiencies and descriptions

A strong feature of the Survey Simulator is interactivity. Several virtual tools are available:

PDA (Personal Digital Assistant) – enables access to essential information about naming, survey requirements and findings during virtual inspection. Gives access to attached documentation, photos, drawings, manuals and reporting templates.

Flashlight – necessary in dark areas as with real on-board surveys

Camera – essential in preparing documentation of deficiencies during virtual inspection

Spray – handy tool to mark-up deficiencies

Telescopic boom (cherry picker) – useful when checking upper part of ship’s structure

Raft – common way of inspecting upper parts of internal structures of tankers when tanks are filled with water.

Demystify Artificial Intelligence for Maritime Applications

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Abstract

This paper explains key technologies of Artificial Intelligence (AI), namely machine learning, expert systems, speech recognitions, gesture recognition, and related techniques. The intention is to give an introduction for laymen illustrating each technique with maritime examples taken from personal experience and literature. The paper also discussed limitations of AI techniques.

1. What is AI?

You've heard of it, and it is powerful, maybe threatening. Artificial Intelligence or "AI" is a term often used, yet little understood. What we don't know, often scares us, but sometimes we also have unrealistic hopes. Much of the common perception of AI comes through Hollywood movies: AI seems to have a nice female voice which lulls us into trusting "her", until "she" starts killing off humans, because somehow "she" developed "her" own mind. This makes generally for most entertaining movies, but has little in common with my experience and view of AI. It just seems to be a new version of the 1970s' misconception of computers and software: "he" (back then, it was generally a "he") says so and therefore it must be true.

The engineering truth behind the term or misnomer "Artificial Intelligence" is a set of tools that may do jobs better or handle tasks we could not handle at all in the past. The tools as such may fascinate; you may also worry what might be done when the tools are used by the wrong people; but the tools as such do not scare me.

There is no coherent definition of what "Artificial Intelligence" is. In its broadest sense, AI is concerned with the investigation and simulation of human intelligence with the ambition to replicate the processes in machines. A (not exhaustive) list of sub-branches of AI encompasses:

- machine learning / artificial neural nets / machine vision
- knowledge-based systems (expert systems, case-based reasoning, Bayesian networks)
- natural language processing / gesture processing
- robotics
- ...

In this paper, I will try to demystify Artificial Intelligence, looking at the first three items and how they may impact the maritime industries.

2. Machine Learning

2.1 Principle

Machine learning and data mining are closely related to computational statistics. In essence, we have glorified statistics here with new, catchy labels attached to it.

Traditionally, the human brain is very good at pattern recognition. Table I shows some x-y combinations which would remain meaningless if shown only for a second. Fig.1 shows the corresponding visualisation, *Zelasny (2011)*. Here we see immediately trends and unusual deviations. Such trend spotting and pattern recognition is a human intelligence ability that machine learning tries to mimic (and take further).

Table I: Sample x-y combinations

I	
X	Y
10.0	8.04
8.0	6.95
13.0	7.58
9.0	8.81
11.0	8.33
14.0	9.96
6.0	7.24
4.0	4.26
12.0	10.84
7.0	4.82
5.0	5.68

II	
X	Y
10.0	9.14
8.0	8.14
13.0	8.74
9.0	8.77
11.0	9.26
14.0	8.10
6.0	6.13
4.0	3.10
12.0	9.13
7.0	7.26
5.0	4.74

III	
X	Y
10.0	7.46
8.0	6.77
13.0	12.74
9.0	7.11
11.0	7.81
14.0	8.84
6.0	6.08
4.0	5.39
12.0	8.15
7.0	6.42
5.0	5.73

IV	
X	Y
8.0	6.58
8.0	5.76
8.0	7.71
8.0	8.84
8.0	8.47
8.0	7.04
8.0	5.25
19.0	12.50
8.0	5.56
8.0	7.91
8.0	6.89

Fig.1: Visual equivalents to Table I – Here we see immediately the patterns, *Zelasny (2001)*

Our standard tools for evaluating such data, e.g. for simple design methods, have been rather primitive and inaccurate. We might have averaged to a single value (coefficient), used linear regression or nonlinear regression analysis based on polynomials, which had the unfortunate tendency to introduce unphysical oscillations for higher orders. These are the standard options Excel offers. And they all fail at least for some of the data sets in Table I.

Wouldn't it be nice to have some mathematical way of mimicking the curve we would instinctively draw through such data sets, ignoring implausible outliers and following the trends our eye sees, something flexible yet smooth and free of inappropriate oscillations? For the naval architect, this is old hat. We have approximated arbitrary point sets for centuries using first flexible thin beams (splines), Fig.2, and later using aptly named spline curves, which do not oscillate and form smooth curves and surfaces. See e.g. *Veelo (2004)* for an overview of such techniques for ship design, automotive engineering or the movie industry.

The machine learning community prefers other functions, such as sigmoid functions, Fig.3. Combining many of these, we have similar basic qualities of flexible approximation and avoiding oscillations.

Fig.2: Traditional splines for ship design, source: TU Berlin

Fig.3: Sigmoid function

Conventional regression has been extensively used in naval architecture in system identification to provide required factors and coefficients. Based on databases of existing designs, coefficients are then interpolated or even extrapolated to calculate coefficients for a new application. This procedure requires the engineer to specify not only which input parameters mainly influence one or more output parameters, but also to specify the type of functional relation between input and output parameters. Most often in the past, simple linear relations have been chosen. Designers plotted data and by visual inspection sometimes chose also simple polynomial relations. This approach is cumbersome and unsuitable for many nonlinear relations. Shortcomings are especially apparent for multi-dimensional input/output data sets.

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are the most popular technique in machine learning. ANNs can generally represent the mapping of multi-dimensional input/output data sets, i.e. an arbitrary number of input variables x_i and output variable y_i . An ANN structure consists of several layers; each layer consists of several nodes. In the example shown in Fig.4, we have the input layer, the output layer, and one hidden layer. The ANN is “trained” on data sets. This training process results in mathematical relationship output variables y_i and input variables x_i , e.g. of the form (for a single-input, single-output ANN):

$$y = c_0 + c_1 \cdot \text{sig} [b_0 + b_1 \cdot \text{sig} (a_{10} + a_{11} \cdot x_1 + a_{12} \cdot x_2 + \dots) + b_2 \cdot \text{sig} (a_{20} + a_{21} \cdot x_1 + a_{22} \cdot x_2 + \dots) + \dots] \quad (1)$$

Here, sig denotes the sigmoid function, Fig.3. After sufficient training, adjusted values for the coefficients a , b , and c are derived and the non-linear relationship is determined. Now the ANN can very rapidly determine values y_i for given values x_i . One might also use the general functional expression of Eq.(1) and use least-square fit methods to determine the coefficients a , b and c . But then we would lose out on a wealth of wonderful jargon and might not be that impressed anymore.

Fig.4: General structure of an Artificial Neural Network

There are countless applications for ANNs in the literature, as pattern matching or trending is needed in countless fields. Popular TV series may show fingerprint matching, facial recognition or machine reading of licence plates – all based on neural nets. General data mining, as found in major internet companies such as Google, Yahoo, Amazon, etc. will involve neural nets, and much of the large financial trading industries will rely on them. Game playing and decision making in some strategic games (chess, backgammon, poker, Go) is another popular application of ANNs.

Finally, “Deep Learning” is a more recent buzz word used when neural nets with two or more hidden layers are used.

2.2. Limitations

Artificial Neural Nets (as the most popular machine learning technique) have in principle no problem in handling arbitrary numbers of input variables. Hence the progress through them that has sometimes fuelled mythical confidence in what they can do. As any other tool, ANNs have their limitations:

- They can't predict the unpredictable. Random events, such as lottery numbers of next week, are by definition unpredictable. Many events involving highly nonlinear (“chaotic”) behaviour are quasi-random. For example, crash-stop manoeuvres of ships are highly non-linear; small changes in the ambience at the begin of the manoeuvre result in largely varying tracks for the stopping manoeuvre, *Söding (1995)*, Fig.5. Subsequently, attempts to predict crash-stop paths using ANNs cannot succeed. If satisfactory agreement is published, e.g. *Moreira and Guedes Soares (2003)*, Fig.6, it is the luck of the draw taking only one of the possible tracks in sea trials for comparison.

Fig.5: Sea trial results of repeated crash-stop manoeuvres for a tanker, *Söding (1995)*

Fig.6: Satisfactory ANN prediction of crash-stop manoeuvre, *Moreira and Guedes Soares (2003)*

- Machine Learning is data greedy. Imagine an arbitrary curve, e.g. the sin-function $\sin(x)$ over one period. For us to recognize the function (= pattern), we would probably need ~ 10 points equidistantly spaced, and twice as many if we have some random selection. For a function of 2 input variables, we would then need 100-400 points to see the pattern or train a neural network. For n input variables, then 10^n - 20^n data points are needed. For many real-world problems, we have many factors driving the problem; e.g. for hull performance monitoring we may look at changing operational conditions (speed, draft, trim, rudder angle) and ambient conditions (water depth, significant wave height, wave direction, wind speed, wind direction, possibly also current speed, current direction), leading to billions of data points to train a neural network properly.

For many maritime problems, e.g. in ship design, we may have $O(10)$ - $O(100)$ data points. Then machine learning no longer works and we have to use natural intelligence, e.g. reducing the number of free variables using physical insight.

- Machine learning is not good for rare events. The relations found are fine for interpolating, especially in regions where we have many data points (= frequently occurring cases). Extrapolating often results in wrong predictions. Machine learning is based on experience, not theoretical reasoning. This may lead to problems in practice, *Bertram (2014)*: “[...], there was a shipowner who was looking for the best trim optimisation for his [...] ships. He looked for suitable candidates and installed a CFD-based system [i.e. based on systematic simulations based on fluid dynamics physics] and a machine-learning system on one of his ships. One fine day, the captain asked both systems for advice. The CFD-based system said: 1m down by the bow. The machine learning system said: 1m down by the stern. [...] the solution to the puzzle was that the comparison was made shortly after installation. The captain had never before driven the ship on that draft and at that speed other than with trim by stern. The machine learning system had, therefore, never “seen” that by trimming by bow the fuel consumption was lower and picked the best solution from its limited experience. Its knowledge base was patchy and thus its recommendation not good.”

2.3. Maritime applications

ANNs are increasingly used in the maritime industries for system identification. *Hess and Faller (2000)* give an overview of early maritime ANN applications. *Mesbahi (2003)* gives an introduction to ANNs and some applications from ship design and marine engineering.

ANNs have been used in

- system identification, e.g. deriving body-force coefficients in ship manoeuvring from model tests or sea trials, e.g. *Moreira and Guedes Soares (2003)*, or diesel engine monitoring, *Mesbahi and Atlar (2000)*
- deriving design formulas from narrow-domain databases, e.g. power prediction for tugs, Fig.6, *Mesbahi and Bertram (2000)* or semi-planing hulls, *Bertram and Mesbahi (2004)*
- meta-modelling using ANNs to interpolate between data sets generated in expensive simulations, e.g. *Harries (2000)*, *Couser et al. (2011)*; in a similar vein, ANNs can be used as to create response surfaces for interpolation of simulation results; e.g. in DNV GL’s ECO Assistant for trim optimization, 300-500 CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) results of power as function of speed, draft and trim are connected smoothly in such a response surface.
- Automatic ship type identification, Fig.7, *Kumlu (2012)*
- Economic predictions, e.g. of freight rates, *Bruce and Morgan (2006)*

Fig.6: Tug power prediction, *Mesbahi and Bertram (2000)*

Fig.7: Automatic ship identification, *Kumlu (2012)*

The ANN software ICE (Intelligent Calculations of Equations) is provided free-of-charge by William Faller (Applied Simulation Technologies), *Roddy et al. (2006)*. The software is easy to use, tries automatically different architectures (i.e. number of layers and nodes per layer) to get best fits, and

allows exporting the resulting mathematical formulas directly to source code of widely used programming languages, *Bertram and Herradon (2016)*.

3. Expert Systems

3.1. Principle

Knowledge-based Systems (KBS) or expert systems (the terms are used here – as in many publications within the maritime industries – interchangeably) are Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools which reason within a narrow knowledge domain. Fig.8 shows the basic structure of an expert system, which might be best explained in its similarity to database management systems such as Excel:

- Knowledge base = a collection of knowledge sets, frequently in IF-THEN form; corresponding to data sets in a database management system; this part is domain specific.
- Human-machine interface = routines to type in knowledge sets, display knowledge sets, initiate action such as inference, etc.; corresponding to common interfaces in database management systems
- Optionally: sensor data; corresponding to automatic data import from sensors e.g. for onboard measurement campaigns
- Inference engine = core software that performs the key task of a knowledge-base system, i.e. bringing input data, sensor data and knowledge (rules) together to derive a conclusion; corresponding to the core database management system that sorts, filters, and performs other data management tasks; this part is domain independent.

Fig.8: Basic structure of an expert system

‘Production systems’ are the most common way to represent knowledge in engineering. Production systems represent knowledge in IF-THEN rules, see the example in Fig.9. Many expert systems combine documented rules (taken e.g. from regulations or laws of physics) and heuristic knowledge, i.e. rules taken from common practice and experience. The KBS approach differs from conventional sequential computing approaches. The rule order in KBS is not critical for the result. However, it may affect the speed of execution significantly. KBS are often useful in developing a knowledge base as they allow rapid prototyping. Once a knowledge base has been established and is expected to remain constant for longer time, it may be incorporated in conventional programming approaches for much faster response times. Case-based reasoning (CBR) systems are special instances of knowledge-based systems. Here the approach is similar to that of lawyers or doctors: Find related cases and study them to derive the best strategy for the current case. (Intelligent) agents are swarms of simple expert systems working (communicating) together.

```

| -----
| DEFINE RULE      :    002-ENCLOSED_SUPERSTRUCTURE
| -----
| GOAL : 'HEIGHT_OF_ENCLOSED_SUPERSTRUCTURE'
| -----
|     IF 'FREEBOARD_DECK' IS EQUAL TO 'SECOND DECK' THEN
|         'HEIGHT_OF_ENCLOSED_SS' IS EQUAL TO 'DEPTH_TO_UPPER_DECK'
|         MINUS 'DEPTH_TO_SECOND_DECK'
|     RULE END
|
| -----
| DEFINE RULE      :    003-STABILITY_CRITERIA_4
| -----
| GOAL : 'AREA_BETWEEN_30_AND_DF_ANGLE'
| -----
| ASSUME THE STANDARD IMO CRITERIA APPLY
|     IF 'DEFAULT_STABILITY_CRITERIA_REQUIRED' IS TRUE THEN
|         'AREA_BETWEEN_30_AND_DF_ANGLE' IS EQUAL TO 0.030 METRE:RADIAN
|     RULE END
|
| -----
| DEFINE RULE      :    015-DRAFT_RESTRICTION
| -----
| GOAL : 'MAXIMUM_DRAFT'
| -----
|     IF 'SCANTLING_DRAFT' IS GREATER THAN 'DRAFT_RESTRICTION' THEN
|         'MAXIMUM_DRAFT' IS EQUAL TO 'DRAFT_RESTRICTION'
|         OTHERWISE 'MAXIMUM_DRAFT' IS EQUAL TO 'SCANTLING_DRAFT'
|     RULE END

```

Fig.9: Rules incorporated in INCODES in pseudo-English, *Welsh et al. (1990)*

3.2. Limitations

The coding of an expert system is relatively simple in well-structured, rule-based domains with extensive, but documented expertise, e.g. fault diagnosis, medical diagnosis, or monitoring tasks. The challenge lies in getting all relevant rules together. This task can get daunting in the following cases:

- Implicit knowledge – Here the expert knows what to do, but cannot express the fundamental rule. For example, we may use the right prepositions in our mother tongue, but most of us will not be able to explain why we choose this or that preposition to a student of our language. We follow our ‘feeling’ of what sounds right. Here, knowledge engineers need to make implicit knowledge explicit, e.g. by observing experts, asking questions and trying to find fundamental rules. This can be a tedious, costly and sometimes error-prone approach. And sometimes, the expert may refuse to cooperate, e.g. for fear that he might be replaced by the expert system and lose his position.
- Fuzzy rules – Many rules are vague. Traffic rules, for example, require us to use headlights when visibility is ‘poor’. Observe cars at dawn and dusk and you will see that this rule is subject to interpretation. Here, a solution may lie in showing a larger group of ‘experts’ a situation and ask for their assessment. Then you may take a typical (average), cautious (lower end) or daring (upper end) value and program this into your system. Again, using multiple experts possibly in multiple situations requires time and effort.
- Changing rules – For implicit and fuzzy rules, the preparation of rule sets may take considerable time. Rules may change within that time, e.g. due to political, economic or technical changes. Then the expert system becomes obsolete before it is finished – the “cathedral effect”. As a general rule, the wider the domain, the more effort is needed and the more likely are changes somewhere within that domain.
- Lack of rules – In some domains, processes are not clearly structured. For example, look at art. Or design. It will be difficult to get three experts in these fields who agree on an approach

or an assessment. Engineers like to think in IF-THEN categories, artists don't. Neither do almost artists, such as ship designers.

For case-based reasoning, the usefulness of a system depends on the number of cases and the associated tags or searching options. It is like a database. You need sufficient references in the system, you need to maintain the system feeding new cases in and you need some smart retrieval algorithms to find the 'right' cases.

3.3. Maritime applications

KBS have been proposed, developed and implemented for a variety of maritime applications, *Bertram (1998,2000,2013)*, including:

- Ship design (conceptual & detailed design, both for ship and components), e.g. *Erikstad (1996)*, *Hees (1997)*, *Es and Hees (2003)*
- Shipyard and port operations, e.g. *Simpson et al. (2003)*
- Ship operation, regular (collision avoidance, ballast control, cargo handling, predictive maintenance, ...), e.g. *Bertram (1998)*, *Statheros et al. (2008)*, *Tam et al. (2009)*
- Ship operation, responsive (fault diagnosis for ship machinery, emergency response, ...), *Kaeding and Bertram (1996)*, *Lunau and Nielsen (1998)*

The main maritime applications of expert systems in practice are found for ship operation. This is not surprising; ship design is a creative and complex process in a rapidly changing economic and regulatory environment. In contrast, collision avoidance follows rules (COLREGs) that have hardly changed in the last 100 years and rules for emergency response are conveniently documented in emergency response plans and handbooks.

Expert systems for ship operation have enjoyed a renaissance in research interest, driven by the quest for autonomous/unmanned ships. With new technologies for sensor data and resulting situation awareness (e.g. automatic ship type recognition, AIS data, or LIDAR), it makes sense to review and update the solutions that have been developed since the 1990s, Fig.10. DNV GL works on combining machine vision and case-based reasoning for next-generation plan approval, Fig.11. The idea is to identify similar plans to the one submitted for approval, retrieve the corresponding cases, and derive recommendations based on these.

Fig.10: Collision avoidance on unmanned ship concept ReVolt by DNV GL

Fig.11: Next-generation plan approval combining pattern recognition and case-based reasoning

4. Speech & Gesture Recognition

4.1. Principle

Speech recognition works on “speech to text” and more recently also on “speech/text to meaning”. The task is simplified by limiting the vocabulary, e.g. just understanding the numbers 0 to 9, ‘yes’,

‘no’, and ‘help’ in phone company or credit card services. Speech recognition may involve system training on an individual speaker who has to read text or isolated vocabulary to the system. Such individual training reduces failure rate significantly. Speech recognition systems for companies or services with many customers cannot be personalized to individual speakers. Such ‘speaker independent’ systems may resort to other techniques to keep failure rates (and customer frustration) to an acceptable limit.

Accuracy of speech recognition may vary with the following:

- Vocabulary size and confusability (“foreign voices” vs. “for invoices”)
- Speaker dependence versus independence (Inspector Clouseau saying “massage”, “reum” or “dewg” would be understood saying “message”, “room” and “dog” by a system trained on Peter Seller’s fake French accent.)
- Discontinuous or continuous speech (“for – pause – invoices” would not be confused with “foreign – pause – voices”)
- Reading vs spontaneous speech (“ah”, “uh”)
- Adverse conditions (the ‘cocktail party’ effect with other people speaking, noisy industrial environment, etc.)

Like many AI techniques, speech recognition has been through manic-depressive cycles. In 2006, Microsoft had an epic blunder in demonstrating its speech recognition software. With time and funding, we have reached widespread acceptance, e.g. in Amazon’s Alexa Voice Service. However, Alexa’s intelligence is very limited in the sense that it performs only a handful of tasks (order online X; play music Y; read latest news; etc.) Nevertheless, the progress within a decade is significant.

Part of the motivation to fund research on speech recognition lies in practicalities of computer development. In “The Imitation Game”, Alan Turing (played by Benedict Cumberbatch) stands in front of the indeed colossal Colossus computer trying to crack the German codes. Today, smart phones have vastly more computing power than the Colossus (or even all of NASA back in 1969 when they put the first man on the moon). Yet, the computer part in the smartphone is only a small fraction of its volume – the size of a smartphone is driven by user interface and energy supply (largely driving the screen). As our hands remain roughly the same size, miniaturization of computers is limited as long as we need manual input and displays. Microphones and cameras can be miniaturized (as we know from our smartphones). Voice control is also useful when we are hands are busy (e.g. driving a car, piloting an airplane, etc.) or when we are handicapped.

Fig.12: Computer (1943); scene from the movie “The Imitation Game”

Fig.13: Smart phone (2016) with vastly more computing power than 1943 computer

Modern speech recognition uses a variety of techniques to understand speech. So do we actually. On the lowest level, you may see speech as a pattern of frequency and amplitude variations. Artificial neural nets may then perform their task of pattern matching and match sound modulation to words. If we have speaker-dependent training and concentrate on making pauses between words, we may get good results, say 95-98% word recognition success rate. Difficulties remain for homonyms, i.e. same or nearly same sounding words, for example C, see and sea. Here, we use context in the sense that we

look at groups of words. ‘Vitamin C’, ‘I can see clearly now’ and ‘deep blue sea’ make it clear to us what homonym should be used. We just look at frequently used combinations of words (just like Google does) and decide to go with the most frequently used term. That may get us to 99% success rate. For rest, humans and computers will remain resigned to resorting to time honored strategies, such as asking to paraphrase or spell out.

Applications of speech recognitions range widely, including control of secondary equipment in airplanes and cars, automatic subtitling, automatic assistants (e.g. Apple’s Siri), mobile email, speech-to-text reporting (e.g. in court reporting), pronunciation evaluation in language e-learning, hands-free user-interfacing with computers (e.g. in Virtual Reality applications and video gaming).

Gesture recognition is akin to speech recognition. It commonly focusses on hand or facial gestures (mimics). Like speech recognition, gesture recognition enables humans to interact with machines (computers, robots, etc.) without touching any controls. Fatigue detection software may look at eye openness patterns and use artificial neural networks to identify fatigue in drivers, pilots or machinery operators, Fig.14.

Gesture recognition is an obvious choice when silence is called for (e.g. in military operations) or imposed (e.g. for divers under water). Generally, the ‘vocabulary’ in gesture recognition is even more constraint than in speech recognition. Interpreting human emotions (such as frustration) is part of research for future man-machine interfaces; MIT’s KISMET is an example for robots recognizing and expressing emotions, Fig.15, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kismet_\(robot\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kismet_(robot)).

Fig.14: Fatigue recognition, www.eyeaalertgps.com

Fig.15: KISMET emotional robot

4.2. Limitations

Most commercial speech recognition software concern English. (Even here, we may get interesting results in the USA looking for ant or aunt killers.) For our purposes, this is good enough as English is the official language of international shipping and the maritime industries perform business largely in ‘international’ English.

Most applications use small subsets of natural language with $O(100)$ to $O(1000)$ words. Humans may use a lot more words, but for the system they are just white noise until words from its vocabulary set are recognized. Most applications reach their limits when the ‘sound quality’ is not good, e.g. frequencies being cut off in (mobile) telephone sound transmission, ambient noise/echo, or accents (try Youtube Voice Recognition Elevator for a demonstration).

Gesture recognition requires cameras catching the gestures. For operators sitting in a fixed place (driver in a car, us sitting in front of our PC screen with a webcam), capturing the face is easy. For moving people, it is difficult. Emotional interpretation is culture dependent. Often, a specific sign language with clearly different signs has to be used.

4.3. Maritime applications

The voice-operated Super Bridge-X system of Mitsubishi allows in principle ‘no-touch’ operation of the ship, *Nagaya (1997)*, *Fukuto et al. (1998)*. Here, the master is addressing the system by speaking (e.g. ordering changes in speed or course, changing displays on computers, etc.) and the system is announcing via a loudspeaker relevant information (e.g. confirmations of accepted orders, warnings and alarms, etc.). The advantages of voice-operation are obvious: The hands and eyes are free for other tasks, e.g. watching the traffic and checking sea charts. The interaction with the bridge system then becomes more like the traditional way of interacting with other humans on the bridge. The system is based only on Japanese as language, understanding ~30 commands or inquiries.

Wauchope (2003), *Wauchope et al. (2003)* present a speech-interactive virtual-reality environment for ship familiarization for the US Navy. Here, “speech interaction provides a highly natural alternative that offers minimal interference with the eyes/hands-busy task of virtual navigation.”

In 2017, DNV GL announced the development of an AI-based customer support system using speech recognition and expert systems to support their DATE (Direct Access to Technical Expert) service, Fig.16.

Fig.16: Speech recognition in DNV GL's customer assistant software

Fig.17: CADDY robot acknowledging diver command to do mosaic

Fig.18: Gesture recognition in CADDY diver support robot, <http://www.caddy-fp7.eu/>

The EU research project CADDY developed underwater gesture recognition for diver support, Figs.17 and 18. The divers need to wear special gloves with clear markings and use a special sign

language, dubbed CADDIAN, with 52 symbols to send messages to the robot. The robot acknowledges with light signals and an LED screen displaying text.

5. Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence is a tool, sometimes using unnecessarily pretentious jargon. Like any other tool, it can be used for good or for bad purposes. Artificial Intelligence as such has no ethics, but it also has no mind or will of its own. Unlike a human, an AI software for playing Go brilliantly will not develop its own initiative or curiosity and start learning chess, for example.

The examples presented show that AI techniques can be put to good use for maritime applications. We can expect more and increasingly sophisticated applications to evolve in years to come.

References

BERTRAM, V. (1998), *Knowledge-based systems for maritime applications*, 26th WEGEMT School, Hamburg, www.wegemt.com/download/wegemt/26th_WEGEMT_School_Expert_Systems_for_Marine_Applications.pdf

BERTRAM, V. (2000), *Knowledge-based systems for ship design and ship operation*, 1st Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Potsdam, pp.63-71, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2000_potsdam.pdf

BERTRAM, V. (2013), *A survey of knowledge-based systems for ship design and ship operation*, Int. J. Intelligent Engineering Informatics (IJIEI) 2/1, pp.71-90

BERTRAM, V. (2014), *Trim optimisation – Don't blind me with science!*, The Naval Architect, September, pp.66-68, www.dnvgl.com/Images/2014_TheNavalArchitect_Bertram_TrimOptimization_tcm8-21468.pdf

BERTRAM, V.; HERRADON, E. (2016), *Predicting added resistance in wind and waves employing artificial neural nets*, 1st Hull Performance & Insight Conf. (HullPIC), Pavone, pp.14-22, <http://data.hullpic.info/HullPIC2016.pdf>

BERTRAM, V.; MESBAHI, E. (2004), *Estimating resistance and power of fast monohulls employing artificial neural nets*, 4th Conf. High-Performance Marine Vehicles (HIPER), Rome, pp.18-27, http://data.hiper-conf.info/Hiper2004_Rome.pdf

BIBULI, M.; BRUZZONE, G.; CACCIA, M.; CHIARELLA, D.; FERRETTI, R.; ODETTI, A.; RANIERI, A.; ZEREIK, E. (2017), *Cutting-edge underwater robotics - CADDY project challenges, results and future steps*, 16th Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Cardiff, pp.101-114, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2017_cardiff.pdf

BRUCE, G.; MORGAN, G. (2006), *Artificial neural networks – Application to freight rates*, 5th Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Oestgeest, pp.146-153, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2006_oestgeest.pdf

COUSER, P.; HARRIES, S.; TILLIG, F. (2011), *Numerical hull series for calm water and sea-keeping*, 10th Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Berlin, pp.206-220, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2011_berlin.pdf

ERIKSTAD, S.O. (1996), *A decision support model for preliminary ship design*, Ph.D. thesis, NTNU, Trondheim

ES, K. van; HEES, M.T. van (2003), *Application of knowledge management in conceptual naval ship design*, 2nd Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Hamburg, pp.350-362, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2003_hamburg.pdf

FUKUTO, J.; NUMANO, M.; MIYAZAKI, K.; ITOH, Y.; MURAYAMA, Y.; MATSUDA, K.; SHIMONO, N. (1998), *An advanced navigation support system for a coastal tanker aiming at one-man bridge operation*, on Control Applications in Marine Systems (CAMS '98), IFAC Proc. 31/30, pp.179-184, <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1474667017384379>

HARRIES, S. (2010), *Investigating multi-dimensional design spaces using first principle methods*, 7th Conf. High-Performance Marine Vehicles (HIPER), Melbourne, pp.179-194, http://data.hiper-conf.info/Hiper2010_Melbourne.pdf

HEES, M.T. (1997), *Quaestor: Expert governed parametric model assembling*, PhD thesis, TU Delft **Error! Hyperlink reference not valid.**

HESS, D.; FALLER, W. (2000), *Simulation of ship maneuvers using recursive neural networks*, 23rd Symp. Naval Hydrodynamics, Val de Reuil

KAEDING, P.; BERTRAM, V. (1996), *Artificial intelligence for ship automation – Technical and economical aspects of reduced crews*, IfS Report 572, Univ. Hamburg

KUMLU, D. (2012), *Autonomous ship recognition from color images*, MSc Thesis, Univ. Southern California, <http://digitallibrary.usc.edu/cdm/ref/collection/p15799coll3/id/64052>

LUNAU, C.P.; NIELSEN, J.K. (1998), *EMMA – Onboard emergency management system for ships*, 26th WEGEMT School, Hamburg, www.wegemt.com/download/wegemt/26th_WEGEMT_School_Expert_Systems_for_Marine_Applications.pdf

MESBAHI, E. (2003), *Artificial neural networks – Fundamentals*, 39th WEGEMT School OPTIMISTIC – Optimization in Marine Design, Mensch & Buch Verlag, Berlin, pp.191-216, www.wegemt.com/?wpfb_dl=45

NAGAYA, S. (1997), *Navigation support system with voice control and guidance*, Int. Marine Electrotechnology Conf., Shanghai

SIMPSON, D.; FURSTENBERG, L.; KALATHAS, E.; BERTRAM, V. (2003), *Virtual prototyping for developing South African ports*, 2nd Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Hamburg, pp.235-246, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2003_hamburg.pdf

SÖDING, H. (1995), *Manövrierfähigkeit von Schiffen*, Lecture Notes, Institut für Schiffbau, Univ. Hamburg

STATHEROS, T.; HOWELLS, G.; McDONALD-MAIER (2008), *Autonomous ship collision avoidance navigation concepts, technologies and techniques*, J. Navigation 61, pp.129-142

TAM, C.K.; BUCKNALL, R.; GREIG, A. (2009), *Review of collision avoidance and path planning methods for ships in close range encounters*, J. Navigation 62, pp.455–476

VEELO, B. (2004), *Variations of Shape in Industrial Geometric Models*, PhD thesis, NTNU, Trondheim, <https://www.sarc.nl/publications/variations-of-shape-in-industrial-geometric-models/>

WAUCHOPE, K. (2003), *Interactive Ship Familiarization System: Technical Description*, Technical

Report AIC-03-001, Navy Center for Applied Research in Artificial Intelligence, Washington,
<http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.7.282&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

WAUCHOPE, K.; EVERETT, S.; TATE, D.; MANEY, T. (2003), *Speech-interactive virtual environments for ship familiarization*, 2nd Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Hamburg, pp.70-83, http://data.hiper-conf.info/compit2003_hamburg.pdf

WELSH, M.; BUXTON, I.L.; HILLS, W. (1990), *The application of an expert system to ship concept design investigations*, Trans. RINA, pp.99-113

ZELASNY, G. (2001), *Say It with Charts: The Executive's Guide to Visual Communication*, McGraw-Hill

A Highly-Efficient Propeller Actuator Disk Replacement

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Abstract

Full 3D propeller analysis in CFD is complex and time-consuming, making it inefficient for early-stage studies and initial convergence iterations. It is therefore common to use a momentum-based actuator disk as a proxy for the propeller. Simplified homogeneous actuator disks are easy to implement, but do not realistically model the radial distribution of blade loading, velocities or forces. Radially-varying actuator disks more closely resemble the wake field velocity outcomes, but do not capture circumferential variations. This paper describes a technique using the HydroComp PropElements® software as an actuator disk replacement for the wake field prediction of velocities and body forces. Using its capabilities for batch scripting and connectivity, it can provide a highly-efficient and easy-to-implement replacement for simplistic actuator disk models.

1. Introduction

Statistician George Box is known for his aphorism, “All models are wrong but some are useful.” Less well known is his deeper insight,

“Now it would be very remarkable if any system existing in the real world could be exactly represented by any simple model. However, cunningly chosen parsimonious models often do provide remarkably useful approximations.” *Box (1976)*

The propeller actuator disk is a fine example of such a “parsimonious model”. It offers a reduced-order computation of the momentum flow through a propeller, and can be useful both independently and as a component within a larger integrated CFD self-propulsion calculation. As it represents a propeller by a thin disk with no geometric details, it is limited to a simplistic analysis of propeller performance and offers no capability for propeller design.

The value of any model of a physical system must also be considered in light of its “efficiency”, as we use the term to describe function versus cost. Computational speed can either reduce the “cost” of propeller analysis or increase its analytical “function”. As a naval architect and propeller designer with forty years of experience, this author would argue that we never actually see a reduction in the time it takes to complete a job. If we have half a day for a propeller design, then we take half a day. In the early days, we used charts and generalized computations – including actuator disk analogs. Now we have the opportunity to drill down into the details with ever more complex models.

In the interest of total workflow effectiveness, however, we look for the best combination of computation speed and model fidelity. An increase in the speed of a CFD system analysis is meaningless if the propeller component is simplified to the point where it no longer represents the deliverable performance of a propeller. Simplification is frequently seen not only with the use of a performance analog (like an actuator disk), but also in the simplification of geometry or in the loosening of convergence tolerances. Conversely, a high-fidelity full 3D propeller model often consumes computational resources without offering valuable additional knowledge of the system’s performance.

So where does the actuator disk sit in the spectrum of hydrodynamic design and analysis tools? Does it still have a place in the current state of numerical hydrodynamics? The answers can be found in assessing the purpose for modeling the propeller component within the larger CFD system. In many cases, replacing an actuator disk in a CFD system analysis with a highly-efficient real-time coupling to HydroComp PropElements® can offer the speed efficiency of an actuator disk with the fidelity of a higher-order analysis – providing a more suitable match between the order of the CFD system model and the propeller component within that model.

2. Actuator disks

There are many papers and references on the mathematics of actuator disks for marine vehicle performance analysis, for example, *Breslin (1994)*, *Bontempo (2017)*, so no attempt will be made to offer any great detail here on their computational underpinnings. In brief, the equilibrium balance for an actuator disk is the delivered thrust loading, which must resolve the sum-of-forces created by the various aspects of ship resistance (or other thrust requirements, such as towing). This “delivered thrust” is specified as “propeller thrust” to account for the thrust deduction (which is typically calculated within the CFD analysis). This thrust is then distributed over the disk area to provide a model for estimating induced velocities, and in some cases axial-tangential forces (often known as “body forces”), using a pre-defined set of open-water curves or an external potential-flow calculation for calibration.

2.1 Actuator disk theory

Actuator disk mathematics is founded on a model of induced axial velocities and corresponding forces based on momentum properties. There is no direct calculation of tangential velocities or propulsor torque. This absence of rotational properties limits its usefulness for many analyses, such as where rotational flow contributes to rudder lift and drag during maneuvering studies.

That being said, there are techniques to estimate rotational velocity and torque with correlation to ideal efficiency (an “impulse theory” model of mass rotation, *Ghose (2004)*), as well as to model tests or other analytical predictions for a reference propeller. (Radial vector velocities are typically neglected in reduced-order models of the propeller.)

2.2 Actuator disk theory

A uniform actuator disk pushes all thrust in a constant distribution through the hub-to-tip disk area. This is the simplest and least useful model for integrated self-propulsion studies.

2.3 Radially-varying actuator disk

With a pre-defined distribution of radial blade loading – such as an elliptical loading – the uniform actuator disk can be manipulated to produce more meaningful and representative results. For, example, the image in Figure 1 is for a total velocity distribution (i.e., effective plus induced) with a radially varying actuator disk.

Note: The velocities represented throughout the paper are for a self-propulsion study of a single-screw general cargo vessel. The min-max color scale is set so that it is the same for all plots of like type.

2.4 Deficiencies and improvements

While the radially-varying actuator disk does a better job at estimating the radial distribution of total velocities through the propeller disk, it still has a number of deficiencies:

- The generated velocities do not include the influence of the inflow distribution circumferentially around the propeller disk.
- It does not include the effects of rotational inflow as a contribution to local blade loading.
- The distribution is often generic in nature, and cannot capture real propeller blade characteristics, such as pitch distribution or blade outline.

Fig.1: Total axial velocity with a radially-varying actuator disk

It is common to see an actuator disk correlated to the results of an uncoupled higher-order propeller code to improve the fidelity of the outcome. For example, one source describes the following approach *Krasilnikov (2014)*:

1. An actuator disk is defined for the subject vessel.
2. A model of radial thrust loading is derived from panel method calculations of a proxy “realistic” propeller.
3. Propeller torque is estimated by a proportional scaling of the thrust loading to the radial torque and thrust from the proxy propeller.
4. This provides a circumferentially-averaged distribution of axial and tangential velocities.

In other words, it is a radially-varying actuator disk – just like the one illustrated in Figure 1 – whose distribution of loading and estimation of torque is based on calculations for a representative proxy propeller. Similar techniques utilize model testing for the thrust-torque relationship, with a generic characteristic blade distribution.

3. An actuator disk replacement

As mentioned earlier, the validity and applicability of a circumferentially-averaged actuator disk model must be carefully considered for self-propulsion studies. This is particularly relevant when the purpose of the study is performance optimization of the hull-propulsor system, where the effect of appendages or “energy saving devices” (ESDs) is to be evaluated. In these cases, replacing the actuator disk model with HydroComp PropElements as a closely-coupled calculation server is justified.

In short, PropElements is a commercial propeller code based on a lifting-line foundation with substantially extended capabilities that allow it to provide high-fidelity viscous and scalable predictions of non-cavitating propeller performance. Using its capabilities for batch scripting and connectivity, it can provide a highly-efficient and easy-to-implement replacement for simplistic actuator disk models.

3.1 Example performance benchmarks

The plots in Figure 2 are examples from in-house validation studies against well-known benchmark propellers. In addition to the quantitative fidelity of the predictions, it is notable that PropElements provides reliable predictions for heavily-loaded (low J) conditions.

Fig.2: Example benchmark KT-KQ validations (DTRC 4119 NSRDC 4382)

3.2 Definition of the propeller

One particularly valuable capability of PropElements is the ability to describe the propeller by its “bounding box” parameters. These include radial distributions of chord, thickness, pitch (or pitch angle), camber, skew, and rake. Thickness and camber distributions at each radius are described by user-selection of a representative foil geometry (e.g., NACA 16 with a=0.8 mean line), with local foil performance predicted using a selected foil prediction model.

Fig.3: PropElements plot of the subject propeller profile and outline

This parametric representation of blade geometry allows for quick development of propeller models for computation. While a model for PropElements can be easily built from parameters, the significant features can also be extracted from a 3D STL file (which, of course, could be the same file used for full 3D rotating-frame CFD computations). In most cases, a design study would be conducted initially with parametric representation of the propeller, with a final 3D propeller blade geometry exported from PropElements for use by the CFD code as needed.

3.2 Prediction of velocity distributions

PropElements allows axial and tangential inflow, and considers the additional influence on axial velocity of select nozzle types (e.g., 19A, 37, circular tunnel, and more). Both axial and tangential induced velocities are predicted, with models available for prediction of upstream and downstream flow lines (as useful for multi-element propulsors, for example).

Fig.4: Example benchmark validation of downstream velocity prediction (PPTC, 20% D)

Fig.5: Axial inflow (left) and total velocity (right, including induced velocities)

Fig.6: Tangential inflow (left) and total velocity (right, including induced velocities)

Full quasi-steady wake-field calculations can be conducted. (Note that these calculations are not unsteady calculations with influence of local blade position.) An example of PropElements wake-field velocity predictions are shown above in Figs.5 and 6 (for the same single-screw general cargo vessel used to predict the radially-varying actuator disk results in Fig.1). As compared to Fig.1, you can see that this prediction captures circumferential distribution of velocity, as well as localized effects of inflow (as found near the 12-o'clock position). Unlike the actuator disk model, it also generates a prediction of tangential velocities, as shown below.

3.3 Body forces

Many CFD codes also accept propeller performance as “body forces”. These are generated axial and tangential forces distributed in the plane of the disk. In most cases, body forces are defined as differentials both radially (dR) and angularly along the radius ($d\theta$). PropElements describes the circumferential differential relative to its length versus angle. This allows the value units to be expressed as pressure-equivalents (force per length per length). Axial and tangential body force predictions for the example propellers are shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7: Axial (left) and tangential (right) body forces

4. Coupling

The CFD code provides the wake-field inflow for PropElements, which then calculates the predicted velocities or body forces for the propeller disk. A simplified description of the process is:

1. The CFD code generates the effective wake field for the propeller by extracting the calculated flow around the hull just upstream of the propeller disk.
2. The propeller disk axial and tangential velocities are passed to PropElements as the inflow for its propeller analysis computations.
3. PropElements can optionally solve for pitch or RPM to achieve thrust matching if this is required.
4. Body forces or velocities are returned to the CFD code to be used as needed.

The specific mechanism of the closely-coupled communication between a CFD code (or any executive software, for that matter) and PropElements is via separate computation with data passed by text files. This allows for the coupling to be possible between differing operating systems sharing network access, such as a Linux CFD code communicating with PropElements on Windows 10.

Data formatting for both instructions to and results from PropElements is based on an object-oriented scripting language. A brief example of scripting that defines a wake slice used by PropElements is:

```
Wake.RadialCount 18
Wake.RadialPos 0.2115 0.2579 0.3043 0.3507 0.3971 ...
Wake.VaVs 0.2391 0.3287 0.4042 0.4530 0.4886 ...
Wake.VtVs 0.0060 0.0015 0.0177 0.0444 0.0610 ...
Wake.VelocitySource WakeDistDist
```

(Note that wake distribution can be in velocity units or non-dimensional, as shown in the example.)

The commands to produce an output file with induced axial velocities for the results the above as output for the CFD code would be:

```
Output.Start "UIndAxial.txt"  
  Propeller.Sections.AddToOutput Count  
  Propeller.Sections.AddToOutput RadialPos  
  Propeller.Sections.AddToOutput UIndAxial  
Output.End
```

To act as a coupled solver for a CFD code, the process must follow these steps:

1. PropElements must first be launched in its “server mode”. (This includes a unique handle ID to insure the fidelity of the calculation process, and that no other application will interrupt the calculations until PropElements is closed.)
2. Once launched, the CFD code can prepare scripts to send to PropElements and pass these through a “run script” utility.
3. PropElements accepts the script, runs the calculation, and produces the output requested within the script.
4. The CFD code watches for a change to the specified output file, after which it utilizes the information as it needed.
5. Steps 2-4 are repeated for each calculation variant until the analysis session is completed.
6. The CFD code sends a command to close the instance of PropElements that is currently being used for the coupled calculations.

4.1 Resource demands

The computational load of PropElements is extremely modest. The example propeller calculations illustrated above were conducted on a business-grade Windows 10 laptop (2.60 GHz Intel I7, 16 MB RAM, 64-bit). A full calculation iteration for a propeller in a wake field with 15 degree slices took less than 20 seconds to produce the output file. Additional generation of wake field plots can be conducted using script commands, which will add a few seconds to each iteration.

5. Conclusions

In many cases, the added value of a full 3D propeller analysis in CFD is not justified for the cost and complexity involved. The traditional application of an actuator disk as a “stand-in” surrogate for a full propeller offers beneficial reduction in complexity and computational resources, but at the cost of model fidelity. It is increasingly necessary to achieve a more realistic model of the radial and circumferential distribution of blade loading. A closely-coupled connection between a CFD code and HydroComp PropElements software offers a high-fidelity and highly-efficient alternative to an actuator disk for the prediction of wake field velocities and body forces. Using easy-to-implement capabilities for object-oriented scripting and cross-product connectivity, it is the ideal replacement for simplistic actuator disk models.

References

- BENSOW, R.E. (20170, *CFD Methods in Ship Hydrodynamics*, Encyclopedia of Maritime and Offshore Engineering, John Wiley & Sons
- BONTEMPO, R.; MANNA, M. (2017), *Actuator disc methods for open propellers: assessments of numerical methods*, Engineering Applications of Computational Fluid Mechanics
- BOX, G.E.P. (1979), *Robustness in the strategy of scientific model building*, Robustness in Statistics, Academic Press, pp. 201-236

BRESLIN, J.P.; ANDERSEN, P. (1994), *Hydrodynamics of Ship Propellers*, Cambridge University Press

GHOSE, J.P.; GORKARN, R.P. (2004), *Basic Ship Propulsion*, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur

KRASILNIKOV, V. (2014), *Numerical Modeling of Ship-Propeller Interaction under Self-Propulsion Condition*, STAR Global Conference, Vienna

Does the Future Ship Designer Need to be a Human Factors Expert?

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Abstract

Increasing automation in ship operations implies fewer personnel on board leading to the eventual introduction of autonomous shipping. Even many service vessels are being designed to incorporate ever greater levels of automation. Thus there might be seen to be less need for the ship designer to consider Human Factors, however the reality is quite the opposite. Secondly, much of what the ship designer has traditionally done is being increasingly automated. So it could be argued the task of the ship designer being reduced, while also being expanded to apply science to better “architecting the ship”. If, at least for complex service vessels, the personnel spaces (living and working) dominate the design of the internal configuration, then the capability to properly apply Human Factors principles must become a key ship design skill. This issue is addressed by firstly considering current views on the application of Human Factors in ship design. This is followed by considering how architects should take on board the large number of human oriented disciplines becoming scientifically based. Work at UCL on discrete aspects of HF investigated for a range of ship types is then outlined, before considering the inference that the nature of ship design education should be changed to reflect a greater emphasis on providing better HF knowledge to prospective ship designers.

1. Introduction

Automation in ship operation implies fewer personnel on board, with the end point of autonomous shipping. There is an ongoing push for greater levels of lean manning, even in the case of service vessels (including naval vessels), which are ships designed not for transporting goods from A to B, but to go to sea to do (unpredictable) activities at sea. Although such vessels are unlikely to be fully autonomous, the level of automation on board will increase leading to fewer personnel on individual ships. Rather than demanding less design attention being paid to human factors in ship design, it may well be that greater emphasis will be necessary. The fewer personnel at sea are likely to be better trained, each with a greater number of roles and responsibilities, and they will be carried on board to primarily deal with contingencies. Traditionally, mariners dealt with such emergent demands and contingencies by having enough people available but this will not be the case in a more automated future. Thus with fewer people at sea there will be a need to have better ergonomics through-out the ship to cope – both for the living and working environment the ship designer is providing.

Secondly, more of the tasks of the ship designer are being automated. Much of what the ship designer traditionally did, such as large parts of hydrostatics & stability, resistance & propulsion and structural calculations, have been automated, and computer based analysis has enabled the less traditionally tractable areas of naval architecture, such as seakeeping, manoeuvring and vibration analysis, to be routinely addressed in ship design. Furthermore, large scale FEA and CFD analyses are being incorporated in computer aided ship design (CASD) suites. Such integrated CASD packages seem to just require the modern ship designer to model their new design or even just modify an existing design and leave the CASD system to then analyse the model. So the scope of the ship designer is both being reduced and, contrariwise, then expanded into a wider number of areas that are also becoming more scientific and open to modelling. One of these is that of “architecting” and “ergonomising” the ship for its more demanding crew and passengers. Thus, ship design research is using scientific techniques and CAD tools to both analyse, *Pawling and Andrews (2018)* and to generate complex ship layouts, *Duchateau (2016)*. Given for complex service vessels, *Andrews (2003)*, and cruise ships, *Levander (2012)*, their internal architecture is dominated by personnel issues, it can be readily argued that the ship designer has to become more human factors aware as these aspects still require the human designer’s intervention.

This issue is tackled by considering first the state of HF in ship design from recent publications by both ship designers and HF experts. A parallel view from urban building design on the need for architects to address the “human sciences”, provides a more extensive view of how these many aspects are becoming more scientific, yet it seems that architects remain wedded to their traditional “creative art”? Some work investigating how the HF facet can be better addressed in ship design, with which the author has been involved, is then outlined, before considering the demanding issue as to whether and how ship design education should give more prominence to HF, given the above trends in ship operations and design.

2. Views on HF in Ship Design

It is worth exploring why HF has been given relatively little prominence in ship design when compared to aircraft or even building design. This can be seen to be due in the former case to both the highly necessary man-machine ergonomics for aircraft crew and short-term (and restrained) habitation, together with the expensive and rarely undertaken aerospace design process compared with the bespoke and under resourced/conservative design and assembly process for most ships. A similar contrast occurs with urban architecture (such as airport terminals and prestige buildings), where the flow of large numbers of people may be a design constraint but wider aesthetics are accepted as a major design driver, whereas in most ship design the demand for economic “efficiency” is paramount. The exceptions in the maritime sector are cruise ships and mega-yachts where architects rather than naval architects bring in design rather than specifically HF skills to achieve for the passengers/owners urban design styles at sea.

Earthy and Sherwood Jones (2005) consider human science knowledge, from the point of view of a classification society primarily focused on merchant vessels, to have six domains, with the first three covering Human Resources and the last three Human Factors:

- Manpower – number of personnel required and potentially available to be involved in the ship;
- Personnel – the cognitive and physical capabilities of the personnel involved in crewing a ship;
- Training – required to provide the crew with job skills;
- Human Engineering – integration of human characteristics into the definition, design development and evaluation of the ship to optimise human/machine performance;
- Safety – identification, assessment and amelioration of hazards to health due to operation of the ship;
- Health and Safety – the risks occurring when the ship and its systems are functioning.

This overlap with safety and risk means that naval architects in particular are concerned with ship safety as fundamental to their practice of ship design. They are therefore likely to take the lead in addressing HF in the overall design of the ship, which is then operated by its master/commanding officer and the crew.

So, what has the ship designer traditionally needed to know about human factors? A good summary is provided in the SNAME compendium on ship design and construction, *Lamb (2003)*. *Calhoun and Stevens (2003)* both provide some necessary definitions as well as outlining aspects associated with the effects on human operators (and passengers where appropriate) of working and living (unlike any other form of terrestrial transport) on board vessels for long durations. This outline starts with human factors, human centred design (HCD) and ergonomics by pointing out that human error is responsible for 80% of maritime accidents. This leads on to consideration of particularly the working environment at sea and how equipment and key working spaces (such as the bridge and machinery control rooms) can be designed “ergonomically” to reduce operator errors.

The term Human Engineering is coined by *Calhoun and Stevens (2003)* to address:

- Techniques to define the role of the human in complex systems, such as those on modern ships up to and including complex naval vessels;
- The need to use simulation and modelling of crew workloads to reduce manning and assess operator/maintainer workloads;
- How advanced man-machine interfaces and computer based decision aids might reduce human error and accidents, while enhancing human performance and ship safety;
- Methods and data to assist ship designers in dealing with HF issues.

Beyond this they then consider human capabilities and limitations that designers need to be aware of. These are seen to be both cognitive (e.g. expectations, memory and data processing, emotional states and boredom, and sensitivity to stress), which are seen to be of growing importance with reduced manning and greater automation, and physical attributes of anatomy and anthropometry plus work and strength limitations. Both sets of attributes seem to be focused on man-machine/console design rather than the whole ship, which ought to be recognised to be a created mobile environment for several to thousands of human beings. Finally, this chapter considers the special environment from a physical standpoint:

- Human sensory limitations, such as illumination and vision, noise and hearing, noise reduction, visual and audio displays;
- Ship motions, both vibrations and acceleration effects on human performance and even living comfort;
- Other sensory and environmental limitations, such as temperature, atmosphere and skin pressure (these could be said to be extreme in two military domains – those of intensely high speed craft and of prolonged submarine operations);
- Fatigue, which is being more and more recognised as a major factor in ship safety.

A contrast to the above detailed “engineering” stance regarding HF in ship design, which focuses on the “micro-ergonomics” of console design and high intensity working space design, is provided by a recent UK publication. This is published by the professional body for mariners and entitled “Improving Ship Operational Design”, *NI (2015)*. It is a new version of a similarly entitled earlier publication, but this second edition takes a more strategic stance so differs from the more direct information structure of the above SNAME book chapter. *NI (2015)* book consists of a series of chapters, each with several discrete contributors. It does also provide an extensive list of references, which include several regularly produced HF guidance documents and web sites, e.g. www.imo.org, www.nautinst.org, and www.he-alert.org.

The first three chapters of the N.I. publication could be said to be scene setting and intended to address the ship designer and have the following titles:

1. Introduction to HCD for naval architects and designers;
2. What the ship designer needs from mariners and ship owners;
3. The maritime domain (context of use).

The first two chapters include contributions by the current paper’s author, who considers the HF issue for designers largely from a naval ship design stance, which is in contrast to the other contributors. The current author therefore draws on his early professional experience of seven months at sea on a range of naval vessels, which his generation of naval constructors were most fortunate to experience and are reflected upon at the end of this paper. These two contributions also address the HF expert who is often frustrated by the continued lack of adequate ergonomic design, particularly in much of the common passageways and general spaces throughout most ships. It is argued that this is in part due to the particular historic nature of both the bespoke-ness of ships and the construction culture in shipyards. Furthermore the fact that the contracted initial cost of a ship results from a very competitive exercise due to the nature of the procurement process, means shipyards compromise on HF detail, if they can get away with it. It also has to be admitted that the naval architect’s design focus remains

on getting right the first four aspects of “S⁵”, see *Brown and Andrews (1980)* and *Andrews (2017)*, for a more recent summary). This primary design focus has been understandable because failures in “stability”, “strength” and even “seakeeping” sink ships, whereas HF can be seen as only indirectly hazarding the ship (despite being the cause of 80% of accidents at sea, as already highlighted in Section 1), even if poor ergonomics can directly and severely hazard the mariner.

The remaining chapters in the N.I. book look at the various HF needs of the principal mercantile mariners and others involved in ship operations:

1. Operational requirements (OR) of the Captain/Officer of the Watch;
2. OR for pilots and tug masters;
3. OR in the engine room and MCR;
4. OR for cargo operations;
5. Living requirements for on-board personnel;
6. The needs of the ship owner;
7. Role and operations of HCD assessors.

So, there could be said to be much in the way of HF guidance to good practice, although the current author’s comments in *NI (2015)* tried to moderate the HF experts’ enthusiasm with the realities of current ship design culture and practice. The question is whether this needs to be changed by the imperatives of automation in ship operations and design. Before this is considered further, the next section draws on pertinent comments in a seminal work produced in the field of architectural design.

3. Architectural Design and the Need to Reflect Advances in the Human Sciences

Many architects have been seen to be very responsive to their clients and aware of the general needs of “human users” of their buildings, since they are less constrained than the ship designer by the extremes of environmental variability and (not at all) by need for their buildings’ mobility. Nevertheless, it has been argued they have not kept up with HF related developments in the built environment. This was most forcibly stated in the widely acknowledged classical text book “Design in Architecture” by *Broadbent (1988)*. This text is “one of the seminal works of design methodology” but more directly relevant to the current consideration of HF in complex design is that it “places (the role of) the psychological and cultural aspects” at the centre of building design.

While Broadbent’s book goes into relevant statistical methods and human science techniques, as well as “basic” and “social” needs, before dealing with design approaches and general methodological insights for architects, the latter could now be seen to be seminal rather than the state of the art they were some thirty years ago. However, his underlying review of the extent of the human sciences is both comprehensive and generic, and thus not overtaken by any subsequent developments in techniques. Broadbent is careful to say, in his review of some twenty-one human sciences that “*some of the human sciences can present the designer with useful information*”. In reviewing his list from a ship design stance, perhaps even fewer could be seen to be relevant to something so dominated by the physics of its potential environment and the need to design for economy, in the narrow and widest senses, as a modern ship. However any such review has to also bear in mind the opening remarks of this paper that the ship designer’s inadequate focus on HF ought now to be modified given the advance of automation at sea and in ship design practice. Broadbent’s list is in alphabetic order, with comment by the current author with respect to each subject’s applicability to ship design (in italics):

Anatomy: systematic description of the human body: *to be drawn on in ergonomics.*

Anthropology (physical): comparison of human physical variation: *to be drawn on in ergonomics.*

Anthropology (social): comparison human societal variation: *to be drawn on in ergonomics.*

Anthropology (structural): Application of structural theory to social anthropology: *probably outdated?*

Anthropometrics: direct measurement statistics: *to be drawn on in ergonomics.*

Archaeology: what survives from past: designers can always learn from past practice, *Coates (1994), Andrews (1994)*.

Demography: statistics of human indicators: *to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Ecology (human): study of human beings in geographical locations: *to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Ergonomics: standards for measuring physical environments and effect on human performance: *the basis of designing a ship's working and living environment for humans*.

Ethnography: descriptive study of peoples: *possibly to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Ethology: historical (cultural) ethnography: *possibly to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Ethology: animal behaviour – insights into psychology: *possibly to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Linguistics: descriptive/comparative study of language: *to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Parapsychology: no empirical evidence: *probably out-dated?*

Pathology: effect on human body of disease: *to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Physiology: systematic analysis of how living organisms adapt: *to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Psychiatry: treatment of mental disease: *possibly to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Psychoanalysis: various means of dealing with the human “unconscious”: *possibly to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Psychology: study of mind or behaviour: *to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Social psychology: study of people in groups: *to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Sociology: study of society: *to be drawn on in ergonomics*.

Broadbent provides more detailed descriptions of each of the above and, obviously, many have developed since his work, such as greater insights into societies or people en mass which could help in designing large spaces on board ships with many passengers (see *Ball (2004)*, for general developments and *Galea et al. (2006)* for a typical simulation approach). About half of Broadbent's listed human science topics have been considered as providing information relevant to being drawn upon in (feeding) the issue of ergonomics/HF in ship design, with a further five “human sciences” with some plausible relevance to HF in ship design. Even so this leaves many disciplines with on-going developments likely to change ergonomic guidance that could inform HCD assessors of HF in ship design (such as *Sherwood-Jones*, author of last chapter, outlined in the previous section, *NI (2015)*). This would suggest that direct expertise in such a large number of disciplines or even deep ergonomic/HF expertise is beyond the generalist naval architect or ship designer. It is probably a similar reaction from the architectural community that has meant in their case they are still focused on the aesthetic or style of their designs – as is the public in its response to prestigious architecture, *Rybczynski (2001)*.

However a simple dismissal as “too difficult” is to disregard the earlier comments on increasing automation, so some middle way needs to be found? Before this is explored the next section considers two applications of HF in ship design. These suggest that the generalist ship designer can respond to some of the HF experts disquiet at how “unconcerned” ship designers seem to be regarding HF. In addition, it could be argued the ship design community seems unaware as to how automation in ship design practice is already changing ship design and the role of the traditional ship designer, *Andrews (2018)*.

4. Ship Design Related Work on Personnel Movement and HF in Ship Safety

Having said that HF experts, such as HCD assessors, consider naval architects give inadequate attention in ship design to HF matters, it is considered useful to outline two projects where the author's research group, as a ship design focused research centre, have been involved in addressing how ship design practice can respond to this concern. In the first of these the UCL group acted as a ship design partner in just one of several large E.U. FP7 research projects, which were considering safety and risk in the maritime domain. This project, *FAROS, Piperakis et al. (2015)*, investigated the relationship between ship design and human performance (particularly error making by operators on board transportation vessels, such as super tankers).

As part of investigating the shipboard environment at both the whole ship level (appropriate to aspects such as ship motions) and local environment, such as accommodation location, the UCL Design Building Block approach to ship design synthesis, *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*, has been used to model both the architecture and the naval architecture of concept level ship representations. The DBB approach to early stage ship design allows the modelling of the internal arrangement of a ship using Design Building Block objects. Fig.1 is a screenshot of the DBBs comprising a single superstructure deck of the VLCC tanker design produced for the FAROS investigation. Fig.1 (left) shows the characteristics of a single DBB, such as its weight and location. These allow the DBBs to be linked to each other and to other features, such as the subdivision, enabling extensive parameterisation of the model for exploring design impacts on HF aspects.

Fig.1: FAROS parametric DBB model showing accommodation (green) and access (blue), *Piperakis et al. (2015)*

Two design variants of the tanker model involving the relocation of the aft located superstructure towards amidships were also developed. The first has the superstructure moved forward by one watertight compartment and in the second the superstructure is moved forwards by two watertight compartments. This led to the rearrangement of some cargo oil tanks (COTs) aft of the superstructure. The upper limit on the forward position of the superstructure was set by a maximum shaft length equal to that of the Emma Maersk class container ships (estimated as 120 m). Two variants were developed with different prime mover arrangements to the baseline. The first incorporated a duplicated prime mover, to remove the single point of failure represented by the main engine. The second variant included a flexible Integrated Full Electric Propulsion (IFEP) system. The three auxiliary gensets providing the hotel load and the main propulsion engine in the baseline were replaced by nine diesel gensets, which would provide all energy requirements. This arrangement can potentially lead to improved efficiency across a wider range of speeds / power demands, which may be of interest in scenarios adopting flexible slow steaming and green technologies, such as wind assistance. Fig.2 illustrates the machinery arrangements of the two variants. These variants were chosen to investigate the effect on the crew of lower motions with an amidships deckhouse location. Noise reduction benefits could also arise from better segregation of the propeller from the working spaces. However, the positioning of COTs in the narrow aft portion of the hull significantly reduces the cargo capacity (by approximately 9% in the example in Fig.2). This is a simple illustration that while improvements can be

made to the working and living environment on-board ships, there is usually some effect on the other desirable or even driving features of something so integrated and interactive as a ship design. So HF concerns have to be assessed alongside the rest of the design evolution and sensibly traded-off by the ship designer with their holistic ship design stance.

Fig.2: Superstructure relocation on the VLCC design by one watertight compartments with mechanical and electrical propulsion systems, *Piperakis et al. (2015)*

The second project was a UK research council (EPSRC) project undertaken jointly with the University of Greenwich (UofG) and sponsored by the UK Ministry of Defence, and therefore focused on naval vessels with considerably more complex manning and HF design issues than on tankers addressed in the FAROS project. In integrating the simulation of personnel movement into the early stage design of ships with complex internal typologies, the project interfaced the UofG simulation tool maritime-EXODUS, *Galea et al. (2006)*, with the UCL devised Design Building Block (DBB) architectural driven ship synthesis approach, *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*, realised in the SURFCON module in QinetiQ's Paramarine ship design toolset, *Bole and Forrest (2005)*. While the maritimeEXODUS tool was devised to simulate large scale evacuation of passengers and crew from passenger vessels (cruise ships and large ferries) this project considered a much more diffuse set of conditions where the crew of the naval combatant in question (UK Type 22 Batch 3 Frigate) could be simulated carrying out evolutions, such as moving through the ship as modelled in SURFCON, Fig.3.

Fig.3: PARAMARINE-SURFCON DBB model of the Royal Navy Type 22 Batch III Frigate baseline, *Andrews et al. (2008)*

This work raised the issue of the degree to which undertaking personnel movement simulations, such as those produced by maritimeEXODUS, affect ship design practice. Firstly, it required more detailed CAD modelling of the ship's internal arrangement than is normal in Early Stage Ship Design (ESSD), when the results of the simulation can still markedly affect major design choices. This is important because the HF experts wish the design to be appropriately responsive to HF needs, but this can only be truly done at an overall design level in ESSD, when the ship design definition is still fluid. It is

possible to go, even in ESSD, to a greater level of definition, as Figure 4 shows, and the results of doing so can then be used to challenge some design preconceptions. One that was explored in the project was whether such a large combatant should have two longitudinal passageways, rather than the current single central passageway, Fig.5 (see *Andrews et al. (2008)* for the outcome of this personnel simulation investigation).

Fig.4: Midships area of the baseline Royal Navy Type 22 Batch III Frigate design showing the addition of ladders and doors in the DBB model (left) and subsequent 2D deckplans generated from the 3D model, *Andrews et al. (2008)*

Fig.5: Comparison of single and double passageways on No 1 and 2 Decks for Royal Navy Type 22 Batch III Frigate, *Andrews et al. (2008)*

A further insight that came from this project was that there can be a large amount of statistically based data resulting from trying to simulate various HF activities, such as personnel movement. This means the naval architect has to devise a useful manner to display the results of such simulations, meaning the information that gives insights into design choices, which can improve those HF related aspects that help (or hinder) the operators at sea. This means the outputs must be presented in a form that helps the designer understand the benefits of making improvements to the operation/safety of the vessel, which usually have a design and cost impact. The fact that these also have to be appreciated by various stakeholders, including owners and budget holders, means these are best provided in visually comprehensible formats, Fig.6 (see *Andrews and Pawling (2009)* for a fuller discussion of the general issue of incorporating HF related analyses in ESSD).

Fig.6: UCL developed interactive visualisation tool for displaying HF relevant explorations, *Andrews et al. (2008)*

What can be concluded at this stage, from these two quite different exercises on quite different ship types, is that we have only just started to model, at a research level, selected HF issues on ships. We are some way from a clear set of guidance on what is appropriate and what can already be confidently modelled in the HF field in a practical manner in appropriate real ship design projects. We are only in the initial stages of exploring what can be modelled and how much might be possible to do, particularly in the very early stages of ship design. It is recognised that this is the best time in any ship design to take into account major topics that influence the major choices in ship configuration and layout. Given that many of the HF related design issues require exploring the architectural features in ESSD, it is clear this can only be done using a responsive ship synthesis, such as the UCL DBB type approach, *Andrews and Pawling (2003)*. Such interactive approaches can incorporate investigating the choices on hull and ship size, and hence performance and cost, and assessing them while addressing high level HF issues, *Andrews (2013)*. Assuming this is a route that ship design should go down to better address HF in ESSD, it is now appropriate to consider how future ship designers can be made more HF aware, while retaining their primary design responsibility for ship synthesis, ship design control and ship safety and performance, *Andrews (2016)*.

5. Should the nature of SD Education change to give HF more Prominence?

Given both the operational and design practice implications of automation, identified initially as to why naval architects ought to give greater consideration to HF aspects, it could be argued that greater knowledge of the fundamentals of much that Broadbent identified for urban design or architecture, listed in Section 3, ought to be expected of those future naval architects who will be primarily focused on ship design. However it is also the case that both the core sub-disciplines of naval architecture (i.e. “S⁴”, *Brown and Andrews (1980)*) are themselves also advancing in knowledge and complexity such that it is difficult for generalist naval architect, typified by the ship designer, “to keep up to date”. This also applies to on-going developments in tools, such as F.E.M. and CFD, as well as overarching topics, such as risk and safety regimes, *Vassalos (2012)*.

Just how much is it reasonable to expect the ship designer to be expert in, beyond the naval architectural and ship design fundamentals? These latter topics still largely govern the design of most ships and it is questionable as to whether future ship designers will need to devote effort to be aware of

developments in HF at the expense of those ongoing developments at the cutting edges of, say, propulsor design or limit state structural design or manoeuvring modelling? All this is a challenge since ship designers need to be aware of developments across all the maritime disciplines and also understand the underlying assumptions and their applicability of any such specialisms to any design proposals, especially novel design options stretching current practice. This “intelligent awareness” has not only an irreducible minimum but is also the best guide as to how to deal with new developments that have a strong bearing on ship design practice. This means there is also a need to cover growing issues of importance many of which relate not just to the human and automation at sea but also the man-machine interface at the “design table” that the modern desktop CAD computer has become.

The author’s view is that while much better understanding of the underlying principles and key assumptions behind a range of human sciences is required of future ship designers, this does not mean that they have to become HF experts. Rather they need to be informed and intelligent ship designers, properly aware of and responsive to this further set of disciplines alongside those of the engineering sciences already seen as appropriate to complex engineering design as it moves ever further into the Digital Age. One manner in which the future ship designer can be made to be more sympathetic to these important HF issues has already been mentioned in Section 2, with regard to *NN (2015)*. That is to say the insights the current author obtained from his extended time at sea from which he benefited prior to commencing his practice of ship design. The most important insight was not the (very useful) technical knowledge of how a ship functions but rather the cultural or even psychological insights from being immersed in that very unique social milieu that arises with a large number of personnel at sea in close and temporally extended proximity. If the large range of HF topics listed in Section 3 seemed somewhat fanciful to prosaic maritime engineers and their ship design practice “ashore”, such a lengthy immersion in seafaring has remained a salutary reminder that life at sea is something very special. As indeed is designing ships for sea-farers, which remains a privilege.

6. Conclusions

The implication of ever more automation in ships means HCD must grow in importance in ship design practice and an architecturally driven basis to ESSD is a good approach for the ship designer to be able to address key HF issues in ESSD.

However the naval architect, as the key ship design discipline cannot become a HF expert any more than being a deep expert in all the many sub-disciplines of traditional naval architecture. However the ship designing naval architect needs to have an awareness of the growing importance and knowledge base behind HF so that they can communicate intelligently with HF experts and be able to provide design proposals that better reflect the demand for more HF kindly and safe environments in vessels. Thus, as ever, the ship designer has to tread the narrow line between over design (i.e. meeting everyone’s expectations) and delivering an affordable and safe product, on time, and one that maintains an achievable performance throughout the vessel’s life. Such a demanding task was ever thus.

References

- ANDREWS, D. (1994), *Trireme to trimaran – The fascination of ship design*, J. Naval Eng. 35
- ANDREWS, D.J. (2003), *A creative approach to ship architecture*, RINA IJME, Sept 2003, Discussion and Author’s response IJME Sept 2004, Trans. RINA 145, 146 (2003, 2004)
- ANDREWS, D.J. (2013), *The true nature of ship concept design – And what it means for the future development of CASD*, COMPIT 2013, Cortona
- ANDREWS, D. (2016), *Ship project managers need to be systems architects not systems engineers*, RINA Conf. Maritime Project Management, London

- ANDREWS, D.J. (2017), *The key ship design decision – Choosing the style of a new design*, COM-PIT, Cardiff
- ANDREWS, D. (2018), *Is a naval architect an atypical designer – Or just a hull engineer?*, IMDC Espoo
- ANDREWS, D.J.; CASAROSA, L.; PAWLING, R.; GALEA, E.; DEERE, S.; LAWRENCE, S. (2008), *Integrating personnel movement simulation into preliminary ship design*, IJME Vol. 150, Part A1.; Discussion and Authors' reply IJME, Vol 150, Part A3
- ANDREWS, D.J.; PAWLING, R. (2003), *SURFCOON – A 21st century ship design tool*, IMDC, Athens
- BALL, P. (2004), *Critical Mass: How one thing leads to another*, William Heinemann, London
- BOLE, M.; FORREST, C. (2005), *Early stage integrated parametric ship design*, ICCAS, Busan,
- BROADBENT, G. (1988), *Design in Architecture: Architecture and the Human Sciences*, David Fulton Publ.
- BROWN, D.K.; ANDREWS, D.J. (1980), *The Design of Cheap Warships*, Int. Naval Technology Expo 80, Rotterdam
- CALHOUN, S.; STEVENS, S. (2003), *Human Factors in Ship Design*, Ch. 15, Ship Design and Construction, SNAME
- COATES, J. (1994), *The Naval Architecture of European Oared Ships*, Trans. RINA136 Part B
- DEERE, S. et al, (2006), *The Impact of the passenger response time distribution on ship evacuation performance*, Trans. RINA 148 Part A1
- DUCHATEAU, E. (2016), *Interactive evolutionary concept exploration in preliminary ship design*, PhD Thesis, TU Delft
- EARTHY, J.; SHERWOOD JONES, B. (2005), *Design for the human factor - The move to goal-based rules*, Proc. IMarEST
- LAMB, T. (2003), *Ship Design and Construction*, SNAME
- LEVANDER, K. (2012), *Cruise Ships – Success factors for the design*, IMDC, Glasgow
- NI (2015), *Improving Ship Operational Design*, Nautical Institute, London
- PAWLING, R.; ANDREWS, D. (2018), *Seeing arrangements as connections: The use of networks in analysing existing and historical ship designs*, IMDC, Espoo
- PIPERAKIS, A.S.; PAWLING, R.J.; ANDREWS, D.J. (2015), *The integration of human factors into preliminary risk-based ship design*, ICCAS, Bremen
- RYBEZYSKI, W. (2001), *The Look of Architecture*, O.U.P. Inc., New York
- VASSALOS, D. (2012), *Design for safety, risk-based design, life-cycle risk management*, IMDC, Glasgow

Parametric Cost Estimation at Azimut Yachts

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Abstract

Mega yacht builder Azimut Benetti is the biggest private group in the luxury boating sector. As the business unit Azimut Yachts is engaged in serial production, the design of a new yacht always means a long-ranging cost determination. In order to predict the cost of new designs, Azimut uses cost estimation relationships (CERs). These formulas are calculated based on technical parameters and labor hours respectively material cost of historical projects. This paper describes the estimation process using the cost management software 'CostFact'. The process includes assessing the usability of available data, deriving the CERs, evaluating their reliability and finally incorporating the results in the calculation of the project.

1. Initial Situation

Cost prognoses play an important role in the design of yachts: During the project start no sufficient information is available for detailed cost calculation. Nevertheless, a cost estimation must be generated quickly and accurately. Predicting costs is also necessary for comparing the actual design with cost targets. When doing so and a prospective cost overrun can be foreseen, design options have to be evaluated and the costs of each option have to be estimated. The information that can be used for cost prognoses depends on the current project phase, Fig.1. As shown in the picture, past projects can be used in all phases for cost predicting. This is done by similarity calculation which means that for one thing the technical data of the historical project and the cost that occurred during its production are examined and for another thing the similarities respectively differences between the project from the past and the current project are analyzed.

Fig.1: Information for cost prognoses according to project phase

2. Current Approaches of Parametric Cost Estimation

While analytical cost planning is primarily based on the assessment of components that generate costs, parametric cost planning can also refer to the functions fulfilled by component systems. Analytical and parametrical cost planning can be combined when planning the costs of a ship: Parametric cost planning is used especially in the early project phases for cost estimations of (main) building groups when detailed information about the components to be used as cost predictors is not yet available. As the project progresses and the available information increases, parametric cost prognosis can successively be replaced by analytical planning at more detailed levels to improve precision.

In parametric cost planning, the costs of previously built objects are compared with their technical attributes to ascertain if there is correlation between the costs and the attributes. A very simple and

common method in ship and yacht building is the use of cost indexes like welding hours per ton steel mass. After deriving the indexes from historical projects, the costs of a new object are predicted by multiplying the selected parameter by the corresponding index. At present, the use of weight as cost driving parameter dominates the scene of parametric cost estimation in shipbuilding, *Shetelig (2013)*. The clear advantage of cost indexes is their very simple use, both for deriving them from previous projects and applying them in new cost forecasts. However, this method assumes that the costs are directly proportional to the selected parameter. Such a linear cost progression is usually not the reality. Furthermore, the use of a mean value provides no insight as to how the costs of the reference object are distributed, meaning there is no indication that the cost prognosis is reliable.

A method that combines the advantages of cost indexes with a field of application that is not limited to linear correlation and also gives information on the reliability of a new cost estimation, is the regression analysis. Similar to cost indexes, this parametric procedure can be used to identify and describe the functional relation between an object's costs and its technical features, but the resulting formula can also refer to a non-linear relationship between cost and technical parameter. Furthermore, information can be gained on the reliability of cost prognoses, which base on the created formula.

Fig.2 presents a fictional example of a non-linear regression analysis where the propulsion power is the variable that affects the cost of the propulsion plant. The regression function is derived from seven already built yachts. The resulting function can be used to predict the cost of a new propulsion plant, based on the required propulsion power.

Fig.2: Regression analysis for the cost of propulsion plants

The execution of a regression analysis is carried out in the following steps, *Fischer and Holbach (2011)*:

1. The technical and economic data from previous projects have to be collected. Furthermore, cost data have to be updated if necessary, due to price increases or other changes.
2. The feature of the calculation object that will be used as cost determining parameter ("Propulsion Power" in the depicted example) must be defined. It is usually identified by a logical estimation of which element has the main effect on cost.
3. The regression function is generated. In general, the regression function is set up in such a way that the difference between the calculated costs and the actual costs is as small as possible.
4. The regression function is evaluated to assess the reliability of a cost prognosis generated by this function.

2. Software Support in Practice by CostFact

The software system "CostFact" was developed especially for the maritime sector. It supports cost management throughout all shipbuilding phases, beginning with the early phases of design and engineering, to the calculation accompanying the production and finally, to the analysis of already concluded projects. When setting up a calculation in CostFact, costs from alternative information sources can be integrated, such as:

- Unit rates
- Supplier proposals
- Previous projects
- Cost norms based on technical attributes

These different cost sources can be combined within a calculation. Typically, the utilization moves from parametric calculation with norms over cost import from previous projects to the direct input of costs or proposals from suppliers. This article focus the parametric approach.

CostFact contains an own module for parametric cost estimation. Compared to conventional calculation with spreadsheets, a main advantage of this module is the capability to integrate existing calculations by import from different sources like Excel-Files or ERP system automatically and to provide a uniform platform for the administration of all information required for parametric cost estimation. By this, such estimates can be carried out very efficiently.

2. CostFact Application by Yacht Builder "Azimut Yachts"

Using an example from real life, the procedure of setting up a calculation based on parametric relations is described in the following. The regarded shipyard performing the cost estimation is Azimut Yachts from Italy. Founded in 1969 for the chartering of sailing boats, Azimut quickly expanded its operations and began to design new yachts. With the acquisition of Benetti in 1985, Azimut became able to construct and produce its own yachts, defining new style and industry standards that revolutionized the boat building industry. In the course of implementing CostFact, Azimut Yachts' specific product breakdown structure was imported into the system. Furthermore, CostFact was populated with some representative projects from the past by importing these calculations from spreadsheet files.

After this general preparatory work was done, the actual parametric specific work started with the definition of the technical attributes which should be provided for use (see the left side of the window shown in Fig.3 with example "Propulsion Power").

In the next step, the elements of the product breakdown structure were assigned to the various technical parameters by selecting them from the list on the right. This designation is based on a technical and economic relationship between the attributes and the structure element (group). In other words, if the characteristic changes, the costs of the group assigned to it would also change. The example shown defines that a change of "Propulsion power" will lead to a cost change of group "YT0501 TRASMISSIONE" (transmission) and all of its subordinated groups.

Finally, for each project from the past the characteristic values of the different parameters were entered. Based on this data and information, a regression analysis was carried out. Fig.4 shows the corresponding window (some values are hidden for confidentiality). The added numbers refer to the description in the following. To begin the analysis, the user first selects the group to be calculated from the dropdown list (1, YT0705 Elettrodomestici in this example). After the selection, the attribute(s) dedicated to this group are displayed in the next list (2). The user selects the attribute that will most likely exert the strongest influence on cost respectively that is already available for the new project (here: Superficie/Surface $L_{max} \times B_{max}$).

Fig.3: Assigning groups to parameters

Fig.4: Regression analysis (values hidden for confidentiality)

Using the next list (3), the object to be analyzed is selected (Material Cost). Once these regression parameters have been defined, CostFact lists all projects in which the cost for the selected group has already been calculated and where the key data is available (4). In addition to the tabular presentation, the reference objects are also displayed in the scatter diagram on the right of the form (5). This visualization enables the user to quickly ascertain whether there is a correlation between the selected objects.

Optionally, the regression function can be weighted by excluding reference objects with inadequate similarity from the reference pool. In the current case (fictional example), the project “AZ9” (6) was identified to be an exception since its characteristics are different from the others projects and therefore untypical for the intended analysis. So, it was deselected in the list.

Finally, the user decides whether or not the costs should be indexed to a defined date. In this case CostFact escalates the costs of each project, based on a) the selected reference date, b) the respective date of the historical project and c) index values which are administered in CostFact centrally, specific for each cost class and calendar year.

In the next step, the regression function is calculated. CostFact uses the “least squares method”. In this method, the optimal adjustment of the regression function has been reached when differences between the sum of the squares of the actual values and those of the model values are as small as possible. CostFact includes four different regression models that are often used in practical situations (linear, potential, exponential and logarithmic). The so called “stability index” (displayed in column “SI”) measures the percentage of variance from the actual costs that can be explained by the regression. CostFact suggests the function with the highest stability index but the user is free to select the regression type they believe will best reflect the actual correlation. In the depicted example the chosen function is the exponential one, saying that the material cost can be calculated based on the technical parameter as:

$$\text{Material cost} = 197,0328 \times 1,0230^{\text{Superficie Lmax*Bmax}}$$

If the regression module is used for an ad hoc cost estimation, the user can already make a cost prognosis for the new object in the same window (“Add to norms” in the menu bar). However, in the example described here it is intended to incorporate the function into the calculation. Therefore, the user adds the derived cost function to the “Norm Pool” what makes it available for application within further projects’ calculations.

The current challenge is a cost prediction in the scope of a tender calculation at a very early stage with only few specification information and the need to generate the estimate very quickly. Against this background the user decides to calculate Material cost YT0705 Elettrodomestici based on the parameter “Superficie Lmax x Bmax” of the new project and the derived norm. To apply the function in the calculation, the user selects the object to be calculated and pulls up the window shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5: Input of parametric function (values hidden for confidentiality)

Besides the option to enter a project specific new function, this form provides access to the norm pool in order to select a stored function. In the displayed example the function that was previously derived by the regression analysis was chosen. The technical parameter of the new project (Surface Lmax x Bmax with 45 m² in the example) was already entered in the central project administration. The preview on the right side of the window shows the resulting number of material cost (548 €). After confirming, the complete function is implemented into the calculation.

The result is shown in the project calculation view that is depicted in Fig.6 (together with other cost inputs): Displaying the product breakdown structure on the left side and the cost data on the right, this view can show the complete calculation – from the single items at the final level of the tree view, via the subordinated and main building groups with sub totals, through to the costs of the complete project on the top level.

Fig.6: Calculation view of completed project (excerpt, fictional)

When a change of the technical attributes takes place, the complete costs can be recalculated self-acting. This is particularly helpful in the first phase with many design modifications. In principle, the complete (rough) calculation can be set up by those parametric functions. By reusing the resulting structure for new projects, it will be sufficient to enter the ship's current attributes and the proposal calculation is created automatically, based on the defined dependences.

References

FISCHER, J.O.; HOLBACH, G. (2011), *Cost management in shipbuilding*, GKP Publishing

SHETELIG, H. (2013), *Shipbuilding Cost Estimation - Parametric Approach*, M.Sc. Thesis, NTNU, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim

Conception of Navigation Assistance System Integrating New Sensor Technologies and Model-based Prediction

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Abstract

The joint project 'GALILEOnautic' aims to develop control systems for fully automated vessels. The application of navigation assistance systems (NAS) is a first approach in conventional manual manoeuvring toward higher level of automation. The paper presents the generic components of a NAS based on manoeuvre prediction. For derivation of the necessary functionality of NAS, the behaviour of experienced navigators during manoeuvring was analysed. Further aspects will be discussed such as adequate precision of ship motion model resulting from actuator and environmental data, additional sensor equipment especially for proximity recognition and demands on the visualisation and personalisation of prediction.

1. Introduction

Marine accidents rise both in terms of number and cost mainly because of human behaviour. In order to avoid collisions and groundings, it is decisive to equip marine vehicles with assistance systems for navigation. Especially in adverse environmental conditions or narrow waterways, such systems can assist the nautical officer during manual manoeuvring. The joint project 'GALILEOnautic' aims to develop control systems for fully automated vessels cooperating in areas requiring highest level of safety and efficiency, such as harbours or narrow waterways. The legal basis and the state of the art in manoeuvring do not allow automatic control in such areas with very small safety margins next to the optimal route. In the first period of the project, the basic structures are developed to process all data of the vehicles in an encounter situation, optimize the routes and control automatically the path following on these routes. In the demonstrated encounter situation, a manually controlled vehicle is involved to reflect the future mixture of crewed and autonomous vehicles. In the planned scenarios, the need results that avoidance behaviour of both vehicle types must be according to the known classic rules. E.g., an evasive manoeuvre needs to be identifiable by the clear change of heading. It also follows that common manoeuvring behaviour has to be adapted for the autonomous vehicles in creation, optimization and automatic control. Simultaneously, the developed methods for unmanned vehicles can influence the current practice in manoeuvring. The reasons are the higher knowledge of the motion process and the environmental measurements as well as the resulting more precise effectivity in actuator settings in combination with high dynamic automatic control. The support in manual manoeuvring can be offered initially in navigation assistance systems with different tools depending on personal requirements to enhance the safety for human beings, environment and machine. In the first period of the project, the methods are evaluated by application in a ship handling simulator (SHS) and for smaller unmanned surface vehicles (USV).

2. Generic Components of Assistance System for Ship Navigation

The assistance system for ship navigation is defined in the presented application as a visualisation of the predicted dynamic motion of the own ship based on the current manual actuator settings and the relevant environmental forces. Therefore, a 'dynamic motion model' provides the main basis for a manoeuvre prediction system, Fig. 1. In a first step, the dynamic model represents the relations between the actuator settings and the resulting motion of the vessel. It takes into account all actuators and their cross connections, such as the different effects of certain rudder angles at various velocities of the vessel or propulsion. The external forces and moments to the hull of the vessel counteract the actuator forces and moments which are described completely in the equations of motion in at least 3 degrees of freedom (DOF). The relationships between actuator settings and resulting forces as well as the model parameters

are described in various lookup tables. The ship-model parameters are tuned by the software tool SIMOPT of the ISSIMS institute by parallel simulation of different manoeuvres to achieve the best fit between measured motion states and model data, *Benedict et al. (2014)*.

These lookup tables must be filled from sufficient measurement data, their interpolation and extrapolation in the complete setting range. The quality and the quantity of the data is to verify whether they are correct describing the characteristic behaviour in all motion states of the vessel. Especially in manoeuvring mode in narrow waterways at small velocity, vessels show a strong nonlinear behaviour. The data will be collected during common vessel operations forbidding maximum actuator settings because of the safety and effectivity guidelines. Additionally, the measurement equipment on board and its interfaces decide about the quality of data. Supplemental sensors are needed to identify a sufficient accurate model for application in an assistance system, in particular sufficiently accurate orientation and position data. In the described investigations, an additional GNSS (global navigation satellite system) receiver (AsteRx3 HDC) and two IMU's (inertial measurement unit) of different precision for comparison only have been applied (Crossbow AHRS440, Xsens MTi-G-710), *Schubert and Gluch (2017)*.

Fig.1: Preparatory work components of a navigation assistance system

The measured actuator and sensor data need to be synchronised and fused. The positioning systems provide different timestamps. The engine data are registered in the voyage data recorder (VDR). Each supplemental sensor is recorded with different sampling rates. Because of this reason, the total set of actuator and sensor data must be synchronised for a consistent timeline before using in modelling. The model depending fusion of the data includes an assignment of weights to the data according to their quality in the current situation.

In harbours or narrow waterways, the precision of measured GNSS data can be insufficient by shadowing effects due to buildings or vegetation. Furthermore, the ECDIS (electronic chart display) maps show wrong or almost inaccurate positions of harbour facilities and isn't suitable to illustrate adequately the navigation process. There are different options to assist the navigation by proximity recognition systems. Typical sensors are cameras, IR cameras, radar or lidar based sensors known from automotive applications. With regard to autonomous shipping, the different sensors will be combined due to their operability under various weather conditions. The effect of large water surface has to be considered in the evaluation of the sensor data. In the result of the measurements, the distances to fix and moving objects are correlated with the estimated vehicle position. In sensor fusion for harbours, the proximity recognition data get the highest weighting because of their highest reliability.

An essential component of a NAS is the collection and provision of the environmental data as well as their impact on the dynamic motion of the vessel. Normally, the nautical officer estimates the environmental conditions and considers them in subsequent manoeuvres. Additionally, the officer can use individual sensors onboard or external to measure the current or the wind but with a few or only one measurement points on the vessel. To consider these data together with the observations in the manoeuvring process, the pilot needs a mental model of their impact on the dynamic motion. The quality of this model depends strongly on the practical experience of the nautical officer. Particularly, extreme conditions are often not covered by individual mental models. An assistance system offers the opportunity to integrate the sum of environmental impacts in the dynamic motion model.

The prediction of the resulting motion from the current actuator settings and the environmental forces needs to be visualised in intuitively comprehensible manner. The visualisation gives the feedback whether the settings are adequate to reach the subsequent planned position. Adequacy is evaluated by correlation of the predicted path and the required space. This needs appropriate map section, zoom level and prediction horizon. During manual manoeuvring, automatic adaption of these monitoring parameters is recommended depending on actual velocity. Alternatively, it should be possible that each operator can choose personal configurations before starting the manoeuvring. Additionally, alarms and hints can be given if the predicted path presents significant risks of collision or grounding, *Baldauf et al. (2017)*.

In an extended version of assistance systems for navigation, the degree of automation will be increased by collision avoidance control based on AIS data of other vehicles in the surrounding and an automatically calculated evasive path. This path is still a recommendation to the responsible operator for manual guidance. A further step towards autonomous shipping is taken with automatic path control *Kurowski et al. (2017)*. The operator can plan digitally the docking manoeuvre, for instance, or load a successful manoeuvre plan which was executed automatically considering the current environmental conditions. On this automation level, the nautical officer acts as supervisor and fall-back option both in one person.

3. Questionnaire-based survey of the common manoeuvring behaviour

In the joint project ‘GALILEOnautic’, there is a letter of intend of shipping company Scandlines. During interviews and observations onboard, an anonymous questionnaire-based survey was developed to analyse the common individual behaviour of the nautical officers during manual manoeuvring from the bridge wings. The first part of this survey addresses the conventional usage of the available monitors and the estimations through the bridge window. In Fig.2, the template is illustrated to evaluate the usage of the multifunction display. The usage is classified on a scale from 0 (=never) to 10 (=always), depending on how frequently each parameter is used during the hole manoeuvring time.

Fig.2: Evaluation template of multifunction display in the bridge wings

Similarly, the estimations through the window will be evaluated. A list of the usual parameters was compiled: distances between bow or stern to the pier, the angle to the pier, the location of the vessel in the fairway, the distances to other vehicles or harbour facilities as well as the environmental parameters such as wind speed or direction of the current. There are blank spaces for individual parameters of each participant.

In the second part, the questioning takes place on desired additional information. Different pictures are shown to support the berthing manoeuvre or the correction for the current. The participant has to decide whether the description in 2D (ECDIS) is clearer than in 3D as well as which parameters in which precision are useful next to the quay. An example of optional berthing support is given in Fig.3. Furthermore, it will be surveyed the usage of route planning in the ECDIS, desired tools for saving and analysing different routes, different optimization criteria for manoeuvring or desired distance alarms depending on the own speed and the mobility of the object.

Fig.3: Description of berthing support in 2D or 3D

The personal opinions in the questionnaire-based survey vary widely and show the highly individualised approach in the navigation and manoeuvring process. As was to be expected, the speed over ground (SOG), the velocities in stern and bow as well as the rate of turn (ROT) are the most frequently used parameters of the multifunction display. Tendentiously, they use more the absolute values than the relative, except for SOGs and ROT. The location of the vessel in the fairway, the resulting correction for current and the distance to the jetty entrance are the most common estimated values by view through the window. Thereby, no distinction is made between the absolute values and their trends. In addition, different distances are assessed regularly such as distance to the quay or to other vessels. The frequency of estimation of the environmental situation depends on the stability of the weather conditions. An additional representation of the vehicle position in relation to the quay, Fig.3, is not desired generally expect in exceptional situations by presentation in the ECDIS. Whereas, the participants desire the additional representation of environmental situation including both current and wind. Especially in poor visibility conditions during the night for example, the resulting forces on the vehicle are difficult to estimate by mental model.

Similarly, most nautical officers favors a digital route planning in the ECDIS. The participants commented that the planned route supports the detection of critical situations and the following decisions. The broad majority considered appropriate the saving of all manoeuvring data including manoeuvre points with velocities, actuator values, environmental data, fuel consumption as well as the difference to the planned route. It was commented that these data are especially useful in the analysis of critical manoeuvres and during training sessions. Data saving immediately affects the results for reasonable optimisation criteria on the one hand of planned route or on the other hand for future developments of automatic manoeuvring. Therefore, the time requirement and the adaption of the manoeuvre plan to adverse weather conditions are the most important criteria for the participants.

Unfortunately, a minimal fuel consumption or a low emission level play a less essential role. A further part of the survey addresses alarms depending on the own actual velocity and the distance to other vehicles or different harbour facilities. The assessment spread broadly because of the additional strong dependency on the harbour characteristics, for example the width of the jetty entrance. They agreed that

no alarms for the distance to other vehicles are needed. For the distances to harbour facilities, the majority prefers the combination of optical and acoustical alarms without increase because of decreasing distance. Until now, the analysis results of desired distances for alarm allow no clear statement. The same applies to addressed prediction horizons. The probable reason is that the participants had no handling habit with distance alarms or prediction tools and cannot gauge effective parameters. The survey must be proofed in these points, perhaps accompanied by training with these new tools.

Fig.4: Motion prediction based on dynamic ship modelling

Consequently, there is a need (at least in psychological terms) to personalise the assistance system in the transition between manual and higher automated manoeuvring. The personalisation has different advantages. Each nautical officer can choose his own additional information depending on the situation onboard and in the environment. He continues to be responsible for the manoeuvring process and there are no legal impediments whereby the acceptance is increasing immensely on both sides. The manoeuvre prediction shows the future motion of the vessel resulting from actuator settings of the responsible officer and the environmental forces. The prediction provides him greater certainty in guidance accompanied by less actuator variations, more effectivity as well as more protection for the machine and the environment. Because of the high precision of the underlying ship-specific model, the mental knowledge base of experienced officer is confirmed or further tuned. During the professional training, the prediction can help to build the own dynamic, mental motion model by simulation without risks. The current practice onboard shows already personalised usage of the monitors or the INS (integrated navigation system) so that this NAS is only a further option.

4. Proximity Recognition

Fig.5 presents a harbour entrance in the ECDIS overlaid with the standard radar detections. The sensor signals show the displacement of the ECDIS data with more than 10 m as well as the defocusing of the radar signals which complicates the estimation of the true object position. This error can have various reasons such as accuracy of the map material, the configuration of radar or the position measurements. Especially in reduced visibility during night or adverse weather, this presentation is used for the orientation and constitutes an additional danger.

Fig.5: Differences between radar detections and ECDIS locations

Therefore, a new proximity recognition system was developed which is suitable in the maritime environment. Fig.6 shows the combination of lidar and radar system installed on the small USV (unmanned surface vehicle) MESSIN, *Majohr and Buch (2006)*, to detect the objects in a 360°-view around the vehicle. In the conception of sensor fusion, the proximity recognition data have the highest weight near harbour facilities or other objects. The sensor combination works in a vicinity of 40 m, *Kupas et al. (2017)*.

The distance measurement by the used radar sensors bases on the frequency-modulated continuous wave (FMCW) overlaid with a sawtooth pattern of the signal whereby the resulting phase shift between transmitted and the received signal reflects the distance. The quality of the measurements depends on the bundling of the beams, the shape and the material of the reflecting objects. The advantage of radar with lower frequencies is that the signals are only slightly attenuated by rain. The in-house development combines 6 single-chip radar sensors TRX_120_001 (Silicon Radar) each with a viewing angle of 60° from which the two opposite sensors are measuring simultaneously, Fig.6.

The centrepiece of the lidar system builds the M16 Eval Kit by Leddartech conceived originally for automotive applications. The sensor sends a pulsed laser light by infrared LEDs and receives the reflected light by photodetector row array. The time of flight serves as a measurement of the distance between sensor and target. The M16 module consists of 16 independent active channels for simultaneous acquisition arranged horizontally with a field of view of 90°. The module is mounted in a case which is rotated by a step motor control with resolution of 1.8° in the range of 270° in heading direction of the USV. The lidar module provides an accuracy of 5 cm depending on the distance of the target. Laser beams are strongly attenuated by environmental impacts.

Fig.6: Lidar-radar-system mounted on USV

The distance data of lidar and radar system are fused locally on a microcontroller board. In the first stage, the result is displayed only in scatter plot. The high accuracy of the sensor system offers further applications such as object identification and direct distance control for automatic docking similar to the schematic diagram in Fig.3. In the summarising assessment, the combination of radar and lidar sensor presents a complementary measurement module in maritime surrounding to ensure the quality of proximity recognition data under various visibility conditions.

5. Summary and Outlook

This paper presents the conception of a NAS for manoeuvring in high safety areas based on dynamic motion prediction. It describes the preliminary works to establish an adequate dynamic motion model serving as basis to predict the future motion of the vehicle resulting from the current actuator settings

and environmental data. The relevant data must be acquired by sensors with sufficient precision to characterise the motion as well as the position in relation to the harbour facilities, for example. The collected data have to be filtered, synchronised and fused offline for modelling and online in the application in NAS or higher automation of manoeuvring. According to the necessary identifiable manoeuvres in mixture traffic of manual and automated controlled vehicles, the conventional behaviour during manual manoeuvring was surveyed questionnaire-based. In the result, the highly individual approaches are obviously in the manoeuvring process itself and in the usage of monitors also. It was concluded that an accepted and frequently used NAS must be offering customisable functionality. But, a personalised NAS gives the chance also to introduce the automation in manoeuvring in a gentle manner. By application of the NAS in practice, the automation process can profit from the feedback to a suitable operation.

In the second period of the project 'GALILEOnautic', higher automation level is planned. The developed methods should be demonstrated by real vessels. The proximity recognition must be redesigned in the number of sensors and in combination with different camera types to adapt the sensor system to the size of the vehicle and the expected environment. The processing of the sensor data is more complex because of the distribution of the sensors on board and probably on shore. The adequate proximity recognition is the precondition for assisted and automated entrancing port and docking, Fig.7. Simultaneously, the expansion and application of the NAS on board should be continue in close cooperation with nautical officers.

Fig.7: Concept of proximity recognition for larger vessels presented in the ECDIS

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References

BALDAUF, M.; MEHDI, R.; FISCHER, S.; GLUCH, M. (2017), *A perfect warning to avoid collisions at sea?* Scientific J. Maritime University of Szczecin 49/121, pp. 53-64

BENEDICT, K.; KIRCHHOFF, M.; GLUCH, M.; FISCHER, S.; SCHAUB, M.; BALDAUF, M.; KLAES, S. (2014), *Simulation augmented manoeuvring design and monitoring – A new method for advanced ship handling*, TRANSNV 8/1, pp.131-141

KUPAS, Int. Symp. Automatic Control, Wismar

KUROWSKI, M.; SCHUBERT, A.U.; JEINSCH, T. (2017), *Generic control strategy for future autonomous ship operations*, 16th COMPIT Conf. Computer, Cardiff, pp.401-412

MAJOHR, J.; BUCH, T. (2006), *Modelling, simulation and control of an autonomous surface marine vehicle for surveying applications Measuring Dolphin MESSIN*, Advances in Unmanned Marine Vehicles, Ch.16, pp.329-352

SCHUBERT, A.U.; GLUCH, M. (2017), *Automatic analysis of ship sensor data applicating in manoeuvre assistance*, Int. Symp. Automatic Control, Wismar

Automated Crack Detection for Drone-based Inspection Using Convolutional Neural Network

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Abstract

Automatic detection of vessel defects such as cracks is a crucial part of developing the autonomous drone-based vessel inspection. This paper presents two crack detection models developed using convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The first model aims to classify cracks in static images by assigning a label to the image to indicate the existence of the crack. We adapt pre-trained classification CNNs into the model and transfer their learned weights by fine-tuning to the crack classification task. The second model aims at localizing the crack in a pixelwise manner and is a fully convolutional network built from scratch. We evaluate the two models on a dataset which is small but shows substantial variation in image quality. This study not only demonstrates the feasibility of machine-learning-based crack detection but also provides some insight into the challenges of developing robust and highly-accurate models for segmenting and classifying amorphous objects such as cracks.

1. Introduction – Drone-based survey with visual intelligence

Vessel safety surveys, such as initial survey, annual survey and renewal survey, are crucial during the lifetime of a vessel. The principles of ensuring vessel safety are regulated by the International Maritime Organization (IMO). The detailed survey requirements are typically specified by classification societies, such as DNV GL, which carry out the survey in accordance with IMO regulations and Survey Requirements. The vessel safety highly depends on the inspection scope required by the classification society and the individual surveyor's competence and knowledge.

The current practice of conducting the vessel survey brings three major issues. First, it typically requires that the human surveyor enters the tanks and inspects visually. The operations may cause fall accidents, oxygen shortage, and rafting accidents. In addition to personnel safety, the second issue is the high cost of conducting a survey. The total cost includes the preparation of the vessel, use of yard facilities, loss of the vessel owner while the vessel is inoperable, and man cost of the surveyor, etc. The last issue is the possible environmental pollution. For instance, releasing water from oil tanks after a rafting-based inspection pollutes the sea water. Therefore, this inspection approach is not allowed in some regions.

To deal with the issues stated above the maritime sector has to explore new technologies which will revolutionize vessel inspection regime in the near future. Particularly, the development of (autonomous) drones has opened up new possibilities. DNV GL has carried out multiple drone surveys on both ships and offshore units. The drone surveys inspected many areas on board, ranging from tanks and cargo holds to external structures such as jack-up legs. Using drones to visually check the condition of remote structural components can significantly reduce survey times and staging cost, while at the same time improving surveyor safety.

The drone-based survey offered by DNV GL currently relies on one surveyor operating the drone while another surveyor monitoring the video feed in real time. To develop an automated survey process DNV GL has a longstanding research & development (R&D) program on developing advanced inspection technologies. Particularly, a research project, named ADRASSO (Autonomous Drone-based Surveys of Ships in Operation) which is funded by Norwegian Research Council, aims at developing an intelligent, autonomous drone for inspections of ships. The drone will fly with mini-

mal pilot operation in a cargo or ballast tank and spot various defects. One major research challenge in ADRASSO is to develop computer vision algorithms/models for automated ship defects detection.

We have investigated both conventional computer vision and deep learning techniques for crack detection in our previous project. This paper summarizes the challenges encountered and results achieved in our previous project.

2. Apply conventional computer vision techniques for crack detection

2.1 Cracks detection for ship safety

Steel ship structures are prone to developing cracks because of their all welded construction, material imperfections, loading conditions, fatigue and corrosion. The cracks normally may not pose a direct threat to the ship structural integrity. However, when a ship is subjected to a sudden impact force typically associated with collision, allusion and grounding accidents, the existing cracks could propagate rapidly and lead to structural failure and compromise the tank leak integrity, *Nair et al. (2017)*.

The potential consequence of cracks may be severe. Therefore, detection of cracks is necessary during periodic ship surveys to ensure ship safety. When surveyors detect any defects, they typically take some photos (using ordinary digital cameras) which are used as the evidence for survey reports. Although DNV GL owns a huge number of images taken during ship surveys, those images pose significant technical challenges when using them to develop the automated crack detection system. The primary reason is that the images were taken for documentation purpose but not for computer vision purpose. Fig.1 shows some examples of the images containing cracks. Those examples reveal the main difficulties when using the images to develop and train the automated crack detection system.

- Images were taken by different cameras under different lighting conditions. The resolutions and qualities vary sharply.
- The shape of cracks is irregular. The size of cracks varies substantially.
- A high percentage of cracks occur in heavily corroded surfaces. The boundary of the crack is hardly recognized.
- Some cracks are hardly detected without ship survey competence.

Fig.1: Examples of images containing cracks

2.2 Computer vision techniques

Computer vision based crack detection has been applied to many industrial processes, including detection of cracks on roads, bridges, tunnels, *Bu et al. (2015)*, *Ehrig et al. (2011)*. The common goals of applying computer vision techniques to detection of cracks in various surfaces are reducing inspection cost, increasing inspection accuracy, and/or ensuring personnel safety.

A crack detection approach typically consists of four main steps as depicted in Fig.2. The principle of developing a computer vision based crack detection system is to extract features from the initial set of images. Particularly, we need to identify features which can distinguish cracks from other objects/ background noises in the images.

Fig.2: Typical crack detection system

2.2.1 Edge detector

The features extracted from an image can be classified into low-level features and high-level features. Low-level features are those basic features that can be extracted automatically from an image without any shape information. For instance, edge detection is one basic technique to interpret images since analysis based on edge detection is insensitive to change in the overall illumination level. Edge detection highlights image contrast which is difference in intensity.

Fig.3: Comparison of edge detectors

A change in intensity can be revealed by differencing adjacent points. Differencing horizontally adjacent points will detect vertical edges while differencing vertically adjacent points will detect horizontal edges. Some edge detectors detect both horizontal and vertical edges such as Scharr, Sobel and Prewitt. Among the commonly used edge detectors, Canny edge detector is known as the optimal edge detector and enhances many existing edge detectors. We tested the classical edge detectors provided by Scikit-image in Python and compare their results in Fig.3. Although Sobel, Scharr and

Prewitt edge detector are able to detect the most visible part of the crack (red circle highlights the crack), all of them also falsely detect the edge of the shadow area (yellow circle highlights the shadow area). The false detection reveals two big drawbacks of those classical edge detectors, i.e. sensitivity to noise and inaccuracy.

Edge detection is a fundamental step in computer vision. To choose edge detectors that fit best to the application we have investigated Canny detector and show the results in Fig.4. Red bounding boxes are used to highlight the edge pixels detected by Canny detector. Canny detector has three adjustable parameters: the width of Gaussian filter, σ , and the low and high threshold for the hysteresis thresholding. By adjusting the three parameters Fig.4(d) yields the best detection result with fewest false detections. Although Canny detector is fairly advanced and can yield good results, it is based on thresholding. To decide the optimal threshold values for images which possess substantial variations is neither trivial nor a robust solution for our application.

Fig.4: Canny detector results

2.2.2. Supervised pixel-level classification

Simply applying edge detector to crack detection is not sufficient. We have developed an approach for crack detection by learning features from the labelled crack pixels. The approach consists of a sequence of computer vision techniques and is outlined in Fig.5. The original RGB (red, green, blue) image is first converted into gray-level image to facilitate calculation of the gradient of the image which can be used to extract information from edges. Then the gray-level intensity and gradient of crack pixels are used as criteria to detect cracks. The more training samples used, the more accurate thresholds of intensity and gradient can be determined.

Fig.5: Supervised pixel-level classification

Fig.6: Example of pixel-level crack detection

Fig.6 provides an example of detecting crack pixels by following the steps depicted in Fig.5. The original image and the corresponding gray-scale format are shown in (a) and (b), respectively. (c) is the gradient of the gray-scale image where the main line of the crack is distinguished from the background. Then we search the original image and use both intensity and gradient of crack pixels as criteria to classify each pixel into crack (marked as red color) and non-crack (kept the original color). The pixel-level classification result is shown in (d) which still contains many red spots which consist of pixels having the same intensity and gradient as crack pixels do. To remove those small spots, the image is transformed into gray-scale image shown in (e). Then morphological closing technique is

applied to (e). After morphological closing, most of the small dark spots are removed and small bright cracks are connected as shown in (f). To further remove the noise, the total variation denoising technique is applied and removes unwanted details while preserving important details such as edges. Denoising also leads to the blurred image shown in (g) which detects the main part of the crack.

The supervised pixel-level crack detection relies on the color and intensity of labelled crack pixels of training images. These two features are still not sufficient for handling diversity and variety of cracks.

The main challenge of computer vision based object detection is to appropriately select a subset of the initial features to contain relevant information from the input data and describe the input data with high accuracy. However, determining the appropriate subset of the initial features demands deep knowledge on computer vision and is very application-dependent. As the convolutional neural network (ConvNet) has become a very powerful technology for speeding up the development of computer vision, the hand-craft feature selection can be replaced by a properly designed ConvNet which directly discovers the features needed for performing the specific task. Thus, we present two ConvNet architectures for crack detection in the following sections.

3. Deep learning model for object classification

Deep learning is a subset of machine learning. The main difference between traditional machine learning and deep learning is in the feature engineering as illustrated in Fig.7. We need to hand-craft the feature in traditional machine learning algorithms. By contract, in deep learning algorithms feature engineering is done automatically by the algorithm. Feature engineering is difficult, time-consuming and require domain expertise. Deep learning algorithms can be more accurate than traditional machine learning algorithms with less or no feature engineering. Remarkably, deep learning ConvNet models have been extremely successful on object classification applications. In this section, we present how to build a crack classification model based on a pre-trained deep ConvNet model.

Fig.7: Traditional machine learning vs. deep learning

3.1. Deep convolutional neural networks (ConvNets)

Deep learning models often consist of multiple hidden layers and are able to solve complex pattern recognition problems. Deep ConvNets have shown outstanding results in object recognition since labelled datasets with millions of images have become available. ConvNets' learning capacity is controlled by varying their depth and breadth. A complex ConvNet architecture can be composed of up to several tens of layers. Lower layers of a ConvNet contain more generic features (e.g. edge detectors or color blob detectors) that should be useful to many object recognition tasks. Higher layers of the ConvNet become more specific to the details of the classes contained in the training dataset. Training deep ConvNets to learn a very accurate mapping from inputs to outputs has achieved excellent results if the input is large amounts of labelled data. However, the deep ConvNets are still not capable of generalizing to conditions that are different from the ones encountered during training the models. When applying deep ConvNets to applications/tasks of computer vision, we often face the challenge that the available dataset is not large enough to train the deep ConvNet.

3.2. Transfer learning

To deal with the difficulty of insufficient training datasets transfer learning has proven to be very promising and powerful technique. Transfer learning refers to the situation where what has been learned in one setting is exploited to improve generalization in another setting, *Goodfellow et al. (2016)*. Transfer learning becomes popular in deep learning area which requires the enormous resources to train models. Many deep ConvNets trained on huge amount of images exhibit a curious phenomenon in common: first-layer features appear not to be specific to a particular dataset or task, but are generally applicable to many datasets and tasks. Features must eventually transition from general to specific by the last layer of the network, *Yosinski et al. (2014)*. The transferability of features decreases as the distance between the base task and the target task increases. But transferring features even from distant tasks can be better than using random features.

To apply transfer learning, we first select a ConvNet model, which has been pre-trained on an abundance of dataset (e.g. ImageNet) for a source task, as a base model. (ImageNet is a large database designed for use in visual object recognition software research. Over 14 million URL of images have been hand-annotated to indicate what objects are pictured. It contains over 20000 ambiguous categories.) The output layer of the pre-trained model has to be replaced by another output layer with two output classes, i.e. Crack or Non-Crack. Then we fine-tune the crack classification model using our dataset. The complete procedure of building, training and testing the crack classification model is described in Section 3.4.

3.3. State-of-the-art ConvNet architectures for object classification

Numerous pre-trained deep learning models have been developed for object classification. For instance, the winners of a large and challenging image classification task, the ImageNet 1000-class photograph classification competition. The winning ConvNet architectures of the ImageNet competition include AlexNet, *Krizhevsky et al. (2012)*; VGGNet, *Simonyan and Zisserman (2014)*; Inception, *Szegedy et al. (2015)*, *Szegedy et al (2016)*, etc. Other state-of-the-art deep learning object classification models include such as ResNet50, *He et al. (2016)* and Xception, *Chollet (2017)*. How to choose a pre-trained model for crack classification is also challenging. Common practice is to test several pre-trained models on the same dataset and compare their performance/accuracy. One example is to compare the classification accuracy of VGG16, VGG19, ResNet50, Inception V3 and Xception all of which have been pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset and included in the Keras core library, <https://www.pyimagesearch.com/2017/03/20/imagenet-vggnet-resnet-inception-xception-keras/>. (Keras is the Python Deep Learning library. It is a high-level neural networks API, written in Python and capable of running on top of TensorFlow, CNTK, or Theano.) The comparison shows that Xception model correctly classified the image with the highest accuracy. Therefore, we choose Xception as the base ConNet architecture and modify it to classify cracks.

3.4. Modified Xception architecture for crack classification

The Xception architecture was proposed by Francois Chollet who is the author of Keras. This architecture extends the Inception architecture by replacing the standard Inception modules with depthwise separable convolutions. (The Inception architecture has been one of the best performing family of models on the ImageNet dataset since its first introduction. It has performed well on the internal datasets of Google as well.) Xception outperforms Inception V3 on several well-known datasets including ImageNet and JFT. (JFT is an internal Google dataset for large-scale image classification task which comprises over 350 million high-resolution images annotated with labels from a set of 17000 classes.)

The Xception architecture is shown in Fig.8 and its last layer decides the number of output classes. The Xception model API provided by Keras has been pre-trained on ImageNet and its last layer is a 1000-class classifier which is the logistic regression layer highlighted by the red rectangle.

Fig.8: Xception architecture, Chollet (2017)

Fig.9: Use transfer learning to build a crack classification model

Our dataset for crack classification contains only 237 images and is fairly small. Data similarity between our dataset and ImageNet is very low. Thus, it might work better to re-train higher layers and the output layer of the pre-trained Xception model. The transfer learning procedure is shown in Fig.9 and described below.

- *Part I: Build a crack classification model*
 - Step 1: *Base model* is the pre-trained Xception model with ImageNet weights. But the last layer (i.e. the 1000-class classifier) is removed.
 - Step 2: *Crack classification model* is the base model plus a logistic regression layer with two outputs.
 - Step 3: Train the crack classification model on our dataset
 - Step 4: Save the weights learned during training the new model
- *Part II: Fine-tune the higher layers of the crack classification model trained in Part I*
 - Step 1: Select a layer number

- Layers before this number will use the weights learned in Step 4 of Part I
- Layers above and including this number will be re-trained based on a new dataset.
- Step 2: Train the new model with a very slow learning rate
- Step 3: Save the weights learned during training
- *Part III: Test the crack classification model*
 - Step 1: Load the new model and weights learned in Step 3 of Part II
 - Step 2: Predict the label of each test images

3.5. Experiments, results and discussion

3.5.1 Dataset

We have collected totally 237 images containing cracks from DNV GL CAP (condition assessment program) reports. It is difficult to detect crack presence in some of those images because the background noise and other objects may confuse our visual perception. We have selected 179 images for training and validating our crack classification model because cracks in these 179 images can be certainly detected without acquiring ship survey competence. Since the training dataset is very small, we divided each image into multiple patches to increase the number of training data points and generate negative data points. Each patch (data point) is labelled as either “Crack” (i.e. positive data point) or “Non-crack” (i.e. negative data point) to indicate presence of the crack. It is worth highlighting that a patch with “Crack” label typically contains only part of a crack.

One common issue existing in all images is that the crack in each image occupies just a few pixels. For instance, the total number of pixels in Fig.6 (a) is 917, 575 but the number of crack pixels is only 9411. That is around 1% of the total number of pixels in the image. This percentage is averagely similar for all 179 images selected for training and validating the model. Consequently, it leads to a very low portion of positive data points in the training and validating dataset. (The machine learning model sees and learns from the training dataset. The validation dataset is used to evaluate the trained model and often to fine-tune the model hyperparameters.) Such phenomenon reveals a severe level of class imbalance which is a common issue for most real-world classification problems. One of the tactics to combat imbalanced classes in machine learning datasets is down-sampling majority class which is to randomly remove samples from the majority class to prevent its samples dominating the learning algorithm. We adopt this technique to deal with the imbalanced classes in our training dataset.

As shown in Table I, Dataset A represents the dataset without down-sampling the negative class. Only 2% data points in Dataset A are positive samples while 98% belong to the negative class. Thus, we have randomly selected 4934 from 120,104 negative samples and created a new dataset B in which the positive class is the same as in Dataset A. Therefore, the ratio of positive data points in Dataset B is increased to 33.33%.

We have divided both Dataset A and B into two sets, training set and validation set. The training set contains 80% data points randomly selected from Dataset A/B and the rest 20% data is included in the validation set. Both Dataset A and B have been used to train the crack classification model introduced in Section 3.4.

Table I: Experiment datasets

Description	Dataset A	Dataset B
Number of total data points	122, 571	7401
Number of positive (Crack) data points	2467	2467
Number of negative (Non-crack) data points	120,104	4934
Positive data points/total data points (%)	2%	33.33%

3.5.2 Training and testing results

Training a deep ConvNet involves optimization of a large set of parameters which are heavily interdependent. It requires a lot of labelled training samples to be fed into the ConvNet until the ConvNet is even close to the optimal solution. In general, the amount of available training data is much lower than the amount of data needed to reach a useful optimum. To compensate for the limited number of available data we can train the ConvNet multiple epochs. This will give the ConvNet time to converge without requiring an impractical amount of data. The general trend of model accuracy increases as the number of epochs increases. But it may have some fluctuations. Therefore, we recorded the weights learned during the best training epoch, i.e. gained the highest training accuracy. The best training and validation accuracy are listed in Table II. Although the training accuracy of Dataset A is higher than Dataset B, this result actually overfits to Non-crack class due to the imbalanced data issue. It is because that the crack classification model has learned too many details of Non-crack data which do not apply to new data.

Table II: Training results (Best training epoch)

	Dataset A	Dataset B
Training accuracy	98.96%	93.75%
Validation accuracy	98.136%	85.28%

To unbiasedly evaluate the crack classification model, we have tested it on the test set which has not been seen by the model before. Specifically, we have chosen 58 images including both crack and non-crack images. Those crack images are actually difficult to be classified by non-surveyors. The test results are summarized in Table III which shows the model trained on Dataset B significantly outperforms Dataset A. It has proven that down-sampling the majority class can effectively increase the classification accuracy. The model trained on Dataset A yielded very high false negative ratio but low false positive ratio. However, false negative is not acceptable because the model will neglect some cracks which may severely impact ship operations.

Table III: Test results

	Dataset A	Dataset B
Number of test images	58	587
Number of Crack images	37	37
Number of Non-crack images	21	21
Number of correct prediction	27	44
Number of false positive	2	7
Number of false negative	29	7
Test accuracy	46.55%	75.86%

Four test examples included in Figs.10 and 11 are chosen to compare the classification results given by the model trained on both datasets. The model trained on Dataset A failed to classify Example (a), (b) and (d) while the model trained on Dataset B did it correctly. However, the model trained on both datasets failed to classify Example (c).

4. Fully convolutional neural network for semantic segmentation

If the surveyor would like to know not only the existence of the crack but also the specific location of the crack, we can build a model to localize the crack in a pixel-level manner which is essentially a semantic segmentation problem. Semantic segmentation is to assign each pixel in the image an object class. ConvNet architectures that have originally been developed for image classification can be successfully repurposed for semantic segmentation. For instance, we can build a “fully convolutional” network that takes input of arbitrary size and produce correspondingly-sized output with efficient inference and learning, Long *et al.* (2015).

(a) Ground truth: CRK; Predicted:NO-CRK

(b) Ground truth: NO-CRK; Predicted:CRK

(c) Ground truth: CRK; Predicted:NO-CRK

(d) Ground truth: CRK; Predicted:NO-CRK

Fig.10: Examples of test results (Crack classification model trained on Dataset A)

(a) Ground truth: CRK; Predicted:CRK

(b) Ground truth: NO-CRK; Predicted:NO-CRK

(c) Ground truth: CRK; Predicted:NO-CRK

(d) Ground truth: CRK; Predicted:CRK

Fig.11: Examples of test results (Crack classification model trained on Dataset B)

4.1 Dataset

As introduced in Section 3.5.1, totally 237 images have been extracted from DNV GL CAP reports. We have selected 102 of 237 images based on the image quality, crack size, and image resolution and manually labelled them on pixel-level. The dataset is divided into a training set and a test set. The training set has included 75 image randomly selected. The remaining 27 images were in the test set. Since the images vary in color and size, the images were cropped around the cracks to reduce the size of training images as well as the time spent on training the ConvNet model. One example is given in Fig.12. The original image contains 14,059,008 pixels while the cropped image only contains 570,690. The number of pixels has been reduced 96%. Thus, the training time has been reduced significantly.

Fig.12: Example of cropping the original image

4.2 A fully convolutional network

Dilated convolution is a convolution applied to input with defined gaps and particularly popular in the field of real-time segmentation. We have developed a fully convolutional network which was inspired by *Yu and Koltun (2016)* and implemented using Keras APIs. The model consists of 10 convolutional layers. The first three layers are conventional convolutional layers and last seven layers are dilated convolutional layers with different *dilation factors*. To ensure that the final output image has the same size as the initial input image does, every convolutional layer has used “padding” to preserve the original input size.

It is worth highlighting that the number of crack pixels in the images varies from 20251 to 115. Low resolution images with tiny cracks will have a relatively small impact on updating the network parameters during training the network. To deal with this issue incorrect predictions of crack pixels in these images have been assigned higher weights when calculating the loss function.

4.3 Training and test results

Our fully convolutional network takes every pixel of the initial input image as a data point and outputs a corresponding label for the input pixel. To evaluate the model performance, we have chosen Recall (ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the all observations in the positive class), Precision (ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the total predicted positive observations), F1-score (weighted average of Precision and Recall) and Intersection over Union IoU (Calculation of IoU relies on the ground-truth area of the target object and the predicted area of the object generated by the model. I.e. $\text{IoU} = \text{Area of Overlap} / \text{Area of Union}$) as the evaluation criteria. The training and test results are summarized in Table IV.

Table IV: Fully convolutional network training and test results

	Training set	Validation set
Recall	68.7%	48.4%
Precision	63.5%	48.6%
F1-score	60.7%	42.1%
Intersection over union	48.4%	29.8%

Fig.13: Test examples (Fully convolutional network)

Four examples of test results are shown in Fig.13. Test example (a) shows that the model has performed well when predicting vertical cracks because most images in the training set contain vertical cracks. Test example (b) reveals that the model has not learned to separate shadows from cracks. Test example (c) gives a surprising result that the model has detected a thin crack in a low-resolution image because the added weight was given for such crack pixels during training. Test example (d) has failed to detect the crack at all. The possible reasons include irregular shape,

discontinuity and the color of the crack. Such type of cracks are very few in the training set. Thus the model might have not learned any relevant features on segmenting the crack.

5. Conclusion

We have investigated both conventional computer vision techniques and convolutional neural networks to facilitate automation of crack detection. Conventional computer vision techniques do not require huge amount of training data while heavily relying on hand-crafted features to detect cracks in images. However, the images were not acquired for computer vision purpose and vary in resolution and quality. In addition, the shape, size and color of cracks are very different. Thus, it is very challenging to find common features to effectively represent those cracks.

Deep convolutional neural networks automatically learn features but demand huge amount of training data to be fed into the network. To deal with the issue of insufficient training data we have used transfer learning to build a crack classification model. The results have demonstrated that transfer learning is an effective technique but still needs further exploration on fine-tuning the model. The imbalanced class problem needs to be solved in order to increase the model prediction accuracy.

We have developed a fully convolutional network to localize the crack on pixel-level. The results have revealed that the model has performed well on predicting vertical cracks because the training set contained a high percentage of vertical cracks. But the model has failed to distinguish shadows from cracks and cannot detect cracks with irregular shapes and discontinuities.

Our experiments have proven how important the amount and distribution of training data are. Therefore, collecting more images is one of our future work. In addition, we will continue exploring how to transfer the state-of-the-art object classification models to both crack classification and semantic segmentation.

References

- BU, G.P.; CHANDA, S.; GUAN, H.; JO, J.; BLUMENSTEIN, M.; LOO, Y.C. (2015), *Crack detection using a texture analysis-based technique for visual bridge inspection*, Electronic J. Structural Eng. 14/1, pp.41-48
- CHOLLET, F. (2017), *Xception: Deep learning with depthwise separable convolutions*, IEEE Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), pp.1251-1258
- EHRIG, K.; GOEBBELS, J.; MEINEL, D.; PAETSCH, O.; PROHASKA, S.; ZOBEL, V. (2011), *Comparison of crack detection methods for analysing damage processes in concrete with computed tomography*, Int. Symp. Digital Industrial Radiology and Computed Tomography, Poster 2
- GOODFELLOW, I.; BENGIO, Y.; COURVILLE, A. (2016), *Deep Learning*, Adaptive Computation and Machine Learning Series
- HE, K.; ZHANG, X.; REN, S.; SUN, J. (2016), *Deep residual learning for image recognition*, IEEE Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), pp.770-778
- KRIZHEVSKY, A.; SUTSKEVER, I.; HINTON, G.E. (2012), *Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks*, Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, pp.1097-1105
- LONG, J.; SHELHAMER, E.; DARRELL, T. (2015), *Fully convolutional networks for semantic segmentation*, IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)
- NAIR, A.; SIVAPRASAD, K.; NANDAKUMAR, C.G. (2017), *Crack assessment criteria for ship hull structure based on ship operational life*, Cogent Engineering 4:1345044

SIMONYAN, K.; ZISSERMAN, A. (2014), *Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition*, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1409.1556>.

SZEGEDY, C.; LIU, W.; JIA, Y.; SERMANET, P.; REED, S.; ANGUELOV, D.; ERHAN, D.; SANHOUCHE, V.; RABINOVICH, A. (2015), *Going deeper with convolutions*, IEEE Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), pp.1-9

SZEGEDY, C.; VANHOUCHE, V.; LOFFE, S.; SHLENS, J.; WOJNA, Z. (2016), *Rethinking the inception architecture for computer vision*, IEEE Conf. Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), pp.2818-2826

YOSINSKI, J.; CLUNE, J.; BENGIO, Y.; LIPSON, H. (2014), *How transferable are features in deep neural networks?*, 27th Int. Conf. Neural Information Processing Systems, pp.3320-3328

YU, F.; KOLTUN, V. (2016), *Multi-scale context aggregation by dilated convolutions*, Int. Conf. Learning Representations

Improving an Already Optimized Ship by Making its Stern Asymmetric

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Abstract

A container ship with a large area propeller is optimized for minimal power and maximum quality of the inflow to the propeller. Both object functions are evaluated at full-scale Reynolds number. The large number of parameters makes a full factorial approach unfeasible. Instead, an estimated Pareto front is computed using a response surface. Starting from a ship with an already optimized gondola, a further power decrease of 2% can be obtained in two ways: (1) By making the aft ship asymmetric such that rotational losses caused by the propeller are reduced. (2) By optimizing the gondola and the tunnel form simultaneously, but keeping the hull form symmetric.

1. Introduction

From several studies in the past it has been demonstrated that the fuel consumption of a ship can be decreased by enlarging the propeller and reducing its rotation rate. One of the work packages in the EU project “LeanShips” aims to integrate the design of the aft part of a container ship and a large area propeller. In *van der Ploeg et al. (2016)* a hull form with a large area propeller is optimized. It is shown that the power required to maintain the design speed can be decreased with 2.7% compared to the original hull form with the large area propeller, by optimizing the gondola using a Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) code. All candidate hull forms evaluated were symmetric. The aft part of the optimized hull form is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1: Fish-eye view of the aft part of the symmetric reference hull

In this research, we try to further optimize the hull using two different approaches that will be described in, respectively, Sections 2 and 3. In the first approach we allow the gondola of the hull to become asymmetric, thereby trying to reduce the rotational losses of the propeller. The asymmetric hull form should be designed in such a way that pre-rotation is generated that increases the efficiency of the propeller. In the second approach, we do not allow the hull to become asymmetric but we simultaneously optimize the gondola and the form of the tunnel. In both approaches, we optimize in a large design space, in which the number of parameters is so high that a full factorial approach is not feasible.

In both approaches we take a fixed propeller diameter of 7 m. The displacement is not allowed to decrease more than 0.2% and the propeller location as well as the ship's main dimensions are fixed. We assume that modifications of the aft part of the hull will only slightly influence the wave resistance. Therefore, the computations are performed without taking into account the ship's generated wave system. The dynamic trim and sinkage as resulting from an initial RANS computation are taken into account. The hull forms are evaluated at full-scale Reynolds number $1.2e9$.

We have two object functions. The first object function is an estimate of the power delivered to the propulsor that is required to maintain the design speed of 13 kn. By minimizing this object function we aim to minimize fuel consumption and emissions. In case of danger of erosive cavitation, one would like to prevent strong variations of the wake in circumferential direction, especially in the top half of the propeller plane. Therefore, the second object function that has to be minimized is a function for the non-uniformity of the effective wake. We want to compute the Pareto front, i.e. the trade-off between minimizing both object functions whereby one cannot decrease the first without increasing the second.

2. Optimization of an asymmetric gondola

For a symmetric, single-screw hull as shown in Fig.1, the remaining energy losses are in part ‘rotational losses’. In order for the propeller to generate a thrust, not only water is accelerated in axial direction, but also a swirl is introduced. This swirl does not contribute to the thrust, although sometimes part of the corresponding rotational losses can be recovered by a rudder bulb. In this paper, we want to investigate whether we can decrease the required power by making the gondola asymmetric, thereby trying to reduce the rotational losses. The asymmetric hull should be designed in such a way that pre-rotation is generated that increases the efficiency of the propeller.

A study to achieve this by means of a wake adapting duct was performed in, *Stierman (1987)*. For the particular case described by Stierman, the amount of rotational losses in the wake was only 1 percent of the total energy power. Therefore, the 6% power reduction could not be explained by the decrease of the rotational losses. This power reduction could be explained by an improvement in propeller-hull interaction, resulting in a reduction of the thrust deduction. Apparently, for this particular case there was flow-separation for the symmetric aft ship and not for the asymmetric aft ship.

In order to analyze the rotational losses, for each hull form the rudder and propeller have to be modeled in the RANS-computations. The geometry of the aft part including the rudder, hub and skeg is shown in Fig.1. The propeller is modeled with a Boundary Element Method (BEM) method, and each hull form will be evaluated by a fully coupled RANS-BEM computation, which is explained in Section 2.3.

The reference ship will be the symmetric hull form shown in Fig.1 that was already optimized (*van der Ploeg et al. (2016)*). Therefore, it will be a challenge to further reduce the required power, especially because this reference ship has a rudder bulb which makes the rudder more effective in recovering the rotational losses.

2.1 Object functions

As already mentioned, the first object function is the power delivered to the propulsor required to maintain the ship’s speed. It can be expressed as $P_D = 2\pi Qn$, in which Q and n are, respectively, the shaft torque and rotation rate. The in-behind propeller efficiency can be expressed as the ratio of the useful power over the delivered power:

$$\eta_{prop} = \frac{P_{useful}}{P_D} = \frac{(1 - w_{eff})T \cdot V_S}{P_D} \quad (1)$$

in which T is the propeller thrust, w_{eff} the effective wake fraction and V_S the ship’s speed. If the thrust deduction fraction is denoted by t , and the nominal resistance by $R_T = (1-t)T$, then from (1) it follows that

$$P_D = \frac{1 - w_{eff}}{1 - t} \frac{R_T \cdot V_S}{\eta_{prop}} = \frac{R_T \cdot V_S}{\eta_{hull} \cdot \eta_{prop}} \quad (2)$$

In which η_{hull} and η_{prop} are, respectively, the hull efficiency and propeller efficiency. Computing the trends in P_D accurately requires that the computed trends in all propulsion parameters in (2) should be accurate. The second object function is the variation of the thrust of a single blade during one rotation cycle of the propeller.

2.2 RANS method

To optimize the asymmetric hull form, we use the RANS code ReFRESKO, www.refresco.org, a community based CFD code for the maritime world. ReFRESKO solves the incompressible RANS equations, which are discretised using a finite volume approach with cell-centered collocated variables. In general, it solves the multiphase unsteady RANS equations, although in this application we will use it to compute the steady, single-phase flow. As turbulence model, we use the k- ω TNT two-equation model, *Kok (1999)*. The computational domain is rectangular, with its dimensions presented in Fig.2. The inflow boundary is located $1L_{pp}$ in front of the bow, and the outflow boundary at $2L_{pp}$ behind the transom. In a (x,y,z) -co-ordinate system fixed to the ship, with $y=0$ being the center plane, x positive aft, and z upward, the lateral outer boundary is located at $y=2L_{pp}$ and $y=-2L_{pp}$, and the bottom boundary at $z=-2L_{pp}$. At these boundaries, undisturbed flow conditions are imposed.

Fig.2: Computational domain around the ship

Fig.2: Wall grid for the RANS method used for asymmetric hull evaluation

For the rather complex geometry, we used Hexpress, www.numeca.com, as the unstructured grid generator. To limit the computational effort, the boundary layer is not fully resolved, but wall laws are used. The grid density is chosen relatively coarse. The characteristics of the 5.4M-cells grid around several parts of the ship are given in Table I. After the hull form optimization, the decrease in both object functions for the optimized hull form will be computed using a refined grid (Section 2.6.1). Fig.3 shows the wall grid of the aft ship. The body forces of the propeller are imposed on a locally refined RANS grid. Approximately 42 cells along the propeller radius and 14 cells along chord direction are used. Towards the leading and trailing edge of the rudder the grid has been refined as well.

Table I: Grid characteristics for the unstructured grid around asymmetric hull forms

	# cells on the hull	y^+	Avg y^+
Bow	21K	394	308
Mid ship	18K	328	254
Stern	63K	402	259
Rudder	36K	730	363

2.3 BEM code and coupling with RANS

By coupling a steady RANS solver for the ship flow and an unsteady BEM solver to simulate the propeller performance, a significant reduction in computational effort can be obtained in comparison to a full, unsteady RANS-RANS method with sliding interfaces. The BEM-method solves the incompressible potential flow equations for lifting surfaces.

The method, designated PROCAL, is being developed within MARIN's Cooperative Research Ships (CRS) for the unsteady analysis of cavitating propellers operating in a prescribed ship wake. It has been validated for open water characteristics, shaft forces, and sheet cavitation inception and extent. The code is a low-order BEM that solves for the velocity disturbance potential. Initial validation studies and details on the mathematical and numerical model can be found in *Vaz and Bosschers (2006)*. The panel distribution on the propeller and the hub is shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3: Large diameter propeller and panel distribution for the BEM code

The RANS-BEM computation consists of the following steps: an initial RANS computation without propeller action is performed to obtain a first estimate of the effective wake field which is used as input for the first BEM-computation. The BEM-computation is performed and the resulting thrust and loading distribution is averaged over all blade positions. The BEM computation also determines the propeller-induced velocities. Next, a second RANS computation is performed, in which the averaged thrust and loading distribution from the previous BEM computation is used. The rotation rate of the propeller is then adjusted using the imbalance between the resistance force from the RANS computation and the thrust predicted by the BEM computation. The effective wake is updated by subtracting the propeller-induced velocities resulting from the BEM computation from the total wake field computed by the RANS method. This process is repeated until the above-mentioned imbalance in the forces as well as the updates in the effective wake field become negligible. For all hull forms, the same correction for wave resistance, roughness etc. is imposed. Due to the small propeller clearance, the effective wake field cannot be extrapolated from a number of planes upstream of the propeller. Instead, the effective field is determined from the swept area of the leading edge, *Rijkema et al. (2013)*.

2.4 Geometry variation

The CAD software package used is Rhinoceros3D, www.rhino3d.com. In this package, a hull form can be described as a Non-Uniform Rational Basis Spline (NURBS) surface. In *van der Ploeg et al. (2016)*, the design space was defined as a parametric blending of a set of basis hull forms created in Rhinoceros3D. This approach has several benefits, for example, it is defined by only a few, physically relevant and ship-specific parameters ensuring that the design space is low-dimensional, *van der Ploeg and Raven (2010)*. However, it has also one disadvantage. Defining the asymmetric basis hull shapes in such a way that they span an effective and low-dimensional design space is difficult. Therefore, it was decided to take an alternative route. The asymmetric gondola is obtained by applying a combination of translation and rotation to the NURBS surface control points. For the parametric modeling with Rhino we use the free plug-in Grasshopper, www.grasshopper3d.com.

2.4.1 Design parameters

The asymmetric hull forms are realized by combining a rotational and a translational deformation of the gondola. The rotation and translation operators are determined by a Bezier curve. The control

points of this curve are the design parameters. The amount of rotation of the gondola and the amount of volume that is translated from portside to starboard can be controlled with the y -coordinate of the curve defined in, respectively, Fig.4 and Fig.5. The rotation can be controlled with 3 parameters, indicated by, respectively, 1, 2 and 3 in Fig.4:

- $R0_Y$, the amount of rotation that is applied just upstream of the propeller.
- $R1_Y$, the amount of rotation that is applied at the next control point.
- $R1_X$, the longitudinal coordinate of this control point.

The translation can be controlled with 4 parameters, indicated in Fig.5:

- $T1_Y$, the amount of volume translated at the first control point.
- $T1_X$, the longitudinal coordinate of this control point.
- $T2_Y$, the amount of volume translated at the next control point
- $T2_X$, the longitudinal coordinate of this control point.

The four translation parameters are all zero at the propeller location and at mid ship.

In addition, the hull shape can be adapted by interpolating towards a hull form that is more slender just upstream of the propeller. The 8th and last design parameter is the amount of interpolation towards this hull form. The idea behind this parameter is to be able to modify the thrust deduction fraction.

Fig.4 Rotation parameters

Fig.5: Translation parameters

2.5 Surrogate model

Since the design space is 8-dimensional, a full factorial approach is not feasible. For example, if we would use 5 hull forms for each parameter, we would have $5^8 = 390625$ hull form evaluations. Instead, we use a surrogate model to mimic the behaviour of the object functions and other propulsion parameters in (2) as a function of the design parameters.

To do this we use the Design of Experiments (DoE) tool package Design Expert to make cubic polynomial response surfaces for the object functions and propulsion parameters. This type of response surface requires significantly more data points than a quadratic polynomial surface, but it is able to capture more details.

The initial design plan contained about 300 hull forms. For each hull form the object functions and propulsion parameters were directly computed with RANS-BEM simulations, and the results were used to construct the response surfaces.

2.6 Results asymmetric gondola optimization

First, we check how well the response surface can predict the relative changes in propulsion parameters. The R^2 values, the mean absolute error (MAE) and the root-mean-square error (RSME) for the relative changes of several propulsion parameters are listed in Table II. The fact that the R^2 values are very close to 1.0, and the errors are very small indicates that the changes in the propulsion parameters as obtained from the response surface agree very well with those directly computed by the RANS-BEM method.

Table II: R^2 , MAE and RSME values

	R^2	MAE	RSME
Power	0.979	0.03%	0.04%
Thrust variation	0.994	0.60%	0.86%
Thrust	0.997	0.02%	0.03%
Ship force	0.997	0.02%	0.04%
Rudder force	0.996	0.10%	0.15%
Rotational losses	0.996	0.05%	0.08%

Fig. 6: Pareto chart of effects for the relative change of P_D

We can study many trends obtained from the response surface. From Fig. 6 it appears that the most important parameter to influence P_D is $R0_Y$, the amount of rotation that is applied just upstream of the propeller. The estimated Pareto fronts, obtained after optimization with a genetic algorithm on the response surface, suggest that a further decrease of the power is possible compared to the 1% of the red points shown in Fig. 7.

The hull form with the lowest P_D is on the edge of the design space. Therefore, we extended the design space by increasing the range for the parameter $R0_Y$, by allowing more rotation of the gondola. The power reduction of the asymmetric hull form, compared to that of the symmetric reference hull form, against the parameter $R0_Y$ is shown in Fig. 8. Again, red symbols indicate the results from the RANS-BEM evaluations for hull forms in the initial design space. Other colours indicate results from the extended design space.

It appears that the reduction of power as evaluated by RANS-BEM is almost 2%. This can be obtained without increasing the variation in the propeller thrust, as is shown in the top-left picture of Fig. 9. To study the change in the propulsion parameters as shown in equation (2), Fig. 9 also shows the decrease of the power against the relative change of these parameters. From this figure, we can conclude the following:

- Compared to the symmetric hull form shown in Fig. 1, a decrease of P_D of 2% is obtained.

- The decrease of P_D is accompanied by a relatively strong increase of both the nominal resistance and the thrust deduction fraction.
- The increase of the effective wake fraction more than compensates for the increase of the required thrust. As a result, the hull efficiency of the hull forms with the lowest P_D slightly increases.
- These hull forms show a propeller efficiency that is more than 2% higher combined with a hull efficiency that is more than 1% higher compared to the symmetric reference. This is partly ‘spoiled’ by an increase in nominal resistance.
- Hull forms from the last extension of the design space have higher propeller efficiency than those of the first extension. This can be explained by the additional increase in the effective wake fraction w_{eff} caused by the extra rotation of the gondola corresponding to the increase of parameter RO_Y .

Fig.7: Estimated Pareto fronts based on different response surfaces. The vertical axis shows the power relative to the symmetric reference hull as shown in Fig.1

Fig.8: Relative change of P_D against the amount of rotation of the gondola

2.6.1 Results on a refined grid

In order to get an idea of the grid dependence in the computed trends, we used a refined grid of 19M cells and analyzed both the symmetric reference hull form and the optimized asymmetric hull form, which is shown in Fig.10. The predicted power reduction using this refined grid was 2.3%, so reasonably close to the percentage as computed using the coarser grid. More results are shown in Table III.

2.6.2 Comparison with RANS-RANS

We also performed a first evaluation of both the reference hull form and the optimized asymmetric hull form in which the BEM-model for the propeller was replaced by an unsteady RANS code, using again 19M cells for the ship. To couple both RANS computations, sliding interfaces were used. Unfortunately, these computations did not show any reduction of P_D for the asymmetric hull form. Table

III shows the propulsion parameters of the asymmetric hull form relative to the reference as computed by both the RANS-BEM and the RANS-RANS code. The computed trends in thrust and torque agree quite well, but for the propeller efficiencies the trends are different. In *Schuling and Terwisga (2018)* a detailed analysis of the rotational losses computed by the RANS-RANS method is made by applying conservation of energy to a small control volume containing the propeller. This analysis shows that the rotational losses are somewhat reduced, but the axial losses increased equally, leaving the propeller efficiency unchanged.

Fig.9: Relative change of P_D against the relative change of several propulsion parameters in equation (2). The symbol legend is shown in Fig.8

Fig.10: Optimized asymmetric hull form

Table III: Propulsion parameters of asymmetric hull form relative to those of the reference (Fig.1)

	P_D	T	Q	n	η_{hull}	η_{prop}
RANS-BEM	-2.3%	+8.7%	+4.9%	-6.9%	+0.7%	+2.0
RANS-RANS	+0.3%	+9.8%	+5.5%	-4.9%	-0.3%	+0.3

3. Simultaneous optimization of the gondola and the tunnel form

Within the LeanShips project, the gondola of the hull form was optimized. In *van der Ploeg et al. (2016)* the procedure that was followed and the results obtained are described in more detail. In this section, we describe how the gondola and the tunnel form can be optimized simultaneously. The hull forms are not allowed to become asymmetric.

3.1 Computation of the object functions

The first object function is the same as used in the previous section: the power P_D given in equation (2). Herein the achievable propeller efficiency η_{prop} is obtained from the B-series of propellers, *Kuiper (1992)*. The thrust, wake fraction, number of blades, propeller diameter and revolution rate are fixed, while the optimum blade area ratio and pitch ratio for each hull form are found from the B-series. The towing resistance R_T is computed by a first RANS computation without propeller action. To compute the thrust deduction fraction t , we perform a second RANS computation including a force distribution representing the propeller with an imposed thrust T_0 . For all hull forms, we impose the same thrust T_0 that contains a correction for wave resistance, roughness etc. This imposed thrust should be a reasonable estimate of the thrust T required for self-propulsion. Assuming a linear behaviour between the resistance force on the hull and T_0 , the thrust deduction coefficient can then be computed from $t=(R_0-R_T)/T_0$ with R_0 the resistance force from the second RANS computation. The second RANS computation also computes a wake field including the propeller action: the so-called total wake. From an earlier full RANS-BEM computation that is performed for the initial hull form we obtain the propeller-induced velocity field. The estimated effective wake is obtained by subtracting this induced velocity field from the total wake. Hence the assumption is that the induced velocity field is the same for all hull forms.

The second object function is similar to the one used in the previous section. Again, it is a function for the non-uniformity of the effective wake field. To be precise, it is the L_1 -norm of the variation of

$$\beta = \tan^{-1} \left(V_x / \left(\omega \frac{r}{R} - V_\theta \right) \right) \quad (3)$$

with V_x and V_θ the axial and tangential velocity components respectively, θ the angular position in rad. and ω the propeller rotation rate in rad/s. β is the undisturbed propeller inflow angle and its variation in circumferential direction as the propeller rotates is $\partial\beta/\partial\theta$. This second object function is determined from integration in circumferential direction and over a range of radii from the hub to the tip.

3.2 RANS method

The rudder and skeg are not taken into account in the RANS computations. Because this keeps the geometry relatively simple, we can use a boundary fitted, structured grid. Therefore, the RANS solver is different from the one used in Section 3. The hull forms are evaluated with PARNASSOS, a RANS code developed and applied by MARIN and IST, *Hoekstra (1999)*. It computes the steady, turbulent flow around ship hulls by solving the discretised Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations for steady, incompressible flow. For the optimization of the hull we use Menter's one-equation turbulence model, *Menter (1997)* with the Dacles-Mariani correction, *Dacles-Mariani (1995)*.

The inflow boundary is located $0.5L_{pp}$ in front of the bow, and the outflow boundary at $1.5L_{pp}$ behind the transom. Due to symmetry considerations, only the starboard side is taken into account. In an (x,y,z) -co-ordinate system fixed to the ship, with x positive aft and z upward, the lateral outer boundary is a quarter of a cylinder with axis $y=z=0$ and radius $1.0L_{pp}$. At this boundary, tangential velocities and pressure found from a potential-flow computation are imposed. The number of nodes in longitudinal, girthwise and wall-normal direction is, respectively, 569, 53 and 161, leading to a total of 4.9 million nodes. More details about the RANS solver, the grid, the automatic grid generation, and the RANS-BEM coupling can be found in *van der Ploeg et al. (2016)*.

3.3 Deformation of hull forms

The design space is ‘spanned’ by a number of so-called basis hull forms as described in *van der Ploeg et al. (2016)* and *van der Ploeg and Raven (2010)*. Parametric deformations of the geometry are obtained from interpolation between these basis hull forms and the original hull form. The parameters of the hull forms to be evaluated are the percentages of the respective basis hull forms. In our case, we have used four basis hull forms. These basis hull forms are compared with the original hull form in Fig.11. The two hull forms shown in the left pictures vary the gondola. The one shown in the top-left picture makes the gondola more slender. The two hull forms on the right vary the tunnel form. The one shown in the top-right makes the tunnel wider; the one shown in the bottom-right picture makes the tunnel lower.

Of course, these deformations are not independent and therefore we cannot choose every parameter in the range 0.0...1.0 without obtaining very weird hull forms. Therefore, we follow a different approach: we define the hull form shown in red in the top-left picture as the original hull form, and the other hull form as variations. In that case, we can choose all parameters in the range 0.0...1.0.

Fig.11: Comparison of four basis hull forms (red) with the original hull form (black). Top left: L. Bottom left: M. Top right: N. bottom right: O

3.4 Surrogate model

As mentioned before, we use four basis hull forms. Therefore, a full-factorial approach that would use 5 steps to go from one hull form to the next; a total of $5^4=625$ hull form evaluations would be required. Using only 5 steps from one hull form to the next probably will not give a sharp Pareto front. In order to get a sharp Pareto front with only a limited number of hull form evaluations, we again use a surrogate based optimization. This time we chose a space-filling Latin hypercube design of experiments. After evaluating the object functions with the two RANS computations as described in Section 3.1, we use the package Dakota to build a Kriging response surface, and use this response surface to compute a Pareto front, using a genetic algorithm. Of course, since it is based on the ‘surrogate’, the Kriging response surface, it is only an approximation of the Pareto front that would have been obtained by using the values of the object functions obtained from a direct evaluation.

3.5 Results of the simultaneous optimization of the gondola and the tunnel form

The red symbols in Fig.12 show the results of the hull forms corresponding to the initial design of experiments. We chose 80 hull forms in this initial design and completed it with some hull forms on the edge of the design space. We can use the information to build a Kriging response surface. The black points show the results from a genetic algorithm applied to this response surface. Since the thus obtained estimated Pareto front is based on the response surface, its computation does not require any hull form evaluations, and can be done in only a few seconds. This estimated Pareto front is indicated by the black symbols in Fig.12. It tells us not only the estimate of the decrease of the object functions, but also for which choice of the parameter this can be obtained.

To verify the quality of this estimated Pareto front, we took a number of corresponding hull forms and evaluated both object functions with two RANS equations as described in Section 3.1. The results are indicated as green symbols. These symbols are all very close to the estimated Pareto front. Hence in this case the surrogate modeling helped to reduce the number of actual evaluations of hull forms, while still computing a dense Pareto front.

Fig.12: Computed and estimated Pareto fronts for the symmetric hull optimization

Fig.12 shows that compared to the hull form shown in Fig.1 that contains an already optimized gondola, P_D can be decreased by only about 1%. However, a further analysis showed that the hull forms with the lowest power were obtained on the edge of the design space, with maximum value for the third parameter and minimum value for the fourth parameter. From an analysis of some hull forms that correspond with negative values for the fourth parameter it appeared that those hull forms still fulfilled the constraints. Therefore, we did a similar optimization in an extended design space, allowing negative parameters for the third parameter. This parameter was allowed to get values between -0.3 and 1.0. As a consequence, the design space contains hull forms with a lower tunnel and an extremely small propeller clearance.

The results are shown in Fig.13. In this case, the estimated Pareto front is not as good as shown in Fig.12. For some hull forms, the location on the predicted Pareto front has been connected to the location in the plot as actually computed by the two RANS equations. This is indicated by the lines in the plot that connect black squares and green squares. The estimate of P_D is quite good, but the predicted decrease in the wake object function can differ significantly from the actually computed value. Therefore, we made a new response surface, based on the information in both the green and the red squares. A genetic algorithm performed on this updated response surface gives a new estimated Pareto front indicated by the black '+' symbols. This updated Pareto front differs significantly from the first estimate. In the extended design space the trends in especially the wake object function are

very difficult to predict by a response surface, because the object function becomes extremely sensitive to parameter variation for hull forms with a very small propeller clearance.

Although in this case the estimated Pareto fronts do not correspond that well with actual evaluations of the object functions, they can still help us to determine in which ‘corner’ of the design space we should look for an optimized hull form. We chose one extra set of parameters, checked whether the corresponding hull form satisfies the constraint, and evaluated both object functions with RANS. We chose the parameters set as $(0.0, 1.0, -0.5, 0.0)$, meaning that we combined hull form L with 100% N and -50% O . The result is indicated by the brown square in the plot. It appears that a decrease of P_D of almost 2% can be achieved, without an increase of the second object function. Of course, we have no guarantee that this hull form is ‘optimal’. It may well be that a further decrease of P_D is possible. The lines of the hull form, corresponding to the ‘Extra point’ in Fig.13 are shown in Fig.14 in red. The reference hull form is shown in black.

From Fig.13 it appears that the wake object function of the hull form corresponding to the ‘Extra point’ is not very different from that of the original hull form. A comparison between the nominal wake fields (Fig.14) shows that the wake fields are very similar. This is expected, as the hull forms have almost the same gondola.

Fig.13: Computed and estimated Pareto fronts for the extended parameter range

Fig.14: Black lines: hull form that was optimized within the LeanShips project. Red lines: simultaneous optimization of gondola and tunnel, corresponding to the ‘Extra point’ in Fig.13

Fig.15: Nominal wake fields of the hull forms shown in Fig.14

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we optimized the aft part of a container ship with a large-diameter propeller. We started from a hull form with an already optimized gondola. We followed two paths to get a further optimized hull form: (1) by making the gondola hull form asymmetric and (2) by simultaneously optimizing the gondola and the tunnel form. With both approaches, a surrogate method helped to significantly decrease the number of hull form evaluations required for obtaining a sharp Pareto front.

4.1 Asymmetric gondola optimization

We have described a general method to vary an asymmetric hull form by combining a rotation and translation of the gondola, leading to an 8th-dimensional design space. The cubic response surface that is used as a surrogate model predicts the results directly computed by the RANS-BEM method very well.

Improving an already optimized symmetric hull form by making it asymmetric appeared to be quite a challenge. The best hull forms were located on the edge of the initial design space. Therefore, additional hull forms in some extensions of this design space were evaluated as well. These first evaluations show that it is possible to design a hull form that, according to the RANS-BEM evaluations, requires about 2% less power to maintain the design speed, without increasing the variation of thrust. It is expected that a further decrease is possible after building the response surface corresponding to this extended design space and use this to optimize the hull form. In addition, a further decrease of the required power is expected by optimizing the propeller for the effective wake field generated by the optimized asymmetric hull form.

The 2% decrease in power was confirmed by RANS-BEM computations using refined grids, but not by an evaluation with RANS-RANS. Although the trends in computed thrust and torque agree quite well, the trends in the propeller efficiencies are different. The modeling errors in the RANS-RANS approach are expected to be smaller than those in the RANS-BEM approach. Therefore, it would be more accurate to use RANS-RANS computations to evaluate the object functions and propulsion parameters. Of course, a RANS-RANS computation is much more costly than a RANS-BEM computation. Therefore, a multi-fidelity approach might be helpful to reduce the computational costs.

4.2 Simultaneous optimization of the gondola and tunnel form

In the simultaneous optimization of the gondola and the tunnel we did not admit the hull form to become asymmetric. Due to the simplified geometry, structured grids and a much faster RANS solver could be used and only two RANS computations were required to evaluate each hull form. In a

limited design space the gains in the object functions according to the estimated Pareto front agreed very well with the actual evaluations. Because of the sensitivity of the wake object function, this was not the case for an extended design space that includes hull forms with an extremely small propeller clearance. However, the response surface did help to find better hull forms. Again, a 2% decrease of the required power could be obtained compared to the hull form with the already optimized gondola.

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References

DACLES-MARIANI, J.; ZILLIAC, G.G.; CHOW, J.S.; BRADSHAW, P. (1995), *Numerical/experimental study of a wingtip vortex in the near field*, AIAA J. 33/9, pp.1561-1568

HOEKSTRA, M. (1999), *Numerical simulation of ship stern flows with a space-marching Navier Stokes method*, PhD Thesis, Technical University of Delft

KOK, J.C. (1999), *Resolving the dependence of free-stream values for the $k-\omega$ turbulence model*, NLR-TP-99295

KUIPER, G. (1992), *The Wageningen Propeller Series*, MARIN publication 92-001

MENTER, F.R. (1997), *Eddy-viscosity transport equations and their relation to the $k-\varepsilon$ model*, J. Fluids Eng. 119, pp.876-884

PLOEG, A.v.d.; RAVEN, H.C., (2010), *CFD-based optimization for minimal power and wake field quality*, 11th Int. Symp. Practical Design of Ships and other Floating Structures, Rio de Janeiro, pp.92-101

PLOEG, A.v.d.; BLES, G.v.d.; ZELDEREN, J.v. (2016), *Optimization of a ship with a large-diameter propeller*, 19th Numerical Towing Tank Symp., St Pierre d'Oléron

RIJPKEMA, D.; STARKE, A.R.; BOSSCHERS, J.B. (2013), *Numerical simulation of propeller-hull interaction and determination of the effective wake field using a hybrid RANS-BEM approach*, 3rd Int. Symp. Marine Propulsors, Launceston

SCHUILING, B.; TERWISGA, T.v. (2018), *Energy loss analysis for a propeller operating behind the ship*, 32nd Symp. Naval Hydrodynamics, Hamburg

STIERMAN E.J. (1987), *The design of an energy saving, wake adapted duct*, Int. Symp. Practical Design of Ship and Other Floating Structures (PRADS'87), Trondheim

VAZ, G.; BOSSCHERS, J. (2006), *Modeling three dimensional sheet cavitation on marine propellers using a boundary element method*, Cav2006 Conf., Wageningen

The Digital Twin Journey

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Abstract

The value of a complete and accurate digital representation of a ship that is available and maintained throughout the construction and operation of the vessel is being increasingly recognized. This 'digital twin' ideally contains all relevant information about the vessel and is contained within a single software platform. Unfortunately, while the benefits of a digital twin are real, achieving the desired outcome is more challenging than generally thought. Many obstacles, some cultural, some process related, and some technological, commonly appear when trying to create a digital twin. This paper will discuss these and show several examples of digital twin conception.

1. Introduction

If you are like many professionals, you regularly see headlines about the “hot new technology trends” that will completely transform your organization. You see LinkedIn posts and blogs announcing the latest advances and you go to conferences where speakers talk about the Internet of Things (IoT), augmented reality and other developments set to revolutionize everything you do. You have almost certainly heard the excitement about the concept of the “digital twin” but you probably have questions: Are the benefits just hype and practically speaking, how should a shipbuilder go about creating a digital twin of a vessel? We firmly believe that the benefits are real, but we caution that there are many steps that need to be taken before even a partially complete digital twin can be generated. It takes time. It is a journey, but the journey is worth taking.

2. Definition of a Digital Twin

Fig.1: A digital twin is a digital representation of a physical object

Let us first define the concept, and by that we mean, let us define the concept in its full manifestation. A digital twin is a digital representation of a physical object. For each physical ship (including individual sister ships), there should be one, and only one, exact digital replica. If the physical ship changes, the digital model should be updated too.

The digital twin concept is like the term “as-built” but it goes a lot further; it extends throughout the entire lifecycle of a vessel and ultimately includes the use of IoT sensors to regularly keep the physical ship and digital representation in sync.

Under our definition, the geometric data and attributes originating from the engineering CAD tool are included in a digital twin but the complete concept encompasses much more. A digital twin contains details about the requirements of the ship tied to various parts and assemblies plus linkages to items

such as class approvals, simulations and calculations and even paint information. Change requests should be included with appropriate linkages, as should Vendor Furnished Information (VFI) linked to each engine, valve and pump etc. Even the details of specific production processes used for welding and assembly sequencing should be there along with information about work centres. In other words, if there is data about how the ship is built, it should be included as part of a complete digital twin.

But it doesn't stop there. After a ship is delivered, the information should keep being accumulated. To be accurate, the digital twin should include service records, repair and retrofit changes, class surveys, documentation of fouling removal plus actual sensor data of what is going on throughout the vessel. This comprehensive definition admittedly goes beyond how some people use the term but to be complete, an enormous amount of up-to-date information is required.

3. Benefits of a Digital Twin

All this information is to serve a purpose. Indeed, the data in a digital twin is critical to enabling future technological advances. We talked about that point in a previous paper where we described the ship design, engineering and construction techniques that we expect will be used in 2030 and beyond, *Morais et al. (2016a)*. In our paper, we said that we envisioned much greater automation of shop-floor machines utilizing a digital 3D model and we also talked about the use of cyber physical systems, drones and autonomous vehicles, augmented reality, plus greater builder/operator communication via virtual reality. Since these technologies are all data-driven, we explained how the shipyard of the future will require a good digital twin and we talked about how this will enhance shipyards' effectiveness, efficiency and quality.

However, we also noted that the main driver for digital twin adoption will be ship owners interested in saving money in operations over the lifecycle of a vessel. For maintenance, training, and even performance at sea, they will need as much accurate information as possible about everything on the vessel so that it can be processed by computers to recommend optimal courses of action.

The United States Office of Naval Research Science & Technology is already strongly promoting the concept and The US Military Sealift Command has recently selected General Electric for work on a digital twin that will help detect performance degradation before it leads to potential failure. Meanwhile, container ship operators such as Maersk Linke Rickmers Reederei and Hapag-Lloyd have already signed up for classification society DNV GL's "Digital Twin" software to manage a virtual image of their assets in the cloud. Leveraging the digital ship concept is therefore the way of the future but increasingly, ship owners are appreciating its benefits right now.

4. Good News: The Structural Challenge Being Addressed

That means that finally, a longstanding structural challenge is being addressed. As we noted in our 2011 COMPIT paper, one of the key reasons why our industry has sometimes lagged others in using digital technology is a structural factor: payment from owners is tied to certain milestones in the actual construction of a ship, *Morais et al. (2011)*. Thus, historically shipbuilders have always focussed on quickly reaching the next milestone rather than spending the time, effort and money required to implement modern technology and enhance digitization. However, now that owners are increasingly appreciating the benefits of the digital twin for operations, there seems to be an increased willingness to pay for this data. True, what operators mean by a digital twin may be different from what is heard at a shipyard. However, as they move forward they are realizing that they need more data. Indeed, Bourbon is so serious about digital twins that it is selling off 41 old "non-smart" ships that do not have IoT Sensors. The change of mindset regarding the value of digital assets is happening slowly, but the developments listed above are an encouraging sign that the payment problem is at least starting to show signs of resolution.

5. Challenge: What is Your Real Business?

Nevertheless, there are still challenges that are too often overlooked by our industry. Our advice is that before starting to create a digital twin, it is important to step back and think about what business you are really in. This is a point that is not taken seriously enough but as people who write about both the future and history of technology, it is something we think about a lot. We think about how, in 1975, a Kodak engineer invented the first digital camera, yet Kodak resisted capitalizing on it. The management at Kodak thought their business was capturing images on film; they did not realize that their true business, or at least the business that they should really be in, was capturing memories.

Could shipbuilding be like that? Is a naval architecture/marine engineering firm in the business of producing drawings, or is it in the business of producing information needed to build a ship, or perhaps something else? Is a shipbuilder in the business of creating metal vessels, or is it in the business of creating floating structures? Or, to get more extreme, is a shipbuilder more fundamentally in the transportation business? If you start thinking through the implications of what business you are truly in, it will guide your technology choices and tell you where to start when creating a digital twin. You will also recognize the importance of re-examining your business model as Rolls Royce Marine did last year with its contract with Nor Lines regarding ship engines; they sold hours of reliable operation instead of just equipment (power by the hour). This shows that if you go down the path of creating a digital twin, it involves a digital transformation which should lead to a business transformation. Not enough people in our industry have truly grasped that point yet.

5.1. Challenge: Transformation Required

And while we are talking about digitization of information, note that merely digitizing current paper-based processes substantially lessens the potential benefits. It is like scanning paper roadmaps as pdfs. That has some advantages in terms of portability and searchability, but it does not have the power of Google Maps. Again, it must be stressed that before you do anything, you must really think through what you are trying to accomplish and how to optimize the technology. This may lead you down a different but better path than what you originally would have chosen.

5.2. Challenge: Shipbuilding is Complex

You also must have a realistic understanding of what is involved in digital twin creation in a shipbuilding context which is more challenging than might be assumed. Shipbuilders generally realize that they are experts in building ships, not implementing software and technology so it is commonly understood that IT expertise is required. However, the scope of the challenge is often underestimated. This is because, it is easy to forget that in many different ways, shipbuilding is demonstrably more complex than almost any other industry, *Morais et al. (2011)*. For instance, if you just consider the number of parts involved, building a ship is far more complex than building a car, or even an airplane. And besides the fact that in shipbuilding we are dealing with far more parts, a big reason for the greater complexity is that in a shipyard, each department has so many silos of information that must be harmonized. Of course, other industries have various departments with independent databases and those industries have made good progress in overcoming that challenge. However, it is not the number of diverse sources of information that makes integration difficult in shipbuilding (though, the number of separate databases at a shipyard could be an order of magnitude greater than what is common elsewhere). No, the bigger issue is the number of connections between all the silos of data. The number of connections makes it exponentially more complex to harmonize the information. It is like comparing a human being to a simple mustard seed. A mustard seed has 25,000 genes while humans have thousands less. However, the human genes have all sorts of connections between them while the mustard seed genes have comparatively fewer. It is like that in shipbuilding. In our industry, there is an enormous number of connections between different departments because unlike in almost any other industry, shipbuilders design, construct and procure at the same time! It is quite a challenge to integrate all the information from all those databases covering all those functions into a single digital twin.

Fig.2: One reflection of shipbuilding complexity: Number of parts and hours

5.3. Challenge: Legacy Data Systems

An additional challenge is that shipbuilders are contractually required to be able to access old information which is often in legacy systems using very old hardware. Upgrading this and migrating data is costly and in many cases, these old systems lack the data required for new technology.

5.4. Challenge: The Platform Problem

Another thing to note regarding the complexity of digital twin creation is that in shipbuilding there are so many specialist software applications required. A number of these applications may be part of (or sit on top of) a particular software “platform”, and are well integrated, but shipbuilding is so complex that multiple platforms are still required and you have to find a way to harmonize different information from different systems. This adds to the challenges of creating a digital twin.

6. How to Overcome the Challenges

Because no single software can store all the information required and because shipbuilding is so complex, if you are going to create a digital twin, you can only digitize a bit at a time. So where should you begin? Below is what we have found to be the best approach during our consultation projects at large naval shipyards.

6.1 Develop a Clear Vision, Strategy and Goals and then Focus

Before starting work, we again stress that you must know what you are trying to achieve and then think through what information is required. This calls for narrowing your focus to one or two key business benefits to be achieved with a digital twin. There are incremental steps to move your organization forward but you must have a clear vision, a sensible strategy and then focus on a realistic goal after first doing some clear thinking.

For instance, are you focussed on repairs and refits? Do you want to improve quality control? Or do you want to limit the need for changes? Do you want to provide a deliverable package for the owner/operator to use with their digital ship strategy during operations? Or do you want to be the industry expert for autonomous ships? The answers to questions like these will guide you as to where to focus your efforts. By focussing on narrow objectives, companies have found that it makes the first few steps on their digital twin journey more successful, enjoyable and profitable, with reduced risk.

As you are planning, you should naturally look at where you are starting from and then map out workflows and processes in your desired end state. However, you should only map out your future at a high level. As you progress through a project in an “agile” way, you should continually learn more, which will probably cause you to refine or even substantially alter your goals.

A key point is that you should be looking at things holistically and thinking about whether a digital twin and the technologies it enables will open up new opportunities that were not there before. As stated earlier, you do not want to just digitize your current workflow since it was designed when the tools, culture, requirements and technology were different.

Do not be fearful. The shipbuilding industry has undergone successful transformations before. The invention of CAD applications with a centralized data repository led to concurrent engineering rather than serial engineering practices plus the enhanced ability to do pre-outfitting. Significant improvements are possible. You just have to be alert to the opportunities all along the way and make sure that as you are creating a digital twin, you are actually making things better; if information is difficult to access, people will make separate copies of the data they need and you will be back to having out of sync, siloed information, not a true, accurate, unified digital twin.

6.2 The Importance of People

It is also good to keep in mind that as you develop your plans, you should be reminded of the three key considerations in any project: people, process and tools.

Everyone knows that people are the most important factor influencing success yet generally when this is mentioned in technical circles, it is either treated as a mere platitude, or it is considered to be like an unsolvable puzzle; engineers would rather debate technology choices than deal with humans with all their complicated desires and emotions. Fortunately, we can say from experience that there are time-tested techniques that we have found helpful.

First, have a representative for each stakeholder (manager, leads, IT, end users etc.) engaged throughout the entire project. This will significantly help guide communication and decision-making along the way and also will help ensure that you continually correctly prioritize solving the highest value problems.

Second, identify champions and influencers at several various levels in the organization. In particular, look for champions who are experienced but are also open to change. You want to have people on your side who are respected by their peers.

Third, promote transparency. To do a job effectively, people need to know for whom a job is being done, what the job is, and why it is being done. Make sure to be very open about the context of the digital twin initiative. If someone wants more information, tell them. We regularly deal with national security projects and understand that there are times when information is restricted. However, generally speaking, there are rarely any valid secrets that should be hidden from employees.

Finally, encourage teams to have a “disagree and commit” attitude. You should support vigorous debate but acknowledge that there rarely will be unanimous agreement on everything. The key is that teams must make a decision and then commit to it once a decision has been made.

6.3 Create a Platform of Platform Ecosystem

Next, we have to discuss tools, or, in this case, the underlying software platform for the digital twin. It must be something that can store, coordinate, automate and guide information and people. However, as explained earlier, due to the complexity of shipbuilding with all its specialist applications for ERP, MRP, PLM, IoT etc., there is no system that can do everything well. Therefore, what you will require is a platform of platforms and those platforms should be flexible and adaptable so that nothing constrains how you run your business.

Fig.3: No one software platform will solve all needs of shipbuilders

Previous papers of ours went into detail about desirable technical features of software platforms, *Morais et al. (2013, 2016b)*, but at a high level, you want to start by selecting a platform that has the ability to easily connect to other platforms. There are various ways these connections might be made. For instance, you should see if the platform allows connections via APIs and whether the software platform has a true open architecture. You should also look for the ability to leverage commercial off-the-shelf tools such as SQL and note if the platform has a community of partners who have created connectors between the platforms you want to use. The key point to note is that you ultimately want to find a way to connect them because a true digital twin requires interaction and synchronization between multiple systems and sources of data.

Once you are satisfied with the choices, we recommend that you make the software vendors themselves responsible for building the integrations. After all, they are supposedly the software experts, it should not fall to the shipbuilder to handle this.

6.4. Agile Implementation

Furthermore, software and IT projects, should be implemented following the best practice of the software world which is substantially different from shipbuilding. The way that almost every industry-leading web or software project is rolled out these days is by following “Agile” development principles. Some of the organizing ideas behind the Agile approach are as follows.

Fig.4: Agile approach (incrementally delivering value) vs. Big Bang approach

6.4.1. Incrementally Deliver Value

In Agile, you rapidly and incrementally deliver value. You pick a short time period and then, within that deadline you must have finished something that is complete, in and of itself and which you believe will immediately be of benefit. This contrasts with the “Big Bang” approach where you work on a project for a long time and only deliver value at the very end, all at once. A key advantage of the Agile approach is that you get a return on your investment faster and you reduce the risk of failure and wasting large amounts of time. At any point, after each increment is completed, you can stop if you so choose and be reasonably confident that you have done something useful.

6.4.2. Build, Analyse, Learn, Repeat

All along the way in Agile, you are learning. Indeed, certain Agile “frameworks” such as “Scrum” have mandatory regular ceremonies where you carefully analyse your work and the results it achieved. You determine if you are solving the right problems, get feedback from stakeholders, ponder how to do things better, and then based on the data plus discussion, you decide what to do in the next short time period. You keep doing this repeatedly, getting better and better.

6.4.3. Reduce Uncertainty: Riskiest Assumption Test (RAT)

The first thing you must learn is whether or not what you are doing even makes sense. The main way to do that is by experimenting rather than debating. You prioritize your work initially by regularly doing a Riskiest Assumption Test (RAT). By quickly getting answers as to what assumptions are correct, you can avoid going down the wrong path.

6.4.4. People make things work

Note that the Agile approach is quite different from how a lot of companies have historically worked. Because it is based on proof, not on hierarchy, political agendas, and bureaucracy, in and of itself an Agile approach is empowering. It helps create a positive, collaborative, can-do corporate culture that keeps people engaged.

6.4.5. Transparent Communication

An important way of keeping people engaged is to make sure that everyone knows what is going on and to give them the information in a digestible format. The CEO and VPs of the shipyard may not want to know about technical details of your digital twin initiative, but they will want to know what goals you are trying to achieve, what is your progress and how that fits in with a bigger picture. Furthermore, all employees will want to know how things are going to impact them. If you are transparent about what you are doing, it will ease anxiety, especially, since if you are following an Agile approach, you will be doing the right things right and clearly delivering benefit to the organization.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, because so much new technology for increasing efficiency in both ship construction and operation depends upon accurate and comprehensive data, a digital twin of a ship is necessary and increasingly, this is being recognized, particularly by ship operators. Some of them are even starting to re-examine their business models which everyone should do as disruptive new technology comes along. Creating a complete digital twin of a ship is a massive undertaking so it is necessary to prioritize according to what will deliver the most value. After you develop a clear vision and strategy, you should focus on something small and achievable. During the project, prioritize people over process and tools and note that you will end up dealing with a platform of software platforms which all need to be integrated. Creating a digital twin is a complex IT project but by using an Agile approach, you will incrementally add value and ultimately be successful.

References

MORAIS, D.; DANESE, N.; WALDIE, M. (2016a), *Ship design, engineering and construction in 2030 and beyond*, High-Performance Marine Vehicles Conf., Cortona, pp.297-310

MORAIS, D.; DANESE, N.; WALDIE, M. (2016b), *Open architecture applications: the key to best-of-breed applications*, 15th Int. Conf. Computer and IT Appl. Maritime Ind., Lecce, pp.223-233

MORAIS, D.; WALDIE, M.; LARKINS, D. (2013), *Empowered engineering: Availability of engineering data throughout the shipyard*, Int. Conf. on Computer Applications in Shipbuilding, Busan, Vol. III pp.67-76

MORAIS, D.; LARKINS, D.; WALDIE, M. (2011), *Driving the adoption of cutting edge technology in shipbuilding*, 10th Int. Conf. Computer and IT Appl. Maritime Ind., Berlin, pp.523-535

Mobile Visualization for Finite Element Model and Assessment Result of Whole Ship

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Abstract

Nowadays, the structural analysis using the finite element model for whole ship is essential for large commercial ships. This model covers fine-mesh model and fatigue assessment model of about 1 million meshes, so it is difficult to handle these in 3D environment. These models and assessment results are used not only for engineers in shipyard but also for various stakeholders such as ship owners, classification society, and other department designers to share, discuss, and improve or verify the design. In this paper, we introduce a quick and light visualization method of the whole ship structure analysis model and assessment results.

1. Introduction

The application of CSR-H (Harmonized-Common Structure Rule), IACS (2015), has made the structural analysis an essential task from the initial structure design stage of ships such as tankers and bulk carriers, *Shibasaki (2016)*. Because the range of analysis also covers all cargo holds, the structural analysis model is also close to the whole ship model except for the engine room area and the bow. Container carriers and LNG Carrier are generally structured in line with the trend of enlargement, the finite element (FE) model for whole ship is essential for large commercial ships. The whole ship structure analysis model including fine-mesh model and fatigue assessment model consist of about 1 million meshes, so it is not easy to handle in 3D environment of the entire model and visualize it in the commercial CAE software. Moreover, if the load cases reach dozens and the analysis result files for each case are combined, a DB of several gigabytes is required. The visualization of these individual results also takes about a minute (1 million mesh with deformation in spectral plot) in the whole ship model environment.

On the other hand, the finite element models and assessment results are used not only for engineers in shipyard but also for various stakeholders such as ship owners, classification society, and other department designers to share, discuss, and improve or verify the design. Usually this collaboration, work was performed using the structural analysis report most of image capture for the assessment result or CAE S/W equipped laptops.

If the lightweight visualization in the mobile environment using the low capacity DB independent from CAE S/W, it would be highly usable. In this paper, we introduce a quick and light visualization of the whole ship structure analysis model and assessment results in the mobile environment (AOS, IOS) and PC environment (Windows, Mac) through the lightweight CAD viewer (Open CASCADE CAD Assistant V 1.0, <https://www.opencascade.com/content/cad-assistant>). This paper presents the efficiency of lightweight visualization method by comparing and analyzing the visualization speed and file size for the whole ship structural analysis model and analysis results with SeaTrust-HullScan, Korean Register (KR) developed structural assessment software.

2. Overview of SeaTrust-HullScan

Korean Register (hereinafter referred to as KR) developed SeaTrust-HullScan (hereinafter referred to as HullScan), a 3D model-based engineering software for evaluating ship design based on CSR-H, and officially launched and distributed it in 2014.

As shown in Fig.1, it mainly consists of two modes, the rule scantling mode, and direct strength assessment (hereinafter referred to as DSA) mode (Pre/Post system of FEM, except a solver). Various calculations on compliance with ship design rules including CSR-H for bulk carrier and tanker and KR rules for all type of ships can be performed based on the geometry model of a ship, *Son et al. (2016)*.

Fig.1: Overview of KR Structural Design and Assessment Software for Ships (SeaTrust-HullScan)

Fig.2 Outline of Consistent Utilization of Finite Element Modeling

Furthermore, as shown in Fig.2, the model paradigm for HullScan has been extended from 2D geometry/ 3D finite element model to 3D geometry/ 3D finite element model to utilize 3D CAD model of a whole ship that has been created and utilized in the initial design phase in the major shipyards in Korea, recently. In addition, we developed the interfaces in HullScan to all initial structure CAD (AVEVA Marine, Intergraph S3D, NAPA Steel, and TTM ISD) for the shipbuilding that are used in the initial structure design divisions in Korean shipyards.

This allows users of HullScan to create cross-section model for the rule scantling automatically in real time by importing 3D CAD models without the need to create a new model. In result, this can reduce design man-hours buried in the modelling jobs during the initial structure design phase where design changes frequently, so that the design engineers can focus on engineering work. In addition, we developed various functions of 3D CAD model to be automatically modelled as a finite element model. The generated coarse-mesh model can be automatically modelled with a fine-mesh, and very fine- mesh, in accordance with the purpose of design and structural analysis, and vice versa.

Coarse mesh models are usually created manually referencing 2D construction drawings using general-purpose FE modelers such as Patran, Hyper Mesh, and FE Gate or specific software provided by the classification society such as SeaTrust-HullScan, SeaTrust-Holdan, DNV-GL Genie and BV VeryStar 3D. Recently, an FE model, automatically generated from the initial structure 3D CAD for shipbuilding such as NAPA Steel and TTM ISD, is also utilized. Furthermore, HullScan can automatically generate FE models after importing shipbuilding 3D CAD models.

The FE models generated by software other than HullScan are compatible with each other through the BDF file, the input format of MSC Nastran. In other words, although a coarse-mesh model can be generated in various ways depending on the S/W preference of design engineers, and 3D CAD environment of shipyards, in order to set the boundary condition and to set load case automatically in compliance with CSR-H, FE model should be input to the class structure design and strength evaluation S/W to be complete as the analysis model. The FE model, which is prepared for the evaluation of yield strength, is created in BDF format, and the calculation is performed through NASTRAN. The result is received as F06 file, and it is subjected to be imported again to the class structure design and strength evaluation S/W for the post-processing and analysis of results.

The concept of coarse-mesh modeling, and the linkage with other CAE S/W and CAD systems, and the concept of fine-mesh modeling and automatic generation of very fine-mesh from coarse-mesh can be found in the previous work, *Son et al. (2017)*, Fig.2.

All these different purposes of FE models can be visualized and handled in the mobile environment, not only the geometries and topologies but also properties and assessment results. Here, we analyze the characteristics of the whole ship structural analysis model and presented a lightweight structural analysis FE model expression method both for model and analysis result to overcome the limitation of existing commercial CAE S/W in accordance with the increased environment of operation.

3. Mesh file format for the lightweight visualization

In general, there are lots of mesh representation method in the form of file such as STL (STereoLithography), OBJ (Wavefront), BDF (MSC Nastran Format), and PLY (Stanford Polygon File). As STL format mostly focus on the tria mesh and only supports the geometries and topology between node and mesh. OBJ format extends the mesh representation method to quad mesh. And BDF format also can express the tria and quad meshes with properties and material of the plate (2D element) and stiffeners (1D element), but it supports too many presentations for input model and load case and constraint for FEM analysis for the various purpose structural analysis. In this paper, we focus on the PLY format for the lightweight representation for meshes.

PLY, which is polygon file format or Stanford triangle format, of which file extension is *.ply. It is defined and introduced by *Turk and Levoy (1994)*. It was originally developed for processing 3D

scanning data. As it is inspired by OBJ format, but it made improvement of limitations of OBJ such as the arbitrary mesh properties and grouping. A famous Stanford Bunny model as shown in Fig.3 is presented in the PLY format.

Fig.3: Stanford Bunny model in the PLY format

PLY format supports both binary and text representation (ascii). Once we take a look for Stanford Bunny file in the text representation, Fig.4, it consists of header for summarized information for whole meshes such as number of node and element and additional data type for properties, and body for actual detailed data for each node and mesh. The geometry can be defined in the node (vertex) coordinate in the form for float type (x, y, and z). And topology can be defined face element with indices of node number which is the order of the presentation in the format. For detail, Stanford bunny model consists of 35,947 nodes (vertex) and 69,451 (face/ all tria mesh). As users can define the arbitrary properties after the default properties of node coordinate, in this example, the confidence in float, and the intensity in float, node data are written in five columns. As we can easily figure out that after 35,947 lines of node data, it follows mesh (face) data in the form of list vertex indices. As we can see in the example first mesh is defined in tria-mesh with three different nodes (21216, 2115, 20399). In general, after all tria mesh are written down, then higher-order meshes such as quad, penta, etc.

Fig.4: Detail Representation of PLY format

4. Ship FE Model in PLY format

Ship structures are mostly consist of thin plate and stiffener so that 2D element for plate and 1D element (mostly beam element) for stiffener are commonly utilized. As we see the example of 3 holds model in coarse mesh of bulk carrier as shown in Fig.5, most of meshes are quad elements. 1D element will be represented in the line segment if we just write down the topology of two nodes as it is defined in FE model, detail sectional representation of stiffener cannot be found in the lightweight model, so that we extrude the 1D element to set of 2D elements using flange and web dimension and its normal of 1D element as shown in upper left-hand side of Fig.5.

Fig.5: Feature of FE model of a ship

In order to explain how we can define this kind of a ship FE model into PLY format, the much smaller area for hopper connection with quad and tria and beam elements are shown in Fig.6. In the header, we describe material key which are used in this model as comment, because PLY does not support string or char type for properties. For node information, we not only define absolute coordinate of node in x, y, and z but also additional coordinate of node in x, y, and z. When we visualize deformed shape after structural analysis, these additional coordinates indicate initial position of node and the default coordinate indicate the deformed position in scale-up for the effective visualization. For mesh description, we additionally define element normal vector (x, y, and z) and plate thickness, corrosion margin, and mesh-size and material key. These additional arbitrary properties can be defined by user-own taste, and for the specific purpose. Which means these are flexible arguments, if compatible 3D CAD model viewer, such as Open CASCADE CAD Assistant V1.0 (Open CASCADE 2016), supports this kind of flexible properties concept, then these variables can be effectively visualized with geometries.

As shown in Fig.6, this example model has different plate thicknesses which are shown as different colors, and 1D element can be found in line segment in left-hand side of Fig.6 that are actually flat bars and angles as shown in the right-hand side of Fig.6. When the selected models are exported in PLY, then 1D element automatically converted into 2D element as shown in the right-hand side of Fig.7 after extruding function in SeaTrust-HullScan. User can indicate extension of FE model to be

exported and file path and name, and whether it is combined with structural analysis model together or model itself.

- ✓ Hopper Connection Area Coarse Mesh Model
- ✓ Node: 35
- ✓ 2D Element (Plate): 25
 - Quad: 23
 - Tri: 2
 - Quad Percentage: 91.3%
- ✓ 1D Element (Stiffener): 8


```

HullScanFE_ARConnection.ply
1 ply
2 format ascii 1.0
3 comment Korean Register: SeaTrust-HullScan //Comment
4 comment Material 0: Mild //Comment for Material
5 comment Material 1: HT32 //Comment for Material
6 comment Material 2: HT36 //Comment for Material
7 comment Material 3: HT40 //Comment for Material
8 element vertex 53 //Num. of Node
9 property double x //Node Value 1 (Default)
10 property double y //Node Value 2 (Default)
11 property double z //Node Value 3 (Default)
12 property double P_x //Node Value 4 (User Define)
13 property double P_y //Node Value 5 (User Define)
14 property double P_z //Node Value 6 (User Define)
15 element face 37 //Num. of Elem.
16 property list uchar uint vertex_indices //Elem. Topology (Default)
17 property float nx //Num. of Node //Node no. //Elem Value 1 (User Define)
18 property float ny //Elem Value 2 (User Define)
19 property float nz //Elem Value 3 (User Define)
20 property double Thickness //Elem Value 4 (User Define)
21 property double Corrosion-margin //Elem Value 5 (User Define)
22 property double Mesh-size //Elem Value 6 (User Define)
23 property float Material //Elem Value 7 (User Define)
24 end_header
  
```

Node Info.						
Node No.	Node No.1	Node No.2	Node No.3	Node No.4	Node No.5	Node No.6
25	68520.0	-12225.0	2400.0	68520.0	-12225.0	2400.0
26	65940.0	-11410.0	2400.0	65940.0	-11410.0	2400.0
27	66800.0	-13251.1	2400.0	66800.0	-13251.1	2400.0

Elem. Info.						
Elem. No.	Elem. No.1	Elem. No.2	Elem. No.3	Elem. No.4	Elem. No.5	Elem. No.6
78	3	0	10	16	-0	-0
79	3	28	23	1	-0	-0
80	4	10	4	3	9	0
81	4	22	16	10	21	0
82	4	10	0	15	9	-0

Fig.6: Definition for FE model of a ship in PLY format

- ✓ Node: 35
- ✓ 2D Element (Plate): 25
 - Quad: 23
 - Tri: 2
 - Quad Percentage: 91.3%
- ✓ 1D Element (Stiffener): 8

- ✓ Node: 53
- ✓ 2D Element (Plate): 37
 - Quad: 35
 - Tri: 2
 - Quad Percentage: 94.3%

Fig.7: Automatic Conversion of 1D Element to 2D Element

Fig.8 shows the result of visualization in the mobile viewer using this PLY format. As we can see, all user-defined properties for node and element can be shown in hierarchical pane in the left-hand side of the viewer and all property values are well kept with the model within PLY format.

Fig.8: Mobile visualization of FE model in PLY format

When we extend the arbitrary properties in the head of each PLY format with deformation value in the node, and Von-Mises stress in the element that can be obtained in the result file of structural analysis (F06 format of Nastran), then result can be accessible in the mobile environment with much lighter file size than that of the original result file. The deformed position of node with scale-up factor can be calculated for all nodes in the model so that the deformed shape for each analysis load case can be visualized in the mobile environment as well.

5. Various visualization results of whole ship FE model

As we explained in Section 2, whole ship model for LNG carrier with fine-mesh model with almost 650K meshes are generated in SeaTrust-Hullscan. It takes about 30 s to access the whole DB, and it takes 0.5 s delays when user handle the whole 3D model. Once we export this FE model in the form of PLY, as we explained in the previous chapter, 1D elements are automatically converted to the meshes so that almost 850K meshes over all. When we open this PLY format model in the mobile viewer, CAD Assistant, it only takes less than 5 s, and no delays in 3D model handling as shown in Fig.9.

Demo environment for 3D model handling is as follows; PC (Windows 7 Ultimate 64bit O/S, Intel Core i7-4770 3.4 GHz Dual Core CPU, 8 GB RAM) with SeaTrust-HullScan V 1.2207, Mobile (Android 7, LG-F800S, Qualcomm Snapdragon 820 4 GB RAM) with Open CASCADE CAD Assistant V 0.9.

It offers user interaction with dual touch for 3D model handling in the mobile viewer, such as 1 finger movement for rotation, 2 finger movement for panning, and 2 finger pinch-to-zoom as shown in Fig.10. One big difference between commercial CAE S/W and lightweight mobile viewer with PLY format is the selection for each mesh. In mobile viewer with PLY format, meshes are not selectable so that if we want to check the property or analysis result, values as colors are only available. If the detail view for specific structural area should be checked, then plane-clipping can be one possible solution.

As we can see in Fig.11, file loading time and file size for mesh model are much smaller than those for analysis results. In the example of the LNG Carrier, file size for over 20 load cases are larger than 1 GB. When we export the FE model with analysis result, it can be much smaller in the file size, because the model and analysis result can be express in the same line for text format. If the load cases to be exported grow, then just one column for each load case is needed.

Fig.9: Outline of whole ship FE model mobile visualization

Fig.10: User interaction for 3D model handling in the mobile environment

Fig.11: The whole ship FE model in deformed shape with result visualization in the mobile viewer

We could confirm the rapid loading of the model and the operability of the 3D model compared to the existing CAE S/W. In addition, we improved the usability of this lightweight whole ship structure analysis model by allowing to use the lightweight whole ship structure analysis model even in the multi-platform based of mobile environment and PC environment without relying on CAE S/W to enable various stakeholders to collaborate. To show the effectiveness of PLY format for whole ship FE model, we have tested not only LNG Carrier with fine-mesh model, but also, container carrier with girder-sized mesh, and PCTC with longitudinal mesh, and naval vessel with coarse mesh as shown in Fig.12.

Fig.12: Mobile FE model visualization for various ship type

6. Conclusion and future works

In shipbuilding design, 3D modeling has been applied and used at all stages, and processes are being improved so that many tasks can be efficient. In this study, we proposed a method to visualize, share, and manipulate the results of ship 3D structural analysis model quickly and effectively in a collaborative environment.

The PLY format, which is a highly scalable visualization mesh format, is used to define the data structure to match the characteristics of the ship structural analysis model, and the results are presented. In addition, we confirmed lightweight visualization performance and mobile application possibility for various ship types. The lightweight whole ship FE model can be utilized to review the design with VR environment after stereographic output, and furthermore after some touchup for texturing and lightening for VR rendering, this model also can be transformed to the VR simulation ship model. And we will carry out further research and development that can be utilized as a kernel of ship design approval system based on 3D model in the future. This mobile visualization technology with lightweight ship model can be utilized as the plan-less approval platform for the filed surveyor of classification society or quality manager in shipyard in near future, and it can be further developed to be the viewer for the digital twin ship in the operation phase.

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References

IACS (2015), *Common Structural Rules for Bulk Carrier and Oil Tankers*, 1st January 2015 Issue: International Association of Classification Societies

SHIBASAKI, K. (2016), *Shipbuilding industry's perspective on the new IACS Common Structural Rules*, Tanker Structure Cooperative Forum 2016, Korea

SON, M.J.; PARK, H.G.; LEE, J.Y.; LEE, J.H.; KIM, J.O.; WOO, J.J. (2016), *Development of Auto FE Modeling for enhancement of the productivity in modeling based on CSR-H*, 13th Int. Symp. Practical Design of Ships and Other Floating Structures, Denmark

SON, M.J.; WOO, J.J.; PARK, H.G.; LEE, J.Y. (2017), *Auto-Fine Mesh Generation for Local Analysis based on the Consistent Finite Element Model*, Int. Conf. Computer Applications in Shipbuilding, Singapore

Approaching Design Review by Classification Society based on Digital Information Derived from the Customer's Design Models

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Abstract

The paper explores how the designer's 3D model can be reused by the Classification Society for verification of the hull structure. A digital data exchange schema (DEX) is developed for this purpose. The schema can represent the Vessel form (geometry, topology, attributes) including functions (functional requirements). The schema can also support business specific processes in the form of a process layer. The schema implements the Society's approval process supporting the comment exchange between the Society and designer/yard. A 3D digital model established early in the design stage and shared among stakeholders will eliminate the need for producing 2D drawings for the verification of the design by the Society.

1. Introduction

The role of the Classification society during the new-building phase is to verify and approve that the design fulfils Class and Statutory requirements (i.e. the Rules), http://www.iacs.org.uk/document/public/explained/CLASS_KEY_ROLE.pdf. The Society carries out a technical review of the design plans and related documents for a new vessel to verify compliance with the applicable rules and regulations. Today, the review process is purely document based. Current practice in vessel classification is to base the verification job on documents prepared and submitted by the designer/yard. Documents may consist of drawings, descriptions, calculations, reports, procedures, certificates and similar information describing e.g. the design, installation, testing, operation, maintenance or status of an object, *DNVGL (2018a)*. For the hull design verification, 2D drawings have been the single most important design document exchanged between yard/designer and the Society. The Society must manually build up their own verification and calculation models based on the submitted documents if independent calculations are required. This process is time-consuming and error-prone. For every design revision, the society may need to do a re-verification. The final design approved by the classification society is marked by a set of approved "stamped" drawings.

Computer Aided Design (CAD) models are now displacing technical drawings and documentation as the main product definition in several major industries. Within the last ten years or so, the engineering industry in automotive, aerospace and construction has gradually converted to using CAD models directly for communicating designs to manufacturers, builders, maintenance crews, and regulators. The shipbuilding industry is also gradually switching to creating the engineering record in digital models.

Shipyards and classification societies must modify the traditional design documentation and review process and enable direct 3D digital classification process to improve the exchange of information between the different stakeholders and ultimately accelerate the classification process. Compared to traditional drawing approval, the advantages include: reducing shipyard workload with fewer drawings to create, improving quality and a common understanding of design and class comments by using a 3D design representation directly, optimizing the calculation process by directly interfacing the 3D design model with all calculation software such as structural and stability software, improved transparency and support for automation and increased self-service.

However, shifting to a fully digital and model-based design review process does not come without challenges and barriers. We will identify the main challenges and barriers to overcome to enable a fully digital classification in the following sections. We will also present possible solutions to some of the challenges, without claiming that we have all the answers.

2. Design verification and validation in the digital environment

2.1 Main challenges and barriers

Moving to a fully digital and model-based environment raises, among others, technical, process and legal (related to the Certification Process) issues for the companies involved. Based on a study from the aerospace industry, the following concerns of moving to a full model-based definition (MBD) environment were identified, *Quintana et al. (2010)*:

1. Data accessibility and visualization – most downstream users (including suppliers and customers) do not have access to CAD software, and therefore a visualization tool that allows them to read and use digital datasets must be adopted;
2. Data content – downstream users need to be confident that the 3D digital datasets will carry the drawing's core information;
3. Data presentation – engineering drawings follow international standards in terms of how the data is organized and structured and so must digital models;
4. Data management – an appropriate method must be put in place to manage and record revisions of the digital datasets;
5. Data security – a mechanism that incorporates security features (confidentiality, authentication, integrity, and non-repudiation) when accessing, exchanging and interacting with digital datasets will be required; and
6. Data retention – today typically only 2D data is stored and used for legal purposes.

A fully digital data exchange and model-based review process between designer/yard and the Society share all the above challenges. In addition, the Society must replace the current document-based comment management process with a digital version. The comment management process is the formal way how the Society communicates non-compliance and observations to the designer/yard. Today a comment is recorded with a reference to the submitted document in the society's comment management system. Additionally, red-marking on drawings (typically used for hull drawings) can become part of a comment. All comments which have not been resolved at the time of approval are listed in the approval letter issued by the society. I.e. the Society's comments can travel together with the approved documentation through the downstream processes. Therefore, the data accessibility and visualization capabilities for downstream users additionally need to cater for comments associated with digital datasets.

2.2 Data accessibility

We foresee that the designer/yard will supply the 3D design representation as a dataset in a fully digital classification environment. Normally, this dataset will be created in a proprietary CAD system. For downstream users to have access to it and to properly exploit it; the dataset must be converted to a non-CAD file format. Once the dataset has been converted, a viewer application to adequately display the converted dataset will be required.

This poses to main requirements to the exchanged dataset (i) A CAD neutral exchange format, and (ii) Adequate dataset viewer capabilities. The Long Term Archiving and Retrieval (LOTAR) International Visualization Working Group, www.lotar-international.org, has developed a detailed requirements document for 3D Visualization with the aim to replace 2D drawings. The document addresses requirements and use-cases related to the long-term archiving and retrieval of 3D visualization information. The objective is to define common recommendations for long-term archiving and retrieval of 3D visualization information. In a study for the aviation industry, *Quintana et al. (2010)*, requirements to drawing less environment were collected from downstream users of 3D CAD models. Their main findings were two-fold: (i) the importance of having a neutral CAD independent format for exchange of digital mock-ups, and, (ii) having a good toolset for viewing, annotating and red-marking the 3D models.

2.3 Data viewing and markup

Traditionally, drawings are used for communication in the industry because they are the clearest way to tell someone what to make and how to make it. They are considered as a graphic universal language which in many industries are standardised, *ISO (2013)*. The fundamental purpose of an engineering drawing is to carry, control and maintain a product's definition in a precise and clear way with no risk of misinterpretation or assumption. Technical drawings provide a means to communicate product complexity in a comprehensible and effective manner thanks to its visual abstraction.

Many in the industry have moved away from a reliance on drawings. Engineering drawings are no longer considered as primary product definition sources or as master representations of products as the integration of CAD systems within the product development process has become the standard, *Quintana et al. (2010)*.

However, in shipbuilding, it is still an explicit requirement that the designer/yard shall provide the Classification society with Class drawings documenting the design to be approved to the Society's Rules.

Fig.1: Naval architects know how to read and interpret traditional 2D drawings. There is no similar common standard in place for visual verification of 3D models

The left graphics in Fig.1 illustrates a 2D engineering drawing. The drawing presents the graphical elements in a clear and well known visual context. This is achieved using standardised drawing elements in the form of annotations, drawing legends, and other mark-ups. This universal language is based on industry standards like e.g. *ISO 128-15:2013 "Presentation of shipbuilding drawings"*, *ISO (2013)*. It is a syntactic standard and uses a set of standardised symbols to communicate the design information in a precise way. I.e., the symbol for a type of welding seam is standardized. The semantics, however, is not part of that standard. I.e., a welding symbol pointing to a cut-out is a valid engineering drawing according to the standard even if the represented information is questionable. Note that a syntactic standard is very flexible and easier to adopt than a semantic standard.

For the 3D visualisation as illustrated by the right graphics in Fig.1, the visual representation of the 3D model is lacking context and standardised ways of annotating the different objects. Having a rich toolset for viewing and markup of 3D models will be important for preserving efficiency when moving from working with 2D drawings to a fully digital classification process.

2.2 Data content

Downstream users need to be confident that digital datasets can replace information received today in drawings. Considerable effort has been spent in developing standard protocols for product definitions both in the shipbuilding and other industries, *ISO (2004,2010,2014)*. Due to its broad scope, the application protocol AP218 is a semantic standard with the aim to support the need for data exchange during the early stages of the design in a consistent manner. However, due to the generally limited support by software vendors, the shipbuilding protocols are not used in actual commercial ship design

projects today, *Bronsart et al. (2005)*. focus of the various ISO standardization initiatives has been to support product definitions with the primary aim to build and produce the asset, i.e. the ship. The product-oriented ISO standards are difficult to use as a basis for digital classification by the Classification Societies, as these (semantic) standards become too information rich and are not particularly adapted to the society’s needs. There is no available digital standard supporting Class requirements and constraints as per today. Attempts have been made to establish such standards in the past, *Haenisch and Langbecker (1999)*, *Polini (2011)*, but nothing has materialized.

The DNV GL Rules, *DNVGL (2018b)*, state specific requirements to which design documentation the designer/yard must submit to the society. The Rules also specify the content of these documents, see Table I for an excerpt. The table is showing the required information for a mid-ship section drawing. As we can see, the required information is, in fact, *semantic* information (ship-length, moulded depth and breadth etc.) which accompany the graphic visualisation of the mid-ship section.

However, providing semantics in the format of a drawing or document makes it impossible to re-use the information in a digital classification process. The challenge for the Society is to extract the required information and represent it in a *semantic* standard targeted for digital classification.

Table I: Example of a structure plan (drawing) required by the Rules, *DNVGL (2016)*

Code	Title	Definition
H052	Mid-ship section drawing	<p>A drawing of the mid-ship transverse section providing information of geometric dimensions, scantlings, and material specifications. The following information shall be included on the drawing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - length of ship L - greatest moulded breadth B - moulded depth D - mean moulded summer draught T - block coefficient CB - maximum service speed V - class notations. <p>For vessels that may carry dry bulk cargo, as applicable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - for each cargo hold MH: the cargo mass MH corresponding to the homogeneously loaded condition at maximum draught with 50% consumables - for each cargo hold M_{Full}: the cargo mass of the hold filled to the top of the hatch coaming with a cargo with the density of the greater of 1.0 t/m³ and MH/V_{Full} (volume of cargo hold up to top of the hatch coaming) - for each cargo hold MHD: the maximum allowable cargo mass in the hold according to design loading conditions with specified holds empty at maximum draught with 50% consumables - distributed loads for inner bottom of each cargo hold - distributed loads for deck and all hatch covers - design steel coil loads in terms of weight, length, diameter and dunnage arrangement. - specification if transverse bulkheads separating cargo holds are watertight <p>For vessels that may carry containers, as applicable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — stack weights of 20 ft and 40 ft containers and mixed stowage, in holds, on hatch covers, and on decks — minimum mass in one typical 40 ft bay on scantling draught. <p>For vessels with class notations POLAR and Icebreaker:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - maximum design ramming speed (VRAM) in ice infested waters - design speed for continuous icebreaking operation (VB). <p>For vessels with class notation GRAB:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - weight of grab.

3. Digital Classification

3.1 A digital class information package

In the future, we envisage a digital newbuilding classification process supporting all stages from pre-contract to delivery.

The definition of a digital information package replacing today's documents/drawings submitted to the Society will be instrumental in achieving this vision. Such a Class Information Package (CIP) can be ingested by the authoring system and later retrieved by the Society, Fig.2.

Fig.2: Class Information Package (CIP) prepared by designer/yard and submitted to the Society

The CIP must not only be able to replace the information submitted by today's 2D drawings, but should also carry context information (i.e. the purpose or the design intent including maturity of the objects contained in the package) and support the Society's formal approval process (i.e. comment issuing, comments management and stamping). The authors have therefore proposed to develop a CIP in the form of a Digital Exchange Specification (DEX) supporting the necessary exchange capabilities between designer/yard and the Society.

Based on our current research, *Astrup and Cabos (2017)*, the DEX is proposed to have the following capabilities:

- A lightweight and CAD-neutral representation of the 3D geometry.
- The ability to carry both precise and approximated geometry representations depending on the intended use.
- The ability to grow the product definition information throughout the design lifecycle.
- The ability to describe function and process related information.
- The ability to reference function and process information to the 3D model using multi-layered annotations.
- A referencing mechanism which is robust to 3D model design changes.
- An easily extendable schema to cater for the new function and process related data.

The information contained in the DEX is therefore structured into three groups, Fig.3:

What: The vessel hull form described by its geometry, features, materials, topology, ...

Why: The functions of the vessel represented by a Class-specific taxonomy which enable us to link atomic objects represented in the WHAT part to regulatory and class specific requirements and constraints.

How: Process and business-related data represented by layered annotations describing requirements and process information for e.g. approval, change management, inspection, testing etc.

In this way, it is possible to separate the digital product form definition (the ship itself) from the process and life cycle specific data (annotations), Fig.3.

Fig.3: DEX 3D information structure with layered annotations

4. DEX Form schema definition

The general DEX schema follows the W3C standards for XML, <https://www.w3.org/standards/xml>, and serialises only one root element: dexXML. Directly under the root element follows the WHAT, HOW and WHY parts of the schema in the form of the schema elements Form, Function and ProcessLayer, Fig.4.

The lightweight 3D model is described by the DEX Form and the DEX Function schema definitions. The focus in the current research is to develop the DEX Form schema covering the hull structure. This development follows the ship specific concepts described by AP218, ISO (2004).

The DEX Function schema describes Class specific taxonomies. These are represented in the form of Catalogues, Fig.4. The DEX Function part is designed to be interchangeable between Classification societies (each society may provide their own Catalogue). The Vessel and possibly Equipment are subtypes of Form meaning they will carry geometry and topology information. The DEX Form schema describes completely the vessel hull form and inner structures including the ship concepts, topologies, and attributes. The Form part is intended to replace today's 2D drawings as documentation of the design. Hence, Form must convey the same information as the designer provides today in the form of 2D drawings.

Fig.4: dexXML root with sub types including details of the dex:Vessel type

The `dex:Function` is represented by the `ClassCatalog` element. This element carries Class specific taxonomies which shall be assigned to the `Form` elements. The `ProcessLayer` carries business specific information describing specific business transactions covered by the schema. The `Form` part of the schema is designed to be free from business and the Society specific information. The schema also incorporates the `UnitsML` mark-up language developed initially by NIST and later taken over by the OASIS group, www.oasis-open.org. The `UnitsML` types allow for an unambiguous unit implementation in the `DEX` schema.

As seen from Fig.4, the `Vessel` element carries information on `ClassificationData`, `TonnageData`, and `StatutoryData`. The `StructureGrouping` with subtype `Structure` contains the hierarchy of ship specific concepts, geometry, topology and attributes. The `CoordinateSystem` element defines the vessel specific coordinates system in world coordinates. Below the `Structure` element, the schema describes a `Panel` type, Fig.5. A panel may consist of any number of plates represented by `dex:Plate` and can be split by any number of seams (`dex:Seam`), stiffened by any number of stiffeners (`dex:Stiffener`), cut by `dex:Hole2DContour`, and has a geometry definition given by the `UnboundedPanelGeometry` element. In addition, the panel geometry may be limited by other objects through a reference mechanism which carries additional topology information.

The ability to uniquely identify an object as well as preserve information about its ownership by the authoring system is fundamental to the `DEX` model. Once a `DEX` object instance is created, it is critical that it can be uniquely identified for its entire lifecycle. The ability to both exchange and archive data is not possible without this capability. For example, if multiple software applications are used to annotate or refer to an instance of a structure item like e.g. a stiffener, having a unique identifier associated with each instance allows for exchange and storage in a common archive with the capability of tracking design changes between different CIP revisions.

Fig.5: `dex:Structure` and subtypes

5. DEX Process Layer

5.1 Introduction

Traditionally, a paper or PDF document is the most granular information carrier for design or product documentation that is used by the Society's approval process. (An exception to this are proprietary data files as input to widely accepted calculation tools like Napa, FEA applications.) Moving away from engineering drawings as design and product definition will lead to changes in the communication interface between designer/yard and the classification society. Based on technical documentation by PDF documents the relevant communication topics are:

- Approval status by document
- The comment issued by the Society regarding the document
- Documentation Requirements are given as a document type

Using the vessel hull steel structure as an example of the DEX Form format, we foresee the following communication scenarios (the list is not exhaustive):

- Approval Status of a CAD object inside the designer's CAD work environment
- The comments issued by the Society pointing at individual CAD objects and/or spatially grouped objects inside the designer's CAD work environment
- 3D red marking regarding of individual CAD objects and/or spatially grouped objects
- Documentation Requirements which allow for preliminary maturity status of individual parts in the DEX Form file

The pattern for this new level of communication between designer/yard and the Society makes it possible for CAD objects being the smallest granulate of exchanged information that we can chat about. However, this does not imply that the Society will explicitly verify and approve every single atomic object contained in a CIP. The authors believe that we need to add a layer or envelope around the DEX Form which describes the individual objects. The Society will use this combined package (the CIP) as the basis for verification and approval. There are reasons why it is important for the Society not to mix the above-outlined communication with the details of the hull data exchange format DEX Form. They are:

- The newbuilding service consists of approval and site survey, i.e. the Society's communication that is relevant for site survey needs to be process-able without access to hull specific software.
- The above is true for all other approval disciplines or downstream users.
- Verification tools (specialist applications of approval engineers) are specific to a technical discipline or problem scope, i.e., there are a lot of them. It is not reasonable to implement interpretation of the Society's communication to all these tools.

A designated DEX Process Layer is defined to establish the separation of domain and application specific (WHAT) content and the communication (HOW) about it. The following subsections will detail on some relevant aspects of the DEX Process Layer.

5.2 The class information package

To support the fundamental change of enabling communication about WHAT elements defined inside a DEX Form instance file the respective WHAT element needs to be made visible at the process level. A DEX Process file instance thus needs to be capable of referencing (or pointing at) individual or atomic objects represented in the WHAT part (DEX Form). This is enabled by a set of pointers to WHAT elements located inside a referenced DEX Form file. The pointers are established by W3C XPointer, <https://www.w3.org/TR/xptr-framework/>. Figs.6 and 7 illustrate the concept.

Legend

- ①+② The authoring system ingests a CIP in two steps :
 - a) The DEX Form
 - b) DEX Process layer
- ③ The CIP is submitted to the Society (i.e. uploaded to a portal)
- ④ The CIP is stored in a managed and secure data store
- ⑤ A key which uniquely identifies the CIP can be sent back to the author
- Ⓐ A user with access rights
- Ⓑ Access the CIP using the key
- Ⓒ View the CIP in a review tool

Fig.6: Digital approval based on CIP

Fig.7: A ClassInformationView represented by a hierarchy of DEXItemPtr pointing at individual objects in a DEX Form file

Each pointer has its own identifier and can carry additional attributes:

- External key: Optional string field. The author of the content can provide an identification of the referenced object that is unique and stable/managed in his work context. The external key can be prepared as a structured string that also contains a reference to the authoring application and application release.
- Maturity (ForReview, Preliminary, Modified): Defaults to ForReview. The author of the content can state the maturity level with implication for the review by the Society.
- Version: Optional. The author of the content can provide a version number to individual DEXItemPtr. This option helps to deal with changes on subsequent submissions. Referring to PLM concepts, the digital information package is a Society-specific product view, Siemens (2013), Eigner (2014).

Depending on the complexity of the data inside the WHAT file enabling a communication about the individual WHAT elements can be desirable or not. The digital information package can point to the WHAT file itself. In this case, all communication will only refer to the complete content of the WHAT file. In the simplest case, the class information package facilitates small or simple content (Sec. 6.1). This represents today's practice where a drawing/document is the WHAT file.

In the more complex case, where we allow for a granular communication about individual objects in the WHAT file, can give benefits to both designer/yard and the Society. The concept of `DEXItemPtrDEXItemPtr` inside a separate process layer sets no limit to this granularity. At both ends of the communication pipe though, there are parties/applications which need to deal with this granularity. In both cases, author and reviewer, tool support will be necessary, see section 5.5. Negotiating the suitable level of granularity is driven by:

- On which level does the author of the content want to specify maturity status.
- On which level does the author of the content want to point to modifications compared to an earlier revision.
- On which level does the author of the content want to analyze approval status and the comments issued by the Society.
- Which level of granularity is most effective to the reviewer.

To avoid confusion about the proper granularity on a certain case, simple rules can be introduced. Such rules can depend on

- Type of WHAT file, i.e. documentation requirement.
- A general upper limit for the depth of hierarchy or number of managed elements.
- Negotiated project-wise

5.2. Rule aspect

Today, the designer/yard submits an engineering drawing to the Classification Society documenting the design. A drawing will typically have a spatial focus describing a part or area of the vessel, e.g. a mid-ship section or an area in the fore ship. In addition, the drawing has a given purpose. This to provide the information required to show compliance with a specific rule or regulatory requirement. The Society's rules typically state a list of drawings/documents which must be submitted to cover the full scope of requirements for a vessel given Main Class, and additional Class Notations. This is an aid to the designer to plan the drawings/documents to be produced. The designer/yard has flexibility on how the full documentation package is put together (i.e. the drawing list). The current process requires each document to be mapped to a document requirement.

The authors believe the concept of layered annotations and the DEX lightweight 3D model, Fig.3, can cater for a more flexible and transparent exchange and approval process. The information contained in today's drawings can be abstracted into two dimensions: (i) a spatial subdivision of the vessel into manageable parts, and (ii) the rule dimension (which is today represented by the document requirements). This is envisaged in Table II together with the concept of the Class Information Package (CIP) introduced earlier. The designer/yard decides on how to subdivide the vessel into manageable parts. This adds flexibility to the process and caters for different ship types. The society may provide a ship specific template to aid designers in this (the analogy to today's process would be the document requirements). The Rule aspect will be fixed as these are the ship type specific requirements. The list of applicable rule aspects will be governed by the Main Class and additional Class Notations and is of course discipline specific. The example given in Table II displays a possible set up for the Hull discipline. The Society may, in addition to the CIPs exemplified by Table II also require other class information packages to be submitted, e.g.

- General information (semantics for ship main particulars etc.)

- Welding table
- Arrangement and watertight subdivisions
- Standard details

We also foresee that compliance to some rule aspects should be documented using traditional design documents as is done today. A typical example would be the loading manual (a required document by SOLAS) or e.g. the welding table. It is important to note that a CIP does not completely prevent the designer from submitting documents as part of a CIP.

Table II: Rule dimension, spatial subdivisions and CIP

	Aft ship	Cargo area	Fore Ship	Super structure	Engine room
Rule Aspect						
<i>Prescriptive</i>			1		2	
• Minimum req.		✓		✓		
• Local strength		✓		✓		
• Global Strength		✓				
• Buckling/slenderness		✓				
<i>Finite Element</i>						
• Yield		✓	3			
• Buckling		✓				
• Fatigue						
<i>For Information</i>						

CIP

It can be up to the designer/yard which rule aspect to be addressed by a CIP. In this way, the process will allow for a degree of flexibility. Some designers/yards will prepare a CIP which covers every rule aspect and submit this as one package, while others may choose to split a structure part into several submissions covering e.g. only the prescriptive requirements first, and later the finite element rule aspects. However, the Society and the designer/yard will agree on the main CIPs through the contract with the Society like what is done today based on submission of traditional design documentation. At the end of the project, all contracted CIPs will be submitted covering all required rule aspects.

In the case of complex systems such as hull or integrated control systems, design and approval tasks come in sequence on the timeline, Fig.7. Usually, fundamental design decisions need to be taken before the first submission to the Society. At the same time, the Society cannot give a final approval statement as the documentation is incomplete at this early stage. Late class feedback on important decisions can thus cause unnecessary delay for the designer or manufacturer.

Fig.7: Latency between fundamental design decision and class feedback in the traditional document-based approval workflow

The class information package shall thus facilitate a design documentation that can be prepared and submitted right at the time of a fundamental design decision to collect an early class feedback that

focusses on the design decision. For this purpose, two DEX features are used jointly inside to specify a targeted question by a class information package:

- Rule Aspect: Functional documentation requirement focusing on which approval task the documentation shall be used for (see Table II).
- Maturity Status: An optional attribute to WHAT element pointers which allows the author to indicate parts of the submittal as being `Preliminary`, in contrast to `ForReview`.

The use of maturity status should properly combine with the desired rule aspect to form a class submittal that is complete for approval of the announced rule aspect.

By means of the rule aspect concept, the class information packages can be tailored to the work schedule of the designer. Or it can even facility a documentation that is tailored to one urgent design decision. In the latter case, DEX improves the latency between design decision and class feedback by speeding up the creation of documentation to the Society and strictly focussing the approval task. Of course, an approval assigned to a class information package with limited rule aspect is only valid for that rule aspect. Class information packages which contain preliminary parts will not get approval status but will be assigned as examined.

5.3. Comment handling

Exchanging comments and replies between designer/yard and the Society describes a communication about the content targeted by a class information package. Today, DNV GL's comments refer to a document, e.g. an engineering drawing represented as a PDF file. The detailed reference to a structural element or position is only provided by a (natural language) text description as part of the comment's text body. In the case of engineering drawings, markup annotations in red (so-called red marking) can be part of a comment as an additional illustration.

Since a comment is not necessarily closed at the end of the design phase such comments need to be followed up by craftsmen and surveyors on site. It is even more complicated for comments on type approval documentation for equipment or components. They need to be followed up for every single physical instance built and installed and may even apply to altered designs whose approval is based on the original type approval. At DNV GL, comments are hence treated as data objects referring to PDF documents and are managed centrally.

With DEX and `DEXItemPtrs` (see Sec. 5.2), we aim at managing more granular targets for comments. This provides benefit to both designers and the Society:

- Comments can be filtered by spatial position
- The designer/yard can import comments with target reference provided by position and/or an object reference to his work environment
- Comments can be overlaid to subsequent design releases for more efficient replies and "closed" statements

Red marking can be transferred to 3D space as well as DEX Form provides a 3D geometry representation. Communication between designer/yard and the Society needs to be clear and precise. 3D markup thus needs to consider things like view direction, active select set, or active cutting planes. This complexity in consistently representing 3D markup is addressed by existing file formats like PRC, http://help.adobe.com/livedocs/acrobat_sdk/9/Acrobat9_HTMLHelp/API_References/PRCReference/PRC_Format_Specification/prc_overview.html. DEX will thus select and adopt a suitable file format for this purpose.

5.4. Approval Status

Same as comments the approval status describes communication about the content targeted by a class information package. Providing approval status information at the level of `DEXItemPtr` leverages transparency on a more granular level than by document-wise assigned status.

If a designer uses the “external key” capability of `DEXItemPtr` he can import approval status information to his work environment and manage approval status as an attribute to the objects which are addressed by the external key. Such an integration of the designer’s work environment with a Class API which provides the approval status helps the designer to be aware of existing approval state on objects he is about to change. The level of granularity to which such a feature may apply is obviously restricted by the hierarchy of `DEXItemPtr` shared with the Society.

5.5 Tool support

The tool support for a DEX based design review by the Society involves two types of tools:

1. tools facilitating the exchange of DEX data (technically and legally)
2. tools enabling the desired benefits at the two ends of the communication line

5.5.1 Facilitating the exchange

In the first place, the partners in a DEX based communication need to be able to read and write DEX. I.e. import and export interfaces for DEX need to be available in the respective work environment. While designers are used to a 3D work environment already, the Society additionally needs to lift the work environment for visual design verification from 2D drawings to 3D DEX.

Fig.8 summarizes the transactions which facilitate the communication between designer/yard and the Society. Technically, the communication can run via the user interface (UI) of the Society portal (see also Fig.6) or via a dedicated programmable interface (API).

When submitting a design documentation to the Society this transaction involves uploading the content and providing the metadata of the approval order and the explicit confirmation of that order. The content can consist of the lightweight 3D model (DEX Form and DEX Function, see Fig.3) only. In Fig.8 this option is marked as (i1). In this case, all defaults of the DEX Process schema apply, i.e. the complete content is `ForReview` and there are no `DEXItemPtrs` which define a more granular breakdown for the communication with the Society (comments and approval status).

If a DEX Process file is part of the uploaded content (i2), it may provide tailored definitions of a class information package making use of the concepts for rule aspect and maturity as outlined in the sections 5.1 and 5.2.

All other transactions in Fig.8 is related to the communication about the submitted content.

Besides the technical demands for a DEX based communication, there are also legal aspects. An engineering drawing is a standardized (syntactic standard) way to document a design and is a precisely defined visual presentation of the content at the same time (facilitated by PDF as standardized file format and free PDF viewer). For 3D DEX content the visual presentation very much depends on the tool which renders this visual presentation from 3D DEX. Thus, an authoritative reference (see also Fig.6) is necessary which renders the legally binding visualization. Such a reference can be established by a software application that is available for all communication partners or by a neutral file format that already ships with a reference application like 3D PDF and Adobe Acrobat Reader. In the case that DEX becomes a semantic standard that completely covers the information scope to be exchanged an authoritative reference can be omitted.

communication transaction	interactive (UI)	linear (API)
submit DEX to Class	i1: upload DEX Form	
	i2: upload DEX Form/Process	
Class publishes comment	download Class comments (CIP/DEXItemPtr as reference to target object)	get Class comments (CIP/DEXItemPtr as reference to target object)
reply to Class comment or "closed" note	download replies (CIP/DEXItemPtr as reference to target object)	get/post replies (CIP/DEXItemPtr as reference to target object)
Class publishes approval status	download approval status (CIP/DEXItemPtr as reference to target object)	get approval status (CIP/DEXItemPtr as reference to target object)

Fig.8: Use of DEX in communication with the Society for different transactions

5.5.2 Enabling benefits

Further tool support is necessary to enable more benefits founded on the fact that with DEX the information carrier between designer/yard and the Society will be data. Which new features can be facilitated very much depends on the individual infrastructure which exists at a designer or the Society.

With a 3D CAD system being the work environment of a designer/yard it is straightforward to think about integrating with the Class API functions outlined in Fig.8. This will provide designers with comments and approval states which are attached to their CAD objects.

A PLM solution (Product Lifecycle Management) in place at the designer's site will allow to consistently link attributes (i.e. approval status and comments) to CAD objects which may change between submission to the Society and receiving of comment or status.

6. Application example

The focused transaction between designer/yard and the Society of the application examples will be the submission of content for a verification by the Society. The discussed sample submissions deal with the following cases:

1. simple CIP content that is sent without DEX ProcessLayer
2. complex CIP content with a granular definition represented by the ClassInformation View
3. a CIP definition that is tailored to requesting verification of a critical design decision

6.1 Simple content

DEX Form/Function content can be submitted without DEX ProcessLayer. In this case, the defaults from the DEX ProcessLayer schema apply. A simple submission thus ships

- without ProcessLayer definition,
- with a rule aspect, equal to all applicable rules,
- with a maturity state ForReview for the complete content.

Consequently, an approval status assigned to such a simple submission concerns the complete applicable rule scope and the full content of the submission. Any comment only targets the submission in total.

This case facilitates the communication with the Society as it is today, i.e. on “document” level. Apart from the ability to write DEX Form/Function files this case does not require any further process changes for the content author (yard, designer, or other authors).

6.2 Granular CIP definition

Making use of the `ClassInformationView` (CIV) definition the designer/yard can present a flat list of targetable objects or a sophisticated object hierarchy by using the grouping feature (`DEXItemPtrGroup`).

With such a granular CIV definition, the Society’s approval process can target each object represented as `DEXItemPtr` with a comment. Provided an external key as an attribute to the `DEXItemPtr` the designer/yard can import the comment which points to a valid object identification in his work environment.

The Society will assign an approval status only to the complete CIV definition preserving the specification of rule aspect and/or content maturity. But the designer/yard is free to invert this structure inside his work environment and produce a view that shows approval status as an attribute of the object. This way a designer/yard could keep track of implications to previous approvals in the case of late design changes.

6.3 Support critical design decision

The `ClassInformationView` illustrated in Fig.7 can be used to point only to a small part of the content shared with the Society via a DEX Form/Function file. Using maturity status and rule aspect the content that is presented for verification can be additionally reduced in terms of the addressed technical subject.

Thus, a CIV definition can be used to request verification of a very detailed topic. For the designer/Society, this is beneficiary since the latency between design decision and feedback from the Society, Fig.7, is addressed in two ways. The necessary design documentation for the Society is created automatically by export to the DEX Form/Function file format. The feedback from the Society can be fast since the request is very targeted and well put. For the Society, this way of documenting urgent and targeted verification jobs allows for better transparency and in-process verification.

7. Conclusions and recommendation for further work

The paper summarizes technical and legal prerequisites to a vessel design review process based on digital information packages which are directly derived from 3D design models. Based on these prerequisites a solution is proposed of how to efficiently ingest digital information to the design review process and how to manage communication based on this digital information. The proposal has been outlined on a hull approval scenario as the sample discipline.

The authors believe that exchanging digital information between designer/yard and the Society will enable some important benefits. The documentation can be packaged in a more flexible way. It can thus be more targeted to the designer/yard work schedule or even focused on singular urgent design decisions. Manual process steps in the preparation of the Society documentation can be reduced significantly which will result in time gains. Direct reuse of the exchanged information with calculation tools provided by the Society will speed up response times. Facilitating digital information pieces as the target of communication between designer/yard and the Society can be used to leverage transparency of approval status inside the designer/yard work environment.

The presented solution is intended to be applicable not only to the hull discipline, but to any other design discipline in shipbuilding.

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References

ASTRUP, O.C.; CABOS, C. (2017), *A model based approval process for basic hull design*, ICCAS Conf., Vol. 3, pp.39-48

BRONSART, R.; CANTOW, U.; GRAFE, W.; KOCH, T. (2005), *A collaborative platform for ship design*, ICCAS Conf.

DNVGL (2016), *Rules for Classification: Ships Part 3 Hull Chapter 1 General principles*, DNV GL Rules for Classification: Ships, DNV GL

DNVGL (2018a), *Rules for Classification: Ships Part 1 General regulations*, DNV GL

DNVGL (2018b), *Chapter 3 Documentation and certification requirements, general*, DNV GL Rules for Classification: Ships, DNV GL

EIGNER, M. (2014), *Modellbasierte Virtuelle Produktentwicklung*, Springer

HAENISCH, J.; LANGBECKER, U. (1999), *Exchange of structural design data for hull cross section approval*, EMSA Protocol

ISO (2004), *ISO 10303-218 Ship structures*, Int. Standard Org., Geneva

ISO (2010), *ISO 10303-214:2010 Core data for automotive mechanical design processes*, Int. Standard Org., Geneva

ISO (2013), *ISO 128-15:2013 - Technical product documentation (TPD) – General principles of presentation – Part 15: Presentation of shipbuilding drawings*, Int. Standard Org., Geneva

ISO (2014), *ISO 10303-242:2014 Managed model-based 3D engineering*, Int. Standard Org., Geneva

POLINI, M. (2011), *A neutral XML schema for basic design stage interface to class societies*, ICCAS Conf.

QUINTANA, V.; RIVEST, L.; PELLERIN, R.; VENNE, F.; KHEDDOUCI, F. (2010), *Will model-based definition replace engineering drawings throughout the product lifecycle? A global perspective from aerospace industry*, Comput. Ind. 61/5, pp.497-508

SIEMENS (2013), *PLM XML Schema Functional Description*, Siemens Product Lifecycle Management Software Inc., Cambridge

Cloudless Skies in Early Design?

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Abstract

One goal of the SHIPLYS project is to increase efficiency and integrity of early design processes while maintaining full flexibility, creating additional space for creativity and improving affordability, in particular for SMEs. We present the approach chosen to realise a fully distributed design environment of loosely coupled design tools utilising REST-based services, reviewing the architecture, services, interaction models and integration principles that have been conceived to enable designers to execute complex design processes effectively and yet more thoroughly. We also look at security and data protection facets, which require careful consideration in distributed systems.

1. Introduction and Background

The European shipbuilding sector, with more than 300 shipyards and a network of over 9,000 subcontractors (mainly SMEs), accounts for a total of about 350,000 jobs and a turnover of around €34 billion per year, *Bharadwaj (2017)*. Nevertheless, this sector is facing a global competition steadily becoming fiercer with the strategic investments in ship building and repair being made in the Far East and low labour cost countries. Furthermore, client expectations enforced by additional rules and regulations coming into force, for vessel quality, pollution controls and through life performance are becoming more sophisticated. Consequently, in order to provide the best offer during the bid stage, it is indispensable to be able to create innovative designs and at the same time, reliably predict the innovation's impact on building costs, ship quality and operational performance.

Major progress has been made in the fields of numerical simulations, computing technologies and efficient organization of distributed working environments. Yet, the calculation and modelling to do in order to take advantage of this progresses is difficult and time consuming – especially for SMEs without a large overhead of trained staff and tools – due to difficulties in integrating data flows between incompatible tools and formats for different design stages. To a certain extent, SMEs are limited in their ability to make use of technological advances while innovations are considered as a critical precondition for survival. In order to apply innovation with economically acceptable risk, there is a need to reduce the cycle time and costs of designing processes (especially during bid preparation stages). This will enable an SME to

- develop multiple alternative designs, leading to an improved final design,
- perform more thorough risk assessment at earlier stages of design,
- increase the level of confidence in the innovation-based ship's performance and costs across the complete product life-cycle (from design to production, operation, ... up to the decommissioning)

This is achievable by decreasing the amount of time and financial resources needed for the early design which should facilitate more detailed pre-bid-designs which can be assessed more thoroughly (e.g. by performing early numerical studies, production simulation, LCA etc.) .

SHIPLYS has proposed to address these issues by applying three main concepts, *Bharadwaj (2017)*:

- introducing a framework of distributed services (allowing exploitation of multi-level synergies) to establish a state-of-the-art design tool chain:

This concept aims to solve several problems such as providing cost-efficient access to sophisticated tools and methodologies, i.e. enabling SMEs to use otherwise unaffordable technologies on a job-based costing model, simplify design iterations and re-execution of calculation jobs creating updated versions of affected data. Also, a project-wide infrastructure for shared access of monitored and versioned data increases collaboration effectivity and the level of overview, *Koch et al. (2017a)*.

- allowing more effective reuse of previously generated information (reducing cycle times):
This is inspired by other industries efforts and experiences in identifying and capturing the useful implicit information already present in existing CAD/CAE data. In particular, the Building Information Model approach, *Lu and Li (2011)* increasingly adopted in the oil & gas and construction sectors appears to be based on promising principles such as product- and life-cycle-oriented data standardization.
- introducing 3D-models in early design by enabling automatic data generation/rapid virtual prototyping (allowing to investigate alternative designs):
The last concept takes advantage of the previous two aspects and aims to drive pre-bid design much further, including preliminary production simulations based on 3D-prototypes.

In order to validate these concepts, three scenario types have been chosen to be investigated. Scenario 1 addresses the comparison of innovative alternatives as well as the evaluation of a design's life-cycle impact as it is about optimisation of designs for a short-route ferry using hybrid propulsion. In scenario 2, the full potential of SHIPLYS framework will be applied on the newbuilding design of a multi-purpose carrier. Scenario 3 should show the applicability of the SHIPLYS framework to retrofitting and repair cases and deals with the retrofitting of a scrubber system to a ferry.

Looking at the underlying information technologies, hardware and software developments continue at a rapid pace, while the cost of their use has stabilised at low levels. Nevertheless, as complexity and variety of systems and solutions increases, it cannot be considered an easy task at least for smaller organisations to deal with these advances in an efficient way. An example is the introduction of “cloud” technology, where marketing efforts of vendors might have created more confusion than assurance, not at least due to the increasing concerns about cyber-security. For organisations that are dependent on protecting their intellectual property to maintain their competitive advantage and specialised know-how, the common perception of “The cloud” creates many unanswered questions – if not threats – and thus inhibits the unconcerned adoption. What is commonly overlooked in this discussion is the fact that these propositions are based on several powerful technological developments (often summarised as cloud technologies), for example virtualisation, <https://www.vmware.com/pdf/virtualization.pdf>, containerisation, www.docker.com, provisioning and scalability, <https://www.openstack.org/software>. These technologies provide a great potential for improvements without the actual ultimate need to utilize remotely operated 3rd party cloud services. However, to accomplish this, the use of these technologies needs to be tailored to the needs of the business users.

2. Improving Early Ship Design Processes

The SHIPLYS design solution's ambition is to maintain and improve the competitiveness of Europe's SMEs in the maritime industries, especially small- and medium-sized shipyards and engineering offices by enabling them to generate offers that are thoroughly investigated. To allow investigation of various aspects of a ship's performance over the entire life-cycle or to assess inherent production risks (e.g. time schedule, capacity, and technical demands) as well as a dependable estimation of design and production costs, a simulation-based approach has been chosen. Obviously, such kinds of simulations have to be implemented using three-dimensional models. But how do we get there before the bid?

One important component of the SHIPLYS approach is to formalize, capture/store and reuse the explicit and implicit assumptions and decisions at conceptual design stage that are part of the design engineer's vision and nowadays often not documented. This already begins even before conceptual design where we introduce tools to identify the requirements of the ship based on specifications or

tender documents, store them and evaluate the degree of the design's compliance automatically. Formalizing design decisions can only be done when using a comprehensive, industry-specific data model that is capable of capturing all relevant facets of the product. For this purpose, we are using a data-model that takes advantage of the effort invested in various standardization procedures. The vision of this concept is a project environment where integrated tools can access and process every relevant piece of information generated during the project.

Another idea we are pursuing is to formalize the design process itself by means of an attributed process model, *Koch (2017)*. It is based on a graph structure of design activities related by their required or optional inputs and generated outputs, *Brandes (2002)*. Such a model provides the basis to perform repeated dependency analysis operations to identify design activities that are ready to perform or to identify the missing data that is needed to perform a specific design activity. This way, we can monitor the progress of the design process and provide suggestions for pending operations. Furthermore, it facilitates the identification of dependencies resulting from outdated calculation results, e.g. due to design changes. It also enables us to identify lack of data or missing tool support, where target-oriented automation would allow driving the design process much further. With this preparatory work done, we aim to develop rapid virtual prototyping tools or use functionality of already existing software to close the identified gaps, often by generating three-dimensional models. Example use cases could be:

- generating a (preliminary) three-dimensional hull form from given main parameters,
- generating (preliminary) mid-ship section and main structural elements from hull form and ship purpose,
- generating (preliminary) block sections and assembly structures from structural elements,
- ... and many more applications.

As this approach allows including sophisticated design tasks such as operation-related calculations and production simulation, another important target of SHIPLYS is to perform full life cycle impact analyses. To simplify and improve the evaluation of a design's overall quality compared to another design, a multi criterion decision making support technic should be developed as well. Last but not least, the concept of loosely coupled services and clients allows efficient distributed working on the project among many participants.

3. Integration and Information Management

3.1. Integration of Tools

Since the early design is commonly dependent on a diversity of standalone software components (often with limited data exchange capabilities) an important element of our approach is the creation of a framework for integration of various software components. These components may cover a wide range such as full-scale applications, analytical programs, smaller or larger utilities, database management systems or other data sources, and software libraries. Such components originate from 3rd parties or end-users (e.g. utility type tools developed for the specific needs of a design scenario).

In general terms, integration of such components must be based on the following assumptions:

- In many cases modification of an existing component is either not possible or impractical. This is particularly true for commercial 3rd party components which may often appear in the form of a black-box type of software with no access to sources and limited configuration options. Such components will often mandate a specific runtime environment, which cannot be changed. As a consequence, integration should be possible without any real modification of such components.
- Components will often operate on input and output data streams of known formats combined with interactive control by the user, as is the case, for example, for applications performing

computationally intense calculations. It must be assumed that sufficient documentation or similar explanatory material will be available such that some standardised “glue” code can be provided in the project for such components to provide the required input and control data or consume the output of interest.

- Alternatively or additionally, software components or tools may have their own data management capabilities. For this kind of components data access interfaces will often be available.
- A further variant may be constituted by some degree of built-in extensibility e.g. by means of scripting or plug-ins. This is particularly relevant in highly interactive components such as modelling systems.
- It should also be possible to develop new components with minimal constraints concerning the implementation technology, e.g. free choice of runtime platform and programming environment and other technical constraints. This is mandated also by the fact that such components will often be based or be dependent on existing algorithms or sub-components and/or reliance on existing know-how among development staff involved.

Based on these assumptions, the following general design goals have been established for the project, *Koch et al. (2017b)*:

- Scalability (computational capacity, parallelisation, as well as storage capacity)
- Minimised programming technology constraints for software components:
 - runtime platform
 - programming platform
 - language and time zone
- Support for loosely-coupled, distributed operations: components may reside on hosting systems as long as they are reachable via network
- Light-weight integration of black-box type components
- Maximised support of functional requirements of early design processes

For purposes of prototype implementation, the following “Integration Methods” have been defined:

3.1.1. Glue code

This integration method provides functionality to expose component functionality of black-box type software via a SHIPLYS framework client. This Integration Method is particularly useful for non-interactive computation modules, Fig.1. Examples: standalone modules like weight or CoG calculations, resistance prediction, FEM or CFD processors.

Fig 1: Glue code integration method

3.1.2. Data access interface

This method is applicable to systems operating on some sort of data management platform, see Fig.2. It can range from simple file system level retrieval to full-scale data management system access. Examples: CAD or PDM system data retrieval, import, export or drawing extraction.

Fig.2: Data access integration method

3.1.3. Plug-ins

For systems or components that provide mechanisms to extend or tailor their functionality via e.g. a plug-in API or a scripting environment, this method (Fig.3) can be used to enable such systems to interact themselves with the SHIPLYS framework. For example, this may be realised as menu/user interface additions in user interfaces that effect some data retrieval or trigger a calculation in another remote component. Examples: many CAD systems, geometry design tools.

Fig.3: Plugin integration method

3.2 Features of the Approach

The following main features define important characteristics of the approach:

- REST services – the framework is based on a set of services accessible via a REST HTTP API utilising JSON encoded payloads. REST over HTTP relies on conventions layered on top of the ubiquitous HTTP protocol. Strong reasons for using this approach are the scalability of connection services and systems as well as the flexibility in implementation both in terms of actual design of the API itself as well as the relative easiness of support across a wide range of implementation platforms and operating systems.
- Process model support – the goal of providing guidance and process management capabilities during the design process is accomplished by providing a process definition and process monitoring capabilities.
- Data model support – to accomplish the required self-documenting data model services and to facilitate self-adjusting software components, a meta-data interface as part of the REST API is provided. This interface exposes (sub-)schemes, entities, attributes and build-in low-level type definitions to define the data models in use by a framework implementation. By providing such interface functionality, consuming software will be able to establish references to its local data models.
- Data state – to provide data life-cycle support functions including dependency analysis, it is possible to accompany any data entity instance with data state information: version (e.g. as a time stamp), origin (identifying the creating component), quality (e.g. vacant [needed but missing], required, estimated, calculated, validated, etc.)

- Function registration and activation – the framework provides lookup and locator functions for software components and the functionality supported by them. Components can register themselves in terms of component identification and description as well as individual operating instances (e.g. CAD system X running on host Y, offering a set of functions Z).
- Security – a design project usually involves multiple parties assuming different roles during the project execution. Since commercially sensitive information is created, protection of such intellectual property is mandatory.

4. Process Model

The ISO 10303 standard was started in 1984 as an effort to develop a series of application oriented data exchange standards and tooling methods for the computer-interpretable representation of product information and for the exchange of product data, *ISO (1994)*. While a full scale implementation has been accomplished in several industries, e.g. the automotive and aircraft industry, other parts of the standard have provided the basis for more complex approaches like the Building Information Model (BIM) for the building and construction industry, *ISO (2013)*. The adoption in the maritime industry has been somewhat fragmented and inconsistent due to many reasons. Nevertheless, the core content – the detailed data model repository – has served well in various technologies and influences various standardisation efforts such as geometry exchange, *ISO (2001)*, *ISO (2011)*, technical document management *S1000D (2016)*, or OpenHCM, <https://openhcmstandard.github.io/>. The shipbuilding related parts of the standard (*ISO (2004)*, *ISO (2003)*, *ISO (2005)*, *ISO (2004a)*) provide a wealth of concise data definitions which have demonstrated their production-readiness after many years in productive operation, e.g. *AES (2018)*.

An interesting, but often overlooked feature of this series of standards is the set of mandatory Application Activity Models (AAM). Thanks to the elaborated synchronisation between the shipbuilding related Application Protocols (APs) by means of the so-called “Ship Common Model”, all activity models in the “Ship” series of standards link together and can be seen as focussed subsets of a complete life-cycle activity model for marine vessels and structures.

Fig.4: A sample activity definition from the attributed process model

All shipbuilding-related APs apply the IDEF0 modelling method, *AFWAL (1981)*, to describe the activity functional model. In these models, activities are organised to create a deeply structured

hierarchy. The ISO 10303 Application Activity Model for ships (“Ship AAM”) provides a detailed and comprehensive description of the top-most process (A0 – “Perform ship lifecycle”) and its main sub-activities:

- A1 – Specify ship
- A2 – Complete and approve ship design
- A3 – Produce and inspect a ship
- A4 – Operate and maintain a ship
- A5 – Decommission and disassemble

The early design phase is represented in activity A12 – “Prepare bid” which is structured into some 60+ activities. Based on this initial set of definitions, a design process has been derived and extended, formalised and converted into a fully attributed process definition, *Koch (2017)*.

5. Data model

An important element of integration is mutual agreement on the foundation data entities (“business objects”) to be communicated between participating software components. Working with a common data model appears as an attractive and elegant solution. However, based on experiences from precursory projects some consideration must be given to the following issues:

- Beware of the reinvention of the wheel: there are many existing data standards and de-facto standards out there. Many engineering and commercial aspects have been covered, but probably not all and not always at the required level of granularity (either too detailed or too coarse).
- But is a monolithic approach a realistic solution? It would seem an overwhelming task to derive a fully integrated model from this. For this reason, the project consortium has taken a close look at e.g. the BIM approach, *Lu and Li (2011)*, which among other aspects is an example of a business domain oriented amalgamation of various contributing standards and rules.
- Project development dynamics are another critical success factor: as several work packages and tasks are advancing concurrently within the project, an intense level of modifications and corrections has to be expected also on the data model side, thus dependencies on progress of other tasks must be mitigated.

A conclusion derived from these requirements and considerations is the need for self-explanatory, machine readable data model definitions that may evolve over time. It means that an implementation should not only provide the classical information management functions for storing, retrieving or locating instances of data entities, but should also provide meta data about the underlying model definitions. This is a well-known concept found in various advanced programming environments as well as in some data management systems with different levels of functionality. In practice the effort to utilise this information tends to be quite high due to the proprietary nature of such systems. Fig.5 shows how the different layers of data definition and data management are linked.

Fig.5: Data management layers

6. SHIPLYS Framework

Due to the diversity of tools involved in the design process, it is obvious that the shipyard needs described above cannot be met by a monolithic piece of software. Instead an open framework of loosely coupled components is provided to ensure:

- registration of different software tools
- well-defined and secure communication between tools
- concurrent working on the same project
- process monitoring

The SHIPLYS framework shown in Fig.6 fulfils all these requirements using internet for the communication. It comprises two general types of communicating parties: clients representing software components which are requesting information from or triggering execution of tasks by services and services representing software components which are servicing requests of clients to deliver information or to execute a task accordingly.

The service types defined for the SHIPLYS framework are:

- **Meta Service**
This service operates as a kind of dictionary for both data and process models. It provides data models applicable to projects and organizational information managed by data services. It also provides the process model definitions that can be utilized to perform process monitoring, dependency analysis and progress assessment.
- **Data Service**
These services provide the ability to store and load data for projects, represented in compliance with the data model(s) provided by the Meta Services. Along with the storage functions, data state information is also maintained.
- **Software Registry**
The Software Registry holds the references to all software tools which can be registered to define the tool chain. Clients interact with the Software Registry to review the list of known software components, to select a suitable tool for a task at hand and to find Job Services (see below) that can execute specific software tools.
- **Job Service**
Within the framework, many job service end points can be active. A Job Service is a service that waits for an authorized request from a client to perform one or more activities (defined in the process model) using a specific instance of a registered software tool. Such a request will result in the Job Service starting a client that connects the software instance with the framework, requesting necessary data, performing the activity and storing results (by interacting with Data Service(s) to store the results).
- **Authorization Service**
The Authorization Service provides the fundamental security functions. It manages the association of rights granted to identities and operating permissions applicable to service end points and processes requests for registration of services and authorization requests from clients.
- **Certificate Agency (CA)**
This is an optional feature: since the framework is intended to be operating over the network, a secure authentication mechanism must be established. Generally, a Certificate Agency provides digital certificates that facilitate the use of asymmetric encryption between end points (clients and services) and provide unique identification /authentication of any certified end point. While it is perfectly possible to manage such certificates by utilizing commercial services for this purpose, the provision of a local CA along with the framework components helps to avoid bureaucratic overhead and cost and simplifies operation.
The fundamental function of the CA service is to take certification requests and to return

certificates. It can also be used to perform Certificate revocation in case a previously issued certificate needs to be invalidated. As part of its operation it will also maintain a registry of all certificates issued.

Fig.6: Services of the SHIPLYS framework

The core technology applied in the implementation of the SHIPLYS framework is defined as the Representational State Transfer (REST) over HTTP, *Fielding (2000)*, which provides a high degree of platform independence, since only network communication standards apply.

JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), *JSON (2017)*, has been adopted as the payload data format for representing the request and response content. This is not mandatory and can be complemented by other types of payload as required.

Security features are essential in order to ensure secure network-based data transfer to prevent unauthorized access to the project data and use of services. The two main functions provided by the security related components are authentication and authorization which have been realized within the SHIPLYS Framework.

- Authentication provides support to answer to the question “Who is the user?”, i.e. to certify the identity of an acting entity (e.g. a user running a client or a service acting autonomously or on behalf of a user). In order to protect confidential information that is passed over the wire, a mechanism is required identifying the acting entity and supporting message signatures. Such a mechanism is provided by the Transport Layer Security protocol TLS, *RFC (2008)*, which – when combined with the Hypertext Transfer Protocol HTTP, *RFC (2014)* – results in Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure HTTPS. In order to provide the highest possible security level and to prevent that random clients get access to the framework end-points, the mutual authentication is used after a client has been successfully registered.
- Authorization provides the functionality to answer the question “Is a certain identity authorized to perform a certain operation on certain protected resource belonging to a specific service?” For networked services, the dominant security method today is OAuth 2.0 *RFC (2012)*, an industry-standard protocol for authorization and therefore has been used within the SHIPLYS framework. Depending on the specific case the OAuth 2.0 describes several main approaches, called grant types, how to protect the resource server. For the framework the grant type “Assertion” has been selected as the most suitable and well combinable with the chosen authentication mechanism as both of these mechanisms use

certified documents. Using the Assertion grant type a client provides a certificate issued by the certificate agency to the authorization service. After a successful verification of the certificate the authorization service generates an appropriate access token containing access rights and provides it back to the client. Finally, the client provides the access token to the protected resource and after a successful token verification it gets access to the API.

7. Prototyping

For prototyping purposes, a demo environment has been established as a proof-of-concept, Fig.7. This is based on a demonstration scenario that starts with a tender document for a multi-purpose carrier. The design process is initiated by using a tool for requirements identification and evaluation. After formalizing requirements, the design is continued by defining further basic parameters a conceptual design tool, which generates as one result the hull definition. This hull form is processed by RSET, *Depetro and Hoey (2013)*, a compartmentation definition and optimization tool. Hull form and compartments are then used to define the main frame section and other structural elements, to estimate weights and to perform basic strength calculations in the ship design software CAFÉ, *Bralic et al. (2011)*. All of this information is finally used in SEASAFE to calculate hydrostatics, http://www.seasafesoftware.com/webpage/htm/about_seasafe_package.htm. The complete process can easily be performed in one day.

Fig.7: Prototype scope

8. Conclusions and Outlook

The framework development has shown to be an interesting approach to make use of technologies evolving from the next generation of distributed systems. At the same time, these information technology-oriented mechanisms have been applied in a very concrete application-oriented context for early ship design methodology. This results in some interesting features and capabilities:

- Definition and maintenance of a tool set (or tool chain) becomes fully transparent and manageable, that making the working environment fully configurable,
- Access to tools is provided in a consistent way,
- Due to the distributed nature of the framework, the working environment is scalable. For example, computational intensive applications can be provisioned on computing nodes. Depending on the actual needs this can be realised either on moderately sized local CPU resources or by remote facilities.

With the framework being operational, next steps will be for example: to create a design process monitoring tool that is capable of documenting the progress of early ship design using the underlying process model, to integrate a wider selection of tools and to realise additional application scenarios (which have already been prepared in the project) – including a retrofitting case.

Future development could also put additional focus on the possible improvements with regard to communication among additional partners such as suppliers or subcontractors cooperating in a design project.

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References

- AES (2018), Topgallant Information Server, <http://www.atlantec-es.com/topgallant-product-is.html>
- AFWAL (1981), *ICAM Architecture Part II-Volume IV - Function Modeling Manual (IDEF0)*, AFWAL-TR-81-4023, Materials Laboratory, Air Force Wright Aeronautical Laboratories, Air Force Systems Command, Wright-Patterson Air Force Base
- BHARADWADJ, U. (2017), *Ship Lifecycle Software Solutions (SHIPLYS) – an overview of the first phase of development and challenges addressed*, Annual Conf. Int. Maritime Association of the Mediterranean (IMAM), Lisbon
- BRALIĆ, S.; FRANK, D.; KLANAC, A.; CACE, B. (2011), *CAFE: An innovative multi-user system for rapid generation of ship concepts*, COMPIT Conf., Berlin
- BRANDES, U.; EIGLSPERGER, M.; HERMAN, I.; HIMSOLT, M.; MARSHALL, M.S. (2002), *GraphML Progress Report: Structural Layer Proposal*, 9th Int. Symp. Graph Drawing (GD '01), LNCS 2265, pp.501-512
- DEPETRO, A.; HOEY, R. (2013), *Rapid generation and optimisation of ship compartment configuration based on life cycle cost and operational effectiveness*, https://www.bmtdesign.com.au/media/4752073/optimisation_of_ship_compartment_configuration.pdf
- FIELDING, R. T. (2000), *Architectural Styles and the Design of Network-based Software Architectures*, PhD thesis, Univ. of California, www.ics.uci.edu/~fielding/pubs/dissertation/fielding_dissertation_2up.pdf
- IDEF (2018), *IDEF0 Function Modelling method – Strengths and Weaknesses*, Knowledge Based Systems, http://www.idef.com/idefo-function_modeling_method/
- ISO (1994), *ISO 10303-1: Industrial automation systems and integration - Product data representation and exchange - Part 1: Overview and fundamental principles*, ISO, Geneva
- ISO (2001), *ISO 10303-214: Industrial automation systems and integration - Product data representation and exchange - Part 214: Core data for automotive mechanical design processes*, ISO, Geneva
- ISO (2011), *ISO 10303-203: Industrial automation systems and integration - Product data representation and exchange - Part 203: Configuration controlled 3D design of mechanical parts and assemblies*, ISO, Geneva

ISO (2003), *ISO 10303-216: Industrial automation systems and integration - Product data representation and exchange - Part 216: Application protocol: Ship Moulded Forms*, ISO, Geneva

ISO (2004), *ISO 10303-215: Industrial automation systems and integration - Product data representation and exchange - Part 215: Application protocol: Ship Arrangement*, ISO, Geneva

ISO (2004a), *ISO 10303-218: Industrial automation systems and integration - Product data representation and exchange - Part 218: Application protocol: Ship Structures*, ISO, Geneva

ISO (2005), *ISO 10303-227: Industrial automation systems and integration - Product data representation and exchange - Part 227: Application protocol: Plant spatial configuration*, ISO, Geneva

ISO (2013), *ISO 16739: Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) for data sharing in the construction and facility management industries*, ISO, Geneva

JSON (2017), *ECMA-404 JSON Data Interchange Format*, ECMA Int. <https://www.ecma-international.org/publications/files/ECMA-ST/ECMA-404.pdf>

KOCH, T.; KREUTZER, K. (2017), *Refactoring early ship design methodologies*, IMAM 2017, Lisbon

KOCH, T.; RANDALL, G.; HOEY, R. (2017a), *Existing prototyping models and approaches in shipping and other industry sectors*, <http://www.shiplys.com/library/deliverables/d31-existing-prototyping-models-and-approaches-in-shipping-and-other-industry-sectors>

KOCH, T.; RANDALL, G.; HOEY, R. (2017b), *Requirements for the Integration of SHIPLYS tools and compatibility with existing tools*, <http://www.shiplys.com/library/deliverables/d33-requirements-for-the-integration-of-shiplys-tools-and-compatibility-with-existing-tools/>

LU, W.W.S.; LI, H. (2011), *Building information modeling and changing construction practices*, *Automation in Construction* 20/2, pp.99-100

RFC (2008), *RFC 5246, The Transport Layer Security (TLS) Protocol Version 1.2*, <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc5246>

RFC (2012), *RFC 6749, The OAuth 2.0 Authorization Framework*, <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc6749>

RFC (2014), *RFC 7230-7237, Hypertext Transfer Protocol HTTP/1.1*, <https://www.w3.org/Protocols/rfc2616/rfc2616.html>

S1000D (2016), *International specification for technical publications using a common source database*, Issue No. 4.2, <http://public.s1000d.org/Downloads/Pages/S1000D/Downloads.aspx>

Leveraging Big Data for Fuel Oil Consumption Modelling

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Abstract

Fuel oil consumption constitutes over 25% of a vessel's overall running costs. Therefore, accurately forecasting, and optimising fuel costs majorly impacts a vessel's operation sustainability and profitability. This paper presents data-driven, multivariate main engine fuel consumption models leveraging the vast amount of data currently being recorded onboard vessels. Different data-driven modelling methodologies, such as shallow neural networks, deep neural networks, support vector machines, and random forest regressors are presented and implemented, comparing results. The suggested multivariate modelling allows the uncovering of latent interconnections that increase the robustness of the model in varied operating conditions.

1. Introduction

Efficient operations of vessels are desired from various maritime industry stakeholders such as ship operators, Classification Societies, consultancy companies, maritime regulators, and policy makers. Efficient operations lead to both decrease of Green House Gases (GHGs) and operating cost reduction. This desire can be justified by financial reasons, such as reduced fuel consumption and decreased maintenance costs. Ronen (2011) notes that when bunker fuel price is at around 500 USD per ton, fuel costs correspond to approximately 75% of the total operating cost of a large containership. Accordingly, Stopford (2009) notes that fuel oil consumption constitutes approximately two-thirds of a vessel's voyage costs and over one-quarter of a vessel's overall running costs. For this reason, shipping companies are lately focusing on implementing fuel efficiency measures. In order to monitor fuel efficiency and eventually offer a formalized optimization approach to fuel consumption, a suitable modelling framework that can take into account relevant variables (measurements) and their correlation is required.

The purpose of this study is to develop a fuel consumption model that utilizes data obtained from the noon-reports that are transmitted daily back to shore. Compared to other approaches where modelling is performed using the data acquired through specialized sensors, implementation of this approach has an infinitesimal cost as no additional hardware is required. Through that, scaling this methodology from vessel- to fleet-level becomes a triviality. Additionally, unlike methods that utilize data from sea- and shop-trials for modelling, this method provides the flexibility of permitting only the utilization of data corresponding to a specific period and/or vessel's operational profile for modelling.

2. Background

This section provides an overview of scientific literature, pertinent to this paper. First, methodologies relevant to fuel efficiency and fuel consumption modelling are included. Besides, a synopsis of data-driven techniques pertinent to the modelling requirements of this paper are presented.

Bialystocki and Konovessis (2016) performed a statistical analysis of noon reports of a Ro-Ro vessel to identify the influence of factors such as ship's draft, displacement, weather force and direction, and hull and propeller roughness. Once several corrections suggested are applied to obtained data along with relevant filtering, curves for each frequently-observed sea state are fitted. This provides a simple algorithm that approximates fuel consumption. Lu et al. (2015) developed a semi-empirical method for the prediction of operational performance of ships. This method is based on modelling still water and added resistance components. Through that, the ship's operational performance is modelled, taking into consideration weather and sea state. This model is then utilised to optimise the ship's voyage route.

Beşikçi et al. (2016) suggested the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) for the prediction of ship fuel consumption at various operational conditions. Additionally, a Decision Support System (DSS) is elaborated for real-time, energy efficient operations. The suggested methodology is compared against Multiple Regression (MR) analysis, displaying superior results. *Meng et al. (2016)* suggest a data pre-processing methodology based on outlier-score-based data. Following that, two regression models are developed in order to link available data to fuel consumption. The first model connects the ship's fuel consumption with its speed and displacement. The second model builds on the first, utilising the information provided by the first while also including weather conditions. They validated the work performed utilising noon-report data from 13000-TEU containerships.

Cichowicz et al. (2015) provide a methodology for first-principles, time-domain modelling of main and auxiliary engines for assessment of life-cycle ship performance and energy efficiency. Speed and draught are taken into consideration, along with hull fouling and deterioration of engine performance. Sea state is included implicitly by considering an additional ME load. The methodology was demonstrated using data from 3700-TEU containership. *Coraddu et al. (2017)* performed a comparison of white, grey, and black box models for the estimation of fuel consumption, concluding that grey-box models can effectively forecast fuel consumption when only limited historical data are available.

Trodden et al. (2015) focuses on data pre-processing and suggests a methodology, ancillary to the ones elaborated above, for splitting available ship data into steady-state chunks that can then be used for fuel efficiency monitoring.

From the above, modelling of vessels' fuel oil consumption is an active research field with multiple different approaches being realised concurrently. Up to now, modelling attempts seem to be focused either on the evaluation of noon-report data using first-principles modelling or a priori knowledge, or on a noon-report dataset or the use of high-frequency data along with a machine-learning approach. This paper aims to examine how noon-report data can be combined with different machine learning approaches and whether acceptable results can be achieved through that.

3. Methodology

The methodology elaborated in this section concerns a) the description of a suitable pre-processing technique for the acquired dataset; b) the derivation of multiple models following different modelling methodologies; c) the optimisation of the hyperparameters of these models; and d) the comparison of those models so that modelling techniques that offer the best performance are identified. Fig.1 shows the suggested methodology with all suggested modules and their relevant interconnections.

Fig.1: Suggested methodology

3.1 Data pre-processing

A cursory data cleansing is performed on the dataset by detecting and removing inaccurate records. This is performed by filtering for range constraints depending on the type of the attribute. Additionally, based on previous knowledge of the field, recorded attributes are transformed into attributes that can better convey the information contained. For example, while an original dataset may contain aft and fore drafts, those are transformed into draft amidships and trim, two measurements that can more

accurately be used as predictors for the FO consumption of the vessel.

All numerical attributes in the dataset are standardized by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance. Therefore, for a numerical attribute x , a standardised attribute x' is produced by

$$x' = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}$$

where μ is the mean value of all values belonging to that attribute and σ its standard deviation. All attributes are standardised so that all attributes can contribute equally to the objective function that is used for model training.

3.2 Modelling methodologies

All modelling methodologies presented below are methodologies relating to regression analysis. Regression analysis is a set of statistical processes that aims to derive a relationship between several dependent variables (predictors) and an independent (target) variable.

Regression models can be derived with a varying level of complexity and consequently accuracy of results. Therefore, possible methods span a wide range of options, from closed-form linear models to deep (i.e. multi-layered) neural networks.

Different modelling approaches can be split into parametric and non-parametric. Parametric models assume some finite set of parameters θ . Given these parameters, any future prediction, x , are independent of the observed dataset D so that:

$$P(x|\theta, D) = P(x|\theta)$$

In other words, θ is assumed to capture all variance contained in the dataset D .

Therefore, even if the complexity of a dataset is unbounded (potentially infinite), the complexity of the model is bounded. Linear models such as linear regression and Support Vector Regressors (SVRs) with a linear kernel are parametric models.

In contrast to that, non-parametric models assume that the dataset distribution cannot be defined using any finite number of parameters. Therefore, the amount of information that θ can capture grows with the number of training data points in dataset D . Decision tree regressors, random forest regressors and SVRs with a Radial Basis Function (RBF, a non-linear kernel used in support vector machines to allow the learning of non-linear mappings) kernel are considered non-parametric as the number of parameters grows with the size D .

Finding the optimal model-derivation methodology is non-trivial as this is affected, among others, by the quantity and quality of available data, and the nature (also complexity) of the problem at hand.

3.2.1 Decision tree regressors

Decision tree regressors are a non-parametric, supervised regression method. Decision tree regressor models learn simple decision rules inferred from the dataset features and predict the value of the target variable through those, *Hastie et al. (2009)*.

Decision tree regressors do not produce a continuous output in the traditional sense. Instead, these models are trained on a training set whose outputs lie on a continuous range. Their output ends up being the mean value of the training set observations that reside in the same node.

3.2.2 Random forest regressors

Random forests are based on the bagging (bootstrap aggregating) meta-algorithm, a technique that aims to reduce the variance of an estimated prediction function, *Hastie et al. (2009)*. In the case of random forest regressors, a number of de-correlated decision tree regressors are produced based on the available training set. Then, the output of the random forest regressor is calculated by averaging the results of individual decision trees.

3.2.3 Support vector machines

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) in their simplest form constitute a two-class classifier in cases where the two classes are linearly separable. SVMs work by deriving the optimal hyperplane, i.e. the hyperplane that offers the widest possible margin between instances of the two classes. (In geometry, a hyperplane is a subspace whose dimension is one less than that of its ambient space. For example, in the case of observations with two attributes (therefore positioned in a 2D space), their separating plane will be one-dimensional, i.e. a line.) Their functionality can be extended by the introduction of a non-linear kernel, allowing them to learn non-linear mappings, i.e., classify between non-linearly separable classes, *Theodoridis (2008)*.

SVMs can also be built as regressors, *Smola et al. (2004)*. Support Vector Regressors (SVRs) work in a similar way, this time trying to fit a hyperplane that accurately predicts the target values of training samples within a margin of tolerance ϵ .

3.2.4 Shallow & deep neural networks

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are computing systems, inspired by the way biological nervous systems work. Various ANN architectures exist, offering superior performance at many machine learning tasks, including classification and regression. ANNs are extremely versatile as they can accurately model complex non-linear behaviours.

ANNs are based on an interconnected group of connected units (neurons) where each connection between these units can transmit a signal from one to another. The receiving unit can process that signal and then pass it on to the next unit.

Two important parameters of ANNs are the number of hidden (between input and output) layers and the number of units per layer. Excluding the input and output layers that always exist, different architectures call for different number of hidden layers and units. Accordingly, different activation functions can be implemented, altering the complexity learnable by the model.

Consequently, depending on the number of layers implemented, ANNs can be classified as shallow and deep. While no formal rule exists to separate shallow and deep neural networks, *Schmidhuber (2015)*, usually networks that have more than 1 hidden layer are considered deep. As the number of layers increases, the model can “learn” more non-linear behaviours. At the same time, training becomes more computationally expensive and the risk of overfitting the dataset also increases.

3.3 Model hyperparameter optimisation

A number of model hyperparameters can be altered to affect the model performance. (The term hyperparameter refers to model parameters that are set before model training begins, e.g. parameters that affect model architecture or the number of training iterations.) As the optimal hyperparameter values cannot be known a priori, an optimisation routine is employed to identify the best hyperparameter values for each model. An unsophisticated method to do so would be building a grid containing all possible combinations of selected hyperparameters and exhaustively evaluating each to select the best combination. However, this carries a significant cost due to the sheer number of combinations that are

evaluated (especially in the case of multiple tuneable hyperparameters per model). Another approach is to employ a random search implementation. There all hyperparameter ranges are randomly sampled, usually producing more accurate results given a predefined number of draws, *Bergstra and Bengio (2012)*.

3.4 Selection of best model

In order to reasonably ensure that selected hyperparameter values are actually close to optimal and not merely overfitting the model, a k -fold technique is implemented. There, the training dataset is split into k subsets and an iterative process runs k times, using $k - 1$ subsets for training and the remaining one for testing. Therefore, for each hyperparameter combination several results are obtained and averaged. Using the same technique for all models, allows us to identify the model that performs best while at the same time ensuring good generalisation capabilities.

4. Application description, results, and discussion

In this section, a case study utilising noon-report data from a reefer vessel is included. 834 data points were available, corresponding to approximately 2.5 years of noon-report data. An overview of the available attributes can be seen below in Table I.

Table I: Noon-report measurements used for model training

#	Name	Units	#	Name	Units
1	Speed (noon)	Knots	8	Sea state	(1-12)
2	Engine speed	RPM	9	Sea direction	degrees, summed in 12 bins
3	Sea current (relative to vessel)	knots	10	Slip	%
4	Wind force	(1-12)	11	Draft fwd	m
5	Wind direction	degrees, summed in 12 bins	12	Draft aft	m
6	Daily M/E FOC	tn	13	Daily steam hours	hr
7	Daily distance run	nm			

These data were pre-processed to keep only points where all required attributes were available and where the following conditions were met:

- Daily steam hours > 10
- Daily M/E FOC > 5 tn
- Speed (noon) > 8 nm
- Engine speed > 20 RPM

These values were selected to only take into account data points that correspond to relatively steady state conditions, without significant transient instances, e.g. manoeuvring. Following this pre-processing, 512 data points were kept. A histogram of the selected attributes is shown in Fig.2. Additionally, Daily M/E FOC and Daily distance run were combined into a single “FOC per distance run” attribute, in order to more accurately represent model target. Then, 20% of the data were kept aside for model validation, leaving the rest for model training. As a brief investigation of the available training dataset, a correlation matrix was obtained, focusing on how “FOC per distance run” correlates with other attributes, shown in Table II.

Data were scaled following the technique discussed in Section 3. Following that, models discussed in Section 3 were trained. Each model was then trained using the hyperparameters that Scikit-learn, *Pedregosa et al. (2011)*, considers default. Additionally, random search over hyperparameters pertinent to each model was performed to identify optimal values. In order to identify optimal models and hyperparameters, the coefficient of determination (R^2) (see *Glantz et al. (1990)*) was evaluated for each

model produced at each fold. The Neural Network model utilizing default hyperparameters is not included as the relevant model failed to converge.

Fig.2: Histogram plots of attributes used for model input after pre-processing

Table II: Correlation of “FOC per distance run” to other attributes

Attribute	Correlation
Engine speed	0.777729
Sea State	0.491557
Slip	0.470700
Wind force	0.429272
Speed (noon)	0.398368
Draft aft	0.129491
Draft fwd	-0.012756
Sea direction	-0.053529
Wind direction	-0.079869
Sea current	-0.279159

An overview of obtained results is presented in the box plots of Fig.3 shown below. The value inside each box corresponds to the median (second quartile) score of this model in k -folding, the top and bottom of the box respectively correspond to the first and third quartiles. The whiskers represent the lowest point of data within 1.5 Interquartile Range (IQR) of the lowest quartile and the highest point of data within 1.5 IQR of the upper quartile. Accordingly, the mean of the dataset is noted by a triangle. Data points beyond the whisker range as shown individually as small circles. A logit y-axis is used to emphasize model performance in the range of 85-95%, i.e. the most interesting range as all candidate models are performing around that range.

Fig.3 shows how the default hyperparameters included in Scikit-learn are reasonably effective, as in most cases only a miniscule gain in accuracy was obtained after the hyperparameter optimization loop. Additionally, most modelling attempts delivered overall good results, with a mean/median accuracy of over 80%. While random search improved the results of decision trees, the results overall were inferior to those obtained by random forests.

Fig.3: Box plot of R^2 score obtained from different models and hyperparameters in k -folding

Moreover, neural networks performed rather poorly in this case study. As noted above, default hyperparameters yielded a model that failed to converge. While models with hyperparameters obtained through random search fared better, results were still significantly worse off than those obtained through other modelling techniques. An additional key remark is how increasing the depth of the neural network did not provide better results and, in fact, delivered worse mean accuracy in all attempted cases.

The best accuracy was obtained by random forests and RBF-based SVMs, both after optimizing their hyperparameters. Comparing the two models, the SVM model yielded higher mean/median scores. However, it should be noted that the random forest model yielded a lower spread between different folds (i.e. less elongated box and whiskers).

Having selected the model that performed best in k -folding, the same parameters are now tested in the dataset held aside for validation. There, a score of $R^2=0.8230$, corresponding to an accuracy of 82.3% was obtained, ensuring that the model developed generalizes well.

5. Conclusions

This paper presented a data-driven methodology of estimating main engine fuel oil consumption of sailing vessels through the use of noon-report data. An overview of the current state of research in this field was provided, followed by a compact description of the main idea behind multiple regression modelling approaches.

The case study included showed, step-by-step, the approach adopted for model pre-processing, training and selection of optimal model. The efficiency of most modelling approaches was observed, especially the accuracy of support vector machines and random forests. These models, while on their own do not have much practical use, can be used as a basis in a wide variety of applications, from weather routing, to optimising performance, to estimating more specific fuel consumption values, making vessels more attractive to potential charterers.

To conclude, future research includes examination of this problem in the existence of denser datasets and whether that alters the model ranking described above. Furthermore, additional modelling techniques can also be examined.

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References

BERGSTRA, J.; BENGIO, Y. (2012), *Random search for hyper-parameter optimization*, J. Machine Learning Research 13, pp.281-305

BEŞİKÇİ, E.B.; ARSLAN, O.; TURAN, O.; ÖLÇER, A.I. (2016), *An artificial neural network based decision support system for energy efficient ship operations*, Computers & Operations Research 66, pp.393-401

BIALYSTOCKI, V.; KONOVESSIS, D. (2016), *On the estimation of ship's fuel consumption and speed curve: A statistical approach*, J. Ocean Engineering and Science 1/2, pp.157-166

CICHOWICZ, J.; THEOTOKATOS, G.; VASSALOS, D. (2015), *Dynamic energy modelling for ship life-cycle performance assessment*, Ocean Engineering 110/B, pp. 49-61

CORADDU, A.; ONETO, L.; BALDI, F.; ANGUIA, D. (2017), *Vessels fuel consumption forecast and trim optimisation: a data analytics perspective*, Ocean Engineering 130, pp. 351-370

GLANTZ, S.A.; SLINKER B.K. (1990), *Primer of Applied Regression and Analysis of Variance*, McGraw-Hill

HASTIE, T.; TIBSHIRANI, R.; FRIEDMAN, J. (2009), *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*, Springer

LU, R.; TURAN, O.; BOULOUGOURIS, E.; BANKS, C.; INCECIK, A. (2015), *A semi-empirical ship operational performance prediction model for voyage optimization towards energy efficient shipping*, Ocean Engineering 110/B, pp.18-28

MENG, Q.; DU, Y.; WANG, Y. (2016), *Shipping log data based container ship fuel efficiency modeling*, Transportation Research Part B: Methodological 83, pp.207-229

PEDREGOSA, F.; VAROQUAUX, G.; GRAMFORT, A.; MICHEL, V.; THIRION, B.; GRISEL, O.; BLONDEL, M.; PRETTENHOFER, P.; WEISS, R.; DUBOURG, V.; VANDERPLAS, J.; PASSOS, A.; COURNAPEAU, D.; BRUCHER, M.; PERROT, M.; DUCHESNAY, E. (2011), *Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python*, J. Machine Learning Research, 12, pp.2825-2830

RONEN, D. (2011), *The effect of oil price on containership speed; fleet size*, J. Operational Research Society 62/1, pp.211-216

SCHMIDHUBER, J. (2015), *Deep Learning in Neural Networks: An Overview*, Neural Networks 61, pp. 85-117

SMOLA, A.J.; SCHOLKOPF, B. (2004), *A tutorial on support vector regression*, Statistics computing,

14/3, pp.199-222

STOPFORD, M. (2009), *Maritime Economics*, Routledge

THEODORIDIS, S. (2008), *Pattern Recognition*, Elsevier

TRODDEN, D. G.; MURPHY, A. J.; PAZOUKI, K.; SARGEANT, J. (2015), *Fuel usage data analysis for efficient shipping operations*, *Ocean Engineering* 110, pp.75-84

Technology Mega Trends That Will Change Shipbuilding

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Abstract

A research project under the Japan Ship Technology Research Association (JSTRA) surveyed innovative technologies from various sectors and countries. The results are described. We extract important technology fields and discuss how they can change shipbuilding technology and maritime industry.

1. Introduction

We investigated new technologies adopted in other industries and advanced technology implementations in a maritime industry worldwide, and discussed future ship technologies 30 years from now by considering the applicability of these technologies to the maritime industry. In our project, we surveyed literature and interviewed relevant parties (universities, research institutions, manufacturers, etc.) to extract technologies that could be applied to ships in the future. We then analysed individual technologies from the viewpoint of feasibility/maturity and magnitude of impact. This led to a technology roadmap to organize short-term and medium-term R&D projects. We extracted noteworthy technologies (6 fields, total 116 cases) for future ships and analysed them. Finally, we conceived a future ship concept based on assorted innovative technologies in this project.

This paper describes important technology fields found in the project. In particular, the paper summarizes essential meanings for these technologies and how they can change shipbuilding technology and maritime industry in the future.

2. Technical problems of shipbuilding

Why does shipbuilding not progress in automation or digitization as in an automobile industry and a consumer electronics industry? Technical factors are summarized as follows:

- **Large and heavy objects in shipbuilding**
A ship is large and parts handled there are often much larger than humans. It is difficult to efficiently control such large and heavy objects, and it takes much energy and cost to move and rotate them. Also, because a ship is a huge structure, it exceeds the range of human recognition ability. In shipbuilding, workers gather in relatively large structures for their work. In addition to not being able to overlook the entire image of a large object, it is also difficult to grasp all activities of the many scattered workers.
- **Work based on human recognition**
Ship production is not repetitive production of a same thing; in most cases, it is one-of-a-kind. Precise handling and control of a gigantic structure itself is difficult, and the thing to be made also changes each time. Therefore, the manufacturing process is not standardized and depends on human recognition and judgment, which makes shipbuilding a human-centric task. The shipbuilding work involves human intervention, but there are many tasks even child could do. Mechanization and automation even for these tasks have not advanced much.

These factors explain why modernization in shipbuilding has lagged behind other industries. But now new technologies allow overcoming the traditional obstacles. The fundamental architecture of shipbuilding has not changed from that of old days: A lot of people gathering, collecting materials, cutting, forming and assembling based on paper drawings. However, this scenario may change in the future. Important technical factors are information technology, robotics, material technology and so on.

3. Technology mega trend in shipbuilding

We extracted six key technology areas that can give solutions to classical problems in shipbuilding (and its automation). In this chapter, we will explain why these technologies can solve problems of shipbuilding, and how these technologies change shipbuilding.

3.1. IoT technology

- Always connected world, Data driven society
By ultra-downsizing computers (nanotip), sensorization of human and machines in the IoT (Internet of Things), using next-generation communication standard "5G" for fast data transfer in the IoT, employing ultra-high resolution camera and advancing interface technology such as VR/AR (Virtual reality/Augmented Reality), computers will be embedded everywhere around us in the near future. While we may not be aware of them at all, the transparency of computers progresses. This means the fusion of real world (Physical System) and cyber space (Cyber System). Linking information from sensor networks with a powerful computing capability of cyber space (simulation and data assimilation), we will move towards becoming a more efficient society. The amount of information also increases enormously. Access to information becomes easy; we will have almost any information and data at the tips of our fingers. We will analyze large amounts of data in an instant and discover new things that way. It will be nothing special to judge something based on the complete amount of data around it. Ultimately, more accurate decision making will result from our data driven society.
- Real value of real data
The essence to utilize real data is an arrival of an ultimate customized society. If it is natural to take individual data from everyone and everything, optimize products and processes individually for a person or a thing. In the case of a ship, customized design and operation will be become standard for all ships. NYK and Japan Marine United Corporation (JMU) designed a new propeller that can reduce fuel consumption by 1.2% by analyzing the actual operating condition of the propeller under sailing, Fig.1. This case is just the beginning of a larger trend: From now on, it will be common to customize even niche products individually.

Fig.1: Observation of an actual ship's propeller with a small camera (Source: NIKKEI)

In the ultimate customized society, not only is optimization and efficiency improvement of society promoted, but also personalities and unique features can be addressed easily and

explicitly. This leads to diversification, flattening and democratization of our society. A company's size or dynamics of scale are no longer an issue. Those who provide better customization will win. Targets of customization cannot be limited to design and construction of ships. Shipyards will be expected to expand customization service, e.g. post-delivery maintenance service of a ship, optimum operation support service, optimum repair and improvement work service per every voyage, etc. Ships will be customized and updated frequently, not only during construction or 5-year drydocking intervals.

- **Changes in thinking on safety**
There may be major changes in philosophy on ship safety, design philosophy and inspection philosophy of a vessel that is constantly being updated. In ship design, thoughts on safety factors and preliminaries will be fundamentally changed. In ship inspection, the idea of fixed inspection intervals will change (an inspection system will also be customized for individual ships).
- **Construction traceability**
In a shipbuilding factory, where sensors, wearable terminals or monitoring system are widespread, it is possible to record all activities of construction, which allows accurate tracing of construction. It also means that we can quantify capabilities of shipbuilding sites and shipbuilding skills, leading to performance and competitiveness monitoring of shipyards or even workshops.
- **Connected and visualized information**
Connecting and visualizing information is not merely making information visible. The essence of visualization is to clarify the information and make it (widely) accessible. Once information gets on a computer, it leads to a network. Information on shipyards is not only clearly visualized, but the information transcends the shipyard and spreads around to all relevant stakeholders. In essence, this will remove physical limitations and constraints. If information is released from constraints of physical space, everyone can access and share that information. Not only staff or direct stakeholders of a shipyard can access the information, but in principle anyone. Information is open, and everyone will be involved in the maritime industry. Ship development in the future will be carried out jointly with various people on open platforms on the cloud. There are no place restrictions there. Equal opportunities are given to everyone, and everyone will be able to do what they like and what they do best. Individuals are respected. That will be the natural way of living and working in the future. The concept of "people working at a shipyard" may disappear.
- **Generalization of shipbuilding**
Remixes with other information also will occur. The classification "shipbuilding information" makes no sense. Information in a shipyard is hyperlinked with all other information on a cloud. A method common to other industries, such as car and aircraft industry, will be used on a common platform (Generalization and commonality of shipbuilding). The function of the product also fuses, and the classification of product itself disappears. The classification of ships, airplanes, cars and trains may melt, and we will see a commonization progress. Ships, airplanes, cars, buildings etc. with a same brand and mutual compatibility may evolve.

3.2. Deep learning and robotics

Shipbuilding is a typical manufacturing that requires human's perception. If this recognition can be transferred to machines, this will lead to a shipbuilding revolution. The essence of application of deep learning technology for shipbuilding is to equip machines with eyes (machine vision) and separate miscellaneous "recognition" skills from human.

- Introduction of machines with eyes
For shipbuilding, assorted R&D has been done on applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) (expert systems, case-based reasoning, etc.). However, it has been proven difficult to express the enormous "recognition" existing in shipbuilding on explicit knowledge. Meanwhile, deep learning has enabled machines to abstract from the real world by seeing important elements. With deep learning, it became possible to express human recognition and exercise skills. Until now, recognition and exercise that even child can do was difficult for computers, but this will finally be possible (Moravec's paradox, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Moravec%27s_paradox).
- Development of cognitive machine
In the future, much of the recognition tasks in shipbuilding work can be transferred to Artificial Intelligence. (Ship operation itself is also transferred to machines as autonomous ships). As a result, many shipbuilding operations are automated and robotized. In the future, welding work will advance further in automation. Optimum welding conditions and operations will be judged using machine vision after looking at welding spots. Many assembly processes will be also automated. Assorted tasks requiring recognition and judgment will be transferred to machine, e.g. welding, painting, transportation, material handling, palletting, tool preparation, bending, strain relief, crane and so on.
- Digital shipyard
Deep learning will revolutionize production management in shipbuilding. Activities of workers and motions of blocks are recognized all the time by their real data and deep learning. We can see everything individually; so we can track and follow up individually. We will be able to quantify, digitize, and mechanize work even for human-centric labor-intensive industries like mass production, line-up manufacturing industries. Specifically, in order to realize the digital shipyard, which we define as "production plan based on numerical value, production management based on numerical value", we are now engaged in R&D on formulation of standard time and work procedure for individual work in shipbuilding. Artificial Intelligence also recognizes veteran skills and transcends beyond it. In design tasks as well, many routine work moves to machines. Designers will focus on creativity and advanced engineering skills.
- Direction of R&D of robotics in shipbuilding
Robots with "eyes" by deep learning become important for future robot development. For example, there may be a robot that automatically collects tools necessary for a work, a drone to periodically observe positions and conditions of blocks, and an inspection robot.

Fig.2: "Smart construction" by KOMATSU; Periodically measure the topography of a construction site with a drone, <http://smartconstruction.komatsu/introduction/>

- Importance of data
Deep learning requires a large amount of data necessary for training. In the future, we will be able to collect and manage such Big Data. The mother factory/ship yard becomes a data center.

For industries supported by human perception like shipbuilding, a way of data driven should be suitable. Shipbuilding may be a main stream of the next Industrial Revolution through AI applications.

3.3. Human interface technology

- All to Native - We treat 3 dimensions as 3 dimensions.
In various scenes of shipbuilding, ways of thinking have not escaped from 2d world. Expressions and design methods of shipbuilding have been built on the basis of 2 dimensions (drawings), but 2d thinking and mindsets are still found even in the evolving 3d CAD world. For example, despite being able to uniformly represent a hull shape as 3 dimensions in a 3d CAD system, it is designed to be down-dimensioned within specific cross sections (traditionally a cross section of a frame, a water and a buttock). Moreover, traditional lofting methods derived from a drawing in an old lofting room are introduced even into a design using computers. We simply do not use existing 3d information effectively. It is necessary to reconstruct expressions and handling methods. Structural FEM and CFD are cases where 3d information is effectively utilized, but handling of 3d information is still insufficient in design and production. For example, angles or outer plates may optimally arranged with respect to a curved surface geometrically without following a frame or a water line. By being released from a 2d world designer mindset, design will be freed and this should lead to better and innovative products.
- Natural User Interface (NUI), AR technology
Augmented reality technology (AR technology) is a new information interface that transforms large amounts of data and information into images and movies and superimposes them on a real world. AR shortens the gap between a real world and a digital world and draws out capabilities or potentials of humans that have not yet been exploited. In the future, a problem will not be a lack of data and knowledge, but how to absorb them and act on them. The interface with humans has become a bottleneck, and AR is expected to be a solution to this problem. A combination of machine performance and human-specific strength should lead to much higher productivity and greater value creation compared to either case alone. The solution necessary to realize this opportunity is a powerful human interface to fill the gap between a digital world and a real world.

AR application for pipe install

AR application for welding

Fig.3: Wearable devices aid in production and record progress in real-time

- On-site design
The use of a mobile terminal such as a tablet not only allows seeing 3d views but also allows freely accessing data from a shop floor. This opens opportunities to use information equally and diversification of information generation. Currently, it is common that organizations and roles are divided into separate design and production sites, as it is thought that such division

will lead to efficiency improvement. With the spread of AR technology, information will integrate seamlessly between design and production sites. This not only eliminates the gap of communication between design and production departments, but ultimately allows "on-site design" such as determining specifications or generating drawings at the shop floor.

- **Fusion of human and computers**
Computers of a new architecture imitating the human brain (neuro-synaptic computing) and information interfaces applying brain science may be sequentially introduced to design and production sites at shipyards. This will ultimately lead to a future where human brains and computers are connected. In such a future scenario, it will be possible to directly download or upload knowledge or memories to and from computers. Information exchange such as thoughts and feelings may no longer be expressed via language, but may be exchanged directly from brain to brain or brain to computer. This may eliminate misunderstanding and lack of understanding.
- **The future of skill transfer**
Brain-to-computer research results are also utilized for skill transfer. It will become possible to directly convey craftsman's skills, etc. to a brain (such as neurofeedback technology) instead using language or drawings. The common way about acquiring skills will change.

Fig.4: Nissan's Brain-to-Vehicle (B2V); B2V interprets signals from the driver's brain to assist with driving, <https://www.nissan-global.com/EN/TECHNOLOGY/OVERVIEW/b2v.html>

- **Shipbuilding data custodian**
Thoughts and emotions can be recorded on a computer. We can track and stream our life and our work as it is. We can recall everything and regenerate what we have experienced. We also use AI to exploit the tremendous data of a life's log. Self-measurements become commonplace, and we can understand "how to make my time most productive" or "what kind of work is most suitable for me" by analyzing the data. Ultimate customization and personalization to individuals will also proceed, and an "AI data custodian" will accompany each worker in the future.
- **Human augmentation, shipbuilding augmentation**
We can connect and extend our brain not only with computers but also with robots (fusion of human, computer and machine). Machines become a human's extended sense, organ and body.

Table I: Concept of AW (Augmented Worker) and AS (Augmented Shipbuilding)

Ability	Augmentation	Tools / Technologies
Sense (touch, hearing, eyesight, smell)	See something we cannot see, hear things we cannot hear. Sixth sense.	4K eyesight, AR, high resolution hearing, noise cancellation, laser scanner, IoT, etc.
Physical ability	Super X (X: force, dexterity, size, etc.), extension of limb, amplification of amount of activity.	Power assist suit, cooperative robot, drone, insect device, etc.
Thinking, imagination and memory	Intelligence amplification (IA), external memory storage	AI, VR, IoT, BMI (Brain Machine Interface), etc.
Expression and communication	New human interface	Gesture input, NUI (Natural User Interface), BMI (Brain Machine Interface), SNS, automatic translation, etc.

3.4. 3D printer

- Additive manufacturing

At present, 3D printing can only produce small parts and has limitations in strength and type of materials used. However, these issues should be fundamentally resolved soon and 3D printing is expected to spread rapidly also in shipbuilding. This will in turn advance the use of composite materials in ships. The ONR (Office of Naval Research) of the US Navy published a report to explore the possibility of producing the whole ship using 3D printing. In the Netherlands, a metal propeller was 3D printed and approved by a class. 3D printers overcome constraints of a place of manufacturing. Everyone can make a product if there is the 3D data of the product to produce. If we send the data via the internet, we can make it available anywhere. The manufacturing ability will no longer be tied to a specific place, and anyone can do shipbuilding business anywhere.

Fig.5: 3D printed metal propeller named “WAAMPeller”, <https://3dprintingindustry.com/news/damen-shipyards-worlds-first-3d-printed-propeller-121112/>

3.5. New material

R&D efforts have been made for higher strength and more flexible steels. These achievements are being incorporated into the shipbuilding industry. Meanwhile, we see R&D on smarter materials or functional materials in other industries.

- From wood to iron and then carbon in the future?
Future ship materials will increasingly involve composites of various materials (steel, carbon, and organic material). We see already the practical use of CFRP (composite fibre reinforced

plastics) in aerospace and the automotive industry. New nanocarbon materials such as carbon nanotubes (CNT), Fig.6, and graphene could be game changers. Ship structures have moved from wood to steel. Carbon may bring the next revolution.

Fig.6: Carbon nanotube as game changing material; left: structure; right: black CNT and white hair

- Smarter and functional materials
Nanocarbon material is not only a good structural material, but also a good functional material e.g. for built-in electronic circuitry, semiconductors or heat exchangers. Ship outfitting work may dramatically change (e.g. embedding electrical materials and printed circuit board directly into hull material by printing). By realizing ultra-light ships, we may also see different hull forms and structural designs for volume carriers such as cruise ships, mega-yachts, ferries and navy vessels, Fig.7. Concept on LCA (life cycle assessment) including ship recycling would also be affected. We may see increasingly high-performance materials with a variety of new features such as transparency, Fig.8, ability to reactively adjust shape or mechanical properties (biomimetic technology, Fig.9), self-healing, and intelligence (with sensors embedded).

The Ship of the Future

The ship of the future may be made of carbon nanomaterial, and this should be comparable innovation with past innovations of ships that material of ships varies from wood to steel. The ship made of carbon realizes the enhancement of its structural performance, and a dramatic lighter body as well. The ship of the future has unthinkable shape, structure style and inside arrangement that we have never seen. Its shape and structure may seem like the body of sea creature, and some electronic devices and cables may be merged into hull structure. Thanks to a new feature of the ship with super lightening and new shape, and hydrogen-powered ship as well, ships of the future may be completely environmentally friendly one that never use fossil fuel, emit any pollution to sea and air while their sailing.

Ship operation with a computer connected with human
Future of ship operation also would have changed a lot. It will be able to operate the ship more freely by further interaction between human and computer. Recently, the progressive R&D on technology that connects the human brain and the computer has been studied. In the future, ship may be operated by information directly downloaded from the brain of a sailor. There is also automatic ship operation by artificial intelligence technology.

Morphing technology
Technologies that a ship hull deforms mechanically or materially depending on her surrounding environment. In the aircraft industry, the related technology to move the wings in flight has been under research and development. For even a ship, study has been promoted in Europe to move the ship shape freely by using a smart material.

Biomimetic engineering
Industrially imitation of the superior functionality of an organism. The frictional resistance reduction by imitating shark skin surface, biomimetic hull form and structure, new propulsion system that imitate the propulsion system of the mackerel or jellyfish have been studied recently for a ship.

Printed electronics
The technology that a solar panel or an electronic substrate and so on is directly printed onto the surface or into the ship hull. In a ship of the future, solar panels or electronic circuits are spread everywhere around to the outer shell or the deck. The entire ship might be a large display, and sensors or cameras can be added by the clicker from any location of the ship. New attraction can be played for citizens in the harbor she calls at.

Carbon material
Although the CFRP that already been put to practical use in the aircraft industry or the automobile industry may be also applied to a ship in near future, emerging technology on carbon nanomaterial such as carbon nanotube and graphene may drastically change a ship of the future. They will work as a possible structural material, but also as a functional material such as a semiconductor or capacitor and so on. Computers including various sensors or electric cables may be implanted directly into a ship hull in the ship of the future.

Hydrogen-powered ship
Hydrogen technology is a very promising technology for fewer natural resource country. Fuel cell using hydrogen might have become mainstream for ship propulsion in the future, as hydrogen can sufficiently store and transport renewable energy. The future of the ship might be a zero energy and a zero emission ship.

Bionic Structure and Membranes
The current system of the structure of the ship hull is not necessarily the best. Studies of the structural system that imitates the style of the creature have been made. The optimum hull structure will be created in the future with realization of a carbonic ship and 3D printing technology for shipbuilding.

Fig.7: The concept of future ship by JSTRA

Fig.8: Conception of a ship composed of transparent structural members by Aluminium nitride, SeaOrbiter by Jacques Rougerie

Fig.9 Examples of biomimetic materials. Lotus-Effect for hull coatings reduces frictional resistance and improves antifouling performance.

3.6. Hydrogen technology – From ZES to NES

Similar as for cars and planes, we will see shipping move towards low and eventually zero CO₂ emission scenarios. The vision of a future zero emission ship (ZES) combines various energy-saving technologies and sources of renewable energy, such as wind and solar power, bio-fuels, tapping into wave and tidal energy. Hydrogen technology will play a key role, as hydrogen allows efficient storage of energy generated offshore, such as wave and wind energy, solar power or even artificial photosynthesis using offshore algae farming. In general, sustainable shipping will play an increasing role. As we need to protect and preserve the habitat environment of our oceans, management of biological resources and water in a sustainable way will result in the demand for a “Non-negative Effect Ship” (NES). Design and operation of ships will then be aligned with this ultimate goal.

Fig.10: Concept of offshore wind energy converted to hydrogen to fuel ZES, Rohde and Sames (2014)

Fig.11: “GreenFloat” concept of a future city by Shimizu Corporation. Magnesium extracted from sea water is used to construct the floating city. Using solar and marine energy, vegetables are cultivated in a plant factory.

4. Conclusion – Shipbuilding 4.0

Emerging technologies such as a 3D CAD, advanced simulation technology, 3D printer, laser scanner, AI and so on will become commoditized, and become just as natural tools as scissors and chopsticks now. From now on, how to utilize these tools to shipbuilding becomes the key issue.

The influence of these megatrend technologies on a maritime industry is as follows:

- Ultimate customization and shift to service business
- Always connected - Development by open platforms and open innovation
- Standardization & commonality
- Automation and data driven
- Personally optimized and customized ways of working
- Pursuit of ultimate environmental conservation
- Exploring new forms of ships

The response to these movements is the activity of "shipbuilding 4.0".

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References

CHENEY-PETERS, S.; HIPPLE, M. (2013), *Print Me a Cruiser!*, Proceedings Magazine 139/4

MATSUO, K. (2017), *Innovative Technologies for Maritime Industry & Future Scenario*, 10th HIPER Conf., Zevenwacht, pp.160-177

MATSUO, K. (2016), *Augmented Reality Assistance for Outfitting Works in Shipbuilding*, COMPIT Conf., Lecce

ROHDE, F.; SAMES, P. (2014), *Conceptual design of a zero-emission open-top container feeder*, 8th HIPER Conf., Duisburg

Optimization of Part Arrangement in Engine Room

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Abstract

This paper presents a new approach for engine room design based on the modularization concept including the part arrangement optimization. The characteristics of the proposed methods are as follows. First, attention was paid to piping systems of multiple bulk carrier series of different sizes. The cost and length of the piping system as well as the similarity and the commonness of the modules and arrangements were considered. Second, to define an effective module that could be commonly used in different ships, a design structure matrix was adopted. Third, in the arrangement design, an optimization system was developed using a genetic algorithm to obtain a similar pattern for module arrangement in multiple series ships with specific consideration toward the cost and similarity. Some examples using the proposed method are shown at the end of paper.

1. Introduction

In the shipbuilding industry, continues improvements in production methods in order to achieve higher values of design efficiency. Various production concepts, such as block division, modularization, and ship-building with a standard design are possible solutions for achieving improved production capability. Typically, the initial design of an engine room is performed based on advance design data, such as reference ship data, design constraints, and theoretical optimum solutions. Engine-room design, including the piping system, is a complex process. As such, modularization of its design is an effective strategy to minimize complexity of the system. In applications such as shipbuilding, individual designs of the piping system inside an engine room and their specifications and arrangement differ significantly from one ship to another owing to differences between ship sizes. These differences occur because individual ship designs are developed exclusively on the basis of different equipment used by ship owners as well as different engine-room requirements.

With due consideration of the above characteristics of piping-system design in shipbuilding applications, it is important for shipbuilders to develop a method based on standard modularization whilst considering the variety of series ships having different sizes. In addition, development of a standard module arrangement is also important to achieve overall design optimization. The concept of engine-room modularization was first introduced by several researchers, *Cort and Hills (1987)*, *Hills and Wels (1989)*. These studies, however, resort to a rather simple modularization approach that involves use of a standard compartment for each ship. Standardization of modules for various series ships has not been considered previously.

The view on modularization is gradually changing, and nowadays, the modularization concept is being utilized to target overall optimization of a vehicle in the automobile industry. Consider the example of Nissan Motor's common module family (CMF); it efficiently designs various models, such as small cars, sedans, and SUVs by simply changing the combination of engine compartment, cockpit, and front and rear underbodies as modular units. Adoption of such a modularization concept provides an opportunity to enhance engine-room designs in shipbuilding.

Based on the above considerations, we have been developing the system to optimize the engine room of various series ships based on the modularization concept, *Gunawan et al. (2017)*. In this paper, we proposed the optimization method of module arrangement with specific consideration toward the cost and similarity.

2. Related Studies

As previously discussed, modularization and part arrangement with regard to piping design are important considerations to realize overall optimization of engine-room design in series ships. As such, many studies related to these aspects have been performed in the past.

The concept of modularization, for use in engine-room design and its arrangement was first introduced by *Jaquith et al. (1996)*. They proposed a concurrent engineering system to simplify the construction of outfitting and equipment used in the engine room. Big data system was adopted to identify all components in the engine room. Further, all components were grouped inside the big outfit unit. *Baade et al., (1998)* explored the modularization concept based on grouping of system components inside an engine room. Further, they proposed the concept of engine-room modularization in the form of a modular standard container, based on function volume. In this study, a standard modular frame was considered. A novel modularization methodology was reported by *Tomassoni et al. (2003)*. In their study, they proposed an advanced design methodology of grouping machinery equipment into a functional volume and block and an interface was considered between them. As the result, the design cost, production cost and construction cycle time were significantly reduced. All researchers involved in the study, used their experience to design the modular outfitting and components inside the engine room. Consequently, an engineer-experience-based modular arrangement was created.

In 2009, automatic modularization of the engine room was introduced by *Koga et al. (2009)*. They adopted the design structure matrix (DSM) to generate a modular division of the engine room of a ship, through use of the modular division algorithm, and subsequently evaluated the result using functional completeness and module independency. To evaluate the effective modular structure, functional-completeness and system-independence analyses of the module were performed.

With regards to engine-room arrangement, several researchers, *Wu et al. (1998)*, *Kim et al. (2009)*, *Kimura (2011)*, *Lee et al. (2013)* have employed various algorithms and sequential coordination to optimize machinery arrangement and pipe routing. Their research focused on the optimization of engine room arrangement, plant-equipment layout, and pipe routes. However, modularization of engine-room equipment was not part of these studies.

Table I: Summary of previous studies based on application of modularization concept in ship building

Authors	Objective			Methods			Target Ship	
	Modularization	Arrangement	Pipe Routing	GA	Fuzzy	Rule/Other	One Ship	Series
Koga et.al	O	X	X	X	X	DSM	O	X
Baade et.al	O	O	X	X	X	Grouping	O	X
Jaquith et.al	O	O	X	X	X	Big Data	O	X
Tomassoni et.al	O	O	X	X	X	ERAM	O	X
Hills and Cort	O	O	X	X	O	Grouping	O	X
Wels and Hills	O	O	X	X	X	Grouping	O	X
Wu et.al	X	O	O	X	O	A* Algorithm	Δ	X
Lee et.al	X	O	O	X	O	A* Algorithm	Δ	X
Kimura	X	O	O	O	X	S-Organization	Δ	X
Kim et.al	X	O	O	X	O	Rule Based	Δ	X
This Paper	O	O	X	O	X	DSM	O	O

O: Yes X: No Δ: Several Components

Table I presents a summary of previous studies performed with regards to application of the modularization concept in ship building. As can be seen in the table, all extent studies included therein have, in some way or another, focused on modularization and part arrangement of only either a single ship or several individual components; series ships, in particular, have not been considered in any of these studies.

Therefore, we discuss a new modularization concept and arrangement considering these characteristics:

- (1) The target ships are various types of series ships;
- (2) The commonness of the modules for all ships is considered;
- (3) Similarity in the module arrangement for all ships is considered; the proposed concept is used in an actual ship design process and the effectiveness is evaluated.

3. Problem Definition

3.1. Target ships

Details of target ships considered in the proposed research may be listed as follows:

- (1) Multiple series of bulk carriers with different capacities are considered. Respective sizes of the series considered herein are handymax (58000 DWT), panamax (82000 DWT), and over panamax (98000 DWT).
- (2) A single series consists of a significantly large number of ships.
- (3) The piping system inside the engine room of each ship comprises a fuel system, lubricating-oil system, seawater system, freshwater system, compressed-air system, and steam system.
- (4) Each ship also comprises different components and arrangements in the piping system based on the requirements of the owner.

3.2. Target process of this paper

A typical piping-system design process consists of the following four stages:

- (1) Owner requirements
This refers to ship-owner requirements or desires that need to be considered to fulfill the target-ship mission. This information is associated with characteristics and operation of an existing ship.
- (2) Piping diagram
The piping diagram for each system is examined after the designer collects the information from the owner. The piping diagram depicts the correlation between equipment and instrumentation.
- (3) Part arrangements
This stage focuses on analysis of the spatial arrangement of all parts. In general, part arrangement is usually performed based on reference-ship characteristics, designer experiences, and the theoretical optimal solution.
- (4) Pipe routing
Pipe-routing design is important to eliminate crossovers and interference in a pipe patch. In this study, the pipe patch was determined after all parts were appropriately arranged. The pipe routing design depends on designer experience and the number of parts.

This paper lays greater emphasis on part arrangements; therefore, the piping diagram is already fixed, and pipe routing is not considered.

3.3. Basic concept

The primary objective of this study is to develop a methodology for arranging engine-room parts through use of the modularization concept with due consideration of various kinds of series ships. To fulfil this objective, part arrangement is divided into the following two problems.

3.3.1. The module definition problem

Modularization involves grouping of parts with strong dependency into a single group. Modularization for common parts must be separate from that of optional parts. The output of this process is obtained in the form of a common module for ships belonging to various series types and an optional module for any particular ship. Modularization requirements are as follows:

- (1) Modules should be defined for a single ship, a single series ship, or for various series of ships.
- (2) Based on owner requirements, both common and optional modules must be flexible to changes in capacity and size without any change in module configuration.
- (3) It must be possible to use a combination of common and optional modules to obtain a new ship type based on owner requirements.
- (4) To effectively utilize the modularization concept, complex connections must be included in the module. Therefore, all connections between individual modules must be minimized.

3.3.2. Module arrangement problem

Following the module definition process, the defined modules are arranged inside the engine room. This process has been termed as the module arrangement problem. The following points are considered in this step:

- (1) Various constraints, such as space requirement for maintenance, area for fixed components, etc. are considered.
- (2) Similarity of arrangements is considered for either a single ship, a series of ships, or various series of ships.
- (3) Pipe costs are minimized with respect to pipe length, diameter, material, etc.

4. Overview of Modularization

The module definition problem is addressed in the following three steps. Details of modularization process is shown in the reference, *Gunawan et al. (2017)*.

4.1. E–R model

To establish relationships between various parts, the proposed study employs the entity–relationship model (or E-R model), which graphically represents logical relationships between entities (objects). The model was first proposed by *Chen (1976)* at the MIT. In E–R modelling, objects are represented by an entity, its relationship, and attributes, all of which may be defined as follows:

- (1) An entity may either have a physical or logical existence. The proposed study identifies equipment, including cooler, heater, purifier, filter, etc., as entities. Valves and branches are also considered as entities.
- (2) Relationships denote the manner in which the entities are related to one another. In this study, pipes connecting individual entities are identified as relationships.
- (3) Attributes basically refer to properties of entities. In this case, the flow capacity, heating value, part size, pipe diameter, etc. are considered as attributes.

Fig.1(a) and (b) depict the E-R model for each ship. In this case, there are 2 E-R models. Subsequent to generation of the integration E–R model, individual E–R models were integrated into a single model with specific focus on entities and their relationships. The entities, in this case, are estimated to be similar; therefore, similar entities and relationships can be integrated into a single entity or relationship. Thereafter, the entities and relationships are classified into the following two types; first, common entities and relationships. These entities and relationships are employed in all types of ships. Second, optional entities and relationships: These entities and relationships are used in only a few of the ships – a certain series of ships, or ships built for certain owners.

4.2. Modularization using DSM

DSM is a network modelling tool used to represent elements in a system and their interactions. It enables the user to model, visualize, and analyze the dependencies among different entities of any system and derive suggestions for the improvement or synthesis of a system, *Eppinger and Browning (2012)*, *Lindemann et al. (2009)*. The most important step in the DSM process is the clustering operation. During the clustering operation, separate matrices for common and optional parts were first generated. Subsequently, the weights for the connections were set in-line with the following rules:

- (1) Connections for common parts: The weight is assumed as the cost per unit length of the corresponding pipe.
- (2) Connections for optional parts: Weights are first calculated in a manner similar to that for common parts. Subsequently, they are multiplied with the corresponding installation probability of connections.
- (3) Once the weights are set, separate clusters of common parts and optional parts are generated, thereby generating clusters (modules) for the entire assembly.

Flow path of the DSM procedure followed in this study is depicted in Fig.1(d-f).

Fig.1: Modularization procedure

4.3. Modularization result

In the proposed study, each ship comprised six piping systems. Consider the example of a seawater system; it comprises 233 common and 8 optional components. Fig.2 shows the modularization result of the seawater system. This modularization was realized for a single ship or a series ships as well as

for ships belonging to various series types that could be established with 15 common and 2 optional modules. Each module could be varied in capacity or size without changes in its configuration. It was, therefore, possible to configure a new piping system with a combination of all modules. Detailed of modularization result reported in the reference, *Gunawan et al. (2017)*.

Fig.2: Modularization result for the seawater system

5. Optimization of the Module Arrangement

5.1. Basic concept

In arrangement design, modules defined in the previous section are arranged inside the engine room. To realize an arrangement for series ships of different sizes, the following concepts were introduced in this study:

- (1) Arrangements of three series ships were executed simultaneously. This provides the flexibility to consider various options at once.
- (2) In the aforementioned case, the design space becomes relatively large; moreover, it is difficult to obtain an optimum solution within a limited time when positions of modules are directly treated as design variables. Therefore, decks within the engine room and individual modules were divided into meshes.
- (3) The cost of pipes and similarity of arrangements were set as objective functions.
- (4) A genetic algorithm was adopted for the sake of optimization.

Deck as well as module information were first input by the user. Later, the genetic algorithm-based optimization was performed on data. Characteristics of the genetic algorithm, used in this study, include chromosome representation and fitness calculation.

5.2. Initial condition (user input)

Deck, module, and inter-module pipe information were input by the user prior to the commencement of optimization. These were treated as initial conditions for the arrangement optimization algorithm.

5.2.1. Deck information

Fig.3 depicts a simplified example of deck information; the following information was input as deck information:

- (1) The black area represents hull boundary of the ship.
- (2) The grey area represents a few fixed parts, such as the main engine and tank. The arrangement of parts and pipe, however, could not be accomplished.
- (3) The green area is provided as maintenance space. The arrangement of parts is not allowed but for pipe arrangement is allowed.
- (4) In the white area, all parts were arranged.

In this study, three series ships were set as targets with each ship having a three-deck structure. Therefore, information on nine decks was input as the initial condition. Consequently, the mesh size was set as 40×40 cm.

Fig.3: Deck information

5.2.2. Module information

Module information comprises the information concerning on the size and limitations of the arrangement. As seen in Table II, modules A and B possess a size of 6 columns \times 4 rows and 5 columns \times 5 rows, respectively. Both modules (A and B) were to be arranged on the 3rd deck. Module A was to be arranged on the portside and module B on the starboard side.

Table II: Example of module information

ID	C	R	PARTIAL	3 rd DECK	2 nd DECK	S or P
A	6	4		1		P
B	5	5		1		S

5.2.3. Pipe information

Pipe information indicates the number of pipe connections between modules along with weight-per-unit-length data for each pipe. The data are used to calculate the pipe length and weight. Table III gives an example of pipe information. As denoted by red circles in the table, there exists a single pipe between modules A and B; the weight per unit length (kg/m) for this pipe was determined to be 5.67 kg/m.

Table III: Example of pipe information

ID	A	B	C	ID	A	B	C
A	1	1		A	5.67		
B	1	1		B	5.67	3.24	
C		1		C		3.24	

5.3. Design variables and gene representation

The basic unit of a chromosome is the arrangement information of one module for three series ships.

Fig.4 shows the gene sequence for a module of 58BC, 82BC, and 98BC series. This illustration demonstrates single module placement for 3 series ships. The gene sequence is further divided into four parts; the first part is reserved for deck decision while others determine module positions in the three series ships. In Fig.4, the module position of 58BC is "7", 82BC is "6" and 98BC is "10". The number is assigned to free meshes on the deck in consideration of fixed components and pre-existing arranged modules (Fig.4). Corresponding modules, therefore, are arranged at mesh "7" for 58BC, mesh "6" for 82BC and mesh "10" for 98BC.

Fig.4: Gene representation for module placement

5.4. Objective function

As previously mentioned, piping cost and similarity in arrangement for ships belonging to various series types were set as objective functions in this study.

5.4.1. Cost calculation

In this study, the lengths of individual pipes were calculated based on the 2D calculation, height calculation and offset calculation which are shown in the followings:

(1) 2D calculation

2D calculation is used for the calculation of rough pipe length. The pipe length is calculated based on the following rules:

- The two extreme ends of each pipe were considered to be centers of connected modules.
- The horizontal distance and vertical distance between centers, is calculated as the pipe length as shown in Fig.5.

(2) Height calculation

As shown in Fig.6, the height of connecting module is different and its affect the length of pipe. In this paper, pipe height is calculated by Eq.(1) for same deck and Eq.(2) for different deck. Hence h_1 and h_2 are determined based on the past module data.

$$L_{Height} = |h_1 - h_2| \quad (1)$$

$$L_{Height} = \text{deck height} + h_1 - h_2 \quad (2)$$

h_1 : height of module 1

h_2 : height of module 2

L_{Height} : pipe height between modules

Fig.5: 2D calculation

Fig.6: Height calculation

(3) Offset calculation

As discussed in (1), center of each module is used for 2D calculation. On the other hand, actual connecting point is not the center but having offset (Fig.7). Fig.8 shows the relations between module size and offset where module size (x) is calculated by using Eq.(3). Then offset is decided by using the equation shown in Fig.8.

Fig.7: Offset calculation

Figure 8: Relation between module size and offset

$$x = \frac{R_s + C_s + R_f + C_f}{4} \quad (3)$$

- R_s : rows number of starting module
- C_s : columns number of starting module
- R_f : rows number of finish module
- C_f : columns number of finish module

(4) Total pipe length and its evaluation

Based on the previous discussion, the total piping length is calculated by using the Eq.(4)

$$L = L_{2D} + L_{Height} - Offset \quad (4)$$

- L_{2D} : length using 2D calculation
- L_{Height} : pipe height between modules
- $Offset$: length of offset

Fig.9 compares the correlation coefficient between piping calculation using 2D calculation (L_{2D}) and the proposed method (L). Based on the Fig.9, the correlation coefficient is improved by using the proposed method and the estimation accuracy is improved. Therefore, cost of the pipe is calculated by using the diameter, material and the result of Eq.(4).

Fig.9: Correlation graph comparison

5.4.2. Similarity calculation

The position of modules for each series was normalized using the following equation:

$$(x, y) = \left(\frac{x_o}{\text{sum of columns}}, \frac{y_o}{\text{sum of rows}} \right) \quad (5)$$

- x : column position after normalize
- y : row position after normalize
- x_o : original column position
- y_o : original row position

Subsequently, similarity was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Similarity} = \frac{\sum \{ \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2} + \sqrt{(x_2 - x_3)^2 + (y_2 - y_3)^2} + \sqrt{(x_3 - x_1)^2 + (y_3 - y_1)^2} \}}{\quad} \quad (6)$$

- (x_1, y_1) : module normalize coordinate of 58BC
- (x_2, y_2) : module normalize coordinate of 82BC
- (x_3, y_3) : module normalize coordinate of 98BC

The above equations represent a summary of the relative distance of one module within the normalized.

6. Arrangement Result

6.1. Problem definition

To evaluate the effectiveness of our study, following optimizations were performed:

- Case 1: Current arrangement in the company.
- Case 2: Optimization of a single ship.
- Case 3: Optimization of one series of ships.
- Case 4: Optimization of ships of different sizes belonging to various series.

Bulk carrier ships with capacities of 58000, 82000, and 98000 DWT were considered as target structures in this study.

6.2. Optimization result and discussion

6.2.1. Optimization result

To solve the above optimization problem, a genetic algorithm (described in a foregoing section) was adopted. The time taken by the optimization program to perform necessary calculations was approximately 3 hours. Fig.10 shows the result of the optimization operation (case-4). As shown, modular arrangements of all three series of ships are generated in a single optimization run.

Fig.10: Optimization result of case-4

Fig.11: Differences of optimized arrangements on the 3rd deck belonging to three different cases

Table IV: Optimization result

RESULT		CASE 1	CASE 2	CASE 3	CASE 4
58 BC	Cost	100	97.77	97.94	98.15
82 BC	Cost	100	97.25	97.63	97.87
98 BC	Cost	100	98.38	98.55	98.77

6.2.2. Cost comparison

The costs and pipe lengths for Cases 1–4 are compared in Table IV. The cost for Case 1 were set as 100. Case 2 is the most optimum in terms of cost. However, there are very slight differences between corresponding values for Cases 3 and 4 in comparison to Case 2.

6.2.3. Comparison of arrangements

Fig.11 demonstrates positions of modules (3rd deck on the portside) corresponding to Cases 2–4 for the three series of ships. As shown in the figure, modular positions for the three series of ships are different for Cases 2 and 3. However, in Case 4, modular positions for the three series of ships are almost similar although the size of their corresponding modules and decks are largely different. A similar arrangement has been found to be beneficial in terms of maintenance and design/production lead time. Therefore, Tsuneishi Shipbuilding Co., Ltd, employed the proposed arrangement for designing their ship.

7. Conclusion

This study presents a new piping system arrangement with respect to series ships in line with the modularization concept. To this end, design and layout of the piping arrangement was first divided into two stages—module definition and module arrangement. To define an effective module that can be commonly used for different ships, the DSM method was adopted. Furthermore, for determining module arrangement, an optimization system was developed using a genetic algorithm to obtain vastly similar module-arrangement patterns for ships belonging to various series types with specific consideration to piping cost and similarity. As a result, a similar arrangement design for ships belonging to various series types is generated in which cost of pipe is almost same as the optimization result intended for each ship.

References

- BAADE, R.; KLINGE, F.; LYNAUGH, K.; WORONKOWICZ, F.; SEIDLER, K.M. (1998), *Modular outfitting*, J. Ship Production 14/3, pp.170-179
- CHEN, P. (1976), *The entity-relationship model toward an un-fined view of data*, ACM Transactions on Database Systems 1/1, pp.9-36
- CORT, A.; HILLS, W. (1987), *Space layout design using computer assisted methods*, Naval Eng. J. 99/3, pp.249-260
- EPPINGER, S.D.; BROWNING, T.R. (2012), *Design Structure Matrix Methods and Applications*, MIT Press
- GUNAWAN; HAMADA, K.; DEGUCHI, T.; YAMAMOTO, H.; MORITA, Y. (2017), *Optimization of piping system arrangement in series ships using the modularization concept*, Int. Conf. Ship and Offshore Technology (ICSOT), Jakarta, pp.1-9
- HILLS, W.; WELS, M. (1989), *An efficient compartmentation method for use in preliminary ship design*, Int. Conf. Computer Applications in Shipbuilding (ICCAS), pp.141-153
- JAQUITH, P.E.; BURNS, R.M.; DUNBARR, S.E.; FONTAINE, B.J.; NELSON, H.A.; SILVEIRA, J.L. (1996), *Modular engine room design and construction for the strategic sealift ships*, J. Ship Production 12/4, pp.230-243
- KIM, S.Y.; MOON, B.Y.; SHIN, S.C. (2009), *Evaluation criterion of machinery arrangement design in a ship engine room*, J. Ship Production 25/3, pp.117-125
- KIMURA, H. (2011), *Automatic designing system for piping and instruments arrangement including branches of pipes*, Int. Conf. Computer Applications in Shipbuilding (ICCAS), Trieste, pp.93-99
- KOGA, T.; NIWA, T.; AOYAMA, K. (2009), *A modular design method for an engine room based on an integrated network description and division*, 10th Int. Marine Design Conf., Trondheim, pp.1-9

LEE, D.M.; KIM, S.Y.; MOON, B.Y.; KANG, G.J. (2013), *Layout design optimization of pipe system in ship engine room for space efficiency*, J. Korean Society of Marine Eng. 37/7, pp.784-791

LINDEMANN, U.; MAURER, M.; BRAUN, T. (2009), *Structural Complexity Management*, Springer

TOMASSONI, C.; HUYNH, T.; SCHILLER, T. (2003), *Production-based design methodology for shipboard machinery spaces*, J. Ship Production 19/1, pp.53-63

WU, B.C.; YOUNG, G.S.; SCHMIDT, W.; CHOPPELLA, K. (1998), *Applying fuzzy functions and sequential coordination to optimization of machinery arrangement and pipe routing*, Naval Eng. J. 110/6, pp.43-54

Modular Authoring of Augmented Reality Based Service Instructions

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Abstract

Service and repair instructions are increasingly supported by Augmented Reality tools. Currently, AR content is created manually and exclusively for a single product, requiring a large amount of effort to prepare the animated 3D-CAD models and annotations. This process is separated from existing content management and does not reuse instruction templates for new products and variants. In this paper, we describe a toolkit for AR based service instruction modules which can be employed in the authoring of maritime service instructions e.g., for maintaining and repairing compressors or engines. Moreover, we provide an overview of the usage of the AR based instructions and integration of the authoring toolkit in industrial processes.

1. Introduction

Over a ship's life cycle, the costs for maintaining and repairing it and its equipment components represents a significant proportion of the operating costs. To reduce ship downtimes, maintenance and repairs need to happen quickly, be conducted as independently of the ship's location as possible and be cost-effective. In order to meet these requirements, large component suppliers and service providers need concepts to more flexibly and productively design maintenance and repair work. Generally, service technicians are given maintenance and repair instructions on paper so that they can execute the accrued work. The documents span a number of pages and additional required information has to be laboriously sought in tables and lists. Furthermore, the documents usually only represent the original delivery state and lack information about on-site installations or modifications. Consequently, work plans and lists of spare parts frequently deviate from the pre-formulated ones. Research on outfitting sections during the construction of ships has shown that the use of Augmented Reality (AR) for digitally supplying information can increase productivity by up to 19%, *Friedewald et al. (2016)*. It is also believed to have considerable productivity and cost potential in the maintenance of ships. This is particularly true if on board personnel can conduct maintenance and repair work at sea, thus avoiding the expense of having to transport the component manufacturer's service technicians to the ship.

As part of the WASSER research project, the Institute of Production Management and Technology is developing a digital AR based service document (DARS) for efficiently supplying personnel with information during maintenance and repair work. To ensure the success, all required documents (e.g., inspection and test instructions, maintenance and repair manuals) are presented to personnel on AR tablets or AR glasses and enhanced with animations. The animations will clarify the instructions, thereby reducing assembly errors. Moreover, feedback data will be automatically collected by the software and new tasks derived when needed. In order to create the digital instructions, existing documents first have to be manually converted and prepared, which entails considerable effort. The animations also have to be newly generated and stored for each work step. Creating specific animations for non-standard task is especially laborious and requires considerable expertise in CAD programming. In an effort to counter this expenditure, this paper presents an authoring system that allows AR service instructions to be developed with minimal effort. To do so, we will describe the development of a toolkit of information modules which allows AR service instructions to be configured specifically for each situation. Following that, we will also present the implementation and prototypical visualization of the generated service instructions.

2. Supplying Information during Servicing

To keep the good working order of a machine or to restore its functionality after a breakdown, the operator executes maintenance measures. Maintenance measures are generally divided into inspection,

maintenance, repair and improvement work, *DIN (2012)*. For maintaining complex machines and systems such as ships motors or their auxiliary units, the operator contracts service divisions from the respective manufacturer. To conduct the service work, employees essentially need to know the following information:

- What needs to be done?
- When does it need to be done?
- Where does it need to be done?
- How is the task to be done?

Usually, service divisions distinguish between planned and unplanned maintenance work. Planned maintenance work is concerned with standard tasks. For these tasks, all the required information is stored in the job cards and work plans.

Job cards summarize the key order data and roughly indicate the task to be executed: What? When? Where? Work plans provide a more detailed description of the tasks to be executed along with supplementary documents that contain additionally required information: How? All the required maintenance work is listed in the work plans including inspection and maintenance work, replacing worn parts, troubleshooting or repair work when machines and systems break down. Work plans are generally organized as a sequence of steps. Every step has a description of the task and references to additionally relevant information. This supplemental information includes necessary tools or aids, consumables, replacement parts as well as technical data e.g., tightening torque. Usually, this information is stored in tables and lists and must be sought out individually for each step. Experienced workers often know the work plans and only look-up selected information. Untrained personnel with little experience must rely on searching each of the pieces of required information from the work plans and apply them one-by-one. Experience has shown that although it is necessary to read the work plans, untrained personnel in particular, are seldom prepared to do so

Fig.1: Mental effort to transfer tasks and availability of information per type of service order

Unplanned maintenance work is based on the specific conditions and situation at the place where the maintenance is executed. To prepare personnel for these jobs, job cards and/or work plans have to be developed ad hoc on demand. These ad hoc documents must be adapted and compiled, or created newly

especially for the specific maintenance situation. When creating the documents, the service division's work 'preparation team' uses existing documents and amends them to the on-site situation. Fig.1 summarizes the different service contracts and identifies these deficits:

- Tasks to be executed are not clearly presented, thus requiring inexperienced workers to invest more effort to transfer them.
- Quality issues result from workers who fail to invest the required effort to transfer them or do not completely read the work plans.
- With ad hoc operations, there is a lack of available information for both experienced and inexperienced workers.

3. Augmented Reality Based Service Instructions

Visualizations that can integrate the situation on-site are particularly well-suited for improving the depiction of work that needs to be executed. Augmented reality, which enriches real environments with virtual elements, *Azuma (1997)*, is capable of this. Generally, for industrial AR applications, both textual and geometric information about the work to be executed are superimposed on the work object and shown on a display device e.g., an AR tablet or AR glasses.

3.1 Presentation of Information

Compared to conventional paper drawings, AR applications have the following advantages when supplying service technicians with information relevant to work steps, *Halata (2018)*:

- Work on/with three-dimensional geometries can be better illustrate, thus leading to a reduction in errors when executing the work.
- Relevant additional information can be superimposed directly on the corresponding place, reducing the effort to find this necessary information.
- Especially with complex and non-repeating tasks, in which the tasks that need to be executed are not known, the information developed specific to the situation clarifies the complex tasks and reduces errors.

As a part of the research project PROSPER, digital work documents were developed, *Friedewald et al. (2016)*, and in subsequent work modified for service calls, *Friedewald et al. (2017a)*. The user interface of the digital work documents is modularly structured and allows different visualization and interaction functions to be turned on and off. Fig.2 shows the user interface for the digital augmented reality based service documents (DARS) for an exemplary engine maintenance. The DARS display (1) shows the camera's live image and the virtual superposition of the objects. This is done by using different tracking methods. One of the most common tracking methods is marker based tracking, in which markers that can be identified by the camera are employed in the environment, allowing objects to be placed in the correct position. In doing so, the object recognition has to take into account that in contrast to a pure assembly, maintenance and repair also involves disassembling components. The superposition is further enriched by highlighting the affected components or playing animations of the maintenance task. The work plan is found on the left side of the display (2). The work steps that need to be executed are shown on the right, and additional information for each specific step can be retrieved via a selection menu. Further functions, which depict different supplementary information are stored in another selection menu (3). Selecting 'final status', depicts all of the work steps in the executed target state. Thus, the engine, for example, can be depicted in the disassembled state, providing the worker with a preview of the work that has to be done. The current view can be frozen (4) in order to briefly lay the device down or to be able to discuss the situation with a colleague. The remaining functionality is still available. The display (1) can be switched to CAD mode at any time. The CAD mode has generally the same functionality as the AR mode. Instead of the camera image and the superimposed environment, the CAD model of the expected object is shown directly. Thus, when using the CAD mode, markers do not need to be installed. Moreover, it can be used outside of the work environment or in another location

in the workspace, in order to get an overview. The point-of-view can be oriented and set by the service technician using standard views and touch gestures. Once a step is completed it can be marked 'done' (5) and when needed, an error report can be generated (with a camera shot or a written description).

Fig.2: AR based service instruction, *Friedewald et al. (2016)*

Implementing AR based service instructions has the following potentials:

- In the digital work plans, the user receives a stepwise depiction of the work that is to be executed. This also provides the user with a temporal relation: *What? When?*
- In the work plans, the task descriptions, enriched with geometric visualization and animations, define the work operations and clarify the question *“How?”*.
- The geometric allocation of components in the camera display visualizes for the user the location for the action: *Where?* In particular, with ad hoc operations and unfamiliar environments, this function helps users orient themselves better in the environment and to more quickly find the location for the action. At the same time, complex installations/removal situations can be better clarified with the aid of animation paths. With untrained personnel, this function helps them to more quickly work their way in, without having to search instructions and stored drawings in order to find where the action needs to be taken.
- Displaying further information, helps communicate the conditions under which operations need to be executed and answers the questions *“How?”*. Particularly with ad hoc operations and unclear environmental conditions on-site, this function helps personnel to better prepare for implementing it on-site.

3.2 Generating Information

In order to prepare Augmented Reality based service instructions, it is imperative to generate the information content that is to be visualized. The so-called Authoring specifies the procedure and content of the AR session. The author defines the visible content by linking geometric, meta data (work plans,

additional information, documents, appointments etc.) and functionality and assigning a tracking method to them. As soon as the camera identifies the tracking object, the user's view is enriched with information such as virtual objects and text, *Heinig (2015)*.

Existing authoring tools are proprietary desktop editors which have been developed by the respective software providers for a concrete AR application. Most software solutions are aimed at visualizing standard maintenance tasks with simple animations e.g., remove a bolt with a spanner. Generally, experienced service technicians already know how to use standard tools and to complete simple work steps though, thus further instruction on these tasks is not needed. However, instructions and support for service technicians who have to execute ad hoc operation requiring them to follow situation specific procedures yet lack information on how to proceed, are neglected, *Roberto et al. (2016)*. There are no suitable approaches for these cases and independent of existing approaches, the authoring remains a manual, time consuming process that means considerable expenditure. It thus remains an important task to reduce the effort required to prepare and manage AR based service instruction.

To not burden indirect areas with additional expenditures for creating information, the authoring process needs to be designed as effortlessly as possible. It is therefore necessary to systematically transfer and reuse already available work plans and instructions into the new system. The prerequisite for this is the modelling of a uniform data format that includes visualizations. Another challenge is finding a way to easily produce animations. This is especially true for those animations where it is not possible to fall back on ready-made templates and special maintenance situations must be considered. At the same time, it is necessary to have tools for verifying maintenance content in real-time and which also allow the impact of the content to be verified in AR. Above all, the planning and executing ad hoc operations, in which maintenance instructions must be individually tailored to the maintenance or repair work on site and the component's environment (e.g., the engine), has to be simplified.

4. Modular Authoring Concept

Following, in order to be able to meet the aforementioned challenges, we will describe our approach to a consistent authoring process. Our approach is aimed at designing a DARS authoring system for generating service instructions for maintenance and repair work on ship equipment components such as engines or compressors. Geometric data as well as additional work plan data for the equipment components are already available. The authoring has to be based on this data, extend it with additional information about operations and depict it visually so that it is clearly understood. To do so modules which can be subdivided into three categories – data, content and tools – are required, Fig.3. The data category targets the import and reuse of already existing information and describes the connection to industrial databases and subsystems.

Fig.3: Module overview

The second category refers to the necessary extension of the program for generating digital content. The last category concentrates on the required tools users can implement to generate content.

4.1. Data

Generally, available data includes data about orders, work plans, spare parts and design. This data is necessary to generate the job cards and (ad hoc) work plans described in Section 3. Depending on the business, data is managed using ERP, PDM/PLM or content management systems (CMS). Usually data about orders, work plans and spare parts is stored in an ERP system, while design data is managed by a PDM/PLM system. Connecting to the PDM/PLM system makes it possible to access CAD models and part lists required for geometrically depicting the maintenance objects in DARS. Moreover, the connection provides access to always up-to-date design data. Changes and modifications to design data made by participating divisions are assigned a version number and directly transferred to the new system. In addition to work plan data, enterprises generate and manage technical documents about the maintenance objects. Technical editorial systems, which are allocated to the content management system (CMS), generate, update and edit the documents. The technical documents describe instructions for inspections, maintenance, repairs and troubleshooting. To supplement these instructions, further documents including lists of tools and aids, consumables or technical values (e.g., tightening torque) are stored. This information is critical for service personnel and as mentioned in Section 2, it currently needs to be laboriously sought out in these other documents. It is thus vital that these supplementary documents also be depicted in the DARS. The prerequisite for this is a CMS connection. In order to clearly present content and reduce search times, corresponding geometric and meta information from existing databases have to be merged and simultaneously depicted. Therefore, part list entries (e.g., component levels and names) must be linked with corresponding CAD models. This is managed automatically via uniform identifiers. The generated CAD component list is enriched with additional component relevant information such as required tools or tightening torques. To do so, attributes, which describe the type of supplementary information, are set for the components. Each attribute is assigned a corresponding characteristic e.g., a value or a name. Fig.4 provides an overview of the links between the geometric and meta information and shows the attribution of the generated CAD components. The attribution of CAD components can be extended as desired and adjusted to the various operational requirements. The linking of geometric and meta information and the extension of CAD models with supplementary information relevant to components form the foundation for the authoring process.

Fig.4: Linking geometric and meta data information

4.2 Content

In the preceding section, we described the data basis required to digitally supply information during service work. In this next section, we will discuss what other content is necessary in order to clearly present this data in the DARS. This content can be subdivided into four classes: work plans, animations, feedback and constrains.

4.2.1. Work Plans

The DARS is responsible for visualizing the work plan. The work plan reflects the work sequence and describes it. This content, which is already available in a CMS, is transferred to the authoring system (Section 4.1) and can be opened in it. The work step descriptions are linked to the corresponding components with the aid of uniform identifiers (e.g., component names). To prepare service technicians for assignments where the workload can only be conditionally estimated because the on-site situation of the maintenance object is not sufficiently known, there must be a possibility to modify existing work plans to given circumstances. Depending on the application scenario, modifications might include generating new work plans or steps, or editing existing work plans. Fig.5 provides an overview of the basic modules for generating work plans. The program modelling of the digital work plans follows a standard system: Each work plan is described by a sequence of work steps with defined position numbers. Both the work sequence and linked work steps have a name, a unique identification number and a type designator. These identifiers make it possible to store and reuse generated modules in the authoring system. Furthermore, attributes, which subdivide the information modules into different classes (e.g., required qualification level or access permission), can be stored for the information modules. The DARS user logs in with their account on the display system and the work is displayed in the degree of detail allocated to their qualifications, thus avoiding disassembly and assembly errors due to untrained personnel. When editing work plans, the author can edit content and enrich supplement information such as tips, text, images, video or audio data. To do so, the author uses the imported data from the databases described in Section 4.1.

Fig.5: Modules for developing work plans

4.2.2. Animations

To clarify work tasks, an animation generator is used to create and store animations that supplement work steps. The animations are divided into three categories: movement, effect and scene animations. Up to now, service personnel have had to derive the actual assembly/disassembly situation of the object on-site from the written description. Any errors in interpreting the instructions could cause mistakes during the assembly/disassembly and increase costs. Technical editors have thus worked extensively to ensure written descriptions are as clear as possible. Often, it is not enough to just summarize what needs to be done and long passages of text are therefore unavoidable. However, if we look at what happens in practice, it is specifically these long texts that are frequently not read and are omitted. Since written presentations are not sufficient, a visual representation must be generated instead. The first category, movement animations, entail repositioning objects along a defined path as well as rotations (around its

own axis). These types of animations are primarily used to visualize assembly/disassembly work. Effect animations on the other hand, support users in pinpointing the selected maintenance object. By highlighting objects with a colour, they can be more quickly allocated to a work step and thus reduce search times. Finally, the third category, scene animations, supports the above described CAD mode. The creator of the animation can set the virtual camera so that users can visualize the maintenance object from a suitable perspective.

4.2.3. Feedback

Documenting the conducted work is a key element of servicing. The documentation module helps generate application specific templates for the feedback of data from the operation site. The authoring system provides different modules which can be combined to create digital feedback forms for different work steps. These modules are subdivided into: selections of predefined entries (single and multiple choice), open text fields, or photographs. Digital feedback forms can be customized for each work step and tied to it. Generated forms are saved and can be selected for reuse as a template. When creating feedback forms, authors can choose from different configurations. To compile measurements, they can create an open text field and define the measurement designator and technical unit (e.g. amps, volts). To record test values, the author creates corresponding entries for the selection options. When the work step for example is ‘check the engine noise’, the service technician can choose between the predefined possibilities: ‘not noticeable’, ‘noticeable’, ‘strongly noticeable’ (single choice). While inspection objects, any special incidents that occur can be noted in an additional comments box or with saved photos. For this feedback data, the author places an open text field with a defined designator and activates the option to include photos. Besides compiling inspection data, progress data, which describes the status of a work step (‘still to do’, ‘in progress’, ‘done’), can be logged in the work plans.

4.2.4. Constrains

Determining the state of a maintenance object through measurements and tests is always related to a decision and deriving actions, Fig.6. Service technicians record the values for the measurements and check, evaluate them and decide which actions (measures) are to be taken. These decisions are tied to conditions e.g., exceeding a given operating value or wear limit. The inspection plans are used to laboriously assign conditions, only then can the required work plans be found before implementing the necessary measures.

Fig.6: Event oriented work plan

To reduce the amount of work, in DARS, events (e.g., entered test values) are linked to selected functions. The linked functions refer the user e.g., to the work plans needed to execute the measure as a result of the occurring event (e.g., exceeding the wear limit). The DARS creator uses the authoring system to define events and link them to the functions. In addition to events during inspections, events from the progress data can be linked with designated functions. In a sequence of work steps, the next

step can only be processed/activated when the preceding step has been marked done. When the “done button” is toggled, the button object triggers an event designated “clicked”. Other objects such as the next work step, react to this event and are opened or superposed. The same functionality can also be applied for diagnosing faults during repair work. During diagnostics, service technicians record test values, thus triggering events in the program. The objects stored in the program e.g., work plans react to the events and are recommended to the service technicians as solution measures.

4.3 Tools

The content described in the preceding section should be able to be generated as easily as possible. The functions required to do so can be subdivided into two categories: generating 3D scenes and animations, and generating text oriented elements e.g., descriptions and conditions.

4.3.1. Virtual Reality

As research on shipbuilding engineering with Virtual Reality (VR) has shown, *Nedess et al. (2009)*, due to the visualization of immersive 3D objects and interaction with them, Virtual Reality systems are superior to traditional 3D systems in regards to interaction, *Xu et al. (2008)*. This advantage can also be used for creating digital maintenance instructions:

- The loaded CAD models and/or laser scan data of the captured environment can better visualize the maintenance situations, thus allowing obstacles and possible challenges to be identified early-on.
- Animations are generated by manipulating 3D objects. The user can grab 3D objects directly with the controller, positioning and orienting them as desired. There is thus no need to tediously create position and orientation parameters, as is the case with conventional CAD applications.
- After recording the animation, the user can play the stored animation in the virtual environment, test it for suitability and modify it as needed.
- The VR session can also be used to prepare service technicians for the operation on-site. The animations in the virtual environment allow the generated maintenance work to be demonstrated in advance and discussed if necessary. At the same time, the corresponding work plans are displayed and used to prepare the work.

These advantages of virtual technologies significantly impact productivity, especially when creating service instructions for ad hoc operations.

4.3.2. Desktop

Due to its suitability for text, a desktop application is better suited for creating descriptions of work steps or supplementing existing work plans with. The desktop application also includes the animation creation for phases that precede and follow the generation of work plans. Both visualization concepts are based on the same software solution for the authoring system and allow the user various possibilities for interacting and entering data to take into account different applications.

5. Prototypical Implementation

Having introduced the individual components of a system for authoring digital augmented reality based service documents in the preceding sections, we will now clarify how to work with the system.

5.1. Ad hoc Authoring with Virtual Reality

Fig.7 depicts the implementation of the authoring system modules in the Virtual Reality application. At the start of the VR session, the user imports the required CAD models into the software program. The user guides the session via the controller. The controller’s buttons are assigned to user interaction

and control features. With these, the user can navigate the virtual environment, manipulate models and operate buttons on the immersive menu.

Fig.7: Virtual Reality authoring for Augmented Reality based service instructions

The menu allows the user to configure work plans and to compile the information content for each work step. To do so, the user activates the corresponding work step and selects content such as animations. The menu window adjusts to the selected elements and shows the user further options. At the same time, the controller's button assignments adjust to the selected content, so that the user can select specific functions directly from the controller e.g., start and end recordings. This allows the user to easily operate and quickly select required functions. To generate an animation, the author uses the controller to grasp the CAD model that is to be animated and moves it along the correct disassembly path, Fig.8. To ensure the correct disassembly path, the software program recognizes when a selected component will collide with one of the surrounding components and restricts movement according to the collision-free paths.

Fig.8: Recording animations

For simple animations, e.g., moving along a longitudinal axis, the software independently recognizes the collision-free way and creates an animation. The user then sets the length of the movement animation via the controller menu. When done, the generated scene content can be played and verified in terms of its completeness and suitability. The 1:1 depiction of the CAD model in the virtual environment, allows the user to replay the stored animation with the actual size of the components. Possible complications with the assembly/disassembly can thus be better visualized and discovered already during the VR session and planned anew. At the end of the VR session, the created content is stored in an internal data format and can be visualized on the DARS.

5.2. Visualization of Ad hoc Work Plans with DARS

Fig.9 shows the generated work plan as displayed on the digital Augmented Reality based service document. The data is imported in the DARS and can subsequently be opened and displayed. The work plan is selected via the menu and the corresponding work steps are visualized. When a work step is selected, the stored information content is shown and the corresponding 3D objects of the components in the actual environment are displayed. Where applicable, the assembly or disassembly is also animated. Via the work step controls, the previously generated animations can be played or the emulation can be returned to its original state. Moreover, via the colour differentiated buttons, it is possible to report the status of a work step and when needed to add information textually.

Fig.9: Digital Augmented Reality based service document

5.3. Virtual Reality Support during Servicing

Should questions or uncertainties arise while executing a work step, the service technician can also call the head office for assistance. Through a connection between the DARS and the VR environment with a contact person from the head office, the actual on-site situation can be transferred as well as the uncertainties or problems that arose, so that a solution can be found by the remote contact person/expert. Again, due to the use of VR, the expert receives a clearer impression of the on-site situation, *Friedewald et al. (2017b)*. The software program provides a report of the technician's current task in DARS and the selected work plan. At the same time, the corresponding session is loaded in the VR environment and opened. First, data about the work progression (i.e., done, active, remaining work steps) from the DARS is synchronized with the work plan in VR. The expert can thus better understand the actual work progression and verify it. Parallel to the work plan, the expert sees the state of the maintenance object's assembly/disassembly. The transmission of the DARS' camera position lets the expert see the technician's current perspective and orientation on-site. Thus making it easier for the expert to immerse themselves in the technician's situation and to more quickly identify the problem and possible errors. Given a sufficient connection, audio and video signals can also be transmitted. The expert uses the authoring functions described above in Section 4 to instruct and support the technician in solving the problem. To develop the instructions, the expert creates work steps with task descriptions. To clarify the work steps, the expert uses the animation functions. In addition to the animations, the author/expert

can access and use symbols such as arrows. These symbols allow the expert to guide the technician to the correct component position. Fig.10 shows the use of 3D navigation arrows to clarify the work task. The expert selects the arrow symbol in the immersive menu and uses the controller to move it to the correct position of the maintenance object. The transformation data of the arrow object is transmitted via the remote connection to the AR system. The technician can then see and track the positioning in real time based on the orientation of the arrow, then execute the intended task e.g., an inspection and provide feedback. The use of 3D navigation arrows is particularly well suited when there is no CAD data for the real environment and 3D laser scans data of the real environment have to be used for generating digital work plans, Fig.10.

Fig.10: Virtual Reality Support during Servicing

6. Summary

The use of Augmented Reality based service instructions to support service technicians during maintenance work covers a wide range of use cases. These include for example inspection, maintenance and / or repair work on engines and / or plants in the maritime industry. At the same time, the AR based service instructions are used by differently qualified employees. The maritime suppliers have thus worked extensively to fit the information content to the respective use case. This paper shows how information modules can be used to author AR based service instructions for different use cases in a modular way. For this purpose, the required information modules are worked out and summarized in categories. At the same time, a structure for configuring the information contents from the modules is prepared, which enables a uniform representation of the information contents for different maintenance use cases in the maritime industry. To not burden indirect areas with additional expenditure for creating the information modules, the article describes a procedure for transferring existing information content from the databases and subsystems of the maritime suppliers. The usual and laborious way for generating animations is the use and adaption of predefined templates. To counter this effort especially for ad hoc operations with a high degree of customization a Virtual Reality interface for the creation of instructions and animations has been developed. The use of VR application is particularly suitable for the preparation of service instructions in the case of unexpected repair task in which ad hoc a solution must be achieved to avoid a long-term machine failure.

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References

- AZUMA, R.T. (1997), *A survey of Augmented Reality*, Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments 6, pp.355-385
- DIN (2012), *DIN 3105: Grundlagen der Instandhaltung*, Beuth
- FRIEDEWALD, A.; HALATA, P.; MELUZOV, N.; LÖDDING, H. (2016), *Die Produktivitätswirkung von Augmented Reality in der Unikatfertigung*, Megatrend Digitalisierung - Potenziale der Arbeits- und Betriebsorganisation, GITO-Verlag, pp.141-162
- FRIEDEWALD, A.; MELUZOV, N.; ROST, R. (2017a), *Potentials of Augmented Reality in aircraft assembly and MRO*, 6th Int. Workshop on Aircraft System Technologies (AST 2017), Aachen, pp.295-306
- FRIEDEWALD, A.; MELUZOV, N.; ROST, R.; SCHRÖDER, H. (2017b), *Virtual-Reality-Support bei Wartungsprozessen*, ESI-Forum in Deutschland, Neu-Isenburg, pp.110-116
- HALATA, P. (2018), *Augmented-Reality-gestützte Informationsversorgung für die Unikatproduktion*, PhD thesis, TU Hamburg-Harburg
- HEINIG, M. (2015), *Nutzung von Virtuellen Technologien für die Montageplanung von Unikaten*, PhD thesis, TU Hamburg-Harburg
- NEDESS, C.; FRIEDEWALD, A.; SCHÄFER, C.; SCHLEUSNER, S.; NEUMANN, L. (2009), *Schiffbau-Engineering mit Virtual Reality - Adaption an die Unikatfertigung (USE-VR)*, Final Report, TU Hamburg-Harburg
- ROBERTO, R.A.; LIMA, J.P.; MOTA, R.C.; TEICHRIEB, V. (2016), *Authoring tools for Augmented Reality, an analysis and classification of content design tools*, Design, User Experience, and Usability: Technological Contexts, Springer, pp. 237–248
- XU, J.; TÜMLER, J.; MECKE, R. (2008), *A Concept for Augmented Reality Based Authoring of Augmented Reality Content*, 7. Paderborner Workshop Augmented & Virtual Reality in der Produktentstehung, Paderborn, pp.95-106

Estimating Ship Emissions Based on AIS Big Data for the Port of Rio de Janeiro

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Abstract

Automatic Identification System (AIS) data stores huge quantity of information regarding the safety of ships and port facilities in the international maritime transport sector. However, this big database is not only useful for the security of ships operations and port facilities. It can also be helpful for other important functions in maritime traffic such as reducing environmental impacts. This study develops an analytical approach to quantify ship emissions in the Guanabara Bay of Rio de Janeiro (Brazil) using AIS database. The model is applied to quantify Green House Gas (GHG) emissions through the assessment of fuel consumption calculated for each individual vessel. The results show that the proposed methodology is efficient to estimate total ship emissions over Rio de Janeiro Port area and Guanabara Bay. We suggest that quantifying the amount of emissions from ships in order to fulfil IMO regulations and reduce the health impacts of people who are living in surrounding areas of high maritime traffic is important for decision makers and for the maritime authorities.

1. Introduction

Every day, more than 2.5 quintillion bytes of data are created. This is known as big data, the datasets whose size and structure is beyond the ability of typical programming tools to data collection, store, manage and analyses in a reasonable time and exceed the capacity of their perception by a human, *Zicari (2014), Miloslavskaya and Tolstoy (2016)*.

Big data is present in key sectors and it has revolutionized the industry over the past several years. Companies across the various travel and transportation industry segments as airlines, airports, railways, freight logistics and others have been handling large amounts of data for years. In addition, today's advanced analytics technologies and techniques enable organizations to extract insights from data with previously unachievable levels of sophistication, speed and accuracy, *IBM (2014)*. Nowadays, big data is getting popular in shipping where large amounts of information is collected to better understand and improve logistics, emissions, energy consumption and maintenance. Using satellite navigation and sensors, trucks, airplanes or ships can be tracked in real-time. In shipping, the automatic identification system (AIS) and vessel traffic services (VTS) are mainly used to prevent collisions at sea. However, storing this information in data warehouse for a certain period allows the scientist to extract hidden knowledge from this bulk.

In early 2017, the ship world commercial fleet grew by 3.15% and reached a total of 1.86 billion DWT that consisted of 93161 vessels including bulk carriers, oil tankers, general cargo ships, container ships and others. Consequently, it produces a major marine traffic and a growth of fuel consumption contributing to global Green House Gas (GHG) emissions at sea impacting the climate change, *UNCTAD (2017)*. Ship emissions as a source of air pollution have been outlined in various studies worldwide, *Cooper (2003), Dalsoren et al. (2009)*. The GHG emissions of ship engines have raised the concern of International Maritime Organization (IMO) on the consequences for environment and human health. IMO first adopted MARPOL Annex VI in 1997. At present, IMO limits the main air pollutants in ships exhaust gas (sulphur oxides SO_x, nitrous oxides NO_x, Particulate Matter (PM), and Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) emissions from tankers). It also regulates shipboard incineration, and prohibits deliberate Ozone Depleting Substances (ODS) emissions. IMO introduces Emission Control Areas (ECA), and it defines the energy efficiency design index (EEDI) and ship energy efficiency management plan (SEEMP). These regulations aim to reduce emissions and increase ship energy efficiency.

Some authors focused their research in emissions calculation in various regions around the world. In this study, we identify three locations of the emission evaluations. The first devoted to assess the emissions in oceanic navigation. The second devoted to the evaluation of emissions in coastline and inland waterways. The last one focusing on emissions around ports, Table I. However, the emissions studies in the literature are mostly located in Europe and Asia, opening a gap for studies on emissions in South America.

Since 2009 studies about emissions are presented in literature, the first developments are in Turkey by the same group of researchers, *Deniz and Kilic (2009)*, *Deniz et al. (2010)*, *Kilic and Deniz (2010)*. These studies are about the estimation of shipping emissions in Candarli Gulf, Izmit Gulf and in the region of Ambarli port, the amounts of emission from ships can be calculated with the activity-based emission model.

Nunes et al. (2017) reviewed 26 papers about emissions calculations since 2010. In the majority of the cases the calculation of emissions are in port and during anchoring, most authors attributed that to container ships. Almost of studies reviewed are in Europe and Asia.

Styhre et al. (2017) analyzed the level of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from ships in port based on annual data from four ports in four continents (Gothenburg, Long Beach, Osaka and Sydney). They established that the potential to reduce emissions in a port area depends on how often a ship revisits a port. Also in this study, South America is not considering.

Heitmann and Petersen (2014) analyzed how much the shipping sector could contribute to efficient global CO₂ emission reductions and thus could always achieve global cost savings. *Fan et al. (2016)* study the emission factors of domestic vessels and ocean-going vessels and the potential impact of ship emissions on the surrounding atmospheric environment. They concluded that ship emissions have a significant impact on the entire Yangtze River Delta region and on greater East China. Moreover, *Winnes et al. (2015)* quantified the potential reductions of ships GHG emissions from efforts implemented by the port of Gothenburg.

From this state of the art review, five different methods to assess the emissions has been identified. The main equations have been related below whereas Table I: specify which method is used in each related publication.

$$E_{CO_2} = \frac{D}{V} \times (\%MCR \times RP \times SFOC \times EF_{CO_2})_{ME} + \frac{D}{V} \times (\%MCR \times RP \times SFOC \times EF_{CO_2})_{AE} \quad (1)$$

Where,

E_{CO_2}	is the total emission of CO ₂ over the journey in kilograms (kg);
D	is the total distance travelled on the journey in nautical miles (nm);
V	is the average cruising speed of the vessel in knots (kn=nm/hr);
$\%MCR$	is the average load on the particular engine as a fraction of the total installed power of the particular engine. <i>MCR</i> stands for ‘maximum continuous rate’.
RP	is the maximum rated power of the main or auxiliary engines in kilowatts (kW);
$SFOC$	is the specific fuel-oil consumption rate of the engine in kg of fuel per kilowatt-hour of engine output (kg/kWh);
EF_{CO_2}	is the emission factor for CO ₂ for the fuel type used by the main or auxiliary engines in kg of CO ₂ emitted per kg of fuel burnt;
ME	is the main engines of the vessel;
AE	is the Auxiliary engines of the vessel.

$$E_{At\ Sea} = D \times [ME \times LF + AE \times LF] \times EF_{At\ Sea} / V \quad (2)$$

Where,

$E_{At\ Sea}$	is the total emission in grams (g);
D	is the total distance travelled by ship in nautical miles (nm);
V	is the speed of the vessel in knots (kn=nm/hr);
ME	is the main engine load in kilowatts (kW);
AE	is the auxiliary engine load in kilowatts (kW);

LF is the load factor (%);
RP is the maximum rated power of the main or auxiliary engines in kilowatts (kW);
EF_{At Sea} is the emission factor.

$$\sum E_{ikms} = t_{km} \times P_{kms} \times EF_{ims} \quad (3)$$

Where, **E_{ikms}** is the emission amount of pollutant which occurs from machine k of s type of ship during the operation mode m;
t_{km} is the running time of k machine working on m operation mode;
P_{kms} is the power of the k machine defined by the type and the gross tonnage of the ship;
EF_{ims} is the specific emission amount of engine depending on the ship type and operation mode.

$$\text{Equation 1: } E_i = \sum_{jklm} S_{jkm}(GT) \times t_{km} \times F_{ijklm}$$

Where, **E_i** is the total emission of pollutant i;
S_{jkm}(GT) is the daily consumption of fuel j in ship class k in mode m as a function of gross tonnage;
t_{km} is the days in navigation of ships of class k with engine type l using fuel j in mode m;
F_{ijklm} is the average emission factor of pollutant i from fuel j in engine type l in mode m (detailed average emission factor).

The last methodology identified is the ship traffic emission assessment model (STEAM) developed by *Jalkanen et al. (2009)* in their studies around the Baltic Sea area. The model is based on AIS data and uses some algorithms to estimate the emissions with the IMO curves for NO_x emissions as well as for the prediction of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, SO₂ and CO₂ emissions.

Table I identifies each study, including information about year of publication, the authors involved, the methodology used based on the above detailed equations, the application zone of the methodology, the continent, and the location (1: oceanic navigation, 2: coastline and inland navigation, 3: ports).

Table I: Summary of the state of the art related to ship emissions assessment

Title of the study	Year	Reference	Methodology	Application zone / Continent	Group
Carbon emissions from international cruise ship passengers' travel to and from New Zealand	2010	<i>Howitt et al. (2010)</i>	Eq. 1	New Zealand / Oceania	1
Estimation of shipping emissions in Candarli Gulf, Turk.	2010	<i>Deniz et al. (2010)</i>	Eq. 2	Candarli Gulf, Turk / Europe	2
Inventory of shipping emissions in Izmit Gulf, Turkey	2010	<i>Kilic and Deniz (2010)</i>	Eq. 3	Izmit Gulf, Turkey / Europe	2
Estimation of Exhaust Emissions of Marine Traffic Using AIS Data (Case Study: Madura Strait Area, Indonesia)	2010	<i>Pitana et al. (2010)</i>	Eq. 4	Madura Strait area / Oceania, Asia	2
Estimation of exhaust emission from ocean-going vessels in Hong Kong	2012	<i>Yau et al. (2012)</i>	Eq. 4	Hong Kong / Asia	1
A Comprehensive Inventory of the Ship Traffic Exhaust Emissions in the Baltic Sea from 2006 to 2009	2013	<i>Jalkanen et al. (2013)</i>	STEAM	Baltic sea / Europe	2
Atmospheric emissions of European SECA shipping: long-term projections	2013	<i>Kalli et al. (2013)</i>	STEAM2	Baltic sea, the North sea, and the English channel / Europe	2
Policy change driven by an AIS-assisted marine emission inventory in Hong Kong	2013	<i>Ng et al. (2013)</i>	Eq. 3	Hong Kong	1
Ships in a city harbour: An economic valuation of atmospheric emissions	2013	<i>McArthur and Osland (2013)</i>	Eq. 2	Port Ofbergen in Norway / Europe	2 & 3
Emission inventories for ships in the arctic based on satellite sampled AIS data	2014	<i>Winther et al. (2014)</i>	Eq. 1	Arctic area north of 58.95n / ECA	1

An AIS-based approach to calculate atmospheric emissions from the UK fishing fleet	2015	<i>Coello et al. (2015)</i>	Eq. 4	UK fishing fleet / Europe	2
Methodologies for estimating shipping emissions and energy consumption: A comparative analysis of current methods	2015	<i>Moreno-Gutiérrez et al. (2015)</i>	Eq. 1	Strait of Gibraltar / Europe	2
The Estimation of Container Ship Emissions at Berth in Taiwan	2015	<i>Cullinane et al. (2015)</i>	Eq. 2	Berth in Taiwan / Asia	2 & 3
An AIS-based high-resolution ship emission inventory and its uncertainty in Pearl River Delta region, China	2016	<i>Li et al. (2016)</i>	Eq. 1 and 2	Pearl river delta region, China / Asia	2
Global assessment of shipping emissions in 2015 on a high spatial and temporal resolution	2017	<i>Johansson et al. (2017)</i>	STEAM3	Worldwide	1
High-spatiotemporal-resolution ship emission inventory of China based on AIS data in 2014	2017	<i>Chen et al. (2017)</i>	Eq. 2	China / Asia	2
Contribution of ship emissions to the concentration of PM2.5 A comprehensive study using AIS data and WRF-Chem model in Bohai Rim Region, China	2018	<i>Chen et al. (2018)</i>	Eq. 2	Bohai Rim region, China / Asia	2
Estimation and assessment of shipping emissions in the region of Ambarli Port, Turkey	2009	<i>Deniz and Kilic (2009)</i>	Eq. 4	Ambarli Port, Turkey / Europe	3
Air quality impact assessment of at-berth ship emissions: Case-study for the project of a new freight port	2010	<i>Lonati et al. (2010)</i>	Eq. 4	Mediterranean Sea / Europe	3
Ship emissions and their externalities for the port of Piraeus e Greece	2010	<i>Tzannatos (2010)</i>	Eq. 2	port of Piraeus e Greece / Europe	3
Estimating GHG emissions of marine ports: The case of Barcelona	2011	<i>Villalba and Gemechu (2011)</i>	Eq. 2	Barcelona / Europe	3
Estimating transportation-related greenhouse gas emissions in the Port of Busan	2011	<i>Shin and Cheong (2011)</i>	Eq. 3	Port of Busan / Asia	3
Estimating the environmental costs of port related emissions: The case of Kaohsiung	2012	<i>Berechman and Tseng (2012)</i>	Eq. 2	Kaohsiung, Taiwan / Asia	3
An Investigation on the Effects of Ship Sourced Emissions in Izmir Port, Turkey	2013	<i>SaracoLlu et al. (2013)</i>	Eq. 2	Izmir Port, Turkey / Europe	3
Assessing greenhouse gas emissions from port vessel operations at the Port of Incheon	2013	<i>Chang et al. (2013)</i>	Eq. 4	Korea's Port of Incheon / Asia	3
Current and future emission estimates of exhaust gases and particles from shipping at the largest port in Korea	2014	<i>Song and Shong (2014)</i>	Eq. 2	port in Korea / Asia	3
Manoeuvring and hotelling external costs: enough for alternative energy sources?	2014	<i>Sanabra et al. (2013)</i>	Eq. 2	Spanish port / Europe	3
Ship emissions inventory, social cost and eco-efficiency in Shanghai Yangshan port	2014	<i>Song (2014)</i>	Eq. 2	Shanghai / Asia	3
Sulfur dioxide emission estimates from merchant vessels in a Port area and related control strategies	2014	<i>Liu et al. (2014)</i>	Eq. 2 and 3	Port of Kaohsiung, Taiwan / Asia	3
Evaluating the social cost of cruise ships air emissions in major ports of Greece	2015	<i>Maragkogianni and Papaefthimiou (2015)</i>	Eq. 2	ports of Greece / Asia	3
Modelling of ship engine exhaust emissions in ports and extensive coastal waters based on terrestrial AIS data e An Australian case study	2015	<i>Goldsworthy and Goldsworthy (2015)</i>	Eq. 2	Australian coast and Australian ports / Oceania	3

Port-city exhaust emission model: an application to cruise and ferry operations in Las Palmas Port.	2015	<i>Tichavska and Tovar (2015)</i>	STEAM	Las Palmas port / Africa	3
Estimating ship emissions based on AIS data for port of Tianjin, China	2016	<i>Chen et al. (2016)</i>	Eq. 2	port of Tianjin, China / Asia	3
Effects of slow steaming strategies on a ship fleet	2017	<i>Cepeda et al. (2017)</i>	Eq. 1	Bulk carrier ship fleet, route Brazil to China	1
Air emissions from ships in port: Does regulation make a difference?	2017	<i>Tichavska et al. (2017)</i>	STEAM	Las Palmas, St. Petersburg, and Hong Kong / Africa, Europe and Asia	3
Estimation and spatio-temporal analysis of ship exhaust emission in a port area	2017	<i>Huang et al. (2017)</i>	Eq. 2 and 3	Ningbo-Zhoushan port in China / Asia	3
Ship emission inventory and its impact on the PM2.5 air pollution in Qingdao Port, North China	2017	<i>Chen et al. (2017)</i>	Eq. 2	Qingdao Port, North China / Asia	3

Table I helps us to identify the state of the art methodology among the 36 studies reviewed. Eq.(2) appeared to be the most used, see Fig.1. Later in this paper, Eq.(2) will be improved in order to assess the emissions.

Fig.1: Methodologies used to inventory the ship emissions based on Table I

Despite the existence of several studies about the quantification of the impact of contaminants on the environment of the Rio de Janeiro Bay there still a lack of studying the emissions of the marine traffic in the region. Table II identifies several papers on environmental factors including information about year of publication, the authors involved. Most of the studies relates to water pollution and concentration of pollutants in the Bay. Only one study deals with supply boats emissions trying to identify what is the proportion of the emissions related to ships in the data measured by the air pollution meters of the State Institute Environment (INEA).

In this paper, detailed characteristics of the emissions over Rio de Janeiro are reported based on AIS data. The estimations show the quantity of tonnes of CO₂, SO₂, NO_x, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} emitted and dispersed around the Rio de Janeiro bay. This study complies with the objective of inventorying emissions around Rio de Janeiro (Ganabara Bay including port), following the recommendations of the IMO to lower emissions until 2020. If emissions are not estimated, we could not reach the goal of reducing them.

Table II: Summary of the environmental factors studied in the surrounding of Guanabara Bay

Title of the study	Year	Reference	Factors studied
Spatial variation, speciation and sedimentary records of mercury in the Guanabara Bay (Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)	2012	<i>Covelli et al. (2012)</i>	Hg accumulation in bottom sediments on the northwestern side of the Bay.
Stormwater impact in Guanabara Bay (Rio de Janeiro): Evidences of seasonal variability in the dynamic of the sediment heavy metals	2013	<i>Fonseca et al. (2013)</i>	Concentration and fractionation of the heavy metals within the sediments of the bay.
Emissões de NO _x e SO ₂ por embarcações do tipo supply boat fundeadas no Porto do Rio de Janeiro e o impacto na qualidade do ar	2015	<i>Machado de Paula (2015)</i>	NO _x and SO ₂ emissions from supply boats anchored in Guanabara Bay
Comparações entre medições em tempo real da pCO ₂ aquática com estimativas indiretas em dois estuários tropicais contrastantes: o estuário eutrofizado da Baía de Guanabara (RJ) 2016	2016	<i>Cotovicz et al. (2016)</i>	Concentration of water pCO ₂ , with calculations based on pH and total alkalinity (TA) in two contrasting Brazilian estuaries: GB and the São Francisco River Estuary (Alagoas).
Spatio-temporal variability of methane (CH ₄) concentrations and diffusive fluxes from a tropical coastal embayment surrounded by a large urban area (Guanabara Bay, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)	2016	<i>Cotovicz et al. (2016)</i>	Urban pollution as CH ₄ to the coastal waters
Ecological risks of trace metals in Guanabara Bay, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil: An index analysis approach	2016	<i>De Carvalho Aguiar et al. (2016)</i>	Contamination of Guanabara Bay through the selection of different environmental indices as metal contamination and also investigate potential biological hazard.
An environmental overview of Guanabara Bay, Rio de Janeiro	2016	<i>Soares-Gomes et al. (2016)</i>	Geomorphology, climatology, hydrology, geography and biodiversity aspects
Microplastic pollution of the beaches of Guanabara Bay, Southeast	2016	<i>De Carvalho and Neto (2016)</i>	Composition and distribution of micro-plastics and small plastic fragments on the beaches of Guanabara Bay
Environmental change in Guanabara Bay, SE Brazil, based in microfaunal, pollen and geochemical proxies in sedimentary cores	2017	<i>Neto et al. (2017)</i>	Sediment transport of pollution (municipal wastewater, deforestation, urban runoff and industrial effluents)
The urban heat island in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in the last 30 years using remote sensing data	2018	<i>Peres et al. (2018)</i>	Analysis of land-surface temperature of "vegetation" land-use class in Metropolitan Area of Rio de Janeiro
Determination of water quality, toxicity and estrogenic activity in a nearshore marine environment in Rio de Janeiro, Southeastern Brazil	2018	<i>Do Nascimento et al. (2018)</i>	It evaluates the estrogenic potential of water sampled from different depths and from areas with differential contamination levels throughout Jurujuba Sound

2. Methodology and data

2.1. Study area

The Guanabara Bay is an oceanic bay, located on the Southeast Brazil in the state of Rio de Janeiro between 2240S and 2300S latitude and between 04300W and 04318W longitude. The Bay is known as the second largest bay in area in Brazil (after the All Saints' bay). It has an area of approximately 384 km², including islands. On its western shore lies the city of Rio de Janeiro and fifteen other municipalities. The populated region around the studied area is composed by the following 16 municipalities, Fig.2. It was representing 12 million people in 2017 based on Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics data. The main port area in the Ganabara Bay is the Port of Rio de Janeiro, located in downtown of the homonymous city of Rio de Janeiro at 2345 S and 4445 W, Fig.3. International shipping associated with the development of the country and petroleum industry increased the marine traffic through the Bay, which poses significant risks to the biodiversity and the marine environment, the livelihood of the coastal communities, and the fishing and tourism industries. Five types of facilities are distributed throughout the bay that are heart of industry and mass transit of people.

These places are: dry cargo terminal, passenger terminals, petroleum terminals, shipyards, navy facilities and yacht clubs. This study examines the distribution of the emissions produced by the marine traffic that may potentially affect up to 12 million people.

Fig.2: Map of the regions surrounding the bay with total of habitant in 2017 based on Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics data

Fig.3: View of Guanabara Bay included six types of industrial/commercial facilities in the area

2.2. Automatic Identification System (AIS) data and ship information data

The Automatic Identification System (AIS) is a mandatory collision avoidance system required to be installed on ships by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and the Maritime Safety Administration of several countries. The AIS system makes it possible to locate the great majority of vessels throughout the world. International voyaging ships with a Gross Tonnage (GT) of 300 or more, passenger ships of all sizes, domestic vessels with a GT of 200 or more traveling in coastal waters, and inland ships with a GT of 100 or more, are all required to be equipped with AIS. Special purpose vessels

such as military ships, fishery ships, sports ships, and public service ships are exceptions, *Chen et al. (2016), IMO (2003)*.

There are in fact two type of AIS, *Kerbiriou et al. (2017)*:

1. Class A: transponders are mandatory on board merchant ships exceeding 300 tonnages and all passenger ships meeting SOLAS standards (merchant navy, ferries, etc.).
2. Class B: transponders concern small ships that are not required to comply with SOLAS conventions (recreational vessels, fishing vessels of less than 15 meters, etc.), to enable them to adapt voluntarily to the AIS system.

In this study, both AIS-A and AIS-B has been considered.

The objectives of IMO implementing the AIS system are to enhance the safety and efficiency of navigation, safety of life at sea, and protection of maritime environment. AIS facilitates communication between vessels and assist vessel traffic control functions in congested ports, locks and waterways, *Kerbiriou et al. (2017)*. The reported AIS data can be divided into static, dynamic, and voyage-related data categories: static information includes ship name, ship type, length, breadth, etc.; dynamic data includes ship speed over ground, navigational status (operating mode), heading, rate of turn, position, etc.; and voyage-related data includes current draught, description of cargo, and destination, *IMO (2003)*. Besides ship information reported by AIS, detailed data for ship type, ship size, date of construction, design speed, gross tonnage and power of the engines can be obtained from others databases such as Marine Traffic or IHS.

This work is based on data collected by the AIS base station called UFRJ-COPPE for January and February 2018. The hardware consist in one omnidirectional Sirio GP6E antenna of $2 \times 5/8\lambda$ (162 Mhz), one AIS receiver COMAR SLR350N and one Raspberry Pi 3 to provide Ethernet connectivity and to host a NMEA multiplexer server. A NMEA message decoder as well as a Microsoft SQL server compose the data warehouse configuration. The main table in the database contains 196 different fields extracted from the messages. The average range of the configuration is 11 NM with a maximum of 74.5 NM. The average AIS messages quantity is about 395 per minute. The location of the system is plotted in Fig.3 **Error! Reference source not found..**

Fig.4 shows the distribution of the type of ships of the 317 vessels recorded during the period of the study (January and February 2018). The vessels that presented less than 500 AIS position reports in the DB has been disregarded in this study.

Fig.4: Distribution of the type of ships

2.3. Estimation of ship emissions

The methodology of ship emissions assessment has been adapted from Eq.(2). The CO₂, SO₂, NO_x, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} emissions has been calculated between two report positions of a vessel using **Error! Reference source not found.** proposed by *Entec (2002), Goldsworthy and Goldsworthy (2015)*. This formulation depends mainly of the installed power of the ship engines, type of the fuel used as well as of the load factor of the engine. However, these data are not provided by the AIS.

$$E_{i,j,k,l} = P_j \times LF_{j,l} \times T_{j,k,l} \times EF_{i,j,k} / 10^6 \quad (5)$$

$$LF_{j,l} = (AS/MS)^3 \quad (6)$$

Where,	$E_{i,j,k,l}$	Total emission of pollute <i>i</i> from engine <i>j</i> using fuel type <i>k</i> during operation mode <i>l</i> (tons);
	P_j	Installed power for engines <i>j</i> (kW);
	$LF_{j,l}$	Load factor for engine <i>j</i> during operation mode <i>l</i> (%);
	$T_{j,k,l}$	Operating time for engine type <i>j</i> , using fuel type <i>k</i> during operation mode <i>l</i> (h);
	$EF_{i,j,k}$	Emission factor for pollute <i>i</i> from engine <i>j</i> using fuel type <i>k</i> (g/kWh);
	AS	Actual Speed (knots);
	MS	Maximum Speed (knots).

The following steps has been applied to obtain the installed power of the main engines in kW:

1. Preferentially use the real data of the propulsion system when available (from Marine Traffic)
2. Else, use the regressions presented in Table III to assess the installed main engines power in kilowatts. These regression has been established analysing a sample of the world fleet database considering 11127 ships.

Table III: Regressions to obtain the information about rated power of main engine by ship type

Ship type	Quantity	Mean of power	STDV of power	Engine type	Regression equation	R ²
AHTS	3174	5581,18	3525,54	MSD	kW = 2,4099*GT + 1416,8	0,7358
Tanker	1108	2613,88	3218,28	SSD	kW = 12,753*GT ^{0,6404}	0,9099
Container	557	25329,86	20001,74	SSD	kW = 3,0051*GT ^{0,8615}	0,9424
Bulker	404	7987,68	4975,47	SSD	kW = 23,444*GT ^{0,5634}	0,9474
General Cargo	1211	2381,23	2050,77	SSD	kW = 0,555*GT + 282,8	0,8934
Fishing	1985	931,34	814,07	MSD	kW = -4E-05*GT ² + 1,4125*GT + 358,69	0,742
OSV	1531	5174,06	2105,61	MSD	kW = 15,357*GT ^{0,7322}	0,7286
Cruise	26	33430,90	28987,76	MSD	kW = 0,5885*GT ^{1,0176}	0,9826
Pleasure Craft	33	1634,19	1966,94	HSD	kW = 1,7562*GT + 472,95	0,725
Vehicle Carrier	67	8938,13	7040,49	SSD	kW = 15,902*GT ^{0,665}	0,8413
Tug	946	2121,11	970,89	MSD	kW = -0,008*GT ² + 11,312*GT - 84,006	0,5017
Diving Vessel	85	5183,33	4234,57	MSD	kW = 0,3742*GT ^{2,1622}	0,8266

The emissions factors used in this study are taken from *Fan et al. (2016)* considering the machine type as ME and the oil type as RO for all the ships. For each engine, the corresponding emission factors were applied, as described in Table IV. The auxiliary engines used for generating energy on-board has been disregarded in the present study due to the difficulty to obtain the correct installed power of this type of equipment.

Table IV: Emission factors (CO₂, SO₂ and NO_x, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5}) for pollute and fuel type for each engine type (g/kWh), *Chen et al. (2016), Fan et al. (2016)*

Machine type	Engine Type	Oil Type	CO ₂	SO ₂	NO _x	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}
ME	Slow Speed Diesel (SSD)	Residual Oil (RO)	622	10.30	18.10	1.378	1.22
ME	Medium Speed Diesel (MSD)	Residual Oil (RO)	686	11.31	14.00	1.193	1.22
ME	High Speed Diesel (HSD)	Residual Oil (RO)	686	11.31	12.7	0.65	0.50

3. Results

Total estimated emissions from ships for January and February 2018 as well as an estimation of the annual average are presented in Table V. The CO₂ emissions are the most important with over than 40000 t per year followed by NO_x and SO₂ emissions. The AIS data allowed plotting a high-resolution geographical characterization of emissions.

Table V: Total of emission due to marine traffic in Rio de Janeiro

	CO ₂	SO ₂	NO _x	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}
	[Tons]	[Tons]	[Tons]	[Tons]	[Tons]
Jan. and Feb. 2018	6701.4	111.0	147.9	12.9	12.8
Annual average	40208.4	666.0	887.4	77.4	76.8

(a) CO₂ emissions

(b) SO₂ emissions

(c) NO_x emissions

(d) PM₁₀ emissions

(e) PM_{2.5} emissions

Fig.5: Distribution of emissions in tons per year around Rio de Janeiro (Guanabara Bay)

The heat maps of the quantitative assessment of the emissions are illustrated in Fig.5. These maps have been constructed using Google maps API through solution provided by Raffael Vogler in (www.joyofdata.de). The API calculates the heat map based in the contribution of each point in 50 pixels of distance. The map's maximum intensity is fixed at 2.5 t and is represented by the red color. Color gradient follow the default order: light green, yellow, orange and red, representing roughly 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% or more of the maximum intensity. The peak of the emissions is observed at the south part of the bridge between Rio de Janeiro downtown center and Niteroi municipalities.

The assessment of the emission impacts on the population of the surrounding municipalities is out of the scope of this study. To be able to reach this objective, other important source of emissions should be considered as well as other important factors such as dispersions and dilution.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

The Rio de Janeiro Guanabara Bay, one of the busiest ports of Brazil, has a great environmental and socio-economic importance for the region of the study. Its current state of environmental degradation including by GHG emissions poses risks to the human populations of its surroundings, who use its waters for pleasure, transportation, or for their livelihood. This study focus the assessment of the emissions due to marine traffic base on 2 months AIS data (January and February 2018). The major findings of this study, which is the first ship emission inventory for this zone, may be summarized as follows: Total estimated emissions from ships for January and February 2018 are 6701.4 tons of CO₂, 111.0 tons of SO₂, 147.9 tons of NO_x, 12.9 tons of PM₁₀ and 12.8 tons PM_{2.5}. Continuously storing AIS data will allows us in the near future to better understand the distribution of ship emissions in the Rio the Janeiro Bay. However, a special attention should be payed to the construction of consistent databases about the ship engines installed power for both main propulsion and auxiliary power units.

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References

- BERECHMAN, J.; TSENG, P.H. (2012), *Estimating the environmental costs of port related emissions: The case of Kaohsiung*, Transportation Research Part D, 17, pp.35-38
- CEPEDA, M.; ASSIS, L.; MARUJO, L.; CAPRACE, J.D. (2017), *Effects of slow steaming strategies on a ship fleet*, Marine Systems & Ocean Technology 12/3, pp.178-186
- CHANG, Y.T.; SONG, Y.; ROH, Y. (2013), *Assessing greenhouse gas emissions from port vessel operations at the Port of Incheon*, Transportation Research Part D 25, pp.1-4
- CHEN, D.; WANG, X.; LI, Y.; LANG, J.; ZHOU, Y.; GUO, X.; ZHAO, Y. (2017), *High-spatiotemporal-resolution ship emission inventory of China based on AIS data in 2014*, Science of the Total Environment 609, pp.776-787
- CHEN, D.; WANG, X.; NELSON, P.; LI, Y.; ZHAO, N.; ZHAO, Y.; GUO, X. (2017), *Ship emission inventory and its impact on the PM 2.5 air pollution in Qingdao Port, North China*. Atmospheric Environment 166, pp.351-361
- CHEN, D.; ZHAO, N.; LANG, J.; ZHOU, Y.; WANG, X.; LI, Y.; GUO, X. (2018), *Contribution of ship emissions to the concentration of PM2.5: A comprehensive study using AIS data and WRF/Chemmodel in Bohai Rim Region, China*, Science of the Total Environment, pp.1476-1486
- CHEN, D.; ZHAO, Y.; NELSON, P.; LI, Y.; WANG, X.; ZHOU, Y.; GUO, X. (2016), *Estimating ship*

emissions based on AIS data for port of Tianjin, China, Atmospheric Environment 145, pp.10-18

COELLO, J.; WILLIAMS, I.; HUDSON, D.; KEMP, S. (2015), *An AIS-based approach to calculate atmospheric emissions from the UK fishing fleet*, Atmospheric Environment 114, pp.1-7

COOPER, D. (2003), *Exhaust emissions from ships at berth*, Atm. Environment 37, pp.3817-3830

COOPER, D.; GUSTAFSSON, T. (2004), *Methodology for calculating emissions from ships: 1. Update of emission factors*, Report Series Swedish Methodology for Environmental Data 4

COTOVICZ, L.; KNOPPERS, B.; BRANDINI, N.; POIRIER, D.; COSTA SANTOS, S.; ABRIL, G. (2016), *Spatio-temporal variability of methane (CH₄) concentrations and diffusive fluxes from a tropical coastal embayment surrounded by a large urban area (Guanabara Bay, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil)*, Limnology and Oceanography, pp.7-15

COTOVICZ, L.; LIBARDONI, B.; BRANDINI, N.; KNOPPERS, B.; ABRIL, G. (2016), *Comparações entre medições em tempo real da pCO₂ aquática com estimativas indiretas em dois estuários tropicais contrastantes: o estuário eutrofizado da Baía de Guanabara (RJ) e o Estuário oligotrófico do Rio São Francisco*, Quimica Nova 15, pp.1-9

COVELLI, S.; PROTOPSALTI, I.; ACQUAVITA, A.; SPERLE, M.; BONARDI, M.; EMILI, A. (2012), *Spatial variation, speciation and sedimentary records of mercury*, Continental Shelf Research 35, pp.29-42

CULLINANE, K.; TSENG, P.-H.; WILMSMEIER, G. (2015), *The estimation of container ship emissions at berth*, Int. J. Sustainable Transportation 10/5, pp.466-474

DALSØREN, S.B.; EIDE, M.S.; ENDRESEN, Ø.; MJELDE, A. (2009), *Update on emissions and environmental impacts from the international fleet of ships. The contribution from major ship types and ports*, Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics 9, pp.2171-2194

DE CARVALHO AGUIAR, V.; NUNES DE LIMA, M.; COUTINHO ABUCHACRA, R.; FERREIRA FALHEIRO ABUCHACRA, P.; BAPTISTA NETO, J.; VARGAS BORGES, H.; CALÔR DE OLI-VEIRA, V. (2016), *Ecological risks of trace metals in Guanabara Bay, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil: An index analysis approach*, Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety 133, pp.306-315

DE CARVALHO, D.; NETO, J.B. (2016), *Microplastic pollution of the beaches of Guanabara Bay, Southeast*, Ocean & Coastal Management 128, pp.10-17

DE MENDONÇA OCHS, S.; DE ALMEIDA FURTADO, L.; DUARTE PEREIRA NETTO, A. (2015), *Evaluation of the concentrations and distribution of carbonyl compounds in selected areas of a Brazilian bus terminal*, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, pp.9413-9423

DENIZ, C.; KILIC, A. (2009), *Estimation and assessment of shipping emissions in the region of Ambarli Port, Turkey*, Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy 29/1, pp.107-115

DENIZ, C.; KILIC, A.; CIVKAROGLU, G. (2010), *Estimation of shipping emissions in Candarli Gulf, Turkey*, Environ Monit. Assess. 171, pp.219-228

DO NASCIMENTO, M.L.; SANTOS, A.D.; FELIX, L.; GOMES, G.; DE OLIVEIRA E SA, M.; DA CUNHA, D.L.; BILA, D.M. (2018), *Determination of water quality, toxicity and estrogenic activity in a nearshore marine environment in Rio de Janeiro, Southeastern Brazil*, Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety 149, pp.197-202

ENTEC (2002), *Quantification of emissions from ships associated with ship movements between ports*

in the European Community, Final Report, European Commission, Entec UK Ltd.

FAN, Q.; ZHANG, Y.; MA, W.; MA, H.; FENG, J.; YU, Q.; CHEN, L. (2016), *Spatial and Seasonal Dynamics of Ship Emissions over the Yangtze River Delta and East China Sea and Their Potential Environmental Influence*, Environ. Sci. Technol., pp.1322-1329

FONSECA, E.; BAPTISTA NETO, J.; SILVA, C.; McALISTER, J.; SMITH, B.; FERNANDEZ, M. (2013), *Stormwater impact in Guanabara Bay (Rio de Janeiro): Evidences of seasonal variability in the dynamic of the sediment heavy metals*, Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science, pp.161-168

GOLDSWORTHY, B. (2017), *Spatial and temporal allocation of ship exhaust emissions in Australian coastal waters using AIS data: Analysis and treatment of data gaps*, Atmospheric Environment 163, pp.77-86

GOLDSWORTHY, L.; GOLDSWORTHY, B. (2015), *Modelling of ship engine exhaust emissions in ports and extensive coastal waters based on terrestrial AIS data e An Australian case study*, Environmental Modelling & Software 63, pp.45-60

HEITMANN, N.; PETERSON, S. (2014), *The potential contribution of the shipping sector to an efficient reduction of global carbon dioxide emissions*, Environmental Science & Policy 42, pp.56-66

HOWITT, O.; REVOL, V.; SMITH, I.; RODGER, C. (2010), *Carbon emissions from international cruise ship passengers' travel to and from New Zealand*, Energy Policy 8/5, pp.2552-2560

HUANG, L.; WENG, Y.; GENG, X.; ZHOU, C.; XIAO, C.; ZHANG, F. (2017), *Estimation and spatio-temporal analysis of ship exhaust emission in a port area*, Ocean Engineering 140, pp.401-411

IBM (2014), *Big data and analytics in travel and transportation*, IBM Big Data and Analytics, pp.1-12

IMO (2003), *Guidelines for the installation of a shipborne automatic identification system (AIS)*, Int. Maritime Organization, London

JALKANEN, J.P.; BRINK, A.; KALLI, J.; PETTERSSON, H.; KUKKONEN, J.; STIPA, T. (2009), *A modelling system for the exhaust emissions of marine traffic and its application in the Baltic Sea area*, Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics 9, pp.9209-9223

JALKANEN, J.P.; JOHANSSON, L.; KUKKONEN, J. (2013), *A comprehensive inventory of the ship traffic exhaust emissions in the Baltic Sea from 2006 to 2009*, Ambio 43, pp.311-324

JOHANSSON, L. (2011), *Emission estimation of marine traffic using vessel characteristics and AIS-data*, Aalto University

JOHANSSON, L.; JALKANEN, J.P.; KUKKONEN, J. (2017), *Global assessment of shipping emissions in 2015 on a high spatial and temporal resolution*, Atmospheric Environment 167, pp.403-415

KALLI, J.; JALKANEN, J.P.; JOHANSSON, L.; REPKA, S. (2013), *Atmospheric emissions of European SECA shipping: long-term projections*, WMU J. Maritime Affairs 12, pp.129-145

KERBIRIOU, R.; LEVEQUE, L.; RAJABI, A.; SERRY, A. (2017), *The Automatic Identification System (AIS) as a data source for study maritime traffic*, 7th Int. Mar. Science Conf., Solin, pp.1-18

KEUKEN, M.; MOERMAN, M.; JONKERS, J.; HULSKOTTE, J.; GON, H.D.v.d.; HOEK, G.; SOKHI, R. (2014), *Impact of inland shipping emissions on elemental carbon concentrations near waterways in The Netherlands*, Atmospheric Environment 95, pp.1-9

- KILIÇ, A.; DENİZ, C. (2010), *Inventory of Shipping Emissions in Izmit Gulf, Turkey*, Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy 29/2, pp.221-232
- LI, C.; YUAN, Z.; OU, J.; FAN, X.; YE, S.; XIAO, T.; ZHENG, J. (2016), *An AIS-based high-resolution ship emission inventory and its uncertainty*, Science of the Total Environment 573, pp.1-10
- LINDSTAD, H.; SANDAAS, I.; STRØMMAN, A. (2015), *Assessment of cost as a function of abatement options in maritime emission control areas*, Transportation Research Part D 38, pp.41-48
- LIU, T.K.; SHEU, H.Y.; TSAI, J.Y. (2014), *Sulfur dioxide emission estimates from merchant vessels in a port area and related control strategy*, Aerosol and Air Quality Research 14, pp.413-421
- LONATI, G.; CERNUSCHI, S.; SIDI, S. (2010), *Air quality impact assessment of at-berth ship emissions: Case-study for the project of a new freight port*, Science of the Total Environ. 409, pp.192-200
- MACHADO DE PAULA, R. (2015), *Emissões de NOx e SO2 por embarcações do tipo supply boat fundeadas no Porto do Rio de Janeiro e o impacto na qualidade do ar*, Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Escola Politécnica & Escola de Química, Rio de Janeiro: Programa de Engenharia Ambiental
- MARAGKOGIANNI, A.; PAPAETHIMIOU, S. (2015), *Evaluating the social cost of cruise ships air emissions in major ports of Greece*, Transportation Research Part D 36, pp.10-17
- McARTHUR, D.; OSLAND, L. (2013), *Ships in a city harbour: An economic valuation of atmospheric emissions*, Transportation Research Part D 21, pp.47-52
- MILOSLAVSKAYA, N.; TOLSTOY, A. (2016), *Big Data, Fast Data and Data Lake Concepts*. Procedia Computer Science 88, pp.300-305
- MORENO-GUTIÉRREZ, J.; CALDERAY, F.; SABORIDO, N.; BOILE, M.; VALERO, R.; DURÁN-GRADOS, V. (2015), *Methodologies for estimating shipping emissions and energy consumption: A comparative analysis of current methods*, Energy 86, pp.603-616
- NETO, J.A.; BARRETO, C.F.; VILELA, C.G.; DA FONSECA, E.M.; MELO, G.V.; BARTH, O.M. (2017), *Environmental change in Guanabara Bay, SE Brazil, based in microfaunal, pollen and geochemical proxies in sedimentary cores*, Ocean & Coastal Management 143, pp.4-15
- NG, S.; LOH, C.; LIN, C.; BOOTH, V.; CHAN, J.; YIP, A.; LAU, A. (2013), *Policy change driven by an AIS-assisted marine emission inventory in Hong Kong and the Pearl River Delta*, Atmospheric Environment 76, pp.102-112
- NUNES, R.; ALVIM-FERRAZ, M.; MARTINS, F.; SOUZA, S. (2017), *The activity-based methodology to assess ship emissions - A review*, Environmental Pollution 231, pp.87-103
- PERES, L.D.; DE LUCENA, A.; ROTUNNO FILHO, O.C.; FRANÇA, J.d. (2018), *The urban heat island in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in the last 30 years using remote sensing data*, Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinformation 64, pp.104-116
- PITANA, T.; KOBAYASHI, E.; WAKABAYASHI, N. (2010), *Estimation of exhaust emissions of marine traffic using AIS data*, IEEE OCEANS Conf, Sydney
- SANABRA, M.; SANTAMARIA, J.; DE OSES, F. (2013), *Manoeuvring and hotelling external costs: enough for alternative energy sources?*, Maritime Policy & Management
- SARAÇOLLU, H.; DENİZ, C.; KILIÇ, A. (2013), *An investigation on the effects of ship sourced*

emissions in Izmir Port, Turkey, The Scientific World Journal, pp.1-8

SHIN, K.; CHEONG, J.P. (2011), *Estimating transportation-related greenhouse gas emissions in the Port of Busan, S. Korea*, Asian J. Atmospheric Environment 5/1, pp.41-46

SOARES-GOMES, A.; DA GAMA, B.; NETO, J. B.; FREIRE, D.; CORDEIRO, R.; MACHADO, W.; PEREIRA, R. (2016), *An environmental overview of Guanabara Bay, Rio de Janeiro*, Regional Studies in Marine Science 8, pp.319-330

SONG, S. (2014), *Ship emissions inventory, social cost and eco-efficiency in Shanghai Yangshan port*, Atmospheric Environment 48, pp.288-297

SONG, S.K.; SHONG, Z.H. (2014), *Current and future emission estimates of exhaust gases and particles from shipping at the largest port in Korea*, Env. Science & Poll. Research 21, pp.6612-6622

STYHRE, L.; WINNES, H.; BLACK, J.; LEE, J.; LE-GRIFFIN, H. (2017), *Greenhouse gas emissions from ships in ports – Case studies in four continents*, Transportation Research Part D 54, pp.212-224

TICHAVSKA, M.; TOVAR, B. (2015), *Port-city exhaust emission model - An application to cruise and ferry operations in Las Palmas Port*, Transportation Research Part A 78, pp.347-360

TICHAVSKA, M.; TOVAR, B.; GRITSENKO, D.; JOHANSSON, L.; JALKANEN, J. (2017), *Air emissions from ships in port: Does regulation make a difference?* Transport Policy

TZANNATOS, E. (2010), *Ship emissions and their externalities for the port of Piraeus, Greece*, Atmospheric Environment 44, pp.400-407

UNCTAD (2017), *Review of maritime transport 2017*, United Nations

VILLALBA, G.; GEMECHU, E. (2011), *Estimating GHG emissions of marine ports - the case of Barcelona*, Energy Policy 39, pp.1363-1368

WANG, K.; FU, X.; LUO, M. (2015), *Modeling the impacts of alternative emission trading schemes on international shipping*, Transportation Research Part A 77, pp.35-49

WESTERLUND, J.; HALLQUIST, M.; HALLQUIST, Å. (2015), *Characterization of fleet emissions from ships through multi-individual determination of size-resolved particle emissions in a coastal area*, Atmospheric Environment 112, pp.159-166

WINNES, H.; STYHRE, L.; FRIDELL, E. (2015), *Reducing GHG emissions from ships in port areas*, Research in Transportation Business & Management 17, pp.73-82

WINTHER, M.; CHRISTENSEN, J.; PLEJDRUP, M.; RAVN, E.; ERIKSSON, Ó.; KRISTENSEN, H. (2014), *Emission inventories for ships in the arctic based on satellite sampled AIS data*, Atmospheric Environment 91, pp.1-14

YAU, P.; LEE, S.; CORBETT, J.; WANG, C.; CHENG, Y.; HO, K. (2012), *Estimation of exhaust emission from ocean-going vessels in Hong Kong*, Science of the Total Environment 431, pp.299-306

YUAN, J.; NG, S.; SOU, W. (2016), *Uncertainty quantification of CO₂ emission reduction for maritime shipping*, Energy Policy 88, pp.113-130

ZICARI, R. (2014), *Big Data: Challenges and Opportunities*, Big Data Computing, pp.103-130

Model-Based Class Approval and Site Inspection

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Abstract

This paper shows how product certification processes such as class approval in shipbuilding can be supported using a 3D model-based approach and highlight the benefits. Historically class approval and site inspection are processes that require numerous drawings, transferred between class society and shipyard. More recently, many industries have shifted from drawing-based processes to 3D model-based processes, to save time and to add functionalities for approval engineers for a more efficient approval process. E.g. digital signatures, annotations that convert directly into data-management systems, search functions, or digital highlighting. 3D PDF allows creating fully customizable 3D documents that serve this purpose.

1. Introduction

Ships are designed and build in accordance with certain rules and regulations of the classification society. In the initial survey the classification society controls the strength and quality of the materials as well as the workmanship, when the ship is built. These surveys have been done in the past mainly with the so called “approval drawings”, which are provided by the ship building company to the classification society. To reduce the time and costs needed by creating and reviewing these approval documentation, this paper proposes a different approach to these approvals, using a 3D PDF document instead of the 2D drawings.

2. Class approval and site inspection processes

- Participants
The two participants in the class approval and site inspection process are obviously the classification society and the shipbuilding company. The classification society, which is executing the approval, is chosen by the prospective owner of the ship.
- Process steps
In the upcoming subchapters the different process steps of the classification process shall be explained briefly.
- Designing the ship
The design of the ship is done by the shipyard, most likely using CAX-Tools. The data is therefore saved as 3D representations inside some data management system with all its corresponding metadata. This data is used as the basis for all the following processes.
- Creating, providing and reviewing the approval documentation
Whenever the shipyard has created a revision, that, in their eyes, is ready for approval, they are creating the approval documentation and providing this documentation to the classification society. There the approval engineer proceeds with the class approval. He checks the structural integrity of the proposed design and compares it to the standards. If he has any remarks/complains regarding the design, he will add those in comments and makes these comments known to the shipyard.
- Changing the design of the ship according to the remarks
Based on the remarks from the approval engineer, the shipyard adjusts the design of the ship (again with CAX-Tools). These design changes are expensive, and it should be the target of the yard to avoid these “late” changes. It is possible that a second iteration of the approval document

must be created and is reviewed by the classification society again.

- **Constructing and inspecting the ship/building units**
After the yard gets the approval from the classification society, it starts the construction of the ship. When the ship (or one of the building units for larger vessels) is finished, the classification inspects, if the ship/building units have been built according to the previously approved design. If there are any remarks to the built ship/building units by the approval engineer, the yard must adjust the already constructed ship/building unit. As changes after construction are very expensive, the shipyard tries to avoid having any of these remarks.
- **Classify the ship**
If the construction is finished and has been approved by the classification society, the ship gets classified by the same society and is “ready for use”.

2.3. Used information

As the processes focus mainly on the structural integrity of the ship, the main source of information is structural design of the ship. This design can be found in the data management/storage systems of the shipyard and is further processed for the class approval and site inspection (normally as a 2D drawing, in this paper proposed as a 3D PDF document). Additionally, yard standards that aren't part of the 3D model (e.g. for connections) are given to the classification society, the approval of these standards is (mostly) done in a separate process.

3. Model-based solution

As the name of this paper suggests, the proposed solution is to switch from a drawing-based approval process to a model-based solution process. As the digitalization is currently a focus of multiple industries, it is time for shipbuilding to try to switch the drawing approval and site inspection processes to a model-based approach. Following the chosen solution and its benefits is displayed.

3.1. Chosen solution

The chosen solution is based on the 3D PDF technology. The main benefits of this technology are the abilities to create a data container consisting of 3D and 2D data (attaching further documents to certain 3D objects or the PDF document in general is possible) as well as meta-data and information regarding the product structure. Furthermore, the solution can be adjusted to the underlying process and support the participating employees during these. Additionally, the creation process, that can handle data from every major CAD, PLM or ERP system, can be fully automated. It is also based on common standards, which contribute to the longevity of the documents and their usage. Fig.1 shows the user-interface is displayed. The different features of this UI will be discussed afterwards.

Fig.1: User-interface of the chosen solution

3.1.1. 3D area

The biggest part of the user interface is used by the 3D Area, Fig.2, which is displaying the 3D Data that has been chosen during the creation process of the 3D PDF.

Fig.2: 3D Area

The user can manipulate the current view based on his requirements with different operators which are chosen by buttons, that are placed around the 3D area:

1. The “standard” graphical manipulators are those to rotate, pan or zoom the 3D area and the buttons to select these manipulators are located at the top of the operations bar on the right site.

Fig.3: Buttons to rotate, pan and zoom (top to bottom) the 3D area

Additionally, there is a button, that can be used to center the 3D area on a chosen 3D object.

Fig.4: Button to center the 3D area on a chosen 3D Object

2. Next on the list are buttons to manipulate the visibility of the 3D objects. These buttons can be used to store the visibility of 3D objects or temporarily hide 3D objects that are blocking the view of the user.

Fig.5: Buttons to save the visibility, load the saved visibility, hide an object or show the last hidden 3D object again (top to bottom)

3. Lastly, the user has also the possibility to cut through the 3D Area and have a chance to “look into” the structure. This can be achieved by the **section** operators located on the bottom of the template.

Fig.6: Operators to create sections

3.1.2. Model structure

The included model can be structured, Fig.7, (and its structure can be adjusted during the creation process of the document to meet the needs of the user). This structure is displayed on the left site of the UI. The structure can also be used to manipulate the 3D area (e.g. hiding, showing, isolating, centering or coloring substructures). There is also a bidirectional link between the model structure and the 3D area, meaning, that whenever the user selects an object in the 3D area or a branch in the model structure it gets highlighted in the opposite one.

Fig.7: Model structure

3.1.3. Saved views

Below the model structure the available views are shown. With these views the user can save and open the camera position and visibility of objects in the 3D area (somewhat like the save and load visibility buttons described in chapter 3.1.1). Whenever the user creates a comment or measurement (see chapter 3.1.5.) another view is created, so that other users can retrace on which basis the comment/measurement has been made.

Fig.8: Saved views

During the creation process it is also possible to automatically create standard views of the 3D area and reduce the time, the user needs to navigate through the 3D area.

3.1.4 Meta-data

Every 3D object has associated attributes, Fig.9. The attributes of the currently selected 3D object are shown below the saved views. The user is also able to use these attributes to filter and/or highlight objects that are fulfilling the criteria defined by the user.

Eigenschaft	Wert
Deck	05
Layer	201
Material	A36
Name	XLW 448
Ship Grid Support	LONG 6=3600
Thickness	8.0
Type	Physical Plate

Fig.9: Meta-data for the currently selected 3D object

Currently, there are two different methods implemented that allow the user to analyze the model based on attributes:

1. The user can use the color-coding to get a quick overview, which 3D object has which attribute value (e.g. the thickness of the different steel-parts), Fig.10.

Fig.10: Color-coding and legend for the attribute "thickness"

Fig.11: Filter-tool (can be toggled on/off and replaces the color-coding)

2. The user can also filter the 3D objects based on attributes, defining up to three different filters and combine them with the AND or OR operator, Fig.11. Afterwards he can choose, if he wants to hide the objects included or excluded by the filter or wants to make the 3D objects that are excluded by the filter transparent.

3.1.5. Add measurements or comments

As previously stated the user is also able to add measurements or comments inside the 3D area, Fig.12. For each of these actions he has a different button at his hands. These comments and measurements can be stored permanently in the 3D PDF and later be exported from it to be transferred to for example a PLM-System.

Fig.12: Buttons to start the measurement or comment tool (top to bottom)

3.2. Benefits

The benefits, that the chosen solution provides compared to the traditionally used 2D drawings, can be divided into benefits during the creation and the usage of the approval documents, as well as any following processes.

3.2.1. Benefits during the creation

The creation process of 3D PDF documents can be highly automated, resulting in no (or very little) interaction of the user, Fig.13. The creation process can also be based on multiple source systems, even progressing data from different systems into the same 3D PDF document/template.

Fig.13: Creation process of a 3D PDF document

3.2.2. Benefits during the usage

Many of the features, that have been shown in the previous chapters, cannot be used on a 2D Drawing as these are not realizable on a print-out / “standard” 2D PDF. The different features have been developed in close cooperation between the shipyard and the classification society, with the main benefit being the reduced amount of time during the approval and site inspection of (sections of) the ship.

3.2.3. Benefits in following processes

As all the comments and remarks are saved inside the 3D PDF document and can be extracted, these can mark the start of a new process (e.g. engineering change requests needed to fulfill the class approval requirements) in the corresponding system. Based on these created follow-up processes, the shipyard can track which remarks of the class society have been taking care of and which are still not solved.

4. Conclusion and outlook

The 3D PDF technology can create benefits during the class approval and site inspection processes, if the templates and given functionality in the documents are aligned with the usage of it. Meaning, that a

3D PDF document shouldn't be used, just because the shipyard is able to create them.

The displayed solution is only a first version and still has much room for improvement. The 3D PDF technology should be tested thoroughly in the future and in the context of this use-case, to further reveal any further time-reducing potentials.

Additionally, this technology has been used by other industries in multiple disciplines (engineering, approval, data storage, manufacturing or parts management to name a few). The benefits, which were achieved in those industries using 3D documents (instead of 2D), could be "shifted" to the maritime industry as well and might contain some larger potentials for improvement.

References

CHRIST, J.; PFALZGRAF, P. (2012), *3D PDF-Technologie*, PROSTEP AG, Darmstadt

IACS (2015), *Classification societies – what, why and how?*, IACS, London

VAN DOKKUM, K. (2011), *Ship Knowledge*, Dokmar Maritime Publishers BV, pp.120-123

Situational Awareness and Obstacle Avoidance for a Wind Propelled Marine Research ASV

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Abstract

In this paper, the situational awareness and obstacle avoidance system of the wind propelled marine research ASV ASPire is described. Detailed descriptions are provided regarding: (1) The higher level route replanning system utilizing interval analysis. (2) The image processing algorithms used on the Thermal Image Camera output for obstacle detection. (3) The adaptations of the voter based control system for using the results from 2.

1. Introduction

In this paper, the situational awareness system of the wind propelled marine research platform ASV ASPire, *Friebe et al. (2017)*, is presented. The context for the situational awareness system is provided by briefly describing the current state of the art regarding situational awareness for unmanned surface vehicles, based mainly on *Liu et al. (2016)*, in Section 2.

The ASPire is a 4 m long keelboat with a custom built free rotating rigid wingsail rig. An image of the vessel can be seen in Fig.1. The architecture of the situational awareness system in relation to the navigation system is presented as follows. On a logical level, the system can be divided into two main parts - obstacle detection and collision avoidance. The collision avoidance system is separated into a higher-level route replanning module and a lower-level reactive system integrated into the regular navigation system. The software architecture of the situational awareness, collision avoidance and control system is described in Section 3.

Fig.1: The wind propelled autonomous vehicle ASPire

For obstacle detection the ASPire is equipped with an AIS (Automatic Identification System) transceiver and a forward looking Thermal Imaging Camera (TIC). The sensor selection is discussed in the paper and has also been motivated in earlier work, *Friebe et al. (2017)*. The AIS provides position, course and speed data about surrounding (commercial) ships that is straightforward to interpret. The TIC has a Field Of View (FOV) of 24° horizontally and 18° vertically. The thermal image is processed in order to estimate the amount of navigable space available for choosing course in the field of view. The algorithms are described and results for test images are illustrated in Section 4.

The higher-level path replanning module utilizes interval analysis methods. The original set of waypoints and the navigable zone restricted by sea depth and location of other vessels as retrieved by AIS are inputs to the module. The result is an updated set of waypoints for the vessel. The algorithm is described and simulation results are presented in Section 5. Close range vessels and the visible navigable space interpreted from the thermal image are input into the lower-level reactive system integrated with the navigation system through a voter based mechanism. The voter based system has been described in earlier work *Less'ard-Springett et al. (2017)*, but it has been adapted to utilize the output from the thermal image processing as presented in this paper. The adaptation is described and simulation results are provided in Section 6. In Section 7, conclusions and future work are discussed.

2. Situational Awareness and Obstacle Avoidance for ASVs, Current State of the Art

In *Liu et al. (2016)* guidance techniques are classified as:

- 1) Path planning, which can be further classified into:
 - a) Global path planning, where optimization methods such as Genetic algorithm (GA) can be used, or heuristic search algorithms, such as the widely used A* search algorithm. Cost functions can include for example spatiotemporal characteristics, collision probability estimates, fuel consumption and weather considerations. In global path planning, static obstacles can be considered.
 - b) Local path planning that includes line-of-sight (LOS) and potential fields (PF) methods. In local path planning, reactive path planning based on dynamic obstacles can be incorporated.
 - c) Hybrid path planning that combines global and local path planning. These often utilize hierarchical architectures.
- 2) Path replanning, where dynamic obstacles are taken into account. Methods are classified as:
 - a) Protocol-free collision avoidance i.e. methods that don't consider COLREGs. Methods have been based on for example differential equations, level sets and optical flow, and have been connected to different sensors and obstacle detection methods.
 - b) Protocol-based collision avoidance, where the methods are adapted to COLREGs. There are many examples of methods adapted or extended for compliance with COLREGs, such as for example A* and velocity obstacles. COLREGs compliance is important for safe interaction between manned and unmanned vessels.

Also in *Liu et al. (2016)* environment perception methods and sensors are classified in active and passive perception methods depending on whether the methods include transmitting signals or not.

- 1) Passive perception methods include monocular vision, stereo vision, and Infrared vision
Visible light vision based systems generally have a long range, and do not consume large amounts of energy. However, the range is affected by various conditions such as daylight, rain, fog and waves. The thermal infrared region corresponds to mid and long infrared wavelengths (respectively 3-8 m and 8-15 m). TIC gives reliable information during night time, and are also less affected by fog than visible light cameras, especially for the long-wave infrared spectrum *Liu et al. (2016)*.
- 2) Active perception methods include LIDAR, Radar, and Sonar
Radar is the gold standard in maritime navigation, that has been proven reliable in various weather and lighting conditions, and is also recognized in COLREGs as an accepted tool when navigating in limited visibility. Sonar is a valuable tool for detecting underwater obstacles and defining sailing zones, which can be of particular importance when navigating outside of fairways.

3. Software Architecture

The ASPire's control system utilizes a message based architecture for communication between the various threads responsible for sensor readings, communication, control and command execution.

Fig.2 shows an overview of the software architecture related to situational awareness and obstacle avoidance. AIS information regarding other vessels in the vicinity, and the visual field representation from the TIC are fed into the world state representation of obstacles and interacting structure, the Collidable Manager. The interpretation is further described in Section 5. The Collidable Manager bypasses the message based system, and contains protected data that can be shared between threads.

Fig.2: Software Architecture Overview

The AIS information in combination with the Mission planning and Sailing Zone information is utilized by the higher level Route Replanner, which is further described in Section 4. The output from the Route Replanner is a new set of waypoints, which is fed into the Waypoint Manager. The Local Navigation Module controls the ASV’s target course, and is implemented by means of a voter based control system, that is described previously in *Less’ard Springett et al. (2017)*. The visual field representation of the thermal image camera and the AIS information of close vessels, both stored in the Collidable Manager, are utilized here for reactive collision avoidance purposes. This is further described in Section 6.

4. Higher-Level Route Replanning

The purpose of the higher-level route replanning is to adjust the route defined by existing waypoints in order to avoid possible collisions with other boats and to ensure that the route stays within sailing zones. The sailing zones are typically predefined based on static information of islands, reefs, shallow waters, etc. In essence, the route replanner reads the list of waypoints and checks if there is any risk of collision with another vessel or if the ASV ASPire crosses the border of a given sailing zone. If so, the route replanner modifies the list of waypoints by modifying the position of one or several waypoints or adding new waypoints in order to avoid possible collisions with other boats and ensure a route within sailing zones. Possible collisions with other boats are calculated by linearly extrapolating the trajectory of other vessels based on speed and course obtained by AIS data.

The algorithm is divided in two main steps repeated for each trajectory segment, i.e., each trajectory between two waypoints. The first step is to detect any possible collisions with an obstacle or crossing

of sailing zone borders. If a possible collision or border crossing is detected, the path replanning step is initiated. In this step, interval analysis allows the set of all feasible velocities to be determined, i.e., all velocities that allow the ASV ASPire to stay in the sailing zone and to avoid collisions. This set is computed thanks to a paving method, with a given accuracy. Then, the velocity closest to the initial velocity of the ASV ASPire is selected and used to calculate new waypoint coordinate.

4.1. Collision detection

The main idea for the collision detection is from the last part of *Jaulin and LeBars (2012)*. The article proposes a collision detection algorithm based on interval analysis. Interval analysis can provide some tools to find guaranteed solutions to sets of inequalities or equations. For implementing the algorithm some assumptions are made. The sailing area is approximated by a two-dimensional plane, with a fixed cartesian frame Oxy . From AIS we obtain speed, course and the position of an arbitrary number of m vessels at time $t = 0$ with a known accuracy. For calculating the future positions of the other vessels, the speed and course are considered constants. The position $\mathbf{m}^i(t)$ of the i^{th} detected boat at time t thus satisfies:

$$\mathbf{m}^i(t) = \mathbf{a}^i t + \mathbf{b}^i, \quad i \in \{1, \dots, m\} \quad (1)$$

\mathbf{a}^i and \mathbf{b}^i are vectors of \mathbb{R}^2 which correspond to the velocity-components in the fixed Cartesian frame and the initial position of the i^{th} boat. Velocity and position are further associated with an uncertainty which yields two boxes $[\mathbf{a}^i]$ and $[\mathbf{b}^i]$ which enclose \mathbf{a}^i and \mathbf{b}^i respectively. The possibility to include uncertainty is handled by interval analysis and is one reason for using this approach in the current implementation. For the ASV ASPire, it is assumed that its trajectory is given by:

$$\mathbf{m}^0(t) = \mathbf{a}^0 t + \mathbf{b}^0 \quad (2)$$

The vector \mathbf{b}^0 is the initial position, and the vector \mathbf{a}^0 is determined by the ASV speed and the line to be followed, i.e, by two consecutive waypoint positions on the planned route. For the algorithm, the waypoints therefore must be expressed in the fixed cartesian frame of the two-dimensional plane. In a first approximation, the initial position of the ASV ASPire is set to the first waypoint. Some estimates of the velocity of the ASV ASPire on the trajectory segments are also needed. Often, it will correspond to the GPS speed projected on the course, but when in tacking mode this will obviously not be true. Still, it is possible to make an estimation of the velocity over a trajectory segment. Again, the uncertainties of the estimates on initial position and velocity will yield two boxes $[\mathbf{a}^0]$ and $[\mathbf{b}^0]$ which enclose \mathbf{a}^0 and \mathbf{b}^0 .

In reality, the initial position of the ASV ASPire may not be on the first waypoint and an easy adjustment is to create a waypoint from measured current position in the initialization of the algorithm. For reliability of the method, it is important to position the ASV ASPire on the line between two waypoints.

In order to prove that a sailing trajectory is safe, *Jaulin and LeBars (2012)* proposes a method based on interval analysis. The basic idea is to examine the trajectory for possible collisions in a time interval $[0, t_{max}]$. There is a collision on the trajectory if:

$$\exists i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \exists t \in [0, t_{max}], \mathbf{m}^i(t) = \mathbf{m}^0(t) \quad (3)$$

That is, if the following system has a solution:

$$\begin{cases} (\mathbf{a}^0 - \mathbf{a}^i) \cdot t + \mathbf{b}^0 - \mathbf{b}^i = 0, \\ t \in [0, t_{max}], i \in [1, \dots, m] \\ \mathbf{a}^0 \in [\mathbf{a}^0], \mathbf{a}^i \in [\mathbf{a}^i], \mathbf{b}^0 \in [\mathbf{b}^0], \mathbf{b}^i \in [\mathbf{b}^i] \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Expressed using interval analysis, this gives:

$$\exists i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0 \in ([a_x^0] - [a_x^i]) * [0, t_{max}] + [b_x^0] - [b_x^i] \text{ and} \\ 0 \in ([a_y^0] - [a_y^i]) * [0, t_{max}] + [b_y^0] - [b_y^i] \text{ and} \\ 0 \in ([a_y^0] - [a_y^i]) * ([b_x^0] - [b_x^i]) - ([a_x^0] - [a_x^i]) * ([b_y^0] - [b_y^i]) \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

In order to check for collisions between the two waypoints, t_{max} is chosen so that the ASV ASPire reaches the second waypoint at t_{max} . An estimate of t_{max} is based on the previously mentioned estimates of velocity between two waypoints. For the case of several waypoints, the collision detection scheme is repeated for each segment of the trajectory. For the case of several waypoints, the initial positions of the ASV ASPire and other vessels are updated in order to correspond to the estimated values at the beginning of each new trajectory segment. The initial positions are calculated based on the assumed constant velocity of the other vessels.

4.2. Detection of the crossing of the sailing zone borders

The sailing zone is modeled as a list of polygons providing borders the ASV ASPire should not cross. Each polygon is modelled by the list of the coordinates of its vertices. These coordinates are expressed in the fixed Cartesian frame in the two-dimensional plane. In order to determine crossing of borders, the algorithm draws inspiration from the example presented in *Jaulin (2001)*.

The case for detecting border crossings is similar to collision detection and the trajectory of the ASV ASPire is a segment between two waypoints. The case of several waypoints is handled in the same manner as for the collision detection. Consider two boxes A and B. The box A is the initial position of the ASV ASPire, and the box B is the final position. The i^{th} vertex of a polygon is denoted by V_i . Let $[A, B]$ denote the set of all the segments with an endpoint in A and an endpoint in B. For each polygon of the sailing zone, it is necessary to examine if:

$$\forall i, \forall S \in [A, B], \quad [V_i, V_{i+1}] \cap S = \emptyset \quad (6)$$

If this condition is true for all sides of all polygons, the ASV ASPire never crosses the sailing zone border. However, it is difficult to implement this criterion. For an easier implementation, the contrapositive is considered instead and the corresponding relations are:

$$\exists i, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \exists S \in [A, B], \quad (V_i, V_{i+1}) \cap S \neq \emptyset \text{ and} \\ \exists D \in (A, B), \quad [V_i, V_{i+1}] \cap D \neq \emptyset \text{ and} \\ [V_i \cup V_{i+1}] \cap [A \cup B] \neq \emptyset \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

Let (A, B) denote the set of all the lines supported by a point in A and a point in B, (V_i, V_{i+1}) the line supported by V_i and V_{i+1} , $[V_i, V_{i+1}]$ the segment linking V_i and V_{i+1} , and $[A \cup B]$ and $[V_i \cup V_{i+1}]$ the smallest box including A and B or V_i and V_{i+1} respectively. The last condition is important for a special case, where all the points are aligned. In that case, the two first conditions will be true event if the trajectory does not cross the polygon side. The first two conditions are not implemented directly, instead the following equivalence is used:

$$\exists i, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \det(\overrightarrow{V_i B}, \overrightarrow{V_i A}) * \det(\overrightarrow{V_{i+1} B}, \overrightarrow{V_{i+1} A}) \leq 0 \text{ and} \\ \det(\overrightarrow{V_{i+1} V_i}, \overrightarrow{V_i A}) * \det(\overrightarrow{V_{i+1} V_i}, \overrightarrow{V_i B}) \leq 0 \text{ and} \\ [V_i \cup V_{i+1}] \cap [A \cup B] \neq \emptyset \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

If this is true for one of the polygons of the sailing zone, then the trajectory of the ASV ASPire will cross the border determined by this polygon.

4.3. Path replanning

As in the detection step, interval analysis is also used for the path replanning step. The general idea is to compute the set of all velocities that allows the ASV ASPire to avoid collisions and ensure it stays within the sailing zone, i.e., all feasible velocities.

For that purpose, separator algebra is used. A separator is an interval analysis tool that aims to approximate the solution set of an equation. A separator corresponding to the collision condition of each obstacle, and to the crossing condition of each side of each polygon of the sailing zone is constructed. Then, the union of all these separators is computed. Finally, the set of all the feasible velocities are computed with a paving method. Then, the velocity which is closest to the initial velocity of the ASV ASPire is chosen.

This velocity is kept for the time it would take the ASV ASPire to reach the waypoint with its previous velocity. This assumption allows us to compute a new waypoint which replaces the former waypoint. The last waypoint of the list is assumed to be a checkpoint and not modified. If it would need to be modified, a new waypoint is added before the last. However, if the last waypoint is inside the final position uncertainty box of the ASV with the new waypoint, the last waypoint is replaced. To build the collision separators, the same conditions as in the detection part are used. In order to express these constraints as sets the following reformulation is used:

$$\exists i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \begin{cases} [b_x^i] - [b_x^0] \in ([a_x^0] - [a_x^i]) * [0, t_{max}] \text{ and} \\ [b_y^i] - [b_y^0] \in ([a_y^0] - [a_y^i]) * [0, t_{max}] \text{ and} \\ ([b_y^i] - [b_y^0]) \in \frac{([a_y^0] - [a_y^i])}{([a_x^0] - [a_x^i]) * ([b_x^i] - [b_x^0])} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

For separators representing sailing zone border crossings, the same conditions as for the detection step cannot be used. The two first conditions can be used, but not the third because it is a logical relation, and separators deal with sets or arithmetic relations. The third condition is given by:

$$\exists i, \quad [V_i \cup V_{i+1}] \cap [A \cup B] \neq \emptyset \quad (10)$$

This condition is true if the two boxes are overlapping. Fig.3 illustrates an example of two overlapping boxes. Let $[V_i \cup V_{i+1}]$ represent the blue (upper) box, and $[A \cup B]$ the red (lower).

Fig.3: Example of two overlapping boxes

Fig.4: Result of the paving process

The two boxes are overlapping if:

$$\begin{cases} \max(d_1, D_1) - \max(L_1, l_2) \leq 0 \text{ and} \\ \max(d_2, D_2) - \max(l_1, L_2) \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

In Fig.4, a paving of the set of feasible velocities, represented on the (V_x, V_y) plane, is illustrated. In this simulation, there are three obstacles, and the sailing zone is defined by a square around the evolution area of the ASV. Speeds from -5 m/s to 5m/s on V_x and V_y are explored. Since these speeds exceed the capacity of the ASV, the simulation will explore whether the ASV will cross any sailing zone borders. The red boxes are inside the set of velocities that lead to a collision or to border crossing. The yellow boxes are on the border of this set. Finally, the light blue boxes are outside this set and thus represent the set of feasible velocities. The green box is the velocity chosen by the algorithm.

5. Thermal Image Processing

The software system handling thermal camera frames is based on the popular computer vision library OpenCV. Due to the huge range of possible items to be found at sea, no image recognition software was employed. Instead, our implementation is based on pattern identification so that free space is detected instead of obstacles. The navigation system is then able to decide the best route avoiding the zones where no free space is to be found. Each frame is processed independently while the video handle is open. An example thermal image is displayed in Fig.5, and the interpretation process is displayed in a flowchart in Fig.6.

Fig.5: Example thermal imaging camera frame

Firstly the algorithm checks if the camera is under calibration, a repeated process during which the frame stream might be stuck or irresponsive, thus if a green square is found, the thread is halted until calibration is finished. Secondly, the inclination is corrected using tilt data coming from the compass and, in case of data dispatch delay (detected comparing the acquisition timestamp with current time) or complete lack of data, a Hough line transformation is employed to detect the longest line and take it as the horizon to rectify the frame.

Rectified frames are fed in a Gaussian filter to eliminate noise and through a Canny filter to outline objects' contours. Then, using the horizon previously discovered, the system defines the specific ROI (Region of Interest) from the bottom till the horizon, excluding every part of the frame falling on the upper zone as the distance is negligible.

Fig.6: Algorithm flowchart

Going through the frame column by column using a column width equal to 1° of bearing, clustering contours to detect obstacles; iterating from the bottom left corner to the top right one, external elements identified are pushed to the Collidable Manager that will bridge the Obstacle Detection node with the Local Navigation node using the voter system. Examples of intermediate results from the different steps are shown in Fig.7.

Fig.7a: Example thermal image

Fig.7d: Example thermal image

Fig.7b: Detected lines and horizon from 7a

Fig.7e: Detected lines and horizon from 7d

Fig.7c: The free space (white) from 7a before horizon cropping

Fig.7f: The free space (white) from 7d before horizon cropping

6. Adaptation of the Voter Based Control System

Voter based systems were first developed at Carnegie Mellon University in the mid-1990s, *Rosenblatt (2010)*, and have a long history of applications in real-world systems, including the Mars Rovers and autonomous surface vessels, *Larson et al. (2006,2007)*. The ASPire uses a voter based control system for sailboat navigation and obstacle avoidance. Each voter has a specific objective that is translated into votes for the possible target courses of the ASV. The voter based control system is architecturally appealing, as it enables separation of concerns and modularity. The voters are:

1. WaypointVoter - movement towards the waypoint.
2. WindVoter - beating when needed due to the wind direction.
3. ManeuverVoter - staying on the same course to avoid unnecessary maneuvers
4. ChannelVoter - staying within the channel between two consecutive waypoints.
5. ProximityVoter - avoiding close obstacles.

The votes are combined to make a decision of the target course. The visual field representation of the thermal image camera in the Collidable Manager, and also AIS information for close vessels, are utilized in the ProximityVoter for reactive collision avoidance purposes.

6.1. Thermal Image Camera visual field representation

The visual field information, or amount of free space in the visible field from the TIC is added to the Collidable Manager with the ASV's current heading. In the Collidable Manager the information is inserted into a map where absolute bearing values are mapped to amount of free space. The lower and higher limits for the currently visible field are also stored. Thus, if the vessel turns, a larger amount of bearings are available in the map, than those currently within the field of view. The time of update for each bearing is also stored. When a map value has not been updated for a certain amount of time, the amount of free space at the bearing is gradually increased. After an additional amount of time, map values are considered outdated and deleted. In the tests described below, the time limit for start of increasing the free space is 10 s, and the time limit for deletion of old values is 30 s.

6.2. Adaptations of the ProximityVoter

The ProximityVoter takes into account the AIS information as described in *Less'ard-Springett et al. (2018)*. However, in general this should be incorporated into the higher level deliberate route replanning system. Here, we describe how the visual field information is incorporated.

As explained in Section 5, a number is given for each course in the thermal imager camera's field of view, that represents the relative distance of obstacle free space in this particular direction. The ProximityVoter utilizes this information for calculating votes in the following manner:

1. Votes are decreased in areas outside the current field of view.
2. If an obstacle is visible in a direction, votes are decreased for this direction and in an adjacent range. The decrease depends on the relative distance of obstacle free space in the following manner:

$$voteAdjust = k * \frac{100 - relativeFreeDistance}{100} \quad (12)$$

k is a weighting factor. The adjacent directions within a range of $adjacentLimit$ degrees are also decreased. Let:

$$directionDist = abs(dir - obstacleDir) \quad (13)$$

$$distanceFactor = \frac{adjacentLimit - directionDist}{adjacentLimit} \quad (14)$$

Thus, votes are decreased with

$$\begin{cases} vote_{max} * voteAdjust * distanceFactor & \text{if } directionDist < adjacentLimit \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

3. If an obstacle is visible, votes are increased in directions 90° starboard and port of the obstacle, in adjacent ranges, as described in 2, Eq.(12)-(15). The starboard side has a higher weighting, because this is the preferred route of escape. However, it may not always be feasible to go in this direction due to wind constraints.
4. Votes are set to 0 in the non-navigable directions into the wind.

6.3. Simulation and test setup

The control system of the ASPIre has been set up to run connected to a simulator. On the simulator side, configurations are set up for interacting vessels, as described in Table I. The Distance at Closest point of Approach (DCPA) is given for each test case. For the upwind cases, where the ASV is beating, the resulting DCPA may be affected by the tacking movements of the ASPIre. Therefore, five different tests with slightly different starting positions of the interacting vessel are performed for each case. Then the minimum and mean DCPA values are calculated for these tests, to decrease the effect of the beating track.

The ASPIre's horizontal FOV is configured in the simulator to 24°, as is the case for the TIC on board. If the interacting vessel's midpoint is within the field of view, information is added to the visible field representation, related to the distance between the vessels.

$$relDistance = \begin{cases} 100 * \frac{distance}{maxVisibleDistance} & \text{if } distance < maxVisibleDistance \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

This value is set for a range of adjacent bearings proportional to

$$\frac{maxVisibleDistance - distance}{maxVisibleDistance} \quad (17)$$

so that a closer vessels occupies a larger space in the view. The maximum visible distance is set to 500 m in the simulation.

6.4. Results

As can be seen in test cases 1 and 2 in Table I, the DCPA is increased considerably for head-on cases, when using the ProximityVoter. The test case 1 simulation can be viewed here: <http://bit.ly/2u7VsJw>. In test cases 3 and 4 it is clear that the DCPA is increased for vessels approaching from starboard side. The simulation of test case 3 can be viewed here: <http://bit.ly/2G2t7fN>. There is a limit for when the interacting vessel enters the FOV too late, or not at all. In test case 5, the interacting vessel never enters the FOV and the ProximityVoter is obviously ineffective.

For vessels approaching from port side, the collision avoidance proves less effective - for test case 6, the DCPA is clearly lower when using the ProximityVoter than without. This is due to the preference of making way to starboard side. In this case, this means that the ASV will turn starboard and go in parallel with the interacting vessel until it has passed. The simulation of this case can be viewed here: <http://bit.ly/2HQgRji>

Test case 7 is similar, the DCPA is almost the same as when running without the collision avoidance, due to the preference of turning starboard. In test case 8, we see the same limit as in the starboard case - if the interacting vessel does not enter the FOV or enters it too late, the system is unable to prevent a collision. Also for the overtaking situation in test case 9, we have the same situation.

Test cases 10 and 11 involve static obstacles on starboard and port side of the path, respectively. We can see that the obstacle avoidance system is capable of increasing the DCPA in these cases.

In Table II, results from simulations with the ASV going upwind in beating mode are presented. We can see a similar situation here, where the collision avoidance is effective in increasing the DCPA for the head on and starboard cases in Test case 1-3. Again, we see that for the port cases in Test case 4-5 the collision avoidance is less effective.

Larson *et al.* (2007) described a problem with the Voter based system. that it occasionally would fluctuate between two possible choices, and this would lead to a near collision. In one of the beating test cases with an interacting vessel from port side, this kind of oscillatory behaviour could be observed. The simulation of this case is available here: <http://bit.ly/2prcc0n>

Table I: Simulations in non-beating mode

Tests, non-beating mode	Speed of interacting vessel (m/s)	DCPA with ProximityVoter (m)	DCPA without ProximityVoter (m)
1. Head on	3	21.44	3.94
2. Head on	10	4.91	0.80
3. Starboard crossing further ahead	3	70.23	52.38
4. Starboard crossing close	3	19.82	15.30
5. Starboard crossing behind	3	21.8	21.76
6. Port crossing further ahead	3	79.96	48.79
7. Port crossing close	3	13.84	14.34
8. Port crossing behind	3	26.62	26.60
9. Overtaking	3	14.65	14.69
10. Static obstacle starboard side of path	3	39.11	1.41
11. Static obstacle port side of path	3	30.83	19.46

Table II: Simulations in beating mode, min and mean of five tests

Tests, beating mode	Speed of interacting vessel (m/s)	min DCPA with ProximityVoter (m)	mean DCPA with ProximityVoter (m)	min DCPA without ProximityVoter (m)	mean DCPA without ProximityVoter (m)
1. Head on	3	10.28	12.53	1.30	5.60
2. Starboard crossing further ahead	3	119.25	130.00	36.40	72.80
3. Starboard crossing close	3	6.93	82.00	3.45	17.47
4. Port crossing further ahead	3	29.96	130.01	59.12	72.79
5. Port crossing close	3	4.29	18.45	5.41	21.71

7. Conclusions and Future Work

7.1. Higher-Level Route Replanning

During various tests potential issues with using this algorithm in real conditions have been identified:

First, for now it is assumed that the speed of the boat can be controlled. Theoretically, it depends on the projection on the boat course of the force applied on the wingsail, as well as on the wind speed

and direction, on the heading of the boat, and on the angle of attack of the wingsail. In theory, the angle of attack is controlled by the angle of the tail wing. However, this has not been evaluated sufficiently in practice, and it may prove to be less straightforward to control the speed.

A simple way to bypass this issue could be to choose a new velocity which has the same speed as the actual velocity. Indeed, it will require more tests in real conditions, but it might be possible to assume that our speed can remain constant, as soon as we process the collision avoidance on a reasonable time interval, such as every few minutes. The higher level route replanning can also be performed on the server side on shore, as long as the bandwidth allows for transmission of AIS information and waypoints.

The current implementation does not take into account that the vessel may need to beat upwind, and that this affects the speed towards the waypoint. The wind direction would need to be considered.

Another issue is the fact that when the collision avoidance calculation is performed for a long route, the uncertainty box becomes very large. Thus, this method in the current implementation is not useful for replanning of complete long missions. However, we are mainly concerned with risks of collision in a limited timespan.

7.2. TIC FOV limitation

The narrow FOV of the thermal imager is a severe limitation. The algorithm performed significantly worse when only the currently visible information was used and detected obstacle bearings were not stored for a period of time. The ASV attempted to return to its course immediately after losing sight of the obstacle, leading to smaller DCPAs.

There will be cases where a collision can occur since the ASPIre is unable to detect an interacting vessel due to the narrow FOV. There will also be cases, where the ASV is unable to detect an interacting vessel in time to perform an appropriate maneuver. Due to the slow movement of the ASPIre, this may be the case for an interacting vessel at high speed even if it is detected at a reasonable distance. An option that would improve matters slightly would be to have a Thermal Image Camera with pan option that can cover a larger FOV. Addition of sensors such as visible light cameras, LIDAR and/ or Radar is another option for improvement.

7.3. Thermal image processing

The images analysed in Section 5 were retrieved from the TIC using a video grabber during the summer of 2017. In the current system, the analog video signal is captured through a PiCapture SD1. This is likely to result in higher image quality. The image resolution differs, and parameters will likely need to be tuned accordingly.

Tests of the image processing system will be necessary with images from different sea states, weather and lighting conditions. It is not certain that the image processing algorithm will work satisfactory in all conditions.

7.4. COLREGs

Regarding COLREGs, there are several limitations with the described approach. The ASV does not classify obstacles, so it is not aware if the obstacle is an interacting vessel or some other kind of obstacle. In the case the obstacle is a vessel, the ASV is only aware of the bearing, it does not know the position and course of the interacting vessel, nor is it able to determine if the other vessel is a sailing vessel. Thus, the collision avoidance system is unable to determine if it is the Stand-On Vessel or the Give-Way Vessel in a particular situation. Since the ASPIre is wind propelled, it will be the Stand-On Vessel according to COLREGs in cases when the interacting vessel is a power boat.

Nevertheless, the system will always attempt to steer away from the obstacle. A starboard maneuver is preferred, as this will likely be expected from other actors. However, a port maneuver may be performed, in particular if this is needed due to the wind conditions. The system appears to work reasonably well for interacting vessels approaching from ahead or starboard side.

7.5. Voter based system and reactive collision avoidance

As has been described with other voter based systems and observed for some test cases, the system may switch between two possible choices, ending up with a near collision. One possible way to mitigate this somewhat would be to adapt the ManeuverVoter. Currently the ManeuverVoter increases votes slightly around the current heading of the boat for avoiding unnecessary maneuvers. An alternative could be to increase votes around the previous course selected by the system as this might increase the chance that a selected maneuver is performed

Parameter tuning could also be considered, e.g., by increasing the weighting of the possible port maneuver. This would likely improve the behaviour when an interacting vessel is approaching from port side. On the other hand, performing a port maneuver could possibly be less expected by other vessels and thus make the system less predictable.

Parameters will also need to be tuned when the voter based system is run with the visual field information from the thermal image processing as opposed to the simulator generated visual field.

It can also be noted that there is no formal guarantee that the voter based system will be able to avoid obstacles, or make optimal decisions.

7.6. Sea trials

The entire system needs to be properly evaluated in sea trials. Such trials are planned for the summer of 2018.

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References

FRIEBE, A.; OLSSON, M.; LE GALLIC, M.; LESS'ARD-SPRINGETT, J.; DAHL, K.; WALLER, M. (2017), *A marine research ASV utilizing wind and solar power*, OCEANS 2017, Aberdeen, pp.1-7

JAULIN, L. (2001), *Path planning using intervals and graphs*, Reliable Computing 7:1

JAULIN, L.; LE BARS, F. (2013), *A simple controller for line following of sailboats*, Robotic Sailing 2012, Springer, pp.117-129

LARSON, J.; BRUCH, M.; EBKEN, J. (2006), *Autonomous navigation and obstacle avoidance for unmanned surface vehicles*, SPIE 6230 Conf., Unmanned Systems Technology VIII, 623007

LARSON, J; BRUCH, M.; HALTERMAN, R; ROGERS, J.; WEBSTER, R. (2007) *Advances in Autonomous Obstacle Avoidance for Unmanned Surface Vehicles*, Defense Technical Information Center

LESS'ARD-SPRINGETT, J.; FRIEBE, A.; LE GALLIC, M. (2018), *Voter based control system for collision avoidance and sailboat navigation*, Robotic Sailing 2017, Springer, pp.57-68

LIU, Z.; ZHANG, Y.; YU, X.; YUAN, C. (2016), *Unmanned Surface Vehicles: An overview of*

developments and challenges, Annual Reviews in Control, Elsevier 41, pp.71-93

ROSENBLATT, J.K. (2010), *DAMN: A distributed architecture for mobile navigation*, J. Experimental & Theoretical Artificial Intelligence 9:2-3, pp.339-360

Fitting Watertight NURBS Patchworks over Irregular Curve Networks with LEANURBS

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel method for the extraction of a patchwork of NURBS surfaces from a solid model that is represented by a network of intersecting curves of arbitrary topology. Its purpose is to produce export files in standard formats such as IGES and it specifically addresses issues that third-party software have in dealing with high numbers of patches and minute gaps due to fitting tolerances. The patches produced by this method can cover large parts of the model and reduce the number of exported patches by several orders of magnitude. Touching edges of adjacent patches are mathematically equivalent so that the patchwork is free of gaps.

1. Introduction

Non-uniform rational B-spline surface patches (NURBS patches) form the basis of most geometric modellers. A NURBS patch is a mathematical method that is used to describe the shape of a sculpted surface, and its application in design software is more due to convenience for the programmer than to productivity of the designer: NURBS patches have a number of drawbacks that designers are forced to fight with if they are to use such modellers to sculpt a large smooth surface of arbitrary topology with strict geometric requirements such as a ship hull. These drawbacks are described in detail in *Veelo (2004)* and are generally acknowledged, see *Sharma et al. (2012)*. Fortunately for naval architects, alternative hull form modellers exist, such as Fairway — the versatile hull design module of PIAS developed by SARC — that has been in production for decades, *Koelman and Veelo (2013)*.

Fairway eliminates the drawbacks of NURBS patches by not using them for design tasks altogether. Instead, the designer works on a network of intersecting curves. The topology of this network is arbitrary and the curves are under the complete control of the designer, without unintended dependencies in their definition. Any number of curves can intersect in one point and the mesh cells in this network can have any number of sides. Based on the curve geometries, the system automatically constructs and maintains a continuous watertight surface across the entire network by filling the cells with another kind of surface patches: so-called transfinately interpolating surfaces. NURBS aren't applicable here. This surface is used for visualisation, for interpolation of new curves and for generating faceted export files like STL.

Apart from the freedom in modelling that the designer is offered by this approach, an important aspect of Fairway is its capabilities for curve fairing. Even though a continuous surface is defined across intersection points, curves can be allowed to deviate from each other at their common intersection by a configurable degree, what we call the fairing deviation. This way, network consistency can be temporarily traded for increased curve fairness, in support of an iterative process towards a consistent and fair surface — much in the same way as lines plans have traditionally been faired by hand, *Koelman (1997,1999)*. In practice, the fairing deviation is seldom completely reduced to zero but left at a certain production accuracy. This fact is of relevance for the method presented in this paper.

The irony, though, is that one can seek to solve challenges in a design process by inventing new methods, but designers don't live on an island: they rely on the possibility to exchange the product of their design with other systems. In earlier years, data exchange in the form of curves was sufficient, because all that was required for production were curves: stiffener profiles, plate contours and template drawings are all unambiguously defined by curves. But in modern years, where structures are analysed numerically and evaluated in virtual reality, surfaces play an increasingly important role. These third-party systems expect data to be handed to them in the form of NURBS patches. And so

there is an additional problem to be solved, the problem of conversion between essentially incompatible data representations.

Until recently, Fairway had tackled that problem through the pragmatic application of a conventional NURBS surface fitting algorithm to a regular grid of surface points for each network cell individually. Each four-sided cell produced one NURBS patch and each n -sided cell produced n smaller NURBS patches. Although that method is straightforward and relatively time-efficient, a typical production-ready model can contain hundreds of curves producing thousands of very small NURBS patches. And, due to the approximating nature of fitting algorithms, there would always be minute gaps between the patches no matter how low the tolerance would be set. Perhaps not surprisingly, systems on the receiving end have problems dealing with such patch clouds — which in itself illustrates that NURBS patches are not the be all and end all of surface representation.

Fairway users desire the ability to export a hull form as a smaller set of larger NURBS patches that do not need cumbersome surface repair or stitching. By means of a considerable investment in research and development, SARC has succeeded to meet this desire with a completely new method for constructing NURBS patches over curve networks — baptized LEANURBS, an acronym for **Lowest Effective Amount of NURBS** — which is presented in this paper. The next section will briefly recap surface fitting theory. Section 3 presents the theoretical core of our contribution to fitting a 3D surface to irregularly structured data. Section 4 is about the measures that prevent gaps between patches, including considerations regarding the fairing deviation mentioned earlier. Section 5 discusses the definition of patch contours and partitioning of the shell. Section 6 shows that theories not always work in practice, and describes adjustments that make them work most of the time nonetheless. Words about performance are given in section 7, followed by applications and future work in section 8.

2. Basics of surface fitting theory

Fitting parametric surfaces to point clouds is a field of research on its own. As we only have space for a coarse classification of approaches here, we limit ourselves to the fitting of quadrilateral patches:

1. Fitting a 3D quadrilateral patch to a grid of points. The grid is required to be regular, with points evenly distributed in rows and columns.
2. Fitting to an irregularly structured point set on a rectangular domain. The fitting is done in one dimension only.
3. Fitting a 3D surface to an unstructured point set.

Algorithms for 1. and 2. are presented in *Dierckx (1993)*, amongst other places. The first approach is used in Fairway for the fitting of NURBS patches to individual network cells and comes with the drawbacks that we have set out to eliminate. Since we want a single patch to cover a larger region of our network of curves, which has an arbitrary topology and cells are arranged irregularly, we cannot produce a regular grid of points that covers the geometry of the network in sufficient detail. So we need an approach that applies to an irregularly structured point set.

The second approach does cover the irregularity requirement but is not directly applicable because NURBS control points (which are regularly structured) can only be adjusted in one dimension to match the irregularly structured data points. This can only be used to fit to, for example, a height field in a topological map, not to shapes that are curved in all three dimensions such as ship hulls.

What we seem to need is an algorithm from the third category. However, this kind of problems is hard to solve and typically requires application of artificial intelligence. The field is still being actively researched, see *Zhang et al. (2016)* and *Marinić-Kragić et al. (2018)*. Besides, the approximative nature of the algorithms also applies to the patch borders, meaning that the problem of gaps between patches remains.

3. 3D fitted surfaces over irregularly structured data

What we have found is a way to simplify the problem, so that the straightforward one-dimensional fitting algorithm (from the second category above) can be applied to construct a three-dimensional patch that fits the irregularly structured data.

Given a rectangular region on the Fairway surface that we want to fit a NURBS patch to, we start with a simple surface patch G that coarsely approximates the internal surface shape of the region, but is an exact match along the borders. The difference between G and the Fairway surface can be seen as an offset. Computing offsets of NURBS surfaces is in general a complicated matter, see *Piegl and Tiller (1999)* and *Ravi Kumar et al. (2001)*, but we can keep things relatively simple in this case. The non-uniform offset can be expressed as a direction vector field O and a magnitude, the scalar field S . G , O and S are all bivariate “surfaces” in the mathematical sense that they are defined on a two-dimensional parameter space. This means that the fitted surface F can be expressed as the linear combination

$$F = G + O \cdot S \quad (1)$$

Since G matches the region borders, S is zero along the borders and the direction O is irrelevant along the borders. This means we can choose O as we see fit, leaving S as the only unknown. S is one-dimensional and has a rectangular domain, so it can be generated easily by an algorithm of the second category that is readily available from *Dierckx (1993)*.

Fortunately, every component on the right-hand side of equation (1) can be expressed as a B-spline surface patch, as we'll illustrate shortly. B-splines are equivalent to NURBS with uniform weight factors, making them non-rational. Standard algorithms from *Piegl and Tiller (1997)* can be applied to make these B-spline patches compatible with each other, with identical degrees and knot vectors, and equal numbers of control points. With compatibility in place, F can be computed as a (non-rational) NURBS by applying the arithmetic operations in (1) on the control points of G , O and S . We'll now take a closer look on how G , O and S can be defined.

3.1. Definition of the basis surface G

The basis surface can be defined as the bilinearly blended Coons patch expressed in B-spline form, interpolating the four boundary curves of the region. This requires the boundary curves to be defined as B-spline curves, but more on that later. As a first step, opposing boundary curves are made compatible by standard procedures of degree raising, reparameterisation and knot refinement. The three components of the Coons patch (two ruled surfaces between two pairs of opposing boundaries and one bilinear surface between the corners) are easily constructed and expressed in B-spline form. These are then made compatible again and combined linearly. This process, and the algorithms that produce compatibility, are described in detail in *Piegl and Tiller (1997)*. Because this surface is an exact match at the patch boundaries, the internal shape of the patch is a suitably coarse approximation of the internal shape of the Fairway surface region.

3.2. Definition of the vector field O

As we have hinted to earlier, we are quite free to choose O , as long as there is a unique projection for any pair of parameters (u, v) from $G(u, v)$ through $O(u, v)$ onto the Fairway surface within the bounded region. A uniform direction vector extracted from the linear component of the Coons patch would probably work in many cases, but we expect better results if the local normal vector on G can be used. However, textbooks teach that the surface normal of a B-spline patch cannot itself be expressed as a B-spline because of the square root in normalisation. Fortunately, normalisation is not important to us: As long as we have a direction vector of any non-zero length we can scale it to get from G to F . As it turns out, a field of direction vectors that is merely orthogonal to G can be expressed in B-spline form.

Fig.1: The basis Coons patch G with orthogonal offset vectors to the Fairway surface, viewed somewhat from the side (top) and below (bottom)

First, two B-spline representations for the first derivative of G are constructed, one in either parameter direction u and v , representing tangent vector fields in these directions. This is accomplished by standard procedures described in *Piegl and Tiller (1997)*, and results in B-spline patches of lower degree in one direction and also lacking one row or column of control vectors compared to each other. Compatibility in degrees is restored by degree raising, which also doubles (internal) knot values and adds rows or columns of control vectors. So, once again, application of knot refinement algorithms produce compatibility between the two derivative patches, so that they only differ in the values of control vectors. Taking the cross product of corresponding control vectors produces orthogonal control vectors that, when combined with the knot vectors of the compatible tangent patches, produces the B-spline representation O of the vector field that is locally orthogonal to G . It does no harm to add a normalising step after the cross product to give the control vectors equal length, and helps reduce unnecessary variation in O so that the fitting algorithm may have an easier job to find a matching S .

3.3. Determination of the scalar field S

The scalar B-spline patch S is produced by the fitting algorithm, which takes as input scale factors s_i for certain (u_i, v_i) parameter pairs that are irregularly distributed over the rectangular domain. These

parameter values are produced by a search: starting from a known three-dimensional point p_i on the Fairway surface (on a curve or somewhere on a transfinite surface) we search for the (u_i, v_i) for which $O(u_i, v_i)$ passes through that point p_i and $G(u_i, v_i)$. That is, we minimise the shortest distance between the point p and a line through $G(u, v)$ in direction $O(u, v)$. Once the parameters have been determined, s_i results from the vector projection of the difference between p_i and $G(u_i, v_i)$ on $O(u_i, v_i)$:

$$s_i = \frac{(p_i - G(u_i, v_i)) \cdot O(u_i, v_i)}{|O(u_i, v_i)|^2} \quad (2)$$

Note that the vertices of G are ordinary control points, the vertices of O are three-dimensional vectors and that the vertices of S are one-dimensional scalars.

Fig.1 shows an example of what the basis Coons patch G looks like, applied to the bulb of the “Duisburg Test Case”, *El Moctar et al. (2015)*. The network of resulting NURBS control points is shown in black. Note the exact fit to the Fairway curves around the patch boundaries, and how offset vectors are locally orthogonal to G .

4. Mind the gap!

The definition of the basis surface G in the previous section assumed the boundaries to be available as B-spline curves. Fortunately, the majority of curves in a Fairway model are effectively B-splines already (NURBS with uniform weight factors). They can however extend past the patch region and therefore may be too long. The standard algorithm of knot insertion, also given by *Piegl and Tiller (1997)*, allows a B-spline curve to be trimmed at any parameter value, producing a new B-spline with a shape that is exactly identical to the original (for as far as it extends). This implies that two adjacent patches can be given borders that are mathematically equivalent, producing an absolutely watertight connection. The two patches can even run along different lengths of the curve, producing a T-joint, still without gaps because their borders are derived from the common boundary curve.

Not all curves in a Fairway model are pure B-splines: conic sections like circular arcs are rational B-splines, that is, proper NURBS. Secondly, Fairway allows so-called slave curves to be defined as the linear combination of other curves and constants. Slave curves have no NURBS representation at all. These non-B-spline curves can be converted to B-splines by sampling them densely and fairing a B-spline through them by application of Fairway’s built-in fairing methods. This is an approximation, but as long as the same procedure is performed for both patches on either side of such a curve, it will produce an identical border.

So, by deriving the four bounding splines of G from the curves in the Fairway network, we principally ensure that adjacent NURBS patches possess identical geometries on their shared border, and should be free of gaps. However, there are two intricacies that require special actions to defend that principle. Firstly, the fitting algorithm always produces an approximation according to a given tolerance, meaning that S is not guaranteed to be zero along the borders. Since G is already a perfect fit along the borders, in order to not introduce a perturbation there, we simply transfer the boundary control points of G (after it has been made compatible with O and S) straight to F and only perform the arithmetics on internal vertices.

The second intricacy is due to the fairing deviation mentioned earlier, which intentionally allows curves in a Fairway model to deviate from their shared intersection point by a configurable degree. So after boundary curves have been trimmed to the correct length, they probably do not yet connect exactly. In order to produce watertight connections at the patch corners, the trimmed curves are given an affine transformation to stretch and tilt them so that they start and end at common intersection points with other bounding curves. Because of the affine invariance property of B-spline curves, the transformation can simply be applied to the control points of the curve. However, this is not a straightforward process: When the corner of one patch is on the edge of another patch (forming a T-joint), that

corner should be shifted onto the other edge after that edge has been stretched and tilted. And because that edge may connect to a corner (or two) that itself forms a T-joint, there is a tree-like dependency graph that must be traversed of curves that should be stretched and tilted in order. We are talking about minute adjustments to the curves, but if we are to guarantee a patchwork that is free of gaps, we need to be pedantic.

To conclude this section, we should probably address a question that the observant reader may have: “Why couldn’t degree raising, reparameterisation and knot refinement be used to achieve compatibility between touching NURBS patches generated by the old scheme, eliminating gaps there?” The reason is that the fitting algorithm of the first category produces a B-spline surface patch that has a parameterisation that is not necessarily linearly compatible with the network curves at its borders. A non-linear re-parameterisation is possible but complicated and approximative, and would increase the number of control points for little gain. It would not completely eliminate gaps and therefore not be worth the trouble. To the contrary, an algorithm from the second category works on input where each sample point has an accompanying pair of parameters, so that the fit is actually performed in parameter space and therefore needs no reparameterisation. That is an essential trait in the elimination of gaps.

5. Partitioning the shell

Having developed a theory for fitting NURBS surface patches to large regions over irregular curve networks, remains a practice for partitioning a network into four-sided regions. Fortunately, the Fairway graphical user interface has a tool for defining regions already, in which the user identifies corners of the region in a clockwise order. This tool is used to paint regions of the shell in a different color, or define regions of developable surfaces or define the contours of shell plate expansions. We have simply extended its use for the definition of export surfaces, if the region has exactly four corners and no knuckles in the internals of the region sides. Currently, the user is responsible for the partitioning of the shell into export regions interactively.

During this interactive process, the user is likely to experience that partitioning a ship hull, which is of arbitrary topology, into purely four-sided regions not always has an obvious solution. Often one is left with one or more “holes” with three or five or more sides. Again, this is another reminder that NURBS surface patches are not the be all and end all for surface design. Nevertheless, a working solution can usually be found with a few creative measures.

Fig.2: The “Duisburg Test Case”, *El Moctar et al. (2015)*, partitioned in quadrilateral shell regions

A three-sided hole can in some cases be successfully filled with a four-sided patch by cheatingly placing one of the corners somewhere along one of the sides of the hole. This is called a degenerate corner, and works best where the side has a bend with high curvature and the surface is ideally flat. An example would be the transom stern, bounded by the deck line, centre buttock and aft frame: the degenerate corner can be placed in the bilge of the frame. Another example can be seen in Fig.1, which has a degenerate corner in the lower front of the bulb.

If a hole has more than four sides, it can be subdivided into two or more four-sided regions by interpolating auxiliary curves, for example by intersection with an oblique plane. Such an auxiliary curve can be seen in Fig.2, in the bilge at around the middle of the aft ship, where three regions meet in a Y-formation.

6. Serving the fitting algorithm right

This is the part where we discover that theories not always work in practice. When we finally completed the implementation of all algorithms and had assembled a working system, our first tests delivered results of varying quality, some of which were downright disappointing. The culprit turned out to be the fitting algorithm, which showed to be picky about the data that it is served. The symptoms were warnings about rank deficiency and severe rippling in the generated patches.

The core of the problem, actually, is that NURBS patches are built on a regular grid of control points that are distributed along rows and columns over their quadrilateral domain. Because patches often are necessarily tapered to achieve a complete patchwork arrangement over the hull, the spacing between control points can vary considerably across the patch. If sampling points (the input to the fitting algorithm) are taken from an even distribution across the region, this will lead to a scarcity of information where control points are densely packed. This causes the rank deficiency warning, which means that there are many solutions that would all produce a “valid” fit. Just increasing the density of sampling points is not a trustworthy remedy because it also increases data points in the wider areas of the patch, which motivates the algorithm to insert additional rows and columns of control points because that reduces the mean fitting error, and thereby the problem of rank deficiency is kept in place.

We have countered this problem by comparing the lengths of the borders of the region to get a measure of the concentration of control points, so that the spacing of sampling points can be adjusted accordingly across the region. This works well for typical cases where opposite sides of a region have different lengths. But should a region be narrow in the middle and wide along the sides, then this strategy will not be able to prevent rank deficiency. The pragmatic approach is then to have the user split the region in two at the narrow section, which will work around the problem.

But providing appropriate density of sampling points does not prevent all ripple effects. When sampling points happen to align more or less with rows or columns of control points, the fitting algorithm is tempted to decrease the fitting error by adding another row or column in between the sampling points. Because the fitting algorithm has no notion of aesthetics or global smoothness and only aims at minimising the mean fitting error, it is happy to place that row quite a bit off if that produces a better fit at existing points, because there are no points near the new row that would keep it in place. Typically, this does not produce a single ridge but several ripples running parallel, probably because undulation causes additional rows of control points to be added. Again, increasing the sampling density does not mitigate the effect, it just causes finer and more ripples.

We have found that ripples can be prevented in most cases by adding a random jitter to the parameters at which points are sampled from transfinite patches, so that alignment with control points is greatly reduced. Of course, sample points taken from curves can still align, so it may be necessary for the user to increase sample point density or maybe remove a curve or two from the model if they are not essential for the definition of geometry and are not relevant for construction.

Fig.3: The fitted NURBS patch with sample points, viewed somewhat from the side (top) and below (bottom)

To conclude this section about input to the fitting algorithm, we should mention sampling point weighting. The algorithm allows different weights to be given to individual points, to make some points more important than others. Since curves are the authoritative definition of geometry in Fairway, and the transfinite surface patches that fill the network cells derive their geometry from the curves, it makes sense to give points that are sampled from curves a greater weight than the points that are sampled from patches. That works well if many curves run skewly across the region, which often is the case, but since only samples from patches can be jittered, giving emphasis to curves can, again, cause ripples to emerge. The same counts for choosing a higher sampling density on curves than in cells. Tweaking these values does affect the balance between success and failure.

Fig.3 shows the same region as Fig.1, with the sample point separation decreased to 0.4 m and fit completed. Note the jitter of sample point positions, the increased density of the NURBS control network (in black), and the smoothness of the resulting surface.

7. Performance

There are many steps in the construction of LEANURBS, but the ones that require most time are the search for parameters and the fitting step. These depend heavily on the number of sample points, so that the time it takes to produce a NURBS surface patch grows roughly quadratically with increasing sampling density. This means that, for example, fitting with a separation of 0.01 m can take 100 times longer than fitting with a separation of 0.1m. Therefore, we have made this density configurable in the GUI, per region, and the NURBS patch can be generated and previewed per region in the GUI. It is recommend to start out with a large separation, like a tenth or fifth of the longest side of the region, which will produce a patch in less than a second, then assess the result and decrease the separation only when necessary. The largest separation that still produces a good fit depends of course on the internal shape of the region: a completely planar surface produces a perfect fit with a minimum of sampling points. The patch in Fig.3 was produced in less than nine seconds. By the way, the issue of performance speed is not of prime importance, because the LEANURBS method is not applied in the hull design process itself, but only occasionally, when the hull shape is ready to be exported to other software.

Fig.4: Graphical user interface (GUI) showing sampling density and preview

LEANURBS typically have a highly non-uniform knot vector, and unevenly spaced rows and columns of control points, which are also high in number. This stems primarily from the many knot refinement steps necessary to obtain compatibility between opposing boundary curves and patch components, which is inevitable for the elimination of gaps. The number of control points is additionally increased by the fitting algorithm. We have not found that receiving systems have a problem with these patches, but it does mean that they are badly suitable for interactive design by control point manipulation — but that should hardly come as a surprise.

Users should be aware that the fitting algorithm can only add whole rows and columns of control points that run across the entire patch, even when their added control is only required in one area of the region. So, a sensible partition of the shell that takes this mechanism into account can help to prevent excessive numbers of control points, which of course also affects the performance of the fitting algorithm both in speed and quality.

There are two other problems that can arise from an unfortunate surface partition. Firstly, there may be local minima in the search for parameters (u, v) if the surface shape varies wildly within the region. This means that a solution cannot be found. This is of course detectable so that the corresponding sample point can be discarded, and a satisfactory fit may still be obtainable. Secondly, problems will arise if the orthogonal vectors originating from the base surface have more than one intersection with the Fairway surface. This is not very likely but if it occurs it will cause a discontinuous parameterisation which will definitely produce a distorted NURBS patch shape. Usually, these problems do not arise in typical shell partitions, assuming partitioning by a diligent user, and are easily detected visually in the preview.

Fig.5: The “Duisburg Test Case” completely described by LEANURBS patches

8. Applications and future work

Let it be clear: even with this considerable investment in NURBS surface patches, we are not going to implement NURBS surface editing functionality in Fairway. What we have illustrated is that one can trade a high number of small patches for a low number of large patches, but at the price of a high number of control points, making editing impractical. Whenever a designer has the desire to control a Fairway surface by means of control points, we offer a better method, developed in *Veelo (2004)*, called spatial deformation based on radial functions, that even gives control over the extent of the surface on which the manipulation has effect. That is a flexibility that cannot be offered by pure NURBS modellers or subdivision surface modellers.

Obviously, the main application of LEANURBS is export of Fairway geometry in standard exchange formats such as IGES. In addition, we are currently in collaboration with Friendship Systems to develop an exchange protocol utilising LEANURBS to establish a lossless exchange of hull geometry back and forth between Fairway and CAESES, which is a flexible CAD and optimization platform for fast and comprehensive design studies with simulation tools. Fig.6 shows the generated LEANURBS as imported by CAESES. Due to the absence of gaps, CAESES had no problem generating a water-tight mesh.

Fig.6: LEANURBS imported in CAESES. Courtesy Friendship Systems

Whereas we currently rely on manual partitioning by the user, *Ardavani (2017)* has shown that this task can largely be automated by application of a genetic algorithm. Proof-of-concept code exists, but has yet to be brought in production. One possible application could be to have the algorithm propose a partitioning, that subsequently can be adjusted or perfected by the user.

9. Conclusion

Although it is widely acknowledged that the NURBS surface method is less suitable for hull shape design and modelling, it keeps on haunting us: With PIAS/Fairway a better, non-NURBS surface method is available, but still other software suites, such as for CFD, FEM or engineering, require their import data to be in NURBS format. Simple conversion from the Fairway surface patches to NURBS surface patches has been available for years, but induced some problems, such as the resulting large number of NURBS patches. In order to provide a solution — and hence solve a problem that was introduced by inappropriate choices of others in the first place — a cunning framework of geometric modelling tools has been constructed, which converts a Fairway hull representation to a set of NURBS surfaces that are watertight, and limited in number.

References

- ARDAVANI, M. (2017), *Modeling and Simulation of Ship Shape Topology*, Master thesis UvA-VU
- DIERCKX, P. (1993), *Curve and Surface Fitting with Splines*, Monographs on Numerical Analysis, Oxford University Press (Fortran code: www.netlib.org/dierckx)
- KOELMAN, H.J. (1997), *Hull form design and fairing: tradition restored*, 6th Int. Marine Design Conf., Newcastle upon Tyne, pp.421–428
- KOELMAN, H.J. (1999), *Computer Support for the Design, Engineering and Prototyping of the Shape of Ship Hulls*, Doctoral thesis, TU Delft
- KOELMAN, H.J.; VEELO, B.N. (2013), *A technical note on the geometric representation of a ship hull form*, Computer-Aided Design 45/11, pp.1378–1381
- MARINIĆ-KRAGIĆ I.; ĆURKOVIĆ, M.; VUČINA, D. (2018), *Adaptive re-parameterization based on arbitrary scalar fields for shape optimization and surface fitting*, Eng. Appl. of Artificial Intelligence 67, pp.39–51
- MOCTAR, EL, A.; SHIGUNOV, V.; ZORN, T. (2012) *Duisburg Test Case: Post-Panamax Container Ship for Benchmarking*, J. Ship Technology Research 59/3, pp.50–64
- RAVI KUMAR, G.V.V.; SHASTRY, K.G.; PRAKASH, B.G. (2002), *Computing non-self-intersecting offsets of NURBS surfaces*, Computer-Aided Design 34, pp.209–228
- PIEGL, L.; TILLER, W. (1997), *The NURBS Book*, Monographs in Visual Communication, Springer
- PIEGL, L.; TILLER, W. (1999), *Computing offsets of NURBS curves and surfaces*, Computer-Aided Design 31, pp.147–156
- SHARMA, R.; KIM, T.-W.; STORCH, R.L.; HOPMAN, J.J.; ERIKSTAD, S.O. (2012), *Challenges in computer applications for ship and floating structure design and analysis*, Computer-Aided Design 44/3, pp.166–185
- VEELO, B.N. (2004), *Variations of Shape in Industrial Geometric Models*, Doctoral thesis NTNU 2004:106, hdl.handle.net/11250/241067
- ZHANG, Y.; CAO, J.; CHEN, Z.; LI, X.; ZENG, X.-M. (2016), *B-spline surface fitting with knot position optimization*, Computers & Graphics 58, pp.73–83

Using Augmented Reality to Improve Collision Avoidance and Resolution

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Abstract

Based on the Cognitive Work Analysis, described in a previous paper, an Ecological Interface is designed and built for the Augmented Reality application at Willem Barentsz. Incorporated, a.o., is the concept of Velocity Obstacles. This innovative way to visualize the problem space and solution space, provides the navigator with real time information about the possible combinations of course and speed that avoid intrusion into an other ship's protected zone. Hence, it is anticipated that this will result in better Situation Awareness, leading to less close encounters, a.k.a. near misses, and fewer collisions.

1. Introduction

The subject of Collision Avoidance (CA) has been much described and debated over the past decades. In the Royal Institute of Navigation's Journal of Navigation (JoN) alone, over 500 articles covering CA have been published since the 1950s. This illustrates both the importance and the complexity of the matter.

From the earliest article covering CA published in the JoN onward, *Le Page (1949)*, many valuable viewpoints, strategies, detection methods have been described. Every introduction of shipboard technology, e.g., RADAR, AIS and ECDIS, and each introduction of regulatory, e.g., Vessel Traffic Service (VTS) and Traffic Separation Schemes (TSS) gave reason to adapt new methods or extend existing ones. *CheeKuang Tam et al. (2009)* provided a comprehensive review of existing strategies. In this paper, we don't intend to introduce a new or adapted strategy on CA, but to illustrate how Augmented Reality (AR) might help in visualizing relevant elements of a CA method. The selected CA method in this paper, targets on visualizing so called *velocity obstacles*. These velocity obstacles can be seen as combinations of the own ship's heading and speed that will lead to the intrusion of someone else's Ship Domain (SD). The latter method was first introduced for use in marine navigation by *Degré and Lefèvre ((1981)* and elaborated on later by various authors, e.g, *Egil Pedersen et al. (20039)* and *Rafal Szlapczynski (2008)*.

The concept of AR is also not new, however, an interface design providing visual cues to assist the watch officer (WO) in his complex task of safe navigation has not yet been published. In *Procee et al. (2017)*, the design principles of such an interface are described. A first instance of this interface has been materialized lately. This paper describes the presumed functionalities and the motivation based on both theoretical underpinnings of the design method and the background of the first author in marine navigation.

2. Ecological Interface Design and Abstraction Hierarchy

2.1. Situation Awareness

There have been more than a few definitions of Situation Awareness (SA) developed over the past. In their review, *Breton and Rousseau (2003)* classify 26 definitions and methods to measure SA. In this paper the definition of SA is based on that of *Endsley and Jones (2012)*, p.13-29. According to their definition, SA can be broken down into three levels. The interface design, explained in this paper, addresses these three levels of SA.

The first step in achieving SA, i.e., Level 1, deals with the perception of elements in the environment. This means that the visual objects around the Own Ship (OS) must be seen and recognized, and their status or behavior with regard to the OS must be understood. The intuitive thought about AR, namely that just by adding a synthetic marker at the same visual location as the element will help in achieving SA, is misleading. It might even have detrimental effects when, e.g., 'perceiving the marker' is interpreted as 'perceiving the element'. In this paper the focus lies on CA, which in this case is narrowed down to entities underway on the sea surface, i.e., ships.

The second step in achieving SA, i.e., Level 2, deals with comprehending the situation. This means that in the case of CA the WO must get an understanding of the *meaning* of a target with its course and speed and position relative to the OS. By providing a meaningful cue, e.g., the direction of change in bearing, it is expected that the WO is helped in understanding whether a target will pass astern or ahead, or even does not pass astern or ahead at all. The latter being an indication of a close encounter in the future.

The third step. Level 3, covers understanding the projection of the future status. In the case of CA this means that the WO must have an understanding about the predicted closest distance, Closest Point of Approach, CPA, and the time it takes to reach this closest point of approach i.e., time to CPA, TCPA. It is expected that the WO can be supported in understanding the future status by, e.g., showing the target's velocity obstacle in the AR interface.

2.2. Abstraction Hierarchy

Burns and Hajdukiewicz (2004), p.16-17, motivate the purpose of developing an Abstraction Hierarchy (AH). In the case of CA, the conventional work domain model, i.e., measures to detect collision danger is provided by several sources, e.g., *IMO (1972)*, *Petty (2004)* or *ICS (2016)*. This model relies primarily on detection of a target, visually or by RADAR, and determining the change in bearing of that target. The underlying line of reasoning is that when a target's visual bearing is not changing, risk of collision exists. When RADAR is used for CA, the underlying principle remains the same.

The introduction of the Automated Identification System (AIS), however, implies complications with respect to CA. Firstly, the bearing to the object is determined by calculation instead of direct observation. Secondly, the data on which this calculation is based was in the first place provided by the target itself. Since AIS does not provide in an integrity monitoring mechanism, additional information is needed to solve this integrity issue. This might be solved, e.g., by visual augmented reconnaissance, i.e., co-location of the synthetic marker on top of the target. Despite these complications and the relative lack of debate about it, *Stitt (2004)*, AIS has gained broad support for providing another tool for CA, *Tijardovic (2009)*. *Hua-Zhi Hsu et al. (2009)*, show through simulator experiments that the use of AIS is beneficial to the effectiveness of target detection and avoidance. This justifies the adoption of AIS derived information in the proposed AR interface.

The Abstraction Hierarchy (AH) in Fig.1 shows five levels of abstraction that define the relation between the *purpose* of the processes, i.e., the top level, and the *physical form*, i.e., the level closest to the worker. This AH shows the process of building, maintaining and enhancing SA within the system boundary of an individually operating WO, working on a motor vessel that is underway in any area and in any kind of weather and at any time of the day.

Here, the top-level purpose of navigation is defined as, we have to work *effective*, i.e., goal-driven exploitation of the ship as economical system, we have to work *efficient*, i.e., maximizing output at minimal cost of operation, and we have to work *safe* in order to preserve the value of human, environmental and material assets. The way we do that is by getting underway, *locomotion*, i.e., moving assets from one place to another, thus adding value to it. While locomotion in the absolute sense is thus related to efficiency and production, locomotion relative to (possibly moving) obstacles is key to collision avoidance. Also, we do that by providing and using information, e.g., routeing

orders, nautical publications. The third way to do that is by bringing in expertise, i.e., the heuristics that have been developed to get the work done, in other words, to reach the purpose.

Fig.1: Abstraction Hierarchy Situation Awareness through AR interface

The Generalized function level shows the ways to realize these abstract functions. If we restrict this to CA, which in Fig.1 is emphasized by the pink colored area, we can define two functions to reach our purpose of effective, efficient and safe, namely, collision avoidance and integrity monitoring. Integrity monitoring, e.g., checking whether the broadcast position of a target aligns with the observed position relative to the OS, is done by the physical function object sensing. Collision avoidance is realized by the four physical functions shown in Fig.1, i.e., we need information about both the OS and the target's speed and direction in order to determine whether danger for collision exists as well as both the OS's and target's position relative to each other.

The information which is produced by these physical functions is displayed to support the user in his purpose, i.e., the task of safe, efficient and effective sailing. This physical-form layer is the base on which the AR interface is built. Fig.2 shows a first prototype of an AR interface for CA. In the prototype the real world can be seen, e.g., parts of the bridge console, the ships bow and sea space, together with augmentation, like target symbols, heading marker and direction markers for every whole degree. The augmentation is shown on top of the real world, hence, it may be regarded as head-up display, as opposed to a head-down display, e.g., RADAR.

Restricted to CA, the user needs heading information, which is shown through the Heading Marker (HM) combined with the figure for the actual Gyro course, see item **A** in Fig.2. The user needs also speed information, this is shown in two ways, by a vertical scale, see item **B** in Fig.2 and indirectly by the length of the OS vector in the shown diagram, item **C**. Items **D**, **E** and **F** represent targets. The meaning of the target symbol is shown by its shape and its color. The motivation for the use of target

symbols is given in the next subsection. The fourth, CA related, information source, is the Velocity Obstacles diagram. This is shown as item **G** in Fig.2. This diagram shows combinations of OS's speed and heading (a.k.a. Gyro course) which will, when no actions are undertaken, sooner or later result in the intrusion of the OS in the target's SD, and is thus a reflection of the relative velocities with respect to the surrounding moving objects.

Fig.2: Example of AR interface in a simulation scenario

2.3. Ecological Interface Design

Van Paassen et al. (2018) among others introduce recent developments, i.e. approximately 25 years, of Ecological Interface Design (EID) in various work domains. For the specific domain of locomotion an overview of 13 EID designs is presented. Whereas the majority of these focus on aviation, *Ostendorp et al. (2015)* give a detailed suggestion for marine piloting. Other suggested sources for EID can be found in, e.g., *Burns and Hajdukiewicz (2004)*, *Bennett and Flach (2011)*.

Within the work domain boundary mentioned in the previous section on AH, i.e., a single WO on the motor vessel's bridge, underway in any weather, at any time and in any area, EID materializes in a number of elements. The overarching EID's framework, to visualize the *ecology*, is related to these elements that are incorporated in the AR interface.

Apart from the elements related to CA, which are described in the previous and, more detailed, in the following section, there are, e.g., a framework of compression lines, symbols for ATON and a cross-track distance (XTD) scale to visualize ecology.

The compression lines are constantly moving underneath towards the observer, thus giving the impression of OS's movement relative to the ground. When OS drifts, i.e., due to wind, or is set from

its course due to, e.g., the tidal stream, the moving pattern of compression lines provide an immediate cue. Perceiving this cue requires skill based behavior, e.g., with low cognitive demand.

ATON function as (real) markers of fairways and dangers, hence, they are an inherent part of the ecology. The reason to incorporate ATON symbols in the AR interface is to augment the ecology. The function of ATON is given by their color, their shape and in some cases, their topmark. These cues, i.e., color and shape, are used for the internationally adopted chart symbols and are also used for the symbols in the AR interface. Hence, perceiving these cues, requires rule-based behavior *Rasmussen (1983)*, however, because these symbols are already part of the WO's body of knowledge, it is expected that the mental burden related to perceiving them is low.

The XTD scale shows OS's position relative to the intended track. It is therefore an implicit indication of OS's affordance. The allowable deviation from the track can be taken into account by the WO, or the borders of the validated path, i.e., the width of the track that is checked for dangerous features, can be shown in the XTD. In both cases the allowable space, or affordance, is inherently shown.

2.4. Symbol design

The design of a meaningful target symbol for use in an AR interface is a process that has not yet ended. However, in order to reach a first prototype, a number of assumptions have been made. The first assumption is that every target within visual range must be shown by at least a marginal visual cue in order to confirm the integrity of the AR system. Motivation for this can be found in *Rasmussen (1983)*'s theory of SRK based behavior, namely, when, e.g., a distant target is seen by the observer without the inherent confirmation by the system, i.e., by showing a synthetic visual cue, the observer will utilize problem solving skills, i.e., knowledge-based behavior, in order to verify the system's integrity. An algorithm that balances between the two extremes of a minimum necessary user's computational need in order to perceive, i.e., the conventional perceptual psychologist's approach, and the preferable absence of user's computational need, i.e., the Gibsonian view in order to perceive, see *Bennett and Flach (2011)* (p.83), is yet to be developed.

A second assumption is that the WO is primarily interested in the relative change in bearing of the detected target. This is because formal training uses this method to detect risk of collision. Observing consecutive visual bearings, e.g., by using compass and azimuth device, is the conventional way to do that. When RADAR is used, consecutive bearings by Electronic Bearing Line (EBL) can be observed as well. The introduction of the Automated RADAR Plotting Aid (ARPA) provides a derived relative vector of the target. The direction of this vector is an indication for collision danger when it points towards the OS. In all three cases, it takes time, usually about 3 minutes, to ascertain a reliable outcome. This reliability is restricted to the target's and OS's unaltered course and speed. Each change in course and speed of either target or OS, results in unreliable ARPA data again for approximately the next 3 minutes.

Utilizing AIS, the received target's position, course and speed, results, almost instantaneous, in a derived relative vector, CPA and TCPA. From this it can be inferred what the change in bearing of the detected target will be. This information is shown in the AR interface by two types of symbol shape. The shape, either ' $<$ ' or ' $>$ ', is chosen for its unambiguous simplicity. Relative to the OS, the target will move either to right or to left. In case the change in relative bearing is insufficient, i.e., leading to a critical CPA, the symbol is neither left nor right, hence, ' $|$ '. As said, the effectiveness and user acceptance of this prototype must be validated by empirical experimentation.

The third assumption is that experienced WOs apply an intuitive threshold in TCPA to get alarmed by a detected potential intruder into the OS's SD. *Westrenen and Ellerbroek (2017)* motivate that a projected intrusion within a time range of 450 seconds is considered as conflicting. This definition is aimed at analyzing the frequency of near misses. However, their paper also mentions that consulted training experts deem a time range of 600 seconds as acceptable. Another perspective to this, is that TCPA can be considered as 'escape time', in which case several factors, e.g., the maneuvering

characteristic of both ships, will influence the time range or TCPA to define a critical situation. A globally agreed value on TCPA alarm limit does not exist, in practice the WO uses his personal heuristic or the value prescribed by his most senior colleague, usually the captain.

Fig.3: Decision diagram for symbolization of targets

The AR interface that is discussed here, uses three levels of alarm based on calculated TCPA and CPA, see Fig.3. If the target is crossing either OS's bow or its stern and stays out of the OS's SD, i.e., has a CPA larger than the dimension of OS's SD (shown in Fig.3 as dPZ), the symbol is neutrally colored, gray. If the target is predicted to enter OS's SD within an arbitrarily defined time limit (TCPA) of 12 minutes, the symbol will be colored magenta. Else, the danger is considered imminent, i.e., the target has a critical CPA but there's time to escape, which results in the color orange, meaning it's neither neutral nor dangerous. As said, the value for the TCPA alarm limit depends on several factors and is not globally defined or agreed upon. Hence, the threshold for alarming must be adjustable by the WO in order to function as an effective alarm.

2.5. Velocity Obstacles

The principle functioning of Velocity Obstacles (VO) is well described by a variety of sources, e.g., *Degré and Lefèvre (1981)*, *Ellerbroek (2013)*. Whether the concept of VO was first introduced in shipping or in aviation is irrelevant, the importance is that it has landed on more solid ground now, partly due the introduction of an innovative AR interface as discussed here, partly because of the research into novel ways to support aviators in free flight and Air Traffic Controllers in their controlled airspace.

Usually the proposed way of visualizing the conflict zone is by augmenting an existing display, e.g., RADAR, with an overlay showing the maneuvering envelope and the projected conflict space. The expected acceptance and effectiveness of such a combination lies in the experience that the user already has with the existing display, e.g., RADAR.

Experienced marine RADAR observers are able to generate situation awareness based on the projection of RADAR target returns on a display, which is usually about 50 cm in diameter and covers a range between three and twelve nautical miles. This RADAR picture presents the observer a scaled orthogonal view on the world around the OS. However, when this orthogonal view is projected in perspective, i.e., used in a Head Mounted Display (HMD) for AR, the perception of distance and direction relative to OS changes dramatically. For this reason, the projection of the conflict space versus the solution space can hardly be done in perspective. Therefore, an alternative is created in the Conflict Space Diagram (CSD). *Degré and Lefèvre (1981)* (p. 299, Fig.3-4) suggest already a first instance of CSD showing a T-shaped marker projecting vertically a critical speed interval at the present course, and horizontally, a critical course at the present speed. It is not clear whether this CSD was materialized.

An adoption of the T-shaped marker is the proposed CSD used in the AR interface (see Fig.2 item **G**). The horizontal axis comprises of all possible headings relative to the present HM, i.e., Gyrocourse. This means that the affordance, i.e., the allowable option to change heading, either to Starboard or to Port, is shown to the WO. The vertical axis comprises the speed envelope, meaning the affordance in changing speed from the maximum of 16 knots in this example, as shown in Fig.2, to zero. The OS vector, Fig.2 **C**, which is visually aligned with the bow, shows the present speed by its length. From the orthogonal projected conflict zone defined in polar coordinates, i.e., bearing and range, the ACZ is transferred to Cartesian coordinates and shown in the CSD. When the need arises to alter course and/or speed in order to avoid intrusion in the target's SD, the shown solution space indicates possible combinations that can be chosen by the WO.

It is expected, that adding the display of conflict zones from natural and cultural elements, e.g., shoals and ATON, as well as adding the visualized overarching purpose, i.e., to arrive at the destination, safely, timely and using the planned means, will provide an interface that is rich in visual cues. The latter is a requisite for Recognition Primed Decision making (RPD), a principle first introduced by *Klein (1998)* which seems very suited to modeling the decision-making process of the WO. Fine tuning the AR interface in order to support RPD will be covered in a later paper.

Still under development is the user's need to relate the actual target's position with the associated

conflict space in the CSD in order to avoid utilizing problem solving skills by the user. The urgent need to support the user in that, is convincingly demonstrated by the shown example, Fig.2, based on a complex situation with nine targets around. *Borst et al. (2017)* have resolved this issue for an orthogonal (RADAR) presentation in the air traffic control domain.

Another, still unresolved, issue is that the user needs to know how much time is left before actual intrusion into the target's SD takes place. In some, complex, cases for example, it can be necessary to use one target's ACZ for a limited time in order to solve a more urgent conflict with another target. The visualization of this affordance is not yet incorporated. It is suggested that an ordering of color, limited to, e.g., four steps, can be used to express the time to intrusion. This will present a ACZ colored with a single hue, which is subdivided into, e.g., four sections which are ordered by using increasing values of that single hue. In this suggestion, the visual variable hue represents a meaning, i.e., it's a ACZ. Because there is no difference in the meaning of one ACZ to another, hue is not changed from one ACZ to another.

3. Ship's Domain, Protected Zone

Throughout this paper, we will use the term Ship's Domain (SD) as equivalent to the term Protected Zone (PZ), the former having a broader use in marine navigation. In order to discriminate between important or dangerous targets displayed in the AR interface, the SD or ship's domain needs to be defined. The general idea is that targets are not allowed to intrude in the OS's SD. Potential intruders in the SD need to be timely located in order to take evasive measures if necessary. Different from air traffic, where the SD, is defined as a circular area of five nautical mile radius around the airplane, the dimension of the SD of a ship is not globally defined. Many studies have been done in this field, as will be briefly discussed here.

Although the concept of SD is not broadly known among seafarers, almost all seafarers work with the criterion of a predetermined minimum distance (CPA). The latter can be regarded as a circular shaped SD. However, from the observation of traffic, as well as from interviews with seafarers, in reality the SD might have a more complex shape and a different dimension compared to the CPA limit in use.

Fujii and Tanaka (1971) introduced the concept of Ship Domain with the aim of defining the maximum capacity of Japanese fairways. They inferred a relation between the dimension of the SD and the length of the ship, or gross tonnage, on the basis of RADAR-observed traffic in the Tokyo Bay. *Fujii and Tanaka* suggested the SD to be of an elliptical shape around the own ship. *Goodwin (1975)* refined the concept of SD with the aim of marine traffic engineering and traffic control. She derived the dimension of the domain from statistical analysis of both simulator observations and observed traffic in the Thames Estuary. *Goodwin* suggests three sectors around the own ship, each with a radius depending on sea area, traffic density and ship's size, i.e., length over all and Gross Tonnage.

Pietrzykowski and Magaj (2017) analyzed the apparent SD around vessels sailing in the traffic separation scheme (TSS) Bornholmsgat (Baltic Sea) on the basis of AIS data. They also suggest an elliptical shaped domain with dimension independent of ship size in the so called 'precautionary area'. However, when sailing in open sea they found a considerable different dimension of the ship domain. Also, high traffic density in the traffic lane was observed to reduce the length of the domain while the width of the domain remained the same.

Since the early and much cited papers of *Fujii, Tanake and Goodwin*, many studies and methods to determine the dimension of the SD have been published. *Zec (1995)*, *Goodwin and Kemp (1977)*, *Curtis et al. (1987)*, *Lamb (1983, 1989)*, *Goodwin and Kemp (1980)*, *Marcjan et al. (2013)*, *Ning Wang et al. (2009)*, *Goerlandt et al. (2012)*, *Goodwin et al. (1983)*, *Goodwin (1978, 1975)* Up to the introduction and global implementation of AIS in 2004 these methods were based on RADAR observations or simulator assessments. Heading information of a vessel cannot be obtained from RADAR observation thus forces a generalized approach by counting the number of targets per OS's

sector or introducing noise by using the observed course over ground (COG). By using the AIS incorporated target's heading information this noise can be eliminated to a certain extent, some noise will remain due to the uncertain quality of the provided heading, e.g., corrected for speed and latitude error, or not.

As Fujii and Tanaka stated: "The boundary of effective domain is more of a psychological barrier than of a stone wall". From this it can be inferred that with the progress of time, the 'intuitive' ship's domain might have changed as result of new generations of navigators that have started working at sea, helpful navigational instruments like GPS, AIS and ECDIS have been introduced and economic pressure has increased, which often resulted in a reduction in crew size.

Therefore, a feasible, realistic and acceptable ship domain can only be determined through the analysis of contemporary traffic patterns. Analyzing the traffic density in the so called 'hot-spots' of shipping, gives a clear indication about the apparent acceptable margins of CPA in use today. *Pietrzykowski and Magaj (2017)* suggested a minor axis of about 500m. and a major axis of about 2,700m. based on one week observation of AIS data in the precautionary area of the TSS Bornholmsgat.

Fig.4: AIS positions of traffic in the Vlieland Junction area

Raw AIS data, received from the Willem Barentsz location at Terschelling, enables the analysis of high density data, i.e., unfiltered and not downsampled data. Data were logged during an arbitrarily

chosen period of one week and the data window was limited to the greater area around the Vlieland Junction, Fig.4. The Vlieland Junction area, where two traffic flows cross, is generally considered to be a hot-spot, i.e., a high-risk area. This is partly due to the high daily average of passing ships, Table I, but also due to the lack of VTS assistance outside territorial waters, and lastly due to a relatively large number of vessels crossing the traffic lanes because of the location of the busy fishing port of Harlingen, which is situated south east of the Vlieland Junction area.

Table I: Daily average number of passing ships (any size)

Westbound from German Bight	39
Eastbound into German Bight	39
Southbound into Southern North Sea	24
Northbound from Southern North Sea	31

During the week from 2 September 2016 to 9 September 2016, 805 unique ships passed the area. For any discrete moment of time, e.g., a whole minute, the traffic situation was analyzed and the distance and relative bearing from any vessel to the nearest target was calculated. This resulted in about 70,600 targets in every direction relative to any own ship. These were limited to an arbitrarily chosen distance of 12,000m. ($\pm 6\frac{1}{2}$ nm.) for reasons of computing efficiency and practicability. From this a selection (distance $< 2,000$ m.) is depicted in a polar plot (see Fig.5) in order to visualize the apparent SD. Together with the relative bearing and distance of all relevant targets, an ellipse is plotted as suggestion for the apparent SD.

Fig.5: Relative bearing and distance to all targets

A number of observations can be made from this plot. Firstly, the suggestion made by *Fujii and Tanaka (1971)* that the shape of the SD is an ellipse centered around the own ship still holds. Secondly, the dimension of the ellipse appears to be larger than what *Fujii and Tanaka (1971)* suggested, both width and length appear to be roughly similar to the dimension that *Pietrzykowski and Magaj (2017)* suggested. Thirdly, the dimension of the apparent SD seems to be about 500m. on

either side, and about 1000m. as well ahead as astern. Fourthly, a towed barge carrying its own AIS station had passed the area during the week of observation, this is represented by the two isolated clouds of dots at about 400m. from the OS, both dead ahead and astern respectively. The explanation for the large, i.e. $\pm 200\text{m}$, variation in distance between tow and tug is not clear either the length of the towing line is changed shortly before making the entry in the precautionary area, or noise has entered due to down sampling to whole minute intervals. This has not been investigated further.

Former nautical cadets, *Bijkerk (2017)*, *Bos (2016)*, *Hurkmans (2017)*, interviewed about thirty captains and officers on board during their final internship. From these interviews a variety of views on the intuitive SD emerged. However, the general picture of the SD, also referred to as Safety Zone, is comprised of sectors instead of an ellipse, which conforms to *Goodwin (1975)*'s approach. The dimension of these sectors is found to vary in detail, $\pm 0.2\text{nm}$., but the general view is that targets are unwanted in a bow sector of $1\frac{1}{4}\text{nm}$. ($\pm 2.3\text{km}$.) and a stern sector of $\frac{1}{2}\text{nm}$. (0.9km .) irrespective of ship's type and length. From these interviews, it became clear that, despite that a SD has not been defined globally, nor at company- or ship's scale, the individual WO intuitively uses an area around his ship in which he doesn't want any targets. It also became clear that the dimension of this area depends on many variables, but it is larger at the bow than at the stern. This is remarkable in view of the widely used minimum CPA criterion, which would result in a circular shaped SD.

Kant et al. (2017) analyzed 73 simulator runs consisting of head-on situations on starboard bow in order to establish the distance at which the OS's WO reacts with a course change. From their observations, they found that subjects, with experience varying from student to licensed mariner, responded on average at a passing distance of less than 0.6nm . ($\pm 1.1\text{km}$) at their starboard side. This remarkably larger distance, as compared to the SD dimension found from the former mentioned analyses in the precautionary area of Bornholmsgat and Vlieland Junction, respectively, might be explained by the open sea situation. This simulated scenario consisted of two ships in an unrestricted sea space.

Pietrzykowski and Magaj (2017) found that the dimension of the SD varies from area to area. They found that the length of the SD inside the precautionary area was about half the length of the SD in traffic lanes.

The explanation for the relatively small width, as compared to length, can be found by the area under examination. Half the number of analyzed ships in the wider Vlieland Junction area do not cross the precautionary area, instead they follow the traffic lane into the German Bight or enter the southern North Sea from the north. These ships do frequently overtake each other in the relatively narrow traffic lanes. Because overtaking is generally considered to be a safe manoeuvre, several small CPA situations are observed. This generates a bias towards a smaller width in the observed SD.

4. Conclusion

The aim of this research into the dimension of the SD was not to establish in great many detail the definition and varying dimensions and dependencies of this domain, but to derive a realistic criterion for discriminating potentially dangerous targets from the rest. This is needed in order to generate acceptable, effective alarms in the AR interface. From the aforementioned analyses, it appears that the SD seems to be elliptical shaped, about twice as long as it is wide, sometimes symmetrical around the OS, sometimes shifted towards the bow of OS. The circular shaped SD is neither mentioned nor observed. Hence, in perspective of its intended use and without claiming to generate the complete and globally valid model for the SD, the basics of SD for use in the AR interface can be derived from this analyses.

References

BENNETT, K.B.; FLACH, J.M. (2011), *Display and Interface Design*, CRC Press

- BIJKERK, L. (2017), *Safetyzone rondom de Jumbo Jubilee*, Internal MIWB report
- BORST, C.; BIJSTERBOSCH, V.A.; VAN PAASSEN, M.M.; MULDER, M. (2017), *Ecological interface design: Supporting fault diagnosis of automated advice in a supervisory air traffic control task*, Cogn. Tech Work (16.9.2017)
- BOS, M. (2016), *Critical Safety Zone Model of MS Prinsendam*, Internal MIWB report, Unpublished
- BRETON, R.; ROUSSEAU, R. (20003), *Situation Awareness: A Review of the Concept and its Measurement*, Technical report, Defence Research and Development Canada, Valcartier
- BURNS, C.M.; HAJDUKIEWICZ, J.R. (2004), *Ecological Interface Design*, CRC Press
- CURTIS, R.G.; GOODWIN, E.M.; KONYN, M. (1987), *The Automatic Detection of Real-Life Ship Encounters*, J. Navigation 40(3), pp.155–365
- DEGRÉ, T.; LEFÈVRE, X. (1981), *A Collision Avoidance System*, J. Navigation 34(2), pp.294–302
- ELLERBROEK, J. (2013), *Airborne Conflict Resolution in Three Dimensions*, PhD thesis, TU Delft
- ENDSLEY, M.R.; JONES, D.G. (2012), *Designing for Situation Awareness*, CRC Press
- FUJII, Y.; TANAKA, K. (1971), *Traffic Capacity*, J. Navigation 24(4), pp.543–552
- GOERLANDT, F.; MONTEWKA, J.; RAVN, E.S.; HÄNNINEN, M.; MAZAHERI, A. (2012), *Analysis of the near-collisions using AIS data for the selected locations in the Baltic Sea*, www.ufficiensea.org
- GOODWIN, E.M. (1975), *A Statistical Study of Ship Domains*, J. Navigation 28(3), pp.328–344
- GOODWIN, E.M. (1978), *Marine Encounter Rates*, J. Navigation 31(3), pp.357–369
- GOODWIN, E.M.; KEMP, J.F. (1977), *A Survey of Marine Traffic in the Southern North Sea*, J. Navigation 30(3), pp.378–385
- GOODWIN, E.M.; KEMP, J.F. (1980), *Collision Risks for Fixed Off-Shore Structures*, J. Navigation 33(3), pp.351–356
- GOODWIN, E.M.; LAMB, W.G.P.; KEMP, J.F. (1983), *Quantitative Measurements of Navigational Safety*, J. Navigation 36(3), pp.418–429
- HSU, H.Z.; WITT, N.A.; HOOPER, J.B.; McDERMOTT, A.P. (2009), *The AIS-Assisted Collision Avoidance*, J. Navigation 62(4), pp.657–670
- HURKMANS, R. (2017), *The Critical Safety Zone model of MV Roerborg*. Internal MIWB report, Unpublished
- ICS (2016), *Bridge Procedures Guide*, International Chamber of Shipping
- IMO (1972), *The International Regulations For Preventing Collisions At Sea 1972 (COLREGs)*, International Maritime Organization, London
- KANT, C.; LEUNEN, J.v.; DE VRIES, E. (2017), *Onderzoek Safety range*, Internal MIWB report, Unpublished

- KLEIN, G. (1998), *Sources of Power*, MIT Press
- LAMB, W.G.P. (1983), *The Estimation of the Mean Size of Ship Domains*, J. Navigation 36(1), pp.130–136
- LAMB, W.G.P. (1989), *Calculation of the Geometry of Ship Collision Zones*, J. Navigation 42(2), pp.298–305
- LE PAGE, L.S. (1949), *A Collision Warning Radar Display*, J. Navigation 2(1), pp.78–81
- MARCJAN, K.; GUCMA, L.; GUCMA, M. (2013), *Studies on ship domains in different navigational areas for nautical incident model development*, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281101885>
- OSTENDORP, M.C.; LENK, J.C.; LÜDTKE, J.C. (2015), *Smart Glasses to support maritime pilots in harbor maneuvers*, 6th Int. Conf. Applied Human Factors and Ergonomics (AHFE 2015), Vol.3, pp.2840–2847
- PAASSEN, M.M.v; BORST, C.; ELLERBROEK, J.; MULDER, M.; FLACH, J.M. (2018), *Ecological Interface Design for Vehicle Locomotion Control*, *IEEE Trans. Human-Machine Systems*
- PEDERSEN, E.; INOUE, K.; TSUGANE, M. (2003), *Simulator Studies on a Collision Avoidance Display that Facilitates Efficient and Precise Assessment of Evasive Manoeuvres in Congested Waterways*, J. Navigation 56(3), pp.411–427
- PETTY, J.A. (2004), *The Mariner's Handbook*, The UK Hydrographic Office
- PIETRZYKOWSKI, Z.; MAGAJ, J. (2017), *Ship domain as a safety criterion in a precautionary area of traffic separation scheme*, Int. J. Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation 11(1), pp.93–98
- PROCEE, S.; BORST, C.; PAASSEN, R.v.; MULDER, M. (2017), *Toward Functional Augmented Reality in Marine Navigation: A Cognitive Work Analysis*, 16th COMPIT Conf., Cardiff
- RASMUSSEN, J. (1983), *Skills, rules, and knowledge; signals, signs, and symbols, and other distinctions in human performance models*, IEEE Trans. Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, SMC-13(3)
- SZLAPCZYNSKI, R. (2008), *A New Method of Planning Collision Avoidance Manoeuvres for Multi-Target Encounter Situations*, J. Navigation 61(3), pp.307–321
- STITT, I.P.A. (2004), *AIS and Collision Avoidance - A Sense of Déjà Vu*, J. Navigation 57(2), pp.167–180
- TAM, C.K.; BUCKNALL, R.; GREIG, A. (2009), *Review of collision avoidance and path planning methods for ships in close range encounters*, J. Navigation 62(3), pp.455-476
- TIJARDOVIC, I. (2009), *The Use of AIS for Collision Avoidance*, J. Navigation 62(1), pp.168–172
- WANG, N.; MENG, X.Y.; XU, Q.Y.; WANG, Z.W. (2009), *A Unified Analytical Framework for Ship Domains*, J. Navigation 62 (4), pp.643–655
- WESTRENEN, F.v.; ELLERBROEK, J. (2017), *The Effect of Traffic Complexity on the Development of Near Misses on the North Sea*, IEEE Trans. Systems, Man, and Cybernetics
- ZEC, D. (1995), *An Algorithm for a Real-Time Detection of Encounter Situations*, J. Navigation 49(1), pp.121–126

Development of Multi-Purpose VR Simulator for a Ship from 3D CAD Model

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Abstract

As VR (Virtual Reality) devices become more popular and the base of VR-based technology has expanded, attempts to combine emergency response training for seafarers in the field of marine safety and survey training for ship surveyor have continued. The ship surveyor makes a scheme of reasonable ship operation by examining whether the ship has been properly constructed in accordance with the rule of classification societies and international conventions or whether the facilities of the ship in operation meet the standard stipulated by law. This paper describes two applications of VR simulators with same VR framework. First application is the development of survey simulator based on virtual ship environment that enables the surveyor minimize trial and errors to survey the ships. And the other application is the VR based crew training system for the on-board emergency situations required by the International Safety Management Code (ISM Code). By using such a VR-based training simulator, trainees may improve competence in operation quality such as survey, emergency response.

1. Introduction

The shipbuilding industry is introducing the Digital Twin concept to integrate and operate information on activities occurring during the life cycle of the ship such as design, construction, operation, and disposal in the ship 3D model with the 4th Industrial Revolution. This concept is being used to support workflow and reduce the production cost in the ship building phase, and in the future it will be able to evaluate the customer's operability in connection with the cloud service and simulation platform. Efforts are being made to use the 3D ship model as a platform in order to provide improvement guidelines for identified risk factors based on the performance data acquired during operation.

On the other hand, various solutions using the virtual reality related to the ship are being released recently. Each company is expanding the VR application areas such as engineering and education in the construction and operation of ships, and the demand and application range of VR is rapidly expanding due to the development of various VR devices. For examples of applications using VR, a navigation simulator that supports bridge operators' navigation training, a welding training simulator to improve the safety of welding workers, and a fire training response system for ship crew are being developed. Potential VR system users experiencing the breakthrough of VR in recent years are demanding specific and diverse operational functions for individual vessels such as realistic vessel description, fast execution speed, various character work descriptions, and etc. In order to reduce the VR construction time and cost effectively, it is necessary to use the 3D CAD model generated by the design phase and a common framework to quickly convert various ship 3D models to the VR environment. We will introduce a common framework and a variety of simulators using it to build a simulator for a variety of operators who are performing on the stage of a ship.

2. Related works

In the shipbuilding and offshore plant industries, efforts are being made to apply VR technology for various purposes such as cost reduction during the construction process and training for safe operation. These techniques are focused on simulations that can be used in the construction and operation stages centered on 3D ship models. KRISO has developed a ship navigation simulator that operating navigation like a real ship bridge based on VR technology. Dassault has developed a system that evaluates and verifies the design and assembly procedures of shipbuilding stages using 3D model, <http://www.3ds.com/products-services/delmia/products/>.

Fig.1: Simulators in shipbuilding and offshore industry: (a) FMB Simulator, KRISO (b) DELMIA, Dassault (c) Activity Visualization Platform, AVEVA (d) Survey Simulator, DNV GL

AVEVA visualized the plant safety procedures and action tips using virtual plant models and characters, http://www.aveva.com/-/media/Aveva/English/Products/Literature/AVP/AVEVA_AVP.ashx. And it simulated production process and operational safety procedures. However, this does not extend to the VR simulation system although the operator's safety check procedures and methods are expressed in 3D environment. In this paper, to construct a VR simulator based on a 3D ship model, a 3D CAD model produced in a ship design stage was introduced. And we show how to utilize that to fit with our VR environment. Recently, research on VR technology has been actively used for the construction of ship based VR environment. Oculus Rift DK2, <https://www.oculus.com/en-us/dk2/>, is used as a compatible HMD (Head Mount Display). Since the application of immersive technology based on HMD is important factor as a training simulator, we constructed a simulator by combining Unity 3D, <https://unity3d.com>, and Oculus Rift DK2.

The 3D VR based application system described in this paper, for example, a survey simulator and a crew safety training system, construct a virtual ship environment so that the operator can learn necessary information realistically. We also applied the HMD output to the virtual environment so that the worker can directly experience the various risk situations facing the field and take various measures to secure safety. For this reason, in addition to the 3D ship model, various effects were applied to provide a similar environment to the actual ship, such as ambient light, reflected light, shadow, and preprocessing were performed to smooth the processing of large graphic objects on many hull members and design parts, minimizing load during simulator operation.

3. Common Framework for Construction of Ship VR

3.1. Common Requirements

In order to construct a virtual ship space similar to the real ship environment, and to allow each user's virtual character to interact with the ship's navigation devices, hull members and equipment, there exist

common requirements shown as Table I. Most of the requirements depend on the purpose of the VR system, but the general functions for building a ship based VR environment do not change much.

Table I: Common Requirements of Ship Based VR Simulator

Item	Common Requirements
Target 3D Ship Models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe ship part <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - hull (all types of members) - equipment, machinery - Pipe - Accommodation • Describe materials based on real picture for each member of ship • Describe shadows according to sunlight and lantern lighting for each position of ship. • Provides a way to indicate the degree of corrosion of a ship • It provides a function to display the cross section of ship
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describes the waves that exercise in real time, depending on the situation • Provides the ability to control the intensity of sunlight. • Describes shipyard dock facilities (scaffold, crane, etc.) • Describe port facilities
Virtual Character Actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the moving situation according to the structure of the ship • Provide a view of the virtual character • Provide a way to pointing marks and see the information • Provides photo shooting function • Describes spray marking behavior • Provides lantern lighting function • Describes crashes and collisions • Describes movements on stairs and ladders. • Describe the movement of the transport boat
Database	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides a function of inputting a marker and information for a specific location. • Provides the function to register the reference image. • Provides the ability to register a reference document.

3.2. Architecture of Ship VR system

As shown in Fig.2, the VR-based ship training simulator system proposed in this paper consist of two stages. The first step is the 3D model creation of the ship, the scenario application, and the preprocessing procedure to construct the virtual ship environment. In the second step, the virtual image is generated by receiving the user input and the training is performed through the interaction with the inspection DB. When 3D mode used in the design process is used to create the VR environment, it is necessary to perform geometry correction, simplification, format conversion. The 3D model then is reconfigured the hull and equipment used according to the scenario. At this stage, the animation template of the character to be used by the scenario is created. For the hull and equipment of the ship, in order to process global or local light sources, shadows, etc. in real time, the pre-calculation must be performed in advance for those kinds of effects. First of all, texture mapping is performed for all kind of members and equipment. The texture picked up from camera or high resolution real image template were mapped to the unwrapped 3D geometry. And then lightings and shadows are calculated. After that for reduction of real time rendering time, the occlusion culling that calculating occluded region of camera considered view frustum as shown in Fig.3. In the operation stage, constructed VR ship environment interact with the user characters that perform actual behavior to achieve a purpose of scenario. All of the information related with the execution is stored in database. The output of the execution scenes was displayed in a head mount display (HMD) or monitor.

Fig. 1 Architecture of Ship Based VR Simulator System

3.3. System Implementation

3.3.1. Pre-processing Module

3D model for building a virtual 3D ship environment can be directly modeled based on drawings or utilize the 3D models created from the design and production stage. In this paper, we present a simple procedure to utilize already modeled 3D ship CAD data as Fig.3 need to preprocess Fig.3. In general, a conversion error occurs in the process of transform 3D data from original format to target format such as gaps due to difference of tolerance, normal flipping, geometric inconsistency.

Fig.2: Pre Process for Ship Based VR Simulator System

This paper does not deal with methods and procedures for correcting conversion errors of various 3D model format data. Using Blender3D, an open source 3D modeling software, we presented a way to effectively handle the conversion of the hull plate when converting KR's 3D model format to the universal 3D format.

Fig.4: Inconsistent normal of ship plates (surface)

(a)

Fig.5: different result of 'Occlusion Culling' in Unity3D Engine
 (a) partitioning for occlusion culling in Unity3D engine (b) $h = 120$ (c) $h = 80$ (d) $h = 30$

When the normal line of ship's plate is N_{pn} , the central reference point in ship is P_{ref} , and the vector connecting the center of the plate geometry and the reference point is V_{pn} , Python code to find and

process the inverted normal is described as Fig.4. Complex, sophisticated 3D models require long computation time in real-time rendering and cause performance degradation. To overcome these problem, considering the purpose and effect of the operation, it is necessary to perform precomputation on simplification, lighting, and occlusion of the 3D model. In this study, 'Decimation' function of Blender3D was used to reduce the number of polygons, and the texture was processed after 'Unwrapping' the model. The textured model, then is passed to 'Lightmapping' module for shadow, ambient light and global illumination, 'Occlusion culling' module for exclusion parts not necessary for rendering as shown in Fig.5.

3.3.2. Operation Module

The system operation module plays a main role in the VR simulator, such as running the system in real time by interacting with data and user input based on the preprocessing data constructed in the previous section. In the visualization module, the ship model, GUI, the movement of the virtual character, the surrounding environment are rendered in real time. The scene management module performs processing user input, selection, event, and interface with the database. The scenario manager deals with the model configuration, events, and items according to the simulation location, Fig.6.

Fig. 6 Operation module of the survey simulator

4. Extension of Common Framework

4.1. VR Based Ship Survey Simulator

In order to maintain the classification of the ship continuously, the ship must maintain the effective state of receipt by inspecting regular, intermediate, annual inspection, propeller shaft inspection, docking inspection and boiler inspection according to the Rules for Classification. For this purpose, the

owner of the vessel shall request the ship to be inspected at the time of ship inspection, and the Surveyor shall carry out the inspection in accordance with the relevant rules and regulations during the relevant inspection schedule.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.7: Sample scenes of KR VR Based Survey Simulator (a) main scene for selection of ship region (b) exploring hold region (c) exploring engine room

This educational system, which is being carried out by most ship inspection organizations, traditionally

has the following problems. First, in the theoretical education, the trainee experiences the inspection environment through indirect media such as photographs and videos. Therefore, it is difficult to recognize and understand the actual survey situation. On the other hand, on-the-job training is exposed to dangerous situations such as suffocation for falling. Second, the system of accumulating and communicating the inspection know-how of each surveyor for the succeeding surveyor is insufficient and new trainees are not able to utilize the experience of the senior surveyor.

In order to solve these problems, VR-based system which enables the vessel inspector to check the rules and regulations necessary for ship inspection at any time in the virtual ship space using the virtual reality framework, we developed a VR based inspection training system.

4.2. Ship Crew Safety Training Simulator

As a different application of ship VR training simulator, we have developed a VR - based crew training system capable of multilateral role sharing for the on - board emergency situations required by the International Safety Management Code (ISM Code). This system defines the scenarios for the emergency response training of the ISM Code and provides an immersive environment for systematic and prompt response to ship safety management inspection and inspections.

Fig.8: VR based safety training simulator for ship crew (a) captain view (b) chief officer view (c) 1st engineer view (d) deck crew view

5. Conclusion

Recently, the dramatic improvement in performance of graphics hardware and software engine has made it possible to make VR technology popular and configure simulator at low cost. In the shipbuilding industry, VR based simulator system using 3D ship model made at the stage of ship design is actively being constructed. In this paper, we have developed a framework that provides common functions for ship - based virtual reality implementation and its various application system development and extension. These systems will be synchronized with evolving graphics hardware and software to expand into a variety of virtual reality training systems needed by the shipbuilding industry.

Furthermore, we plan to increase the usability of this simulator by providing a authoring tool that allows users to make scenario themselves.

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References

- AN, G.I.; HWANG, J.S.; HWANG, H.J. (2017), *Development of VR-based Visualization System of Configuration Information for the Facility*, Bulletin of the Soc. Naval Arch. Korea 54(3), pp.3-6
- CHOI, S.H.; LEE, M.H.; LEE, J.Y. (2016), *A Comparative Analysis of User Experience in Home Energy Saving Awareness Using Immersive Virtual Reality and Mobile Augmented Reality*, Korean J. Computational Design and Engineering 21(4), pp.397-408
- GONG, I.Y.; AN, S.P.; JANG, H.J.; HAN, J.S. (2017), *VR-based Offshore Plant Education System*, Bulletin of the Society of Naval Architects of Korea 54(3), pp.7-10
- JUNG, H.K.; PARK, H.J. (2016), *Web-based 3D Virtual Experience using Unity and Leap Motion*, Korean J. Computational Design and Engineering 21(2), pp.159-169.
- LEE, G.C.; CHUNG, K.I.; MUN, D.H.; YOUN, C. (2015), *A Study on Plant Training System Platform for the Collaboration Training between Operator and Field Workers*, Korean J. Computational Design and Engineering 20(4), pp.420-430
- PARK, G.P.; JO, A.R. (2017), *Development of VR Panorama System for Offshore Plant*, Bulletin of the Society of Naval Architects of Korea 54(3), pp.16-19
- PARK, K.B.; LEE, J.Y. (2016), *Comparative Study on the Interface and Interaction for Manipulating 3D Virtual Objects in a Virtual Reality Environment*, Korean J. Computational Design and Engineering 21(1), pp.20-30

Bee-Swarm Inspired Cooperative Robotics and Augmented Reality for Seafloor Exploration

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Abstract

Mapping and exploring seafloors is a challenging technical task. Our answer is a fleet of micro robotic autonomous submarines providing a robust and scalable solution. Taking inspiration from bee swarm strategies, an innovative solution for underwater mapping tasks is proposed. Underwater maps near coastal areas have been used to create a free app to explore near-coast underwater topologies using smartphones and Augmented Reality.

1. Introduction

In 2016, the XPRIZE organization launched the Shell Ocean Discovery XPRIZE competition, <http://oceandiscovery.xprize.org/>. Like their other competitions such as the Google Lunar XPRIZE and the Ansari Space XPRIZE, this competition is designed to drive global innovation and technology development. For this challenge however, they are not looking to the stars, but heading to the deep.

The goal of the Shell Ocean Discovery XPRIZE is to encourage innovation in automated ocean exploration and bathymetric mapping. The world does not have a map of its own oceans and with current ship-based technology the cost and time to produce a detailed map of the sea floor would take decades and cost billions. An automated robotic solution can break-down these barriers and unlock the mysteries of the deep oceans.

The targets for the first round of the competition are:

- create a bathymetric map of a 500 km² target area up to 2000 m deep
- the map must have 5 m horizontal accuracy and 0.5 m depth accuracy
- find and image a target object at the 2000 m depth
- complete above tasks within 16 h using an automated solution with only shore based control

The targets are easy to describe but, from a technical viewpoint, extremely difficult to achieve. There are no existing solutions in the market today that can fulfil all these requirements. A new solution has to be found. It will need to be bold, innovative and different to what exists today.

This global competition has attracted teams from around the world from both industry and academia. We are one of the teams.

This paper describes how our engineers have taken inspiration from nature to develop a fleet of miniature robotic submarines that we named Marine Bees. They take their design from real bees, not just for the way they look, but also because they mimic the behaviour of real bees and the operation of a hive to explore and image the ocean floor.

2. Distributed Robotics

A key aspect of ocean exploration and bathymetric mapping is that it is a scalable problem. If there is a device that can map 100 m² of the ocean floor then using the same device in series, over time, it can be used to map 1 km², then 10 km² and so on. Likewise, multiple copies of the device can be used in parallel, so 100 of them together could map 10 km² at the same time. This is a scalable problem which allows large and complex tasks to be completed using multiple devices each performing part of the task. In robotics a scalable problem can be solved using swarm or distributed robotic techniques.

The primary difference between distributed robotics and standard robotics is that in distributed robotics there are multiple, low-cost, simple robots instead of a single, custom-built, complex robot.

The advantages of distributed robotics are:

- Robustness: operation continues even if single robots are lost or malfunction.
- Scalable: time or area constraints can be overcome by adding more robots.
- Flexibility: each robot follows simple rules yet the emergent complex group behaviour is adaptable to changing environments.
- Design Optimization: each robot is designed to do one and only one task. The design of each robot can be optimized with respect to that task.
- Lower cost: it can be cheaper to develop hundreds of simpler robots compared to one complex robot, due to economies of scale and mass production techniques.

Overall a distributed robotic solution is well suited to ocean exploration but what should this solution look like?

2. Bees for Inspiration

The closest analogy for distributed robotics is found in nature, specifically in insect populations. The organisation of ant colonies, termite mounds, and bee hives all display key features that distributed robots can emulate.

For our ocean exploration technology we have chosen a distributed robotic solution that mimics the behaviour of bees and the operation of a bee hive. Bees were chosen because they closely match what we are trying to achieve.

Just as the real bees leave their hive and fly into the fields and woods looking for flowers, returning to tell the other bees what they have found, our Marine Bee submarines do exactly the same. They dive down to the bottom of the ocean floor, spreading out to explore and map an area. They bring back their nectar, which for us is the data and images. Returning to the surface they share the data with the other Marine Bees so they can decide where to explore next. Each bee is exploring on its own, but there are lots of bees all doing that simultaneously to cover a large area.

Our solution is inspired by nature but how far can we model real hive behaviour and will it be suitable for ocean mapping?

3. Marine Bees – Miniature Robotic Submarines

The basic building block for our solution is the Marine Bee, Fig.1. This is our realization of a single bee in the hive. Each Marine Bee has many features of a full sized Autonomous Underwater Vehicle but they are smaller and cheaper. Their limitation is that due to their size and power, they can only explore a small area on their own.

The main body of the bee is the manoeuvring system consisting of multiple props to drive the unit underwater and a guidance system to manage its position and attitude.

The head of the bee is the payload and is interchangeable to provide different features. One of the key aspects of distributed robotics is that each robot has one and only one specific task. This is achieved using different payloads.

The standard head, or payload, is a visual system that includes cameras and range finders which enable the bee to measure distances in its environment, for mapping, and also for collision avoidance.

Fig.1: Eauligo Marine Bee

4. Bee Exploration Algorithms

Fig.2 shows typical exploration patterns that a robotic submarine could follow. To explore an area, the submarine can follow a course, either over a grid or along a spiral, taking measurements at regular intervals. This is brute-force exploration, the goal is to visit each point within the region.

Fig.2: Brute-force exploration

However, if we look at the foraging patterns of real bees they do not take a brute-force approach. A bee does not fly in a regular pattern to explore each area. Studies of bee foraging behaviour have shown that bees tend to follow simple heuristic rules, with evidence of spatial memory only when a bee has spent a lot of time in a particular area. The bees try to enhance energy returns by minimizing flight costs, resulting in highly directional flights with minimal variation in direction, combined with short flights in areas of flowers with high potential and longer flights in areas of low reward.

The difference with brute-force exploration and bee foraging is that in brute-force exploration all points are considered the same, to create the map each point must be visited. In bee foraging the goal

is for the bee to find nectar or pollen, they are visiting specific flowers using strategies to maximize the return. Not every point for them in a garden is important, only the flowers that give the most reward are targeted.

To mimic the behaviour of real bees with our Marine Bees we need to introduce a concept of nectar, or value, during the exploration process. For us the value is in the measurements and images that the Marine Bees take of the ocean floor. Our nectar is data. Unlike brute-force exploration we cannot consider all data as equal, we need to take into account the qualitative aspect of the data, not just its quantity. Just as bees optimize their strategy to find flowers that maximise the amount of nectar returned for energy expended, the Marine Bees need to maximise the quality (not quantity) of data collected against battery consumption.

For a bathymetric map the data is just a measurement of depth, what does quality of data mean in this case? When we talk about quality of data, we actually mean the ability to collect the data. The ocean floor is unpredictable and the Marine Bees can only be programmed with basic heuristic rules and very limited Artificial Intelligence algorithms. There will be many situations where it will be difficult to collect data, or the data will be inaccurate. Some examples are:

- Areas with poor sensor readings, such as terrain that can cause confusing sonar echoes or areas with high silt content that block visual images.
- Areas with strong sea currents that limit the robot's speed or result in excessive battery consumption to make progress.
- Areas with many obstructions or difficult terrain, that again results in high power usage to navigate.

As stated, the goal for each Marine Bee is to collect the best data versus power use. Therefore in areas where conditions are good, and data can be collected with low power consumption, a Marine Bee should maximize its time in these regions. These are the gardens with flowers full of nectar. In areas where conditions are bad these areas should be passed quickly, just as real bees fly rapidly across areas bereft of flowers. Our overall algorithm for exploring the ocean floor looks like Fig.3, a bee foraging pattern.

Fig.3: Bee exploration

3. Floating Hives – Autonomous Surface Vessels

Each Marine Bee is able to explore a small part of the ocean floor and by using many bees together we can map large areas. However, we need a way of getting the bees to their target location and a way of sending data back to shore. Continuing the analogy, the surface part of our solution is a floating hive.

The hive is an autonomous surface vessel that manages a cell of 50 bees, Fig.4. Initially the bees are stacked inside the hive. The hive drives out to the target location and drops the bees at spaced intervals. The hive also acts as a communication hub, when the bees return to the surface they transmit their data to the hive which then relays the data back to land. Finally, the hive will recapture each bee as it returns ready for the return voyage.

The hives also provide the spatial memory for the bees. In a real bee hive the bees dance to communicate what they have found and where to explore next. The Marine Bees are too simplistic to store representations of areas that have been explored and where best to go next. This functionality is provided by processors in the hives which store copies of the data returned by the bees and build the overall spatial map of the area. Using this map the next cell of bees is sent out to explore new areas.

The hives are essentially floating HQs, they provide communication to the shore and they manage a group of bees.

Fig.4: Floating Hive

4. Conclusion

In this paper we have presented a solution for ocean exploration based on distributed robotics inspired by the behaviour of bees and the operation of a bee hive. The key elements are a simple, low cost miniature robotic submarine, an exploration algorithm based on bee foraging, and autonomous surface vessels which act as floating hives to manage a group of bees.

Testing and optimization of our solution is still ongoing but based on the current performance we will need around 200 to 300 Marine Bees working together to complete the challenge set by the Shell Ocean Discovery XPRIZE. An impressive number of robots that will be deployed to depths up to 2000 m, we hope we will get them back.

References

BURNS, J.G.; THOMSON, J.D. (2006), *A test of spatial memory and movement patterns of bumblebees at multiple spatial and temporal scales*, Behavioral Ecology 17, pp.48-55

OSBORN, J.L.; CLARK, S.J.; MORRIS, R.J.; WILLIAMS, I.H.; RILEY, J.R.; SMITH, A.D.; REYNOLDS, D.R.; EDWARDS, A.S. (1999), *A landscape-scale study of bumble bee foraging range and constancy, using harmonic radar*, J. Applied Ecology 36/4, pp.519-533

SAHIN, E. (2004), *Swarm Robotics: From Sources of Inspiration to Domains of Application*, Swarm Robotics, pp.10-20

WADDINGTON, K.D. (1979), *Flight patterns of three species of sweat bees (Halictidae) foraging at Convolvulus Arvensis*, J. Kansas Entomological Society 52/4

Shipyard DES Simulation Framework and its Applications

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Abstract

This paper proposes a simulation framework for improving a shipyard's supply chain management competence consisting of production, procurement, and logistics through the virtualization of plan-do-see (PDS) cycle using discrete event system (DES) simulation. The core of the proposed methodology is building a simulation framework that includes a platform for a flexible modelling environment with systematic performance evaluation indicators, such as key performance indicator. Then, the shipyard block logistics simulation example is introduced using the proposed framework. In addition, the process-centric simulation modelling method is introduced that considers a shipbuilding production management system and analyses the detailed operation of the DES simulation engine, which is calculated based on the future event list. The shipyard DES simulation framework is expected to eliminate the waste by maximizing the fast and precise decision-making capabilities of shipyard supply chain management.

1. Introduction

The shipbuilding industry production methods differ from the automobile and the semiconductor industries, which can be classified as mass production and line production. The shipbuilding industry which can be classified as a project-based system utilizes a job shop method. Products move along predetermined paths during line production, where it is common for one facility to perform a single process out of the many required to manufacture the product. Conversely, multiple processes are completed by workers or equipment in a specific space for the job shop method. The operator and facility are used flexibly in the unit production process, rather than being dictated by it. Therefore, the job shop production environment is operated differently from the line production; thus, there is a difference in how the production environments are managed.

The manufacturing industry has studied virtual production and simulation technologies to identify the problems that may arise in the production process and to confirm the feasibility of a production plan. For most of the methods using these technologies, a virtual environment is constructed to simulate the actual physical environment and the manufacturing process so that problems that may occur in the actual production environment are verified in advance. In order to obtain meaningful results, it is necessary to accurately create the detailed virtual environment. The characteristics of the production method and physical environment should be accurately reflected to ensure the proper level of simulation sophistication. It is difficult to express the job shop production method of the shipbuilding process using these modelling techniques that are based on the line production method and environment. Most of the commercial simulation programs target the automobile and semiconductor industries that mass produce using line production. Consequently, there are many limitations to modelling the shipbuilding production system using these existing methods and tools.

To overcome this problem, a simulation framework has been proposed that includes methods and procedures for adapting existing simulation technology to shipbuilding production systems, *Woo et al. (2016)*. Other methods for modelling and simulating the shipbuilding production environment have also been proposed, *Kim et al. (2002,2005)*, *Aoyama et al. (1999)*, *Krause et al. (2004)*. However,

most of these studies do not include specific methods of use or solved the problems that are currently occurring with one-off temporary projects. The shipbuilding simulation framework mentioned above not only reflects the characteristics of the shipbuilding production environment, but also includes the continuous use of the shipyard. In this paper, the details of the simulation framework proposed by *Woo et al. (2016)* are analysed and the actual shipyard applications are summarized. The paper also provides a detailed explanation of how the framework reflected the characteristics of the shipyard production environment and how the simulation methods were implemented.

2. Shipyard DES simulation framework

2.1. Basic structure

The basic structure of the shipyard discrete event simulation (DES) framework is divided into the four parts shown in Fig.1: information model, simulation platform, evaluation indicators, and simulation objects.

Fig.1: Shipyard DES simulation framework, *Woo et al. (2016)*

The information model is a 6-factor information model that divides the shipyard information into six representative categories: product, process, facility, space, human resource, and schedule. Various existing studies have suggested that only product, process, resource, and schedule information are needed to create a manufacturing simulation model, *Woo (2005)*. However, in the shipyard DES framework, resources are detailed in order to express the production environment of the shipyard.

The simulation platform consists of a standard model, a simulation platform component, a simulation base engine, a data adapter, and a result reporter. The standard model is a predefined standard model for quickly and easily modelling various shipyard environments. At this time, the standard model is expressed by the process-centric modelling method to reflect the production environment of the shipyard. The simulation platform component refers to a separately developed component that can perform the simulation smoothly based on the standard model. This framework is based on the concept of extending various components, such as the shortest path search algorithm, space allocation algorithm, and others for shipyard block logistics simulation. The simulation base engine is the basic logic for performing the simulation. There are various methods to perform simulation, such as agent-based simulation and discrete event system simulation. In this study, discrete event system simulation can be performed based on the future event list (FEL). The data adapter and result reporter are components for smooth information conversion and output. The simulation framework analysed in this study does not target an individual shipyard; thus, it is important to convert information from various shipyards and report the results according to the requirements of each. A data conversion component and a result reporting component are included to facilitate this functionality.

The evaluation indicators are used to quantitatively evaluate the simulation results. Currently, the evaluation index can utilize the key performance indicators (KPIs) used for production management at the shipyard. The simulation framework is applied to the simulation objects, and the goals of the

problem to be solved are based on these objects. The shipbuilding industry has a complex mixture of problems with various characteristics. Therefore, it is necessary to clarify the object to be simulated and the target of the problem to be solved.

In summary, the simulation framework proposed by *Woo et al. (2016)* involves setting simulation goals and determining the appropriate KPIs. The simulation model is constructed using a simulation platform, and the required information is used according to the format defined in the 6-factor information model.

2.2. Flexible modelling environment

Based on the component-based modelling method, the shipyard simulation framework enables users to develop and apply components that perform various functions. The current components are classified as a data conversion adapter component, a simulation engine component, and a simulation reporter component. The data conversion adapter converts the model data so that it can be utilized in the simulation system in which the shipyard data is constructed. The simulation engine implements the algorithm that is used during the simulation. The simulation reporter outputs the data recorded by the simulation engine to a user-defined form.

Fig.2: Resource-based simulation modelling results

In this framework, a process-centric modelling method is proposed for the simulation, whereas most commercial simulation software packages use a resource-centric modelling method. However, the shipbuilding process simulation model is suitable for the process-centric modelling method due to the characteristics of the shipbuilding production system. The resource-centric modelling method is suitable for the line production system with fixed equipment. This is not suitable for a shipbuilding system in which the types of facilities are varied and the transportation route of the product is not constant, Fig.2. On the other hand, the process-centric modelling method can represent the shipbuilding process as a simple network model. It is suitable for representing the production method of the job shop method applied to most shipbuilding production systems. Furthermore, as it is based on the shipbuilding process, it is easy to communicate with the person in charge.

2.3. Systematic performance evaluation indicator

In this study, the method of analysing simulation results based on a KPI was established for systematic and quantitative simulation results evaluation, Fig.3.

- A. Create value driver tree (VDT): Create a VDT that utilizes the KPI of the shipyard's production pyramid as the top node
- B. Create pruned driver tree (PDT): Create a PDT by removing drivers that cannot be quantified or formulated among the VDT configuration drivers.
- C. Input simulation results value: Input the simulation results into the bottom driver of PDT.

- D. Simulation results analysis: Analyse the simulation results using a VDT scenario.
- E. Visualization through dashboard: Visualize the simulation results according to the performance level of the achievement pyramid.

Fig.3: A method of analysing simulation results based on KPI

3. Simulation engine

The behaviour of the simulation engine is divided into logistics and non-logistics cases. When the logistics are not considered, an event is generated on the basis that the product is put into the process. A product is put into the process after it is initially judged to determine the feasibility of doing so. Because the product can occupy the space where the process is performed, the property to be changed at the time of goods receipt is changed. Then, the equipment required to perform the process is assigned to a predetermined rule. Next, the process is performed according to a predefined value. Then, the equipment is released again, and if there are several subsequent processes, the next process is decided. The shipment logic is executed to change the attributes when the product exits the process. Finally, the product is shipped from the process, and the process is repeated. When all the products are put into the process, an event to be performed in the future is generated, and the list is created and managed by the simulation engine. The simulation engine checks the event and attribute values according to the time registered in the list.

When considering logistics in the simulation, the logic between processes must be included, which is defined as a logistics token, *Jeong et al. (2017)*. The logistics token determines where the product is located and what transportation facility it is using. In the shipyard, a buffer time is placed between processes to establish a production plan. If the buffer is longer than the predetermined time, the product is moved to the stockyard. Logistics tokens include the ability to send products to the stockyard, accounting for the time between processes. In order to find the optimal path, a component that includes the path search algorithm is used. The simulation time considers the moving distance of the product and the speed of the transporting equipment. If the product arrives at the destination, the simulation rechecks the FEL and proceeds to the next event. Even when the logistics are considered, the same process as when the logistics corresponding to the logistics token is terminated is not performed.

4. Applications

The shipyard block logistics simulation system was constructed to verify the proposed framework and the results analysed in this study, Fig.4. The results of the block logistics simulation were derived by considering the operation logic of the proposed framework and engine. For this purpose, we defined two products with a predefined process, workplace, start date and end date. It is assumed that this product sequentially performs the assembly → pre-processing → painting process. Simulating the logistics with these input conditions allows the verification of the start and end times, equipment used, product, transportation route, and the workshop information, as illustrated by the Gantt chart in Fig.5, details which cannot be confirmed during planning using traditional processes. It is possible to check

the type of equipment used during the buffer period, the shelf period, and the utilized route information in detail, such as the transportation routes shown in Fig.6.

Fig.4: Shipyard block logistics simulation system based on the framework

Fig.5: Shipyard block logistics simulation results #1 (Gantt chart)

(a) Path of transporter #1001

(b) Path of transporter #1002

Fig.6: Shipyard block logistics simulation results #2 (transportation routes)

5. Conclusions

In this study, the shipbuilding simulation framework proposed in previous studies was analysed in detail, with a focus on component-based methods and process-centric modelling methods. A method was proposed to set up and refine the simulation goals and analyse the process of the simulation engine in terms of logistics and non-logistics models. It was confirmed through a simulation example of shipbuilding block logistics that the proposed method can be useful for the development of a shipbuilding simulation system.

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References

- AOYAMA, K.; NOMOTO, T.; KENTARO, W. (1999), *Development of a shipyard simulator based on Petri nets*, J. Marine Science and Technology 4/1, pp.35-43
- JEONG, Y.K.; LEE, P.; WOO, J.H. (2017), *Shipyard Block Logistics Simulation Using Process-centric Discrete Event Simulation Method*, J. Ship Production and Design 33/3, pp.1-12
- KIM, H.; LEE, J.K.; PARK, J.H.; PARK, B.J.; JANG, D.S. (2002), *Applying digital manufacturing technology to ship production and the maritime environment*, Integrated Manufacturing Systems 13/5, pp.295-305
- KIM, H.; LEE, S.S.; PARK, J.H.; LEE, J.G. (2005), *A model for a simulation-based shipbuilding system in a shipyard manufacturing process*, Int. J. Computer Integrated Manufacturing 18/6, pp.427-441
- KRAUSE, M.; ROLAND, F.; STEINHAUER, D.; HEINEMANN, M. (2004), *Discrete event simulation: An efficient tool to assist shipyard investment and production planning*, J. Ship Production 20/3, pp.176-182
- WOO, J.H.; KIM, Y.; JEONG, Y.K.; SHIN, J.G. (2016), *A research on simulation framework for the advancement of supplying management competency*, J. Ship Production and Design 32/4, pp.1-20
- WOO, J. H. (2005), *Modeling and Simulation of Indoor Shop System of Shipbuilding by Integration of the Product, Process, Resource and Schedule Information*, Ph.D. Thesis, Seoul National University

Machine Learning in Ship Production

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Abstract

Development of information and communication technology caused geometric growth in data and consequently, importance of technology related to data analysis is increasing. Shipbuilding industry also involves uncertainty and large variability in production, which greatly requires data analysis technology such as machine learning. Especially, the industry is not efficiently adapting to the production environment with a changed standard time data system related to production such as unit production cost and lead time, and requires an improvement plan. This paper used machine learning to predict lead times for fabrication, assembly, spool making and painting on shipyards. This was to suggest a new management method of a standard data system for a time element called process lead time among production data. Process variables were selected through not only various data pre-processing using open-sources R and Tensor Flow, but also correlation analysis and analysis of variables to analyze correlation with lead time. Various machine learning and deep learning algorithms were applied to create lead time prediction models. Furthermore, the prediction models were evaluated with evaluation criteria such as MAP (mean absolute percentage) and MAPE (mean absolute percentage error) to investigate the applicability of the machine learning methodology suggested in this study for predicting standard working hours.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Advancing information society caused the size of data to grow geometrically, and as a result, big data technology for systematic collection, storage, and analysis of massive data is developing rapidly. Massive data refers to a data size that is difficult to collect, store, and analyze with conventional methods or tools. Attempts to create added value through big data technology is increasing drastically especially in industries with the fourth industrial revolution. The shipbuilding industry is also making various efforts related to big data. In sales, the most prevalent studies are on predicting types of ships by analyzing international market conditions, and in design, they are on predicting supply through BOM and design data analyses. Moreover, in production management, studies on topics discussed in this paper, which are standard working hours and standard lead times, are in progress.

The conventional method for managing standard working hours is based on causation relation where the working hours and lead times are analyzed by adding standard unit of working hours to the supply that was calculated from product information. However, such method is still due for further studies on supply calculation or standard time unit due to the complexity of products and various variables from field work, despite many years of research.

On the other hand, big data analysis methodology is a statistical-based analysis method that only analyzes correlation for data that can be expressed in numbers or texts regardless of the product or processing technology. Thus, it is anticipated that standard working hour prediction models can be derived for products of corresponding work through machine learning in regard to the relationship between related variables and recorded (or planned) data by applying big data analysis methodology to standard working hours.

1.2. Objective

This study used big data analysis to conduct a study on prediction models using standard time data from shipyards. Recorded data on fabrication, assembly, and procurement at a shipyard was collected to define a scenario from the perspective of shipbuilding production and applied learning algorithms in R and Python.

This study applied machine learning and deep learning algorithms to fabrication, assembly and procurement data on ship building. Machine learning and deep learning algorithms were applied in various ways to create lead time prediction models according to different analysis cases. Prediction models were evaluated by comparing the lead times from the prediction models built with different algorithms with recorded lead times.

2. Related Studies Trend

Jo and Kang (2016) discussed cases by classifying big data that was applicable to manufacturing industries according to product development, making process, sales and marketing, and after-sales service. The text mining case for improving efficiency of design processes of automobile parts in the product development area showed that analyzing data included in the design verification text could reduce man hour and time required to identify the key issue.

Jung and Sim (2014) tried reducing welding cost by analyzing work patterns of welders through weld data analysis. For this, algorithms in R and regression analysis were used on a large number of weld work pattern variables to study the patterns of electricity usage and length of wire consumption.

Ham (2016) did a preceding study of this paper on improving procurement management by predicting the lead time from the making process to the installation process of spools, where long delays occur in later working stages amongst outfitting. This study defined lead time by dividing the supply chain of piping processes into 6 processes and performed multilinear regression analysis and PLS regression analysis. However, data pre-processing was insufficient in this study, which resulted in high error rates in lead times of different processes.

Hur et al. (2015) analyzed man hour data of design and production processes of ships to predict man hours on shipyards. Variables related to man hour were defined and prediction models were derived using multilinear regression analysis and decision tree. However, considering that construction periods of ships on shipyards are 1 to 2 years on average, there were limitations in collecting long term data and insufficient consideration of external factors outside the working space.

Lee et al. (2014) used text mining to inspect in advance the various types of errors that occur during the construction process of offshore structures. Analyzing text log data allowed understanding and visualizing error trend analysis and related error analysis, which provided important information that were valuable for the making process.

The National Information Society Agency, *NIA (2016)*, led a task on big data cloud service development for analyzing making processes on shipyards as part of a pilot project on big data. This task involved process mining-based analyses of big data on making processes in order to analyze processing delays and load to study the current state of processing and reasons for delay, and used this to improve work efficiency.

Kim et al. (2016) suggested a big data platform that was based on Hadoop, which is a method of distributed processing of big data. Moreover, it was used in weight estimation of upper structures of offshore plants to study the possibility of implementing big data in the field of offshore structure development. However, data for analysis was insufficient due to security problems from shipyards and using only simple linear regression analysis was not enough to test various analysis algorithms.

3. Analysis Algorithm and Its Applications

3.1 Machine Learning Algorithm

Machine learning is a field of AI and is a technology that uses various possibilities, the combinatorial theory, mathematical optimization techniques, statistics and algorithms to build an ideal learning model, *Lee et al. (2014)*. Since the purpose of machine learning is to build a model using data, not only selecting suitable input data, but also selecting the appropriate algorithm for the problem is important. Machine learning algorithm is determined by how the training data is used. Training data with a label is classified as supervised learning and without a label is classified as unsupervised learning, Fig.1.

Fig.1: Algorithms of machine learning

The purpose of this paper was to develop a prediction model in order to improve standard data for working hours. Therefore, since this was defined by the output of lead time, which was the subject of prediction, machine learning algorithm in this study was limited to a supervised learning algorithm. Moreover, linear regression, neural network, and decision tree were used, which were known to be suitable for numerical prediction among supervised learning algorithms.

3.2 Deep Learning Algorithm

Conventional machine learning frequently involves humans intervening in or defining before the process where a computer derives characteristics from a given set of training data. Therefore, it comes with errors that occur in this process. The approach of using multiple layers of neural was not used since it had problems including nonlinearity, limited number of weight according to number of layers, and over-fitting. However, such problems were resolved when efficacy of multi-layer neural networks was proved with the development of computing performance of computers and algorithms, and consequently, deep learning is being widely used in the AI field, *Kim (2016)*.

This paper applied a deep learning algorithm (Multilayer perceptron algorithm, Fig.2) in addition to linear regression, neural network and decision tree to achieve a higher prediction accuracy in the study case on spool making and painting processes. Deep learning library used in this study was ‘Keras’ written in Python.

Fig.2: Concept of multi-layer perceptron

4. Data Analysis Process

The data analysis process was defined with four steps: data collection, data processing, model building, and data evaluation, Fig.3. In the data collection step, shipyard data selected for predicting production lead time was collected according to process, and various data processing techniques were applied to build a model. Next, collected shipyard data was studied by defining process variables and by data mining for data processing. The next step involved data classification for creating prediction models, and machine learning and deep learning algorithms were applied to create prediction models according to the algorithms. Lastly, performance of the prediction models was evaluated using evaluation index to evaluate resulting data.

Fig.3: Process of data analysis and machine learning

4.1 Data Collection

The data collection step collected data according to purpose of analysis. Collected shipyard data was classified into 3 types, the cutting process, erection process, and spool procurement process, as shown in Table I. However, for spool procurement, the procurement process was further divided into making, painting, stocking outside the enterprise, and stocking within the enterprise. This paper selected lead times of making and painting processes as subjects of analysis, since they had significance on spool processing variables.

4.2 Data Processing

Data processing is absolutely necessary in order to analyze data, which has errors introduced even from the process of selecting variables for algorithm application. Particularly, the most important preprocessing of data is articulating data by applying various feature engineering methodologies to derive effective variables.

Table I: Data collection

Analyzed Data	Subject of Prediction
Cutting Process Recorded Data	Cutting Lead Time
Erection Process Recorded Data	Erection Lead Time
Spool Procurement Recorded Data	Making and Painting Spool Lead Times

First, independent and dependent variables are defined in order to apply the algorithm, and data mining is done for each variable to search and eliminate outliers or missing values to prevent errors in analyzed results beforehand. The fundamentally simple and easy way of finding outliers or missing values is visualizing the distribution of a variable. This paper obtained and processed data distribution or outliers through graphs such as histograms and boxplots. Data distribution was found through histograms to understand data asymmetry including skewness, and outliers of data were easily confirmed visually through boxplots. Moreover, since analysis methods can be applied in different ways according to form and number of variables, correlation analysis was done between continuous variables and distribution analysis was done between categorical variables from the processing variables defined for lead time prediction.

Fig.4: Data analysis

This was the step where training data for building a prediction model and evaluation data for evaluating the prediction model were distinguished, and machine learning and deep learning algorithms were applied. Training data was used to build the prediction model and evaluation data was used to evaluate the prediction accuracy of the prediction model. Typically, training data and evaluation data are classified approximately at a ratio of 7:3. Training data was applied once processed data related to processing variables was classified. Here, the machine learning algorithm used R while the deep learning algorithm used Python to build models.

4.4 Data Evaluation

The data evaluation step evaluated the performance of the prediction model using evaluation criteria. This evaluation criteria for the prediction model performance (or prediction accuracy) used mainly

MAE (mean absolute error), MAPE (mean absolute percentage error), and RMSE (root mean square error), and R^2 , which evaluates the degree of representation of regression analysis, was added. Calculations for such evaluation criteria allowed quantitatively deriving error and accuracy between predicted values from the prediction model and recorded values from actual data, Table II.

Table II: Evaluation criteria

Evaluation Criteria	Equation
MAE	$MAE = y_i - \hat{y}_i $
MAPE	$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)/\hat{y}_i $
RMSE	"SE" = $\sqrt{[\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2]/n}$
R^2	$R_a^2 = 1 - \frac{n-1}{n-p-1}(1-R^2)$

5. Data Analysis for Predicting Shipbuilding Production Lead Time

This study collected production process data from a shipyard and defined analysis scenarios according to demands from different production management perspectives in order to apply various learning algorithms. Three case studies each on lead time of cutting, lead time of block erection, and lead time of spool procurement at shipyards were introduced in this paper

5.1 Lead Time Prediction for Block Cutting Process

The first case study in this paper used recorded data from cutting processes as training data to predict lead time of structural steel cutting. Shipyards consider various factors in the planning stage of a cutting process. These typically include block information, work days and weather. Therefore, independent variables were defined by additionally considering external factors of the process when analyzing recorded data. Seven independent variables were defined in the end and lead time was selected as the dependent variable.

Correlation analysis and analysis of variables were done to analyze the correlation between the defined independent variables and lead times. First, rainfall was eliminated as an independent variable from correlation analysis between continuous variables. Moreover, analysis of variables results showed that all categorical variables influenced lead time.

Fig.5: Independent variables of block cutting process

Thus, the ultimately defined independent variables defined six independent variables as shown in Fig.5. Furthermore, outliers were identified and eliminated through box plot analysis, and standardization was done using log transformation since skewness of the dependent variable was large.

Fig.6: Independent variables of block erection process

Fig.7: Independent variables of spool procurement process

5.2 Lead Time Prediction for Block Erection Process

The second case study predicted lead time of erection processes of ship blocks. Since ship blocks contain various information including block code, block type, size, and weight, it was used as input data. Correlation analysis showed continuous variables mostly having high correlation, and thus, independent variables were reduced to diminish the effects of multi-collinearity. Analysis of variables showed that all categorical variables influenced lead time. Therefore, five continuous variables were excluded from the final list of defined independent variables and thus, ten independent variables were selected to be defined and analyzed as shown in Fig.6. Moreover, outliers were identified and eliminated through box plot analysis and standardization was done with log transformation since skewness of the dependent variable was large.

5.3 Lead Time Prediction for Supply Chain of Offshore Plant Spools

The third case study analyzed spool data to improve standard data of supply chain for offshore structures. Construction of ships and offshore plants on shipyards comprise of complex processes from design to production. Offshore plants especially mostly involve spool in the outfitting process but procurement management suitable for such condition is difficult, which creates problems from delivery delays.

Supply chain data from shipyards not only contains time series data of spool according to processes, but also various data related to making and installation. Supply chain of spool is comprised of series of processes from making process to installation process. Among these, this study chose lead times of making and painting processes.

The analysis process was done in the same manner as in the previous case study. First, various process variables were selected according to spool characteristics as the first step and 17 independent variables were defined. For dependent variables, lead times were classified by making and painting processes. Analysis of variables and correlation analysis for analyzing correlation between variables were done to eventually reduce the number of variables that affected lead time to 14 and defined them as shown in Fig.7.

Moreover, outliers of variables were identified and eliminated using boxplot. Additional transformation was not done since lead time distribution analysis showed that the lead times for making were evenly distributed. Since a high number of outliers were present due to missing values in lead times for painting, data was reduced through simple elimination.

6. Prediction Model Result Analysis

6.1 Machine Learning Prediction Model

The machine learning algorithm applied linear regression, decision tree and neural network models and created a prediction model according to data. This study performed prediction by distinguishing Case 1 with raw data applied and Case 2 with preprocessing applied to analyze influence of data preprocessing. Thus, a total of 24 models were created from classifying four types of data according to analysis cases. Prediction models for cutting process, erection process, stool making process, and stool painting process are shown in Tables III to VI, respectively.

Table III: Result of machine learning (block cutting process)

	Regression		ANN		Tree	
Case	1	2	1	2	1	2
MAE	13.32	7.42	12.91	7.96	11	7.72
MAPE	169%	95%	162%	91%	126%	82%
RMSE	21.91	10.39	21.55	11	19.51	10.84
R ²	0.24	0.36				

Table IV: Result of machine learning (block erection process)

	Regression		ANN		Tree	
Case	1	2	1	2	1	2
MAE	12	9.13	13.58	8.65	9.36	8.21
MAPE	255%	133%	334%	126%	148%	117%
RMSE	18.71	15.54	20.18	15.29	15.73	14.21
R ²	0.34	0.38				

Table V: Result of machine learning (spool manufacturing)

	Regression		ANN		Tree	
Case	1	2	1	2	1	2
MAE	8.46	4.54	5.08	4.34	4.96	4.28
MAPE	35%	19%	20%	18%	19%	18%
RMSE	10.95	5.86	6.98	5.65	6.98	5.57
R ²	0.38	0.43				

Table 1: Result of machine learning (spool painting)

	Regression		ANN		Tree	
Case	1	2	1	2	1	2
MAE	10.57	3.78	4.48	2.98	4.35	3.66
MAPE	32%	25%	34%	25%	49%	24%
RMSE	11.5	5.14	6.37	4.36	3.59	5.15
R ²	0.33	0.44				

Results of analyses done according to evaluation criteria showed that prediction improved for Case 2 with data pre-processing applied for every process data. In terms of algorithm, prediction accuracy was outstanding for the decision tree model. In addition, considering that prediction accuracy for lead time of spool supply chain was higher than cutting and erection processes, lead time seemed to have a significant influence depending on process variables.

6.2 Deep Learning Prediction Model

The deep learning algorithm applied the multi-layer perceptron model using library ‘Keras’. ‘Keras’ provides intuitive API for deep learning models and runs engines exclusive for deep learning such as Tensorflow, Theano, and CNTK. Since modules provided by Keras are short and simple, this study defined analysis cases according to basic parameters. Structure of multi-layer perceptron essentially allows selecting and defining parameters such as Epoch, Activation, Batch Size and Hidden Layer. Updating weight according to Epoch and Batch Size enables model learning for minimizing loss function of the deep learning model. This study set Epoch to 200 cycles and classified analysis cases according to the number of Hidden Layer and size of Batch Size. In order to evaluate effects of data distribution, standardization of input data was done and prediction model results according to log transformation of output data were analyzed. With respect to model settings in Case 1, Case 2 and Case 3 were defined according to Batch Size, Case 4 and Case 5 according to number of Hidden Layer. Furthermore, Case 6 was defined to confirm execution of standardization of lead time, Table VII.

Table VII: Model case of MLP

	Data	Hidden Layer	Batch Size
Case 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MLP ▪ Output Log (x) 	3	100
Case 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MLP ▪ Output Log (x) 	3	50
Case 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MLP ▪ Output Log (x) 	3	30
Case 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MLP ▪ Output Log (x) 	5	100
Case 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MLP ▪ Output Log (x) 	10	100
Case 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MLP ▪ Output Log (o) 	3	100

Final performance analyses of the prediction models were as follows in the order of (1) cutting process, (2) erection process, (3) spool making process, and (4) painting process.

Table VIII: Result of deep learning (block cutting process)

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
MAE	6.18	6.04	6.25	6.25	6.60	7.59
MAPE	108%	106%	115%	110%	126%	69%
RMSE	8.14	8.13	8.23	8.21	8.37	11.13

Table IX: Result of deep learning (block erection process)

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
MAE	4.11	4.18	4.00	4.12	4.61	4.27
MAPE	16%	18%	16%	16%	17%	16%
RMSE	5.49	5.49	5.38	5.56	6.18	5.83

Table X: Result of deep learning (spool manufacturing)

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
MAE	4.11	4.18	4.00	4.12	4.61	4.27
MAPE	16%	18%	16%	16%	17%	16%
RMSE	5.49	5.49	5.38	5.56	6.18	5.83

Table XI: Result of deep learning (spool painting)

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
MAE	3.38	3.23	3.36	3.81	4.48	4.40
MAPE	24%	22%	22%	24%	27%	24%
RMSE	5.20	5.13	5.29	5.99	6.91	6.84

Cutting and erection processes had the smallest error rates in Case 6, where lead time standardization was done. Lead time of spool supply chain had a small error rate in Case 3 with a small Batch Size. It was determined that the influence of standardization with log transformation was significant considering the large skewness in distributions of cutting and erection lead times in previously analyzed results. On the other hand, standardization of lead time did not have a significant influence on spool making and painting lead times since they had relatively even distributions. Moreover, weight updates occurred more frequently with smaller Batch Size. Therefore, this showed that increasing the number of weight updates was more effective in increasing performance of a prediction model than increasing the number of hidden layer.

6.3 Analysis of results

Results of analyses done according to different algorithms for predicting ship production lead time are shown in Fig.8. Analysis of results according to process data showed that making and painting processes of spools had relatively low error rates while block erection process had the highest error rate. Moreover, in terms of algorithm, neural network and decision tree models showed improved results compared to the conventional linear regression model, and the model applied with deep learning algorithm had the best performance.

Fig.8: Result of machine learning w.r.t. each case

7. Conclusion and Future Study Plan

This paper applied the machine learning methodology to systematically construct standard data of production lead time managed by shipyards. Lead time standard data from a ship production perspective have large variability, which imposes limitations on calculating supply or hours with the conventional engineering methodology. Therefore, a prediction model for production lead time considering various product properties and resources at shipyards was created to improve standard data with variability highly subjected to production environment.

Data analysis and prediction model building used open sources such as R and Python, and various machine learning and deep learning algorithms available from the development conditions were applied. Shipyard data collected in this paper was classified into 3 types and analysis results were as follows.

The first analysis case predicted cutting process lead times. Recorded data from a mid-term schedule of cutting processes was collected to create lead time prediction models with different algorithms. Average MAPE (mean absolute percentage error) was approximately at 80%, and the deep learning algorithm showed the best predictability. The second analysis case predicted lead times of a ship block erection process. Various process variables of a block was collected and used as independent variables to create prediction models. Results showed an approximate average MAPE (mean absolute percentage error) of 100%, which was highest in all the analysis cases. In terms of algorithm, the deep learning algorithm showed the highest predictability. The third analysis case predicted lead time of a spool supply chain for offshore plants. As done in the previous cases, prediction models were created with different analysis algorithms, which showed an average MAPE (mean absolute percentage error) of 18% for making lead time and 25% for painting lead time.

Analyses results according to different algorithms showed variations depending on process data but it was confirmed that performance of prediction models with the deep learning algorithm was outstanding. Furthermore, focusing more on data pre-processing during the analysis process compared to in previous studies showed decreased error rates in prediction models. This showed that a more systematical

management of standard data was plausible through lead time prediction compared to the current standard lead time management. Furthermore, predicted standard lead times would be applicable in work planning to support swift decision making and provide insight on selecting analysis methods and parameters according to process data.

Machine learning algorithms are typically used often for making predictions, but deep learning algorithms offer various methodologies for simple numerical predictions as well as analysis of time series data. Thus, if time series prediction is allowed for various processes in terms of shipyard production, it will allow improved decision making abilities during work planning.

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References

CHO, S.J.; KANG, S.H. (2016), *Industrial application of machine learning*, Industrial Engineering Magazine 23(2), pp.34-38

HAM, D.K. (2016), *A study of data-mining methodology in offshore plant's outfittings procurement management*, M.A., Korea Maritime & Ocean University, Busan

HAM, D.K.; BACK, M.G.; PARK, J.G.; & WOO, J.H. (2016), *A study of piping leadtime forecast in offshore plant's outfittings procurement management*, J. Society of Naval Architects of Korea 53(1), pp.29-36

HAN, S.H. (2016), *Study on introduction of big data in Korea manufacturing area*, Technopark, Incheon

HWANG, K.O. (2001), *Development direction of production management system for digital shipyard*, J. Society of Naval Architects of Korea 38(1), pp.42-46

JANG, Y.J. (2012), *Utilization of big data technology in manufacturing area*, Communications of the Korean Institute of Information Scientists and Engineer 29(11), pp.30-35

JUNG, S.H.; SHIM, C.B. (2014), *A study on a working pattern analysis prototype using correlation analysis and linear regression analysis in welding big data environment*, Korean J. Korean Institute of Communications and Information Sciences 9(10), pp.1071-1078

KANG, M.M.; KIM, S.R.; PARK, S.M. (2012), *Analysis and utilization of big data*, Communications of the Korean Institute of Information Scientists and Engineer 30(6), pp.25-32

KIET (2013), *Utilization plan of big data for strengthening manufacturing competitiveness*, Korea Institute for Industrial Economics & Trade, Seoul

KIM, S.H.; ROH, M.I.; KIM, K.S. (2016), *A study on big data platform based on hadoop for the applications in ship and offshore industry*, Korean J. Computational Design and Engineering 21(3), pp.334-340

- KIM, Y.J. (2013), *Corporate innovation through the introduction of advanced analysis system based on big data*, Industrial engineering magazine 20(1), pp.43-49
- KIM, E.J. (2016), *Introduction to artificial intelligence, machine learning, Deep Learning learned by algorithm*, Wikibooks: Paju
- KIM, Y.J. et al. (2013), *A Study on the Bigdata technology and analysis technique for vessel design automation*, Summer Proc. Korea Institute of Communications and Information Sciences, Jeju, pp.213-215
- KIM, J.W. et al. (2015), *Deep learning algorithms and applications*, Communications of the Korean Institute of Information Scientists and Engineer 33(8), pp.25-31
- LEE, J.G.; LEE, T.H.; YOON, S.R. (2014), *Machine learning for analysis of big data*, Communications of the Korean Institute of Information Scientists and Engineer 31(11), pp.14-26
- MOON, S.E.; JANG, S.B.; LEE, J.H.; LEE, J.S. (2016), *Technology trends of machine learning and deep learning*, J. Korean Institute of Communication Sciences 33(10), pp.49-56
- NIA (2016), *Casebook of fusion of global big data in 2016*, National Information Agency, Daegu
- SEO, J.H.; YONG, H.S. (2016), *Performance evaluation of LSTM and GRU using tensorflow*, Winter Proc. Korea Institute of Information Sciences and Engineers, Pyeongchang, pp.211-213

Virtual Reality in the Field of Numerical Marine Simulation

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Abstract

This paper presents how Virtual Reality (VR) technologies can be used inside an engineering office to get a better understanding of physical phenomena, especially marine flows. Different use cases illustrate the pros and cons of the state-of-the-art VR solutions. An outlook outlines the work to undertake in the next years to fully integrate VR tools into the ship design workflow. The presented use cases include static and dynamic CFD simulations for a submarine and a frigate in 3D virtual environments.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in Virtual Reality (VR) have introduced new ways to work and analyze numerical simulations and experimental datasets. With a wide range of display devices, interaction devices and software solutions, virtual reality technologies and now augmented reality technologies offer many possibilities that need to be explored. This paper presents how these technologies can be used inside the engineer office to analyze and intuitively interact with datasets to provide a better understanding of physical phenomena.

VR has already been successfully used in maritime industry for shipbuilding, *Alonso et al. (2012)*, *Larkins et al. (2013)*, *Morais et al. (2017)*, *Sakari et al. (2017)*, for training, *Bertram and Plowman (2018)*. However, VR possibilities have not been used to help scientific and computational engineers analyze simulations involving large scalar and vector field results. These simulations results are used to design ships and are generated by all engineering disciplines (mechanics, hydrodynamics, acoustics, electromagnetics,...). While researchers and numerical engineers tend to simulate larger and larger dynamic systems, efficient tools are needed to analyze and post-process them. VR technologies, that become more and more affordable have to be explored to bring new solutions.

The objectives of using VR in the field of numerical marine simulation are to:

- maximize the use of 3D models and simulations, give better insights to users,
- reduce time needed to analyze complex numerical simulations,
- improve understanding of the 3D data,
- detect singularities,
- give ideas to innovate by providing a new perspective to numerical results.

The main challenges are multiple: How to put simulation results inside VR devices? Which interactions are the most convenient? Can VR vision be shared with other colleagues? How deep VR tools can interact with simulation software?

The first section of this paper presents the different hardware and software used for VR, the second section details the different VR use cases explored with discussions about pros and cons of each solution, and the third part gives an overview of the future work to be accomplished to have fully integrated VR solutions.

2. Hardware / Software

This section presents a short but not exhaustive review of the different hardware and software.

2.1. VR hardware

Many solutions have been developed from small VR devices to large immersive CAVE (Cave automatic virtual environment):

- Head-Mounted Display (HMD) are worn on the head and have a display optic. It uses room scale tracking technology, allowing the user to move in 3D space and use motion-tracked handheld controllers to interact with the environment. First HMDs that dated back to the nineties suffered from high latencies that caused cybersickness. Recently, gaming industry led developments for new affordable HMD devices with reduced latencies. HMD is a good candidate to explore numerical simulation results.
- With a lightweight eye-tracking, interactive 3D screens create 3D rendering of objects. A simple stylus is used to manipulate objects and interact with them. It can be used to work with two screens, one 2D classical screen used to configure 3D scene, and a 3D offering 3D rendering. These 3D interactive screens are perfectly suited for education purpose and also a good candidate to explore numerical simulation results.
- CAVEs are immersive VR environment, where projectors create immersion in a whole room. These devices are the most expensive and require high definition content. They are perfectly suited for training purpose, but not really for analyzing daily generated results.

2.2. VR software solutions

Over the last decade, several software packages have been developed to provide VR experience. This software is tightly developed with VR hardware. Below is a short list of the current solutions.

- Game oriented engines such as Unity 3D and Unreal Engine include VR modules. Most VR applications are currently produced with these two packages.
- HTML5 technology with WebGL, WebVR and specific JavaScript libraries like Three.js allow to create 3D VR applications within web browsers.
- Many companies propose dedicated plugins to propose VR experience for 3D software. For example, Techviz develops 3D visualization solutions to be used on top of engineer classical CAD software.
- Scientific software tools that are classically used to analyze simulation results also propose VR modules. *Su et al. (2015)* presented different VR solutions based on ParaView. ParaView is an open-source software solution used to analyze large datasets produced by numerous simulation software. It is based on VTK (Visualization ToolKit) as its computational and rendering engine. *Martin et al. (2016)*, *Mc Kenzie et al. (2017)* and *Leary et al. (2017)* have presented a VR dedicated ParaView. The first releases of this VR version support HTC Vive head mounted display. It is based on OpenVR and SteamVR SDK to propose VR functionalities on Windows OS. For the time being, ParaViewVR allows to analyze stationary results. ParaView and ParaViewVR are the main software tools used to conduct the present experiments.

3. Uses cases

This section presents two use cases based on the analysis of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations with different VR devices. For each use case, points of view of different users are also presented.

3.1. Analysis of a CFD computation for BB2 submarine

A first use case is presented on a modern generic SSK-class submarine, the BB2, with "Joubert" hull form design. The BB2 is a non-existing submarine, designed to enable international cooperation on benchmark and validation studies, *Joubert (2004, 2006)*. A CFD computation of the BB2 with a drift angle is analysed: pressure coefficient on submarine are analyzed as well as vorticity with isosurfaces

of Q-criterion, *Jeong et al. (1995)*. The objectives are to analyze the flow around the rudders and propeller with a great precision. This use case is tested with a HMD that provides an immersive experience and with a 3D interactive screen.

3.1.1. Analysis with a HMD

The installation is composed of a HTC Vive Head-Mounted Display with two hand- controllers and the associated tracking devices. ParaViewVR is used to load and post process simulation results. The first release ParaViewVR (version 5.2.0) was initially used to analyze this computation: the two hand-controllers allow to move around the submarine, zoom in and out around areas of interest. The users can also grab objects with one hand controller, rotate it. A newer release (version 5.4.1) introduced some new post processing features to interact with presented results:

- Dynamic probe location allows users to fetch data (e.g. velocity or pressure) at specific locations by pointing an artificial ray to areas of interest.
- Dynamic mesh slicing / clipping is an interesting post-processing while analyzing spatial field results: it allows to cut isosurfaces dynamically and visualize phenomena that cannot be seen globally.

Figs.1 to 3 are screen captures of ParaViewVR interface. Fig.1 shows the 3D model with the two virtual hand-controllers. Fig.2 presents the dynamic slicing possibilities and Fig.3 shows the interactive menu used to perform different actions.

New and experimented users found the experience interesting, it really gives new perspective to 3D simulation results that are classically analyzed on 2D screens. Users only need few minutes to really feel comfortable with immersion. The few post-processing functionalities are easy to use. Moreover, visualizing results of numerical simulations in HMD reveals to be a great communication tool.

Despite all these advantages, this solution presents some drawbacks that all HMD VR devices suffer:

- A dedicated room is required. This may seem harmless, but even if this dedicated room is close to the engineer office, it requires some preparation and time to move datasets from working desktop to VR installation.
- Using a HMD is not a working habit, and some users have the feeling they are more playing than working with such a device.
- Users can not work for hours with this device: even if HMD are reactive and manufacturers are working to limit cyber-sickness, users can not use HMD more than 30 minutes.
- For the time being, the users cannot fully configure their scene from the immersive environment: all post-processing functionalities are not directly accessible and the users need to remove and put on the HMD.
- Only one person can use the HMD at a time and benefit from the 3D rendering.

Fig.1: Screen capture from the left eye of the HMD

Fig.2: Screen capture of live mesh slicing

Fig.3: Screen capture of dynamic interaction menu

Immersive VR provides great experience. However, all post-processing functionalities are not available from VR environment, unlike other devices like 3d interactive screen.

3.1.2. Analysis with a 3D interactive screen

This demo uses a classical ParaView release (version 5.2.0), a ZSpace 200 screen and a specific development based on ZSpace SDK to allow communications between ParaView and the 3D screen. This specific plugin was developed by Kitware France and EDF R&D. A similar installation has been proposed by *Su et al.* (2015).

ZSpace 200 is a 3D interactive screen with a lightweight eye-tracking device and a stylus, Fig.4. The 3D screen has tracking sensors that follow the user movements; it dynamically updates to display the correct perspective. The 3D rendering gives a real 3D feeling with a nice perception of depth. It feels natural to move from a configuration screen to a 3d rendering screen. The 3D rendering can be shared between several users: it can be used during meetings for design reviews.

At the moment, the combined use of ParaView and ZSpace is experimental, but sounds really interesting and promising.

Fig.4: Installation of a 3D interactive screen

3.2. Analysis of a dynamic CFD computation for DTMB

Many simulations involve dynamic results with transient phenomena. For the time being, ParaView VR version does not support animation. So, the previous VR analysis is not possible in a dynamical way and another 3D VR display software tool has to be selected.

In this second use case, the marine flow around the DTMB 5415 ship hull with imposed sway oscillations is dynamically analyzed. This ship model was designed by the US David Taylor Model Basin (DTMB) in the early 1980s and is heavily used for experimental and numerical benchmarks, *Forgach (2001)*. Points of interests include the free-surface flow and elevation, and vortices evolution close to propeller and rudders area. The CFD numerical results for such a simulation are large in terms of memory use: to give an idea, each time step generates 500 MB of data for free surface and vorticity. The global simulation represents 20 GB for 400 time steps. This large amount of data cannot be directly loaded and visualized on a regular laptop. To overcome this difficulty, the results are down sampled and imported in a generic VR game engine (Unity 3D) that supports dynamic animation. The challenges for this use case consist in finding the good reduction factor to keep as much precision as possible for the displayed results. The strategy adopted to reduce the volume of data is to project the free surface elevation, initially stored as a triangular mesh, on a coarser Cartesian grid. Vortices are also down sampled by mesh decimation using VTK algorithms. The good trade-off for this use case is to reduce by a factor three the dataset volume, so that simulation results can be loaded and stored into the RAM.

The results can be seen in Fig.5. The users can navigate above and below sea surface to inspect vortices. Two horizontal scrollbars allow to play with time: the first one allows to create a pause on a specific time step and the other allows to set the frame rate. Their respective positions are set with one of the hand controller. These time functionalities reveal to be extremely interesting for users that appreciate the simplicity to analyze a specific region at a specific time step and look at the dynamic evolution with a specific frame rate.

Figs.6a and b present the difference between the down sampled version (with Unity 3D) and the original simulation exported results (with classical ParaView). Even if the down sampled version represents correctly geometries, an accurate analysis requires the original results. HPC remote visualization is one solution to be tested.

Fig.5: Dynamic CFD analysis with Unity

Fig.6a: Down sampled vortices

Fig.6b: Original vortices

4. Future work

The presented use cases have demonstrated nice features, that need to be enhanced to fully integrate VR tools into engineers' design workflow. Having devices close to the engineer desktop is one way to ease the use of these technologies, but it is not the only limitation. Future work should focus on the following points:

- Simplification of workflows to import numerical results inside VR installations. At the moment, the time needed to prepare 3D is quite large, and may be repellent for users.
- Development of new interactions to access post-processing functionalities.
- Development of live post-processing functionalities in the VR environment, like requesting

stream lines at some points or creating volumetric slices. Some proofs of concept have already been developed but live post-processing requires to think of a global architecture that can trigger computations from the VR environment.

- Handling large datasets. At the moment, most of VR devices exclusively run on Windows which are generally not machines on which large simulations run. At the moment, numerical results have to be down sampled to be analyzed. Solutions have to be found to overcome this limitation; maybe HPC remote visualization is the solution.
- Communication standardization between hardware and software: the lack of standards makes it not trivial to integrate new devices to existing post-processing software. At the moment, too much effort is put to develop solutions that work with only one device and one software, even if some standards start to emerge like OpenVR.

At the moment, some solutions are already available to address these points, but they are still experimental. This will allow to explore even more complex numerical simulations with VR devices.

Finally, with the development of augmented reality devices, numerical simulation results can also be brought in situ, on ships: this also opens a wide spectrum of possibilities.

5. Conclusion

This paper presented the use of VR technologies for numerical marine simulations. After a short review of current VR devices and software, different use cases were presented. Through these use cases, the benefits of VR have been presented, pros and cons of each VR device were discussed for static and dynamic result analyzes with different VR devices. The users report that VR gives new and unique perspectives of numerical results, can reduce analysis time by providing a better understanding of simulated phenomena. These tools can also drive innovation. It is also undoubtedly a great communication tool. From the present experience, interactive 3D screens seem to be better suited to analyze numerical simulation results than immersive devices. There are still several challenges that need to be better addressed to fully integrate VR tools into the engineer design workflow: large dataset handling, relevant interaction developments, communication standardization between software tools and devices are essential to make VR devices everyday tools.

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References

- ALONSO, V.; PÉREZ, R.; SÀNCHEZ, L.; TRONSTAD, R. (2012), *Advantages of Using a Virtual Reality Tool in Shipbuilding*, 11th COMPIT Conf., Liege
- BERTRAM, V.; PLOWMAN, T. (2018), *Virtual Reality for Maritime Training – A Survey*, 17th COMPIT Conf., Pavone
- FORGACH, K.M. (2001) *Comparison of ITTC-78 and DTMB Standard Ship Performance Prediction Methods*, David Taylor Model Basin, Bethesda
- JEONG, J.; HUSSAIN, F. (1995), *On the identification of a vortex*, J. Fluid Mechanics 285, pp.69-94
- JOUBERT, P.N. (2004), *Some aspects of submarine design part 1- Hydrodynamics*, DSTO-TR-1622
- JOUBERT, P.N. (2006), *Some aspects of submarine design part 2- Shape of a Submarine 2026*, DSTO-TR-1920

LARKINS, D.; MORAIS, D.; WALDIE, M.; (2013), *Democratization of Virtual Reality in Shipbuilding*, 12th COMPIT Conf., Cortona

LEARY, P. O.; JHAVERI, S.; CHAUDHARY, A.; SHERMAN W., MARTIN, K.; LONIE, D.; WHITING, E.; MONEY, J.; MCKENZIE, S., (2017) *Enhancements to VTK enabling scientific visualization in immersive environments*, IEEE Virtual Reality (VR), pp.186-194

LOSURDO, M. (2016), *Augmented reality visualization with Hololens of 3d numerical simulations*, https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/augmented-reality-visualization-hololens-3d-numerical-marco-losurdo?trk=portfolio_article-card_title

MARTIN, K.; DEMARLE, D.; JHAVERI, S.; AYACHIT, U. (2016), *Taking ParaView into virtual reality*, <https://blog.kitware.com/taking-paraview-into-virtual-reality/>

McKENZIE, S. (2017), *Kitware eases development of virtual reality applications*, <https://blog.kitware.com/kitware-eases-development-of-virtual-reality-applications/>

MORAIS, D.; WALDIE, M.; LARKINS, D. (2017), *The Evolution of Virtual Reality in Shipbuilding*, 16th COMPIT Conf., Cardiff

NORDBY, K.; BØRRESEN, S.; GERNEZ, E.; (2016), *Efficient Use of Virtual and Mixed Reality in Conceptual Design of Maritime Work Places*, 15th COMPIT Conf., Lecce

SAKARI, L.; HELLE, S.; KORHONEN, S.; SÄNTTI, T.; HEIMO, O.; FORSMAN, M.; TASKINEN, M.; LEHTONEN, T., (2017) *Virtual and Augmented Reality Solutions to Industrial Applications*, 16th COMPIT Conf., Cardiff

SHETTY, N.; CHAUDHARY, A.; COMING, D.; SHERMAN, W. R.; O'LEARY, P.; WHITING, E. T.; SU, S. (2011). *Immersive ParaView: A community-based, immersive, universal scientific visualization application*, IEEE Virtual Reality Conf.

SU, S.; CHAUDHARY, A.; O'LEARY, P.; GEVECI, B.; SHERMAN, W.; NIETO, H.; FRANCISCO-REVILLA, L. (2015), *Virtual reality enabled scientific visualization workflow*, IEEE 1st Workshop on Everyday Virtual Reality (WEVR)

Appification of Propeller Modeling and Design via CAESES

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Abstract

This paper describes a web-based Application (webApp) for geometric modeling and design of propellers. The App builds on CAESES as a flexible Computer Aided Engineering environment which allows offering selected functionality sub-sets via a standard web-browser. For the webApp the expertise of a propeller designer is combined with the design data of the Wageningen B-series. Building on CAESES' parametric modeling techniques, a propeller (comprising blades, hub and fillets) is generated with just a handful of inputs. The App then provides a watertight geometric model and determines the efficiency. In the final step, the geometry can be downloaded, e.g. as an STL file to be used in a numerical propulsion test or for 3d-printing. Along a design example for illustration, the underlying CAESES technology of modeling and "appification" will be presented. Commercial and academic use cases of webApps will be discussed.

1. Introduction

Cloud computing, Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) and web-based applications are changing the way designers and simulation engineers perceive their working environment. While many types of engineering tasks may still be done most efficiently on local hardware, running software for which a long-term license has been purchased, other jobs can be more economically realized outside the office. For instance, on one side of the spectrum a heavy-duty viscous flow analysis can be transferred to a high performance computing (HPC) center to utilize a large number of processors for fast turn-around time *Albert et al. (2016)*. On the other side of the spectrum smaller technical applications, so-called technical Apps, may be run that offer very specific functionality that is dedicated to a certain task, *Harries (2017)*. This paper focuses on the latter situation, i.e., the development and offer of a technical App that is accessible via a standard web-browser, constituting a web-based application (webApp).

The webApp in question has been developed for the geometric modeling and design of propellers, see <https://www.wageningen-b-series-propeller.com>. It builds on CAESES as a flexible CAE system (Computer Aided Engineering). CAESES allows wrapping selected sub-sets of functionality and offering it via a web-browser from any device (from smart phones to workstations) for intuitive, albeit inherently limited, work flows. The expertise of an experienced propeller designer has been combined with data from the Wageningen B-series *Oosterveld and van Oossanen (1975)*. The idea is to generate added value for the app user quickly and conveniently without claiming an all-encompassing functionality.

Building on CAESES' parametric modeling techniques a propeller, comprising blades, the hub and fillets, is generated with just a handful of inputs. The "Wageningen webApp" then offers a watertight geometric model and determines the propeller's efficiency. In the final step, the geometry can be downloaded, for instance as an stl-file to be used as a stock-propeller for a numerical propulsion test or for rapid prototyping via 3d-printing.

A design example will be presented for the propeller of a fast power boat, *Albert et al. (2016)*, *Abt and Harries (2016)*. Using the example for illustration, the underlying CAESES technology of modeling and "appification" will be presented. Furthermore, commercial and academic use cases as well as limits and potentials of webApps will be discussed.

2. Apps

Since the advent of smart phones and tablets in 2007 and 2010, respectively, millions of Apps have been developed and are being utilized by billions of people every day. In March 2017, Google Store offered about 2 800 000 apps while the Apple App Store featured 2 200 000 apps, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/276623/number-of-apps-available-in-leading-app-stores/>. In January 2018 the most popular apps belonged to the following categories: games (25%), business (9.8%), education (8.5%), lifestyle (8.3%) and entertainment (6.1%), <https://www.statista.com/statistics/270291/popular-categories-in-the-app-store/>.

Apps are defined in <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/App> as follows:

- Mobile app, software designed to run on smartphones and other mobile devices
- Application software that causes a computer to perform tasks for computer users
- Web application or web app, software designed to run inside a web-browser

A common characteristic of many apps is that the user can do certain things very easily and quickly, typically within a clearly prescribed set of actions. Let us take a photo app as an example, the category photo & video ranking at position 14 (2.2%) of popular apps. You start the app, load a photo, modify it, for example by applying a filter from a limited set of preconfigured filters, save or discard the changes, possibly share the photo and, finally, close the app. If that is what you want, it is the perfect tool. If you want to do something different with your photo you need to find another app that is doing the job. As an alternative, you can install a potent photo editor on your computer and do all sorts of sophisticated things after you have familiarized yourself with the tool.

Neither approach is better than the other. Rather the use cases are different. Apps aim at convenience, speed and fair results while powerful software solutions aim at comprehensiveness, flexibility and top quality. An app can be utilized with limited knowledge while the software solution requires expertise, see also *Harries (2017)*.

3. CAESES as a backbone for appification

Engineering does not show among the top 20 of popular apps, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/270291/popular-categories-in-the-app-store/>, if the category actually exists. This may not really come as a surprise, the worldwide number of engineers simply being too low and engineering challenges being too diverse. Still, there is a (growing) market for web solutions in various fields of engineering such as

- Sharing of generic utilities (that would otherwise not be accessible),
- Offering of encapsulated solutions for well-defined engineering tasks (externally for third parties and internally for colleagues),
- Communication and engagement (with customers),
- Education and illustration.

Currently, the most limiting factor of making software available to engineers via the web is that many excellent tools have been developed at a time when nobody could think of sharing them with a large group of external users. To start with a tool would need an intuitive Graphical Users Interface (GUI) that can be accessed remotely without any local installation, ideally via standard technology such as a web-browser. Moreover, an ecosystem would be required that takes care of launching the tool, also many instances when several people work in parallel, and – at some point – of administrating the obligatory business aspects such as payment and invoicing. Technically, CAESES has been extended to provide such a system and may serve as a backbone for “appification.” In the context of this paper, appification is the conversion of an engineering solution from a stand-alone tool originally meant to run on local hardware into a web-based service.

CAESES itself is a flexible PIDO environment (Process Integration and Design Optimization) with geometric modeling for robust variable CAD (Computer Aided Design). It originates from simulation-driven design of functional shapes *Harries (2014)* and allows wrapping any tool that can be executed in batch-mode via input and output files as shown in Fig.1. Details of tool integration are given in *Harries et al. (2015b)*, *Albert et al. (2016)* and *Harries et al. (2017)*. In general, once a tool has been integrated all the functionality of CAESES such as file handling, data management, data processing, data conversion etc. are readily available. As will be shown below by means of the illustrating example, this is complemented by a novel approach of providing access to CAESES and any tool coupled to it through the web.

Fig.1: Tool integration via templates

4. Design task

The webApp shall be illustrated for a meaningful design task in naval architecture: A new propeller shall be developed for a given vessel. Here a small power boat, similar to the classic Riva Junior from 1966, is to get a replacement propeller, say after damage of the existing propeller or for adjusting to new operational requirements such as lower top speed for the sake of reduced fuel consumption at top and at cruising speed. The power boat was subject to prior numerical simulations as presented in *Albert et al. (2016)*. Fig.2 shows the parametric model along with the CFD results.

(A) Parametric model realized within CAESES (B) Viscous flow simulation with free trim and sinkage at 18 kn computed with FINE/Marine

Fig.2: Power boat studied for propeller design *Albert et al. (2016)*

The boat has a length over all of 5.86 m and a maximum beam of 2.2 m. Its displacement volume is 1300 kg at a design draft of 0.32 m. The CFD analysis of the bare hull yields a calm-water resistance of about 1600 N (both viscous and wave resistance) at cruising speed of 18 kn at a dynamic trim angle

of 5°. Thrust comes from a single three-bladed propeller on a shaft line inclined at 15° and attached to an engine with 180 hp (132 kW). The shaft line features a bracket and steering is realized via a spade rudder. Top speed is well above 30 kn in ideal conditions at full engine load and around 4800 rpm. Some boats feature a direct shaft line while others come with a reduction gear box.

The resistance of the power boat was estimated for speeds up to 32 kn, using the 18 kn resistance from the CFD simulation as a reference point. Conservative allowances for shaft, bracket and rudder resistance as well as wind resistance have been made, so that the total resistance was assumed to be 2780 N at 18 kn and 4600 N at 32 kn.

5. State-of-the-art propeller design

A propeller specialist receiving the order for a new propeller would engage their state-of-the-art tools and build on their experience. It is not intended to suggest here that a webApp would replace this diligent piece of engineering. Instead, it shall be shown, for the sake of comparison, what a design would look like if done at the highest level. This will help to highlight advantages and drawbacks.

In general, a propeller design has to meet several basic requirements: It needs to match the specified engine working point (e.g. full engine power to be absorbed at nominal engine rpm), it must provide sufficient blade and hub strength to transmit full engine power and, additionally, it has to avoid harmful cavitation characteristics. There are further important objectives which depend on the application and on the customer. Highest possible efficiency is the most natural and the most frequent target while low noise and vibration (e.g. yacht) or a good bollard pull (e.g. tug boat) may also be asked for. Further aspects need to be taken into account if several operating conditions have to be considered, for instance a fast patrol boat propeller with good top speed performance should also feature low noise levels at lower speeds or a controllable pitch propeller should perform well at different speeds for its corresponding pitch settings.

In the propeller design example for the power boat, the top speed condition determines the blade design. The high power density (i.e., power to propeller disc area) and the large shaft inclination angle call for careful considerations regarding acceptable cavitation performance. Otherwise, cavitation erosion damages might occur already after only a few hours of running at full speed. Of course, operating the same boat at lower rpm with lower power output and at lower speed greatly reduces the cavitation extent and any noise or vibration excitation. It should be noted that a fixed pitch propeller with the highest possible efficiency at full speed (and full power) will also have the highest possible efficiency at intermediate speeds. This is why it suffices to consider the design at top speed as the critical condition.

A propeller design is generally done in an iterative way: The first step consists of determining the main particulars such diameter, mean pitch and blade area. The number of blades is either specified by the customer or selected on the base of considerations like efficiency, noise and vibration excitation and/or manufacturing costs. The propeller diameter is limited due to the space available, including proper clearances. However, even if the available space is large, the most efficient propeller features a finite diameter due to friction and the kinetic energy left behind in the slipstream. These different kinds of losses often have opposing trends. Consequently, the task is to find the optimum diameter with the smallest sum of losses.

At the beginning of a new propeller design, it is quite common to assess propeller efficiency by means of test results from propeller series. The Wageningen B-series *Oosterveld and van Oossanen (1975)* is most popular due to its wide range of propeller parameters and due to the availability of polynomials that represent propeller performance. It is also utilized as the basis of the webApp, see below. Although this propeller series has been designed more than 50 years ago, the test results remain valuable and are employed to identify trends and optima, yielding starting points for more sophisticated computations. Within such a B-series optimization the required blade area is generally selected via an empirical method taken from *Burill (1962)* (Burill diagram) or *Auf'm Keller (1966)*

which originate from systematic scale model tests conducted several decades ago but still remain useful for first estimates.

After the first selection of the propeller main particulars, a custom propeller design calls for the modeling of geometrical details as well as the prediction of associated propeller performance. For example, the desired mean pitch can be obtained with different radial pitch distributions (e.g. incorporating “tip unloading” for reduced cavitation extent) and, similarly, the same blade area can be obtained with different blade contours (e.g. pointed or wide blade tips). Furthermore, the designer can vary skew-back and rake in order to adapt the blade shape to the propeller aperture and to take advantage of three-dimensional flow effects. Finally, also the shape of the blade sections can be adapted by changing the maximum thickness and camber at certain blade radii and by modifying the distribution of thickness and camber along the chord. This controls steady and unsteady blade pressure distributions and, hence, the extent and characteristics of cavitation. Blade edges can be made especially thick for more robustness (e.g. for inland waterway vessels, dredgers or ice breakers) or explicitly thin (e.g. for high speed propellers).

The methods used to predict propeller performance should be capable of capturing the effects of all blade details in order to enable the designer to make the right decisions from one design iteration to the next. Numerical potential flow methods, extended to account for viscous flow effects, are most suitable for this task, providing steady and unsteady blade pressure distributions and cavitation patterns for the critical operating conditions within short computational time. Vortex-lattice methods and boundary element methods are used in optimization where numerous design candidates are automatically generated, assessed and varied. Blade and hub strength have to be considered during the design iterations, too. In general, the blade designer must find a balance between sufficient blade strength (thick and wide blades) and optimum hydrodynamic properties (thin and narrow blades). For low noise propellers, these two fundamental requirements might even point into the same direction, but for most propellers, the optimum blade is as thin and as narrow as possible with regard to strength. Towards the end of a sophisticated design process viscous flow simulations can be employed to check whether there is any risk of undesirable flow patterns which might have been left undetected during the potential flow analyses. For further details and background see e.g. *Breslin and Andersen (1996)*.

Due to the large number of parameters defining the blade shape, a propeller designer may either rely on his or her experience, fixing certain parameters early on, or leave all parameters free in order to find the best possible custom design for a certain application. In the latter case, it is advisable to employ an automated optimization process which varies the free parameters, builds the detailed blade geometry, assesses this blade geometry in terms of strength and hydrodynamics, compares the results with those of previous design candidates and continues with a new set of free parameters until no further improvement can be found. CAESES can be employed for this as it offers a wide range of formal optimization strategies.

For the design example at hand, custom designs have been prepared, incorporating several special features in order to improve propeller performance. Therefore, the custom design and the “equivalent” B-series propeller do not only have different blade shapes (easily distinguishable at first glance), but also different design details, most importantly in the blade sections. It goes without saying that this design effort is only justifiable if the propeller will also be manufactured within tightly set tolerances.

6. Propeller design based on the Wageningen B-series

The Wageningen B-series data can be used to determine suitable propeller main particulars for a given design task. The basic results consist of optimum propeller diameter and number of blades (if not specified beforehand) along with mean pitch, blade area, and the corresponding propeller open water curves. *Oosterveld and van Oossanen (1975)* specifies how these propeller main particulars determine all other blade details, like skew-back, rake, radial pitch distribution, blade contour, and blade section shapes. Also the hub diameter and contour are described.

Strictly speaking, this would already yield the final B-series design. However, a few modifications appear to be beneficial and have been made available within the webApp: Firstly, it is advisable to check the blade strength. As a result of basic beam theory, bigger propellers require relatively thicker blades than smaller propellers and absolute blade thickness depends on material properties. Therefore, it may well turn out that the basic B-series propeller does not meet the actual strength requirements, necessitating some design modifications. Vice versa, it might also turn out that the original blade thickness of the B-series is much thicker than needed, so the design can be modified towards thinner blades. Due to the shape of the B-series profile sections with mostly flat pressure faces, a change of blade thickness also affects the effective blade section camber which brings about a similar effect as a slight pitch modification. However, this effect has been neglected in the current version of the webApp. Secondly, thinking about small adaptations, it appears easy and without too much risk to vary the blade rake. The original B-series propellers feature rather pronounced backward rake which not always fits the purpose. Consequently, it appears worthwhile to adjust the rake to the actual propeller aperture. Finally, the B-series propeller hub might not be suitable for the actual application. In order to generate a proper hub, the webApp determines the required diameter of a steel shaft for the specified engine output and shaft rpm and selects the corresponding hub dimensions according to ISO4566.

Naturally, one could think of several more smaller or larger modifications of a B-series propeller design, but it should also be understood that any deviation has an impact on hydrodynamics which cannot be determined without more sophisticated analyses as discussed above. As a conclusion, a B-series propeller design cannot be adapted in every detail to the actual working conditions. Especially, the blade sections have inferior properties compared to modern profile shapes.

7. Geometric modeling of propellers within CAESES

The design process of the B-series propeller in CAESES is divided into three parts:

- Profile definition along with the blade creation,
- Hub modeling and
- Merging process to create the final and watertight propeller geometry.

In the very first step, 2D profiles are defined by using either mathematical formulas or any other curve type that is available within CAESES, such as spline curves. In the case of the B-series, there is a set of equations that can be used to create 2D section point data, *Oosterveld and van Oossanen (1975)*. These data points are interpolated and scaled according to their chord length. CAESES allows users to define methods and expressions in so-called feature definitions which are an integrated programming environment for custom scripting, Fig.3. The 2D profile generation is parametric and, once defined, always follows the user input such as changes of the diameter or the thickness distribution.


```

28
29 // chord length of 4, 5, 6 and 7 blades propellers
30 fvector3series chord_1([[0.2,1.662*AR*D/z*crf,0],[0.3,1.882*AR*D/z*cf03,0],[0.4,2.050*AR*D/z,0],[0.5,2.1
31
32 // chord length of 3 blades propeller
33 fvector3series chord_2([[0.2,1.633*AR*D/z*crf,0],[0.3,1.832*AR*D/z*cf03,0],[0.4,2.0*AR*D/z,0],[0.5,2.12*
34
35 // chord length of BB-Series propeller
36 fvector3series chord_3([[0.2,1.6*AR*D/z*crf,0],[0.3,1.832*AR*D/z*cf03,0],[0.4,2.023*AR*D/z,0],[0.5,2.163
37
38 interpolationcurve chordcurve()
39
40 if (BB)
41   chordcurve.setData(chord_3)
42 elseif (z>3)
43   chordcurve.setData(chord_1)
44 else
45   chordcurve.setData(chord_2)
46 endif
47

```

Fig.3: Snipped of a CAESES feature for defining the B-series chord length

For the B-series, a number of discrete sections (typically eight to nine) are created as 2D curves and transformed into the 3D space as cylindrical sections, based on the specific radii taken from the literature. The 3D sections are subsequently skinned by a NURBS surface, creating a mathematically closed definition of the main blade as shown in Fig.4. See also *Harries and Käther (1997)*.

Fig.4: Initial blade surface generated by interpolating the transformed B-series sections

Fig.5: Using a propeller tip feature for closing the blade with a smooth surface

The main blade is left open at the tip region. In order to close it, a dedicated surface feature is used within CAESES (which is shipped with the software). The NURBS representation of the blade, i.e., its control vertices and knot vectors, serve as input to this tip surface feature. The tip surface is created such that it takes the same number of vertices and the same values for the knot vectors and weights in profile direction. As a result, a continuous transition from the blade to the tip is ensured with tangent information being taken from the control net structure of the blade surface, Fig.5. The tip surface ends in a singularity at the outer diameter of the propeller.

The shaft is determined from the inputs, namely, engine power output per shaft, RPM, material and gear ratio (if applicable). Based on this information, the upstream and downstream diameters of the hub are calculated for the chosen propeller material via the rules set in ISO4566, Figs.6 and 7. The smaller downstream hub diameter depends on the boss length which is also taken from the ISO standard. In order to define the blade's thickness distribution, an internal optimization is triggered based on the user inputs. These inputs are the actual power that includes transmission losses, the water density, rpm, gear ratio, propeller diameter, the vessel speed, the expanded area ratio, number of blades and the Reynolds number.

Fig.6: Blade and hub geometry with hub diameters calculated using ISO4566

Fig.7: Definitions of the upstream and downstream hub diameters

These input data are converted into target values for the torque coefficient K_q and the advance ratio J (for definitions see *Breslin and Andersen (1996)*), which have to be met by finding the corresponding pitch. As a result, the iterated pitch value and the calculated thrust coefficient K_t value are known. As can be imagined, the success of this optimization depends on the design scenario, i.e., it may happen that no meaningful propeller can be identified that would serve the input.

The K_t value found gives the thrust which is then also used to calculate the blade root thickness via basic beam theory. It is computed using the thrust value, the material information, the pitch angle and the chord length at the root, the number of blades and the torque value. Meanwhile, the tip thickness is fixed with a value of 0.5% of the propeller diameter. These root and the tip thickness values are taken to create a linear thickness distribution between the hub and the tip. With this information, the 2D sections are completely defined and the 3D surface can be generated, as described above.

For creation of a solid geometry the blade surface is copied and rotated according to the number of blades. The hub might need to be extended in axial direction to fully intersect with the blade surfaces since for most input settings the initial hub from the ISO4566 turns out to be too short. The blade surfaces still need to be extended at the root area such that they are reaching into the hub geometry. An intersection operation is then undertaken which results in a watertight solid body as depicted in Fig.8. The fillet radius is typically set to be 75 % of the blade root section thickness. Once the fillet between the hub and blade geometry is applied, the remaining hub geometry is shortened again to keep the overall hub size to a minimum length. Finally, the propeller's weight and its volume are calculated from the solid geometry as additional information for the user.

Fig.8: Final solid geometry, also showing the extended hub for generating a valid intersection

8. Application

8.1 Converting a CAESES project into a webApp

The process of converting a CAESES project into a browser-based webApp is based on a set of XML-files. These files contain the information for the web-browser, defining the front-end layout and the inputs.

A snippet of the XML file for the Wageningen webApp is given in Fig.9. The relevant propeller data can be specified along with their (acceptable) ranges and value types. Typical input types are float numbers with lower and upper bounds, integer numbers such as the number of blades and string enumerations to define the material. For each new page in the webApp, a separate XML file is required. Fig.10 shows the view corresponding to the XML snippet given in Fig.9. In addition, for the Wageningen webApp there are XML tags which define buttons for downloading the geometry.

Basically, the user can define any CAESES command to be triggered when a button is clicked in the front-end. In the case of a download of either an STL- or a STEP-file, a CAESES export command is triggered remotely for the final propeller geometry object, Fig.11.

The XML files are simple to understand and can be created manually by using any ASCII text editor so that a high level of customization is possible. Alternatively, a user can directly save a project set-up by clicking on a button in the CAESES GUI. This automatically generates an XML file that is ready to be displayed as a webApp, Figs.12 and 13.

```

<div id='ship' class='content-container'>
  <h3>Ship and Environment</h3>
  <fs-input type='double' object='00_INPUT|VS' label="VS" unit='kn' >setDesignVariableValue</fs-input>
  <fs-input type='double' object='00_INPUT|W' label="Wake Number" >setDesignVariableValue</fs-input>
  <fs-input type='double' object='00_INPUT|RHO' label="Water Density" unit='kg/m^3'>setDesignVariableValue</fs-input>
</div>

```

Fig.9: Snippet of the XML file for the first page of the webApp

Fig.10: webApp view of the XML file

Fig.11: Buttons can be defined in the XML file to download the final solid propeller geometry

Fig.12: Saving a project setup as an XML for direct usage as a webApp

Fig.13: Browser view in which bounds of free variables are (automatically) converted to sliders

8.2 Docker technology

CAESES includes a web-server implementation which reads the corresponding XML files. The CAESES application and project files are packed as Docker images and uploaded to a private Docker registry, <https://www.docker.com>. Multiple servers represent a Docker Swarm which load-balances the CAESES requests. A proxy server implementation distributes all CAESES sessions to the Docker Swarm. As soon as a webApp is started a user session is launched within which a CAESES instance is being run in batch-mode on a (remote) server (here hosted by FRIENDSHIP SYSTEMS). Each user session is encapsulated in a secure environment so as to ensure confidentiality. The communication between the end user's web-browser, e.g. Firefox, Chrome, and the CAESES container instance uses AJAX, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ajax_\(programming\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ajax_(programming)), called to exchange values and other data such as geometry. The browser front-end is fully responsive and handles requests from various devices such as mobile phones, tablets and workstations.

9. Results and comparison of designs

A first design was made for a gasoline engine of 132 kW at 4800 rpm with a direct shaft line as introduced in section 4. Due to the very high number of revolutions a fairly small propeller diameter is needed. Therefore, a diameter of 254 mm (10 inches) was assumed for the three-bladed propeller, matching the 4800 rpm. It can be quickly seen from running the webApp that the limitations imposed by the propeller parameters of the B-series, especially the limiting blade area ratio (EAR) of max. 105 %, make it practically impossible to generate a suitable B-series design whose cavitation performance at full power would not be critical. Even a custom design, undertaken in parallel, featuring the same small diameter of 254 mm, would result in a very high expanded area ratio above 120 % and would still show heavy cavitation at full power. The webApp therefore serves to investigate if a gearbox is needed or recommended. Subsequently, a second design was undertaken for which a gearbox was introduced to reduce the shaft speed and, hence, cavitation. With a ratio of 1:1.65 the revolutions at top speed are lowered from 4800 rpm to 2909 rpm. This allows to employ a substantially larger propeller with a diameter of 340 mm. Setting the expanded area ratio to 105 % (i.e., to the maximum), a B-series propeller can be generated successfully with the Wageningen webApp as shown in Figs.14 to 16. Fig.17 shows a screen-shot of the underlying CAESES instance. Again, a custom design was made for comparison. The B-series propeller design having the disadvantage of relatively thick blades, the state-of-the-art custom propeller with much thinner blades, as elaborated in section 6, performs quite a bit better. Both designs are shown in Fig.18 while the most important results are summarized in Table I. The custom propeller is somewhat smaller and more compact.

Fig.14: First page of the Wageningen webApp, allowing input for the design task

Fig.15: Second page of the Wageningen webApp, featuring computed results and geometry

Fig.16: Third page of the Wageningen webApp, featuring tessellated geometry

Fig.17: Propeller setup in the graphical user interface of CAESES, corresponding to the first page of the Wageningen webApp

(A) webApp propeller

(B) Custom design

Fig.18: Views of Wageningen B-series propeller and of custom design

Table I: Comparison of resulting designs

	Wageningen B-series propeller from Wageningen webApp	Custom design by expert
Design id	(A)	(B)
Diameter D	0.340 m	
Gear ratio i	1.65 (reduction)	
Values at cruising speed of 18 kn		
rpm of shaft (engine)	1834 (3026) (from vortex-lattice)	1810 (2987) (from vortex-lattice)
Power consumption	45.5 kW	43.6 kW
Open water efficiency η_0	0.647 (from vortex-lattice)	0.674 (from vortex-lattice)
Values at top speed		
rpm of shaft (engine)	2909 (4800)	2909 (4800)
Power consumption	132 kW	
Open water efficiency η_0	0.691 (from vortex-lattice) 0.739 (from webApp)	0.753 (from vortex-lattice)
V_s attained	31.8 kn (from vortex-lattice) 32.4 kn (from webApp)	33.0 kn (from vortex-lattice)

For a fair comparison both the B-series propeller from the webApp and the custom design were (re)computed by means of the same vortex-lattice code. The performance computed from the vortex-lattice code lies a little lower than what the Wageningen polynomials used within the webApp predict, Table I. The custom design gives better efficiency, yielding higher top speed and less power consumption at cruising speed.

10. Usage and perspectives of webApps

10.1 Typical use cases

The target groups of the Wageningen webApp as presented are the following:

- CFD specialists that need a high-resolution stock propeller for self-propulsion analysis,
- Naval architects that know the input data for their design (diameter, revolutions per minute etc.) but do not have the background knowledge for generating the geometry,
- Quick double-check and/or estimate for the expert,
- People that want to replace a propeller that was damaged and for which dimensions are known (naturally, the propeller to be replaced must be sufficiently close to a B-series design),
- Hobbyists that would like to have a reasonable propeller for their project (water-bikes, foils etc.) and that would not have the financial means to engage an expert,
- Students that would like to get an appreciation of propeller geometry and design.

In general, there are different types of users and providers that can benefit from the application of tools. In general, a wider group of beneficiaries are consultants that have expert knowledge and/or tools for specific applications for which they see a certain market that is, however, difficult to access. These people and/or organizations can utilize the CAESES application environment to complement their approach of marketing and dissemination. Potential providers of (paid) webApps therefore are

- Universities that have developed very specialized tools and/or skills,
- Companies that would like to streamline applications for internal usage,
- Companies that want to convert in-house tools to externally available solutions,
- Consultants that wish to scale up their expert knowledge to a wider market.

10.2 Further webApps

In addition to the propeller webApp discussed here several additional webApps are hosted at <https://www.friendship-systems.com/products/web-apps/>, one of which being a webApp for the geometric modeling of the power boat as considered in the design task presented.

An example webApp with a flow code wrapped within CAESES and made accessible via a web-browser can be found at www.HOLISHIP.eu/approach. It stems from the European research and development project HOLISHIP that addresses the holistic design and optimization of maritime assets *Harries et al. (2017)*. In this webApp the potential flow code v-Shallo by HSV A is coupled to a parametric hull model of a generic RoPAX ferry realized within CAESES. The main purpose is to illustrate that targeted applications, even though far from being trivial, can be made available to a wider community. For the sake of steering the imagination a series of screen-shots made on a smart phone is given in Fig.18.

(A) Defining geometry (B) Launching the simulation
 (C) Viewing the free surface (D) Viewing the pressure distribution

Fig.18: webApp for modeling and numerical simulation of a RoPAX ferry

11. Conclusions

Offering engineering services via the web is a novel and promising way to “democratize” design tasks and work flows. The Computer Aided Engineering system CAESES has been extended to support web-based applications (webApps). An elaborated webApp for the design and geometric modeling of propellers, the so-called Wageningen webApp, has been presented to illustrate ideas, the underlying technology and potential. An example propeller design was shown for a fast power boat. The webApp is fast and easy to use. Naturally, it cannot be expected that an app yields the same level of quality as a custom design as has been shown. Nevertheless, the propeller webApp hopefully serves as an invitation to think of what could be offered in the future, possibly to increase markets, benefits and use cases for engineering services that span from simple utilities to complex and sophisticated offers.

The webApp discussed can be accessed via <https://www.wageningen-b-series-propeller.com>

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References

- ABT, C.; HARRIES, S. (2016), *Pushing processes and performance by parametric design of boats and yachts*, 24th Int. HISWA Symp. Yacht Design and Yacht Construction, Amsterdam
- ALBERT, S.; HARRIES, S.; HILDEBRANDT, T.; REYER, M. (2016), *Hydrodynamic Optimization of a Power Boat in the Cloud*, High-Performance Marine Vehicles (HIPER 2016), Cortona
- BRESLIN, J.P.; ANDERSEN, P. (1996), *Hydrodynamics of Ship Propellers*, Cambridge Univ. Press
- BURRILL, L.C.; EMERSON, A. (1962-63), *Propeller cavitation: Further tests on 16in. propeller models in the King's College cavitation tunnel*, Transactions of the North East Coast Institution of Engineers and Shipbuilders 79
- HARRIES, S. (2014), *Practical shape optimization using CFD*, Whitepaper, <https://www.friendship-systems.com/company/papers>

HARRIES; S., (2017), *Living in the Cloud – How Web-Based Apps will make High-Tech more Accessible*, The Naval Architect Magazine, September, pp.64-68

HARRIES, S.; ABT, C.; BRENNER, M. (2015a), *Upfront CAD – Parametric modeling techniques for shape optimization*, Int. Conf. Evolutionary and Deterministic Methods for Design, Optimization and Control with Applications to Industrial and Societal Problems (EUROGEN), Glasgow

HARRIES, S.; CAU, C.; MARZI, J.; KRAUS, A.; PAPANIKOLAOU, A.; ZARAPHONITIS, G. (2017), *Software Platform for the Holistic Design and Optimisation of Ships*, Jahrbuch der Schiffbau-technischen Gesellschaft

HARRIES, S.; KÄTHER, B.L. (1997), *Rechnererzeugte Propellergeometrien – Computer Aided Geometric Modeling of Propellers*, Jahrbuch der Schiffbautechnischen Gesellschaft

HARRIES, D.; MacPHERSON, D.; EDMONDS, A. (2015b), *Speed-power optimized AUV design by coupling CAESES and NavCad*, 14th Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Ulrichshusen

ISO 4566:1992, *Small craft with inboard engine – Propeller shaft ends and bosses with 1:10 taper*, German version EN ISO 4566:1995

KELLER, J. AUF’M (1966), *Enige aspecten bij het ontwerpen van scheepschroeven*, Schip en Werf, No.24

OOSTERVELD, M.W.C.; OOSSANEN, P. VAN (1975), *Further Computer-Analyzed Data of The Wageningen B-Screw Series*, NSMB Publication No.479, reprinted from International Shipbuilding Progress, Vol.22 No.251

Vessel-in-the-Loop Architecture for Testing Highly Automated Maritime Systems

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Abstract

This paper describes a concept to integrate a real vessel as a test platform into a simulative maritime testbed to decrease the gap between simulation and field tests. This supports the front-loading of verification and validation by providing a Vessel-in-the-Loop platform to support the system engineering and scenario-based testing. A typical use case is the test of a prototypical collision avoidance system of an autonomous vessel in a realistic environment. Therefore, a Vessel-in-the-Loop platform efficiently provides the test environment including virtual ships to simulate a sea traffic scenario such as a damaged container carrier with losing containers. The Vessel-in-the-Loop environment provides verification and validation tools a platform to examine the behaviour of the collision avoidance system under nearly real-world conditions. Herewith we highlight the challenges of the simulative and physical integration, provide a concept for the Vessel-in-the-Loop architecture and implement it in the test environment eMIR.

1. Introduction

Modern technologies for highly automated guidance, navigation and control of a vessel result in high challenges for the verification and validation (V+V) due to system complexity, functional reliability, safety and security. These challenges are increased by open system of systems and resulting changing system networks as well as the integration of intelligent systems to realise the needed functionality. The complexity of these highly automated systems means that an isolated test as currently established by regulation and norms (e.g. MSC.252(83)/IEC 61924-2 for Integrated Navigation Systems) is no longer sufficient for V+V. Many system errors are only recognisable as part of the overall system test in a physical scenario, *Damm & Heidl (2018)*. Therefore, new systems engineering methods are needed. For example, a scenario-based approach for V+V of highly automated systems has been established based on projects such as PEGASUS, *Winner et al. (2018)*, and ENABLE-S3, *Nickovic et al. (2017)*. Simulative test methods such as the X-in-the-Loop approach for the front-loading of V+V is widely used in the automotive, maritime and other domains. The behaviour of control units can be tested in a simulated scenario without the expensive real-world infrastructure. Nevertheless, a gap between simulative and real-world testing remains, *Fischer et al. (2016)*.

To conduct these V&V-methods in the maritime systems engineering, test environments such as eMIR are used as test platforms. Parts of the eMIR test environment are the virtual testbed HAGGIS and the physical testbed LABSKAUS. These testbeds are used to collect data (empirical study, constraint and assumption identification) for static V&V or as a real-world environment for dynamic testing of realized modules/components/systems, such as a collision avoidance system. Testbed components such as ships can be virtually or physically represented. For instance, a test scenario with the movement of virtual ships can be programmed by a scenario definition component in a virtual maritime traffic simulator. The real physical ship (the prototype of a new ship model or as a test platform for new operational procedures) can be implemented into this scenario to provoke ship collision scenarios with real-world sensor data, *Bock et al. (2007)*.

To physically perform the test scenarios specified by consecutive test steps which lead to a desirable system, a Vessel-in-the-Loop environment can be used, *Albers and Düser (2010)*. For this, a vessel as a test platform must be put in these specified situations and create the environmental conditions as near as to reality as possible. There will always be difference between the testing under virtual and real-world conditions because of the hard to reconstruct environmental surroundings and the

approximation of dynamic models. To minimise these effects, a virtual and physical testbed can be integrated used to enrich the real-world scenario with simulative data, e. g. for a complex collision avoidance scenario, *Fischer et al. (2016)*. This paper presents a Vessel-in-the-Loop architecture, which considers existing virtual and physical environments. We describe a way to integrate a real ship as a test platform into a test environment containing a virtual and physical testbed. This test platform is supposed to be steered by an external remote position and requires the ability to give sensor feedback of the remote position such as visual camera, environmental influences or ship dynamic to enable controlled test operations. For this, a communication infrastructure is designed and implemented to ensure the transmission of control commands and the sensor feedback between the simulative and physical testbed as well as the system under test. A case study for testing trajectory tracking and collision avoidance controller demonstrates the importance of developing this hybrid testbed to provide virtual collision scenarios.

2. Open-Loop and Closed-Loop Testing Methods

As part of the testing process, components and/or systems are executed and tested in the control loop. For early testing, the system under test is integrated via its interfaces into a simulated testbed for providing the test execution environment and test stimuli in an efficient way. The various methods differ in that the system under test and components of the control loop can each be real or simulated. While at first all elements of the system under test and the test environment are simulated, the replacement of simulated components with real ones occurs successively. This loop-testing is well established in the development of embedded systems, for example for automated vehicles or ships. For testing, carefully designed test environments to realise each control loop method are used, *Klee and Allen (2011)*.

Fig.1 illustrates the distinction between open-loop and closed-loop testing methods. In the open-loop test, a physical testbed must send stimulating signal vectors directly to a system under test and receive its output to evaluate it according to the test reference, e. g. for testing an Automatic Radar Plotting Aids (ARPA) for assistance. In contrast, a closed-loop test uses a simulation model of the control loop, which might additionally be complemented by real components of a physical testbed, e. g. for testing a collision avoidance component for a highly automated Integrated Navigation System (INS). The simulation model receives the output signal of the system under test by a feedback loop and reacts in a suitable way according to the specified test scenario, *Baumann (2006)*.

Fig.1: Open-loop and closed-loop testing methods after *Baumann (2006)*

Testing takes place at various stages of the development process through dynamic testing in the loop, such as Model in the Loop (MiL), Software in the Loop (SiL), Hardware in the Loop (HiL), and finally a real-world test of the entire system in a physical testbed, *Jost et al. (2010)*. Following the loop testing methods illustrated in Fig.2, dynamic testing of the system under test in a seamless simulated and physical environment is performed at each development stage. Testing already very early implementations reduces high development costs following the approach of front-loading of V+V, *Schäuffele and Zurawka (2010)*. Fig.2 shows the procedure described for dynamic testing along the development process exemplified for the development of an autopilot for a vessel. The first prototype is a functional model, which is executed by MATLAB Simulink and tested with the help of a simulated environment. Once the specification has been defined, the functional model is translated

into a specific programming language and the implemented software is also tested through a simulated environment. The next step installs the implementation of the software into the target hardware and finally, a real-world test of the entire system in a physical testbed is made, for example on a ship as a test platform, *Fischer et al. (2016)*.

Fig.2: Seamless testing in the loop by using virtual and physical test environments

As the development phase progresses, the simulative components of a virtual testbed are successively replaced by physical ones. There is a hard break between the conventional HiL and a real-world test. To fill the gap between simulative testing and the testing in a real-world environment, a ViL platform can be used, *Fischer et al. (2016)*. By using a HiL oriented-method, a vessel as a test platform can become part of mixed virtual and physical maritime testbed. This ViL test method enables the testing of highly automated maritime systems for navigating and steering directly on the test platform. The test carrier does not necessarily move in real traffic but in a reference waterway. The reference waterway provides observation equipment and infrastructure for controlling the environment, such as virtual represented ships to complement the real-world scenario.

3. Vessel-in-the-Loop Architecture

The functional requirements of the target system for a ViL architecture testbed derive from the architecture for Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) of a vessel that can be found in detail in *Brinkmann et al. (2017)* which is adapted from *Fossen (2011)*. Fig.3 illustrates the elements and dataflows that need to be considered when designing the ViL platform. The components of the system under test on the left side of the figure represent the functionality of the highly automated system. Depending on the test, these elements are either instantiated by the system under test itself or provided by the testbed. The test platform must perceive various environmental and own state data through sensors and provide it to the simulative environment as well as the system under test, as illustrated in Fig.3.

On the uppermost layer, there is a route element, which performs the task of strategic navigation by finding and modifying routes. The basis for this is the available maritime infrastructure with its services such as an Electronic Navigational Chart (ENC) or a route optimisation service. Going down to the middle layer, there is a traffic layer which requires data about the navigational space, as it is influenced by environmental conditions and vehicles/obstacles in vicinity (e.g. from an Automatic Identification System (AIS) or radar tracks). The traffic component monitors on a tactical level the process of path following (or trajectory tracking) according to the strategically chosen route and can apply local path modifications. Therefore, this is done on a discrete-time short horizon. For this purpose, the guidance component determines intervals of the safe references in the form of trajectories or waypoints and speeds which are passed to as an input to the control component in order to take necessary action to react to the current navigational space. The lowest layer is the control layer that determine the necessary forces and moments to the actuator of the vessel based on the reference

data, provided by the guidance layer, and the hydrodynamic surface environment, provided by the sensor onboard of the vessel such as GPS, IMU, and Engine Control Unit (ECU).

Fig.3: Elements for testing highly automated and autonomous vessels

4. Vehicle-in-the-Loop Platform

The IALA registered test platform eMIR combines a virtual and physical maritime testbed to support the scenario-based V+V of highly automated systems. The testbed LABSKAUS is the physical part of eMIR and located in the German Bight. Moreover, some components are transportable and can be located everywhere. LABSKAUS covers ship and shore side components and aims to build a basis for testing different functional layers of automation of a vessel according to the requirements described in section 2 and 3. LABSKAUS can be used for empirical study of maritime automation systems, seamless support of the system development and demonstration of existing systems. A detailed description of the physical testbed architecture can be found under *Brinkmann et al. (2017)*. The components presented in this section serve as a basis for the realisation of the ViL platform. In the following paragraphs, all relevant components which need to be considered for the ViL platform will be described.

4.1 Reference Waterway

The Reference Waterway of LABSKAUS covers the high-frequency maritime route of the Elbe estuary around Brunsbüttel and Cuxhaven as well as the Jade in Germany. It covers a basic maritime surveillance infrastructure (including AIS, Radar, cameras, wind) and broad band communication via LTE. Additionally, two AIS receivers are connected to two antennas on top of a building of the Jade University of Applied Sciences in Wilhelmshaven, Germany. Under good conditions they can cover Wilhelmshaven, Bremerhaven till Cuxhaven and the East Frisian Isles till Helgoland to enhance the Reference Waterway. The main objective of the Reference Waterway is to provide a completely sensor-covered area. This area is monitored, and the communication technology allows the data

exchange between the components of the testbed and surveillance technology for data gathering. The Reference Waterway is used as an experimental platform and for demonstration of modern technologies by offering an observable area for prototype evaluation. The Reference Waterway can be individually expanded with autarkic stations.

4.2 Communication Infrastructure

LABSKAUS is designed under the paradigm of loose coupling and realised using a message-oriented middleware and a publish-subscribe pattern. This results in a communication infrastructure that decouples all components of the geographically distributed system in time, space and synchronisation. The configuration capability of the middleware allows subdivision of communication channels into subnetworks, e. g. for the logical separation of parallel experiments. A message broker observes the data channels of clients (publisher), redirects data and chooses which consuming client (subscriber) can access it, as illustrated in Fig.4. The communication of ship automation technology is driven by microcontrollers and devices which communicate by using a message-based protocol, such as CAN or NMEA. Therefore, the publish-subscribe pattern is suitable as an event- or message-driven middleware variant. The use of a central message-oriented middleware enables the observability by appropriately subscribing to the central middleware, such as the Test & V+V Management. A subscriber (e.g. a system under test or test observation system) declares information of interest, which the subscriber, and in parallel, all other interested parties, receive when the data has been published.

Fig.4: Distributed software architecture of the message passing middleware

The semantic and structural content of the data objects is flexible because of the message-oriented middleware does not interpret the content of transferred data messages. All system nodes take the function of transmitting the data in accordance with the common data model in S-100 format according to *IHO (2017)* via the central message-oriented middleware. This is done as illustrated in Fig.5 by using the common data model as a conceptual model and corresponding local usage in an implementation by the respective system node, e. g. in C++ or Java. Changing the data formats in the testbed thus does not pose a challenge to the communication infrastructure, *Schill & Springer (2012)*. For this purpose, components that use the testbed infrastructure require the functions shown in Fig.5. First, the transformation of the generated data of a data source into the common S-100 data model takes place. Based on the S-100 data model, S-100 data objects are generated including the corresponding S-100 classifiers which represent unique identifiers and the references to a set of features. These assigned features are for example a sensor datum of an AIS. In this context, the serialisation of an S-100 compliant data object occurs to be published and transmitted via the message-oriented middleware. Serialisation refers to translating data structures and objects into a sequential format to increase the performance of data transfer in a distributed system, such as the highly automated ship. Analogous to this operator process, there is firstly a subscriber which selects and receives one or more desired information via the message-oriented middleware. Then the deserialisation function corresponding to the serialisation function deserializes the transmitted data object and transforms them from S-100 into the respective target format. This communication infrastructure has significance for the integration of a virtual testbed, which will be explained in more detail in the following sections.

Fig.5: Publish and subscribe of S-100 data objects by using the testbed communication infrastructure

4.3 Data distributor

The Navibox is a compact sensor data hub which provides navigational data on board as well as data for maritime surveillance systems. It provides LAN, WLAN and broadband WAN communication facilities. The minimum setup consists of a radar, an AIS antenna and a wind sensor. All sensors which are sending data appropriate to the communication standard NMEA0183 or NMEA2000 and Ethernet can be attached. The Radar Tracking Software from Cambridge Pixels identifies radar tracks and processes radar video. The AIS receiver collects all AIS messages from the AIS transceiver equipped systems in a 35-100 km radius dependent on the antenna height. The AIS messages include static, dynamic and journey vessel information. A wind sensor can gather wind speed as well as angle and is connected to the NMEA2000 bus. An Industrial PC (IPC) takes over the sensor stream management and processing. It houses a message passing broker of the information distribution to the service bus implemented as RabbitMQ based on the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP). In Fig.6, the data connections are shown. The Navibox SW gathers and handles all sensor data. A Navibox is configured to be remotely controlled via network (LTE).

Fig.6: Data connections in the Navibox

The approach has been enhanced so that the software system of the Navibox can be remotely controlled to enable the execution of different scenarios. Commands received by the message-oriented middleware control the data stream within the Navibox software (SW) and allow changing the semantics, quality and quantity of the sensor data. E. g. the wind sensor will send the actual value only every minute instead of every 100ms or it will send the average and/or maximum value of a defined period. Configuring the sensor output for different scenarios will reduce the workload of the network link and the overhead of implementing additional software at the receiver side to adapt the data for the requested input.

The stationary variant of the Navibox has a sturdy pole to carry the sensor head. Two of the stationary Naviboxes are implemented in the reference waterway located at the roof of buildings that are near to the coast. The setup in Cuxhaven is additionally equipped with optical surveillance technologies to

track objects and observe water current/surface behaviour. A plan exists to attach an echo sounder to track movements and ship dynamics under water in the future. An energy autarkic version of the Navibox station is added to run tests on any coast location.

To collect data of a test platform vessel there is the mobile Navibox. It adds a JRC JRL-21 Differential GPS (DGPS) System that can not only add the position, course over ground and speed over ground, but also the true heading and rate of turn to replace a compass. A chart and multifunctional display allows monitoring sensor data on board. The sensor pole will be attached to a vessel and gathers sensor data independent of the ship navigation electronics. Every Navibox is easily extendable for future needs of various sensors.

4.4 Test platform Vessel

On seaside, the testbed includes the vessel ZUSE which got modified to act as a highly adaptable vehicle for validation and verification of automated and autonomous technology, e.g. trajectory controller or situational awareness systems. The test platform vessel is fit for high-sea and fully equipped with sensors and actuator control interfaces for the rudder and the engine. A dSPACE MicroAutobox Embedded PC is used as an interface between the sensor box and the vessel components via its I/O modules. A steering hydraulic pump is installed in parallel to the hydraulic steering wheel to be able to steer the vessel electronically with the aid of a motor driver driven by pulse width modulation (PWM). The ECU of the engine is adapted to take analogue signals from the dSPACE MicroAutobox. To better classify and structure the large number of ship sensors in the context of shipping, a classification into movement sensors, environmental sensors and internal ship sensors takes place. This classification should cover all relevant marine sensors.

- **Movement Sensors:**
 - Positioning: Compass, Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS);
 - Speed and Acceleration: DGPS, Log; Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU)
- **Environmental Sensors:**
 - Above water: Radar, Lidar, video camera.
 - Under water: Echolot, Microphones (acoustic analysis)
- **Internal Ship Sensors:** ECU for engine information, rudder angle indicator

4.6 Simulation Platform

The co-simulation platform HAGGIS (Hybrid Architecture for Granularly, Generic and Interoperable Simulations) supports the verification of safety and efficiency of maritime transport systems. In this context, HAGGIS provides infrastructure for the integration of individual simulators, simulation control components, observers and analysis components. As illustrated in Fig.7, HAGGIS can be subdivided into a modelling, a simulation and an analysis part.

The simulation platform provides a world editor that provides a system model to allow setting up a static scene containing fundamental components / entities of all used resources, actors and environmental factors. The maritime traffic simulator (MTS) implements, executes and observes the behaviour of multiple vessels in a realistic scenario. For this, various functions are provided such as for modelling and importing routes for vessel traffic and coupling with sea charts and environmental simulations. An environmental simulation complements the overall simulation platform by providing maritime environmental factors like wind, current and tide. A sensor simulation is used to generate realistic sensor measurements from a simulated context, e. g. the context of the maritime traffic simulation. To provide realistic sensor data the generated measurements can be extended by statistical, systematic or context-sensitive fault and accuracy models. Using this capability, the sensor simulation takes an important role as the bridge between the virtual environment of HAGGIS and the physical test bed LABSKAUS.

The underlying interoperability layer complements the architecture by providing a S-100 data model and a communication infrastructure based on the High-Level Architecture (HLA) as a communication middleware specified as an international standard under the name IEEE 1516. These aspects are of special importance due to the need to connect the simulation platform to the physical communication infrastructure of LABSKAUS.

Fig.7: Overall architecture of the HAGGIS simulation platform

5. Control of the Test Platform Vessel

In order to use the test platform as vessel in the loop, different control layers must be provided on board according to the algorithm that is tested. These layers go from the engine layer up to the higher level of trajectory tracking and path planning. The control layers that should be implemented is on the vessel and its prerequisite components are summarized below.

Remark: The following components might or might not be used during the process of validation and verification according to the requirement of the system under test. This will be clarified in our use case.

- **Modelling of surface vessels:** Obtaining a suitable dynamic model for the vessel is necessary for the motion control algorithms. The surface vessel model has 6-DOF: surge, sway, heave (x, y, z) which represent the position of the vessel in the three-dimensional space, and roll, pitch, and yaw (ϕ, θ, ψ) which represent the orientation of the vessel. Assuming that the heave, roll, and pitch modes induced by wind and currents are negligible, the dynamic can be represented in 3-DOF for the purpose of the maneuvering, the scope of our testbed. The states of the vessel can then be taken as $\boldsymbol{\eta} = [x, y, \psi]^T \in R^3$ and $\boldsymbol{v} = [u, v, r]^T \in R^3$ where (x, y) is the cartesian position, ψ is the heading (yaw) angle, (u, v) are the body-fixed linear velocities (surge and sway), and r is the yaw rate. It is usually represented in the state space form as follow *Breivik and Fossen (2004)*:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{x}} = f(\boldsymbol{x}) + g\boldsymbol{\tau} + g_w(\boldsymbol{x})\boldsymbol{w}_l(t) + \boldsymbol{w}_h(t)$$

where \boldsymbol{x} is the states of the system, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the actuator forces and moment, \boldsymbol{w}_l and $\boldsymbol{w}_h(t)$ are the low frequency and high frequency components of the disturbances. The parameters of the functions f , g , and g_w are estimated using parameter estimation techniques.

- **Actuator Controller:** Our first step for controlling the test vessel is to be able to accept reference commands for both the rudder angle and the engine speed in RPM. This is achieved using two proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller that accept reference rudder (δ_{ref}) and RPM (n_{ref}) and provide the necessary manipulated signal. The PID has three parameters which are tuned experimentally on-board. The manipulated signal of the rudder is a pulse width

Fig.8: Rudder and Engine Control Block Diagram

modulation sent to a hydraulic motor pump connected in parallel to the steering wheel, and the manipulated signal of the RPM is an analog voltage sent to the ECU. A block diagram for that is shown in Fig.8. The Actuator controller has also a control allocation subcomponent that transform forces and moments to appropriate rudder and engine speed values.

- **Motion Controller:** The next step is to have a motion control algorithm that has different configurable objectives based on the system under test. This motion controller is preconfigured before starting the test. It is the component that determines the necessary forces and moments to be provided by the vessel in order to achieve the control objective. There are many control objectives that have been studied in the literature, *Fossen (2011)*.
 - **Setpoint regulation:** It is a special control objective where the setpoint is constant. The application of this could be dynamic positioning (DP) where the objective is to steer the vessel slowly to the desired position and heading and then maintain them by counteracting environmental forces.
 - **Path following:** The test vessel should follow a predefined path independent of time which means that no restrictions are placed on the temporal propagation along the path. For this technique Line Of Sight (LOS) PID is employed.
 - **Trajectory tracking:** The control objective is to steer the system output $\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ to track a time varying reference $\mathbf{y}_d(t)$ that is usually generated by a reference model, USV dynamic model, or an optimization technique. In this case time propagation is talking into consideration which is necessary in collision avoidance. One popular technique is Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC), *Abdelaal et al. (2016)* where a nonlinear optimization problem is formulated to minimize the deviation of the vessel states from a time varying reference generated over a finite horizon by a virtual vessel.
- **Last-line of Defence Collision avoidance.**

The test carrier vessel can be used to test different algorithms ranging from simple autopilot to advanced controllers and collision avoidance algorithms. This might put the vessel into a collision risk with nearby encountered vessels which motivates the idea of providing an accurate collision avoidance technique. Unlike collision avoidance techniques, which treats the problem as a controller independent path planning problem and feed the input as a setpoint to the controller, *Wang et al. (2015)*, last line of defence can either work independently, or be integrated into the controller and combined with trajectory tracking or path following. Due to the ability of NMPC to handle input and state constraints over a selected future horizon, collision avoidance is formulated as nonlinear time varying state constraint for its optimization problem. By defining the vessel ship domain as the area around the ship that should be free from other ships and obstacles and by choosing either circular or elliptical geometry, the collision avoidance constraint can be formulated as in *Abdelaal et al. (2016)*.
- **Route Planning**

The route planning component is an essential geo-related decision support tool, especially in

intelligent transportation systems (ITS). It is responsible for generating the route of the ship, defined by a sequence of waypoints, for the whole mission or trip and usually is executed once by the operator of the test carrier ship. Each waypoint is defined using Cartesian coordinates (x_k, y_k) for $k = 1, \dots, n$. The waypoint database therefore consists of:

$$\text{wpt. pos} = \{(x_0, y_0), (x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$$

Additionally, other waypoint properties such as speed and heading can be defined, that is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{wpt. speed} &= \{U_0, U_1, \dots, U_n\} \\ \text{wpt. heading} &= \{\psi_0, \psi_1, \dots, \psi_n\} \end{aligned}$$

This component must take into consideration different factors, *Liu and Bucknall (2015)*:

Obstacles: for example land, islands, shallow areas, reefs and water depth restricted areas. These information is taken from a Geographic Information System (GIS).

Avoidance conditions: route planning should facilitate the collision avoidance task by avoiding narrow waters that restrict maneuverability. This is very crucial for the last line of defense described later.

No-sail zones: man-made obstacle areas designated due to set national policy or political factors.

Designated navigation zones: zones that need to be navigated through to satisfy navigational safety, for example, traffic separation schemes.

Path smoothness: the planned route line should be smooth, and avoid excessive turning points and overly large steering angles.

Mileage: This component should select the route with minimum distance which corresponds to minimum fuel to fulfil economy requirements.

One of the most effective algorithms used for this problem is the grid map-based algorithms presented as the problem of finding the shortest path between any two nodes, and then extended to A* algorithm, *Hart et al. (1968)*. The best algorithm used for route generation problem is Theta*, which is considered as more sophisticated variant of A*, *Kim et al. (2014)*.

6. Integration of the Test platform into the Simulation Loop

In complement to open-loop-manoevres in the reference waterway, with the vessel-in-the-loop approach it is possible to realise closed-loop-manoevres by integrating the real vessel with the virtual testbed. Fig.9 illustrates the integrated simulation platform and physical testbed infrastructure. The test platform vessel in the reference waterway is supposed to be steered by an external remote position provided by the simulation platform and requires the ability to give sensor feedback of the physical position, such as visual camera, environmental influences or ship dynamics to enable controlled test operations. The data of the test platform is provided by the NMEA2000 bus data acquisition of the Navibox as described in section 4. The Navibox transforms it from the propriety protocols in S-100 and sends the transformed data objects over the message-oriented middleware. The integrated communication infrastructure of the virtual and physical testbed ensures the transmission of control commands and the sensor feedback between the simulative and physical infrastructure. To achieve the data sharing between both virtual and physical environment, a simulation adapter combines the HLA and message-oriented middleware with publish-subscribe mechanism as illustrated in Fig.9. The simulation adapter fulfils the bilateral data exchange between the infrastructure of the physical testbed and the simulators of the virtual testbed. For this, some interoperability mechanisms on different interoperability layers must be considered: Communication protocol, data syntax and semantics. By using a common S-100 data model both on the virtual and physical testbed supports the interoperability.

Nevertheless, the co-simulation must provide a possibility to utilize the inherent models of the virtual testbed by using an API. This API must be able to react to inputs and give outputs according to the defined scenario and the physical situation. For example, the Functional Mock-Up Interface (FMI) is

a widely-agreed tool-independent standard for model exchange by describing the interface of simulators in XML and functionality in C, *Awais et al. (2013)*, [https://svn.modelica.org/fmi/branches/public/specifications/v2.0/FMI for ModelExchange and CoSimulation v2.0.pdf](https://svn.modelica.org/fmi/branches/public/specifications/v2.0/FMI%20for%20ModelExchange%20and%20CoSimulation%20v2.0.pdf).

Fig.9: Integrated system architecture of the virtual and physical testbed

All variables of the simulation model are described in XML by following a XSD schema defined by the FMI Description Schema. For the model execution there is an API in executable DLL files or C source code, *FMI Development Group (2014)*. FMI is just a representative solution to demonstrate the need for an API for the simulators. The ability to combine HLA and FMI to achieve the interoperability of model execution were already shown in various publications. Despite a few divergent requirements, the ViL platform of eMIR follows a similar approach, which is presented below. As Fig.10 illustrates, the virtual testbed HAGGIS provides S-100 data objects in XML over UDP containing all the information which are accessible in the simulation model. The physical testbed uses RabbitMQ as message-oriented middleware with publish-subscribe mechanism that is based on AMQP. The simulation adapter handles these different communication protocols by operations like message splitting, queuing, merging, etc. and realises a consistent integrated virtual and physical environment. Furthermore, the data relevant to the physical testbed must be filtered as a subset of the full S-100 data object sent by the virtual testbed, such as AIS, radar, etc. For this, the semantic handler provides the ability for a user to choose relevant data and send it to the message-oriented middleware by publishing it to the central message passing bus. This process is also possible in reverse order, so that the real-world scenario can also be represented in the simulated environment. This provides the ability to implement closed-loop tests for systems under test according to a scenario specification.

Fig.10: Simulation adapter for coupling virtual und physical testbed

7. Use Case – Testing Trajectory Tracking and Collision Avoidance

A use case for using the aforementioned architecture of our integrated virtual and physical ViL testbed is presented. The testbed is used for testing a trajectory tracking controller developed by the

University of Oldenburg which is the system under test, *Abdelaal et al. (2016)*. The trajectory tracking controller is based on Nonlinear Model Predictive Controller (NMPC) scheme with controller-embedded collision avoidance technique based on elliptical ship domain representation. The system under test is deployed on a IPC with Simulink real-time kernel which is based on On-Time RTOS. The controller is exported into an efficient C code using the ACADO toolkit *Houska et al. (2011)*, and is deployed as S-function with NMEA2000 over UDP interface.

The Route Planning and Actuator Control components are part of the testbed while the motion controller and last-line-of-defence is deactivated. The Route Planning component provides the system under test with the reference trajectory to be tracked by the test platform. The actuator controller is used to allocate the appropriate rudder angles and engine speed from the control forces and moment (the output of the controller). The physical testbed provides the controllers with the position, heading angle, course angle and velocities.

To test the collision avoidance component of the controller, encountered vessels position and velocities must be provided to the system under test. Due to the difficulty of bringing real vessels into a collision scenario with the test platform vessel, the virtual testbed provides virtual vessels, that can be controlled manually or via an autopilot, according to the traffic scenario required. The physical-virtual interaction is, Fig.11: The virtual vessels are subjected to the same environmental conditions measured by the physical testbed on board the test carrier vessel, and the AIS and radar tracks are a concatenation of both real and virtual measurement.

Fig.11: Experimental setup for a collision avoidance system using maritime traffic simulation and sensor simulation (left) and the test platform vessel in the reference waterway (right)

8. Conclusion

This paper provides an architecture for a ViL platform to test systems for highly automated vessels by providing an integrated physical-virtual testbed. In this test environment, the test platform vessel is steered in real see and complemented by simulated data of a virtual testbed. This work introduces the test platform eMIR with special focus on the integration between the physical testbed LABSKAUS and the virtual testbed HAGGIS to create the ViL environment. The testbed is based on the three-layered approach for guidance, navigation, and control, and provides components such as a test platform vessel, reference waterway and simulators aiming to realize a seamless support of the V+V. The HAGGIS simulation platform is integrated into the physical testbed LABSKAUS based on a data exchange in the S-100 data format to have the capability to test the algorithms for specific traffic scenarios which are difficult and/or expensive to test in real environment. A case study of testing trajectory tracking and collision avoidance, with virtual encountered vessels, demonstrate the importance of building such an architecture for vessel in the loop.

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References

- ABDELAAL, M.; FRÄNZLE, M.; HAHN, A. (2016), *NMPC-based trajectory tracking and collision avoidance of underactuated vessels with elliptical ship domain*, IFAC CAMS, Elsevier, pp. 22–27.
- AKYILDIZ, I.F.; MELODIA, T.; CHOWDHURY, K.R. (2008), *Wireless Multimedia Sensor Networks: Applications and Testbeds*, Proc. IEEE 96/10, pp.1588-1605
- ALBERS, A.; DÜSER, T. (2010): *Implementation of a vehicle-in-the-loop development and validation platform*, FISITA World automotive congress
- AWAIS, M. U.; PALENSKY, P.; ELSHEIKH, A.; WIDL, E.; MATTHIAS, S. (2013), *The high level architecture RTI as a master to the functional mock-up interface components*, IEEE Conf., pp.315–320
- BAUMANN, G. (2006), *Was verstehen wir unter Test? Abstraktionsebenen, Begriffe und Definitionen*, AutoTest: Fachkonferenz zum Thema Test und Diagnose in der Automobilentwicklung
- BOCK, T.; MAURER, M.; FARBER, G., (2007), *Validation of the Vehicle in the Loop (VIL); A milestone for the simulation of driver assistance systems*, IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symp.
- BREIVIK, M.; FOSSEN, T. (2004), *Path following of straight lines and circles for marine surface vessels*, Proc. IFAC CAMS, pp. 65-70
- BRINKMANN, M.; HAHN, A.; ÅGE HJØLLO, B. (2017), *Physical testbed for highly automated and autonomous vessels*, 16th COMPIT, Cardiff, pp.56-69
- DAMM, W.; HEIDL, P. (2018), *Highly Automated Systems: Test, Safety, and Development Processes*, SafeTRANS Working Group
- FISCHER, M.; PLÄTTNER, J.; GROLMs, G.; DIRK, A.; LAPOEHN, S.; FRANK, K. (2016), *Virtual prototyping for highly automated vehicle function validation utilizing a vehicle-in-the-loop driving simulator facility*, Proc. DSC, Paris
- FOSSEN, T.I., (2011), *Handbook of Marine Craft Hydrodynamics and Motion Control*, Wiley & Sons
- HART, P.; NILSSON, N.; RAPHAEL, B. (1968), *A formal basis for the heuristic determination of minimum cost paths*, IEEE Trans. Systems Science and Cybernetics 4/2, pp.100-107
- HOUSKA, B.; FERREAU, H. J.; DIEHL, M. (2011), *ACADO toolkit-An open-source framework for automatic control and dynamic optimization*, Optimal Control Applications and Methods 32/3, pp. 298-312
- INTERNATIONAL HYDROGRAPHIC ORGANIZATION, (2017), *S-100 - Universal Hydrographic Data Model*, https://www.iho.int/iho_pubs/standard/S-100/S-100_Ed_3/S-100_Edition_3.0.0.pdf
- JOST, H.; HAHN, A.; HAUSLER, S.; KOHLER, S.; GACNIK, J.; KOSTER, F.; LEMMER, K. (2010), *Supporting qualification: Safety standard compliant process planning and monitoring*, IEEE Symp. Product Compliance Engineering (ISPCE), pp.1-6
- KIM, H.; KIM, D.; SHIN, J. U.; KIM, H.; MYUNG, H. (2014), *Angular rate-constrained path planning algorithm for unmanned surface vehicles*, Ocean Engineering 84/1, pp.37-44

KLEE, H.; ALLEN, R. (2011), *Simulation of dynamic systems with MATLAB and Simulink*, CRC Press

LIU, Y.; BUCKNALL, R. (2015), *Path planning algorithm for unmanned surface vehicle formations in a practical maritime environment*, *Ocean Engineering* 97/1, pp. 126-144

NICKOVIC, D.; HERZNER, W.; MÖHLMANN, E.; GERWINN, S.; GARCIA PADILLA, G.; DIEGMANN, F.; HAKKI, S.; SNOOK, C., (2017), *ENABLE-S3- D3.2.2 v1 V&V Methodology*, <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1F5UnxSzSM4n52fPbrvFCo3iTCDW4kfzU/view>

SCHILL, A.; SPRINGER, T. (2012), *Verteilte Systeme: Grundlagen und Basistechnologien*, eXamen, Springer

SCHÄUFFELE, J.; ZURAWKA, T. (2010), *Automotive Software Engineering Grundlagen, Prozesse, Methoden und Werkzeuge effizient einsetzen*, Springer

WANG, M.; LUO, J.; WALTER, U. (2015), *A non-linear model predictive controller with obstacle avoidance for a space robot*, *Advances in Space Research* 57/8, pp. 1737-1746

WINNER, H.; WACHENFELD, W.; JUNIETZ, P. (2016), *Safety Assurance for Highly Automated Driving - The PEGASUS Approach*, *Automated Vehicle Symp.*, San Francisco

Capturing As-Built Building Progress Data for Efficient Control of Outfitting Processes in Shipbuilding

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Abstract

This paper describes an approach for capturing the current state and progress of construction in a ships outfitting process. Instead of expensive laser scanners, mobile devices like smartphones are used. The collected data is the basis to create point clouds and 3D models, which can be made available to the different service providers. The representation of the current state of construction as a 3D model makes it easier to adapt the production planning without entering the ship. This leads to a reduction of unproductive times and associated costs, which are caused when workers find a deviating state of construction in the ship and thus cannot start working in time.

1. Introduction

Outfitting processes in shipbuilding are marked by different technical crews installing specific components in a determined order and on schedule to finish work in time. Process mapping on shipyards revealed a low level of digitization throughout the outfitting processes. The resulting low transparency regarding current state and progress of construction often leads to miscommunication. Assembly errors and defects are reported too late or not detailed enough. The lack of information requires additional coordination of suppliers and technical crews which results in delays. Besides, the productivity gets lowered by unplanned supplementary work and no value-adding activities as searching for persons in charge. This paper presents an approach for increasing productivity in the outfitting process by implementing tools for digital communication to efficiently coordinate the involved parties. The functionality of the tool comprises the digital capturing of the current state and progress of construction in shipbuilding, especially in outfitting processes, and providing it to all process participants.

2. Current situation

Shipbuilding is characterized through a high level of complexity as well as a high number of companies contributing material, knowledge and working capacity. Within the past decades suppliers became more important as their share in product value increased to 50-80%, depending on the segment, *ECORYS SCS Group(2009)*. Especially in outfitting process a lot of subcontractors and suppliers need to work in time and in the right order to meet the agreed costs and delivery dates. Though the high numbers of parts, being installed by external workers, make it more complicated to share information and status reports.

The rough project planning for installation is done by the shipyard. It is based on design data that is delivered by suppliers and combined to an overall 3D model. Suppliers and subcontractors receive the project plan and the entire ship as 3D model. They use it as a basis for their specific operational planning. Also material is ordered according to installation dates. While building the ship, meetings with employees from shipyard, suppliers and subcontractors are held recurrently. Every contributing team reports the current status of installation. Problems, delays and their reasons are discussed and recorded in documents like excel tables. These documents are distributed to suppliers and subcontractors. Although this document is a main basis to all the crafts, problems occur because of inaccurate information. The loss of details happens on the way from the worker, who is recognizing the problem in the ship, to the coordinator or project manager who is giving report in daily or weekly meetings. The following reasons can be outlined:

- reporting progress as a status in percentage is based on subjective estimate
- misunderstandings in general, for example because of different part naming
- photographs without detailed description or marking, from one perspective only.

Another issue is that too much time elapses between identifying a problem in the ship and spreading information about it to all depended crafts. Summed up, the ship seems like a black box to those installation teams who are yet to enter it. This situation causes different issues which are explained within 3 scenarios.

- Example scenario 1: Installation team A from supplier A wants to start working in the ship as determined in the project plan. When installation team A arrives at the site of operation it is not able to start because another installation team, which should have already finished according to the plan, is still working. Because of dependencies in installation sequence and space, team A has to leave the shipyard and come back another day. Besides unnecessary costs for approaching the shipyard, the supplier also needs to bring back the material he brought into the ship, resulting in a massive loss of time.
- Example scenario 2: Installation team A is entering the ship on schedule. As usual, the workers take the printed technical drawing to the site of operation. This drawing shows the supplier-specific parts only. As there is no possibility to check whether the predecessor installation was completed and there are no other installation teams in the area, the supplier starts installing the parts and completes the installation after some time. Meanwhile or after the completion, installation team B appears. The installation of their parts was planned earlier but as there have been problems at other installation sites in the ship, the schedule could not be kept. Examining the area in order to start his installation process, supplier B notices that the space is blocked by other parts. Instead of trying to catch up the delay, supplier B needs to find out what to do. He needs to contact the shipyard coordinator, who needs to solve the problem. Most likely, supplier A has to dismantle his parts, wait for supplier B to do his installation and then reinstall the parts. This additional amount of work causes extra costs, delays and coordination expenditure.
- Example scenario 3: Supplier A sends his installation team to the shipyard on schedule. They start assembling but recognize that other components, which have been installed earlier by other suppliers, block their work. It is not possible to finish the work as the parts do not fit anymore. Reason for that is a design adaption of already installed parts without informing other suppliers. As the parts do not fit anymore, installation team A stops the work and informs the coordinator. He has to clarify responsibilities and adapt installation planning. Unproductive times for searching for the contact person, coordination, designing, ordering and producing new parts and (dis-)assembling cause extra costs and delays that may endanger the date of delivery.

These scenarios show that a low level of important information regarding the current state of construction could cause additional work and costs. To decrease these inefficiencies, a simple solution is needed to record the current situation in the ship. Making this data available enables suppliers to take a glance into the ship for better planning and easier coordination. In addition, the shipyard coordinator should have access to a tool for counteracting said deviations from the project plan.

Process mapping revealed that there are different approaches for capturing the current state of construction in shipbuilding industry. In addition to status information given as a percentage, photographs are taken in the ship. These photographs can show special areas or parts, for example if an error occurs. Because of this high degree of detail, usually not the whole room is captured. To provide the whole room in one take, 360° photography is used. These pictures can be connected to floor plans and rooms. The user gets a much better impression and overview concerning the whole room. Both can be created with common cameras and corresponding software or even mobile devices like smartphones, equipped with suitable apps. Although panorama or 360° pictures are an improvement compared to normal photos, they still show two dimensions only. The use of 3D laser

scanners solves this problem and enables the user to move through a digital copy of the ship. Nevertheless, 3D scanners are expensive and need to be carried as an extra tool, even if they are handheld. Doing an optical measurement requires an extra walk into the ship because the scanner is heavy and bulky. Therefore it cannot be carried while performing other tasks.

3. Approach to improving transparency about building progress

Different research projects tried to overcome the named problems by capturing the current state of construction as a point cloud. As shown in the project PROSPER, selecting the expedient tool depends on different factors as size of a room, light conditions, accuracy, mobility, costs and others. Applicable hardware for capturing parts as a three-dimensional object are laser scanners, 3D cameras as Kinect or common digital cameras that create a point cloud after using photogrammetric software, *Lödning et al. (2016)*. As the use of laser scanners for construction industry is already common, other approaches established that the combination of laser scanning and photography is feasible, especially if scanned rooms should be viewable in color, *Golparvar-Fard et al. (2011)*, *Ehm and Hesse (2014)*, *Tuttas et al. (2014)*. In the past years, manufacturer of laser scanners recognized the needs of smaller and especially mobile laser scanners. Therefore, hand laser scanners were developed and are available today, e.g. Creaforms portable 3D scanners, <https://www.creaform3d.com/en/metrology-solutions/portable-3d-scanners>. For a high level of flexibility regarding the data acquisition, a toolbox of different methods and hardware should be established. According to the specific requirements of the shipyard or suppliers, one method can be chosen. Findings of the named researches as well as practical tests regarding laser scanner, camera (resp. photogrammetry) and Kinect as a representative for 3D cameras (resp. time-of-flight cameras) are summed up in Table I. Quality was valued regarding measuring accuracy and resolution.

Table I: Characteristics of different technologies

Technology	Time exposure	Quality	Costs	Mobility
Laser scanner	Medium	High	High	Low - Medium
Photogrammetry	Low	Medium	Low	High
3D camera	High	Medium	Low	Medium

Results of process mapping and interrogation of employees and suppliers at a shipyard also revealed, that usability is another important factor to include into the decision process. Therefore capturing the as-built state through photogrammetry was focused. Still the method can be changed into laser scanning if a high resolution is needed. Using the Kinect was neglected as the time exposure is much higher compared to laser scanning, *Lödning et al. (2016)*.

Fig. 1: Workflow

To keep the physical stress and the additional amount of equipment low, camera systems like digital single lens reflex cameras are replaced by mobile devices. These are handy and as they became an everyday object. People are used to handle it and therefore need no special training. Lödning et al. stated that cameras of smartphones are practicable for photogrammetric use, *Lödning et al. (2016)*. The captured data is transferred into a point cloud, which is compared to the 3D model of the ship afterwards. Comparison result shows which parts are installed correctly and which parts will cause delay. A communication and monitoring platform that can be accessed by all involved parties as shipyard and suppliers, displays the updated progress and status. Fig.1 shows the entire workflow.

3.1. Capturing as-built state

The shown workflow starts with capturing the as-built state in the ship with a mobile device. To minimize the problem of holes in the point cloud caused by insufficient overlap in the taken pictures, videos instead of normal photographs were taken. Thus, the user does not have to think about the degree of overlap for finding the right position to release the shutter. Taking a video also results in a shorter time exposure compared to taking pictures. If the user wants to start the process, he opens the camera-app, switches to video mode and starts the recording. The walk through the room should be done as shown in Fig.2 (blue line) with a continuous speed and the mobile device always turned to the middle of the room (blue arrows).

Fig.2: Schematic presentation of exemplary walk through a room

For taking photos for photogrammetry with a digital consumer camera it is necessary to note that specific settings should be fixed for better processing. As explained by Linder, resolution, distance settings, exposure time, f-number and image formats are parameters that affect the photogrammetric results as well as the focal length, *Linder (2016)*. All of the tested devices had a fixed focal length due to their construction. Distance setting resp. auto focus, exposure time and f-number could not be changed by the user. For photography mode ISO-settings could be adjusted, but not in video mode. The opportunity to change camera settings was not equal for all devices. Therefore the only varied parameter was resolution. To ensure, that the data capturing can be done with any consumer mobile device and by untrained users, the video was shot in default video mode.

The tested mobile devices can be divided into tablets and smartphones. Tablets that were brought into the ship were the Samsung Active Tab 2 and Panasonic FZ-M1 Toughpad. Smartphones that were used to capture the rooms were the Caterpillar S60 and Sony Xperia Z5. Compared to the other mobile devices, the best results were provided by the Sony Xperia Z5. The image resolution has been tested in high definition (HD) and video graphic array (VGA) for all devices. To get further information about the relation of exposure times between different technologies, a 74 m² L-shaped room was captured in another test by a mobile device (Sony Xperia Z5), a consumer digital camera (Canon Powershot G15) and a laser scanner (Z+F Imager 5010i). While the scanning process with the

laser took about 20 minutes, the video was shot in less than 2 minutes. Taking reference pictures with the digital camera took the user about 5 minutes. Results are shown in Figs.3-5.

Fig.3: Point cloud from video taken with Sony Xperia Z5

Fig.4: Point cloud from photos taken with Canon Powershot G15

Fig.5: Point cloud from laser scanning with Z+F Imager 5010i

The room has a huge window front, which was covered by paper to improve photogrammetry results from mobile device. Also the found situation in the ship, where windows were covered with translucent foil or cardboard should be simulated. Still one part of the room was brightly illuminated while the other part was darker. This situation as well as the automatic video mode of the smartphone led to results worthy of improvement. They might get better if autofocus and image stabilizer are switched off while shooting the video. This approach is still in testing.

3.2. Processing of photographs

In the next step, the captured data needs to be processed. Therefore the user connects the mobile device with a computer and transfers the video. As photogrammetry works with photos only, single

pictures need to be extracted. This can be done with small effort, only the video location on the computer needs to be linked with the corresponding cutting-program and photo extraction will start automatically. Pictures then are saved in an extra folder. Tests with regard to extraction rates showed, that the optimal extraction rate is 2 - 3 pictures/second. A lower extraction rate leads to the risk of insufficient overlap between two pictures. The generation of a point cloud is started after extracted photos are loaded into photogrammetry software. Doing it for the first time, the user needs a short instruction or manual. After the dense point cloud is generated, the processing is finished. The result now can be used for comparison of current state of construction and 3D model. Fig.6 shows the workflow of capturing and processing the data as well as the result.

Fig.6: Workflow of point cloud generation

First tests showed that the results of processing depend much on the lighting situation. Videos of rooms with a constant level of lighting delivered much better results than rooms with a huge window front on one side and a dark area on the other side. Another finding was that smooth and single-colored surfaces often cause holes in the point cloud. To overcome these issue additional markers can be used for this kind of surfaces. Another tested parameter regarding the captured area was the orientation of the camera. If the room should be captured in its full height from floor to ceiling, portrait format should be used. Time for shooting the video might lengthen minimally.

Fig.7: Results of point cloud processing from parts of rooms in a ship

Another product of photogrammetry can be a mesh instead of a point cloud. This might be a better result for reviews, as the surfaces can be identified more easily. This mesh or even the point cloud can be used for documentation of progress. It could be used for status meetings with the customer as well. Even without comparison to the 3D model, it is possible to make the executed installation visible. That documentation can be used for future projects. If a similar type of ship will be produced again, the collected data might help for a better planning and avoidance of high coordination effort.

3.3. Comparing point cloud to 3D model

As a next step, the before created point clouds can be compared to a given 3D model. The comparison can be done in different technological levels from manual to automatic. First technological level means the simple visual survey of the point cloud. In addition to the 3D model that serves as specified condition, the supplier is able to see whether the preceding work steps of other technical crews have already been finished. As written above the current state of construction can be supplied as a mesh additionally.

Fig.8: Comparison of point cloud and 3D model – technological level 1

The next technological level comprises comparing the 3D model and the point cloud as a whole and coloring the parts pursuant to their existence in the point cloud. No specific part is named but the colored point cloud gives a general view about the progress in the room. This method is not suitable for detailed comparison. Therefore it can be used for the rough overview at the shipyards project controlling department or general status meetings where a detailed discussion is not compulsory.

Fig.9: Comparison of point cloud and 3D model – technological level 2

The highest technical level of comparison will give a detailed report. Point cloud and 3D model will be compared automatically. Every digital part that is found in the form of points can be marked as installed. Additionally, the individual part and the fitting points can be viewed solitary. Results of the comparison can be presented in a list that can be sorted by room, responsible supplier or status of the installation. Also coloring the specific part in the 3D model referring to its status is possible.

Fig.10: Detailed comparison of point cloud and 3D model – technological level 3

Fig.10 shows a detail view of a profile that was marked as installed due to comparison. The corresponding points around this part are colored green. The high diffusion of points around the part is caused by a low density of points and a high tolerance for the matching. Obviously the quality of the point clouds needs to be improved. For reliable results the tolerance must be lowered as well.

3.4. Monitoring platform

Results from data capturing and comparison will be uploaded to a monitoring platform that is accessible for contributing employees and suppliers. Accordingly to the used comparison method (manual, half automatic, automatic) the impact on the project plan has to be noted manually or will be calculated automatically. Visibility settings can be adjusted appropriate to the shipyards wishes and security guidelines. Regardless detailed settings every supplier should be able to log in and check

whether he can start installation on schedule. Even an automatic notification for delays via email is provided.

As the project plan is a way to describe the progress with a high level of detail, a general overview would be useful as well. Therefore a profile view into the ship can be used to show the progress for specific areas like a deck in form of colored and filled circles for the corresponding level of completion. By clicking into a deck, the view will be further detailed through opening a deck plan for example, where every room is colored accordingly his state of installation. An example for the first view can be seen in Fig.11.

Fig.11: Overview of installation progress for the entire ship

The monitoring platform can be opened via mobile device or desktop computer. Besides current state of construction, list of installed or missing parts and the 3D point cloud, other data can be uploaded. For example technical drawings could be attached and dependent crafts would be informed if a change in design occurs. That would avoid the problem of blocking parts in an area as described in example scenario 3 at the beginning.

Summed up, the monitoring platform enables the user to glance a view into the ship at any time and any place. The immediacy of information depends on the frequency of data acquisition, which should be determined. According to whether a special person is responsible for capturing the room or every worker can shoot a video after finishing his work of a day, the update rate differs.

4. Conclusions

This paper presents an approach to handle the problem of low transparency about information concerning the current state of construction in the ship. Coordination effort and costs should be lowered by keeping shipyard and suppliers updated about the progress of installation. Instead of expensive laser scanner or 3D cameras, consumer mobile devices are used to film a room. Therefore no special equipment or training is necessary. After shooting the video, pictures will be extracted and progressed with photogrammetry software to gain a point cloud of the room. In the next step, the point cloud is used to compare current state of construction to the 3D model. This can be done in

different degrees of automation. The result of comparison will then be uploaded to a monitoring platform that is accessible to the shipyards employees and suppliers and gives both an overview and detailed information concerning installation status.

Practical tests showed that point clouds, processed from videos of different mobile devices, can give an impression about current installation status. Under certain ambient conditions semiautomatic comparison is possible. Especially diverging light situations in a room and plain surfaces are a challenge to this method and the point clouds quality. For automatically comparing point cloud and 3D model, further research is necessary and promising as mobile devices are developed further. Latest types with improved cameras as Samsung Galaxy S9 or Sony XZ1 have not been used for testing yet.

The described process still can be conducted with any mobile device as an addition to conventional laser scanning which has to be done anyway for reasons of quality assurance. It is planned to replenish weekly laser scans with daily created point cloud from mobile devices. Changes on schedule can be reported via monitoring platform even if no point cloud was created. The most important step is to increase transparency and immediacy of information about construction progress for the shipyard and participating suppliers to minimize coordination effort, delays and costs.

References

ECORYS SCS GROUP (2009), *Study on Competitiveness of the European Shipbuilding Industry*, Report within the Framework Contract of Sectoral Competitiveness Studies – ENTR/06/054

EHM, M.; HESSE, C. (2014), *3D-Laserscanning zur Erfassung von Gebäuden – Building Information Modeling (BIM)*, Bautechnik 91/4, pp.243–250

GOLPARVAR-FARD, M.; BOHN, J.; TEIZER, J.; SAVARESE, S.; PEÑA-MORA, F. (2011): *Evaluation of image-based modeling and laser scanning accuracy for emerging automated performance monitoring techniques*, Automation in Construction, Bd. 20, pp.1143–1155

LINDER, W. (2016), *Digital photogrammetry, A practical course*, Springer

LÖDDING, H.; FRIEDEWALD, A.; HALATA, P.S.; TIETZE, F.; TITOV, F. (2016), *Verbundvorhaben Produktivitätsmanagement in schiffbaulichen Produktionsprozessen ermöglichen (PROSPER): Teilvorhaben "Basis-Methoden (BASIS)"*, Abschlussbericht, TU Hamburg-Harburg, Institut für Produktionsmanagement und -technik

TUTTAS, S.; BRAUN, A.; BORMANN, A.; STILLA, U. (2014), *Konzept zur automatischen Baufortschrittskontrolle durch Integration eines Building Information Models und photogrammetrisch erzeugten Punktwolken*, DGPF Tagungsband 23/2014, pp.363–372

One Sea: Steps Towards Autonomous Maritime Operations

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Abstract

This paper outlines why maritime autonomy is now a current issue. It introduces One Sea – autonomous maritime ecosystem, a high-profile alliance, with a primary aim to lead the way towards an operating autonomous maritime ecosystem by 2025. The ecosystem was founded by some of the major industrial players in the maritime field together with well-known ICT companies. The paper discusses the activities done by the ecosystem and the steps towards safe autonomous (unmanned, partially unmanned as well as remotely operated) maritime operations. It also addresses the recent achievements and practical examples of One Sea partner companies have done in maritime autonomy.

1. Introduction

The maritime industry is following the technology transformation that sweeps across all industries. Within the past couple of years, the car industry has taken steps towards electricity. In telecom area, traditional landlines have been long since replaced by smartphones making mobility, internet, camera, email et cetera available for everyone. Disrupting business models are emerging in all industries and new players that did not exist few years ago are entering the market. Examples of new entrants in other industries include Tesla, Uber, Airbnb and Amazon to name a few.

Digitalization opens opportunities for maritime industry as well. It is only natural that maritime industry follows the trend. Not maybe in the forefront of the change, but faster than some of us might expect. Fig.1. illustrates the connection between innovation and ongoing transformation in the maritime industry. The center part of the image shows three types of innovations: single innovations, combinatory innovations and systemic innovations. Single technical innovations include improved cameras, radars, etc. Combinatory innovations are combinations of single innovations. These include situational awareness (SA), navigation or communication systems. Finally, systemic innovations are new concepts enabled by multiple combinatory innovations. The outer part of the figure illustrates the relation between technology development and social change. The development of technology opens new opportunities, which need social change to be accepted and taken into use. Autonomous shipping is an example of systemic innovation that is being realized within the next couple of years.

Fig.1: Connecting levels of innovation with technical and social change, Saarni et al. (2016)

Although the concept autonomous shipping is somewhat controversial, it is perceived by many the future of modern marine traffic. It needs to be emphasized that autonomous ships do not necessarily mean unmanned ships. Unmanned ships are highly autonomous. However, manned ships can include highly autonomous capabilities. Also, ships themselves consist also of multiple systems (propulsion, navigation, etc.), which can have different maturity regarding autonomy.

Autonomous ships operate in an ecosystem, where decision-making is based on Big Data, smart algorithms, artificial intelligence and ultimate optimization. Moving to autonomous ships requires redefining and assessing the role of on-board crew, artificial intelligence and the remote-control crew ashore.

There are several drivers for maritime autonomy. First one is safety. Human errors cause 75-95% maritime accidents, *Rothblum (2000)*. Modern technologies will reduce likelihood of accidents as well as the number of lost lives in marine accidents. Second driver is cost. The economic benefit results from fuel savings and reduced number of systems that need to be installed and maintained onboard. Third driver is sustainability. Lower fuel consumption results in smaller ecological footprint and more sustainable logistics. The fourth driver is the reduced risk of supply interruptions. The importance of system reliability increases as the level of autonomy increases in ships and the manning level goes down, which increases the need for standardization. Standardization enables system validation and health management, increase the level of automation in supply chain and support transparency. Finally, it enables new type of business and business models. The current shipping business is built on the collaboration between large number of different actors in various roles. Maritime autonomy will alter the existing roles and introduce completely new roles. Maritime autonomy will also make shipping more integrated part of logistic chain. It will make logistics more lean removing middle men in many instances putting the cargo owner in control of the supply chain. Autonomy can also change the entire system of transporting goods overseas. The size of the transport units as well as ships can be expected to change when digitalization will enable more individual transport solutions straight to customers.

Identifying the change occurring in other industries, understanding its meaning for maritime and desire to influence the direction maritime technologies are developed were some of the primary reasons for establishing One Sea – autonomous maritime ecosystem, which is discussed next.

2. Background of the autonomous maritime ecosystem

2.1. Preparing the ecosystem

The origin of One Sea is in strategy work completed by the Finnish marine industry and its stakeholders who drafted the Strategic Research Agenda 2025 of the Finnish Maritime Cluster, which outlines a roadmap for research in the industry, *NN (2016)*. The SRA work created an initial vision on autonomous vessels, where digitalization becomes tangible in intelligent equipment and systems, as well as in digital services. The objective is to have the first autonomous vessels to sail within few years. The aim is to conduct a wide range of sea trials of digital solutions. The vision created in the SRA was translated into an ecosystem for autonomous marine transport, and DIMECC Ltd was selected to lead the ecosystem called One Sea.

DIMECC stands for Digital, Internet, Materials & Engineering Co-Creation. DIMECC is the leading co-creation platform for digital transformation in Finland. DIMECC's network consists of 2.000+ R&D&I professionals, 400+ organizations, 69 shareholders and 10+ co-creation facilitators.

2.2. Implementing the ecosystem

The Ecosystem for Autonomous Marine Transport was started on 22 September 2016, as the Finnish Funding Agency for Innovation, Business Finland, granted the funding for the ecosystem. The ecosystem is co-funded by Business Finland and the partner companies.

The objective of the initiative is to draft a common development roadmap for the implementation of autonomous, partially manned and unmanned marine transportation. The world’s first unmanned maritime products, services, and a functioning ecosystem should be in place by 2025. As a part of the ecosystem, the Finnish Ministry of Transport and Communications is committed to supporting the development and testing of autonomous vessels in Finland.

Although One Sea ecosystem originates from Finland it is an international initiative that connects some of global pioneers of marine and ICT industries. It is a pre-competitive business-driven alliance bringing competitors and collaborators around the same table to work on a common agenda.

The ecosystem is a link between the key players in the maritime cluster, providers of digital solutions and the public sector. In practice, the ecosystem is creating the circumstances needed for efficient collaboration and coordinates development projects between different players to implement a common roadmap. One Sea is an open alliance welcoming industrial partners to join the ecosystem. The current list of ecosystem partners is listed in Table I.

Table I: One Sea partners

Organization	Description
ABB	ABB (ABBN: SIX Swiss Ex) is a pioneering technology leader in electrification products, robotics and motion, industrial automation and power grids, serving customers in utilities, industry and transport & infrastructure globally. Continuing more than a 125-year history of innovation, ABB today is writing the future of industrial digitalization and driving the Energy and Fourth Industrial Revolutions. ABB operates in more than 100 countries with about 135,000 employees.
Cargotec	Cargotec is a leading provider of cargo and load handling solutions with the goal of becoming the leader in intelligent cargo handling. Cargotec has three business areas: Kalmar, Hiab and MacGregor. Kalmar and Hiab provide solutions and services for cargo handling in ports, terminals and on-road whereas MacGregor offers engineering solutions and services for handling marine cargoes and offshore loads. MacGregor believes that the offshore and marine industries are at the beginning of a new era; employing technology and digital capabilities that could only be dreamt about just a few decades ago. MacGregor invites all major stakeholders for an open-minded, industry transformation cooperation – for a safer, more efficient and more sustainable future.
Ericsson	Ericsson is a world leader in communications technology and services. Our organization consists of more than 111,000 experts who provide customers in 180 countries with innovative solutions and services. Together we are building a more connected future where anyone and any industry is empowered to reach their full potential.
FinFerries	Finferries (Suomen Lauttaliikenne Group) is a state-owned operator of ferry services in Finland. Finferries has over 300 employees working on 44 routes around the country. Finferries runs its 24/7 operation according to the three core values: Safety, Service-mindedness and Profitability. Finferries’ vessels carry about 4 million vehicles and 10 million passengers each year. Finferries’ latest newbuilding Elektra is Finland’s first battery driven hybrid ferry, with battery packs charged directly from the grid. Elektra represents a milestone on the path towards clean shipping.
Finnpilot Pilotage	Finnpilot Pilotage’s mission is to ensure the safe and smooth flow of maritime traffic. Their work reduces environmental accidents. The company employs over 300 pilotage professionals, who work 24/7 to carry out approximately 25,000 pilotage assignments each year. The company pilots 32% of the ships entering all Finland’s ports from more than one thousand different fairways, working tirelessly to provide the safest, highest quality service to their customers.
Meyer	Meyer Turku Oy employs 1,800 persons and specializes in building highly complex,

Turku	<p>innovative and environmentally friendly cruise ships, car-passenger ferries and special vessels. Together with two sister shipyards in Germany, Meyer Werft in Papenburg and Neptun Werft in Rostock, Meyer Turku is one of the world's leading cruise ship builders. The successful shipbuilding tradition in Turku has been continuing since 1737. The company is currently building cruise ships for TUI Cruises. The company will also build two cruise ships for Costa Crociere, Carnival Corporation and Royal Caribbean International.</p> <p>The design and construction of the ships are supported by the subsidiaries of Meyer Turku: Piikkio Works Oy, which is a Cabin Factory in Piikkiö, Shipbuilding Completion Oy, which provides turnkey solutions to public spaces in ships, and ENG'nd Oy, which is an engineering company offering services for shipbuilding and offshore.</p>
Rolls-Royce	Rolls-Royce is applying technology, skills and experience from across its civil aerospace, defence, nuclear power and marine businesses to develop remote controlled and autonomous ships. With experience in secure data analytics and ship intelligence, design, propulsion and machinery expertise it is ideally placed to help define the future of shipping
Tieto	Leading Nordic software and services company. Tieto aims to capture the significant opportunities of the data-driven world and turn them into lifelong value for people, business and society. We aim to be customers' first choice for business renewal by combining our software and services capabilities with a strong drive for co-innovation and ecosystems.
Wärtsilä Marine Solutions	Wärtsilä Marine Solutions enhances the business of its marine and oil & gas industry customers by providing innovative products and integrated solutions that are safe, environmentally sustainable, efficient, flexible, and economically sound. Our solutions are developed based on our customers' needs and include products, systems and services. Being a technology leader, and through the experience, know-how and dedication of our personnel, we are able to customize optimized solutions for the benefit of our clients around the world.
Finnish Marine Industries	Finnish Marine Industries is a co-operation forum for high-technology maritime solution providers, leading marine equipment manufacturers, turn-key suppliers, designers, software and system providers as well as shipbuilding, ship repair and offshore yards.
The Finnish Shipowners' Association	The Finnish Shipowners' Association is a trade association with an interest in industrial and labour market policies. Its members include 25 Finnish shipping companies and 105 ships.
Business Finland	Business Finland is the most important publicly funded expert organization for financing research, development and innovation in Finland. We boost wide-ranging innovation activities in research communities, industry and service sectors.

3. Ecosystem Activities

One Sea has two primary functions. First, to enable the means for autonomous maritime operations and second, to communicate the message of maritime autonomy and its progress. The ecosystem's activities are centred around these functions. Fig.2 shows the ecosystem activities, which are discussed in greater detail in the next sections.

3.1. Roadmap

The One Sea core activities include creation and steering the 2025 vision of the ecosystem and establishing the strategy to pursue the achievement of the vision. Another important core activity has been the creation of roadmaps towards 2025. The roadmap, Fig.3, published in the spring 2017 highlights the perceived technology development, milestones and themes on the way towards commercial autonomous shipping.

Fig.2: One Sea Ecosystem activities

Fig.3 Roadmap towards 2025

Top part of the roadmap envisions that the initial focus will be initially on remote operations, which will gradually move towards more autonomous operations. The need for testing and validation is emphasized on the green background. It is acknowledged that testing is needed both to prove the technology, processes and procedures as well as to assure the regulators and class societies that the solutions are mature and safe. It will also assist in building the social acceptance for maritime autonomy. The path of regulation is on the red background. It is understood that the current regulation needs to be reworked to accommodate autonomous ships. The regulatory work takes time, hence the red background. The light blue area in the roadmap describes the perceived overall development also around the maritime domain.

The bottom part of the roadmap lists identified key themes that are carried out over the course of the development. These include concern on the ethical issues (human factor, AI, etc.), emphasis on the cyber security, development projects and IPR created in the companies (One Sea does not accumulate IPR) and ensuring the education is tailored to accommodate designing and operating with autonomous ships. The legislative work done nationally and internationally is also seen as an ongoing activity.

Deriving from the roadmap, One Sea has identified six main themes, which are the areas of focus for the ecosystem, Fig.4. The main topics are: technology, security (including safety), regulation, traffic control, ethics and operations. The themes are all partially overlapping. One Sea has also established

working groups to progress the topics. Their purpose is to support fulfilling the 2025 vision of autonomous maritime ecosystem.

One Sea seeks to create international standards to efficiently develop the autonomous marine transport. The standards may cover areas, such as safety, testing, data transfer, cyber security, data and systems architecture, artificial intelligence, et cetera. The objective is to harmonise the operational models within the industry with industry-specific regulations, where the rules and regulations drafted by the authorities may not correspond to the rapid development that the sector is experiencing. One Sea also collaborates globally with players within the field of autonomous marine transport.

Fig.4: One Sea main themes and working groups

3.2. The steps towards commercial autonomous ships

The following discusses activities and achievements of One Sea ecosystem for forward autonomy.

3.2.1 Regulation

On 31 December 2015, the Finnish Minister of Transport and Communications Anne Berner has submitted Finland’s official opinion to the International Maritime Organisation on the strategic areas of focus of the IMO between 2018 and 2023. The opinion included a demand to change the international rules and regulations to consider the questions related to the remote-controlled and autonomous marine traffic.

The Finnish Transport Safety Agency, Trafi, operating under the Ministry of Transport and Communications, has coordinated the drafting of an opinion regarding vessel autonomy for the meeting of the IMO Maritime Safety Committee (MSC98) in London on 13 June 2017, in collaboration with numerous other flag states. Trafi also arranged an opportunity for the industry to give a presentation of vessel autonomy in the meeting. The outcome of the MSC resulted in decision to initiate a scoping exercise to “to determine how the safe, secure and environmentally sound operation of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) may be introduced in IMO instruments”, <http://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/MeetingSummaries/MSC/Pages/MSC-98th-session.aspx>.

One Sea has also worked with the Finnish flag state to produce two papers to MSC99 in May 2018. The first one is info paper regarding the test area established in Finland and the other is a working paper considering the definitions for levels and concepts of autonomy.

3.2.2 Testing and validation

Thorough testing in authentic sea conditions is critical to ensure the functionality of systems and technology and to guarantee the required safety and reliability of the autonomous vessels of the future.

With the help of Finnish authorities, One Sea has established a test area in the coastal area of Finland in 2017. The test area titled, Jaakonmeri, was the first one in the world to be globally open to anyone wishing to test autonomous maritime traffic, vessels, or technologies related to it. The test area is managed and controlled by DIMECC Ltd. The test area was awarded by a Finnish Government Bureau, Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment of Southwest Finland. Jaakonmeri Test Area is located on the Finnish west coast outside the municipality of Eurajoki. The coordinates for the area are:

- NW 61 20.75 N 20 55.15 E
- NE 61 19.60 N 21 14.70 E
- SE 61 15.65 N 21 12.67 E
- SW 61 16.85 N 20 54.55 E

Fig.2: Jaakonmeri test area for autonomous and unmanned surface vessels on Finnish coast

The longest side of the area to the north is approximately 17.85 km long and the western side is approximately 7.10 km long. The area is open water and offers opportunities to test also in ice conditions during the winter. The area is closed for all maritime traffic except for the vessels that are tested and other vessel that are part of the test activities during the test period. The restrictions do not apply to the authorities and rescue operations. The test duration can range from one (1) to six (6) weeks. The sea trials will be adapted to other marine traffic in the area, and it will be announced via the Vessel Traffic Service (VTS). During sea trials, the vessels will comply with the international rules of the waterways.

3.2.3 R&D programs and innovation

Research and development projects are an important part of the ecosystem. Although much of the technology required for realizing autonomous maritime is already available, there are items to be researched, clarified and optimized. One Sea ecosystem is a platform for R&D and innovation projects. These projects are joint efforts of One Sea companies, research organizations and companies outside One Sea ecosystem. One Sea seeks to identify and engage with start-ups as well as agile companies (SMEs) to identify innovation, foster growth and co-create technology, solutions and services, Fig.6.

Fig.3: Collaboration with startups and SME's aims to find synergies and solutions

3.2.4 Product and service creation

The most important activity in taking the autonomous maritime industry forward is the product and service creation by the industry. The ecosystem comprises both maritime and ICT companies, hence the development happens on multiple fronts. While companies have a long-term vision on where the maritime industry is headed, the services and products they are creating need to have a business case from the beginning. Thus, the companies are seeking to benefit from the low hanging fruits and build the portfolios incrementally. Fig.7 highlights some of the recent milestones in the development of autonomous ships.

Fig.4: Selected milestones around autonomous shipping recently.

The first milestone to mention is the world's first remote operated commercial vessel, which was demonstrated in Copenhagen harbour in February 2017, <https://www.rolls-royce.com/media/our-stories.aspx>. The Rolls-Royce's demonstration involved manoeuvring a 28m Svitzer Hermod tug from a remote operating center (ROC), where the captain of the vessel was stationed. Although the tug was operated remotely, the vessel had fully qualified captain and crew on board throughout to ensure safe operation in case of system failure and to satisfy the current regulation. The technology involved in the demonstration included systems to give captain full awareness of surroundings in the ROC. Sensors included Radar, Lidar, camera and audio as well as DP system (Dynamic Positioning system). The demonstration was overseen by Lloyd's Register.

The second milestone to point out is the Wärtsilä's demonstration of remote piloting an offshore vessel few months later, <https://www.wartsila.com/media/news/01-09-2017-wartsila-successfully-tests-remote-control-ship-operating-capability>. In this demonstration, an 80-metre platform supply vessel in the North Sea coast of Scotland. The remote navigation was done from Wärtsilä's office in San Diego, California some 8000 km away. The significance of the demonstration is in the communication between the vessel and the shore. The demonstration was carried out using standard bandwidth onboard satellite communication and no land-based technologies were. A DP system played also an important role in the successful 4-hour demonstration.

The final milestones to highlight involve the first product announcements around situational awareness. ABB announced its Ability Marine Pilot Vision product at the end of November 2017 <http://www.abb.com/cawp/seitp202/cb99bdc1a0fe4de9c12581df002e46ca.aspx>. Rolls-Royce published its Intelligent Awareness system in March 2018, <https://www.rolls-royce.com/media/press-releases/yr-2018/06-03-2018-rr-offers-ship-navigators-a-birds-eye-view-with-intelligent-awareness-game-changer.aspx>. Both systems improve the situational awareness thus improving navigational safety and enhance operational efficiency. These systems are support systems. Using them allows the crew to make more informed decisions. Both products are important steps towards autonomous maritime operations. Improving the maritime safety is one of the key elements in the business cases of the new products.

One conclusion drawn from the presented milestones of the autonomous technology is that the technology for remote operations and increased safety is already available. Focus on safety is crucial for the long-term business cases of maritime autonomy. While these milestones are not sufficient in fulfilling the promises of the future, the journey towards autonomous maritime operations is well on its way. This leads into One Sea's other important function. Disseminating the message of maritime autonomy.

3.2.5. Disseminating message of the maritime autonomy

One Sea strives to disseminate the message of maritime autonomy and dispel concerns related to it. Much of this work is done by participating and speaking in conferences, seminars and discussing in different forums as well as publishing papers regarding maritime autonomy. It also includes collaborating with industry, authorities, class societies, research organizations and other stakeholders.

An example of One Sea's active collaboration is the discussion on levels of autonomy. One Sea organized a meeting in Copenhagen on the 13 of November 2017 at the premises of The Danish Maritime Authority. The purpose of the meeting was to bring the parties developing proposals for levels of maritime autonomy and the main industry players together to discuss the proposals that had been made for the definition on the levels of autonomy. The proposals presented in the meeting were from Bureau Veritas, Lloyd's Register, NFAS (Norwegian Forum for Autonomous Ships), Rolls-Royce and UK Marine Industries Alliance. The meeting did not come to any conclusion, but it was incremental in gaining an understanding about the different views. The discussion allowed One Sea to craft the paper on levels of autonomy for IMO MSC99 discussed above.

4. Conclusion

This paper has discussed the relevance of maritime autonomy, its benefits and the implications for the maritime industry. It introduced One Sea – autonomous maritime ecosystem, which is an industrial alliance striving to progress maritime autonomy with the vision of having a business-driven ecosystem in place by 2025. The ecosystem has clear goal and strategy to progress towards safe autonomous (unmanned, partially unmanned as well as remotely operated) maritime operations. Transition from the conventional vessels will take time as the lifespan of the existing fleets are long. The initial implementations will be in local waters and short sea shipping. There will be vessel types where unmanned option may not be suitable for a very long time. However, the safety increasing technologies will be highly applicable in all maritime operations. The journey is has started.

References

NN (2016), *Strategic Research Agenda for the Finnish maritime cluster 2017-2025*, Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment of Finland

ROTHBLUM, A.M. (2000), *Human Error and Marine Safety*, U.S. Coast Guard Research & Development Center, Orlando

SAARNI, J.; NORDBERG-DAVIES, S.; MAKKONEN, H. (2016), *Remote and Autonomous Ships - The next steps*, Whitepaper, AAWA project

<http://www.rolls-royce.com/~media/Files/R/Rolls-Royce/documents/customers/marine/ship-intel/aawa-whitepaper-210616.pdf>

Sensitivity Analysis of Route Optimization Solutions on Different Computational Approaches for Powering Performance in the Seaway

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Abstract

In weather routing systems, the capability to generate reliable fuel saving routes critically depends on the integration of a path optimization algorithm with meteo-marine and ship dynamics models. In this work, a system based on LaMMA meteo-marine forecast and on a novel route optimization algorithm is considered. The sensitivity of the least fuel consumption solutions is analysed considering different simplified ship added resistance parametrisations. The work is in the context of PROFUMO Demonstrator project (ESA-ARTES-IAP), aimed to implement a pre-operational system for routing services based on forecasts improved by the cooperative collection of meteo-marine data from ships.

1. Introduction

The adoption of energy efficiency measures in the international shipping has been recently boosted by the need for the mitigation of environmental impacts, together with the issue of fuel consumption reduction, IMO (2011), Rehmatulla et al. (2017), DNV-GL (2014,2017), ABS. Under the e-navigation paradigm, <http://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/safety/navigation/pages/enavigation.aspx>, Patraiko (2007), and in the technological framework of Integrated Bridge System, IMO (2014), the development of innovative navigation support systems passes through the smart integration of many emerging technologies, Patey (2012), Vossen et al. (2013). These support the functions of data collection, data processing and data telecommunication, Kano (2017), Gunkel (2017), Lund and Gonzalez (2017), and allow to optimally manage and blend energy efficiency with people, cargo and ship safety issues, <http://shopera.org>, Backalov et al. (2016). A growing relevance emerges for numerical modelling of the several interacting components of the mission-ship-environment system, Tillig et al. (2015), Papanikolaou (2011), and for their integration with the technological infrastructure, Perera and Mo (2016), Gonzalez et al. (2017). Operational optimization of ship performance along routes is searched for by weather routing systems, Perera and Guedes Soares (2017), Walther et al. (2016), Wiśniewski and Szymański (2016), Simonsen et al. (2015), and by their integration with operational guidance systems, Nielsen and Jensen (2016).

A key role in this framework is played by space technologies for Earth observation, positioning and communication, <https://artes.esa.int/news/satellites-sea-vdes-offers-global-link-ships>. This explains the motivation of developing the PROFUMO Demonstration project (Preliminary assessment of Route Optimisation for FUEL Minimisation and safety of navigation) within the ESA ARTES Integrated Applications Promotion (IAP) Programme of the European Space Agency (ESA). PROFUMO Demonstration comes out from two previous projects, all three of them coordinated by VITROCISSET Belgium S.p.r.l. (www.vitrocissetbelgium.com). The first one has been COSMEMOS, a proof-of-concept project, developed within the European FP7 programme in the context of the scientific application of the European Galileo satellite navigation system. Then followed by PROFUMO Feasibility, the feasibility phase of the present demonstration project, developed in the same ESA programme. The whole chain of projects is aimed at the implementation of an innovative decision support system for the Mediterranean maritime community, firmly based on space technologies. The system has been designed to deliver innovative weather routing and nowcasting services oriented to fuel consumption and pollution emissions reduction, but also strongly concerned with safety of navigation issues. A relevant point is the near-real-time exploitation of data from sensors present on board of cooperating ships of the service users, that in this way participate to the improvement of the service. Such cooperatively collected data are used in the system to improve meteo-marine forecast,

through data assimilation algorithms, *Kalnay (2003)*, and to improve situational awareness. Space technologies play a relevant role in the system, both in guaranteeing data transmission resources to and from the service users, via cost optimised channels, and by providing a host of environmental data. This include also data from Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS), as GPS and Galileo, planned to be utilised, through innovative processing algorithms, *Antonini et al. (2014)*, to improve meteo-marine forecasts by data assimilation procedures, involving also conventional in-situ data. Channel optimisation is performed by the SkyLink device, developed in the project by ESNAH (project partner, www.esnah.com/esnah).

The capability of weather routing systems to generate reliable optimal routes critically depends on the interplay of the optimization and the ship performance simulation algorithms, in the conditions defined by meteo-marine forecast data. In this work the sensitivity of the optimized routes on some relevant ship modelling details is investigated. A system based on the integration of Consorzio LaMMA (project partner and hereafter simply LaMMA, www.lamma.rete.toscana.it), meteo-marine forecast data and a novel route optimization algorithm, developed by Aleph s.r.l. (project partner, www.alephprogetti.com), is considered. The results of the first numerical tests of the system, are described in this paper. Such tests have been performed to put in evidence the effect, on the optimized routes, of different approaches to the computation of meteo-related added resistance components. A sensitivity analysis is conducted by considering a realistic ro-ro ferry on a given Mediterranean trade line, in a relevant heavy weather case study. The different least fuel consumption optimal solutions obtained by the optimization algorithm are comparatively analysed and some clues are put in evidence on the effects of ship modelling details on optimized routes.

2. Route optimization system components

The three main blocks of PROFUMO Demonstrator integrated modelling system for development of weather routing services are:

- Meteo-marine forecasting
- Ship performance modelling
- Route optimization.

Details of each one of them are described below.

2.1. Meteo-marine forecasting component

The meteo-marine forecasting chain utilised for the numerical tests described in this paper is composed of the mesoscale meteorological model WRF, *Skamarock and Klemp (2008)*, linked in cascade mode to the third generation spectral wave model Wavewatch III, *WW3 (2016)*. The models are those daily used to generate the operational wind and wave forecast of LaMMA, www.lamma.rete.toscana.it/mare/modelli/vento-emare, *Orlandi et al. (2009)*. It covers the whole Mediterranean basin at a resolution of about 12 Km, with forecasts runs repeated twice a day (run in initialization at 00:00 UTC and at 12:00 UTC), for the next five days.

The approach adopted to develop the meteo-marine forecasting component for PROFUMO Demonstrator project is based on gradually upgrading a baseline structure as the LaMMA one above described. The planned upgrading steps are:

- a) Addition of an ocean hydrodynamics modelling component, for forecasting surface currents over the whole Mediterranean basin, based on LaMMA experience, <http://www.lamma.rete.toscana.it/mare/modelli/correnti>, and integrated with data from Copernicus Marine, <http://marine.copernicus.eu>.
- b) Addition of a data assimilation system, to ingest the meteo-marine data, collected by the co-operating ships of the service users and by conventional local observing networks, in order to improve the forecasting skills at high resolution.

- c) Implementation of an Ensemble Prediction System (EPS) approach, *Chu et al. (2015)*, *Hoff-schildt et al. (1999)*, for the rigorous estimate of the reliability of the optimized routing solutions and for the future adoption of probabilistic and stochastic route optimization approaches. Forecast and route optimization reliability measures are key elements in the complex decision making process of the Officers Of Deck (OOD) on board every ship at sea, especially in heavy weather. Preliminary studies on the application of a Mediterranean basin wind-wave EPS system in the weather routing context have already been performed at LaMMA, *Orlandi et al. (2015)*.

2.2. Ship performance modelling component

By exploiting the availability of a complete set of meteo-marine forecast data, quite detailed forecasts of ship performance at sea can be generated. These, in turn, can be included in path optimization algorithms, in order to find optimal routes, accounting for optimization instances (e.g. save fuel and reduce pollution, and/or minimize transit time), and several voyage constraints (e.g. navigational rules and limits, avoid heavy weather and enforce safety of navigation thresholds for people, cargo and ship structures).

In an operational weather routing system, a good “working compromise” must be found between computational times (affecting system response times towards the end users) and modelling details (affecting quality and reliability of the routing service). A primary characteristic is the computational optimization of the used software, that allows to obtain “best results in the least time”. Hence part of the efforts in PROFUMO system implementation are devoted to this relevant goal.

Regarding the modelling of ship seakeeping and powering performance, several approaches are available in the specialized literature. In recent studies performed at LaMMA, a quite detailed approach has been investigated, *Orlandi (2014)*, *Orlandi et al. (2015)*. For powering, engine load and fuel consumption are evaluated through the dynamic balance between propeller(s) thrust and ships total resistance by applying standard algorithms, *Carlton (2007)*. For seakeeping it is based on strip theory and on a detailed treatment of the interplay of ship response functions with directional spectra in output from WWIII model. The overall computational load of all these algorithms is quite large. In order to speed-up the ship performance computational stage of the planned PROFUMO Demonstrator system, an approach based on the off-line computation of Look-Up Tables (LUT), both for ship seakeeping responses and for powering performance has been defined. In the first implementations, the computation of such LUTs is based on very simple approaches and the numerical tests serve for benchmarking and improving the algorithmic structure and as a sensitivity analysis of the adopted route optimization algorithm (described below). In the further development of the system, ship modelling details will be added gradually in the off-line ship modelling component, in order to have better and better ship data, to be coded in the LUTs, whose format will be gradually standardized.

In the first computing tests, only fuel consumption minimization has been considered, schematizing the ship total resistance in terms of a decomposition in the three main components, *Lewis (1990)*:

$$R_{tot} = R_{hull} + R_{wind} + R_{aw} \quad (1)$$

where R_{hull} is the calm-water resistance, and is supposed to be tabulated as a function of ship speed through water, and included as part of the ship specific LUTs. R_{wind} is the wind added resistance, and it is evaluated as:

$$R_{wind} = 0.5 \rho_{air} A_T U_r^2 C_x(\theta_{rwi}) \quad (2)$$

where ρ_{air} is air density, A_T is the ship frontal area, U_r is the modulus of the ship-relative total wind vector (i.e. vector composition of the rel. wind due to ship speed and of the wind components due to meteorological conditions). The longitudinal wind resistance coefficient $C_x = C_x(\theta_{rwi})$ is function of the

ship relative wind angle θ_{rwi} , and is stored as part of the LUTs, considering differing functional shapes, depending on the ship loading conditions (e.g. accounting for possible different containers arrangement and filling factor for a containership, *Watanabe et al. (2016)*). The specific details of R_{wind} could be accounted for by ship specific C_x coefficients, from wind tunnel or/and CFD, but also other meteo-related added resistance terms could be included through transverse forces and moments coefficients (C_y and C_N , resp.) and corresponding “passive rudder” terms, *Szelangiewicz (2006)*, *Bertram (2017)*. Such a detailed treatment of wind forces could be useful for the sound development of weather routing systems for wind assisted ships, *SAIL (2015)*, <http://www.nyk.com/english/csr/envi/ecoship.htm>

R_{aw} is the added resistance in waves, and it is evaluated as:

$$R_{aw} = H_s^2 C_{aw}(U_{ship}, \theta_{rwa}) \quad (3)$$

where H_s is the value of significant wave height and carries the main information regarding the “intensity” of the wave sea-state. The coefficient $C_{aw}=C_{aw}(U_{STW}, \theta_{rwa})$ embodies the interaction between the ship specific response function of added resistance in waves and the directional characteristics of the wave field. In the first implementation of the system a very simple structure is assumed for it, i.e. only the dependence on ship Speed Through Water U_{STW} and on the ship-relative average wave direction θ_{rwa} are accounted for in a phenomenological way (more details on this first approximation are given in 2.2.1 subsection). In further developments of the system, more detailed approaches to the pre-computing of C_{aw} will be adopted, allowing to account for the dependence on other parameters, e.g. $C_{aw}=C_{aw}(U_{STW}, \theta_{rwa}, \sigma_\theta, T_p, \sigma_T)$, where T_p is wave peak period, and σ_θ , σ_T are the spreadings along the wave direction and wave period dimensions of the directional wave spectrum. The dependence on these parameters could be used to store in the LUT specific ship responses in correspondence of swell and wind wave sea states. Moreover, a further generalization of this approach could allow to treat multimodal seaways, by adding a term for each spectral component, *Lawford et al. (2008)*, when partitioned spectral data, *Tracy et al. (2007)*, are available from wave spectral models, *Orlandi and Bruzzone (2011)*, *Besio et al. (2017)*. The estimation of C_{aw} LUTs will be performed, in the off-line phase, by numerical integration of the products of ship added resistance in wave response function with directional wave spectra, *Lewis (1990)*, *Orlandi and Bruzzone (2011)*, or by adopting simplified approaches, e.g. see *Cepowsky (2010)*, *van Den Boom et al. (2013)*. In further development, a similar approach will be extended to threat other seakeeping responses, *Lewis (1990)*, and to include them in the route optimization process, accounting also for safety of navigation, comfort on-board, mission specific operability limits and ship specific structural thresholds.

Once the total ship resistance is computed, based on Eqs.(1)-(3), , the corresponding fuel consumption is determined, by picking the right value of the fuel consumption rate from the respective powering LUT. In such a LUT, fuel consumption rate values are stored, after off-line pre-computing, *Carlton (2007)*, over the needed range of ship speed, and for several values of the engine load, i.e. of the values of the total resistance R_{tot} .

An interesting perspective offered by the availability of measurements during ship voyages, as planned in the PROFUMO system, is the possible integration of meteo-marine and ship performance data to implement “big-data processing” algorithms finalized to check and/or tune the ship specific LUTs. This could allow to cope with some of the deficiencies of numerical ship hydrodynamics, *Dern et al. (2015)*, by exploiting the availability of large datasets of in-service measured data, *Dinham-Peren and Dand (2010)*, *Perera and Mo (2017)*, *Gonzalez et al. (2017)*. In a future perspective, the availability of meteo and sea-state measurements from on-board sensors, also capable of estimating directional wave spectra, could be exploited, by system identification algorithms, to retrieve or tune the structure of ship specific response functions, as the above described $C_{aw}=C_{aw}(U_{STW}, \theta_{rwa}, \sigma_\theta, T_p, \sigma_T)$. Very interesting in this perspective are wave spectral measurements from on-board X-band radars, *Ludeno et al. (2014)*, *Benetazzo et al. (2018)*, and/or ship motions measurement, *Nielsen and Jensen (2016)*.

This approach could be further synergistically integrated with wind tunnel and ship model basin experimental measurements on scale models.

2.2.1. Toy model for the first numerical tests

The first computational tests of the system have been performed by considering a dataset corresponding to a ro-ro ship of about 167 m length, already studied in *Orlandi et al. (2015)*. Data for the calm water resistance and regarding the ship propulsion system (bare hull, propeller, and engines) are those adopted in that study. For the definition of the values of the coefficients for wind resistance $C_x(\theta_{rwi})$ and for added resistance in waves $C_{aw}(U_{STW}, \theta_{rwa})$ described above a very simplified approach has been adopted. A sort of “toy model” with several (numerically) interchangeable alternative variants has been defined, by considering different parametrisations of these coefficients. The goal of this model is not to describe a real ship, it is instead aimed to test the effects of several simple, but physically plausible, combinations of the wind and waves added resistance terms, accounting for different relative magnitudes and different directional dependencies. Fig.1(left) shows the three different alternatives adopted for C_x .

Fig.1: Adopted alternatives for the ship wind resistance coefficient C_x (left panel: “Cos”, “Cont”=Containership, “Pass”=Passenger ship), and for the added resistance coefficient C_{aw} (center “Smooth”, right “Choppy”) for the R_{aw} “High” variant. The adopted sign convention is: C_x , C_{aw} and consequently R_{wind} , R_{aw} are positive when resistance is opposed to ship motion.

The black continuous line shows a simple cosine-like shape (“Cos”), an approach similar to *Hughes (1932)*, that represents the smoothest alternative for C_x . The other two dashed (blue) and dot-dashed (red) lines show data borrowed from literature, for a containership (“Cont”), *Journèe (2003)*, and a passenger ship (“Pass”), *Fujiwara et al. (2006)*.

The center and right panels of Fig.1 show the adopted dependencies for C_{aw} as a function of the relative average wave direction and ship speed. Two phenomenological variants for the angular dependency have been defined. The “Smooth” one (center panel) is considered to correspond to the interaction of the ship with a seaway characterized by a wide wave directional spreading (as in the case of wind sea), that tends to strongly smooth the details of the directional structure of the R_{aw} response function, that can be considered as “dressed” by the wide spectral form. The “Choppy” one (right panel) has structure details to be directly traced to the directional structure of the “bare” R_{aw} response function. This situation is considered to correspond to the interaction with a seaway with very narrow directional spreading (typical of a swell). A linear dependence on ship speed is assumed for C_{aw} in the range of ship speed U_{STW} from 16 to 25 kn, discretized here with steps of 1 kn, as shown. The values of C_{aw} have been tuned in two different variants. The one shown in Fig.1 is defined as “High” and gives, through Eq.(2), estimates of the added resistance R_{aw} in accordance with those computed by the PDSTRIP strip theory program, *Bertram et al. (2006)*. At 19 Knots, with $H_s=2.5$ m in head waves, Eq. (2) gives R_{aw} of about 200 kN. In order to account for the variability of values that can be found by different approaches available in the literature, e.g. *Bertram and Couser (2014)*, a “Low” dataset has

been generated by scaling down the “High” data to fit, in head waves, those from *Cepowsky (2010)*. These give values of R_{aw} (for $H_s=2.5$ m) of about 125 kN.

The powering part of the ship numerical model LUT summarizes the fuel consumption performance of the hull-propeller-engine system, as determined from ship main dimensions and Wärtsilä technical manuals, *Wärtsilä (2001)*. The engines system is composed of four Wärtsilä 12V46-B diesel engines, delivering 11700 kW each at 100% load (at 514 RPM). In this paper a single configuration of propulsive engines has been modelled (all four propulsive engines active), with a fixed combinator rule (the modelled ship has two CPP propellers). In a more generalised optimal routing philosophy, besides route shape, time windows and speed profile optimization, also engine settings (active propulsive engines number and type in relation with ship speed), and propellers pitch-revolutions combinator rules (e.g. see *Coraddu et al. (2013)*) could be included in the optimization space, by computing diverse powering LUTs, for different propulsive configurations. Obviously all in the limits allowed by the available computing power for optimisation (“Course of dimensionality”, *Bellman (1957)*).

2.3. Route optimisation component

The route optimisation algorithms DIJK3, utilised in all the implementations of the first versions of PROFUMO Demo system has been developed in recent years by the project partner Aleph s.r.l. It implements a new kind of approach to the vessel routing problem. Avoiding the discretisation of the research domain into a graph, the algorithm explores the domain and produces solutions for every given point from a single origin (port of departure) or destination (port of arrival). It has been designed to resolve general minimum cost path searching problem in continuous domain and in nonstationary condition by Aleph. It has been integrated in PROFUMO for the first time, within the complete meteo-marine forecasting and route optimisation chain.

A relevant peculiarity of DIJK3 is that it allows to implement customised cost functions in a very straightforward and general way. Based on this, different approaches to the combined effect of wind and waves on total resistance, as those described in the precedent paragraph, can be adopted and simply integrated within the route optimisation algorithm.

3. Case study analysis

A wide set of ship “toy model” variants came out from the possibility of having one of the three Cx variants (“Cos”, “Cont”, “Pass”), and one of the possible “High” or “Low” scaled dataset for C_{aw} , whose directional dependence may be “Smooth” or “Choppy”. A relevant meteo-marine case study has been selected and several voyages have been simulated going from Gibraltar to Port Said (“GiSa” voyages) and vice-versa (“SaGi” voyages). Another analyzed variable is the Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA): for each selected added resistance combination and voyage, 19 different times of arrival have been considered, in steps of one hour. This is relevant for the routing service: in certain shipping services, the times of departure and/or of arrival can be varied (in the limits of suitable windows) searching for better voyage conditions. As a last variant, two constant ship speed conditions have been considered: 19 Knots and 24 Knots. Differences in ship speed induce different fuel consumption due to the different values of resistance components, but also due to a gradually differing sequence of the encountered meteo marine conditions.

The meteo-marine conditions in the selected case study are shown in Fig.2, through significant wave height maps from LaMMA forecasting system. In left panel, the situation in one of the initial hours of the voyage is shown. In right panel the situation in one of the final hours is shown. A wide area of very strong eastward winds (not shown, but indirectly guessable from waves) generates heavy sea states, oriented in zonal direction towards East, over great part of the central and east Mediterranean Sea. Such a pattern drifts towards the eastern part of the basin, reducing its zonal extension and modifying, with a rotation of winds (and correspondingly waves) in the heaviest area that finally assume meridian

direction, from South to North. In this case, the exchange “GiSa”-“SaGi” (that is obviously not relevant for operational purposes) allows to analyze the differences introduced by a sort of “inversion” of the encountered meteo-marine condition: most of SaGi voyages have head heavy weather, while GiSa voyages have prevalently following heavy weather.

Fig.2: Significant wave height pattern for the selected case study. Left panel: one of the initial hours of the voyages. Right panels: one of the final hours of the voyage.

Fig.3 shows the solution that can be obtained with zero meteorological wind (i.e. only ship rel. speed) and zero waves (i.e. completely calm weather conditions). This solution is the geometrically shortest one, of about 3486 km (1882 NM). At the two considered speeds of 19 and 24 kn, it requires ~99 h and 33 h of voyage, and 248 t and 325 t of fuel, respectively. These data can be considered as baseline values to be compared with the results of all the studied variants.

Fig.3: Gibraltar-Port Said/Port Said-Gibraltar (“Gi-Sa”/“Sa-Gi”) shortest route: no wind, no wave solution.

Fig.4: Total fuel consumption data for minimum fuel optimized routes versus ETA delay for “GiSa” (left) and “SaGi” (right) voyages at 24 Knots. Wind resistance: “Cos” (black), “Cont” (blue), “Pass” (red). Added resistance in waves: upper curves, “Smooth High” (Sm Hi); lower curves, “Chopy High” (Ch Hi).

In Fig.4 total fuel consumption data for minimum fuel optimized routes are plotted versus the 19 variants of the ETA. Such variants are in steps of 1 hour w.r.t. 2017/01/11 at 04:00 UTC. The variants in Fig.4 are characterized by: ship speed 24 Knots and R_{aw} “High”. In the left panel the “GiSa” and in the right the “SaGi” voyages data are plotted. In each plot both the “Smooth” and the “Choppy” results are shown. The “Smooth” data are the upper curves and the “Choppy” are the lower curves for both “SaGi” and “Gisa”. This feature marks the main difference emerged from the study: the “Choppy” C_{aw} shape generates lower fuel consumption (it is strongly anisotropic and gives markedly less resistance for following waves) than the “Smooth” one. As expected, far less differences emerged from the different variants of wind resistance coefficient C_x , these are visible comparing black, blue and red lines. These latter differences, together with the overall total fuel consumption, increase in passing from “GiSa” to “SaGi” voyages, in accordance with the fact that in “SaGi” voyages head heavy weather is encountered. The dependency on the ETA delay shows interesting potential fuel savings if ETA time windows are available, but mainly in the “Smooth” version.

The corresponding optimized route shapes are shown in Fig.5, with corresponding plot panels positions: left “GiSa”, right “SaGi”, top “Smooth”, bottom “Choppy”. Only results obtained with the “Cos” wind resistance are shown. Optimized routes for different values of ETA are referred to different colors of the shown palette. The same palette bar is shown over the horizontal axis in Fig.4. A relevant difference emerging is that, with the more anisotropic “Choppy” wave resistance, a sort of “tacking” behavior emerges in the optimized route shapes, characterized by several cusps of rapid ship heading variation. In the “SaGi” case, “Choppy” (bottom, right panel) the last two ETA delay values imply route passing very near the Egyptian and Libyan coast. This can be traced to the fact that the strong anisotropy of “Choppy” resistance does not allow to conveniently cross the very heavy weather area visible in right panel of Fig.2, and obliges the solution to find lower sea states in coastal waters. This kind of solution could be filtered out in real applications of the system, as a consequence of constraints on the minimal distance from coast. Analogously, the greater fuel consumption due to the “Smooth” wave resistance imply the possibility of longer optimal routes for certain values of ETA delay. In such cases the exploitation of the wave shadowing effect of Crete Island becomes viable and some optimized routes pass north of it, with “Smooth” wave resistance.

Fig.5: Minimum fuel optimized routes for “GiSa” (left) and “SaGi” (right) voyages at 24 Knots. Colour palette is for ETA delay values w.r.t. 2011/01/11 04:00 UTC. Wind resistance “Cos”. Added resistance in waves: top panels, “Smooth High”; bottom panels, “Choppy High”.

This point is further illustrated in Fig.6, where, only for the “GiSa” voyages, the optimized routes lengths are shown, for both “Smooth” (continuous) and “Choppy” (dashed), and for all wind resistance variants (black, blue, red). As apparent, in the “Smooth” variants, the first 8 values of ETA delay (blue, green routes) imply markedly longer routes.

In Fig.7 results for “SaGi” voyages at ship speed of 19 Knots, with R_{aw} “Low” are shown. In left panel, total fuel consumption for all the minimum fuel optimized routes are shown. In right panel, optimal route shapes are shown, only for the cases with “Pass” wind resistance coefficient (corresponding to

the red lines in the left panel).

Fig.6: Total length for minimum fuel optimized routes versus ETA delay for “GiSa” voyages at 24 kn. Wind resistance: “Cos” (black), “Cont” (blue), “Pass” (red). Added resistance in waves: upper continuous curves, “Smooth High”; lower dashed curves, “Choppy High”.

Fig.7: Total fuel consumption data (left) and route shapes (right) for minimum fuel optimized routes versus ETA delay for “SaGi” voyages at 19 kn. Wind resistance: “Cont”. Added resistance in waves: “Low”, upper “Smooth”, lower “Choppy”.

In these cases, the wind resistance term effects are more relevant due to lower values of both R_{hull} (smaller due to lower speed) and R_{aw} (smaller due to lower speed and to “Low” variant). Interesting features emerge in both total fuel and route shapes plots.

A complete analysis of the huge amount of data is still not available and the work is still ongoing, but some preliminary general clues are summarized below. They are expressed in terms of percentage (%) increments of fuel consumption and of optimal route length, w.r.t. the (shortest) calm weather solution of Fig.3:

- i) The most relevant term is the added resistance in waves, it adds up to 16% for fuel.
- ii) The directional structure of such term emerged as very relevant in comparing the effects of a strongly anisotropic shape, peaked in head waves, with a much smoother one. The former producing lower fuel increments up to 3-5%, versus 10-16% of the latter.
- iii) Differences in wind resistance coefficient induced fuel increment variations from a fraction of, up to few points of %. Wind added resistance is more relevant in head wind conditions, with smaller values of ship speed through water, i.e. when the other resistance components are relatively smaller.
- iv) Differences in optimal route length increments are usually of the order of 0.5%, but in some cases may arrive up to 2.5%.

v) Variations in ETA may induce fuel increment variations from few points of %, up to about 10%.

vi) Head versus following heavy weather produces differences in fuel increments of 2-4%.

Some of these considerations must be supported by further investigations, due to the idealised character of part of the adopted ship “toy model”. In particular, while interesting clues can be extracted regarding the effects, on optimal route solutions, of the different added resistance approximations, very prudent conclusions can be drawn from these results regarding estimates of realistic fuel saving potential.

4. Conclusions

A system based on the integration of meteo-marine forecast and ship performance models with a route optimization algorithm has been implemented for the development of weather routing services at the Mediterranean scale. The results of the first numerical tests of the system, are described in this paper. They have been performed for benchmarking the algorithmic suite and to put in evidence the effect, on the optimized routes, of different simplified approaches to the computation of meteo-related added resistance components by a sensitivity analysis with typical ro-ro ship data, in a relevant heavy weather case study.

A first schematic synthesis of the results coming out from the large number of obtained routing solutions have been given, and the main point emerged are:

- Added resistance in waves is the most relevant meteo-marine term, contributing to fuel consumption for up to 16%, w.r.t. the calm weather solution. Relevant effects emerged from the tested different directional dependency of such term.
- Wind added resistance implies fuel consumption variations up to some point of percentage w.r.t. the calm weather condition. It becomes more relevant in strong head wind, at low ship speeds (when the other components are lower).
- Also the geometrical shape of the routes may vary considerably, but with quite limited variations in total route length, except in few cases of length variations up to 2.5% w.r.t. the geodetic solution.
- The exploitation of time windows in ETA (and correspondingly in Time Of Departure) may allow interesting fuel savings, up to about 10%.

A relevant feature emerged from this analysis is the importance of correctly parametrising the added resistance in waves for least fuel optimal routing. Also wind added resistance coefficients may influence the optimal solutions, but generally to a quite lesser extent.

A wider and more detailed study is needed to correctly generalize these findings, that are at the moment limited to the performed case study and characterized by a simplified ship modelling approach.

References

ABS (2014), *Ship energy efficiency measures advisory*, American Bureau of Shipping

ANTONINI, A.; BENEDETTI, R.; ORTOLANI, A.; ROVAI, L.; SCHIAVON, G. (2014), *Water vapour probabilistic retrieval using GNSS signals*, IEEE Trans. Geoscience and Remote Sensing 52/3, pp.1892-1900

BACKALOV, I.; BULIAN, G.; ROSEN, A.; SHIGUNOV, V.; THEMELIS, N. (2016), *Improvement of ship stability and safety in intact conditions through operational measures: challenges and opportunities*, Ocean Eng. 120, pp.353-361

BELLMAN, R.E. (1957), *Dynamic programming*, Princeton Univ. Press

BENETAZZO, A.; SERAFINO, F.; BERGAMASCO, F.; LUDENO, G.; ARDHUIN, F.; SUTHERLAND, P.; SCLAVO, M.; BARBARIOL, F. (2018), *Stereo imaging and X-band radar wave data fusion: An assessment*, Ocean Engineering 152, pp.346-352

BERTRAM, V. (2017), *Some heretic thoughts on ISO19030*, 2nd HullPIC Conf., Ulrichshusen

BERTRAM, V.; COUSER, P. (2014), *Computational methods for seakeeping and added resistance in waves*, 13th COMPIT Conf., Redworth

BERTRAM, V.; VELO B.; SÖDING H. (2006), *Program PDSTRIP: public domain strip method*, Software documentation

CARLTON, J.S. (2007), *Marine propellers and propulsion*, Elsevier

CEPOWSKI, T. (2010), *Design guidelines for predicting wave resistance of ro-ro ferries at the initial designing stage*, Scientific Journals Maritime University of Szczecin 22(94), pp.5-9

CHU, P.C.; MILLER, S.E.; HANSEN, J.A. (2015), *Fuel-saving ship route using the Navy's ensemble meteorological and oceanic forecasts*, J. Defense Modeling and Simulation: Applications, Methodology, Technology 12(1), pp.41-56

CORADDU, A.; FIGARI, M.; SAVIO, S.; VILLA, D.; ORLANDI, A. (2013), *Integration of seakeeping and powering computational techniques with meteo-marine forecasting data for in-service ship energy assessment*, Sustainable Maritime Transportation and Exploitation of Sea Resources, Taylor& Francis Group

DERN, J-C.; QUENEZ, J.-M.; WILSON, P. (2015), *Compendium of Ship Hydrodynamics. Practical Tools and Applications*, Les Presses de L'ENSTA

DINHAM-PEREN, T.A.; DAND, I.D. (2010), *The need for full scale measurements*, William Froude Conference: Advances in Theoretical and Applied Hydrodynamics – Past and Future, Portsmouth

DNV-GL (2014), *Energy management study 2014*, DNV GL

DNV-GL (2017), *Maritime forecast to 2050, Energy Transition Outlook 2017*, DNV GL

FUJIWARA, T.; UENO, M.; IKEDA, Y. (2006), *Cruising performance of a large passenger ship in heavy sea*, 16th Int. Offshore and Polar Engineering Conf., San Francisco

GONZALEZ, C.; LUND, B.; HAGESTUEN, E. (2017), *Case study: ship performance evaluation by application of big data*, 2nd HullPIC Conf., Ulrichshusen

GUNKEL, J.; DIETZ, J.; PURUP, N. (2017), *Trim optimization in an operational environment using existing sensor installations*, 2nd HullPIC Conf., Ulrichshusen

HOFFSCHILDT, M.; BIDLOT, J.-R.; HANSEN, B.; JANSSEN, P.A.E.M. (1999), *Potential benefit of ensemble forecasts for ship routing*, ECMWF Research Department Tech. Memo. 287, ECMWF, Reading

HUGHES, G. (1032), *The air resistance of ship's hulls with various types and distributions of superstructures*, Inst. E. & S. in Scot. 75

IMO (2011), *MARPOL Annex VI, Resolutions: MEPC.203(62)*, IMO, London

IMO (2014), *Resolution MSC.64(67), annex 1, Recommendation on performance standards for*

integrated bridge systems (IBS), IMO, London

JOURNEE, J.M.J. (2003), *Review of the 1979 and 1980 full-scale experiment onboard containership M.V. Hollandia*, Report 1349, TU Delft

KALNAY, E. (2003), *Atmospheric Modeling, Data Assimilation and Predictability*, Cambridge Univ. Press, pp.341

KANO, T. (2017), *On the effect of navigation support system – From collecting data to Operational support*, 2nd HullPIC Conf., Ulrichshusen

LAWFORD, R.; BRADON, J.; BARBERON, T.; CAMPS, C.; JAMESON, R. (2008), *Directional wave partitioning and its applications to the structural analysis of an FPSO*, 27th Int. Conf. Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering, Volume 2: Structures, Safety and Reliability

LEWIS, E.V. (1990), *Principles of naval architecture, Vol.3*, SNAME

LUDENO, G.; ORLANDI, A.; LUGNI, C.; BRANDINI, C.; SOLDOVIERI, F.; SERAFINO, F. (2014), *X-Band marine radar system for high-speed navigation purposes: A test case on a cruise ship*, IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters 11(1), pp.244-248

LUND, B.; GONZALEZ, C. (2017), *The big data concept in a performance monitoring perspective*, 2nd HullPIC Conf., Ulrichshusen

NIELSEN, U.D.; JENSEN, J.J. (2011), *A novel approach for navigational guidance of ships using onboard monitoring systems*, Ocean Eng. 38, pp.444-455

ORLANDI, A. (2014), *Detailed powering and seakeeping forecasting for minimal fuel consumption in the next generation weather routing algorithms*, SNAME Western Europe Section, London

ORLANDI, A.; BRANDINI, C.; PASI, F.; TADDEI, S.; DORONZO, B.; BRUGNONI, G.; ROSSINI, G.; BENEDETTI R.; GOZZINI, B.; ORTOLANI, A.; VACCARI, F.P. (2009), *Implementation of a meteo marine forecasting chain and comparison between modelled and observed data in the Ligurian and Tyrrhenian seas*, Volume sulle attività di ricerca scientifica e tecnologica del CNR nell'ambito del mare e delle sue risorse, CNR, Rome

ORLANDI, A.; BRUZZONE, D. (2011), *Numerical weather and wave prediction models for weather routing, operation planning and ship design: The relevance of multimodal wave spectra*, Sustainable Maritime Transportation and Exploitation of Sea Resources, Taylor& Francis

ORLANDI, A.; PASI, F.; CAPECCHI, V.; CORADDU, A.; VILLA, D. (2015), *Powering and seakeeping forecasting for energy efficiency: assessment of the fuel savings potential for weather routing by in-service data and ensemble prediction*, IMAM Conf., Taylor & Francis

PAPANIKOLAOU, A. (2011), *Holistic ship design optimization: merchant and naval ships*, Ship Science and Technology 5/9

PATEY, M. (2012), *Software Systems for Eco-Efficiency in Ship Design and Operation*, NAPA User Meeting

PATRAIKO, E.D. (2007), *Introducing the e-Navigation Revolution*. Seaways, Int. J. Nautical Institute

PERERA, L.P.; GUEDES SOARES, C. (2017), *Weather routing and safe ship handling in the future of shipping*. Ocean Eng. 130, pp. 684-695

- PERERA, L.P.; MO, B. (2017), *Handling big-data in ship performance and navigation monitoring*, Maritime industry IoT developments, Supplement to The Naval Architect, RINA
- REHMATULLA, N.; CALLEYA, J.; SMITH, T. (2017). *The implementation of technical energy efficiency and CO2 emission reduction measures in shipping*, Ocean Eng. 139, pp. 184-197
- SAIL (2015), *Final Report. Roadmap for sail transport: Engineering*, SAIL Project, EU Interreg IVB
- SIMONSEN, M. H., LARSSON, E.; MAO, W.; RINGSBERG, J.W. (2015), *State-of-the-art within ship weather routing*, 34th Int. Conf. Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering, St. John's
- SKAMAROCK, W.C.; KLEMP, J.B. (2008), *A time-split non-hydrostatic atmospheric model for weather research and forecasting applications*. Journal of Computational Physics 227, pp.3465-3485
- SPENTZA, E.; BESIO, G.; MAZZINO, A.; GAGGERO, T.; VILLA, D. (2017), *A ship weather-routing tool for route evaluation and selection: influence of the wave spectrum*, IMAM Conf., Taylor & Francis
- SZELANGIEWICZ, T.; ZELAZNY, K. (2006), *Calculation of mean long-term service speed of transport ships, Part I*, Polish Maritime Research 4, pp.23-31
- TILLIG, F.; MAO, W.; RINGSBERG, J.W. (2015), *Systems modelling for energy-efficient shipping*. Chalmers TU, Dept. Shipping and Marine Technology, Division of Marine Technology, Report No. 15
- TRACY, B.E.M.; DEVALIERE, J.L.; HANSON, T.; NICOLINI, T.; TOLMAN, H.L. (2007), *Wind sea and swell delineation for numerical wave modeling*, 10th Int. Workshop on Wave Hindcasting and Forecasting 12
- VAN DEN BOOM, H.; HUISMAN, H.; MENNE, F. (2013), *New Guidelines for Speed/Power Trials Level playing field established for IMO EEDI*, SWZ Maritime 134, pp.18-22
- VANEM, E. (2014), *e-maritime services for communication with class and for enhanced safety, security and environmental protection in shipping*, Int. J. Traffic and Transport Eng. 4(3), pp.234-252
- VOSSEN, C.; KLEPPE, R.; HJØRUNGNES, S.R. (2013), *Ship Design and System Integration*, DMK Conf.
- WALTHER, L.A.; RIZVANOLLI, M.; WENDEBOURG, C.J. (2016), *Modelling and Optimization Algorithms in Ship Weather Routing*, Int. J. e-Navigation and Maritime Economy 4, pp.31-45
- WÄRTSILÄ (2001), *W 12V46 Diesel Engine Project Guide*, Wärtsilä Marine
- WATANABE, I.; VAN NGUYEN, T.; MIYAKE, S.; SHIMIZU, N.; IKEDA, Y. (2016), *A study on reduction of air resistance acting on a large container ship*, 8th Asia-Pacific Workshop on Marine Hydrodynamics in Naval Architecture, Ocean Technology and Constructions
- WIŚNIEWSKI, B.; SZYMAŃSKI, M. (2016), *Comparison of ship performance optimization systems and the bon voyage onboard routing system*, Scientific Journals Zeszyty Naukowe of the Maritime University of Szczecin 47/119, pp.106-115
- WW3, (2016), WAVEWATCH III R Development Group (WW3DG), *User manual and system documentation of WAVEWATCH III R version 5.16*, Tech. Note 329, NOAA/NWS/NCEP/MMAB, College Park, MD, USA.

Design Patterns for Digital Twin Solutions in Marine Systems Design and Operations

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Abstract

In this paper, we describe a set of design patterns for digital twins. In a digital twin the identity, state and behavior of a real asset, such as a ship, a semisubmersible, an offshore wind turbine or a fish farm, is captured in a virtual model in close to real time. We use design patterns to describe reusable solution templates that can be applied to different classes of marine systems design and operation problems. These patterns combine core digital model building blocks, such as onboard sensor observations of loads or responses, physics-based analysis components, as well as data stream analytics.

1. Introduction

Digital Twin technologies have recently received considerable attention, also within the maritime industries. A digital twin is a virtual model that captures the state and behavior of a real asset, such as a ship, a semisubmersible, an offshore wind turbine or a fish farm, in close to real time, based on sensor input. The virtual model resolution can be based on physics, e.g. structural mechanics and fluid mechanics, or artificial intelligence and machine learning. A digital twin can be considered an extension of engineering simulation and analysis models, but where the state rendering and corresponding derived performance is based on real-time sensor observations rather than anticipated load cases.

In the maritime industry, digital twin implementations are typically complementing a range of other digital asset technologies, ranging from advanced analysis models, product lifecycle models, CFD and FEA, and increasingly big data and machine learning. In this paper, we will consider these different technologies not as alternatives, but rather as complementary technologies that can be combined to achieve important insights into marine systems design and operations.

2.1 Intrinsic characteristics of a digital twin

A Digital Twin can be defined as “a digital model capable of rendering state and behavior of a unique real asset in (close to) real time”. A further dissection of this definition points to the following five core characteristics:

- **Identity**, by connecting to a single, real and unique physical asset, such as a ship, a semisubmersible, a riser, or a wind turbine. When we observe a state on the DT, it corresponds one-to-one with a potential observation on a particular physical asset. In an ideal world, a 1-to-1 cardinality between asset and twin would be preferable. However, pragmatic considerations may imply a 1-to-N cardinality, with several more-or-less well-connected twins, each covering a subset of relevant physics dimensions, IP scope, stakeholder perspectives, sub-systems or processes.
- **Representation**, which implies the capturing of essential physical manifestation of the real asset in a digital format, such as CAD or engineering models with corresponding metadata.
- **State**, which demarcates a DT from a traditional CAD/CAE model, by having the capability to render quantifiable measures of the asset’s state in (close to) real time.
- **Behavior** – reflecting basic responses to external stimuli (forces, temperatures, chemical processes, etc.) in the present context.
- **Context** – describing external operating context, such as wind, waves, temperature, etc., in which the asset exists in or operates within.

There is no universal acceptance for these characteristics being required, or even sufficient. The interpretation of the concept of a digital twin is multi-faceted and varies substantially among different players. Thus, this list should rather be understood as our interpretation, as a backdrop for design patterns to be presented later.

Further, the digital twin is not an end product in itself. Rather it is an “opportunity maker” by acting as a live, rich data source, both beyond what can be offered by point-based sensor configurations and beyond what is directly observable. The opportunities to exploit this opportunity are many and diverse. Thus, in this paper we will outline some of these opportunities in a structured way, by proposing what we consider important patterns for digital twin driven solutions, and by providing examples of how these can provide additional insight and improved decision support in industrial asset management processes.

2. Design patterns

The rationale for using design patterns is observation that there is not one single design for developing digital twin solutions, nor is every solution unique. We tend to be somewhere in the middle, with a mix of commonalities and unique features. These commonalities we try to capture in a design pattern.

The classical text on design patterns is *Gamma et al. (1994)* – often referred to as the “Gang of Four” (GoF). The 23 patterns described in this book is by many considered the foundation for all other patterns. Thus, the digital twin patterns described in this paper are heavily inspired by their work.

The GoF patterns are grouped into creational, structural and behavioral. Creational patterns in software engineering captures how objects are instantiated. This group includes ‘Abstract Factory’ (creating families of objects), ‘Prototype’ (creation by copying) and ‘Singleton’ (creating on globally accessible instance). The digital twin parallel would comprise patterns related to the instantiation of the virtual model and the corresponding behavior implementation.

Fig.1: Design Patterns by *Gamma (1994)*

The GoF structural patterns captures how classes and objects are composed in a (software) system. Examples are the Façade pattern providing a simplified interface to complex sub-systems, the ‘Proxy’ pattern deriving a surrogate object as a placeholder, the Composite pattern generalizing parent-child

hierarchies, and Adapter enabling reusable objects. Similarly, for digital twins the structural patterns will describe how the DT building blocks can be composed to realize a specific solution.

Behavioral patterns in the GoF book describes how objects interact and communicate, and relates to the system's control flow. Examples are the 'Observer' pattern on how state changes can be notified without direct couplings, the 'Memento' pattern for storing state time series, and the 'Visitor' pattern for separating state and behavior. Behavioral patterns for digital twin will be somewhat different, focusing more on how the output from virtual model can be further exploited to provide insights that have a more concrete value in various business process. This can be pattern recognition for anomaly detection using machine learning, or aggregating stress amplitudes for fatigue life prediction.

3. Design patterns for digital twins

The Design Pattern book, *Gamma et al. (1994)*, was a result of decades of accumulated experience from real software system implementations. For digital twins, the situation is different. Though some of the predecessors of current twins can be traced back to the early 1990s, we do not have the same track record in this field as with object-oriented software systems. Thus, the list of patterns presented here should be regarded as a first proposal, to be discussed within the engineering community with respect to both their existence on the list, as well as their definition.

Only to some extent we follow the same grouping as in *Gamma et al. (1994)*, by keeping the 'structural' and 'creational' groups, but splitting the behavioral pattern group into two. Insight patterns relates to the provision of engineering insight based on digital twin output (functional value), while 'computational' patterns focus on how the solution can operate efficiently with respect to computation, storage and communication (form aspects). Also, with respect to completeness, the list of patterns is expected to be extended.

Thus, we propose the following pattern structure:

1. Structural patterns - relating to the composition of the main building blocks constituting the core digital twin solution. We consider
 - a. PDM– DT history based on Product Data Models
 - b. Big data– skeleton twin for “petabytes-of-data” isolated sensor streams
 - c. Baseline– reference twin based on physics-based model behavior
 - d. Load-based – sensor observation of operating context rather than asset response
 - e. Benchmark – DT and simulation in parallel for detecting asset anomalies
 - f. ML Proxy – twin behavior based on machine learning rather than physics
2. Creational patterns - relating to how the digital twin solution is realized
 - a. Proxy by simulation – DT reinforcement learning by simulation
 - b. Dynamic hybrid – context aware switching between physics and machine learning
 - c. Multi-asset – deriving additional fleet members by prototyping
3. Insight patterns - relating to how the digital twin is used together with other resources to create (engineering) insight
 - a. Anomaly patterns – time series analysis detecting deviation behavior
 - b. Root cause – reversed analytics of digital twin for deep, causal understanding
 - c. Foresight – switching the twin from trailing to scouting
4. Computational patterns - relating to how the digital twin solution can be realized efficiently
 - a. Smart storage – avoiding big data fallacy (3V (Already in 2001, Doug Laney warned about the challenges of Big Data related to the three Vs: Volume, Velocity and Variety)) by fidelity-controlled regression
 - b. Offloading – controlled dynamic regression offloading full physics analysis

Of these patterns, we will provide the details only for those in the structural categories.

4. Digital Twin Building Blocks

Table I summarizes the core components being part of the digital twin (structural) patterns.

Symbol	Component	Description
RA	Real asset	The Thing for which we want to create a virtual model.
S	Sensor (real)	A device to provide observations of relevant characteristics of the real asset or its environment. Also defined as a “source that produces a value representing a quality of a phenomenon”, <i>Compton et al. (2009)</i>
DT	Digital twin	The virtual model that reflects the Real Asset in close to real time
OpCtx	Operating Context	The external environment in which the real asset operates. For physics-based digital twins, this will typically be external loads such as waves, winds, heat, etc.

5. Structural patterns for digital twins

Structural patterns are blueprints for the core digital twin architecture. They capture important structural building blocks that links the virtual digital twin model with its real-world counterpart, thus enabling the mutual reflection of state and behavior.

The very idea of maintaining an integrated digital model of real assets go way back, as illustrated in Fig.2. In the maritime domain, one of the major first steps in this direction was the DNV Nauticus development in the mid-1990s. Originally, the project was called “Ship Product Model”, aimed at linking together all information related to the vessels in the DNV fleet into a common repository, where all new and updated information would be immediately available to everyone having access to the system. Thus, it was a digital model reflecting the state of a real asset, but having neither physical sensor observations nor real time behavior computation. (However, the steel thickness measurements by surveyors were input to hull structural strength re-analysis, which to some extent is a predecessor to current capabilities.) With the definition of a digital twin we provided in Section 2.1 the product model does not qualify, but we have still included the corresponding design pattern, PDM Twin, among the structural patterns to provide a historical reference.

Fig.2: Consecutive generations of digital product models and digital twins

Along with the rapidly development of both low-cost sensors and communication technologies, systems and asset increasingly came online. Ship owners reported gathering petabytes of data from hundreds of on-board sensors, but more often than not without the corresponding tools, methods and models for turning data into insight relevant to support real world decision-making. However, during the last three to five years, data science and machine learning have become “commodity capabilities”, offering an opportunity to extract value from the “Big Data” investments during the last couple of decades. This is captured in the design pattern ‘Big Data Twin’.

The structural patterns are normally based on observing some relevant aspects of a real asset, and subsequently recreating this in a digital model. The observations are normally performed by sensors. In most cases, it is preferable to observe asset responses to external loads and context parameters, rather than the loads themselves, since it is these responses that we want to capture in the digital twin. This can for instance be translational or angular velocities, accelerations, temperatures, currents, etc. We consider this the archetypical design pattern for digital twins, captured in the ‘Baseline Twin’ pattern.

In many cases, we choose to observe operating context parameters, either as an alternative, or in addition, to responses. From the end user perspective, this difference is typically not important. However, from an implementation perspective, it requires the modelling of the impact of the external operating context on the asset, typically as loads. This leads to the ‘Load-based Twin’ pattern.

By combining the two aforementioned patterns, we get the ‘Benchmark’ pattern. By this we can compare the behavior of the digital twin derived from the observed responses, with the behavior predicted by the loads. If these are deviating, there is a potentially a developing fault situation.

Finally, we have the ‘ML Proxy’ pattern, where the physics-based, causal model is replaced by an experience-based machine learning model. The main differences between a physics-based approach and this is captured in Fig.3, while the pros and cons of these two approaches are further discussed later.

Fig.3: Physics-based vs. machine learning based digital twin solutions

In the following sections, each of the structural patterns will be defined in more detail, mainly using the same schema as in *Gamma et al. (1994)*. The first two patterns, the PDM and Big Data twins, are only briefly explained, since they fall outside the digital twin definition we provided in Section 2.1.

6. PDM Twin

Fig.4: PDM Twin pattern

Intent	Maintain an updated repository for an asset that records and links together all relevant information according to a common product model schema
Motivation	Before the age of low-cost sensors, communication and computational capacity, the PDM efforts were motivated by the need to bring many separate data stores together, offering a single, integrated system-of-record to be accessed by all stakeholders.
Known uses	A good example of product data technologies applied in the maritime industries is the DNV GL Nauticus system, formerly known as the Ship Product Model, <i>Løvstad and Behrens-Nilsen (1999)</i>

7. Big Data Twin

Fig.5: Big data twin

Intent	Provide a model for navigating to data streams connect to corresponding sensor observations on the real asset
Also known as	Sensor skeleton
Motivation	Providing a visual interface to sensor data, often as an integrated part of asset management systems. From a digital twin perspective, nothing is known of the state and behavior of the asset beyond these specific sensor locations, but this can be derived by analytic services on the client side.

8. Baseline Twin

Fig.6: The Baseline Twin Pattern

Intent	Replicate the state and behavior of an asset in a virtual model in close to real-time based on observed asset responses, thus providing deep and comprehensive insight applicable in multiple client applications
Also known as	Small Data Twin, Physics Expanded Asset Monitoring (PEAM)
Motivation	By combining sensor data input with physics-based analysis in real time, the state and behavior of the asset is no longer confined to the sensor locations only. This reduces significantly the installation cost and complexity on the edge, as opposed to a sensor-direct strategy where existing assets may comprise hundreds of sensors for sufficient monitoring coverage. Further, new virtual sensor locations can be added dynamically, without the need for edge retrofitting.
Applicability	The pattern is applicable to a wide range of asset types, provided that the following conditions are present:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The state and behavior of the asset can be captured in an analysis model with sufficient fidelity to explain relevant phenomena, and at the same time having a complexity level enabling low latency computations The relevant responses can be observed on the real asset with sensors within a feasible quality-to-cost interval <p>Examples of current implementations comprises land-based wind turbines and road bridges.</p>
Structure	The ‘Baseline’ pattern represents the most fundamental approach to a digital twin solution. A set of sensors are placed on the structure, providing real-time observations of the actual behavior that is fed into the digital twin model. Typically, one sensor channel is needed for each degree of freedom. The exact sensor configuration needs to be determined by taking into consideration both the physical behavior of the structure, as well as the relevant load situations.
(Participants)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RealAsset – the asset to be monitored Sensor – observe specific responses on the real asset, and transmit those to the virtual model DigitalTwin – captures the real asset state and behavior in a digital model VirtualSensor – an observation on the virtual model derived from the computational model of the digital twin
(Collaborations)	The Baseline Twin Pattern will typically form the core of a digital twin solution and will collaborate with patterns aimed at extracting and processing the virtual sensor data for additional insight and decision support.

9. Load-based Twin

Fig.7: The Load-based Twin Pattern

Intent	Replicate the state and behavior of an asset in a virtual model in close to real-time based on deriving the asset responses from observations of the operating context
Also known as	Simulation Twin, Indirect Resolution Twin
Motivation	<p>The motivation for deriving the response from observed loads and operating conditions, rather than observing the responses directly, can be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> When we already have sensors measuring load-related context parameters, such as wind speed and direction, waves, vehicles on a bridge, etc. – or that these sensors are less costly and/or easier to install When we already have simulation models bringing us from loads to responses. After all, this is what traditional engineering analysis is all about – anticipating the loads to which an asset is exposed, and then evaluating whether the calculated responses are within the requirements When we have multiple (similar) assets exposed to the same operating environment, reducing the need for sensor installation at the edge
Applicability	The pattern is applicable to a wide range of asset types, provided that the we have models capturing the interaction between the parameters describing the external operating context, the corresponding loads and interactions with the asset, and the resulting responses of the asset from this load. Using a ship as an example, we would need to derive sea loads from observed wave patterns, and further calculate, say ship motion and resulting mid-ship bending moment from these loads.

Consequences	The Load-based twin is based on the assumption that we have a model that accurately transforms loads/operating context inputs into asset responses. While this might be true for intact situations, this pattern will typically be unable to detect failure situations directly.
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10. Benchmark Twin

Fig.8: The Benchmark Twin Pattern

Intent	Continuously compare the behavior of the asset with a simulation-derived expected behavior, for early detection of anomalies and defects
Also known as	Differential Twin
Motivation	The Baseline and Load-based twin patterns enable a continuous monitoring of the actual real asset behavior through a virtual model. However, we don't know whether the responses observed are those that we should expect for a given operating situation. A common solution is to trigger alerts based on fixed threshold values. There are several disadvantages with this approach. (1) anomalies will typically be detected only in extreme situations, which may be too late for remedial action. (2) it typically implies many false positives, that is, alerts triggered by asset responses that was actually expected given the prevailing operating conditions. By the simulation of the expected behavior for an intact asset in parallel to the digital twin, deviations can be detected also for normal operating conditions, and at an earlier stage.
Consequences	From a computational point-of-view, there is an additional cost of running two, often complex, models in parallel

11. ML Proxy

Fig.9: The ML Proxy Pattern

Intent	Create a proxy digital twin model based on data science and machine learning
Motivation	The ML Proxy pattern is basically the same as the Baseline Twin pattern, with the only (but significant) difference that the (real-time) state and behavior of the model is not derived by physics, but rather based on machine learning algorithms. This has the advantage that we don't need to be able to model the physics, which in many cases is complex and costly. The flip side is that to create this model in the first place, we need to have a source for learning.

Applicability	Machine learning based	Physics based
	<p>Advantages: Model derived from data only – no need for domain knowledge Generic and flexible - handles heterogeneous data streams (also non-physics) Model improves over time (reinforcement learning) Good at discovering complex relations and patterns</p>	<p>Advantages: Models capture deep existing knowledge based on Newtonian physics Causal relationships provide insight and understanding Uncertainty controlled by input and modelling accuracy Model has universal validity – predict any point covered by model</p>
	<p>Disadvantages: The availability of training data needed to develop model Correlations, not causality. Black-box, no explanations (in particular, deep learning) Approximation methods, no exact mathematics Predictive capabilities deteriorate quickly outside training set scope Difficult to predict extreme/critical conditions (few observations)</p>	<p>Disadvantages: Require extensive domain (physics) knowledge Computationally intensive, challenge in real-time Complete assumptions about input-output must be made upfront</p>

12. Conclusion

We proposed a set of design patterns for digital twins. We believe this to be an important first step in the maturing of this field. Digital twins will serve a wide spectrum of different needs. Correspondingly, the preferred solution will be different. Design patterns provide the means to capture both the commonalities among different alternative implementations, as well as revealing the differences.

We described only the structural patterns in some detail. We will follow up with a more thorough investigation of creational, insight and computational patterns, combined with examples and industrial use cases. We currently see a rapid development of digital twin technologies. Still, there are many areas requiring fundamental research efforts. In Fig.10, we have indicated some of the key research topics we consider most important for the next five years, both for society as such, and for the maritime industries.

Fig.10: Key research topics for digital twins towards 2024

References

COMPTON, M.; HENSON, C.A.; NEUHAUS, H.; LEFORT, L.; SHETH, A.P. (2009), *A survey of the semantic specification of sensors*, CEUR Workshop 522, pp.17-32

<http://corescholar.libraries.wright.edu/knoesis/664>

ERIKSTAD, S.O.; FATHI, D. (1999), *Applying the STEP shipbuilding protocols as a basis for integrating existing in-house ship design applications*, Int. Conf. Computer Applications in Shipbuilding (ICCAS), Cambridge, pp.415-442

GAMMA, E.; HELM, R., JOHNSON, R., VLISSIDES, J. (1994), *Design Patterns – Elements of reusable object-oriented software code*, Addison-Wesley

LØVSTAD, M.; BEHRENS-NILSEN, S.H. (1999), *NAUTICUS – A lifecycle approach to ship design and decision support*, Trans. Built Environment 42, WIT Press

Fast-Track Vessel Concept Design Analysis (FTCDA)

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This paper presents the Fast-Track vessel Concept Design Analysis (FTCDA) tool, a unified design platform integrating a set of interconnected vessel concept design analyses modules. The holistic view of the FTDCDA tool combines technical, commercial, and operational perspectives. Using regression and multivariate based approximations, the time of vessel concept design development has been reduced to hours, rather than weeks in terms of process time. The overall performance of the developed concept designs is benchmarked with peer vessel alternatives.

1. Introduction

In the early phases of conceptual ship design important decisions must be made for system design concepts. Detailed evaluation of each possible solution is costly in both time and effort. So, an effective and efficient method is needed to explore the design space in terms of critical system parameters. Ship design companies typically are challenged by the need to incorporate among other perspectives; flexibility; innovation; speed; and agility to their business model. The conventional vessel concept design development process, based on work processes relating to the traditional vessel as a design spiral, has proven to be ineffective in later years, when it comes to ensuring very short customer needs response time and securing sufficient accuracy and robustness of the solutions developed. It is, very often, too time consuming and resource demanding to evaluate the appropriateness- and goodness of fit of the number of necessary vessel concept design solution alternatives to be developed and investigated for feasibility. On the other side, it is seen based on some factual numbers from designers, while conceptualization of new product consumes less than 5% of total project design and construction time, almost 90% of possible innovative design solutions take place in this step where knowledge about final product and its overall performance is still shallow, Figs.1 and 2.

Fig.1: Room for innovation in design

Fig.2: Design knowledge and design timeline,
Erikstad (1996)

Ulstein has over the years introduced and implemented an Accelerated Business Development methodology (ABD) to enhance and strengthen its capability to effectively solicit relevant stakeholders' expectations and desires when it comes to the realization of ship designs and new building projects, *Ulstein and Brett (2012)*.

The core elements of the ABD approach, which aims to better guide ship designers, yards, cargo, and ship owners in realizing a business opportunity within intermodal transport or offshore field development work whereby ship design is utilized to achieve a competitive advantage. The approach advocates that a new or improved solution system, where the ship plays a significant role, shall fulfil the needs and expectations of all the involved stakeholders in the best possible way through the multi-attribute decision

making ABD-approach. This approach makes it possible to follow the complex and normally fragmented processes of business development related to maritime transport, offshore oil & gas field, and the pertinent ship design in a systemic and explicit way. As a continual process to its ABD approach and as a response to the need of rapid solution generation and performance evaluation, in the recent year Ulstein has developed a set of interconnected vessel concept design analyses modules into what is today known as the Fast-Track vessel Concept Design Analysis tool and approach (FTCDA). By the means of different multivariate data analysis in addition to other statistical and traditional naval architecture approaches in an integrated tool environment, it has been possible to reduce the time of vessel concept design development, with acceptable accuracy and robustness, to hours, rather than weeks in terms of process and response time to the costumers and the tenders.

This paper presents the FTCDA approach as an integrated conceptual ship design and benchmarking tool that exploits synergies across different design disciplines/modules, in a unified digital analyses platform. This is to empower the designer with the ability to rapidly develop sets of viable vessel concept design solutions, rather than one solution, with permissible accuracy and robustness. The overall performance of the developed vessel concept design solutions is benchmarked with peer vessel alternatives, including existing, relevant vessels in the market, all integrated in the tool data sets for input and output. A holistic approach applied in the FTDCDA-tool combining technical, commercial, and operational perspectives, ensures a more balanced and robust design solution, compared to existing and traditional naval architectural and marine engineering work processes and practices.

In this paper, by the use of some practical design cases, it is reviewed and discussed how fast the FTCDA approach can produce the full configuration and balancing of vessel design alternatives and alterations by varying main particulars and mission required equipment in the very early ship design phase. It is also discussed and shown by specific examples, how such an approach can cater for the necessary sensitivity analysis. The paper also discusses how analytical simulation of the small changes in design particulars and mission equipment on technical, commercial and operational performance of concept design solution, can produce their resulting implications and consequences.

2. Fast track design and construction

Typically, up to mid-20th century common project delivery process has been sequential design–bid–build, with a time period between the completion of one phase and the start of the next one. However, reacting to rapidly changing market dynamics and meeting project timeline in the lowest cost have always been on the mind of project owners. Shorter schedule can lead to shorter manufacturer's time-to-market and reduce the cost of construction financing and overhead costs for the design and construction organizations. The fast-tracking of the project is therefore achieved through the integration of design and construction phases. The fast track project delivery strategy is developed to leverage the ability to perform design, procurement and construction phases simultaneously to enable project schedule reduction substantially. In this context, concurrent engineering created the necessary foundations for Fast-track design-construction. Concurrent engineering developed by Toyota in 70th generally defined as a production management philosophy, which has been widely used in the manufacturing industry over the past several decades to achieve as much as 50% reduction in product development cycle, *Bogus et al. (2002)*. The reduction in schedule is achieved by using concurrent, overlapped processes instead of sequential product and process design. Fast tracking is generally defined as the compression of the design and/or construction schedule through overlapping of activities or reduction in activity durations, *Cho et al. (2010)*. On the other sense, Fast track is commonly entitled to the projects executed using the principles of concurrent engineering to symbolize the reduction in the total schedule from design to commissioning. The design phase assumes increased importance in fast track projects because design and construction are executed almost simultaneously with tiny or no lag between design and construction. The design of industrial projects involves the design of complex and interconnected systems in which design teams from various disciplines need to continuously interact and use data from each other to ensure accurate and safe design. The performance of the design phase is dependent on smooth and timely flow of accurate information from a variety of stakeholders from different organizations that come together to execute the project. The fast track project delivery strategy is being used ever

more aggressively in industrial projects to reduce the time to the market, making the study of best practices for management of design in fast track industrial projects more forceful. The traditional approach to communicating the initial ship design process is the “design spiral”, *Evans (1959)*. This model emphasizes different design tasks should be considered in sequence, in increasing detail in each pass around the spiral, until a single design which satisfies all constraints and balances all considerations is reached. Such an approach requires a number of iterations around the spiral which is generally limited by the available time and budget. In general design spiral, follows the principals of design-bid-build approach. Ulstein FTDCA is based on concurrent engineering philosophy to shorten conceptual design process time.

A fast track conceptual design process and its related design tool box is developed to shortcut the iterative process in early design phases guiding the designer to the right design direction in the very early phase. Reduction in the time spent for iterations and eliminating part of non-value-added design works frees up the time of designers for more work on innovative solutions. Based on practical design experience in Ulstein, shorter design/project initiation lead time, less resources for concept development, better decision making support, better market fit for design solution and final product, enhanced advice to clients and increased design capacity, are expected achievements of applying a fast track approach in the early design phase, Fig.3.

Fig.3: Fast track design approach

2.1. Time and accuracy trade off

The existence of trade-offs between response time and accuracy is an important interpretative problem in choice of reaction time experiments, *Wood (1976)*. Systematic evaluation of the achieved accuracy over the allocated time to produce, conceptual design solution (response time) is a challenging issue for ship design companies. In the past, some ship owners have commented that Ulstein produces early design concepts with high precision, nonetheless at relatively higher response time compared to the competitors which has reduced the chance of further progress in some projects due to delayed response. On the other hand, it is always a risk, when designers are compelled to act quickly, they emphasize on speed rather than accuracy might lead to end up missing the goal of the task entirely or developing solutions not fulfilling the expectations or early design solutions which can be considered faulty. Hence it is realized over the time, response time and accuracy requirements are both important in design tasks but they are sometimes contradictory. *Heitz (2014)* suggests that, often the best way to approach these type of conflicting tasks is to try to move as fast as possible without sacrificing accuracy. In such circumstances making proper balance between response time and accuracy of the solution is critical early design phase decision making criteria.

Permissible achievement of accuracy level in fast track design approach is eminent issue which might lead to less optimal solution in case of negligence of appropriate balance between time and accuracy. According to practical design experience exploiting empirical equations available in the literature normally is the quickest and cheapest way to identify relevant dimension in early design solution, however lower accuracy compared to model test or hull line and 3D model generation approach creates disputes inside organization to choose the direction. As of practical experience, normally, empirical equations in the books, creates 80% computation accuracy compared to model tests. However, this value

varies among vessel segments. For instant equations for straightforward less complex ship types like tankers or bulkers can achieve up to 90% accuracy level while in offshore vessel or cruise ship design, accuracy of the calculation based on empirical equations drops in some cases even below 70%, *Ebrahimi et al. (2015a,b)*. Considering time and cost for running different type of analysis it is experienced, while vessel solution dimensioning based on empirical parametric equations in naval architecture books requires around 1 to 2 days, such response time increases up to 40 days when hull line generation, 3D modelling and CFD analysis are taken into place.

Fig.4: Fast track design time and accuracy trade-off

Fig.4 shows Ulstein FTCDCA schematically. The approach is a multidisciplinary design tool developed to fill the gap between empirical calculation and final hull line and GA development, maintaining a permissible accuracy level of the calculations. Such development has led to shorter response time compared to hull line generation and model test approaches. FTCDCA as an approach is the combination of internally developed parametric models of cleaned data sets for different vessel segments besides calibrated models on weight and power estimates based on actual data from Ulstein built vessels. Verification of the results of the tool in different conceptual design cases, has proven that, 95% confidence level is achievable. Such a significant accuracy level achievement compared to the result of model generation in different technical, commercial and operational aspects of concept development in a very short analysis time has been considerable and greatly appreciated by people especially sales and design.

2.2. Open source tools overview for fast track design application

Application of different open-source web-based tools in ship design is comprehensively discussed by *Gaspar et al. (2014)*. Open source is a development methodology (or philosophy) that is developed in a collaborative public manner as a prominent example of open collaboration, where monetary profit is secondary. Free access to the software code, allowing users to modify and improve the code is the main characteristics of open source approach. In addition, room for customization by users and independency from developer of the tool is achieved with open source technology. Higher flexibility, adoptability and less cost are other achievements in this context. Famous examples of open-source software are Linux operating systems (e.g. Ubuntu, Gentoo) and the Mozilla Firefox browser.

To develop FTDCDA user-friendly and easy to implement in the organization, combination of open source web based tools with Microsoft excel dash-board interface environment is used as a basis for the development. It is observed Excel based environment, simplifies connection of the tool to available data sets which are mainly spread around organization in different Excel sheets. However, detailed mathematical analysis is executed in visual basic and macro coding ability of the excel sheet, whilst Web-GL application in java script coding connected to the tool provides 3D model generation capability of the tool. brief overview about tools used in FTDCDA is given in the following topics.

2.2.1 Microsoft Excel dash board and Visual Basic coding

A dashboard is a visual representation of key metrics that allows to quickly view and analyse data in created user-friendly interface. Using dashboards not only provides consolidated data views, but a self-service business intelligence opportunity, where users are able to filter the data to display just what's important to them. Even though it can be argued Microsoft Excel is not open source tool and requires subscription, but it should be considered internally developed applications in the basis of excel functionalities contains some of the main criterion of open-source web based tools. For instance, while there is no possibility to make substantial changes in MS Excel software, but dashboards and tools developed in the MS Excel environment provides unlimited access to the user to implement required changes or protect the worksheets from any single changes. Visual basic and macro codes are easily accessible and sufficiently flexible to adopt developed tools to new needs of organization/market.

The Ulstein FTCDA initially developed to support the conceptual design of platform supply vessels, while in a meantime the tool is expanded to provide early conceptual design for anchor handlers and offshore construction vessels. In the recent years, Ulstein shifted from designing OSV to cruise ships and fishing trawlers. In such circumstances, due to the flexible nature of the tool, Ulstein FTDCDA was adopted and adapted to new segments on the basis of preliminary developed platform. Within development, implementation and the performance of the FTCDA feed backs from designers and the sales people has led to more functionalities being added to the tool or some being removed or modified to make it more conversant to the needs of the end users. It is seen how capabilities of Microsoft excel as a popular office software is used to develop technical tool to handle conceptual design of the ship with lower price and higher flexibility compared to more comprehensive and costly tools available in the market with its relative pros and cons. Fig.5 demonstrate partial interface of the cruise ship conceptual design tool and its related VB code for wave added resistance calculation. Based on the discrepancies in the functionality of the segments inputs vary among OSV and cruise ship tools, while generic platform and interface of the tool colour codes are almost similar. As of the tool now, Ulstein OSV fast track tool covers PSV, AHTS and OCV segments and Ulstein cruise ship tool covers cruise/exploration, RoPax and luxury yacht segments.

Fig.5: Cruise /exploration FTDCDA interface and back ground VB code

2.2.2 WebGL and Collada

WebGL (Web Graphics Library) is a cross-browser JavaScript library/API, which is used for rendering complement. It allows interactive advanced graphics to be rendered within a web browser and optimizes the hardware use. WebGL does not use plug-ins and there is no need for installs or updates, which is significant advantage compared to the decaying Adobe Flash. WebGL has been used in applications from gaming to science.

Collada (COLLABorative Design Activity) is a file format used to transport 3D assets. It is capable to carry more information about the 3D environment (including geometry, materials, shaders, effects, lights, or even physics and animations), *Gaspar et al. (2016)*. In principle, 3D parts, objects or modules are created in separate 3D software and saved as JSON format. That enables WebGL, collada to read the file in web-based environment and create new 3D models by parametrizing the objects and adding or removing the functional equipment's. Java script code is used to connect WebGL to Ulstein FTCDA. such functionality enables to visualize schematic 3d model of the concept with good enough resolution after defining vessel inputs in the FTCDA tool, Fig.6.

Fig.6: WebGL connected to FTDCDA excel interface for 3D visualization of design configuration

3. Ulstein FTDCDA development methodology

The Ulstein's Fast Track Concept Design Analysis Tool (FTDCDA), is an open source internally developed tool for fast evaluation of different vessel concept options. Exploiting FTDCDA, primary vessel concept design is developed rapidly at any place, requiring almost no extra computational power. The FTDCDA has two main applications, being used as a selling or a design support tool. As a selling tool, it is used to present quietly a solution concept to the client, addressing his/her main expectations and the consequence of variation in design and decision making parameters in the performance of final product. Moreover, as a sales support tool FTDCDA caters real market data of vessels that are already in operation and benchmarks performance of customer expectation with indicative market vessel. As a design tool, it is used by the design team as a mean of exploring design variations before they are further developed into a single solution which will be developed in Basic and Detail design steps.

3.1 FTDCDA structure

Vessel design consists of three main steps of Conceptual design, Basic design and detail design. Concept design practice is typically a decision-making process where the results of simulations and model tests are the inputs of decision making process to balance the vessel design solution. Moreover, available technical, operational and commercial data of similar designs are considered as background data in the new vessel concept development. Following concept development is a basic ship design process where rule proof and prepared for designs and calculations, are taken care of. In the latest stage of ship design, normally, detailed structural modelling, piping and electrical distribution designs including 2D and 3D drawings are generated for production purposes. Fig.7 shows three main ship design phases and differentiates between the concept design process as an "upstream" decision making process compared to a detailed and production planning oriented design activity as a "downstream" engineering activity.

Ulstein FTDCDA functions as a bridge between vessel Concept and Basic design phases, where critical system decisions being made. Such early decision making process requires appropriate inputs presenting the implications and the consequences of any single decision on the final performance of the ship design solution, in a very short and limited concept development time. FTDCDA makes eminent role to provide

sufficient and accurate enough information for fast and robust, vessel conceptual design decision making process.

Fig.7: Ship design steps and FTDCA

The FTDCA is consists of several connected analysis modules (or excel spread sheets). Each module is responsible for handling specific parts of the design process, receiving and providing data from and to other modules. Generic structure of FTDCA, different contributing modules and their internal interactions and dynamics in the tool are represented in Fig.8.

Fig.8: FTDCA modules and internal interactions

Fig.8 shows, Input data including vessel main dimensions required mission equipment and economic and commercial factors including, loan and equity percentage, country of built, fuel cost, etc. are defined by the user. In the transformation and the calculation phase inputs are used in different modules whilst result of some modules are also fed to other module in the tool due to the type of data required for calculation. For instance, calculated areas and volumes are transferred to calm water and wave resistance modules, and on the other side output from these modules are input to power balancing module which has another input from DP calculation as well. Output from power balancing is fed to economy and benchmarking modules for cost estimation and benchmarking calculation, additionally it is stored to be presented in the output sheet as total installed power. Brief insight to each module and methodology of calculation is given further in the following subchapters.

3.1 Design requirement sheet

The design requirements sheet is the main interface between the vessel configurator and the user. This spreadsheet receives all required inputs for vessel configuration purpose as aforementioned. Besides

statistical, historical and database values, regional weather scatter tables, are stored in the tool as a supportive resource of data for further analytical transformations. This spreadsheet is formatted to be printed in A3 format, in colour or black and white, being part of the tool documentation output to be used as a report for the design team or client, Fig.9.

3.2 The output specification sheet

The output specification sheet is the main interface between the vessel configurator results and the user. This spreadsheet presents the main outputs for the vessel configurator, including main dimensions and capacities, deck layout, equipment data, benchmarking analysis, economic analysis and operational scenarios. Results from the different calculation modules are integrated in the output sheet to be communicated in a professional way with the user. A3 communication techniques are used as a basis for layout of input and output sheets (system practice). Moreover, priority of given information, readability of the data and maintaining interactive interface are considered in the development of the input/output sheets. Colouring and layout of the interfaces is developed in consultation with communication technology experts in Ulstein. This spreadsheet is formatted to be printed in A3 format, colour or black and white, being part of the tool documentation output to be used as a report for the design team or client.

Fig.9: Offshore vessel FTDC output sheet

3.3 Calculation / transformation modules

3.3.1 Volume and area calculation module

Vessel volumes and areas in the tool are calculated based on system-based design approach in super structure and accommodation part. The buoyancy volume calculation model is used for the calculation of volume for the marine platform. In the accommodation part, tool serves an opportunity to define required areas both in a manual or automatic way. In the automatic approach, default values for different zones of accommodation are the basis of analysis. These unit areas are the result of statistical analysis on the GA of other Ulstein built and competing market vessel in the segment. Accumulation of the defined vessel areas and volumes creates vessel total required area both in accommodation and hull part.

The vessel GT is the consequence of the total calculated volume based on rule equation. Fig.10 depicts input sheet for cabin configuration and related analysis in volume and area module of the tool based on input data from user. In RoPax vessels, selecting RoRo cargo generates superstructure deck to position expected number of cars and trucks. Out puts from this module are fed to weight and capacity calculation, power balance and price estimation modules.

Fig.10: Cabin configuration and area calculation examples cruise ship FTDCA

3.3.2 Weight and capacity calculation

A classic weight calculation approach is applied in the tool. Vessel light weight is estimated based on steel, mission required equipment and outfitting weights. Different equipment weight are accrued in top of the calculated LWT as manual input or exploiting available values in stored data base in the tool. Hull steel weight estimation equation, is the result of internally developed parametrization of generic mid ship section for each vessel segment and calculating the weight for each combination based on rule loads. Nonlinear multiple regression analysis is applied on the results and a generic equation is created to estimate main hull steel weight. The weight for superstructure and accommodation is estimated based on calculated areas, volume and number of accommodation decks. The OSV main hull steel weight equation (Eq.1) as an example is given here. Developed equations are calibrated and verified based on available steel weight of Ulstein built vessels.

$$(Eq.1) \quad Weight_{Hull} = (1.2 \cdot 0.17 \cdot k_s^\alpha \cdot Loa^\beta \cdot B^\gamma \cdot D^\delta + 1.2 \times 10^k \cdot (Loa \cdot B \cdot D)^\rho - 9 \times 10^{-8} \cdot (Loa \cdot B \cdot D)^\nu + 0.027 \cdot (Loa \cdot B \cdot D) - 223.64) + Weight_{Cb}$$

$$(Eq.2) \quad k_s = \frac{Loa \cdot D}{L_{BP} \cdot T_{Max}}$$

3.3.3 Calm water and wave added resistance modulus

3.3.3.1 Calm water

The calm water resistance module is responsible for estimating the propulsion and resistance parameters for the vessel in calm water condition. It is an evaluation sheet, that does not require inputs from the user. In order to evaluate the vessel resistance, the ITTC 1978 method is used. The method considers that the total resistance coefficient can be decomposed as Fig.11.

Speed power result curve for different cases is calibrated with CFD and model test results. wave making resistance coefficient is finetuned accordingly for X-bow and bulbous bows in the tool. Fig.12 depicts such validation and calibration where almost 5% deviation is observed in the result of the tool compared to CFD results in the speeds above 15 kn.

The wetted surface area is estimated using the calibrated expression from Holtrop and Mennen:

$$S = L \cdot (2 \cdot T + B) \cdot \sqrt{C_M} \cdot (0.453 + 0.4425 \cdot C_B - 0.2862 \cdot C_M - 0.003467 \cdot B/T + 0.3696 \cdot C_{WP}) + 2.38 \cdot A_{BT}/C_B$$

Fig.11: Calm-water resistance decomposition, ITTC 1978

Fig.12: FTDCA speed power curve calibration and verification with CFD

3.3.3.2 Wave added resistance

Ship moving in waves will dissipate more energy than one sailing in still water. This extra-induced loss of energy is called added resistance in waves. Ship motions, in particular, the vertical motions heave and pitch have the largest effect in wave added resistance. Energy and moment method in visual basic coding is used in the tool for wave added resistance calculation, *Perez (2007)*.

$$R_{AW} = \frac{\omega_e^3}{2g} (b_z z_a^2 + b_{z+\theta} z_a \theta \cos \varepsilon + b_\theta \theta_a^2)$$

Or made nondimensional:

$$\sigma_{AW} = \frac{L\omega_e^3}{2B^2 \rho g} \left\{ (RAO_z)^2 b_z - \frac{2\pi}{L_w} (RAO_z)(RAO_\theta) b_{z+\theta} \cos \varepsilon + \frac{4\pi^2}{L_w^2} (RAO_\theta)^2 b_\theta \right\}$$

To be able to simplify the model and parametrize it based on main dimensions and shape factors as an innovative approach for WM resistance calculation closed form expression is used, *Jensen (2004)*. Heave and pitch RAO, and sectional damping calculation are calculated based on closed form expressions, where results are exploited in energy model. Different spectrums are used in the tool which is defined as an input for root mean square calculation. Fig.13 is the schematic process of wave added resistance calculation model in the tool. Output from calm water and wave added resistance calculation is transferred to power balance module for vessel installed power calculation. Total power required for different operational mode and mission required equipment, is calculated in power balancing calculation module.

Fig.13: Schematic process of wave added resistance calculation model

3.3.4 Performance benchmarking module

The performance module of FTDCa is responsible for calculation of the performance measures of merit for developed designed solution and comparing it with market vessel peers. Different vessel benchmarking indexes are developed by Ulstein over the years and explained comprehensively in some conferences globally, *Ulstein and Brett (2015)*, *Ebrahimi et al. (2015,2018)*. Pareto-front and frequency histograms are used in the tool for peer benchmarking. Fig.14 presents performance benchmark of the developed solution in both graphs for Technical Operational Performance Indexes (TOPI).

Fig.14: Benchmarking representation of the developed solution in FTDCa

Payment factors		Operational fees		Operational profile	
Equity	50 %	Terminal disbursement	13938.89114 USD	Transit, loaded, steaming	37%
Loan	50 %	Terminal calls per year	35 times	Transit, loaded, slow steaming	0%
Interest	10 %	MGO price	369 USD	DP2	29%
Repayment	20 years	Crew nationality	Philippine	Waiting	3%
Return on equi	10 %			In port (Loading/ Discharge)	10%
Building count	Norway			*values are estimated	10%
Conversion rat	8.50 NOK/USD			0	11%
		Estimated newbuilding cost			
		Construction cost	60 582 963 USD		
		Mission equipment cost**	78 235 294 USD		
		Profit (5%)	6 940 913 USD		
		Overhead (7%)	9 717 278 USD		
		Total building cost	155 476 447 USD		
		Total building cost	1 321 549 804 NOK		
		** ROVs are not included in the price, just LARS system			
		Brands			
		Designer	Focal Marine & Offshore Corp.		
		Engine manufacturer	Cummins		

Expenditures (USD)		Contract scenarios (USD)		Day rates (USD)		Additional information	
CAPEX	46 315	Bareboat	46 315	Average 3 worst years	62 667	Dayrate based on:	West Africa
OPEX	69 575	Time charter	115 890	Average 10 years period	72 667	Contract type:	Term Market
VOYEX	8 587	Voyage	124 477	Average 3 best years	80 000	Utilization rate:	88 %

Fig.15: Example of economy performance calculation and representation FTDCa

3.3.5 Economy measure and cost estimation module

The economics section presents information related to the designed vessel economic measure of merit. Bottom up structure of the cost model based on 3rd level SFI cost break down approach is used in economy model. Inputs from different modules including, volumes/area's, steel weight and outfitting

weights, installed and propulsion power and required mission equipment are input to this module. Unit costs for material and construction are used based on Ulstein shipyard practices with permissible level of accuracy to estimate vessel construction cost. Labour cost and material cost differences compensated with labour productivity in some other countries like China, Poland and Turkey also are inserted in the tool to calculate construction cost in other countries than Norway. Beside vessel Capex calculation, operational cost of the vessel due to its type of operation, number of crew, maintenance and insurances costs are included in the tool. More over the tool encompasses the Voyex based on fuel cost and operational profile of the vessel, adding the cost for port calls and number of disbursements. Revenue making capability of the tool depends on vessel type and calculated based on stored day-rates for offshore vessels since 2007 or passenger and cargo transportation rates for cruise ships in different cruising routs and luxury classes, Fig.15.

4. Case study

The case study part of this paper is related to the design of an exploration cruise to be operated in Norden Europe area with the following expectation criteria from costumer, Table I.

Table I: Design expectation list

Number of Pax	Number of Crew	Max speed	Ice class	GT
250-280	160-180	17 kn	1B	~10000

To approach this design problem, 6 alternative design solutions are generated with FTDCA, Table II, in the conceptual phase, to fulfil expectation criteria by varying main dimensions, cabin sizes, number of crew and vessel luxury level. Among the solutions, solution D is larger solution well-fitting with premium-high luxury where alternative A3 resembles a modest-medium luxury solution in the requested size. This variation among the solutions is to depict the influence of different design technical and operational aspects on the commercial factors. Demonstrating the implications and the consequences of different parameters on vessel particulars, performance and economy measure in a short time span is the main objective of the FTDCA compared to traditional design approach.

Fig.16: Sensitivity of vessel operability to weather condition in different region
 Table II: Alternative design solutions

Solution Proposals						
	Alt A1	Alt A2	Alt A3	Alt B	Alt C	Alt D
Luxury standard Interior	Medium	Premium Lux	Medium	Medium-Premium	Premium	Premium-high
Ice class notation	Ice B1					
GT	10400	11700	9100	10250	10750	14900
LOA	130	130	130	120	130	150
LBP	120	120	120	110	120	140
Beam	19,5	19,5	19,5	20,0	19,5	21,3
L/B	6,15	6,15	6,15	5,50	6,15	6,57
Depth to main deck	7,3	7,3	7,3	7,3	7,3	7,8
Max. Draft	5,5	5,5	5,5	5,5	5,5	5,7
Design Draft	5,3	5,3	5,3	5,3	5,3	5,5
Passengers	260	260	250	260	260	260
Crew	172	172	125	172	130	200
Crew/Pax	0,66	0,66	0,50	0,66	0,50	0,77
Gust Cabin arrangement (Qty*area)						
Luxury suits	6*70	6*70	5*50	6*70	6*70	6*70
balcony large cabins	20*32	20*32	20*32	20*32	20*32	20*32
Window cabins	104*25	104*25	100*26	104*25	104*25	104*26
Public area/Pax m^2	8,0	13,0	6,0	8,0	12,0	20,00
Crew cabin Arrangement	12*single 80 * 2 men	12*single 80 * 2 men	12*single 80 * 2 men	12*single 80 * 2 men	10*single 60 * 2 men	20*single 90 * 2 men
Dwt	1 420	1 230	1 550	1 350	1 320	1 600
DWT/Pax	5,5	4,7	6,2	5,2	5,1	6,2
Engine_KW_Total	10 000	10 500	9 700	10 500	10 150	12 300
Propulsion Power	6 800	6 800	6 800	7320	6800	7 450
GT/Pax	40	45	36	39	41	57
Max. Speed (knots)	18	18	18	18	18	18
LWT	6200	6400	6100	5900	6300	8 500
St weight	3150	3260	3100	2980	3220	4 350
Number of accommodation deck excluding top deck/bridge	5	5	5	5	5	6
MSI Operability in 5.1 Hs 30% from LCG Norwegian Sea	98,0 %	98,0 %	98,0 %	98,0 %	98,0 %	98,0 %
Vertical Acceleration Operability .05*g limiting 30% from LCG	79,0 %	79,0 %	79,0 %	78,0 %	79,0 %	83,0 %
GM	1,58	1,38	1,73	1,93	1,45	1,55
Natural Roll Period sec	11,8	12,62	11,3	11	12,21	13
SFC Ton/day	20	21,1	19,5	20,3	20,2	25,3
Spped * GT /Power	18,72	20,06	16,89	17,57	19,06	21,80
Price/Pax night break even point USD @ 75%	510	570	440	505	480	700
USD/GT	9 087	9 231	9 341	9 122	9 023	9 396
Opex/Day	53600	59700	51700	53400	47500	67000
USD_Newbuilding_Price adjusted	94 500 000	108 000 000	85 000 000	93 500 000	97 000 000	140 000 000
USD /L*B*D	5 107	5 836	4 593	5 337	5 242	5 618
USD Price /pax	363 462	415 385	340 000	359 615	373 077	538 462

This type of analysis and plotting developed solutions in different market data analytics graphs serves information to figure out ill positioned solutions based on market place data quickly. As a consequence of applying such rapid solution development process is to guide the designers and decision makers into the right track in early design phase. Sensitivity analysis of the vessel operability in different regions is another valuable achievement of fast track tool. Fig. 16 shows the variation in design solution operability by making variation in operational region for four different seakeeping criteria. Such type sensitivity analysis demonstrates the impact of different influencing parameters on the performance of final design solution and opens room for further investigation of design improvements in early phases within a short time span.

4. Concluding remarks and discussion

In this paper, fast track conceptual design approach is defined and explained comprehensively. Similarities and differences between classic design spiral which is based on sequential design approach and fast track approach coming out of the concurrent engineering thinking is explained in this paper. Structure of Ulstein FTDCA is explained and discussed how FTDCA as an open source internal concept design technology, exploits combination of MS excel interface, VB coding and web based open tools including Java coding, WebGL and Collada. Different analytical approaches and computing modulus of the tool explained in detail. Accuracy level of the tool compared to imperial equation, CFD and model test and

it is argued in the paper how gap between empirical equation and CFD/ 3D model creation approach is filled by Ulstein FTDCA. It is argued how 95% of accuracy compared to the result of comprehensive and more complex design tools is achieved in FTDCA. Time and accuracy trade-off in vessel conceptual design phase is discussed in the paper and presented how Ulstein FTDCA, resolved the challenge of these contradicting objectives in conceptual design phase where in a very quick response time, computational power with permissible accuracy level is achieved by the tool. It is shown in the paper by practical cases Ulstein conceptual design response time shorten from an average of 25-30 days, to 2-3 days depending on the type, size and budget of the project as a substantial improvement in conceptual design phase.

References

- BOGUS, S. (2002), *A Methodology to Reconfigure the Design-Construction Interface for Fast-Track Projects*, ASCE & EG-ICE, Washington, pp. 258-272
- CHAVES, O.; GASPAR, H. (2016), *A Web Based Real-Time 3D Simulator for Ship Design Virtual Prototype and Motion Prediction*, 15th COMPIT Conf., Lecce
- CHO, K.M.; HYUN, C.T.; KOO, K.K.; HONG, T.H. (2010), *Partnering process model for public-sector fast-track design-build projects in Korea*, J. Management in Engineering 26/1
- EBRAHIMI, A.; BRETT, P.O.; GARCIA, J.J.; KAMSVÅG, Ø. (2015a), *Better decision making to improve robustness of OCV designs*, 12th Int. Marine Design Conf. (IMDC), Vol.3
- EBRAHIMI, A.; BRETT, P.O.; GASPAR, H.M.; GARCIA, J.J.; KAMSVÅG, Ø. (2015b), *Parametric OSV Design Studies – precision and quality assurance via updated statistics*, 12th Int. Marine Design Conf. (IMDC), Vol.2
- ERIKSTAD, S.O. (1996), *A decision support model for preliminary ship design*, PhD thesis, NTNU, Trondheim
- GASPAR, H.M.; BRETT, P.O.; EBRAHIMI, A.; KEANE, A. (2014), *Data-driven documents (D3) applied to conceptual ship design knowledge*, 13th COMPIT Conf., Redworth
- HEITZ, P.R. (2014), *The speed-accuracy tradeoff: history, physiology, methodology, and behavior*, Frontiers in Neuroscience 8, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4052662/>
- JENSEN, J.; MANSOUR, A.E.; OLSEN, A.S. (2004), *Estimation of ship motions using closed-form expressions*, Ocean Eng. 31, pp.61–85
- PEREZ, F. (2007) *Some methods to obtain the added resistance of a ship advancing in waves*, Ocean Eng. 34, pp.946–955
- ULSTEIN, T.; BRETT, P.O. (2015), *What is a better ship? – It all depends...*, 12th Int. Maritime Design Conf., Vol. 1, pp.49–69
- ULSTEIN, T.; BRETT, P.O. (2012), *Critical systems thinking in ship design approaches*, 11th Int. Maritime Design Conf.
- WOOD, C.C. (1976), *Speed-accuracy tradeoff functions in choice reaction time: Experimental designs and computational procedures*, Perception & Psychophysics 19/1, pp.92-102

CFD-Based Shape Optimization Under Limited Computational Resources – A Study on Adaptive Multi-Fidelity Metamodeling

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Abstract

The paper presents a study on five adaptive sampling methods of a multi-fidelity global metamodel for expensive computer simulations. The multi-fidelity metamodel selects the fidelity to sample based on the prediction uncertainty and the computational cost ratio of high- and low-fidelity evaluations. The sampling methods are applied to four analytical problems and to the CFD-shape optimization of a NACA hydrofoil. The performance of the sampling methods is assessed in terms of maximum uncertainty, root mean square error of the prediction, and objective function reduction.

1. Introduction

Fluid-dynamic shape design of complex industrial systems (such as aerial, ground, and water-borne vehicles) demand the use of high-fidelity numerical solvers with large computational grids to assess accurately the design performance and make sound design decisions. The latter can be achieved by combining computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analyses with a shape/design modification tool (CAD) and a minimization algorithm into an automatic simulation-based design optimization (SBDO). High-fidelity physics-based solvers results in computationally expensive analyses. Furthermore, the optimization algorithm may require a large number of function evaluations to converge to the final solution. Therefore, the resulting computational cost could become very high, making SBDO unaffordable for most users and projects for which limited computational resources and time are usually available.

In order to reduce the computational cost of the SBDO process, metamodeling methods have been developed and successfully applied in several engineering fields, *Viana (2014)*. Metamodel performance depends on several concurrent issues, such as the dimensionality of the problem, the nature (smooth or noisy) of the function, and the sampling approach used for its training, *Liu (2017)*. A priori sampling provides distribution of training-set points, without any knowledge of the function. Sequential sampling adds new training points iteratively, based on the knowledge gathered during the training process. An adaptive sampling for dynamic stochastic radial basis functions (RBF) has been presented in *Volpi (2015)* and compared to dynamic Kriging, *Zhao (2011)*. A multi-criteria adaptive sampling method for dynamic RBF has been presented in *Diez (2015)* for design optimization problems.

In addition to metamodels, multi-fidelity (or variable-fidelity) approximation methods have been developed with the aim of combining to some extent the accuracy of high-fidelity solvers with the computational cost of low-fidelity solvers. Combining metamodeling methods with multi-fidelity approximations potentially leads to a further reduction of the computational cost of the SBDO procedure. Additive and/or multiplicative correction methods might be used to build multi-fidelity metamodels, using high- and low-fidelity evaluations, *Ng (2012)*, *Zheng (2013)*. Several metamodels can be used with multi-fidelity data, as co-kriging, *DeBaar (2015)*, and RBF, *Pellegrini (2016)*. For instance, adaptive sampling methods for multi-fidelity metamodels have been adopted in *Pellegrini (2016)*, based on the multi-fidelity prediction uncertainty.

The objective of the present work is the assessment of five adaptive sampling methods for multi-fidelity metamodeling. These are based on the maximum prediction uncertainty, the expected improvement, *Jones (1998)*, the maximum prediction uncertainty and the objective function through an aggregated

merit factor, and the multi-criteria based on the maximum prediction uncertainty and the objective function.

These methods are applied to four multi-modal analytical test problems with one and two dimensions. Furthermore, the sampling methods are applied to the CFD-based shape optimization of a NACA 2D hydrofoil, addressing the drag minimization at $Re=8.41E6$. The hydrofoil hydrodynamic performance is assessed by RANSE solver ISIS-CFD, developed at Centrale Nantes/CNRS and integrated in the FINE/Marine simulation suite from NUMECA. Mesh deformation techniques and adaptive grid refinement techniques are adopted to allow the automatic shape deformation of the hydrofoil. The high- and low-fidelity are defined by the numerical grid refinement. Once the training process of the multi-fidelity metamodel is complete, a multi-fidelity metamodel-based optimization is performed. The performance of the adaptive sampling methods is assessed by studying the convergence of prediction uncertainty, the normalized root mean square error of the prediction, and optimization procedure.

2. Multi-fidelity metamodeling

Two levels are used: high- (HF) and low-fidelity (LF). The multi-fidelity approximation makes use of stochastic radial basis functions (SRBF), *Volpi (2015)*, which provide the function prediction $\tilde{f}(\mathbf{x})$ along with the associated uncertainty $U_{\tilde{f}}(\mathbf{x})$.

2.1. Extension to multi-fidelity analysis

Consider an objective function $f(\mathbf{x})$, where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is the design variable vector and N the design space dimension. The multi-fidelity prediction $\hat{f}(\mathbf{x})$ is defined by an additive correction to a low-fidelity trained metamodel. The correction is provided by the metamodel of the error ε (difference) between high- and low-fidelity evaluations (f_H and f_L), *Pellegrini (2016)*

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{f}(\mathbf{x}) &= \tilde{f}_L(\mathbf{x}) + \tilde{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{x}) \\ \varepsilon(\mathbf{x}) &= f_H(\mathbf{x}) - f_L(\mathbf{x})\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

The training set for \tilde{f}_L is denoted by \mathcal{L} , whereas the training set for $\tilde{\varepsilon}$ is denoted by $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathcal{L}$. “ \sim ” indicates metamodel prediction and “ \wedge ” indicates multi-fidelity approximation. Assuming $U_{\tilde{f}_L}(\mathbf{x})$ and $U_{\tilde{\varepsilon}}(\mathbf{x})$ as uncorrelated, the uncertainty associated to the multi-fidelity prediction is

$$U_{\hat{f}}(\mathbf{x}) = \sqrt{U_{\tilde{f}_L}^2(\mathbf{x}) + U_{\tilde{\varepsilon}}^2(\mathbf{x})}\quad (2)$$

2.2. Stochastic radial basis functions

$f(\mathbf{x})$ is approximated by means of SRBF $g(\mathbf{x}, \tau)$, where $\tau \sim \text{unif}[1,3]$ is a stochastic tuning parameter, *Volpi (2015)*. Due to the stochastic nature of g , the metamodel prediction $\tilde{f}(\mathbf{x})$ is computed as the expected value (EV) over τ

$$\tilde{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \text{EV}[g(\mathbf{x}, \tau)]_{\tau}, \quad \text{with } g(\mathbf{x}, \tau) = \sum_{j=1}^J w_j \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|^{-\tau} \quad 3$$

where w_j are unknown coefficients, $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm, \mathbf{x}_j are the training points with associated objective function value $f(\mathbf{x}_j)$, and J is the number of training points of the interpolation. The coefficients w_j are determined by enforcing the interpolation $g(\mathbf{x}_j, \tau) = f(\mathbf{x}_j)$ by solving $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{w}=\mathbf{f}$, with $\mathbf{w} = \{w_j\}$, $a_{i,j} = \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|^{-\tau}$, and $\mathbf{f} = \{f(\mathbf{x}_j)\}$. The uncertainty $U_{\tilde{f}}(\mathbf{x})$ associated with the metamodel prediction is quantified by the 95%-confidence interval of $g(\mathbf{x}, \tau)$, evaluated using a Monte Carlo sampling over τ , *Volpi (2015)*.

Fig.1: Adaptive multi-fidelity metamodel updating scheme

2.3. Adaptive sampling methods

New training points \mathbf{x}^* for \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{E} are sequentially defined by the adaptive sampling method, shown in Fig. 1 and described in later sections. Once \mathbf{x}^* is identified, the training sets \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{E} are updated as

$$\begin{cases} \text{If } U_{\hat{f}_L}(\mathbf{x}^*) \geq \beta U_{\hat{\varepsilon}}(\mathbf{x}^*), \text{ add } \{\mathbf{x}^*, f_L(\mathbf{x}^*)\} \text{ to } \mathcal{L} \\ \text{else, add } \{\mathbf{x}^*, f_L(\mathbf{x}^*)\} \text{ to } \mathcal{L} \text{ and } \{\mathbf{x}^*, \varepsilon(\mathbf{x}^*)\} \text{ to } \mathcal{E} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\beta \in [0,1]$ is the ratio of low- and high-fidelity computational cost. In the first case, only a low-fidelity evaluation is performed, while the second case requires both low- and high-fidelity evaluations for the same \mathbf{x}^* . The following sections present how \mathbf{x}^* is defined, based on five adaptive sampling methods.

Two stopping criteria are adopted: (i) when the available budget of function evaluations is consumed and (ii) a check on the minimum distance among the training points of \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{E} to avoid excessively clustered training points, which would produce an ill-conditioned linear system.

2.3.1. Maximum uncertainty

The maximum uncertainty adaptive sampling (MUAS) method has been presented in *Pellegrini (2016)*. This method identifies a new training point by solving the following single-objective maximization problem

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \underset{\mathbf{x}}{\operatorname{argmax}} [U_{\hat{f}}(\mathbf{x})] \quad (5)$$

2.3.2. Expected improvement

The expected improvement (EI), *Jones (1998)*, sampling method identifies a new training point by solving the following maximization problem

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \underset{\mathbf{x}}{\operatorname{argmax}} [\operatorname{EI}(\mathbf{x})] \quad (6)$$

with

$$\operatorname{EI}(\mathbf{x}) = \operatorname{EV} \left[\max[f_{\min} - \hat{g}(\mathbf{x}, \tau), 0] \right]_{\tau}, \text{ with } f_{\min} = \min[f_H(\mathbf{x}_j)] \quad (7)$$

where $\hat{g}(\mathbf{x}, \tau)$ is the multi-fidelity approximation conditional to τ .

Each τ defines a stochastic RBF. The expected improvement is therefore the expected value of potential reduction provided by all SRBFs compared to the minimum at the present iteration of the sampling process.

2.3.3. Multi-fidelity expected improvement

Since the multi-fidelity concept is to keep the high-fidelity training set as small as possible, a multi-fidelity expected improvement (MFEI) is introduced. This identifies a new training point by solving the maximization problem of Eqs.(6) and (7) where $f_{min} = \min[\hat{f}(\mathbf{x})]$.

2.3.4. Aggregate criteria

The aggregate criteria adaptive sampling (ACAS) method identifies a new training point by solving the following single-objective minimization

$$\mathbf{x}^* = \underset{\mathbf{x}}{\operatorname{argmin}}[\hat{f}(\mathbf{x}) - U_{\hat{f}}(\mathbf{x})] \quad (8)$$

2.3.5. Multi-criteria

The multi-criteria adaptive sampling (MCAS) method identifies a number of new training points N_p (user defined) by solving the following multi-objective problem for the minimization of the objective function and maximization of the prediction uncertainty

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{minimize } \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \{\hat{f}(\mathbf{x}), -U_{\hat{f}}(\mathbf{x})\}^T, \\ &\text{subject to } U_{\hat{f}}(\mathbf{x}) > U_{\hat{f}}^* \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $U_{\hat{f}}^*$ is a user defined parameter used to avoid overfitting in the neighborhood of the minimum, *Diez (2015)*. This sampling method produces a non-dominated solution set of potential training points. This is down-sampled to N_p solutions, *Diez (2015)*. Here, $U_{\hat{f}}^* = 0.1\%R$, where R is the function range of the initial high-fidelity training set.

2.3.6. Single- and multi-objective optimization algorithm

A deterministic single-objective formulation of the particle swarm optimization (DPSO) algorithm *Serani (2016)*, is used for the solution of the minimization/maximization problems of Eqs.(5), (6), and (8). Furthermore, it is used for the metamodel-based optimization. The multi-objective extension of DPSO (MODPSO, *Pellegrini (2017)*) is used for the minimization problem of Eq.(9).

3. Benchmark test problems

The effectiveness and efficiency of the adaptive multi-fidelity metamodel is assessed by four analytical tests and one SBDO problem.

3.1. Analytical test problems

The analytical test problems (*Far1*, *MLF1*, *SK1*, *SSFYY2*) are selected from *Huband (2006)*. These problems have dimension ranging from one to two and contains two objective functions. The first objective function is considered as the high-fidelity objective (f_H), whereas the second objective is considered as the error function (ε). Therefore, the low-fidelity evaluation is computed as $f_L = f_H - \varepsilon$.

Fig.2 shows the analytical test problems, the high-fidelity functions are multi-modal and have many local minima. Furthermore, problems #3 and #4 have multi-modal error functions. Three metrics are used to assess the effectiveness of the multi-fidelity sampling methods with the analytical tests. The maximum value of the multi-fidelity metamodel uncertainty, the normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) between the multi-fidelity prediction and the analytical objective, and the validation of the objective function value at the predicted minimum. The NRMSE is computed on a set of 50^N evenly-

spaced points. The objective is evaluated by the analytical function at the predicted minimum. Furthermore, to assess the multi-fidelity metamodel efficiency its performance is compared with a single-fidelity metamodel trained only with high-fidelity evaluations.

Fig.2: High- and low-fidelity and error functions of the analytical test problems

3.2. NACA hydrofoil optimization problem

The problem addresses the minimization of the drag coefficient $C_d(\mathbf{x})$. When optimizing a lifting hydrofoil, it is necessary to compare the different geometries at the same lift coefficient C_l^* . The optimization problem reads

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize } C_d(\mathbf{x}), \\ & \text{subject to } C_l(\mathbf{x}) = C_l^* \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The 2D foil shape is defined by the general equation for 4-digit NACA airfoils. The upper (y_{Up}) and lower (y_{Lo}) hydrofoil lines are computed as

$$\begin{cases} \xi_{Up} = \xi - y_t \sin\theta \\ \xi_{Lo} = \xi + y_t \sin\theta \\ y_{Up} = y_c + y_t \cos\theta \\ y_{Lo} = y_c - y_t \cos\theta \end{cases} \text{ where } y_c = \begin{cases} \frac{m}{p^2} \left(2p \left(\frac{\xi}{c} \right) - \left(\frac{\xi}{c} \right)^2 \right), & 0 \leq \xi \leq pc \\ \frac{m}{(1-p)^2} \left((1-2p) + 2p \left(\frac{\xi}{c} \right) - \left(\frac{\xi}{c} \right)^2 \right), & pc \leq \xi \leq c \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where ξ is the position along the chord, c the chord length, y_c the mean camber line, p the location of maximum camber, m the maximum camber value, and y_t the half thickness, computed as

$$y_t = 5t[0.2969\sqrt{\xi} - 0.1260\xi - 0.3516\xi^2 + 0.2843\xi^3 - 0.1015\xi^4] \quad (12)$$

In this work, two parameters are considered as design variables, the maximum thickness (t) and maximum camber (m).

4. CFD simulation for multi-fidelity optimization

The CFD simulations are performed with the unstructured two-fluid finite-volume Navier-Stokes solver ISIS-CFD developed at Centrale Nantes/CNRS and integrated in the FINE/Marine simulation suite from NUMECA Int.

4.1. Mesh deformation

The unstructured hexahedral meshes for the simulations are generated using HEXPRESS. Like for most unstructured mesh generators, the grids created by this mesher may be quite different for geometries that are nearly identical. This could result in numerical noise in the simulations results. Therefore, the simulations of all the candidate geometries are performed on the same mesh, which is deformed to fit each geometry. The deformation algorithm is based on the work of *Durand (2012)*. The mesh is divided in layers of cells around the geometry. Then, the displacement from the original to the deformed geometry is computed for the faces on the body and this displacement is propagated through the layers of cells. Two smoothing mechanisms are applied: (i) the displacements are diffused over the faces of a single layer, so the mesh deformation becomes more uniform; (ii) a weighting technique is applied based on the distance to the body, such that the deformation goes to zero on the outer boundaries.

4.2. Adaptive grid refinement

After the initial mesh deformation to fit each geometry, the final meshes are obtained with adaptive grid refinement, *Wackers (2017)*. The decision on where to refine the mesh is based on metric tensors, *George (1998)*. The 3×3 criterion tensors \mathcal{C}_i in each i -th cell are computed from the flow solution. These tensors indicate the target size of the cells: in a hexahedral cell, let the cell sizes $\mathbf{d}_{i,j}$ ($j=1,2,3$) be the vectors between the opposing face centers in the three cell directions. The goal of the grid refinement is to obtain

$$\|\mathcal{C}_i \mathbf{d}_{i,j}\| = T_r \quad \forall i, j \quad (13)$$

where T_r is a constant. This is accomplished by refining i -th cells in the j -th direction, until $\|\mathcal{C}_i \mathbf{d}_{i,j}\|$ no longer exceeds the constant T_r . The refinement criteria are based on the Hessian matrix of second spatial derivatives. The interest of this procedure for multi-fidelity optimization is that the cell size in the entire mesh varies proportionally to the threshold T_r , *Wackers (2017)*. Thus, the precision of the simulation can be adjusted by varying this parameter, which makes it easy to automate multi-fidelity simulations. A further advantage is that this technique allows to perform the mesh deformation on the coarse initial grid, instead of a fine grid where small errors in the placement of the nodes can lead to inverted cells. A potential disadvantage is that the refined grids for the different geometries are not the same, which could introduce noise in the results.

4.3. Dynamic positioning

To maintain a constant lift coefficient the angle of incidence for the hydrofoil is adjusted dynamically during the simulations. At regular intervals, the difference between the target and the actual lift is evaluated and divided by the theoretical lift slope of 2D airfoils ($\Delta C_l = 2\pi\Delta\alpha$). The change in angle of attack $\Delta\alpha$, is applied over a few time steps and the flow is allowed to settle, then another $\Delta\alpha$ is computed. The mesh is deformed with an analytical weighting technique, to accommodate the rotation.

4.4. Analytical test problems

An arbitrary computational cost is assigned to each HF and LF evaluation equal to 10.0 and 10.0 β , respectively. Several values of β are considered to reproduce different ratio of computational cost between low- and high-fidelity. Specifically, $\beta = \{0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8\}$. The available computational budget is set equal to a maximum cost of 500 N . The number of samples N_p computed at once by the MCAS sampling method is $N_p = 4$, for all the test problems. Fig.3 shows the convergences of the

maximum uncertainty, the NRMSE, and the validation of the predicted minimum of the sampling methods with $\beta = 0.1$ for the analytical problems. It is worth noting that MUAS and MCAS achieve a significant reduction of maximum uncertainty and NRMSE. Differently, EI, MFEI and ACAS methods do not provide the same reduction. EI, MFEI, and ACAS methods do not converge to the minimum for problems #3 and #4. MUAS and MCAS sampling methods always converge to the real minimum, with MCAS achieving a faster convergence than MUAS for problems #1, #2, and #4.

Fig.4 shows the convergence of the maximum uncertainty, the NRMSE, and the validation of the predicted minimum of the MCAS sampling method for the analytical problems for different β values. The performance of the high-fidelity trained metamodel is also reported for comparison. The multi-fidelity metamodel achieves better or similar convergence than the HF metamodel of the maximum uncertainty, the NRMSE, and the objective function for $\beta < 0.4$, except for problem #3.

Fig.3: Convergences of the maximum uncertainty, the NRMSE, and the validation of the predicted minimum of the sampling methods with $\beta = 0.1$ for the analytical problems

Fig.4: Convergences of the maximum uncertainty, the NMRSE, and the validation of the predicted minimum of the MCAS sampling method for the analytical problems

4.5. NACA hydrofoil

Four adaptive sampling methods are applied to the CFD-based shape optimization problem: MUAS, MFEI, ACAS, and MCAS. The thickness ranges between $t \in [0.03, 0.12]$, the camber ranges between $m \in [0.025, 0.07]$, and the location of the maximum camber is set equal to $p=0.4$. The velocity is $V=10$ m/s, chord $c=1$ m, fluid density $\rho=1026$ kg/m³, and Reynolds number $Re=8.41E6$. The lift coefficient is maintained constant and equal to $C_l^* = 0.6$. The initial mesh for both high- and low-fidelity has 2654 cells, the refinement threshold value T_r is set equal to 0.1 and 0.4 for high- and low-fidelity, respectively. The resulting refined fine and coarse meshes have 11k and 3.6k cells, respectively, Figs.5 and 6. Each high- and low-fidelity simulation requires about 13 and 5 minutes of wall-clock time to converge, respectively. The resulting computational cost ratio is $\beta = 0.3$. A budget of 150 simulations is provided for the adaptive sampling methods, considering both high- and low-fidelity simulations. The

multi-fidelity metamodel-based optimization is performed on a normalized domain $\mathbf{x} \in [0,1]$. The results of the metamodel-based optimization with the four sampling methods are compared with an optimal reference solution for the drag coefficient value ($C_{d,min}^*$) identified by an earlier high-fidelity metamodel-based optimization, *Ploé (2017)*, trained by 150 high-fidelity simulations.

Fig.5: Fine grid, 11k cells

Fig.6: Coarse grid, 3.6k cells

Fig.7: Hydrofoil optimization problem, convergences of the maximum uncertainty, the function minimum, and the function minimum coordinates x_1^* (solid lines) and x_2^* (dashed lines)

Fig.7 shows the convergences of the maximum prediction uncertainty, the drag coefficient minimum, and the corresponding design variables. MUAS and MCAS achieve lower values of the maximum prediction uncertainty than MFEI and ACAS. It is worth noting that the MUAS and MCAS do not converge to the reference minimum. MFEI provides the fastest convergence. MUAS and MCAS do not achieve convergence for the first variable, while all sampling methods achieve convergence for the second variable. Fig.8 shows the multi-fidelity metamodel and training set at final iteration of the four sampling methods. MUAS and MCAS provide a global exploration of the domain. Differently, MFEI and ACAS cluster training points in a small region.

All sampling methods use a similar number of HF evaluations (see Table I), with MUAS and MCAS spreading the HF evaluations over the whole domain. Furthermore, it is worth noting that both MUAS and MCAS request HF training points in the domain corners. Differently, MFEI and ACAS methods focus HF evaluations only in the minimum region.

Figs.7 and 8 show an interesting phenomenon. The convergence of the uncertainty prediction of MUAS and MCAS is noisy (Fig.7). MUAS and MCAS aim at the minimization of the maximum uncertainty, therefore clustering the training points in regions where the uncertainty is high. The metamodel uncertainty is affected by a small-scale noise found in the numerical simulations, in regions with clustered training points. Therefore, MUAS and MCAS add training points in regions where the uncertainty is due to the numerical noise and not to the objective function shape.

The effects of the numerical noise are evident in Figs.8a and 8d. MUAS clusters samples in the neighborhood of $\mathbf{x} = \{0.1,0.35\}$ (Fig. 8a) while MCAS clusters samples in the neighborhood of $\mathbf{x} = \{0.6,0.0\}$ (Fig. 8d). Both MUAS and MCAS methods cluster in such regions mainly LF training points, while MFEI and ACAS methods provide also a less significant clusterization of HF training points.

Fig.8: Training sets and $C_d(x)$ value at the final iteration

Table I summarizes the results of the multi-fidelity metamodel performance. The predicted minimum of the drag coefficient is close to the reference value. Nevertheless, the minimum location identified by the MUAS and MCAS sampling methods is not accurate. The MFEI sampling method uses the greatest number of high-fidelity evaluations, while MCAS uses the lowest.

Table I: Summary of the performance of the adaptive sampling methods for the SBDO problem

Sampling method	$ \mathcal{L} $	$ \mathcal{E} $	Predicted $C_{d,min}$	Coordinates of $C_{d,min}$		$C_{d,min}$ associated uncertainty	Verified $C_{d,min}$	$C_{d,min}^*$	x_1^*	x_2^*
				x_1	x_2					
MU	136	14	7.1759E-3	0.3084	0.0000	0.1092%	7.2582E-3	7.2340E-3	0.3554	0.0003
EI	135	15	7.1545E-3	0.3709	0.0000	0.0087%	7.2371E-3			
AC	138	12	7.1754E-3	0.3620	0.0001	0.0427%	7.2403E-3			
MC	137	11	7.2816E-3	0.3291	0.0000	0.0591%	7.2606E-3			

Finally, Figs.9a-d show the velocity contours of the optimal hydrofoil shape identified by the four sampling methods. The differences of the hydrofoil shapes are not evident, although the velocity contours are considerably different.

5. Conclusions and future work

Five adaptive sampling methods for multi-fidelity metamodeling are presented and applied to four analytical test problems and to the CFD-shape optimization of a NACA hydrofoil. The multi-fidelity

approximation is obtained as the sum of a low-fidelity-trained metamodel and the metamodel of the difference (error) between high- and low-fidelity evaluations. The metamodel is based on stochastic RBF, which provides the prediction and the associated uncertainty. The prediction uncertainty of both the low-fidelity and the error metamodel is used for the adaptive refinement of the low- and high-fidelity training sets, respectively. The ratio of the computational cost of high- and low-fidelity evaluations affect the choice of the fidelity to sample.

The refinement of the training set is performed with five sampling methods. The methodologies aim at: (i) minimization of the maximum uncertainty of the multi-fidelity metamodel prediction, (ii) maximization of the expected improvement (as originally formulated), (iii) maximization of the expected improvement (computed with a different reference to better comply with the multi-fidelity methodology), (iv) minimization of an aggregated merit factor of prediction uncertainty and predicted objective function, and (v) multi-objective minimization of prediction uncertainty and predicted objective function. A parametric study on the effect of the ratio of computational cost between high- and low-fidelity is performed. The multi-fidelity metamodel performance is assessed in terms of convergence of the maximum uncertainty, normalized root mean square error between the multi-fidelity prediction and the high-fidelity function, and convergence of the objective function minimum.

Fig.9: Hydrofoil optimization, velocity contour for the optimal configuration identified with the sampling methods

The results of the analytical test problems have shown that the MCAS sampling method always converges to the objective function minimum with a lower computational cost than other successful sampling methods. Furthermore, the multi-fidelity metamodel outperforms a metamodel trained only with high-fidelity evaluations when β is lower or equal to 0.4. The analytical tests have shown that a multi-modal error function negatively affect the efficiency of the multi-fidelity metamodel. Therefore, the setup of a CFD-based problem should define the fidelities so as to have $\beta < 0.4$ and low-order error. The EI, MFEI, and ACAS methods have shown poor global exploration abilities. Specially, when multi-modal error functions occur.

The CFD-shape optimization problem of the NACA hydrofoil is an interesting challenge for the multi-fidelity metamodel. The existence of numerical noise affects the SRBF interpolation, resulting in large uncertainty of the multi-fidelity prediction in noisy regions of the domain. Therefore, the sampling methods that directly take into account the multi-fidelity prediction uncertainty have been “trapped” in adding training points in such region.

Future work includes comparing the current multi-fidelity results with a metamodel trained only with high-fidelity evaluations for all the sampling methods. Furthermore, the effects of U_f^* on the MCAS method in presence of numerical noise will be assessed, as well as the use of approximation methods (e.g. least square fit) as opposed to interpolation. Finally, the CFD simulation procedures will be optimized to reduce the noise at its source.

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References

- DE BAAR, J.; ROBERTS, S.; DWIGHT, R.; MALLOL, B. (2015), *Uncertainty quantification for a sailing yacht hull, using multi-fidelity kriging*, Computers & Fluids 123, pp.185-201
- DIEZ, M.; VOLPI, S.; SERANI, A.; STERN, F.; CAMPANA, E.F. (2015), *Simulation-based design optimization by sequential multi-criterion adaptive sampling and dynamic radial basis functions*, Int. Conf. Evolutionary and Deterministic Methods for Design, Optimization and Control with Applications to Industrial and Societal Problems (EUROGEN 2015)
- DURAND, M. (2012), *Interaction fluide-structure souple et légère, application aux voiliers*, Ph.D. thesis, Ecole Centrale de Nantes
- GEORGE, P.L.; BOROUCHAKI, H. (1998), *Delaunay triangulation and meshing – Application to Finite Elements*, Hermes
- HUBAND, S.; HINGSTON, P.; BARONE, L.; WHILE, L. (2006), *A review of multiobjective test problems and a scalable test problem toolkit*, IEEE Trans. Evolutionary Computation 10/5, pp.477-506
- JONES, D.R.; SCHONLAU, M.; WELCH, W.J. (1998), *Efficient global optimization of expensive black-box functions*, J. Global Optimization 13/4, pp.455-492
- LIU, H.; ONG, Y.S.; CAI, J. (2017), *A survey of adaptive sampling for global metamodeling in support of simulation-based complex engineering design*, Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization 57/1, pp.393-416
- NG, L.W.T.; ELDRED, M. (2012), *Multifidelity uncertainty quantification using non-intrusive polynomial chaos and stochastic collocation*, 53rd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conf.
- PELLEGRINI, R.; IEMMA, U.; LEOTARDI, C.; CAMPANA, E.F.; DIEZ, M. (2016), *Multi-fidelity adaptive global metamodel of expensive computer simulations*, IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC), pp.4444-4451

- PELLEGRINI, R.; SERANI, A.; LEOTARDI, C.; IEMMA, U.; CAMPANA, E.F.; DIEZ, M. (2017), *Formulation and parameter selection of multi-objective deterministic particle swarm for simulation-based optimization*, Applied Soft Computing 58, pp.714-731
- PLOÉ, P.; LANOS, R.; VISONNEAU, M.; WACKERS, J. (2017), *Bayesian strategies for simulation based optimisation and response surface creation using a single tool - Application to hydrofoil optimization*, 7th Int. Conf. Computational Methods in Marine Engineering (MARINE), Nantes
- SERANI, A.; LEOTARDI, C.; IEMMA, U.; CAMPANA, E.F.; FASANO, G.; DIEZ, M. (2016), *Parameter selection in synchronous and asynchronous deterministic particle swarm optimization for ship hydrodynamics problems*, Applied Soft Computing 49, pp.313-334
- VIANA, F.A.; SIMPSON, T.W.; BALABANOV, V.; TOROPOV, V. (2014), *Metamodeling in multi-disciplinary design optimization: How far have we really come?*, AIAA J. 52/4, pp.670-690
- VOLPI, S.; DIEZ, M.; GAUL, N.J.; SONG, H.; IEMMA, U.; CHOI, K.K.; CAMPANA E.F.; STERN, F. (2015), *Development and validation of a dynamic metamodel based on stochastic radial basis functions and uncertainty quantification*, Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization 51/2, pp.347-368
- WACKERS, J.; DENG, G.; GUILMINEAU, E.; LEROYER, A.; QUEUTEY, P.; VISONNEAU, M.; PALMIERI, A.; LIVERANI, A. (2017). *Can adaptive grid refinement produce grid-independent solutions for incompressible flows?*, J. Computational Physics 344, pp.364-380
- ZHAO, L.; CHOI, K. K.; LEE, I. (2011), *Metamodeling method using dynamic kriging for design optimization*. AIAA J. 49/9, pp.2034-2046
- ZHENG, J.; SHAO, X.; GAO, L.; JIANG, P.; LI, Z. (2013), *A hybrid variable-fidelity global approximation modelling method combining tuned radial basis function base and kriging correction*, J. Engineering Design 24/8, pp.604-622

Weather Routing Simulation as a Tool for Evaluating Ship's Performance in Operation

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Abstract

This paper describes potential of weather routing simulation in terms of its capability as a tool for evaluating ship's performance in operation. While weather routing simulation has been widely employed for enhancing ship's operation efficiency, its capability of predicting ship's performance under realistic weather condition can be utilized in evaluation of ship's service performance. In this study, this aspect of utilization of weather routing simulation is discussed through a variety of voyage simulations on ocean routes for a typical large merchant ship. Sea-Navi" voyage support system is employed in this study. Firstly, its accuracy in predicting ship's service performance is examined by comparing calculated results with on-board monitoring data. Then voyage simulations are conducted, and ship's service performance characteristics are examined for a variety of voyage conditions and long-time period by using weather data base established from the initial values of weather forecast data of the past. Based on average long-term performance characteristics obtained from weather routing simulations, ship's designers can readily evaluate realistic service performance of their designs and effectively improve the designs to enhance service performance by reducing the adverse effect of dominant weather element.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the new international rules established by International Maritime Organization (IMO) have stimulated significant efforts for the reduction of Green-house Gases (GHG) emissions from ocean-going ships in maritime community. Among the IMO rules for GHG emission reduction, Ship Energy Efficiency management Plan (SEEMP), *IMO (2012)*, has large impact on the operation of ocean-going ships. SEEMP is defined as an operational measure that establishes a mechanism to improve the energy efficiency. The SEEMP also provides an approach for shipping companies to manage ship and fleet efficiency performance over time in service. The SEEMP urges the ship owner and operator at each stage of the plan to consider new practice for optimising the performance of a ship. In SEEMP, ship performance monitoring and weather routing are recommended as measures effective for enhancing the performance of a ship in service.

Under these circumstances, optimum routing (or weather routing) which optimizes voyage route in terms of minimum fuel-consumption based on weather and ocean current forecast has been employed widely for reducing GHG emissions and fuel consumptions in shipping. While this type of approach have long been employed as an effective measure to achieve safe operation, their potential as a mean for improving voyage economy has also recognized in their capability of reducing fuel consumption through voyage optimization. Acquisition of accurate weather data is also beneficial for conducting high-fidelity assessment of ship's responses under actual sea weather conditions and enhancing ship's operational safety.

To cope with these environments, Japan Marine United Corporation (JMU) has developed voyage support system called "Sea-Navi" for reducing GHG emissions and fuel consumptions of ocean-going ships, *Orihara and Yoshida. (2010)*, *Orihara et al. (2014)*, *Orihara and Yoshida (2015)*, *Orihara et al. (2016)*. "Sea-Navi" can optimize voyage route under actual operating conditions by taking account of relevant weather parameters, including wind, waves and ocean currents.

In the present study, potential of weather routing simulation in terms of its capability as a tool for evaluating ship's performance in operation is examined. While weather routing simulation has been widely employed for enhancing ship's operation efficiency, its capability of predicting ship's

performance under realistic weather condition can be utilized in evaluation of ship’s service performance. “Sea-Navi” optimum routing system is used in this study.

A description of “Sea-Navi” system is given in the next section. Then the capability of “Sea-Navi” system is examined by conducting route optimizing simulations for trans-pacific voyage cases, where “Sea-Navi” system’s effectiveness in evaluating ship’s service performance in a realistic sea conditions is examined. Brief conclusions are presented in the final section.

2. “Sea-Navi” voyage support system

Voyage support system “Sea-Navi” consists of the following two sub-systems, Fig.1:

- 1) Optimum routing system
Optimum route for safe, economic and ecological (least GHG emission) voyage is provided by use of vessel-specific characteristics of hull and machinery, weather and ocean current forecast data.
- 2) On-board monitoring system
Monitoring is made of actual state of weather encountered, hull responses, installed machinery conditions. Monitored data are transmitted to the shore-based system’s server via satellite communication. With these monitored data, system’s users can conduct voyage performance analysis that confirms exact relationship between actual encountered weather and the vessel’s performance.

Fig.1: Conceptual sketch of “Sea-Navi” system

2.1. Optimum routing system

Sea-Navi optimum routing system calculates an optimum route for the specific voyage case using both vessel-specific performance characteristics and latest weather and ocean-current forecast available on-board ship. Ship’s actual operating condition is properly considered in optimum-routing calculation. Various route types, including great circle, rhumb line, minimum time, minimum fuel-consumption routes can be selected in optimum routing calculation while satisfying safety constraints by setting the limits of safety criteria in terms of ship responses (roll angle, pitch angle, vertical acceleration, bow slamming green water on deck, propeller racing, etc.) as well as encountered weather conditions (wave height, absolute wind velocity etc.). Thus, optimum routes are determined

so that it does not pass the regions where either ships responses or encountered weather conditions exceed the specified safety limit values. In addition, user-specified arbitrary routes can be evaluated together with the optimum routes by simply specifying the way-points of each route.

After execution of the routing calculation, users can easily compare a variety of parameters evaluated for the calculated routes, such as estimated time of arrival, total fuel consumption as well as the time histories of encountered weather parameters (wind, waves, currents etc.) and ship responses along the route.

For the optimum route searching, efficient searching algorithm based on the A+ algorithm of *Hart (1968)* is employed. This enables efficient optimum route searching and allows the system PC to systematically evaluate all the possible routes satisfying user's requirements in a reasonable amount of computation time. For normal conditions, "Sea-Navi" can complete optimum route search in a few minutes on the standard laptop-type PC for the case of trans-Pacific voyage. Using this efficient optimum-route searching capability, users can improve their route plan to a better one that best meets their requirements by trying several routes using Sea-Navi generated optimum routes as a reference.

Route search calculations are conducted on the two-dimensional grid system which subdivides the sea areas in both latitude and longitude directions at a constant interval. Evaluation of cost (objective functions to be minimized in optimizing the route e.g. fuel consumption) is conducted at each grid points along each possible route satisfying the user-defined constraints in terms of safety limits and time of arrival. Among the routes evaluated, the one which offers least cost (e.g. fuel consumption) is selected as an optimum route.

To enhance the benefits of optimum route navigation, optimum routing calculations are usually updated for the remaining leg at a user-specified interval after departure of voyage (usually 1 to 2 days). By using updated routing results, incorrect influence due to uncertainty in weather forecast on optimum routing calculations can be eliminated. In addition, users can select more favourable route for the remaining leg of the voyage using latest weather forecast instead of using that available prior to the departure.

Optimum routing system can be installed on both on-board Sea-Navi PC and shore-side user-terminal which is connected to the system's shore-based Data Centre via Internet. Latest weather forecast data is downloaded twice daily from the Data Centre to the on-board PC (via INMARSAT communication channel) and the shore-side user (via Internet). Thus, optimum routing calculations can be conducted concurrently by all the users concerned, for example on-board personnel and shore-side operators. With this capability, shore-side users could support on-board operations by sending suggestions concerning the voyage planning based on their "Sea-Navi" optimum routing calculations.

2.2. On-board monitoring system

Typical configuration of "Sea-Navi" monitoring system is shown in Fig.2. This system primarily consists of a suite of sensors (whose combination differs for a particular ship) and a system's PC to acquire, analyse and display data. Most of hull-related data (ship's speed, course, heading wind, rudder angle etc.) are obtained from Voyage Data Recorder (VDR) as a LAN output data. Machinery-related data (fuel-oil flow rate, fuel-oil temperature, shaft power etc.) are obtained from an engine-room data logger. Ship motions and encountered waves are optional monitoring items and measured by using dedicated motions sensors and a radar wave analyser. Since the radar wave analyser uses radar image from on-board X-band navigational radar, wave measurement is conducted only several times a day by manually changing the radar setting to short range mode to enhance the resolution of radar image for normal duration of 20 minutes. Measured data are merged as a time-history data file of 20-min length containing all the data items. Then, statistical analysis of the time-history data is conducted in the system's PC. Average, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, significant value and zero up-cross period are calculated all the data items at an interval of 20-minute.

Statistically analyzed monitored data are then uploaded to the shore-based Data Centre at a user-defined arbitrary interval (usually 4 to 6-hour interval) for the assessment by shore-side users. Ship-to-shore data communication is conducted via INMARSAT communication channel.

Fig.2: Configuration of "Sea-Navi" on-board monitoring system

2.3. Ship's performance prediction procedure

To accurately estimate ship's hydrodynamic performance and main engine's fuel consumption under way, "Sea-Navi" employs vessel-specific performance model which is derived from the results of model tests, sea trial and main-engine shop tests.

Still-water speed and propulsive power relationships in a wide range of loading conditions are derived from model tests by taking account of the model-ship correlation obtained from sea trial results. Ship motion and added resistance characteristics in waves are evaluated on the basis of response amplitude operators (RAO's) obtained from both model tests and theoretical calculations. Ship motions and added resistance in a seaway are evaluated by combining the RAO's with appropriate wave energy spectra. Wind forces acting on the hull are evaluated from either wind-tunnel test results or empirical formulae. In a seaway, side force and turning moment due to wind and waves induce drifting of the vessel. Drifting increases ships hydrodynamic resistance mainly due to oblique motion of the hull. In Sea-Navi, the drifting resistance component is considered by evaluating the drifting angles under the influences of wind and waves.

3. Validation of ship performance prediction

Since the high accuracy in weather and ocean current forecast and the performance prediction procedure are indispensable in evaluating high-fidelity ship's service performance, their accuracies are verified by comparing with the on-board measurements.

3.1. Verification of weather forecast data

Estimated weather wind and waves along the subject vessel's actual route interpolated from the forecast data are compared with those obtained from Sea-Navi on-board monitoring system.

In the following, monitored weather data obtained on board a pure car and truck carrier (PCTC) operating in Pacific Ocean are used for the verification of forecast data.

Comparisons of true wind speed and direction, significant wave height and relative wave direction are shown in Figs.3 and 4. Here, relative wave direction is defined relative to ship’s heading. In the figures, time histories of weather parameters are shown on the basis of elapsed time after the start of the selected leg of the voyage. Measured data shown in closed circle are an average of 20-minute time-history data.

Fig.3: Comparison of encountered weather data, Pacific Ocean eastbound voyage.

Fig.4: Comparison of encountered weather data, Pacific Ocean westbound voyage

Concerning wind speed, forecast data agree quite well with measured ones over an entire range of the voyage including the strong wind cases (around 20 m/s wind speeds). It is also noted that the forecast data reproduce the wind velocities variations in the latter half of the westbound voyage case, Fig.3, where absolute wind increased about 4 m/s to around 20 m/s in 24 hours.

As for wave data comparison, forecast data again correlate fairly well with the measured one in both height and direction although the number of measured data is relatively small due to the manual measurement operation of the radar wave analyser. This favourable correlation in wave height can be considered reasonable since the ocean wave prediction is conducted on the bases of forecast wind field data.

From the results of comparison with the measured data including wide range of weather conditions as described above, it can be considered that the wind and wave forecast data employed in “Sea-Navi” can predict actual weather conditions with sufficient accuracy for optimum routing calculations.

3.2. Verification of performance prediction

To examine the accuracy of the performance prediction procedure described in 2.3, estimated performance parameters are compared with the on-board measured ones obtained from “Sea-Navi” on-board monitoring. Ship’s performance parameters (speed, FOC, ship motions) along the trial vessel’s actual route calculated with measured shaft revolution as an input and using weather and ocean current forecast data. Results are compared with those measured on-board.

In the following, monitored ship’s performance data obtained on board a PCTC operating in Pacific Ocean (same vessel as employed for weather comparison) are used for the verification of “Sea-Navi” performance predictions. Two voyage cases same as the previous weather comparison, eastbound voyage case (from Japan to U.S. west coast) and westbound voyage case (from central America to Japan), are selected as representatives of ocean-going voyage.

Fig.5: Comparison of ship’s performance, Pacific Ocean eastbound voyage

Fig.6: Comparison of ship’s performance, Pacific Ocean westbound voyage

Comparisons are made of ship’s speed over ground (speed O.G.), main engine fuel consumption, pitch angle and roll angle, Figs.5 and 6. Time histories of performance parameters are shown on the basis of elapsed time after departure of the selected voyage leg. Except for roll and pitch angles,

averaged values of each 20-minute time-history data are shown in closed circles. Measure roll and pitch angles shown are standard deviations obtained from same time-history data.

As clearly seen from the figures, estimated performance parameters calculated using the procedures described in 2.3, agree quite well with the measured ones. Although some discrepancies are seen in several parameters such as speed O.G. and roll angle, estimations reproduce the general trends of performance variations with reasonable accuracy. From the agreement shown in Figs.5 and 6, adequacy of the “Sea-Navi” performance prediction procedures can be confirmed.

4. Evaluation of Ship’s performance in service by “Sea-Navi” optimum routing simulation

Service performance evaluating capability of “Sea-Navi” optimum routing system has been examined by the optimum-routing simulation of a PCTC (similar vessel as employed for “Sea-Navi” verification described in chapter 3). The routing simulations are conducted for one year duration with a specified interval of departure on the trans Pacific route between Japan and U.S. west coast in which the subject ship (PCTC) sailed along both the great circle (shortest distance) route (GC Route hereafter) and “Sea-Navi” recommended least-FOC optimum routes (OPT Route hereafter) for design load condition. First convergence characteristics of routing simulation results are examined and adequate time interval for routing simulations are evaluated. Then, long-term service performances are evaluated based on “Sea-Navi” routing simulations.

4.1. Convergence study of routing simulation results

To examine the convergence characteristics of routing simulation results in terms of long-term service performance evaluation, convergence of averaged performance parameters with respect to intervals of departure in routing simulations. In this study, intervals of departure from 0.25 day (6 hour) to 8 day are used. First, routing simulations are conducted with a departure time interval of 0.25 day over a duration from January 1 to March 31 in 2017 on the westbound trans-pacific route (U.S. west coast to Japan) at a normal speed (constant shaft revolution) condition.

Typical examples of routing simulation results are shown in Figs.7 to 9. In these figures, three typical cases of westbound trans-pacific OPT route, i.e.

- 1) Northern OPT route which goes through the Bering Sea north of Aleutian Islands,
- 2) Central OPT route close to the GC (shortest distance) route and
- 3) Southern OPT route which traces generally along constant-latitude line

are shown on the weather map (sea surface pressure and wave height distributions). As shown in the figures, OPT route locations are closely related to the weather conditions, in particular, location of large low-pressure systems typical of winter north Pacific. In the case the large low-pressure system exists in the central (close to GC route), OPT route tend to be Northern type to take advantage of strong tail wind and following wing condition prevailing along the north side of the low-pressure system. On the other hand, when the low-pressure system exists north of the Aleutian Islands, OPT route tend to select constant-latitude like route to avoid encountering against wind and head wave condition prevailing the south side of the low-pressure system. Central OPT route is usually selected when the weather conditions along the GC route is relatively calm.

Simulation results of speed loss, Evaluated FOC increase and route distance are shown in Fig.10. Here, performance parameters are evaluated with respect to those evaluated on the still water condition (i.e. no wind, wave, ocean current) on the GC route.

Then, ship’s service performance parameters including voyage speed loss, FOC increase and route distance obtained from the simulations are statistically analysed in terms of average and standard deviation (SD) for each performance parameter with varying departure time intervals. For each departure time interval, average difference relative to the minimum interval case (0.25 day interval) is evaluated as a route-mean sum of respective interval cases.

Fig.7: Comparison of GC and OPT route, case 1: Northern OPT route

Fig.8: Comparison of GC and OPT route, case 2: Central OPT route

Fig.9: Comparison of GC and OPT route, case 3: Southern OPT route

For example, in the case of 1-day departure interval, 4 cases results among which departure data differs by 0.25 day each are analysed for the 3-month duration and the differences between their statistical values (average and SD) and those for the minimum interval case are evaluated in a RMS manner.

Fig.10: Routing simulation results for winter trans. Pacific voyage

Fig.11: Encountered weather data, Indian Ocean eastbound voyage

In Fig.11, convergence characteristics for speed loss, FOC increase and route distance for the winter westbound trans-pacific voyages obtained from routing simulations are compared between GC and OPT route cases. All the evaluated parameters converge monotonically with respect to departure time interval for performance evaluation (ΔT_{Dep}). With a departure time interval of 1 day, differences of averages of performance parameters are less than 1% compared to the minimum interval (0.25 day) case. Thus the departure interval setting of 1 day can be considered as adequate for the evaluation of average values. In the following evaluations, departure interval of 1 day is used for the long-term performance evaluations.

4.2. Long-term evaluation of service performance in the North Pacific

To examine the characteristics of long-term service performance in the North Pacific, “Sea-Navi” routing simulations are conducted for GC and OPT route for a duration of one year (January to December, 2017) with a departure interval of 1 day in both westbound (U.S. west coast to Japan) and eastbound (Japan to U.S. west coast) cases. A PCTC same as used in the convergence study in Sec. 4.1 is used for the simulations. Displacement is set at the design full load condition. Shaft speed is set at normal service condition. So-called “Now-cast” weather data which is constructed from the initial data of weather forecast data of the past (year 2017) is used for the simulations. Ship’s service performance parameters (speed loss and FOC increase) are evaluated with respect to those evaluated on the still water condition (i.e. no wind, wave, ocean current) on the GC route.

Figs.12 and 13 compare voyage-average speed loss and FOC increase for westbound and eastbound cases, respectively. As clearly shown in the figures, in particular westbound cases, speed loss and FOC increase are significantly reduced in the OPT routes. This tendency is remarkable in autumn and winter seasons when adverse weather conditions resulting from east-going large low-pressure systems as shown in Figs.7 through 9 are prevailing. Also, note the tendencies in speed loss and FOC increase are quite different between the westbound and east bound cases. This is mainly due to the north Pacific’s weather conditions which are strongly characterized by the east-going low-pressure systems thus adverse weather conditions (e.g. adverse wind and head waves) are frequent in westbound cases.

Fig.12: Encountered weather and added resistances, Indian Ocean eastbound voyage, laden condition

Fig.13: Encountered weather and added resistances, Indian Ocean eastbound voyage, laden condition

Fig.14: Encountered weather and added resistances, Indian Ocean eastbound voyage, laden condition

From a long-term performance evaluation point of view, differences shown in Figs.12 and 13 indicate that service performances are significantly underestimated if the GC route is selected. Monthly averaged performance parameters (speed loss and FOS increase) are compared in Fig.14. Service performances in OPT route cases are noticeably good compared to those in GC route cases. For example, speed loss is increased by about 1.5 kn. and FOC increase is reduced by about 30% on annual average basis for the westbound case. These differences are significant in the context of ship’s performance point of view and the high-fidelity ship’s service performance predications based on the accurate routing simulations such as “Sea-Navi” can contribute to the realization of high fuel efficiency and low emission in actual operations.

Traditionally long-term performance evaluation of ship’s performance is evaluated on the specified (i.e. fixed) route using long-term weather frequency probability data. While in the sea routes where routing variations are small, such as coastal route and restricted waters, fixed route approach may be

reasonable for the long-term evaluation, optimum routing consideration, that is avoidance of excessive adverse weather conditions, should be made for the trans ocean route cases such as trans-Pacific and trans-Atlantic routes to accurately evaluate ship's long-term service performance.

5. Conclusions

Potential of weather routing simulation in terms of its capability as a tool for evaluating ship's performance in operation is examined. This aspect of utilization of weather routing simulation is discussed through a variety of voyage simulations in the north Pacific.

“Sea-Navi” voyage support system is employed and its accuracy in predicting ship's service performance is examined by comparing calculated results with on-board monitoring data. Then voyage simulations are conducted, and ship's service performance characteristics are examined for a variety of voyage conditions and long-time period by using the past weather data.

It is shown that long-term ship's service performance can be accurately evaluated from “Sea-Navi” routing simulations conducted with a departure interval of 1 day or less. Simulation results indicate that the long-term ship's service performances for trans-ocean cases are significantly affected by the optimum routing and the long-term estimations on the great circle fixed cases result in the under-estimation of annual average service performance in the North Pacific by a magnitude of 30% in FOC increase. It is clearly confirmed that optimum routing effect should be considered for the accurate evaluation of ship's service performance for trans-ocean cases such as the North Pacific.

References

- HART, P.E. (1968), *A formal basis for the heuristic determination of minimum cost paths*, IEEE Trans. Systems Science and Cybernetics 4/2, pp.100-107
- IMO (2012), *Guideline for the Development of a Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP)*, MEPC.213 (63) Annex 9, Int. Mar. Org., London
- ORIHARA, H.; YOSHIDA, H. (2010), *Development of voyage support system “Sea-Navi” for lower fuel consumption and CO2 emissions*, Int. Symp. Ship Design and Operation for Environmental Sustainability, London, pp.73-80
- ORIHARA, H.; YOSHIDA, H.; HIROTA, K.; YAMASAKI, K.; SAITOH, Y. (2014), *Verification of full-scale performance of eco-friendly bulk carriers under actual operating conditions by on-board performance monitoring*, 2nd Int. Conf. Maritime Technology and Engineering, Lisbon, pp.755-763
- ORIHARA, H.; YOSHIDA, H. (2015), *Verification of energy saving capability of optimum routing by full-scale trial navigation*, 14th Conf. Computer and IT Application in the Maritime Industries, Ulrichshusen, pp.343-354
- ORIHARA, H.; YOSHIDA, H.; AMAYA, I. (2016), *Enhanced voyage support system based on detailed weather and performance monitoring*, 15th Conf. Computer and IT Application in the Maritime Industries, Lecce, pp.401-409

Digital Model or Digital Twin?

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Abstract

Despite its frequent use today, the term Digital Twin has been introduced only recently in the maritime domain. Nevertheless, many application cases are proposed in publications and partly realized already. Benefits are expected in diverse usage scenarios, both in production and operation. Reflecting this spread, publication authors use different benefits or properties such as model detail or simulation capabilities to qualify a digital model as being a digital twin. This paper tries to identify those characteristics of digital twins which are common across domains. These might serve as defining properties and could aid in implementation of the concept.

1. Introduction

We all have a certain perception when hearing the term "digital twin". In the maritime domain, it is often connected to a somewhat realistically looking 3D representation of a ship structure. And we think of the digital twin also being updated according to changes which a physical object experiences during its lifetime: changes in configuration, but also changes due to wear and tear.

It is easy to list numerous publications and websites referring to the term digital twin, defining it through its purpose, benefits or degree of realism. An example is given by *Parrott and Warshaw (2017)*: "A digital twin can be defined, fundamentally, as an evolving digital profile of the historical and current behavior of a physical object or process that helps optimize business performance." As stated in *Grieves and Vickers (2017)* the digital twin concept was already described in 2002 as "Conceptual Ideal for PLM (Product Lifecycle Management)" calling it "Mirrored Spaces Model" at that time. Probably one of the earliest mentioning of the term can be found at NASA. Their Technology Roadmap, *Shafto et al. (2010)*, uses it in the context of Simulation-Based System Engineering. "A Digital Twin is an integrated multiphysics, multiscale simulation of a vehicle or system that uses the best available physical models, sensor updates, fleet history, etc., to mirror the life of its corresponding flying twin. The digital twin is ultra-realistic...".

When the intention is to implement a digital twin in IT systems, we need to be able to describe it in terms of its constituents. And we would strive for a wide coverage of component and system types and application domains for which the implementation could be used. Such a description is more difficult to find. Is a detailed simulation model a digital twin? If yes, how detailed does it need to be? Is a digital twin a 3D model? This paper proposes a characterization and a description of the common constituents of a digital twin. A common understanding of its parts would aid collaborative efforts in realizing them and the benefits from their use.

Digital twins exist today for physical objects, for processes (such as manufacturing of specific parts) and even for organizations and people. A prominent example might be the functionality provided by Google Maps: from time to time we receive driving and navigation advice towards our anticipated goal on our mobile phones when entering our car. No interaction is required. The underlying systems obviously has captured previous motion data of us, has a digital representation of our person and can predict our behaviour. This paper will focus on physical objects such as ships and their systems and components, the concepts might also be valid more widely.

2. Benefits of digital twins

A digital twin can have extensive benefits. And, as *Schleich et al. (2017)* write, "digital twin" is understood quite differently in the industry. Different manufacturers focus on different purposes when

investing into the technology:

- to increase the manufacturing flexibility and competitiveness,
- improve product design performance,
- forecasting the health and performance of products over lifetime,
- improved efficiency and quality in manufacturing.

An interpretation and use case which comes close to usage in the maritime industry is given by *Glaessgen and Stargel (2012)*. They write with relation to NASA and US Air Force vehicles, “current approaches for certification, fleet management and sustainment are largely based on statistics and assumed similarity between testing and operational conditions. The digital twin will enable a fundamental paradigm shift if high fidelity simulation is integrated with the vehicle’s on-board health management system, maintenance history and all available historical and fleet data to mirror the life of its physical twin. This would enable unprecedented levels of safety and reliability.”

Collecting examples from more publications one arrives at an extensive but surely still incomplete list of benefits and purposes of digital twins

- to increase the performance of the physical object,
- to optimize maintenance measures,
- to gather knowledge from many similar physical parts to improve future designs or production processes,
- to support autonomy in production, *Rosen et al. (2015)*,
- to realize smart products which may be located at all times and know their own history, current status and alternative routes to achieving their target state, *Uhlemann et al. (2017)*,
- to ensure safety through verifying and/or predicting function in particular in case of planned modifications (cargo containment, propulsion, navigation, stability, structural integrity, system robustness after update of controller software ...),
- to mitigate unpredictable, undesirable emergent behaviour in complex systems, *Grieves and Vickers (2017)*,
- to verify environmental compliance through tracing consumption, routes, cargo of a ship,
- to monitor and control a component within a service contract (“power by the hour”),
- to continuously test and verify Cyber-Physical Systems, in particular before and after upgrades of control software and in connection with the drive towards autonomous ship functions.

The benefits confirm that investing into digital twins can be very worthwhile. For this reason we try to contribute towards having a common view on its constituents in particular regarding that it might have several purposes. What is the common denominator?

3. What characterizes a digital twin?

The broad range of application areas naturally leads to different definitions of the term. For finding a good characterization of what constitutes a digital twin, it appears useful to look at its properties which are more easy to agree with.

Such a property is that the term “twin” in itself suggests that there is a second object – most naturally a physical one – which is “mirrored” by the digital twin. A digital model without a unique physical counterpart might later become a part of a digital twin.

The second property is that the digital twin should reflect changes to its physical counterpart. Otherwise, it would lose its “twin” property.

The third property is that building and maintaining a digital twin bears a cost and hence serves a

purpose. It shall have a positive effect on the physical object. Therefore, it must have some inherent or connected logic -such as a simulation capability- to fulfil this purpose. It models *behaviour*. The degree of detail of a digital twin thereby follows its purpose: it depends on the context the digital twin is made for and intended to be used in. In a business setting, the level of detail will only be as necessary for its specific purpose.

Based on the above properties three elements are proposed to be the constituents of a digital twin. These also follow a quote from Himagiri Mukkamala (GE Digital's head of engineering for the Predix platform): "[The digital twin] is the ability to model your physical asset in a digital world. It's the ability to tie those analytics to these assets and then run the analytics against the data sets that are coming in real time or on a scheduled basis", www.applause.com/blog/digital-twins-iot-faq/.

Apart from its unique physical counterpart the three constituents are

- A. Asset representation: i.e. a digital representation of a unique physical object (e.g. a ship or an engine or part of it)
- B. Behavioural model: Encoded logic to allow predictions and/or decisions on the physical twin (e.g. realized through simulation capability for optimizing maintenance activities)
- C. Condition or configuration data: Data reflecting status of and changes to the unique physical object during its lifecycle phases (e.g. captured through inspections or measurements, updates in case of modifications)

To be able to track the physical changes, it is necessary to relate recorded data (modifications, condition, environment, repair, conversion, sensing) to the representation of the object. Decisions are then supported by a behavioural model which is adapted and loaded based on the recordings, Fig.1.

The actual form and degree of detail of a digital twin depends on its intended purpose. Also, the asset representation and the behavioural model can partly or fully be shared between the digital twins of multiple physical entities – until a physical twin undergoes significant changes.

Fig.1: Constituents of the Digital Twin

3.1. Asset representation

The asset representation describes the physical object. It covers one or several disciplines (electrical, mechanical, software, ...) and optionally the shape of the physical object. This representation has the

purpose to associate captured information from production or operation of the physical object to it. With its help, e.g.

- the actual configuration of a system (parameters and identity of its components) can be described through interlinking its components,
- a vibration measurement can be identified with a point on a gearbox with a certain serial number
- a photo or a visual observation can be identified with a location in the steel structure

and it will become possible to track such recordings over time. Moreover, observations can be correlated across multiple assets of the same type.

The physical object only needs to be modelled up to the degree necessary for identifying the context of the acquired data. E.g. the point location of the vibration measurement needs to be identified with the precision sufficient for a subsequent analysis. In the same way, a visual observation on a steel structure should be associated to its location only as required by subsequent repair advice or corrosion prediction. In both cases, no 3D model might be necessary. The relevant property of the asset representation is that it enables linking of the observation to the behavioural model, e.g. a simulation model.

The asset representation could also be called digital model – but the term model can easily lead to misunderstandings as it is used widely also for other artefacts (such as simulation models). A prominent example for the asset representation is a 3D structural model of the ship. As its purpose here is “associating captured data” this is not a simulation model. Rather, the model is targeted towards easy visualization when graphically capturing findings (thickness measurements, coating damages) and later automatic mapping onto a 3D structural analysis model.

Model provided by Reederei Buss and Neptun
Stahlkonstruktion Rostock

Fig.2: Asset representations of a hull structure (left) and a generator (right) respectively. Both serve the purpose of identifying assets and its parts. Thereby, observations or measurements can be used to update behavioural models and support decisions.

If sister vessels or distinct instances of the same type of component, e.g. a pump, are sufficiently well described with the same asset representation, major parts can of course be re-used for each physical copy. Nevertheless, the captured measurements will differ for each physical copy. If differences between sister vessels or separate instances of components are too large to clearly identify findings, their representations need to be adapted.

In case of machinery components, the asset representation could be much simpler than a 3D model. It might just consist in the serial number of the components, its product type, and a list of its main characteristics, e.g. rpm, power consumption, etc. Additionally, a list of measurement points or a simple drawing could be used to identify measurement locations where data is captured periodically.

In some cases, e.g. monitoring of the tail shaft, a simple sketch of the shaft bearing might indicate measurement locations.

In both cases, through the asset representation condition data can be fed into behavioural models such as simulation models. The asset representation therefore provides the semantics for the observations and leads to a unique identification of what is measured.

To enhance re-usability, the asset representation as part of the digital twin should be built on standardized catalogues of domain specific ship components and parts. For ships, such a catalogue is e.g. given through the Vessel Information System (VIS), *Vindøy (2010)*. Although the asset representation shall make observations of changes to the physical twin uniquely identifiable, large parts of it can typically be re-used for many different physical copies.

3.2. Behavioural model

A digital twin is put together for a purpose. As a cost is associated with it, in a commercial setting we anticipate benefits. As *Parrott and Warshaw (2017)* put it: “The digital twin may enable companies to solve physical issues faster by detecting them sooner, predict outcomes to a much higher degree of accuracy, design and build better products, and, ultimately, better serve their customers.”

For supporting its specific purpose, for predicting and for taking decisions some logic is required which reflects the behaviour of the physical counterpart. In most cases this is coupled with the ability to simulate the physical counterpart considering the recorded physical or software changes. Therefore, this part of the digital twin can be represented by one or several behavioural models covering the respective discipline and or parts of the physical object. Examples are

- a simulation model for the time domain behaviour of a fuel system,
- a mathematical model covering the effect of hull degradation on vessel performance,
- a complex system model covering a dynamic positioning system including its controller software,
- a Finite Element model of the ship hull structure.

An update procedure for the simulation model may be required to reflect observed condition information. The asset representation here is the necessary link to allow automatic updating, or loading, of the simulation model based on measurements or observations.

Fig.3: Re-use of Simulation Models for different Physical Ships. Here, the asset representations are no simulation models. The behavioural models for different simulation purposes (cargo hold analysis, quasi-static global FE analysis, longitudinal strength, etc.) are re-used independently for each physical copy.

As simulation models are often expensive to set up, such models are often re-used for many physical copies of the same asset type, e.g. sister vessels or components of the same product type, Fig.3.

3.3. Condition and configuration data

The digital twin mirrors the life of its physical counterpart. Therefore, it must have the ability to store data reflecting changes of the latter. Most typically, these are changes in configuration, observations such as inspection records, measurements (hand-held or continuous sensing) or other data about modifications to the physical copy (e.g. repairs). Additionally, this can be operational information such as routes taken, environmental conditions / loads experienced by the ship, events such as bunkering, status such as “watertight door closed at...”, etc. Last not least, data acquired during manufacturing (e.g. applied coating and environmental conditions when coating was done) or at commissioning (baseline inspection) can be used to mirror the physical object already during production.

The asset representation is needed so that the recorded data on the physical copy can be attached to it. In this way, semantics is added to the data, it becomes information. Examples are thickness measurements for which the location and time are recorded on the model. The measurement data becomes useful through connecting it to its structural part in the model. Another example is vibration measurements taken periodically on a gearbox. If these periodic measurement results are systematically associated to the asset representation, trends in vibration level can be detected, and maintenance can be planned based on actual condition.

Fig.4: Measurement points associated to asset representation of structure allowing identification of point location and mapping to simulation model (left). Software configuration information (right).

4. Other characteristics of the digital twin

While sharing the above three constituents, digital twins can have a large variety of further properties. Each of them would be regarded as optional with respect to their presence or quantity as it would be difficult to define limits when they are sufficient to qualify for a digital twin. Therefore, the proposal here is to make use of the term digital twin independent of the below listed properties, but rather to fix it at the three parts described in the previous chapter.

4.1. Degree of model detail

As referred to in the NASA Technology Roadmap, see above, the digital twin is “ultra-realistic”. Although for many applications it can be useful to be close to reality, the question is where “ultra-realistic” starts. Moreover, even the subjective degree of realism will depend on the purpose for which the digital twin is assembled: what is realistic for one purpose, might be unrealistic for another purpose.

4.2. Number of ship systems / functions covered

With rising complexity of ships and their systems, it becomes more difficult to master system design in a way that all required functions are delivered robustly. In particular, ships are built today through collaboration between multiple tiers of suppliers: from component supplier, system supplier or system integrator towards the yard as the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM). Requirements, specifications and interfaces need to be exchanged between partners to realize systems which integrate supplied components. Based on this multi-tier collaboration, it appears logical that a similar setup will be reflected in the digital twin: The digital twin of the ship will be realized through the interconnection of digital twins of lower level systems and components (see section below). For this reason, digital twins can exist on every system level of the ship – a single component, such as a thruster, might have a digital twin. So, whether a digital artefact covers sufficient ship functions to represent a digital twin of the ship rather depends on the question whether it fulfils its specific purpose than on the number of included subsystems.

4.3. Coverage of different physical phenomena/engineering disciplines

As above, the question whether the electrical behaviour, the control software, or the mechanical properties need to be modelled into the digital twin very much depends on its purpose and the question whether the respective behaviour needs to be simulated for the respective questions. I.e., a digital twin can well cover only the electrical behaviour if e.g. only the power management system is considered. In a broader context, a twin of the same system might require modelling of the mechanical behaviour of the respective consumers in the system.

4.4. Lifecycle phase covered

Digital twins can be used during operation phase of a product, but also during production, see e.g. *Uhlemann et al. (2017)*. The latter is especially useful

- to record baseline information for handover into operation,
- to optimize future building of the same product,
- to trace construction status.

The design phase can well be used to assemble the required asset representation and the behavioural models, as they are increasingly required for designing complex products. Transferring information from design and production towards operational use would significantly lower cost for building up a digital twin in operation. At the same time, this information might contain critical IP of the designer and/or manufacturer. Therefore, a proper balancing of the level of information exchange needs to be found between the involved business partners.

4.5. Frequency and detail of data exchange and updating

Configuration information of the physical object can well be collected manually during repair or update of the respective ship or component. Also, measurements or observations are today often collected by specialized inspectors or service providers. Nevertheless, the rise of the Internet of Things is an indication that sensor based data collection will increase also onboard ships. Both with manual capturing and automatic transfer of sensor data, condition and configuration information of the ship and its components can be fed into the digital twin.

The same is true for the way from the digital copy of the ship towards its physical representation. Decisions taken based on behaviour simulations or other decision logic can be transferred to the ship for manual action such as repairs. On the other hand, control logic for the ship might be a part of its digital twin. In this case a direct data link to the ship would be useful.

5. The shared digital twin

Ships are built today through collaboration with multiple tiers of suppliers: from component supplier, system supplier or system integrator towards the yard as the OEM. With rising complexity of the ship and its parts the digital twin concept will be realized also on the intermediate tiers, not only on the ship level. E.g. the engine manufacturer, in particular when striving to take over maintenance responsibility as with “power by the hour”-concepts, will have an own interest (and also the best knowledge base) to implement digital twins of the delivered engines through feeding online captured sensor data into own behavioural models. Thereby, maintenance can be controlled, performance can be optimized, and reliability can be ensured.

Building on this, it becomes clear that the digital twin of a lower tier component will become part of the digital twin of the ship. I.e., the digital twin of the ship could be built through assembling the digital twins of its systems. The latter on the other hand could assemble the twins of their components.

Based on this scenario, the different tier stakeholders will need to pass on information of the lower level digital twins up to the higher level. Considering that companies need to protect their Intellectual Property it seems to be natural, that this handover of information will not include all detail:

- the behavioural model which is re-used on the higher tier would not need to cover all internal physical processes. Rather, the response to input signals only needs to be covered up to the required precision,
- condition and configuration data would be delivered as required to deliver the higher tier system function. E.g. only those signals which are relevant for performance and reliability of the ship would be passed on to the ship operator,
- the asset representation would only need to describe the component as required for operation and maintenance, not all its internal constituents.

Because these aggregations and simplifications reduce the level of Intellectual Property (IP) which needs to be passed on, they facilitate the build-up of a shared, and thereby affordable, digital twin of the ship.

As *Boschert and Rosen (2016)* write: “the digital twin is not one complete model of the physical product, but a set of linked operation data artefacts and simulation models, which are of suitable granularity for their intended purpose and evolve throughout the product life-cycle.”

The digital twin of the ship bears complexity by potentially being a combination of shared twins with constituents from different design phases, disciplines and managed (and therefore also updated) by different stakeholders. Through this and the fact that each physical copy can lead to a different configuration of this system, the information management of digital twins can become complex.

6. Summary

Apart from having a unique physical counterpart, a digital twin has three main constituents. The asset representation describes the physical object in sufficient detail that condition and configuration data of the latter can be interpreted. This data can be thereby used to update behavioural models which in turn help giving feedback to the physical object.

Degree of model detail or number of covered components or functions can differ widely for digital twins. Even if this degree/number is low, the updated asset representation connected with a behavioural model can fulfil a purpose and qualify for being a digital twin.

The asset representation as well as the behavioural model can be shape models, in particular if structural matters are in focus. For non-structural parts, such as machinery systems, the behavioural

models will typically not be shape-based, possibly even containing controller software. Therefore, 3D models and digital twins are different things. An asset might be represented by a structured register of the installed components (component type, serial id,...) and their connections without any geometrical information.

Condition and configuration information from the physical object can be transferred through a direct link to sensors but might also be acquired through periodic inspections. In any case, they must be stored specific to the unique physical object. For complex systems, both asset representation and behavioural models can be very costly to produce. For that reason, they might be re-used for several physical copies of the same product type. E.g. several thrusters of the same type might share the same simulation model which is then adapted to the respective condition and configuration data.

Ships result from multi-tier collaborations between designers and manufacturers. With new, “outcome-based”, business models, shared responsibility for integrity and performance of components and systems during operation is emerging. It is anticipated that we will therefore also see multi-tier digital twins in the industry. This means that all three elements, condition data, asset representation, and behavioural models will be shared. Because of obvious interests for safeguarding intellectual property, all three will only be shared in an aggregated way, less detailed than known to the stakeholder in the lower tier. Therefore, access rights and change management will be important capabilities of a system implementing shared digital twins.

References

- BOSCHERT S.; ROSEN R. (2016), *Digital Twin – The Simulation Aspect*, Mechatronic Futures: Challenges and Solutions for Mechatronic Systems and their Designers, Springer, pp.59-74
- GLAESSGEN, E.; STARGEL, D. (2012), *The Digital Twin Paradigm for Future NASA and U.S. Air Force Vehicles*, 53rd Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials and Co-located Conf.
- GRIEVES, M.; VICKERS, J. (2017), *Digital Twin: Mitigating Unpredictable, Undesirable Emergent Behavior in Complex Systems*, Trans-Disciplinary Perspectives on System Complexity, Springer
- PARROTT, A.; WARSHAW, L. (2017), *Industry 4.0 and the digital twin*, Deloitte University Press
- ROSEN, R.; VON WICHERT, G.; LO, G.; BETTENHAUSEN, K. (2015), *About the Importance of Autonomy and Digital Twins for the Future of Manufacturing*, IFAC-PapersOnLine 48/3, pp.567-572, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2015.06.141>
- SCHLEICH, B.; ANWER, N.; MATHIEU, L.; WARTZACK, S. (2017), *Shaping the digital twin for design and production engineering*, CIRP Annals – Manufacturing Technology 66, pp.141-144
- SHAFTO, M.; CONROY, M.; DOYLE, R.; GLAESSGEN, E.; KEMP, C.; LEMOIGNE, J.; WANG, L. (2010), *Modelling, Simulation, Information Technology & Processing Roadmap, Technology Area 11*, NASA
- UHLEMANN, T.; LEHMANN, C.; STEINHILPER R. (2017), *The Digital Twin: Realizing the Cyber-Physical Production System for Industry 4.0*, Procedia CIRP 61, pp.335-340
- VINDØY, V. (2010), *A Functionally Oriented Vessel Data Model Used as Basis for Classification*, PDT Europe 2010, Reading, pp.60-69

An Open and Collaborative Object-Oriented Taxonomy for Simulation of Marine Operations

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Abstract

This paper introduces a taxonomy for marine simulations, based on entities, states and processes. The taxonomy supports the open source Vessel.js library, which contains empirical models for different vessel analyses following an object-oriented approach: seakeeping, resistance and propulsion system working condition. The proposed taxonomy is applied to a ship design case, having entities as the physical element (e.g. ship), states as the behaviour of the ship for a given condition in time and processes as the combination of various states over time. Two preliminary fuel consumption simulations applying the proposed taxonomy are presented in a design space with different ship and propulsion system options: first the vessel sailing through a route, second through the sea states of an operating region. Results are explored with visualizations and Pareto frontier plots for different design objectives. As the Vessel.js library is intended to become a focus for collaborative work, suggestions for its extension and improvement are also presented.

1. Taxonomy for Marine Simulations

The application of simulations to marine operations has lately been expanding and diversifying in the marine industry. This diversification leads to a great variety of methods and approaches to tackle different simulation problems through the value-chain. However, simulation packages are often application specific, not using common vessel models, input or output file formats. Furthermore, they are often built with proprietary software, which means that even if someone is willing to adapt the code to their own needs, it is not possible to do so.

Even simulation applications written for academic purposes are often not built for reusability or inter-connection with other frameworks, even if their source code is publicly available. They may rely on paid numeric packages (e.g. Matlab), and/or they only provide the source code as a printed appendix with no further documentation. If a user decides to simply run the code in their own machine, they may need to copy the content to source files, pay, download and install the correct version of the required package; and only then they will be able to run the scripts. It may be even more difficult to adapt the code to different use cases, or to extract some functionalities for usage in different projects.

Given these problems, this work introduces a simulation taxonomy intended to handle and connect different simulations of marine operations. It uses one physical definition of the vessel to perform simulations of behaviour in operation. An object-oriented, open-source library accompanies the taxonomy. The library is developed in JavaScript, allowing online deployment as web applications with graphical user interfaces, *Gaspar (2017)*.

The library starts with simulation models based on semi-empirical formulas and closed-form expressions. It is intended to be collaborative, so besides having its source code freely available, the library is maintained in an online repository with related documentation. This means that anyone who wants to contribute can discuss, modify or improve it. Over time, this approach should allow easier incorporation of more sophisticated analyses. A motion simulation, for example, could be gradually improved to include strip-theory or panel methods, then time-domain simulation of wave response. The object-oriented approach may also aid the reutilization of code, as the source is split into several objects with different purposes and capabilities.

2. Virtual Prototype Model for Marine Simulations

The basis of the taxonomy is the virtual prototype (VP) representation model proposed by *He et al. (2014)* and previously used in a ship design context by *Fonseca and Gaspar (2015)*. The VP representation model is subdivided into three sub models: an entity model (EM), a state model (SM) and a process model (PM), each one defined as follows:

- **EM**: the entity model defines the physical product or system which is being simulated. It includes design and specification data, 2D and 3D models of the product, and can represent a vessel or other simulated marine system, such as an oil rig or wind turbine, with any level of detailing. For example, general arrangement, structural definition, 3D models and component specifications can be included in the entity model.
- **SM**: the state model represents the system subjected to external static constraints in any kind of simulation. In a marine operation VP, the SM could be the resistance of a vessel at a certain speed, particular given load, and environmental conditions. The considered states are dependent on the behaviour the VP model aims to simulate, so for example, a hull strength simulation would require different states when compared to a seakeeping simulation.
- **PM**: the process model is a succession of different SMs to represent system behaviour over time, or, alternatively, it is the EM subjected to a dynamic constraint. A PM could be, for instance, the resistance model of a vessel sailing on a certain mission through different sea states, or the motion response model of a vessel while performing a heavy lifting operation.

Fig.1 illustrates the relationships between the three models with some examples of possible simulations in a marine operations context. The EM supports both other models, as it represents the simulated system. The SM is the EM under a static constraint, and the PM is the accumulation of several SMs. The PM can be decomposed into several SMs or obtained by applying dynamic constraints to the EM. In the design process, both the SM and PM are used as feedback to modify the EM, i.e., according to the results obtained from the static or dynamic models, the designer adjusts the product to improve its performance, for example, optimizing the hull form.

Fig.1: Virtual Prototyping Representation Model Applied to Ship Design as adapted by *Fonseca and Gaspar (2015)* from *He et al. (2014)*

Due to the complexity of a ship, it is natural that a breakdown is performed so as to better handle it as an entity model. In ship design, some traditional approaches to that breakdown are by functional purpose or physical division of systems, for example:

- The System Based ship design methodology, *Levander (2012)*, divides a ship into functional sub systems for estimating the required area and volumes during the initial design stage.
- The Design Building Block approach, *Andrews and Dicks (1997)*, divides a vessel initially into functional blocks containing geometric and technical attributes, which can be further detailed as the design process advances. The authors draw a comparison with the UCL Ship Weight breakdown, essentially a physical division of ship systems.
- The SFI Coding and Classification system (named after the Skipsteknisk Forskningsinstitut, Ship Research Institute), *Xantic (2001)*, defines a hierarchical ship division based on physical systems arrangement, even if the original definition of those systems is by functional purpose.

The idea of an open taxonomy requires that the EM is able to exhibit and aid handling of both physical and functional characterizations of ship systems. This flexibility yields higher potential for using the models in different contexts during the vessel's lifecycle, i.e., whether the focus is on evaluation of functional performance during conceptual design stage or physical detailing of simulated systems during construction and operation.

State models are snapshots of ship behaviour when subjected to internal or external stimuli, *Gaspar et al. (2012)*. Internal stimuli are simulation constraints which depend solely on states of the internal vessel sub systems. For example, assuming the hull definition of a vessel is known, one can derive its hydrostatic characteristics. Adding weight and spatial definition of internal systems to that model, it is possible to calculate static stability or still-water structural demand for different states of those internal stimuli. The spatial definition, given as a general arrangement or 3D model, could also support a simulation of evacuation time.

External stimuli are simulation constraints which depend on external or environmental states in general and interact with the vessel as a system. Examples of external stimuli are waves, winds, currents or geographic topology. Including these in the model makes it possible to perform simulations such as sailing resistance, propulsion working condition, wave loads and seakeeping.

Finally, process models simulate state changes through time, for example, changes of draft, speed, weather conditions or combinations of these. A simulation of a marine operation is assembled from a sequence of states that change over time. It can be used as a case study to evaluate a vessel's performance in a certain scenario, incorporating external stimuli and operational rules. A lifting simulation, for example, may have an operational rule for interrupting the operation in case the vessel reaches a certain operability threshold according to the current weather state.

3. Taxonomy with *Vessel.js*: An Object-Oriented Open Source Library

This section introduces *Vessel.js* as an object-oriented JavaScript library for the taxonomy. *Vessel.js* is an open source, collaborative project and can be accessed on <http://www.vesseljs.org/>. The repository includes the latest version of the code, documentation with API reference for users and some examples with tutorials presenting the library's main functionalities.

This work starts from the library version presented by *Gaspar (2018)*. Fig.2 gives a summary of the repository's structure at that time. Folder *classes* includes scripts to define a *Ship* object instance, which represents the entity model and calculates state models which depend solely on internal stimuli. Folder *fileIO* contains functions to browse, upload and download JSON specification files. Folder *math* contains mathematical operators used to perform calculations.

We expand on this version of *Vessel.js* to perform simulations of fuel consumption with semi-empirical formulas and closed-form expressions. The following sub-sections detail the VP sub models under this framework, including interaction with external inputs and rules, such as sea state definition and vessel operability criteria.

Fig.2: Vessel.js repository structure as of *Gaspar (2018)*. This work expands on the library to perform simulations following the taxonomy.

3.1. Entity Model: Ship, Propulsion System

Vessel.js defines a Ship object constructor to create an entity model. The vision for the Ship prototype is to support handling and evaluation of ship design data with different levels of detailing. The object-oriented approach is suitable for handling both physical and functional characterization of ships; for example, it is possible to have objects for ship sub systems and append SFI tags to them as properties.

A ‘Ship’ object is instantiated from a JSON input specification defining its physical characteristics. A ‘Ship’ instance includes sub-objects: attributes, baseObjects, derivedObjects, structure and designState, each one with its own set of sub-objects, methods and properties. The first four objects define the EM, while designState handles simulation states.

The ‘attributes’ object can be used to store general information about the vessel such as descriptions and specifications. The base objects define templates for vessel compartments, tanks and outfitting components. The definition includes spatial dimensions, links to 3D model files, and weight information. Derived objects are the vessel components themselves. They are defined from base objects and a single base object can be used as a template for multiple derived objects. A derived object also adds information in addition to its base object: 3D coordinates describing the component’s relative position to the vessel and identification tags according to the SFI group system. The structure object includes bulkheads, decks and hull definition, including its table of offsets. Currently, the most detailed specification available in the Vessel.js repository is a PSV composed of 106 derived objects, as shown in Fig.3. This is the specification used throughout this work.

Fig.3: Visualization of an entity model, a PSV composed of 106 derived objects, *Gaspar (2018)*

The entity model was expanded to provide the physical definition required for a fuel consumption simulation. The ‘Ship’ constructor received a property to specify one or more fuel tanks.

The main PSV specification collects some parameters which are not possible to obtain with the current state of Vessel.js library, i.e.:

- Hull description which is beyond what the library can derive from the table of offsets, for instance whether the hull has a bulb, transom stern or its afterbody form.
- List of hull appendices with respective wetted areas.
- Spare calculation parameters which can be taken as constant, such as natural roll period.

A propulsion system model was also created for the simulations. It is composed of two distinct, independent objects: one for the propellers and another for the power plants.

Propeller objects define physical propeller characteristics: number of propellers, number of blades, diameter and expanded area ratio. Efficiency data is linearized from K_t , K_q curves for the expected working regime (i.e., the high efficiency region of the curves). The linearization coefficients are included as properties of the propeller object.

Power plant objects can be assembled from an engine library. For fuel consumption simulations, properties of an engine specification should include MCR and coefficients for approximation of the SFOC curve as a 2nd or 3rd order polynomial.

A power plant object should have at least one main power providing system, as in this diesel electric example:

```
var powerPlant1 = {
  main: {
    etas: 0.95, // shaft efficiency
    etag: 0.95, // generator efficiency
    engines: [CAT_3516C, CAT_3516C, CAT_C32, CAT_C32]
  }
};
```

In this case, the diesel electrical system supplies power for both propulsion and auxiliary systems. Grouping multiple engines in the same array means they are able to share loads. The array order defines the starting order of engines as the demanded power load increases. Shaft efficiency (etas) and generator efficiency (etag) are taken as constant.

A power plant object may instead have one main power plant with two independent systems which do not share loads. For example, two diesel mechanical systems, each with one or more engines coupled to a propeller. In this case, the power plant should have an auxiliary diesel electrical system for powering other systems. In the following example, this auxiliary system includes two high-speed engines:

```
// create a diesel mechanical power plant
var powerPlant2 = {
  main: {
    noSys: 2,
    etas: 0.99,
    engines: [CAT_3516C]
  },
  auxiliary: {
    etas: 0.95,
    etag: 0.95,
    engines: [CAT_C32, CAT_C32]
  }
};
```

Regarding integration between vessel and propulsion system, we favour a modular approach where propeller, power plant and ship specifications are stored in separate libraries, so it is possible to couple and test different combinations during the conceptual design stage (more details are given in section 4.1.). However, this approach does not necessarily exclude a more integrated one. In the future, it would also be possible to define a default propulsion system inside the main ship specification and override it with a different one in case the user wants to test different configurations.

3.2. State Model

All calculated states in a state model are handled inside a ‘ShipState’ object. It originally contained analysis parameters, such as design speed and number of crew in sub-object calculationParameters and a cache with states of ship derived objects in objectCache. Derived object states are purely dependent on internal stimuli, they contain spatial positioning and tank filling ratios with flags for state version control. This work expands the state object to handle ship states which relate to the vessel as a whole system or depend also on external stimuli. These are now stored in a shipCache property, which lists vessel states for one given time instant with a corresponding version flag.

Following the taxonomy, Vessel.js should be able to handle states that depend on both internal and external stimuli. State models which depend purely on internal stimuli are calculated with methods embedded into a ‘Ship’ instance. In this sense, a ‘Ship’ instance already includes methods for the calculation of hull dimensions, hydrostatic and stability coefficients based on the current state of its derived objects. Furthermore, a ‘Hull’ instance includes methods for calculating hydrostatic coefficients as a function of the draft alone. The ‘Ship’ prototype only needed to be expanded with methods for fuel handling: one for calculating the available amount inside tanks and a second for subtracting the consumed amount.

SMs dependent on external stimuli are obtained using a library of specialized modules which couple to a ‘Ship’ instance and access it to perform calculations. A simulation of fuel consumption includes modules for wave motion response, resistance, propeller interaction and engine fuel consumption:

- **WaveMotion:** wave motion response and bending moment due to waves are calculated using closed-form expressions from *Jensen et al. (2003)*. They estimate vessel RAO response as functions of main dimensions, form coefficients and other parameters available in the early design stage.
- **HullResistance:** the calm water component of hull resistance is calculated based on the *Holtrop (1984)* method. Added wave resistance is calculated with a formula given by *Kreitner* for wave heights up to 2 m, as suggested by *ITTC (2005)*. For higher waves, a 20% wave margin is added to calm water resistance. This is an analogous solution to that proposed by *Bakke and Tenfjord (2017)*.
- **PropellerInteraction:** propeller working condition is modelled as discussed in 3.1.
- **FuelConsumption:** power system working condition is modelled as discussed in 3.1. The fuel consumption state module includes an algorithm for sharing loads among power sources coupled to the same system. The underlying principle is that an additional power source is activated when the previous one reaches 80% of its maximum capacity. This algorithm is heavily based on work by *Voldnes (2017)*.

A ‘Ship’ object instance received as argument by a state module constructor is linked to a property inside the constructed object, which allows modules’ methods to access and modify ship states in an encapsulated manner, as explained in Fig.4. States are modified with method writeResults. A specific array, defined as a property for each state module lists which results should be written to shipState. It can be edited according to the desired output. A memorisation pattern is used to store the results when they are calculated. After stored, they will only be recalculated if the input ship or wave states changed since the previous invoke.

Fig.4: Some of the hullResistance module properties. Method writeResults reads array results and updates the shipState inside the ‘ship’ property.

When calculating ship states during a simulation, it is necessary to reinforce a specific saving order to assure they are updated correctly, as illustrated by Fig.5. A propeller interaction module requires hull resistance and hull efficiency outputs to calculate the required shaft power, and a fuel consumption module requires the shaft power to calculate a corresponding fuel consumption rate.

Fig.5: Interdependence between state modules. State calculation and saving sequence should follow numbering to assure results are properly updated. Module *waveMotion* can be used independently.

3.3. Process Model

A process model is handled by a master script which assembles and iterates over state modules and external conditions to calculate ship states through time. The script may also evaluate and apply operability rules based on the calculated ship states. After the instantiation of the state modules, the script iterates over them to advance the simulation until a final condition, say, maximum time or sailing destination, is reached. A ‘Positioning’ object was created to aid calculation of sailed distance, however, it does not follow the template of other SMs, as its depends on duration of iteration time steps and the other modules do not.

Given the modular nature of the state calculations, it is possible to handle different parts of a simulation independently. The same wave motion module, for example, can be used to calculate maximum bending moment caused by incident waves, or to calculate the amplitude of vertical motion response and then use it to trigger an operability rule.

It is also possible to assemble state modules to update different parts of the simulation at different rates. For instance, one could be interested in calculating motion amplitude response every few seconds but would want to update sailing draft due to fuel consumption only every few hours. Some process models illustrating those use cases will be introduced in 4.2.

The final simulation results are a series of states, collected by time step or other label, depending on the simulation. It contains calculated ship states at the very least but can be expanded to include states of derived objects, such as fuel tanks, if relevant.

3.4. A Simple Simulation Example

This section exemplifies a simulation with a simple process model example where the ship travels through a path while updating fuel tank level and draft, as shown in the flowchart in Fig.6. The code was simplified for easier comprehension.

Fig.6: Flowchart of the fuel consumption simulation

A process model script starts with instantiation of a ship object:

```
var myShip = new Vessel.Ship(shipSpec);
```

The ‘Ship’ object handles the EM and performs SM analyses which are not dependant on external stimuli. It also stores current vessel states. State models which interact with external stimuli, in this case wave condition, are calculated with additional modules. In the example below, the modules are instantiated and the initial states are written to the vessel’s state cache following the update sequence in Fig.5 (resistance, propeller interaction and fuel consumption):

```
var hullRes = new HullResistance(myShip, wagProp, waveDef);
var propInt = new PropellerInteraction(myShip, wagProp);
var fuelCons = new FuelConsumption(myShip);
hullRes.writeResults();
propInt.writeResults();
fuelCons.writeResults();
```

The script will simulate the PM until the vessel reaches its destination. At every iteration, the script calculates the consumed fuel for the last time step, subtracts it from the fuel tanks, calculates a new draft and updates the ship state accordingly.

```
while (stateHistory[time].travelDist < pathDist) {
  consumedFuel = timeStep * shipState.consumptionRate;

  myShip.subtractFuelMass(consumedFuel);

  hullRes.setDraft();

  hullRes.writeResults();
  propInt.writeResults();
  fuelCons.writeResults();

  position.advanceShip(timeStep);

  Object.assign(stateHistory[time], shipState.state);
}
```

In the example above, states are saved to 'stateHistory' at each time step. It becomes a record of ship states through the process model, which can later be downloaded as the final simulation result.

4. Fuel Consumption Simulations with Vessel.js

The following subsections will demonstrate how different fuel consumption simulations can be performed over multiple designs with Vessel.js. Following the taxonomy, a design library of vessels and propulsion system objects will be created by reusing modified versions of the same physical system templates, or entity models. Two different process models will be assembled using the state modules presented in the previous section.

4.1. Design Library: Ship and Propulsion System

The ship library was planned to allow exploration of main dimension combinations during the conceptual design stage. It includes a visualization based on Three.js (<https://threejs.org/>) which receives a parent ship specification and allows the user to linearly scale it inside a given ratio range for length, beam and depth, as shown in Fig.7. When one dimension is modified, the others are automatically adjusted so as to keep displaced volume constant for a scaled draft. It is also possible to fix one dimension and vary another, for instance, fix length, vary beam, and let depth be automatically adjusted by the app to keep volumes constant.

Fig.7: Visualization of different PSV designs created by parametric transformation

The app derives ship object instances based on the design space explored through the visualization. It fixes the beam at a base value, loops through the length, steps over the beam, loops again through the length, and so on. Weights of hull, decks and bulkheads are scaled with their areas. Lightweights of tanks and compartments are assumed to remain constant. As capacities of tanks and compartments scale with volume, they also remain constant. Fixing the scaling ratio range from 0.9 to 1.1 of the parent specification main dimensions and using a scaling step of 0.01, a total of 441 ship instances are generated. Many of them were discarded due to being out of the validity range for the Holtrop method, but valid instances still summed up to 209 for the parent PSV specification used in this work.

The propulsion library contains propeller and power plant objects stored as JSON specifications. The propeller library comprises a selection of Wageningen B-series propellers with typical parameters for ship propulsion (3 to 5 blades, pitch ratio 1.2, expanded area ratio from 0.55 to 0.65).

The power plant library comprises two power plants. The first has two medium speed diesel mechanical systems each linked to one propeller, and two diesel electric systems for auxiliary power. The second power plant has the same four engines as the first one, but all linked as a diesel electric system which shares power loads from propulsion and auxiliary systems. This power plant library was partially adapted from work by *Voldnes (2017)*.

4.2. Process Models for Fuel Consumption

In this section we present two process models for different fuel consumption simulations, both relying on the taxonomy and state modules previously introduced. The first model, *path*, simulates the vessel's fuel consumption sailing through given route and wave conditions. The second model, *lifecycle*, simulates a yearlong trip through the sea states listed on an input annual scatter diagram. The *path* model can be used for calibration of the simulation based on previously known data for a given trip or, in the future, for practical estimations of fuel consumption. The *lifecycle* model can be used for evaluation of design suitability for a given operating region.

4.2.1. Path

The *path* simulation has different update rates for the verification of a new wave state (10 s), fuel tank levels (1 min) and sailing draft due to fuel consumption (1 hour) by default, which can be modified on the HTML interface. The script also contains a rule to slow down the vessel speed by 10% if a vertical acceleration threshold is exceeded, and then try to return to default sailing speed when the wave state changes. This is intended to simulate a voluntary speed reduction in case of excessive motions.

A method was added to change the wave definition back and forth between two different regular wave states at every hour. In the future, this method could be elaborated to incorporate stochastic representations of wave state.

The script starts with the instantiation of a 'Ship' object from a specification and assignment of departure fuel tank levels. Then, it instantiates state modules and calculates initial states akin to what was shown in 3.4. The script then iterates with a base time step of 1 s. It assigns results from the previous time step to the current one and proceeds to verify if it should update states related to time steps for fuel tank levels, draft, and wave state. If so, then it executes the necessary commands for the update and writes the results down to the state cache. By the end of an iteration loop, the operational rule for the vertical acceleration threshold is reinforced and the ship advances one time step in the sailing course. For each change in vessel or tank state, the results are also updated in the current time step of stateHistory. The simulation continues until the ship reaches its destination or runs out of fuel. Fig.8 presents a simplified flowchart of the model.

Fig.8: Simplified flowchart of the path process model. A complete flowchart can be consulted in the *Vessel.js* online repository.

4.2.2. Life Cycle

The *lifecycle* script simulates the ship traveling through all the wave states listed on the scatter diagram for a geographic region. It assumes an equal share of the yearlong trip time for each sea state occurrence on the diagram.

The algorithm is very similar to that presented previously, but instead of iterating until a destination is reached, it iterates through the sea states. Also, the model does not consider fuel tank level or sailing draft variations, as these are not specific to a given sea state.

For each sea state, the script creates a regular wave matching the given characteristics (peak period and significant wave height). A simulation then starts with the vessel sailing through that wave, if necessary reducing the speed until the acceleration threshold criterion is fulfilled. When the motion criterion is fulfilled, the algorithm uses the ship state to calculate travelled distance and consumed fuel for that sea state. Finally, it calculates total fuel consumption and average speed for a yearlong trip. Fig.9 presents a simplified flowchart of the model.

Fig.9: Simplified flowchart of life cycle process model

5. Results Exploration

The life cycle process model was simulated for the 209 ship specifications and 2 power plant specifications introduced, with 2 different propeller configuration options, totalling 836 designs. At this stage, we do not focus on quantitative values, as the model still needs to be validated before results are deemed reliable. The focus is on the utilisation of the same taxonomy to perform different types of simulations for different design proposals, and then on exploration of the performance trade space based on the results.

Two different result visualizations were built for this work using the open source JavaScript library D3.js, *Bostock et al. (2011)*: a parallel coordinates plot, Fig.10, and a scatter plot with Pareto frontier, Fig.11. These are used as example, but there are several other ways to visualize and explore ship design information, *Calleja et al. (2016)*.

Fig.10: Parallel coordinates plot for a life cycle simulation of 836 different designs, colours to differentiate power plants

The parallel coordinates plot has axes for ship main dimensions, fuel consumption, average traveling speed, propeller characteristics and power plant identification number. It has functionalities to support design space exploration, such as reordering of the axes to identify correlation among variables and filtering through selection to answer questions such as “what is the most efficient design among the fastest ones?” or “what is the most efficient design with diesel-electric main propulsion?”. The scatter plot shows fuel consumption and average attainable speed with a corresponding Pareto frontier.

The analyses yielded feasible results: long ships with narrow beams tended to achieve better fuel efficiencies than short ships with wide beams. Naturally, in a design context, stability requirements and roll motions would at some point become compromised when choosing designs with narrower beams. The exploration proposed here can be expanded to tackle those concerns using the Vessel.js library. For example, the metacentric height could be plotted on an additional axis in the parallel coordinates plot, or designs with a GM below a certain threshold could be discarded.

Fig.11: Scatter plot with Pareto frontier for fuel consumption and average ship speed. Dominated solutions appear with opaque filling.

The lifecycle and path apps can be accessed on the project’s repository. The online version of the path app reduces the number of simulated ship instances to some dozens to keep running time in accordance with what is generally expected from a web app. Nevertheless, the path app is still capable of simulating several hundreds of designs when running locally on the client side, but it may take a little longer.

6. Guidelines for Extending the Taxonomy and Library

This paper introduces the first step in the simulation of marine operations using the open source Vessel.js library. This is done with a taxonomic framework which divides the simulation in three interdependent models. The entity model is handled with objects for ship and propulsion system. State models which are dependent solely on internal stimuli are calculated with methods embedded into a ‘Ship’ object instance. State models which also depend on external stimuli are handled with a library of modules which perform calculations using the ‘Ship’ object. The process model is a script which calculates ship states, wave states and operational rules to perform a simulation.

The simulation models used here are quite simple, but they are created with features to foster collaborative development, such as standardisation, modularisation and, in the future, reference documentation. This means the models can be either modified, adapted for specific use cases, or improved by anyone who wishes to make public contributions.

The next applications should expand the taxonomy to deal with motions and other states which evolve through time. The simulations presented in this work relied mostly on sequences of stationary states. They did not model transitions between consecutive states; even wave motion response was calculated as amplitudes. An improved handling of motions and positioning will open the way to the simulation of manoeuvring and interaction between multiple entity models, for instance, a multibody simulation of two or more vessels keeping station next to each other.

In terms of accuracy, the fuel consumption simulation model should be validated with operational data before it is used for practical applications. One suggestion is to compare it to PSV operational data studied by *Voldnes (2017)*, which could also be used as a reference to expand the simulation to a complete operational profile, rather than simply fuel consumption in transit condition. This would include expansion of the entity model to better represent PSV propulsion, including dynamic positioning capabilities.

Furthermore, the current calculation of traveling speed in waves can be improved by coupling it to an attainable ship speed model such as the one proposed by *Kwon (2008)*.

In terms of computational capabilities, all the simulations presented in this work were performed with web browsers running on client-side. A natural step for the future will be to make the library compatible with a server-side framework, most probably Node.js (<https://nodejs.org/>). This will allow the simulations to access higher computational power and execute heavier models. A strip theory model, for example could be integrated to the library either as native JavaScript code or as an external open-source module, for example PDSTRIP, *Bertram et al. (2006)*.

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References

- ANDREWS, D.; DICKS, C. (1997), *The building block design methodology applied to advanced naval ship design*, Int. Marine Design Conference (IMDC), Newcastle
- BAKKE, M.Ø.; TENFJORD, P.S. (2017), *Simulation-Based Analysis of Vessel Performance During Sailing-Describing a simulation platform applied in early stage ship design*, Master’s Thesis, NTNU, Trondheim

- BERTRAM, V.; VELO, B.; SÖDING, H.; GRAF, K. (2006), *Development of a freely available strip method for seakeeping*, 5th Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Leiden, pp.356-368
- BOSTOCK, M.; OGIEVETSKY, V.; HEER, J. (2011), *D³: data-driven documents*, IEEE Trans. Visualization and Computer Graphics 17, pp.2301-2309
- CALLEYA, J.; PAWLING, R.; RYAN, C.; GASPAR, H.M (2016), *Using data driven documents (D3) to explore a whole ship model*, 11th System of Systems Engineering Conf. (SoSE), pp.1-6
- FONSECA, Í.A.; GASPAR, H.M. (2015), *An object-oriented approach for virtual prototyping in conceptual ship design*, 29th European Conference on Modelling and Simulation (ECMS) Conf., Varna, pp.171-177
- GASPAR, H.M.; RHODES, D.H.; ROSS, A.M.; ERIKSTAD, S.O. (2012), *Addressing complexity aspects in conceptual ship design: A systems engineering approach*, J. Ship Production and Design 28, pp.145-159
- GASPAR, H.M. (2017), *JavaScript Applied to Maritime Design and Engineering*, 16th Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Cardiff, pp.428-443
- GASPAR, H.M. (2018), *Vessel.js: an open and collaborative ship design object-oriented library*, Int. Marine Design Conf. (IMDC), Helsinki
- HE, B.; WANG, Y.; SONG, W.; TANG, W. (2015), *Design resource management for virtual prototyping in product collaborative design*, Proc. Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part B: J. Eng. Manufacture 229, pp.2284-2300
- HOLTROP, J. (1984), *A statistical re-analysis of resistance and propulsion data*, Int. Shipbuild. Prog. 31, pp.272-276
- ITTC (2005), *Full Scale Measurements, Speed and Power Trials, Analysis of Speed/Power Trial Data (7.5-04-01-01.2)*, ITTC - Recommended Procedures and Guidelines.
- JENSEN, J.J.; MANSOUR, A.E.; OLSEN, A.S. (2004), *Estimation of ship motions using closed-form expressions*, Ocean Eng. 31, pp.61-85
- KWON, Y.J. (2008), *Speed loss due to added resistance in wind and waves*, Nav. Arch. 3, pp.14-16
- LEVANDER, K. (2012), *System based ship design*, NTNU Marine Technology, Trondheim
- VOLDNES, B. (2017), *Simulation of marine hybrid machinery systems based on vessel operational data*, Master's Thesis, NTNU, Trondheim
- XANTIC (2001), *SFI Group System - A system for classification of technical and economic ship information - Product Description*, Xantic, Svendborg

Data-Driven Ship Design

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Abstract

This paper proposes data-driven methods thinking to the ship design practices, enabling effective data collection, quality, access, analysis and monitoring during the vessel lifecycle. Data is here understood as the key element to extract information and knowledge, and is represented in two complimentary categories, product (ship) and process (design). Ship data is studied via top-down and bottom-up approaches. The first comprises data from regressions, previous designs and parametric studies based on existing solutions, while the second is connected to specific key elements and subsystems that directly affects the mission of the ship. Data from the value-chain is studied under three distinct layers, namely overall standards (i), 3rd party choices (ii) and proprietary data (iii). Product lifecycle management tools advantages and drawbacks are discussed in light of the data challenges presented. Data-driven ship design aims to integrate product and process content according to modern DevOps practices, such as versioning, tracking, monitoring, testing, tuning and feedback. An open and collaborative ship design library is briefly introduced as an incipient initiative aiming to incorporate data-driven methods in ship design. Vessel.js is structured via JavaScript objects containing relevant information about the vessel systems and key components, as well as key performance analyses. A call for collaborative data-driven ship design using open standards closes the paper.

1. Data-Driven Methods for Ship Design

Data drivenness, in essence, is no stranger to maritime engineering and ship design. We are aware of the large amount of information required for a successful design, from properly requirements elucidation, *Andrews (2003)*, to feedback from captains and operators, *Brett et al. (2018)*. What makes then data-driven ship design worth to be studied is the gain when data can be converted to knowledge, and consequentially a more efficiency task-delivery and faster/accurate decision-making. In this context, data driven methods are connected to the build and development of tools, skills and processes that acts upon data. More important, to acknowledge the importance of such methods is to embrace a culture that properly handle data across the whole ship design value chain, *Anderson (2015)*.

Before digging on the implications that data-driven thinking can have in ship design, it is necessary to pay tribute to the large amount of new literature discussing the importance of data that appeared in the last decade. ‘Big data’, ‘business intelligence’, ‘cloud storage’, ‘web services’ are terms that engineers from my and older generations did not hear during their studies, but that now any bachelor student is able to comprehend. The boundaries between data science, computer science, statistics and software engineering are blur, but it is clear that the terms and development in these areas are nowadays extended to (probably) every corner of the scientific community, from health care, *Murdoch and Detsky (2013)*, to conceptual ship design, *Gaspar et al. (2014)*.

The data-driven methods discussed in the rest of this paper are strongly influenced by the data-driven organization studies from *Anderson (2015)*, data science for business from *Provost and Fawcet (2013)* and data driven documents from *Bostock et al. (2011)*. The authors compile in their works a concise and coherent set of tools and terms that I found useful when using ship design field as object of study. A common point among the studies is the idea that good decision making comes from good data, via the data, information, knowledge and wisdom hierarchy (DIKW), knowledge discovery and data mining (KDD) and data-driving decision making (DDD). These concepts are not necessarily new, but have been heavily revisited in light of the large amount of computational power that we have today to process the data and (hopefully) extract knowledge.

Anderson (2015) explores the DIKW idea to deeply focus on the data itself, defining the pre-requisites for an efficient data-driven implementation, here exemplified for the ship design domain:

- **Data Collection:** the gathering itself of all data related to the business among all its sources, such as previous designs, supplier's information, rules, 2D and 3D drawings, sea trial results and operational logs.
- **Data Quality:** connected to the reliability of data. It can be observed in many facets, such as accessibility, accuracy, coherence, completeness, consistency and relevance. Extracting non-relevant (dirty) from relevant data is a key challenge when talking about good quality data, as well as handling missing data. A good conceptual design is strongly connected to the quality of data used to develop it, from the regressions and empirical formulas used to define main lines and dimensions; to the proper elucidation of requirements when defining how the key subsystems of the ship are able to perform the mission when neither the ship or the mission are clearly defined.
- **Data Access:** as important as having the data is fetching it, especially to connect one entry with another, query among all available datasets and share information with others. It can be exemplified as accessing previous designs drawings or being able to include a new system in the supplier's database. More important, the idea that efficient access to data is paramount to a proper data-driven organization, and that data should be as easy as possible available by everyone included in the design process, bounded by legal constraints, proprietary assets and level of risk.
- **Data Analysis:** concerns the transformation of data in the required layer (information, knowledge, wisdom). A report from the design office, for instance, saying that 2500hours were used in the project is pure data. Analysis is to compare it with other similar projects and get the information that previous designs used 10% less hours. Knowledge is understanding the consequences of these additional number of hours, e.g. higher cost for the designer but a more efficient ship to be constructed, saving hours later in the construction phase. Wisdom is connected to using this knowledge in the future, for instance trying to achieve the same amount of yard efficiency in less conceptual hours for future designs.
- **Report/Alert:** connected to the metrics we take from data, exemplified in ship design by the number of hours spent in a conceptual project or at the yard during construction, and how this data must be constantly reported and checked to assure profitability.

Data science in the context of engineering and processing of data is discussed by *Provost and Fawcett (2013)*. They defend that efficient DDD is connected to the merge between intuition (literally gut feeling) and analysis of data. Most of their work consists in exemplifying how to process and visualize information from data in order to gather knowledge. Traditional methods, such as regressions and other fitting models are discussed, as well as more modern techniques, such as clustering and text mining. *Bostock et al. (2011)* is more practical in his approach, proposing an open data-driven library for handle and visualize data, Data-Driven Documents (D3), which has been extremely successful for visualize data in a web environment. *Gaspar et al. (2014)* discuss how using D3 may assist the designer to extract knowledge from the data already available when describing and evaluating a design and presents several examples of this rich visual representation for ship design, Fig.1.

Fig.1: Data-driven methods applied to visualize data during ship design via D3, *Gaspar et al. (2014)*

In the rest of the paper, I use data-driven concepts to investigate how data is understood and handled during ship design. Section two presents a main taxonomy for data, based on the product (ship) and process (design). Later, product lifecycle management as commercial solution for handling data is commented, with pros and cons. Data-driven design is thus presented as an update of the current methods to incorporate modern software development ideas, especially an efficient data feedback into

the lifecycle process, calling for a DevOps approach. Vessel.js is introduced as an open and collaborative library able to incorporate some of the data-driven elements discussed. The paper closes with a call for more open and collaborative data-methods in ship design.

2. Ship Design Data

2.1. Product and Process Data in Ship Design

Data from the product (ship) and process (design) seems to be a good start point when deciding which taxonomy should we use to converge all necessary information required for identifying a good ship. If data is strongly connected to metrics, we are therefore able to evaluate the effect of a data-driven approach by quantifying how better is a ship (e.g. higher performance than previous ship) and how better is a process (e.g. more efficient than the previous design). Note that both measurements of quality are not necessarily linked. A better ship can be obtained from a worse design process, while a more efficient process can create a ship with a lower performance than previous ships, Fig.2.

product worse			
process worse			
	same design process leading to the same ship = cost = performance	same design process leading to a better ship = cost + performance	same design process leading to a worse ship = cost - performance
	improved design process leading to the same ship - cost = performance	improved design process leading to a better ship - cost + performance	improved design process leading to a worse ship - cost - performance
	worse design process leading to the same ship + cost = performance	worse design process leading to a better ship + cost + performance	worse design process leading to a worse ship + cost - performance

Fig.2: Concept of product (ship) and process (design) data quality in ship design, with green areas as objectives when incorporating new data, while red areas present the negative consequences

Assuming that the insights from Fig.2 are connected to the reality of the ship design activity, it is possible to draw certain conclusions regarding product and process data. First, a given design process will deliver a certain ship. If no additional data is incorporated, the same process should lead the same ship as before (yellow zone). The concept of improvement (or the effect of learning, as commented by *Erichsen (1994)*) in both product and process is thus connected to improvement compared to a benchmark, usually previously designs and/or ship. A better process in this context is strongly connected to the additional data that lead to the improvement of the design activities. Therefore, we can measure a better design by either achieving the same ship in lower time or even a better ship in lower time (green zones). The red zone that should be avoided is a more efficient design process that leads to a lower performance ship – no designer is happy to justify lower costs if the price to pay is a product worse than the previous.

Similarly, a better product may be the consequence of improvements in the technology and equipment available, and the same design process can lead to a better ship if established design practices are able to incorporate the data from social and technological developments, such as a more efficient propulsion system or optimized hull lines.

The greenest zone at the centre of the matrix exemplifies the key objective of incorporating new data and methods to the ship design activity: improved design efficiency (less time) with a better final ship

(higher performance). The dangerous of ineffective data and mishandling the wrong information lies on the lower right corners, the reddest zone of the chart, with new data leading to a worse ship at higher cost.

The rest of this section investigates in more detail which type of data is expected to be better handled to achieve a better product (via bottom-up and top-down approaches) and process (via three layers of the upstream value chain) in ship design.

2.2. Bottom Up and Top Down approaches for Ship Data

Ship data can be represented in two complimentary categories, top-down and bottom-up, *Gaspar (2018)*. The first comprises data from formulas, regressions, previous designs and parametric studies based on existing solutions, such as the one commented in *Parsons (2011)*, most of *Watson and Gilfillan (1976)* and *Roh and Lee (2018)*. Such top-down approach to collect data usually finds a practical and consensual solution at short time and cost but lacks in innovation and carries on the bias and out of date insights from previous designs. Bottom-up data is connected to specific key elements and subsystems that directly affects the mission of the ship. Bottom-up data presents different taxonomies for vessel division and understanding, such as in methods like systems-based ship design, *Levander (2006)* and design building block, *Andrews and Pawling (2005)*. Bottom up data is the starting point for innovative and technological break-through designs, but suffers from the lack of knowledge connected to the uncertainty of one-of-a-kind projects.

A classic example of top-down are regression analysis and empirical formulas observed in most of ship design compendiums. A recent work from *Roh and Lee (2018)* adds another example of such compendiums, with formulas for the assessment of a computational ship design. Main dimensions are thus determined by traditional weight and volume equations, Fig.3a. Bottom-up approaches, such as the design building block, Fig.3b, usually starts from the key subsystem that affects the ship's mission, and main dimensions are obtained after the blocks are spatially placed.

Fig.3: (a) Top-down, *Roh and Lee (2011)*, (b) bottom-up approach, *Andrews and Pawling (2005)*, to define ship design data

Note that both approaches are not excluding, and good design practices do use bottom-up and top-down data when necessary, as exemplified in *Levander's (2006)* systems based design approach, combing volume calculation and regressions based on gross tonnage. The current challenge seems to be how to properly connect both ends of the ship data in a same standard, especially during conceptual design. While a well calibrated parametric model is able to fast delivery a feasible solution (Fast Track Tool), *Brett et al. (2018)*, the incorporation of new technologies and disruptive design changes seems to have the opposite effect.

The solution to this discrepancy seems to be yet in the hands of the experienced designer, with the empirical knowledge accumulated in the years of practice playing a larger role in decision-making than any stepwise top-down or bottom-up approach.

2.3. Design Process and Value-Chain Data Layers

The understanding of the physical elements of the ship passes through the merely idea, on the conceptual design phase, to the real and solid parts of the construction and delivery phases. Design and subsequent value chain processes should be able to incorporate this change in the essence of the product though the data type and, more important, keep a common data standard across all lifecycle processes.

Every design company has already some sort of data-driven methodology for handling value chain processes, even if not integrated. Ships are designed and analysed; Yards receive all the drawings and owners and users are able to operate and schedule maintenance of the real product. What differentiates the current system from what data-driven methods aim is strongly connected to the level of integration among the many data layers. Let us take for instance the lifecycle phase between the sales, design and the construction. The final product of the sale is a concept able to convince the owner that she should invest in that ship; the design products are the thousands of drawings required by the yard, while the final product of the yard is the ship itself. Current practice is that a department works on the concept, on an exclusive 3D model, while designers in other departments recreate the same model in several other standards (files, data-types) with much re-work until the final basic documentation. It is not rare for the shipyard to re-do many of the drawings to adjust the outfitting, due to conflicts in standards, data types (files, extensions) and sensitive design/yard information.

Fig.4 connects the traditional upstream processes from the ship design value chain, *Ulstein and Brett (2012)*, from concept to delivery, to a characterization of three data layers across all the phases: overall standards, third-party choices and proprietary data. Such understand of design data is heavily influenced by the author's experience in recent industrial projects, *Gaspar (2017abc)*, *Andrade et al. (2015)*.

Fig.4: Design data across the upstream value chain, with data observed in three layers: overall standards, third-party choices and proprietary data.

The principle behind the insight from Fig.4 states that, while upstream value chain is a common characterization of the lifecycle process, the ship data that is transformed during these processes must be understood in face of three distinct layers. The first is connected to the overall standards that all stakeholders of the design process are able to exchange among themselves. This includes tender packages with initial description of the vessel before gaining a contract, to the presentation of 2D and 3D drawings that are discussed with the clients, suppliers and yards. MS Office and PDF documents are standard in these cases, given that they can be accessed by all involved in the process. For Norwegian yards, SFI codes is yet a common way to link design and construction. While this choice may not be the most effective to the re-use of previous data, it is usually the neat 3D concept that gains the contract for a client, while higher performance is promised presenting data guesses on previous

successful designs. In theory the first layer of overall standards data should be understood and easily readable by all stakeholders during all design phases.

The large amount of options when dealing with more detailing tasks in the design and engineering processes affects tremendously how design data is handled, and it is proposed as starting point to be examined if the objective is a more efficient design process. Such third-party choices are the software, rules, suppliers and yard choices that the designer must consider and/or choose during the design process. The list of such options is too large to detail, and it is usually connected to previous successful choices from the past (e.g. use of AutoCad for 2D and 3D drawings) and promises from the new suppliers (e.g. use of a product lifecycle management suite for tackling product data handling, such as Siemens NX/Teamcenter or Aveva Suite). Such third-party data are usually very effective in presenting knowledge for a specific problem of the ship design task but are so different in definitions and standards that the mapping between one data type to another data type ends up as being a large part of the designer's work, specially via re-engineering and poor re-use of previous models. For the sake of exemplification, imagine a ship designed based on DNV-GL rules, with drawings in the standard for construction in Norwegian yards and European suppliers. The same ship constructed with ABS rules for Chinese yards with Asian suppliers would have a very similar overall presentation (1st Layer), while most of the detailing and equipment needed to be redrawn in the new third-party requirements. As noted, it is not rare that the yard redrawn info from de design office in its own standards just to comply with its standards, increasing not only the time and cost, but the risk of a serious deviation.

Proprietary data is connected to the know-how of the designer's office and yard. The challenge with these type of data is not necessarily its standards or overall type – it can be a calibrated Excel spreadsheet or a complex CFD optimization analysis – but how to protect it when needed and shared when required. Such type of data contains sensitive information from previous tender packages, designs, engineering analyses, suppliers and yard shortcuts and sea trial adjustments. It is not common that even between departments in the same company these type of data is not shared, with colleagues exchange among themselves just the minimum required to satisfy the project manager, usually in a non-numerical data format, such as power point, CAD file in PDF or docx.

3. Product Lifecycle Management Tools: Expectations and Reality

Commercial product lifecycle management (PLM) software are gaining more and more attention (and clients) in the ship design industry, with the promise of presenting a common standard to create, provide storage and sharing capabilities of the value-chain data across the ship design community. This trending goes in line with the development of such methods in other industries (e.g. automotive and aeronautic) and its features aim to tackle some of the ship design data issues discussed so far. Both advantages and limitations of PLM systems used as data-driven tools in ship design are briefly discussed in the rest of this section.

PLM can be defined as the activity of managing a company product all the way across their life-cycles in the most effective way, *Stark (2006)*, and it is one of the best-known methods to maintain a good organization of the product different parts, services, costs and suppliers through all the cycles involving a product life, from conception to scrapping. The PLM umbrella embraces many other concepts, such as modularization tools, product and systems architecture, libraries, product data management and enterprise content management, *Andrade et al. (2015)*.

PLM methods provide a way of dealing with huge amount of data in complex products life-cycle. This can be achieved through many techniques, such as efficient information indexing, database management, product decomposition and analysis and project management. PLM involves not only control over the design and engineering, but also some sort of control over all value chain steps observed in Fig.2. PLM can be divided into six fundamental elements, namely *CIMdata Inc. (2011)*:

1. Database, related to indexation tools and document management
2. Modelling and Simulation tools, composed by all the software used to design and virtual

- prototype the vessel
- 3. Value Chain Processes, related to the management of the lifecycle processes
- 4. Product Hierarchy management, handling the diverse classification ship functions, systems and components
- 5. Product Management, administrating all the information related to every physical component
- 6. Project Management, connecting the processes among the vessel life-cycle

PLM software promises an integrated design platform merging PLM and virtual prototype concepts, such as 3D libraries of components, CAE/CFD tools and re-use of previous designs. This platform benefits from the organizational concepts from PLM methodology, as well as virtual prototype techniques used to simulate main lifecycle process, from design visualization to construction.

A well-integrated PLM system is (theoretically) able to manage product data and process-related information as one system by use of software, providing accessibility for multiple teams across the company, such as CAD models, documents, standards, manufacturing instructions, requirements and bill of materials. However, even if the usage of PDM in maritime industry exposes great advantages, the implementation of the system evokes difficulties due to the necessity of well-established requirements, compatibility and expectations from the PLM/PDM system from the ship design company as well as the shipyard.

Keeping the re-use of 3D models as example of contrast between PLM expectations versus reality, it is possible to affirm that conventional assembly approach, which deals with connection features between pre-defined geometric entities defining the geometric positions, orientations, mating conditions, and parent-child relations is a common 3D strategy used in maritime engineering, *Levišauskaitė et al. (2017)*. It is also called traditional structuring approach where, despite of the CAD software employed in ship design processes, the connection features conserve its essential characteristics. This hierarchical assembly structure that consists of assemblies, components and features, which owns the set of entity attributes, is a distinctive feature of this approach, very similar to a traditional (but rigid) SFI classification system.

Modern PLM systems should be able to overcome such rigidity, incorporating multiple organizational breakdowns for the ship data, treating the design element as an independently managed component of collaborative design with unique and declared characteristics as access privileges, maturity status, position in ship, set of attributes, revision history, unit effectivity, and locking status. In other words, for controlling, accessing and managing the design data the components in the assembly do not need to be hierarchically ordered. Thus, it leaves an option for the ship designers to decide on the level of detail in assembly by making separate parts or subassemblies as design elements. This allows multiple taxonomies/views of an assembly, such as functional and physical, Fig.5, instead of pre-determined subassemblies of a product which add duplicates, *Siemens (2013)*.

Fig.5: Multiple taxonomy for organizational breakdowns, exemplified by functional and physical partitions of a vessel, *Siemens (2013)*

By reading literature favourable to the implementation of modern PLM systems in ship design one may have the impression that the data integration problem is solved, and today designers are able to efficiently handle with a high flexibility the multidisciplinary nature of the design process and efficient 3D re-modelling facilitation. But this is not what is observed in real ship design practices. CAD and PLM tools promises for over two decades that 3D models created at the beginning of the process could be re-used during the detailing process, especially with automatic and parametrized routines able to convert the 3D in 2D with a single click, as well as smartly reusing previous models to parametrize common changes and modular vessel configuration. This is not the reality observed by the author when working direct with ship design companies in industrial projects. Much of the precious engineering time is yet used to convert, fix and re-use old models rather than engineering a more efficient hull or propulsion system.

Criticism from personal field studies shows that the integration and flexibility promised by such systems is not yet delivered in everyday ship design activities, with productivity levels even lowering when fully 3D practices are implemented, touching the core pre-requisites issues for an efficient data-driven implementation methods commented in Section 1. Add to this the economic price of proprietary software, with a high integration cost for purchasing and training among the many engineering and yard departments and limited freedom to customize libraries and engineering procedures. Some of the criticism is also extended to the users of the tool, unable to adapt traditional techniques to the new standard – but who would blame them, if the old technique still gets the work done? Some of the criticism of implementing PLM tools in ship design is listed as follows:

- Additional work to add existing data in the new format/standard/library
- Lack of ship design terms, tools and methodologies incorporated in the available tools, with the designer adapting to a more mechanical engineering approach to traditional ship design analyses.
- Lack of seamless integration with third-party ship design tools
- Proprietary and closed software package, constraining customization
- High cost to acquire, install, train personal and keep servers running.
- Resistance to experienced engineers to use a new tool
- Risk of being locked to a system, and lose independency if features and licenses terms changes
- Ignore that individuals have different preferences on how they solve the problem, and that a certain methodology proposed by the PLM system is not the most effective among users
- Inability to incorporate commonly used ship design files (data types) in the database, as well as to open the large diversity of CAD files
- Forget that Word, Excel and PPT are key means to compile and share information, forcing internal reports

It is my impression that this (lack of) compatibility problem will not solve itself soon, as some PLM vendors advertise. No type of one size fits all software is yet able to properly cover efficient data-drivenness in ship design. On the other hand, PLM tools seems a necessary evil, presenting a great step towards efficient modelling and storage of CAD models, and a large library of model and designs running seamless across the whole engineering office is a reality – these models not necessarily talk the same language, but they are there, in a common place.

4. Data-Driven Ship Design

Compiling what was discussed so far, one can conclude that efficient data-driven ship design methods must connect the fundamentals of data-driven implementation (Section 1) with the many taxonomies for product and process data (Section 2), while keeping the expectations and solving the issues presented by modern PLM systems (Section 3). In other words, data-driven ship design aims to properly identify, understand and manipulate available ship value chain data towards a better process and product. As pointed, every design process has some sort of data-drivenness incorporated to it, given that new and better ships are being developed through the years. The challenge is to make use of these state of the

art techniques and increased computational power in order to keep the next design on the greenest area of the matrix, Fig.2, with more efficient processes giving higher performance ships.

Investigating literature from COMPIT along the years, for instance, we realize that the quality, number of choices and reliability of the tools used to handle the data are only better and better. It includes not PLM tools already mentioned, or the computational power per se available for designers, but the software and methods able to use it. A large number of commercial (and some free) tools are available, such as hull modelling, optimization tools, automatic rule check, CFD, powering and propulsion, flooding simulation and space allocation, to cite few. These standalone ship design tools, that most of the time can be obtained from a link in the internet and a credit card number, shows that we do have the parts that provide data, and consequentially knowledge, to solve a subset of specific ship design problems. The challenge them seems to have a common standard and/or culture able to collect, access, analyse, assure quality and, most important, connect this data among all the lifecycle phases without the need of being locked to a single proprietary and rigid system.

Some of the current challenges to incorporate a data-driven culture in ship design are summarized as follows:

- Gap between prototype (e.g. own optimization tool) and trustable/maintained tool (e.g. ship design suite)
- Integration of tools and methods with current modus operandi
- Integration among software, able to connect standard, third-party and proprietary data, Fig.2, varying from open .PDF files to advanced CFD analyses.
- Accessible to stakeholder among all value chain phases, while keeping the right level between availability and privacy
- Large investment to small number of potential buyers

The answer nowadays for tackling these challenges is simple: specialized engineering data is digested into: word reports, excel spreadsheets and power-point presentations, 2D drawings, with a small part of the information (and consequentially) knowledge being kept between the phases and gates of the process. The bottleneck relies on the large amount of available data formats and software versions that are not able to communicate among themselves, as well as bad software decision making in terms of openness and communication with competitors.

Integrated data-driven should re-uses and builds up on former designs, allowing the designer to really fetch former designs from a database, building up new concepts based on the new information, as well as re-using advanced 3D models for many value-chain phases (sales, concept, basic, construction). A data-driven ship design culture should act on keeping the collected and analysed data as accessible as possible during the design process, focusing not only on a standalone problem but on the holistic of the process, across the whole value-chain. This includes access to the analyses made during the design process, options and behaviour of the systems under the multiple operational scenarios studied, without the filter of a locked proprietary system. A data-driven design must integrate smartly the data used as input and gotten as output from the available ship design tools, as well as incorporating empirical knowledge from stakeholders.

Computer science seems to have understanding the lack of compatibility problem among data well, and the high pace development of internet tools just accelerated the need for common standards and practices, with a pressure to move faster without sacrificing reliability, *Kornilova (2018)*. This is the context where modern software development and operations (DevOps) culture emerged, with the lifecycle of a software project understood as a dynamic process evolving planning, coding, building, testing, release, deployment, operation and monitoring, Fig.6.

Fig.6: DevOps as culture in software development, *Kornilova (2018)*

I believe that an adaptation of DevOps software practices must be done to properly incorporate data-driven methods in ship design. Key technical practices that underpin a DevOps initiative, for instance, include getting teams to standardize on a common set of processes and tools for software delivery, *Kornilova (2018)*. Other relevant practices include:

- Data (and code/methods) available to developers and users
- Version control of files and infrastructure to enable collaboration and rollbacks
- Multi-hierarchical data, allowing plural data tags, such as functional/spatial/economic hierarchies, multiples level via *tags* or object properties (main machinery can be part of a propulsion system in one division (functional) and part of the hull in another division (physical)).
- Data format as open as possible, including numbers (e.g. simulations inputs, codes and results) and models (e.g. 2D and 3D models in open source formats, such as SVG or STL)
- Collaborative storage and editing capabilities, in line with modern software repositories, such as GitHub, with features such as versioning, track of changes, reviews, ownership levels, task assignments, automatic documentation, web interface, intelligent search algorithms.
- Tools to open and manipulate the available data must be accessible to all stakeholders, without the necessity of large installation packages or extensive server configuration
- Continuous integration of collected and generated data, across the lifecycle.

DevOps also makes use of the principle of flow, feedback and continual learning of the relevant data in the process, somehow inspired by Lean practices, using as main metrics the deployment lead time for a given design project, *Kim et al. (2016)*. Attention must be giving to the monitor phase of the process, Fig.6. To monitor is strongly connected to the metrics that we take from data (Section 1), and how these data must be used to improve the quality and analyses of existing products and procedures. A culture of constant monitoring during ship design would allow a systematic and reliable storage, accessibility and quality assessment of the three data layers commented in 2.3. In a simple logic, knowledge is what is produced in a design project, via the analysis of relevant information made by people (developer or user) into content (files). Content thus is the mean to flow knowledge / information across the stakeholders. Feedback is the information gained when the data is used (or misused), with knowledge gained on how to improve in the next iteration. DevOps practices thus aims to include everyone who has a stake in the flow of knowledge by involving them early on in the collaborative process of understanding that content is the key structural element of any design project, *Kornilova (2018)*.

DevOps practices relies heavily on starting with small pilots, scaling up as debug, testing and tuning activities takes place. While ship design is usually a one-of-a-kind project, the virtual prototype technology is fully available to incorporate the small pilot approach, and such culture of testing over and over different designs under different scenarios, scaling up to include one discipline after the other, must be fully incorporated in the ship design activity, especially because the gain of using 3D models

and virtual reality to test and tune analysis, from parametric hull form to seakeeping, *Chaves and Gaspar (2016)*.

5. Vessel.js: a library for Open and Collaborative Data-Driven Ship Design

Vessel.js is a JavaScript library for data-driven ship design combining conceptual ship design with a web-based object-oriented approach. It aims at the development of open and collaborative maritime engineering methods using DevOps practices. Rather than a one size fits all application, Vessel.js is considered a collection of open source examples of product and process that shares a common standard among themselves, while keeping flexibility to be customized according to the designer's need. Such development does not substitute advanced engineering and PLM tools already in practice, but rather presents a free and web-based virtual prototype platform to investigate common academy and industrial ship design tasks.

The starting point of such development is detailed in *Monteiro and Gaspar (2016)*, based on the observation of a continuous increase in the amount of information generated and handled by the design process during the vessels' life-cycle, as well as the challenge to store and exchanged the knowledge accumulated among stakeholders. Besides the standard for physical components and systems identification, it was also identified a need for a common platform for handling different types of analyses results involved in the vessel design process. Ship designers already have at their disposal advance techniques to evaluate the vessels' performance according to different merit figures, such as structural resistance, hydrodynamic forces, seakeeping capabilities and stability. A common open library having the free simulation code available, able to perform key analyses, handle the results and combine the data could definitely make a difference in the field. The conceptual design phase is yet the only real part of the value chain approach by the library, but the object-oriented approach is, in theory, able to include elements and properties from the other phases.

The library is freely influenced in its structure and development by D3, *Bostock et al. (2011)*, referring to a collection of compatible computational objects that work together to accomplish the required design task. These objects are the basic elements which the library sustains itself, building up on examples. Vessel.js represents the vessel as an JSON object, which is used to simulate different configurations, functionalities and behaviours. Currently, the library includes methods for hydrostatic and stability calculations, as well as parametric hull resistance and closed-form seakeeping equations, but it intends to grow to incorporate linear and non-linear hydrodynamics and structural models.

Vessel.js has the ambition to be an open and collaborative web-based library toolset for ship design data, able to handle relevant information about the vessel systems and key components, as well as relevant parametric data when this is within the useful range, with a special flexibility for managing different taxonomies and attributes. The data-driven framework seen here is yet in its early stages and relies heavily on community to grow but is currently able to incorporate both top-down and bottom-up approaches for the product data. The first is based on fast access of previous design data via a library of empirical formulas to create a new ship, while the second is able to incorporate innovative solutions having key subsystems modelled as JSON objects, based on a library of systems, and defining the hull and support systems around it. A more detailed paper on the capabilities of the library has been published in this conference, *Fonseca et al. (2018)*, introducing its design principles, basic functionalities, simulation examples and a call for collaborators. The library is free, open and currently maintained by the Ship Design and Operation Lab at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) (<http://vesseljs.org>).

Fig.7a presents a structure of the current state of the library, including the ship (Ship.js), hull (Hull.js, Structure.js) and behaviour of the ship under different simulations (ShipState.js). Fig.7b presents a 3D representation of a PSV developed in the methods available in the library, using 106 objects to describe the main systems of the ship. Examples of this model used for fuel consumption and propulsion system optimization are presented in *Fonseca et al. (2018)*.

Fig.7: (a) current structure of the Vessel.js library; (b) 3D representation of a PSV using the library

The library is in its early stages of development, and it is not at the current stage able to tackle all the data related challenges discussed in the paper. Efficient handling of ship design data also faces the multifaceted aspect of its objects, with different taxonomies and hierarchies for solving different problems in each of the ship value chain phases. Finding a common standard may be practically unfeasible, and compromises must be done even in an open and adaptable object-oriented data formats, such as JSON. The library has been developed using modern DevOps concepts, with all the available features from a modern repository as GitHub, and my belief is that continuous improvement in coding, testing, feedback and monitoring will be able to tune and calibrate the methods today incorporated to be as reliable as possible when compared to existing commercial practices. This, however, will be only possible if a group of developers and operators from the academia and industry decide that it worth to use and explore the library to create and share new ship design examples.

6. A Call for Open and Collaborative Data-Driven Ship Design

I close this paper with a call for my colleagues and students to consider implementing data-driven methods in everyday design tasks. Simple prerequisites for collecting, storing, accessing and monitoring the relevant ship design data, discussed in Section 1, seems a good start. Emphasis is given in avoiding a one-size-fits-all magic tool that promises to solve all data integration – the realization that one cannot avoid the three distinct data layers at this stage presented in Fig.2 is paramount: it does not matter how integrated are the ship design analyses and drawing the in the CAD tool – the classification society and yard will be sending and receiving knowledge from that data in a different standard, and this incompatibility of a single standard must be included in the process.

In the middle to long term such incompatibility problem can be diminished if open solutions are considered. Giving up proprietary data-files in exchange of a standard among all tools seems to be a feasible path. Take for instance the JSON format, selected to describe the ship design data in the Vessel.js library. JSON structures data by directly representing objects, arrays, numbers, strings, and Booleans. Its purpose is distinctly not document mark-up, different than XML (dominant format in the web until one decade ago). JSON is flexible and does not force a natural way to represent mixed content. For this reason, became the dominant format for web applications, and should grow more, given the rapid growing of Internet of Things concept, and all existing devices will benefit much more if the newly added devices speak the most popular language, *Strassner (2014)*. Trendy concepts like ‘big data’, ‘business intelligence’ or ‘internet of things’ may be substituted in a close future by the ‘next big thing’, but it seems that the main concepts here presented as one understanding of what data-driven design may be will keep resonating. As stated in the first paragraph of this paper, such methods are not strange to maritime design, and the industry proved to be robust enough to keep the traditional successful techniques while incorporating modern concepts, such as virtual prototype and virtual reality. DevOps practices, modern repository features and open standards seems to be the next natural step.

The Vessel.js proposal here discussed are a working in process, and much of the library structure and methods intends to be improved in the years to come. The main point defended in this paper is that technology is not a bottleneck for collaborative data-driven ship design, exemplified by the current fast-paced stage of online web-development, neither the speed of the computer processors and memory size, but rather how efficient ship design data is able to be transferred from books and experience to useful reusable models. While was a good surprise to find in 2018 a new ship design compendium available for purchase, with the instigating name of ‘Computational Ship Design’, *Roh and Lee (2018)*, one may expect that such effort in present formulas and methods could already be digitally available for re-use, with interactive (web-based) examples of the formulas and methods discussed.

As for the development of real ship design engineering in an open library, I recognize the value of current engineering tools and PLM suites; no doubt, they are responsive for the visible gain in productivity that the maritime industry faced in the last decade. But in a long term, I believe that no other framework will allow so much continuing collaboration and re-use of codes and libraries as open and collaborative web-based repositories. Even for more advanced applications, JavaScript libraries are a reliable option, with online compilers such as WebAssembly being an actual standard feature in modern browsers, allowing C and C++ compilation direct from the client, <http://webassembly.org/>.

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References

ANDERSON, C. (2015), *Creating a Data-Driven Organization*, O’Reilly

ANDRADE, S.; MONTEIRO, T.; GASPAR, H. (2015), *Product life-cycle management in ship design: from concept to decommission in a virtual environment*, European Conf. Modelling and Simulation (ECMS), Varna

ANDREWS, D.J. (2003) *Marine design - requirement elucidation rather than requirement engineering*. 8th Int. Maritime Design Conf. (IMDC), Athens

ANDREWS, D.; PAWLING, R. (2008), *Concept studies for a joint support ship*, J. Nav. Eng. 44/2

BOSTOCK, M.; OGIEVETSKY, V.; HEER, J. (2011), *D³: data-driven documents*, IEEE Trans. Visualization and Computer Graphics 17, pp.2301-2309

BRETT, P.O.; GASPAR, H.M.; EBRAHIMI, A.; GARCIA, J.J. (2018), *Disruptive market conditions require new direction for vessel design practices and tools application*, 13th Int. Marine Design Conf. (IMDC), Helsinki

CALLEYA, J.; PAWLING, R.; RYAN, C.; GASPAR, H.M. (2016), *Using data driven documents (D3) to explore a whole ship model*, 11th System of Systems Engineering Conf. (SoSE), Kongsberg

CHAVES, O.S.; GASPAR, H.M. (2016), *Web based real-time 3D simulator for ship design virtual prototype and motion prediction*, 15th Int. Conf. Computer and IT Appl. Maritime Ind., Lecce

CIMdata (2011), *Introduction to PLM*, CIMdata Inc.

- ERICHSEN, S. (1994) *The effect of learning when building ships*, J. Ship Production 10/3, pp.141-145
- FONSECA, Í.A.; GASPAR, H.M. (2015), *An object-oriented approach for virtual prototyping in conceptual ship design*, 29th European Conf. Modelling and Simulation (ECMS), Varna, pp.171-177
- GASPAR, H.M. (2017a), *EDIS Project Proposal to the Research Council of Norway (RCN)*, NTNU, Ålesund
- GASPAR, H.M. (2017b), *EMIS Project: Final Report to the Research Council of Norway (RCN)*, NTNU, Ålesund
- GASPAR, H.M. (2017c), *JavaScript applied to maritime design and engineering*, 16th Conf. Computer and IT Applications in the Maritime Industries (COMPIT), Cardiff, pp.428-443
- GASPAR, H.M. (2018), *Vessel.js: an open and collaborative ship design object-oriented library*, 13th Int. Marine Design Conf. (IMDC), Helsinki
- GASPAR, H.M.; BRETT, P.O.; EBRAHIM, A.; KEANE, A. (2014) *Data-driven documents (D3) applied to conceptual ship design knowledge*, 13th Int. Conf. Computer and IT Appl. Maritime Ind., Redworth
- KIM, G.; WILLIS, J.; DEBOIS, P.; HUMBLE, J. (2016), *DevOps Handbook*, Revolution Press
- KORNILOVA, I. (2017), *DevOps is a culture, not a role!*, <https://medium.com/@neonrocket/devops-is-a-culture-not-a-role-be1bed149b0>
- LEVANDER, K. (2006), *System based ship design*, NTNU Marine Technology, Trondheim
- LEVIŠAUSKAITĖ, G.; GASPAR, H.M.; ULSTEIN, B. (2017), *4GD framework in ship design*, 16th Int. Conf. Computer and IT Appl. Maritime Ind., Cardiff
- MONTEIRO, T.; GASPAR, H.M. (2016), *An open source approach for a conceptual ship design tools library*, 10th HIPER Conf., Cortona
- MURDOCH, T.B.; DETSKY, A. (2013), *The inevitable application of Big Data to health care*, JAMA 309(13), pp.1351-1352
- PARSONS, M.G. (2011), *Parametric Design*, Ship Design and Construction Vol. 1, SNAME
- PROVOST, F.; FAWCETT, T. (2013), *Data Science for Business*. O'Reilly
- ROH, M.; LEE, K.Y. (2018), *Computational Ship Design*. Springer
- SIEMENS PLM software (2015), *4th Generation Design / Providing the next-generation design paradigm for shipbuilders*, Siemens
- STARK, J. (2006), *Product Life-Cycle Management*, Springer
- STRASSNER, T. (2014), *XML vs JSON*, TUFTS University
- ULSTEIN, T.; BRETT, P.O. (2012), *Seeing what's next in design solutions: Developing the capability to build a disruptive commercial growth*, 11th Int. Marine Design Conf., Glasgow
- WATSON, D.G.M.; GILFILLAN, A.W. (1976), *Some ship design methods*, Trans. RINA 119, pp.279-324

On the Operator's Navigation Indicators – From Collecting Data to Operational Evaluation

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Abstract

The National Maritime Research Institute of Japan has conducted research and development on improvement of the ships' operation efficiencies so called "Eco-Shipping Project" of Japanese coastal vessels with energy saving optimum navigation plan. For evaluating operation performance of individual ships, the indicators EENI (Energy Efficiency of Navigational Indicator) and Kn (Energy Efficiency of Propulsion Indicator) were introduced from the viewpoint of operators. For deriving these indicators ships' monitoring data were used and the data were obtained from ordinary navigation equipment and main engine data logger without additional monitoring device. In this paper, the authors introduce methodology to evaluate effect of fouling, displacement etc. of vessels by using these collecting data. The authors apply the methodology to a cement tanker and confirm the applicability of the methodology.

1. Introduction

Shipping companies seek to promote higher efficiency of ship's operation and to evaluate effect of the operation. The national maritime research institute of Japan (NMRI) has developed an Eco-Shipping Project, Kano and Namie (2014a), for domestic coastal shipping to provide energy-saving navigation route and just-in-time speed plans in collaboration with shippers, shipping companies, NPO Marine Technologist (MTL) and others. As a result of this achievement, the navigation support service (eE-NaviPlan) has been put into practical use for 17 Japanese coastal cement tankers since April 2016, and saved fuel consumption exceeding 800 kl (~5% energy saving) of 2016 fiscal year. Just-in-time speed operation holds the prospective effect of major greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction. In addition, due to weather and oceanic forecast information, the schedule keeping and safety operation have improved.

Fig.1: Concept of "eE-NaviPlan services"

For efficient fleet management, it is required to check and verify ship operation status and propulsion performance timely, and to respond quickly if finding a problem. Hence, EENI' and Kn', *Kano et al. (2015b)*, were developed and introduced to evaluate ship's operation and propulsion performance for operators and especially for fleet manager.

EENI and Kn, *Kano et al. (2015a)*, were introduced to evaluate ship's operation and propulsion performance using energy efficiency of a voyage even if the case of both loaded and unloaded conditions in difference size and speed of ships. These indicators were derived from readily available monitoring data such as fuel consumption, displacement, and navigation distance, etc. eE-NaviPlan service adopted energy efficiency navigational indicator (EENI), energy efficiency propulsion indicator (Kn), etc. as indicators of ship operational performance and supports the efficient PDCA for fleet operational management conducted by ship operators.

One of the authors introduced outline of the navigation support system and compared the performance of the vessels with each other using these indicators on a displacement basis, *Kano et al. (2015b)*, *Kano (2018)*. In this paper, we focus on individual vessel, introduce methodologies to evaluate changes in ship performance over time by applying these indicators, and applied the methodology to a cement tanker and confirmed the effect of docking and applicability of the indicators.

2. Operator's Navigation Indicators

Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI), *IMO (2009,2011,2012)*, is adopted as an index of CO₂ emissions from ships by IMO. This index regards the product of the DWT corresponding to the summer full load water lines and the navigation distance as the work performed by the ship. This index based on weight of cargo is not able to evaluate at unloaded voyage.

Furthermore, it is interesting for the operator as well as loading efficiency, but interest in efficiency of unloaded voyage is also high. The EENI and Kn as indicators of navigational energy efficiency and propulsion efficiency were introduced for operators and especially for fleet manager.

2.1. EENI

Hence, EENI was proposed to evaluate energy efficiency of both loaded and unloaded conditions in different size and speed of ships. The indicator is based on the navigational work done by the ship on the product of displacement and sailing distance. This is obtained as follows, based on the ratio of the CO₂ emission converted from the fuel consumption FC and the navigational work. Therefore, EENI is the indicator for energy efficiency of navigation.

$$EENI = \frac{\sum FC_j \times CF_j}{W \times D} \quad (1)$$

By dividing the numerator and denominator by time, it can be transformed as follows.

$$= \frac{\sum SFC_j \times P_j \times CF_j}{W \times V} \quad (2)$$

j is fluid type; *FC_j* is fuel consumption for fuel *j*; *CF_j* is fuel mass to CO₂ mass conversion factor; *W* is displacement (tons); *D* is the sailing distance in nautical miles; *SFC_j* is specific fuel consumption (g/kWh); *P* is main engine brake power (kW).

By clarifying the physical meaning of EENI, it shows that it is proportional to the square of ship speed and inversely to the third root of displacement, *Kano et al. (2014b)*. Then EENI is expressed as follows.

$$EENI = \frac{\sum_j(SFC \times C_{TV} \times v^2)_j \times C_{Fj}}{\rho \times g \times \eta \times \sqrt[3]{1}} \quad (3)$$

C_{TV} is total resistance coefficient, ρ density of sea water and η propulsion efficiency. It may be seen as a volumetric Froude number.

$$Fn'^2 = \frac{v^2}{g \times \sqrt[3]{1}} \quad (4)$$

Since the indicator is a non-dimensional parameter and has a physical meaning, it is easy to understand the data and also possible to investigate voyage performance well.

$$EENI = \frac{\sum_j(SFC \times C_{TV} \times Fn'^2)_j \times C_{Fj}}{\rho \times \eta} \quad (5)$$

2.2. Kn

According to the Eq.(5), Kn was introduced to exclude ship speed effect as follows. Therefore, EENI is the indicator for energy efficiency of navigation.

$$Kn = \frac{EENI}{v^2} \quad (6)$$

Then Kn is expressed as follows.

$$Kn = \frac{\sum_j(SFC \times C_{TV})_j \times C_{Fj}}{\rho \times g \times \eta \times \sqrt[3]{1}} \quad (7)$$

As the fuel-based indicator is requested from the operator side rather than the CO₂ equivalent value, the eE-naviPlan service reports EENI' and Kn' on a fuel (liter-fuel) base to shipping companies, etc. and checks the navigation status for each voyage. This report helps to check the ship's state of operation and specific performance accurately, and also is effective in taking the consideration of energy saving navigation by operators and promoting fuel consumption saving activities.

3. Application of the Indicators

Kano (2018) compared the performance between vessels using indicators such as EENI' and Kn'. Fig.2 shows the one year from April of 2016 to March of 2017 average values of EENI 'and Kn' of Japanese middle/large-sized coastal cement tankers for loaded and unloaded conditions. It was thought that the characteristic curve of EEDI and Kn' quantitatively represents the operational and propulsion performance in the actual sea of the cement fleet in 2016 fiscal year. And it was shown that the navigation energy efficiency improves greatly by upsizing the ship. In addition, it can be seen that the effect of enlarging a smaller ship is great. Since the speed influence is excluded, the variation of the Kn' is relatively smaller than EENI. Characteristic curves of EENI' and Kn' were obtained in the same expression of EEDI's reference line of the cement tankers and these are expressed as follows.

$$EENI' = 2679.7 \times W^{-0.714} \quad (8)$$

$$Kn' = 37606.1 \times W^{-0.790} \quad (9)$$

The characteristic curves of EENI' and Kn' quantitatively represent the operational and propulsion performance in the actual sea of the cement fleet in 2016 fiscal year. These indicators are applicable to many ship types, because they are derived from readily available data such as fuel consumption, displacement, and sailing distance, etc.

Fig.2: EENI' and Kn' distributions and characteristic curve on displacement basis (Cement Tankers)

We have been supporting operators in grasping the ship conditions by showing the average value of the indicators for each voyage. Here, by analyzing these indicators in more detail, it is possible to evaluate the basic performance, such as changes in ship operation over time for each ship. It is expected that this will provide further information for ship operation.

3.1 Target vessel

To confirm applicability of the indicators, the case of a middle-sized cement tanker of coastal areas was considered, Table I.

Table I: Principal particulars of cement tanker for coastal shipping

LOA	120.00 m	Deadweight	7401 tdw
B	18.00 m	MCO	3809 kW
Draft T	9.20 m	Nominal speed	13.2 kn

3.2 Monitoring

Information on the operation of ships required to obtain these indicators is very general information as shown in Table II. This information is automatically monitored and collected sequentially from the existing navigation equipment every ten minutes by onboard PC, and transmitted and accumulated to the onshore server through the land-ship communication measures, Fig.3.

Table II: Monitoring Data Item and Data Source

Item	Measured Item		Data Source
Navigation Condition	Navigation Time	Time of Departure	Crew
		Time of Arrival Port	
	Navigation Route	Ship's Position/Course	GPS/AIS/Gyro
	Navigation Distance		
	Displacement	Draft	crew
Control variable	RPM Main Engine		Engine Data Logger
Fuel Oil Consumption	Fuel Oil Consumption per Hour		Engine Data Logger
Outer Force	Wind Direction/Velocity		Anemometer
	Wave Height/Direction/Period		Forecast Information
Speed	Speed through Land		GPS/AIS/Gyro
	Speed Through Water		Indicate Speed Device(LOG)

the figure on the right shows data at calm sea conditions. It is understood that the data at the calm sea conditions are very well organized. However, if looking in detail, there are some scattered data. This is thought to be due to the influence of uncertain external conditions. Especially, since we use forecast data for waves, we believe that the cause is also the influence of forecast error. In this figure, in addition to EENI and Kn' , the ratio of the RPM of the main engine to the ship's speed is indicated as α . The influence of external force appears in α , and when α is large (small), it turns out that resistance is small (large) and Kn' is small (large).

$$\alpha = \frac{V}{N} \tag{10}$$

V is ship speed through water; N is revolution of main engine rpm.

Fig.4: Time history of indicators of one voyage

Fig.5: Trend of the indicators values before and after docking

The averages on calm sea conditions for each voyage are shown in the Fig.5 based on counting date from docking in October 2016. EENI' varies. Kn' has an increasing trend with time and α decreasing trend. Each indicator is linearly extrapolating to estimate the value of the indicator at the docking date, and the differences are shown in Table III. Considering this as an effect of docking, α improved by 3.7% and Kn' is decreased by about 12.1%, Table IV. However, no significant improvement is observed for EENI. The fact that Kn' is small and EENI' is large means that ship performance is improved, and the crew seem to be enjoying speedy operation.

Table III: Estimate of the indicators values just before and after docking

	Day	α	EENI'*10	Kn'*10 ³
Before Docking	-235	0.0248	0.0495	0.0291
	-166	0.0239	0.0567	0.0319
	-112	0.0242	0.0520	0.0317
	-95	0.0239	0.0560	0.0325
	-87	0.0233	0.0563	0.0349
	-46	0.0239	0.0575	0.0325
	-0	0.0234	0.0547	0.0347
After Docking	+0	0.0242	0.0563	0.0305
	8	0.0242	0.0561	0.0313
	12	0.0241	0.0574	0.0308
	27	0.0243	0.0537	0.0295
	42	0.0241	0.0582	0.0311
	48	0.0239	0.0584	0.0320
	60	0.0241	0.0538	0.0316

Table 4 effect of docking

	Day	α	EENI'*10	Kn'*10 ³
Just Before Docking	-0	0.0234	0.0547	0.0347
Just After Docking	+0	0.0242	0.0563	0.0305
Improved Rate		3.7%	-3.0%	12.1%

4. Conclusions

For efficient fleet management, it is required to check and verify ship operation status and propulsion performance timely, and to respond quickly if finding a problem. Hence, EENI' and Kn' were developed and introduced to evaluate ship's operation and propulsion performance for operators and especially for fleet manager.

In this paper, we have focused on the individual vessels, introduce methodology to evaluate changes in ship performance over time by applying these indicators. Analysis was conducted using collecting data only on calm sea conditions.

A case study using a middle-sized cement tanker of coastal areas was conducted and confirmed applicability of the indicators. As a result, for the target ship, α (ship' speed per engine RPM) increased 3.7% and the Kn' (propulsion performance) improved 12% were evaluated by comparing the estimated α and Kn' values of before and after docking. On the other hand, EENI', which shows the energy efficiency of navigation, was deteriorated by about 3%. Crew of the ship seem to be enjoying speedy operation. This demonstrates the importance of fleet management.

We hope this research contributes to the reduction of global environmental impact and sustainable development for children.

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Reference

IMO (2009), *Guidelines for Voluntary Use of the Ship Energy Efficiency Operational Indicator (EEOI)*, MEPC 1/ Circ. 684, IMO, London

IMO (2011), *Amendments to the Annex of the Protocol of 1997 to Amend the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships, 1973, As Modified by the Protocol of 1978 Relating Thereto, Annex 19*, Resolution MEPC 203(62), IMO, London

IMO (2012), *Guidelines for the Development of A Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan (SEEMP), Annex 9*, Resolution MEPC 213(63), IMO, London

KANO, T. (2018), *On the effect of navigation support system - From collecting data to operational support*, 3rd HullPIC Conf., Redworth, pp.123-134

KANO, T.; NAMIE, S. (2014a), *A study on estimation of GHG emission for speed planning operation using energy efficiency index and time-series monitoring data*, 13th COMPIT Conf., Redworth, pp.167-180

KANO, T; NAMIE, S. (2014b), *A study on estimation methodology of GHG emission by using energy efficiency index and time series monitoring data*, Conf. Maritime-Port Technology (MTEC), pp.35-41

KANO, T.; NAMIE, S.; SHIMURA, Y. (2015a), *On the evaluation methodology applying ship-scheduling /voyage-planning system for CO₂ emission reductions*, Proc. Japan Society of Naval Architect and Ocean Engineers 21, pp.77-82

KANO, T.; SETA, T.; SATO, K. (2015b), *Eco-shipping project for Japanese coastal vessels - Verification project for CO₂ emission reduction with ship-scheduling/voyage-planning system*, 16th Int. Congress of the Int. Maritime Association of the Mediterranean (IMAM), pp.175-182

Design Rules Evaluation through Technologies of Treatment of Big Data

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Abstract

New technologies are appearing in the world that very shortly shall be linked with the design solutions in order to facilitate the same design by providing additional capabilities that were not yet available. These technologies are the consequence of the huge increase of computational capacity, actually called High Capacity Computing, which has derived in a number of capabilities such as much powerful treatment of Big Data and faster searching capabilities. This, shall allow solution providers to engage the design of a part or any concept with the applying rules. Another important step forward is that the integration of the validation of the structural models by the Classification Societies shall be done by using cloud computing or with direct connection with cloud applications. This will result in a faster and more reliable design. Monitored full-scale performance data should be analysed in the future in order to improve the performance conducted at the design and manufacturing stages. Performance evaluations should be made, employing developed monitoring and performance analysis methods, so full-scale performance can be evaluated with a high degree of confidence, and its results can be effectively utilized in the ship design stage. CAD simulation tools and Artificial Intelligence for user guidance, Big Data using Artificial Intelligence to help ship designer for optimizing the 3D model, so it is easy to predict that this is the future. There are many advantages of using CAD in shipbuilding: ease of design with the Design Rules embedded, speed of design, use and reuse of information, etc. It is expected that in the future CAD tools will evolve further and allow greater information management through these new improvements, for instance, using Artificial Intelligence, as described in this article. In general, CAD Systems provide tangible benefits while the process is optimized, reducing design cycle and production, and therefore costs. As a summary, there are several scenarios of improvements, as the Design Rules explained in this paper, for the next years. Some of these improvements may seem unrealistic in the short term, but reality often exceeds expectations in any field, and probably more in technology.

1. Introduction

Design Rules are a very broad, generalist and clearly ambiguous concept that can be applied in many fields. Within the same field of knowledge, different concepts can be called Design Rules. It could be also understood the Design Rules, such as the set of rules and impositions that must be followed to correctly design a product. According to this interpretation and within scope of shipbuilding, it could be referred to the rules in different ways.

If the origin of the rules are analysed, these could be imposed by the rules of the administrations, the rules of the classification societies or the constructive norms of the shipyard or the requirements of the final product that may be imposed or required by the final owner of the vessel.

But it could be also the design rules though as all the knowledge available in the design offices, by the designers and engineers that encompasses knowing how to make a boat or what is best for the design of the different parts of the ship. This also includes the adaptation of the designs to the peculiarities of the installation where the product has to be manufactured. Over time, the office and the shipyard, or its workers, have accumulated a lot of experience about the best way to do certain constructions or processes and that experience is materialized as Design Rules aimed at making a design, construction or process more optimal or efficient. This “best practices” area also related to the “on-the-field” experience acquired by the same workers. We’ll describe later on how these “knowledge” can be properly levered by using latest, not yet “new”, technologies currently available. These rules can also be under-

stood as the set of best practices or guidelines for design. In addition, the set of best practices is applicable to both to the design of the product, as well as to the methodology and means used for design and construction.

But apart from that set of Design Rules, there may be another set of rules that are intrinsic to the designs, and that allow to make an optimal design. These rules are based on the evaluation of the results made by naval designers and shipbuilders. Until now, the evaluation of the results was done in practice, by the naval architects themselves. The attempts to make an evaluation in a systematic way have been based on the standardization of the designs as proposed in the final report about ‘World Class Material Standards & Parametric Design Rules’, *NSRP (2004)*. However, it is conceivable that the emergence of new technologies of massive data processing, known as Big Data will allow it to be possible to evaluate many more design alternatives and more quickly and the question is how that can be made possible. In addition, for those Design Rules that are linked to the standards, it will be possible to evaluate their compliance during the design stage or after the design is completed. However, it is important not to forget that, as all the systems engineering manuals indicate, the evaluation of the Design Rules has greater value if it is done during the design stages than if it is done when the product is already under construction.

At this point it is possible to ask the following questions:

- How can Big Data technologies help to improve the evaluation of Design Rules?
- How can they help to improve the own rules and how can these technologies find out which rules of design must be applied, if they have been applied correctly, or if the rule itself has to be improved?
- How could be possible to extract new rules and guidelines based on the analysis of the designs made by the naval architects?

In this article, there is the intention to analyse what are the different technologies that can be compromised for it and determine if it is possible to incorporate them and how to do it when this is possible.

2. Knowledge Source

It is clear to mention there is a huge volume of information, some facts in the following Fig.1, available for a correct design and building of vessels and shipyards. It is important to expose that the context where all this information is, from one perspective, really complex given the number of regulations, guidelines and, at the end, “rules” that can apply when designing a vessel or a shipyard. However, seen from a different perspective, it becomes a huge opportunity to exploit all this information in a much more “intelligent manner”. The aim of this document is providing a better understanding of what it means by “intelligent manner”.

Fig.1: Some facts as regards data creation worldwide

There are a number of concepts that coexist and very often lead to certain level of confusion: data, Big Data, analytics, data analytics, predictive analytics, prescriptive analytics... all in all they're embedded into a wider concept of Cognitive.

Besides, it must be conscious of the fact that information is not yet limited by the list of "information" depicted in the previous paragraph. What it is declared in that piece is limited to what is called Structured Data. However, numerous studies point to the fact that this structured data cover only a 20% of the information available for us to use.

It is also a reality that there's a huge and continuous generation of information that does not reside in such structured sources of information: manuals, guidelines, reports ... contain huge volumes of information that is actually embedded in "pieces of information" that it is commonly called "documents". All those sources of information currently provide an enormous source of "data" that can be extracted for those encapsulating binders that it is known as "documents".

On the other hand, relatively recent evolution in Computing Capacity, formerly named High Capacity Computing, around 2011-2012 has brought key new capabilities that, jointly with pure data management, have carried us to a much powerful capacity to manage that information, as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2: Evolution in Computing Capacity

By bringing all together is where it is foreseen a huge growth for the information o coming up that can directly be applied to vessel and shipyard construction, this is what it could called Cognitive Naval Construction by using Cognitive Capabilities. Let's talk about how all these Cognitive Capabilities work together with a common purpose, as explained above, to improve the design and construction of offshore elements.

The above image compiles the set of elements within the concept of Cognitive Systems that can be simply applied to Cognitive Naval Systems, given, as described above, the complexity of information (data, rules, guidelines ...) that must be managed to improve the design and constructions of vessels and shipyards.

By looking at the image above it is revealed clearly see two branches of Cognitive Computing, lets study how they apply to Naval Knowledge.

2.1. Analytics

Vessel manufacturers and vessel operators have been storing high volumes of data for years. This volume of information will dramatically increase in the future by connecting every single component in the vessel or shipyard to a data lake where all this information can be analysed and exploited. This analysis can be done from different perspectives and also with differed purposes:

- Descriptive: technology has currently evolved so that it can very easily gather and store data by connecting to a cloud system in almost (increasingly closer) to real time. By collecting all this stored data either when constructing or operating the vessel, can already provide an immediate and (almost) real-time information of the vessel operation and behaviour so that I can use that information to identify early alerts based on this immediate information gathering. By providing all this analytical capabilities in place vessel operators can get a much higher understanding of the vessel behaviour much beyond human reaction capacity and besides, this can be immediately compared with historical information so that abnormal behaviour can also be identified and notified properly.
- Predictive: as seen before gathering and analysis of information of the operation and construction can provide immediate “happening” information, however, modern analytical capabilities allow us to define behavioural patterns based in historical data. By doing it, it’s likely to define statistical patterns that will not only define “regular” behaviour but also data trends on existing set of data. By using those data trends it is possible to predict what the outcoming data will be in a certain period of time with a define level of certainty. By working this way it could be simply predicted whether, based on the data that is being collected, the behaviour of a particular component in the vessel will most likely deviate from a “regular behaviour” thus alerting, and hence allowing to avoid, any undesired behaviour in vessel components and operations.
- Prescriptive: once it has been seen that it could be monitored both construction and operational data in real time and predict the behaviour of any particular component that is measured in the vessel, it may wonder whether it could be taken the most appropriate actions in advance upon a particular undesired behaviour of a component. The answer is obviously yes; by performing the appropriate data analysis it could be also suggested what the most suitable actions will be and also when these actions should be done to minimize impact of those actions to be done.

Fig.3: Cognitive Systems Components, Hurwitz *et al.* (2015)

By combining this three analytical capabilities it is feasible to find different areas for improvement like: predictive quality, predictive maintenance, prescriptive maintenance, and so on. Later on in this article it will be exposed the meeting of placing this prescriptive capability at the top of the angle of the diagram shown in Fig.3, thus highlighting the close connection with the Cognitive branch in that diagram.

2.2. Artificial Intelligence

Similarly to Analytics, a number of concept are included within the *Artificial Intelligence* (IA) and very often confused. However it goes, IA is bringing a dramatic change in the way the information could be managed, related to vessels and shipyards.

There are multiple sources of information in the naval industry that provide information that is not actually structured data that can be analysed in the way it has been described before in this article. Best practices and guidelines like ‘*Offshore concrete structures*’, *DNVGL (2018)*, where a huge list of guidelines and recommendations are described mostly in periphrastic way: “A document made by the Manufacturer of cement which contains the results of all the required tests and which certifies that the tests have been carried out by the Manufacturer on samples taken from the delivered cement themselves.”

Guidelines and recommendations apply to different stages and areas within the vessel construction (e.g. safety, design principles, calculation, testing, reinforcement ...).

First contact with AI would be in the text interpretation of content using Natural Language Processing (NLP) to that an AI system is able to understand the context describe in every piece of text so that it can distinguish whether a piece of text (a pill of information) is intended to deal with either safety, calculation and so for. This is what is called the “conversation intent”. Furthermore, AI capabilities of NLP will also facilitate de association of this intent with a number of entities that keep linked to a particular intent. All these intents and entities are identified, linked and stored for a further treatment that we’ll explain later in this article.

AI capabilities take us much further than pure text interpretation: AI provides text analysis, contextual analysis and semantic analysis. All these AI capabilities will allow vessel and shipyard designers to structure information in a way it could be exploited it in an intelligent manner thus leading to the concept of “Knowledge Representation”. Using AI algorithms vessel designers and operators would be able to read multiple volumes of information while structuring it in a way that can be later explored. It has nowadays become very usual in other industries the usage of these capabilities when solving problems, finding best options that suit a design, providing advice based on previous experience and providing suggestion for later actions so the error could be minimized that might optionally occur.

All these capabilities have led to a highly emerging demand of intelligent systems, using AI Algorithms, evolving to next level of Knowledge Management concept called Cognitive Knowledge Management. In this context of Naval Engineering we’re mostly focused on the automated and intelligent ingestion of huge volumes of information (unstructured data) than can be explored (as described before) and provided to engineers, manufacturers and operators with appropriate information at the right time in the place they need it.

Finally, AI capabilities evolve as time and interaction with users moves on; AI algorithms based on probabilistic algorithms behind the scenes will continuously update their probabilistic rules based on the interaction the feedback and continuous content provided by users and experts. This is understood as “machine learning” since intelligent systems, somehow apply the experience by increasing the confidence rate in their responses, reflecting the capability of learning.

This point leads to one of the key topics that need to be tackled when dealing with any AI solution, in this case for naval design and construction. This topic is related to the need of these systems to be trained so that algorithms that support understanding and reasoning can be adapted to knowledge demand. AI training and implementation methodology fits out of the scope of context of this document.

There is a reason for this model to place Prescriptive Analytics at the top of this pyramidal schema. By joining both pure data analytics capabilities together with IA exploring capabilities, both vessel constructors and operators will benefit for the union of both two worlds. This means either during the design process, construction or operation, engineers, technicians, constructors can have much easier access to multiple resources by joining together both data and experience, meaning knowledge leverage, thus leading to much more efficient and effective designs and processes.

As a complementary tool for better vessel design and construction is the use of Decision Rules. Vessel construction and operation is highly conducted by extensive sets of rules, some of them already tabulated and some others with multiple dependences to a number of variables and parameters. This is the

perfect context for the usage of Operational Decision Rules Systems. These kind of systems provide designers with “natural ways” of defining rules thus avoiding low level coding effort that can be easily modified and updated.

AI can also benefit from using Decision Management Rules Systems by interacting with them always that the AI system is trained to request the collaboration of Decision Management Rules when appropriate thus providing an additional level of intelligence.

All in all, currently, only leading solution designers and developers are already working together with technological companies to come together with much powerful solutions by combining deep shipyard design, construction and operation experience together with most leading technologies, including Advanced Analytics and Artificial Intelligence. However, it is expected that incorporation of these Knowledge Capabilities will progressively and increasingly incorporated to current existing solutions for shipyard and vessel construction in benefit of all the naval sector, in terms of quality, performance, safety and many more advantages to come.

3. Information Lifecycle Management Knowledge Lifecycle Management

The new Knowledge Capabilities described above lead us to real transformation approach for both designers and vessel constructors. So far, and given the extreme volume of rules, regulations, guidelines,... design and construction activities have been continuously ballasted by the need to “manage information” in a proper way; said in a different way, Information Lifecycle Management has been conducting the speed and efficiency of both design and construction.

By incorporating all these Analytical and Cognitive capabilities to both Design and Construction activities, this Information Lifecycle Management has actually evolved to a flow of Knowledge, either it comes from structured data or unstructured data, across both design and construction processes, not meaning anymore a ballast but, much rather an accelerator or catalyser of these corresponding processes helping them actually become much more effective and efficient.

As a consequence of this evolved approach, both designers and construction can focus their efforts of those activities where their personal skills and abilities revert in a much robust product, the vessel. In order to do that in an effective manner, both designers and constructors should clearly identify the activities where the usage of knowledge represent a key factor in their performance.

It is also important to highlight that this Knowledge Lifecycle Management is not only limited to initial stages in the design or construction. Much on the opposite way, Knowledge Lifecycle Management extends on a continuous bases along design and construction activities. Actions like sharing past experiences, providing design advice, notifying about potential alerts... Where not feasible in the past. By adding both Analytical, Decision Rules and AI capabilities together, Cognitive Solutions, to expert knowledge and expertise represent a clear change of paradigm between Information Lifecycle Management and Knowledge Lifecycle Management.

These new paradigm gest seriously impacted and improved by the incorporation of Natural Language Interaction between designers as this interaction can already been performed by using human language, with their different variability depending of geographical locations, languages, etc.

All this capabilities can even be enhanced by adding commentary capabilities based on vision management. Images can also be managed by IA systems so that patterns are recognized so that specific design components can be recognized, but not only recognized; structure components can be checked using in order to find deficiencies, problems, failures, etc. This can also be supported by latest technologies like drones and high quality cameras (including thermal, 3D, high resolution cameras) and Internet of Things (IoT). All these technologies and capabilities fit out of scope of the current document.

4. The Issue in Shipbuilding

Shipbuilding market conditions have suffered a significant evolution over recent years. Ship delivery times have become even shorter, and thus demanding a similar reduction in the design and engineering cycles. On the other side there has been an important reduction in the work force capacity of the shipyards, obliging them to subcontract significant parts of the design work to users with less skills.

The practice of Design Rules is gaining momentum in the shipbuilding industry as its numerous advantages become evident. Shipyards can increase their competitiveness by reducing design time, improving ship design quality and co-operating in the most efficient way with other companies, which need not be shipyards or engineering subcontractors, but also classification societies, equipment suppliers, regulatory bodies and even ship owners. Shipyards, large, medium or small, merchant or naval, want to have Computer Aided Design (CAD) applications with the capabilities of Rules Based Design.

The U.S. National Shipbuilding Research Program, *NSRP (2004)*, promoted and funded a project entitled World Class Material Standards and Parametric Design Rules. The main objective of the project was to develop and implement a Rule-Based methodology for ship design and material selection. The motivation of the project was to enable associated U.S. shipyards to respond quickly to customer inquiries and develop contract design packages, including cost estimates, which in addition to quick response have minimum risk to the yard in terms of price and schedule. As it was exactly described in the project web page, *NSRP (2004)*, the goal was a 33% reduction in cost and cycle time for pre-production processes during the contract, transition and detail design phases.

The Rule-Based methodology, Common Item Database, standards and parametric design tools are applicable to the U.S. shipbuilding industry at large. Among the several tasks covered by this project was the development of a technical approach for the early stage and a parametric ship design tool, which basically consisted of elaborating an integration between several different software devoted to the different aspects of the design.

Another task of the same project was to develop metrics and rules for the Entire-Ship design. As anyone can imagine the complexity was of such magnitude that it had to be focused on three generic ship types for a medium sized shipyard: container ship, product/crude tanker and Ro-Ro ship. The catalogue of captured rules had over 500 rules. This gives an idea of the difficulty of managing this into a single tool. Even more difficult when considering the possible changes in regulations. The task number six of that project was to develop zone Design Rules and material templates for each ship zone, to define generic interim products and to define functional volume design methodology and processes. The conclusion of the project made clear the need and the interest to continue advancing in the aspects related to facilitate the application of Design Rules to the projects. But the difficulty of the advance is so relevant that no clear advances have been made or applied in real cases.

Depending on the object in question the rules to be applied will have a different treatment. Since the application spectrum is so broad, it is necessary to make a detailed analysis and propose solutions to very specific sets of elements. When searching for one or several solutions, several criteria can be considered: strictly conform to the design criteria, comply with administrative rules, and reduce design time as much as possible. It is also necessary to keep in mind that some of the criteria may conflict with one another. In such a case, it is necessary to choose priorities carefully, bearing in mind that certain rules are binding.

In general, the criterion of reducing cost is a correct choice. However, it may be the case that time-saving estimates are not accurate. For example, incorporating tools to control the application of Design Rules will make the use of design tools, ultimately the CAD, more costly in terms of performance of the application, but on the other hand it will result in a design that hopefully does not need modifications. One could also allow the use of unrestricted design tools and incorporate validation tools for Design Rules later on. This would make depending on the training and knowledge of the rules that have the designers, the modifications of the design, were more or less ample. How could be estimated what is most beneficial? Certainly it is very difficult to make a prediction and the result will depend very closely on the type of vessel being projected.

Probably, the most suitable approach is to use an intermediate solution. First, to embed design methods that properly conduct the project by adjusting the use of specific materials or standard elements, equipment, fittings, etc. Second, to provide tools that help to know and to apply the Design Rules established by the different stakeholders. Finally to provide some method or tools to validate the rules in order to assure that the design conforms to them fits the rules.

4.1. Shipbuilding Design

It is completely out of the question whether to use software to make the design model. The complexity of marine designs makes it necessary to use different software applications for the realization of the designs, obtaining the relevant calculations and validating them. It is also evident that the greater integration between different software, the greater the time savings in project development, basically due to the use of the different models in the different applications.

Each stage of the design project will be subject to its own rules as the variety of the same requires to make a specific use of software applications to have the design adjusted to the requirements. This assortment of functionalities and therefore of rules makes it impossible to combine in a single source all the rules, *Muñoz et al. (2017)*. To make matters worse, the rules are constantly changing. This is due to the fact that the rules have different objectives and with each project it may be necessary to readjust them.

Hadjina et al. (2015) propose a methodology based on the Quality Function Deployment (QFD) to take into account during the designs of the naval projects, the experiences obtained with the same by the ship owners and crew. The authors take into account the percentage of remarks obtained after delivery the product to prioritize the set of subjective customer requirements into a set of system level requirements for a future system conceptual design. As a result, they establish a set of guidelines, among them highlights the improvement of the ship Design Rules and procedures and finally they suggest the necessity of elaborating a document of guidelines. In their work it is very remarkable that the 26.4% of remarks, second position after defects in assembly, are regarding noncompliance to the good shipbuilding and seamen practice in terms of working and living on board a ship. And in the fourth level with a 9.3% are the Remarks regarding the accessibility and obstruction during the movement of the crew through the ship. These two groups of remarks could have been reduced if during the design of model in the different applications it had been possible to validate or to consult the Design Rules.

So, currently the ship design process uses CAD as a tool and the application of the Design Rules relies in the designers and engineers. It is therefore necessary to incorporate new methods and tools to facilitate this application.

4.2. Design Stages

Focusing in the different stages of the project can give a good classification of the Design Rules and allow to identify which of the Design Rules deserves to be embed into the CAD or which is the best approach to address this issue, *Muñoz et al. (2017)*.

In the conceptual design, the Design Rules to be considered are related with naval architecture calculations. The evaluation of the stability criteria can be considered as Design Rules. These rules are established by international agreements and published by the International Maritime Organization (IMO). Having the evaluation of the criteria integrated in the CAD shall have a positive impact in terms of cost savings. Otherwise it will be necessary to export the forms into separate format and to make some rework in the specialized software. Most of the specialized software covers the majority of them, but sometimes it is necessary to add specific calculations made with parametric formula. Not all the software are enabled to address it.

Initial and basic design also requires the validation of the structural design from the point of view of the classification societies. For this purpose, models have to be exported into the specific format for the

structural calculation. There is an additional step that adds complexity to this process and it is that the classification societies normally want to review the models by their own means.

General arrangement in the basic design stage also requires the fulfilment of specific Design Rules, as those related with the compartmentation, spaces, volumes, etc. During detail design stage the project is expected to be finished from the point of view of the design. However, it is when more in depth observation of the rules has to be done.

Definition of the specific structural elements have to fit the classification rules, but also a high amount of equipment have to be located in the ship. The location is in many cases subject to determined rules, for dismounting, for functionality or even for aesthetic reasons. The amount of equipment means that following the Design Rules expends a large amount of time and hence, it is where the most of time savings can be obtained. So, it is in the detail stage when the validation is more necessary.

Some software vendors should provide tools and methodologies for controlling the project model from the point of view of the Design Rules and for facilitating the transfer of the model for validation purpose to external and specific applications. The different tools should be adapted in the different stages of the project and also for the different elements of the ship project and the ship design.

However, the number of rules can increase exponentially according to the type of the project, and in some cases, such as naval ships, the amount of rules is so high that it might be impossible to manage all of them, because the application could collapse during the definition of the different elements.

5. Data Treatment

As it was explained, a work methodology was intended to establish with the data that allows to improve the naval designs, the product, and its processes throughout the life cycle. This methodology is based on incorporating all the information, data, available to shipyards and technical offices to build efficient Design Rules and improve existing ones, facilitate the application and verification of existing ones and do it throughout the life cycle.

In the treatment of data, there is a substantial difference with the treatment of Big Data that is done in other areas. Currently, the greatest use and treatment of data is carried out in the fields of Financial Services, Outdoor Media, Retail, Tourism, Transport, etc., which are where there is a massive incorporation of data. In those cases, the objective is to know who, when, why and how is using data from the network all over the world. While in the matter that concerns us for this paper the objective is to get data to obtain a good design or a better process. In comparison with these fields, what is obtained from shipbuilding Design Rules and their application, is tiny, but it does not stop being necessary to carry out the correct treatment of them.

Although in the paper it is writing about using Big Data methodologies to be used in the treatment of Design Rules, as described above, it should not been forgotten that under the concept of Big Data, different technologies are included that make possible the effective and efficient use of the large volumes of data that need to be managed. For all of this it is necessary to take into account the following aspects:

- Variety of typology of Design Rules:
 - Design Rules, understood as normative
 - Design Rules understood as best practices, i.e. the adaptation of the rule to optimize the design and construction processes
 - Design Rules understood as design optimization to improve design efficiency
- Variety in the origin of the data
- Algorithms of data processing for its application in the process of design or production
- Variety in the fields of application of the Design Rules:
 - Design adjusted to requirements and standards

- Product efficiency
- Improvement of production processes

The first stage is the collection of the data. At least the following phases or stages can be considered and they are different depending on the type of data and its final destination:

- Compilation or capture
- Sanitization
- Integrity
- Governance

5.1. Capture and/or Compilation

The compilation of data is intimately related with the origin. In the naval field, the different offices and shipyards have their own working methods and their Design Rules. It can be said that this set forms a static database that must have an initial population. For processes to be effective, this must be centralized and have an efficient data structure. These data structures must be prepared to be applied in the design processes and therefore integrated in the CAD, this is what is known as embedded rules in the CAD, *Muñoz et al. (2017)*. For this the data must have an appropriated structure to the target. As an example, *Albers (2005)* propose the use of the knowledge-based engineering and the systematic storage of the Design Rules in an agnostic format independent of the CAD system, with six descriptors:

- A brief verbal description of the rule
- Eventually a picture
- A mathematical equation as a condition that refers to the part's geometry
- A unique key that identifies the rule and its scope
- Instructions what to do if the condition is true
- Instructions what to do if the condition is false

Description -----	Approval Domain ----
Clocks are to be fitted at a height of 1850mm above the steel deck to the centre of the clock.	Outfit
"Clear deck height - the minimum Clear Deck Height (CDH) is: 2200 mm for main passageway or compartments and spaces where personnel are sometimes required to wear a helmet 2100 mm for compartments and spaces where personnel are not usually required to wear a helmet 2100 mm for cabins and infrequently accessed compartments, e.g. storerooms, workshops"	Outfit
Where URN signature requirements do not impose pipe bends greater than 3 x diameter of pipe, a 3 x Dia pulled bend will be the preferred option. Where spatial constraints do not permit 3 x Dia and manufacturing capability exists an alternative 2 x Dia pulled bend may be used, but only with approval from responsible stage 1 systems owner.	Auxiliary Systems
This rule should be applied in conjunction with rule 472. Bends on pipes should be selected in the following order:- 1st choice - 3D bends with clamping 2nd choice - 3D bends without clamping 3rd choice - 2D bends with clamping (more cost effective than a LR elbow)	

Fig.4: Example of Owner's Design Rules

This proposal can be very suitable to control design variables and results. However, the structure of other types of Design Rules may have to be adapted to the type of rules, such as regulations or requirements. See for example the set of rules to be applied for the accommodation of a naval ship or the structural rules to apply for the physical limitations of the workshop, as shown in Fig.4. These are currently managed in separate and individual documents as worksheets in Excel® or similar.

As regards the rules and standards regulated by the administrations or classification societies. Although many of them are very similar, if not equal, each organism organizes them in a different way. Therefore,

there is no single data source or it is not structured in a logical way that allows computerized systems to processing them by any means. Furthermore, there is not any standard or unique structure of data that facilitates the treatment. So, the incorporation of all these rules in a single and centralized system of Big Data technologies is a great challenge for them.

In relation to the data of the design processes, it is referring here to processes and stages that a user executes during the design of the product. Repetitive processes, which could be detected and executed automatically and with automatic application of the limitations imposed by the rules. For this it is necessary to have a logical format that describes any of the processes and in a format that can be interpreted by a computer system. This type of language always needs an adequate interpreter. An example of this is the *Jason*[®] language. A design tool can record all what is done and then interpreted to do the same or to anticipate the user's action and propose specific actions or do them by themselves using an automated or on demand system, Fig.5.

```
|{"type": "HEADER", "value": {"build": "2018 beta", "host":  
"WS12857", "module": "fpipe", "revision": 280945, "timestamp":  
"2017-11-24T10:14:22+0100", "version": "v80R1.0", "x86_64":  
true, "customer": "SMAR"}}  
, {"type": "DLGMESSAGE", "value": {"timestamp":  
"2017-11-24T10:14:32+0100", "trace": "Forms file not found:  
\nC:/Foran/Ships/V810/TST8fsurf.fsf"}}  
, {"type": "COMMAND_START", "value": {"name":  
"OfsScnFileReaderCmd", "startTime": "2017-11-24T10:16:40+0100"}}
```

Fig.5: Jason script of CAD commands execution

Finally, there is the set of data that are the result of the evaluation of design variables and whose objective is the improvement of the design algorithms, i.e., the Design Rules to improve the efficiency of the project or improve the design itself. These data must be obtained from the product in its exploitation and operation stage. This engages with the Internet of Things (IoT) world and the capture and treatment of data to make decisions that improve the operation of the ships and beyond of this, the own design of future vessels.

5.2. Sanity

According to *Reguero (2017)*, “to obtain bright insights, we must feed the algorithms with data that meet minimum quality”. Data cleansing, data cleaning or data scrubbing is the process of detecting and correct, or eliminate, incorrect or corrupt records of a set of data, table or database; identify incomplete, incorrect parts, inaccurate or irrelevant and replace, modify or eliminate erroneous data. The process of data cleansing can be done interactively, with Data Wrangling, sometimes referred to as Data Munging, tools or in batch, through the execution of adequate scripts. Cleaning can be done manually or by software. Manually means using a tool that allows the classification and cleaning of the vast amount of data. Excel is an excellent tool for that. However, there are also a wide variety of tools specialized in data cleaning such as OpenRefine[®], Trifacta Wrangler[®] and DataCleaner[®], which are simple, fast and very efficient.

To better understand what data cleansing consists of, suffice it to say that the usual tasks are:

- Discard fields
- Match formats
- Correct spelling mistakes
- Format dates
- Remove duplicate columns
- Delete unusable records

5.3. Integrity

After cleaning, the data set must be consistent with others similar in the system. The inconsistencies

detected and eliminated are usually caused by human errors, corruption of data in the transmission and storage processes, or differences in definitions of data for similar entities in different databases. The data must be related each other and with the final objective, in order to be able to correctly infer the scope of application.

The integrity must be by specific applications oriented to the final target. Normally this is done by using specific programming languages that have powerful libraries for statistical algorithms and for processing large structured data files, as *R*[®] or *Python*[®]. It is definitely what is known as data discovery. Data discovery consists in the coordinated use of a series of techniques and methodologies to integrate and analyse different data sources. So that it is possible to discover relationships and behaviour patterns in the data sources and that are not perceptible through traditional analytical techniques.

5.4. Governance

Finally, the data must be stored so that they are accessible to the algorithms that will work with them. There are multitudes of databases and there are many criteria that can guide the choice of database. The most traditional and powerful, such as Oracle[®] or SQLServer[®], now appear a new generation of databases oriented to these technologies. They are the databases known as NoSQL, <http://nosql-database.org>. NoSQL, not only SQL, includes a set of database management systems that differ from the classic relational model, in aspects such as: not only use SQL as query language or that the data does not always have to be stored in tables, normally they do not support JOIN operations, nor completely guarantee Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation and Durability (ACID), and usually they scale well horizontally. Some of them are: Hadoop[®], MongoDB[®], IBM Informix[®], Cassandra[®], etc.

All these steps with being necessary, have to be adapted to the concept that it is intending to handle of application and improvement of heterogeneous, embedded and, if possible, automated Design Rules. In this process, it is essential to be clear about the design and construction process and at what stages of this process it is possible to take advantage of a possible treatment of Design Rules with Big Data methodology.

6. Leverage of Knowledge

How *Evans (2018)* explains in his web site, “Knowledge Management is the process of pulling together people, systems and tools so that an enterprise wide structure is in place for efficient and effective decision making”. It is ironic that so many companies have an abundance of knowledge but fail to use it for managing the business. Knowledge is a critical resource that warrants much more attention. If about managing knowledge it is being discussed, then it is necessary to embrace the concepts associated with knowledge management.

Knowledge management is not only an Information Technology (IT) project. Knowledge management is more about understanding the resource and knowing how to leverage it for growing the business. Technology (such as enterprise portals) is often deployed to help leverage knowledge. However, it may be more important to focus on the information itself, knowing how to classify it and analyse it before it is given everyone access to it. In case of the shipbuilding, this approach is essential. “Ultimately, intellectual assets have become more important than any other because only by means of knowledge can companies differentiate their work from their competitors,” *Stewart (2002)*.

In the same way that prototypes can be used to increase the leverage of knowledge, also design based on Design Rules will allow to grow the leverage of knowledge and with it the value chain of the company. At a time when generational changes coincide with disruptive technological changes, it is more than convenient to find ways to maintain the full legacy of knowledge that people have in the company and empower it with new technologies. It is not only about making a design well, but also about making a good design and the application of Design Rules, standards and norms, but also the knowledge and expertise of the companies contribute to that task.

Big Data technologies open opportunities for us to allow all that knowledge not to be lost, but rather to be

taken advantage of. In addition, technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning can give this increase in value that helps companies survive. The application of these technologies can be found in very different stages of the design process.

In the beginning of the design process, the results of previous designs can be used for preparing the new designs that improve the previous design. Of course, this can be done by direct application of knowledge, but if there were a single source to consult that knowledge, it would be easier and more efficient to do that task. It is increasingly common for companies to incorporate “lessons learnt” databases into their process, but in practice the introduction of this information is so tedious, that it is left to the end as the last step that nobody pays attention to what really deserves. It is about fulfilling an obligation and when someone intends to consult it, the information obtained is a repetition of data without any value. This could be resolved if there was an automated way to feed that information. For this reason, it is necessary to structure the data that could be required to recover or maintain for the future. Carrying out this work first passes through the selection of those variables whose results are data that assess value in the future for decision making.

Some proposals have been done as regards the previous, such the interesting investigation of *Sjöman et al. (2017)*, where they describe a theoretical framework for an evolutionary repository for capturing information and knowledge from real industry projects, and sharing this output for both researchers and practitioners in engineering design.

Once it has been defined what it is required to obtain, it is necessary to have the appropriate algorithms to correctly relate the collected data and their relationship with the design variables to determine the influence of one on the other. It is about not only presenting the information but also crossing as much as possible so that all the possible relationships between one and the other can be found. Having powerful algorithms allows to explore and analyse everything that human beings would take much longer.

This is where machine learning starts playing its role. The incorporation of learning algorithms and learning models through what is known as Support Vector Machine (SVM). SVMs are supervised learning models with associated learning algorithms that analyse data used for classification and regression analysis. Given a set of training examples, each marked as belonging to one or the other of two categories, an SVM training algorithm builds a model that assigns new examples to one category or the other, making it a non-probabilistic binary linear classifier, although methods such as *Platt (2000)* scaling exist to use SVM in a probabilistic classification setting. An SVM model is a representation of the examples as points in space, mapped so that the examples of the separate categories are divided by a clear gap that is as wide as possible. New examples are then mapped into that same space and predicted to belong to a category based on which side of the gap they fall, *Cortes and Vapnik (1995)*.

Finally, it is necessary to have the appropriate infrastructure to take advantage of all the information collected. In this sense, systems such as Hadoop® provide all the support that may be needed. Hadoop® is an infrastructure technology that allows the storage and processing of large volumes of data, through a storage system and distributed computing, which makes use of: a few servers up to thousands of them, and simple programming models. The Hadoop Ecosystem® is made up of a set of tools that have emerged to facilitate the management and analysis of Hadoop® data. In this way, it is possible to find tools to load and transform data, others for the query of stored data, cluster management, streaming and Machine Learning.

But the entire infrastructure requires that all the knowledge to which it is making continuous reference is implemented. In this sense, large companies such as IBM makes available to this objective, systems such as Watson IoT®, *IBM (2018)*, which deploys a broad set of solutions to give intelligence to all this data collection.

7. Conclusions

The Design Rules in any of the described form are part of the knowledge of the shipbuilding companies and it is appropriated to have them accessible in all the stages of the design and building process. The heterogeneity of rules due to their origin or application means that it is not possible to incorporate a

single treatment system, but rather to address what provides the most added value to the final product. To take advantage of the knowledge provided by data management and the value they have in the context of Design Rules in shipbuilding, some aspects must be addressed. Depending on the scope wanted to achieve when looking for a solution to the different aspects that are involved in this matter.

It would be necessary to decide on a single data structure and how, unfortunately, that will not happen will require an introduction of the data manually. The question here is whether it would be possible to develop a technology capable of interpreting all those rules and adapting them to an adequate data structure to facilitate the search and application. Does it make sense? Is someone willing to pay for that added value?

The current existing tools are oriented to the processing of the data in order to know commercial behaviour of the consumers or the use and behaviour of objects in order to elaborate maintenance or use processes. The case of the Design Rules is quite different due to several reasons:

- There is not a high volume of data
- This volume of data is not renewed with certain frequency
- The ultimate purpose of these data is much more complex than the previous one

Therefore, it is necessary to redefine the processes of data acquisition and processing and as a consequence, also the tools.

References

ALBERS, A.; BURKARDT, N.; MARZ J.; HAUSER, S. (2005), *Computer aided evaluation of design rules for micro parts*, Int. Conf. Engineering Design, Melbourne

CORTES, C.; VAPNIK, V.N. (1995), *Support Vector Networks*, Machine Learning 20(3), pp.273-297

DNVGL-ST-C502 (2018), *Offshore Concrete Structures*, DNV GL

EVANS, M.H. (2018), *Excellence in Financial Management (exinfm)*, <http://www.exinfm.com/index.html>

HADJINA, M.; MATULJA, T.; RUBESA, R. (2015), *Methodology for the ship exploitation feedback inclusion for improving the ship design and production process based on adjusted QFD method*, Scientific J. Maritime Research 29, pp.107-114

HURWITZ, J.; KAUFMAN, M.; BOWLES, A. (2015), *Cognitive Computing and Big Data Analytics*, John Wiley & Sons

IBM (2018), *Cognitive computing*, <https://www.ibm.com/developerworks/learn/cognitive/index.html>

MUÑOZ, J.; PEREZ, R.; SANTANA, S. (2017), *Naval ship design rules embodiment in a CAD tool*, ICCAS Conf., Singapore

NASA (2007), *Systems engineering handbook: NASA/SP-2007-6105 rev1*, Technical report, National Aeronautics and Space Administration

NSRP (2004), *World class material standards and parametric design rules*, <https://www.nsrp.org/project/world-class-material-standards-2000-214>

PLATT, J. (2000), *Probabilistic outputs for support vector machines and comparison to regularized likelihood methods*, Advances in Large Margin Classifiers, MIT Press

REGUERO, P. (2017), *Luca - Blog*, <http://data-speaks.luca-d3.com/2017/06/tus-datos-mas-limpios-casi-sin-frotar.html>

ROOZENBURG, N.J.M.; EEKELS, J. (1995), *Product Design: Fundamentals and Methods*, A Wiley Series in Product Development, John Wiley & Sons

SJÖMAN, H.; ERICHSEN, J.A.B.; WELO, T.; STEINERT, M. (2017), *Effortless capture of design output. A prerequisite for building a design repository with quantified design output*, Int. Conf. Engineering, Technology and Innovation (ICE/ITMC), Funchal

STEWART, T.A. (2002), *The Wealth of Knowledge: Intellectual Capital and the Twenty-First Century Organization*, Currency Doubleday

Design Space Exploration for on-board Energy Distribution Systems - A New Case Study

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Abstract

This paper demonstrates the usefulness of an automatic topology generator that uses genetic algorithm techniques to generate many alternative system designs and in doing so enables design space exploration for on-board energy distribution systems. This will provide better insight in the relation between design requirements (e.g. budget), system design solutions and important performance characteristics like ship survivability in early design stages. The basic idea is to apply proven techniques as used for ship configuration (i.e. hull and layout design) to the design of “ship service systems”. The case study will consist of multiple, interconnected systems on board an Ocean-going Patrol Vessel that distribute electric power, chilled water and mechanical (propulsion) power.

1. Introduction

Design space exploration using Genetic Algorithm (GA) techniques is a well-known approach to map design solution spaces, *Deb (2001)*. The purpose of design space exploration is providing insight in how requirements, constraints, technical design solutions and performance characteristics relate. This is achieved by automatically generating many alternative design solutions, order of magnitude is $10^3 - 10^5$ (or even above) and comparing these with respect to their scores on objective functions, see Fig.1. In case of opposing objective functions this leads to a set of Pareto-optimal design solutions. Exploring the design space and evaluating the (Pareto-optimal) design solutions helps illustrate the existing design freedom and provides insight into what is driving design requirements. This insight is vital to arrive at (ultimately) a single, balanced, well-founded design solution that can serve as input for later design stages in which the selected concept designs are worked out in more detail.

Fig. 1: Principle of design space exploration using GA techniques applied to system concept design

Design space exploration using GA techniques has also been applied in the context of early stage ship design, e.g. *van Oers (2011)*. Together with *Duchateau (2016)*, he enabled (semi-)automatic generation of multiple, and varying, ship concept designs or “ship configurations”. However, the way on-board energy distribution systems are incorporated in the generated ship configurations is deemed inadequate. Systems are in practice designed (with sufficient detail) in later ship design stages. This means the generated ship configurations lack concept designs of on-board energy distribution

systems, thus limiting the ability to use the exploration results to provide insights in performance characteristics driven by energy distribution system design, such as warship vulnerability. It also may lead to sub-optimal system performance, vulnerable systems or high re-design costs if a major revision of the ship configuration is needed in later design stages.

To address this important issue, an Automatic Topology Generation (ATG) tool for on-board energy distribution systems was developed. In the ATG tool network theoretic descriptions, i.e. the way in which “nodes” (system components) are connected by “edges” (connections between components) as specified in an “adjacency matrix”, of energy distribution system topologies are generated using GA techniques. As an example, a (very) simplistic system topology is shown at the right-hand side of Fig.1 to provide the reader with an idea of the generated design solutions. In this example, a diesel-generator set (DG) supplies electric power to a switchboard (SWB) which distributes the power to an electric motor (EM) that drives a propeller (Prop) through a gearbox (GB) and a chilled water plant (CWP) that provides chilled water to a heat exchanger (HE) through a main pipe line (Pipe). The system topologies generated by the ATG tool are larger and more difficult but can be principally understood with this simple example. The set-up and considerations of the ATG tool is extensively discussed in *de Vos et al. (2018)* but will be recapitulated in section 3 of this paper as well. The basic idea is that the design space exploration approach of *van Oers (2011)* to ship concept design can also be applied to on-board system design. This should lead to better insight into the driving system design requirements and enable a better integration of system concept designs into ship concept designs. This improved integration in turn enables better assessment of the availability of vital components and systems after a warship is hit, i.e. warship vulnerability; see *Duchateau et al. (2018)* and *Habben Jansen et al. (2018)*.

To elaborate, Fig.2 depicts the process of early stage ship design, in fact an extended version of earlier V-diagrams of the process. Distribution system design is integrated as a parallel process including the interaction with ship concept design.

Fig.2: V-diagram representing the ship and system early stage design process

Route A (A1-A2) represents the design space exploration approach to ship concept design by *van Oers (2011)* and *Duchateau (2016)*. Route B (B1-B2) represents the design space exploration approach to system concept design enabled by the ATG tool for on-board energy distribution systems as described above.

Furthermore, in order to integrate the generated topologies in ship designs not only the connections between components (e.g. pipes, cables) must be routed but also the main components physically placed in order to size ship machinery spaces (arrow D2). To address this issue a method was developed for first-principle dimension prediction of components of energy distribution systems, see

Stapersma et al. (2015). The method first sizes the core of machines / equipment using first principles and then applies (manufacturer) data-driven correlation factors to predict the dimensions of the overall machine. This method is regarded as inherently safe and fundamentally more correct than methods relying only on manufacturer data and leaving out preliminary design of the core of system components.

Although this “sizing of components” ultimately is necessary, this paper will demonstrate only the usefulness of the first methodology: automatic topology generation, as an early stage ship design decision support tool. The ATG tool will be used for exploring the design space for distribution systems by automatically generating large numbers of system concept designs, perhaps better known as “one-line diagrams” or “energy flow diagrams”, specifying the system components and connections between them. The case study will consist of a number of interconnected energy distribution systems: the electric power, chilled water and propulsion systems on board of an Ocean-going Patrol Vessel (OPV). The same OPV was used in *Duchateau (2018)* to demonstrate automatic routing of system connections through a ship concept design using similar GA techniques. He used it to visualize the trade-off between overall system connection length and warship vulnerability. In this paper, the trade-off between “system claim” (or impact) of the systems on the ship and “system robustness” will be visualized. These design objectives for systems are important aspects of total costs and ship survivability. This paper also discusses the definition of system robustness and compares two objective functions that try to capture this difficult concept in early stage ship design, which also helps in demonstrating the usefulness of the ATG tool.

2. Recapitulation Automatic Topology Generation tool

The ATG tool as a method to automatically generate many system topologies is introduced and elaborately explained in *de Vos (2018)* and is recapitulated in this section. The ATG tool uses a Genetic Algorithm (GA) to “populate” a design space with system topologies (representing system concept designs or design solutions) in turn enabling design space exploration. While generating topologies, the GA minimizes two opposing objective functions for which a number of available options will be discussed in this section as well. At the end of this section a hypothesis is formulated concerning the performance of two of the available objective functions. This hypothesis is tested in the subsequent sections in which system topologies are generated for the case study with the ATG tool to demonstrate its usefulness.

2.1. Approach and calculation procedure

The GA used in the ATG tool is a version of NSGA-II (Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II), *Deb et al. (2002)*. Depending on the settings of NSGA-II the number of system topologies generated by the ATG tool is between 10^3 and 10^5 (or even higher). The design space and a Pareto front of non-dominated system topologies are visualized by the ATG tool as main graphical output. See Fig.1 again for the principle of automatic design solution generation using GA techniques or the appendix for examples of system topologies generated by the ATG tool. A system designer can study the generated Pareto front and its topologies to gain insight into the driving design requirements and to select one or more promising system concept designs that need further development.

System topologies are generated by the ATG tool as NSGA-II varies network theoretic descriptions of energy distribution systems. Applying network theory to on-board energy distribution systems here means system components are modelled as “nodes” and system connections are modelled as “edges”. A system topology then is a network (or graph) captured mathematically in an “adjacency matrix”. NSGA-II varies the element values in the adjacency matrix using functions that mimic biological cross-over and mutation processes, thus generating different networks or “individuals” from a biological perspective. Each individual generated is a system topology for the interconnected on-board energy distribution systems under consideration. Fig.3 shows the general calculation procedure in the ATG tool – an elaborate explanation can be found there. Vector \mathbf{x} represent the generated system topologies, the repair function ensures that all system components are connected to the

network (in case NSGA-II generates networks with unconnected components) and the objective functions are used to evaluate the generated system topologies. Steering may be applied to help NSGA-II search and populate the relevant parts of the design space.

Fig.3: Calculation procedure ATG tool, *de Vos (2018)*

In contrast to conventional network theory a node in the ATG tool can have one of two functions, i.e. there are two types of nodes according to the node differentiation framework that was already introduced in *de Vos (2014)*. The role a node can have is either “converter” or “hub”. Converters are suppliers and / or users of a certain type of energy flow, like engines, generators, transformers, pumps, heat exchangers, etc. Hubs are (major) junctions in the network topology; they do not supply or use energy themselves, energy simply “passes through” (although in practice a small portion of the incoming energy may be lost in the hub as heat). Hubs gather all incoming energy from suppliers and distribute it to the different connected users. Examples are switchboards, distribution panels, gearboxes, main pipe lines and valve chests. Note that edges are differentiated as well in the ATG tool according to the specified, different types of, energy distribution systems. Types of edges that may exist are e.g. 440V, CW (Chilled Water), Mech (rotating mechanical power for propulsion), etc.

Differentiating between different nodes and edges has several advantages:

1. The generated system concept designs are more realistic in comparison to using general nodes and edges as one can relate to practical system components and connections found on board ships.
2. In practice components may have different roles in different distribution systems, e.g. a switchboard is a hub in an electric power distribution system but may require chilled water for cooling in order to operate. This makes the switchboard a user in the chilled water distribution system. The developed node and edge differentiation framework is able to deal with this dual (or multiple) functionality of system components.
3. The amount of possible system topologies (i.e. the size of the design space) is drastically reduced as “non-negotiable (or a-priori) constraints” concerning the inputs and outputs of system components follow from the differentiation. To clarify, consider an Electric Motor (EM) as an example. An EM requires electric power of a certain voltage as input and supplies mechanical power to e.g. a gearbox as output; it is meaningless to connect the electric motor to e.g. a main pipe line for Chilled Water (note that the latter is valid for the output of the EM, it may require CW as an input if it is a water-cooled motor). This example shows that constraints can be set up based on physical principles. These constraints are indeed of the “non-negotiable” type.

A major disadvantage of differentiating between types of nodes and edges, which adds (marine) engineering knowledge to network theory, is that many of the general network theory concepts and metrics lose applicability.

The generated system topologies are ranked by NSGA-II with respect to two opposing objective functions: system claim and system robustness. System claim aims to capture weight and space requirements of the distribution systems, their procurement and installation costs, and system operability. The first two are important aspects of the impact systems have on the overall ship design and total investment costs. The latter, system operability, is related to Human-Machine Interaction and asserts that systems with less components and connections are easier to understand and operate for human operators (which most probably applies to control systems as well). Two versions of the system claim objective function, differing in the way system claim is measured, have been developed and implemented in the ATG tool. These are discussed in section 2.2.

System robustness is the second, opposing design objective which will require more system components and connections. System robustness is an ambiguous term with many definitions. *De Vos (2018)* defined system robustness in the context of naval ship design as “The ability of energy distribution systems on board of (war)ships to withstand perturbations in system operation to a certain extent”. Seven different versions of the system robustness objective function, or its inverse: system vulnerability, have been developed and implemented in the ATG tool. They differ in the way system robustness is measured. These system robustness metrics (or indicators) are discussed in section 2.3. Two of the seven versions are for now considered best, i.e. they are more or less in line with the given definition of system robustness. These two system robustness objective functions are used and compared in later sections of this paper.

A further elaboration in section 2.2 and 2.3 of the system claim and system robustness objective functions is necessary as the fidelity of the generated system topologies highly depends on the quality of these functions. This is true in general for any optimisation algorithm, not only for genetic algorithms. Then again it is difficult, if not impossible, to have high-quality functions, i.e. accurate assessment, of system claim and robustness in (very) early design stages. Drastic simplifications of the design objectives are necessary to be useful in inherently low-detailed early stage design tools like the ATG tool. This is also the reason for having multiple options and metrics for the two opposing objective functions. In addition to a list of systems components and their functions (converter / hub), the ATG tool might require further input depending on the chosen objective functions. For example, the (approximate) location of the components in the ship or the vitality of components (i.e. does a component fulfil a vital function?). The different objective functions, their workings, and their required inputs are discussed further below.

2.2. System claim objective functions

As stated, system claim can be subdivided in to weight and space requirements of the distribution systems, their procurement and installation costs, and system operability. Combining all of these quantities in one objective function is not an easy task, especially not in early design stages. Still, one can try to do so when the aim is to enable design space exploration as then the accurateness of the functions to determine the objective is not as important as in later design stages; a qualitative design solution comparison is sufficient.

Two versions for the system claim objective function are defined in the current ATG tool. The first was introduced in *de Vos (2018)* and simply counts the number of connections and components in a generated system topology. The idea behind this metric is that system claim scales (and increases) with the number of connections and components. Since objective functions are minimised by NSGA-II, system topologies with fewer components and connections are preferred. Note that the number of components is in fact constant during a single run with the ATG tool and is added only for comparison between runs with the tool. Therefore, this first system claim objective function is briefly called “n_connections” in the remainder of this paper. Clearly n_connections represents a crude approximation of the reality of system claim but the trend of the function is assumed to be correct.

The second version for the system claim objective function is more detailed and requires an approximate or exact location of the system components inside the ship. This objective function calculates the combined length of all connections in a generated system topology and uses this length as a metric for which system is “better” from the system claim perspective: shorter overall length is preferred, i.e. topologies with few and short connections. The length of a connection, if it exists in a generated system topology, is calculated from the distance between the connected components. This distance may be calculated using different techniques: Eulerian distance, “city-block” routing distance, etc. The main difference with the length calculation of *Duchateau (2018)* is that no information on ship spaces is included in the ATG tool. This means that it is unknown whether the calculated distance can actually be applied as a routing as it might pass through tanks, blast proof bulkheads, etc. Hence, the calculated length of a connection is at this stage an approximation of the actual cable, pipe, duct or shaft length, but is again considered sufficient for comparing system topologies.

Additionally, approximate locations may also be formulated to match a rough sketch layout of the ship design. Here system components may be allocated to certain decks (above/below waterline), certain zones (fwd, midship, aft), or even PS, CL, SB. This method gives an intermediate accuracy between counting connections (version 1) and using connection length (version 2). However, using a length-based metric (as described above), whether based on a crude or more refined ship configuration, requires more detail and input than the first system claim objective function (n_connections), while it only better approximates the system installation costs part of system claim, but barely does so for procurement costs, weight and space requirements, and system operability. This is the reason the remainder of this paper will use the first system claim objective function.

2.3. System robustness objective functions

As system robustness is an ambiguous term it is even more difficult to find a suitable objective function for the second design objective than it is for the first. How should one measure system robustness? With weight and space requirements, as well as with costs, the unit in which to measure the quantity is at least known. A discussion on the applicability, accurateness or other model performance characteristic can be held when a model is available to determine these quantities, but the metric is known (e.g. kilograms, cubic meters or euros). This is not the case with system robustness.

It was argued in *de Vos (2018)* that an attempt to increase system robustness in early system design stages should focus on improving system reconfigurability by increasing the number of disjoint paths between hubs. The system robustness objective function presented in that paper does so by maximizing the flow in hub-hub sub-matrices of the generated adjacency matrix, i.e. system topologies with more connections between hubs are preferred. Moreover, not only are more connections between hubs preferred, max-flow-between-hubs even prefers ring distributions (if sufficient hub-hub connections are available to make rings) over other distribution patterns. In a practical setting, such hub-hub connections are bus-ties between switchboards, cross-connect gear transmissions, and undirected “communication” pipes between main pipe lines in a fluid distribution system, allowing reconfiguration of the system in case of system damage.

This “max-flow-between-hubs” objective function is based on the observation that in design practice system robustness of on-board energy distribution systems is increased by, *de Vos (2018)*:

1. “increasing redundancy by duplicating supplying components and supply lines to vital users,
2. introducing separate “islands” in the system topology that are able to operate as stand-alone systems in critical operations (islands should then also be physically separated; i.e. located in different zones in the ship separated by fire-resistant and watertight bulkheads),
3. increasing reconfigurability of the distribution systems by increasing the number of paths between suppliers and users. This is one of the reasons for interconnecting the aforementioned islands by so-called cross-overs”

The latter measure is the main reason for measuring system robustness by the potential flow between hubs in the max-flow-between-hubs objective function. A consequence of choosing this metric is that the other robustness measures are not part of the objective function and need to be introduced in the ATG tool in a different way. The number and type of system components are input (as discussed), so the measures of redundant components and (potential for) separate islands, i.e. sub-systems of suppliers, hubs and users, are captured in the input of the ATG tool. The main (topological) measure that is missed is increasing the number of direct supply lines to vital users. This is solved in the ATG tool by specifying the required number of supply lines of a certain type of energy for a (vital) component in the input for the tool. For example, if a vital user requires 440V the number of required 440V supply lines for that user may be specified as two. The vitality repair function then ensures that vital users have the required number of supply lines of a specific energy type as defined by the system designer in the input. The number of supply lines is, in other words, a “non-negotiable constraint” when max-flow-between-hubs is the applied system robustness objective function, like the connectedness of the system (also in repair function).

An alternative robustness objective function, developed by *van Leeuwen (2017)* and used by *Duchateau (2018)*, does not require the number of required supply lines as input to the ATG tool. This objective function is based on percolation theory; it employs a depth-first search of the remaining system topology after one or more random hits take out nodes or edges to determine whether “end users” are still connected to the required suppliers; i.e. whether a path exists (then percolation is possible) between vital end users and components generating the required energy. The method is fundamentally different from the max-flow-between-hubs in that it is not a deterministic a-priori objective function but the a-posteriori outcome of a Monte Carlo based vulnerability analysis on the topological level.

The method is called “vulnerability connectivity” by *van Leeuwen (2017)*, but mathematically connectivity implies the number of disjoint paths between nodes. Furthermore, vulnerability is again an ambiguous term. One could define vulnerability as the inverse of robustness, but that does not help much if robustness is not well defined. More importantly vulnerability may not be exactly the inverse of robustness, *de Vos (2018)*. Here the robustness objective function of *van Leeuwen (2017)* will be called “hurt-state-percolation”. This function does require end users to be defined that are considered to be vital and as such must remain operational even after damage impairment to enable the ship to perform its mission. Note that, with regards to the required input to the tool, the difference with the max-flow-between-hubs objective function is that one or more components are declared vital and not the potential consequence of this declaration: an increased number of supply lines. As a consequence, the ATG tool will determine itself which topological robustness measure is preferable: adding redundancy in supply lines (A) or increasing overall system reconfigurability by interconnecting hubs (C), when generating system topologies with hurt-state-percolation as applied robustness objective function and `n_connections` as system claim objective function.

The hurt-state-percolation objective function is more in line with the earlier specified definition of system robustness and the given practical robustness measures than the max-flow-between-hubs objective function. Furthermore, the function may fit better with the explorative nature of early-stage system design and the evolutionary nature of the genetic algorithm. Finally, the hurt-state-percolation function, being a topological vulnerability analysis, can also be employed to establish the validity of earlier design choices or simpler design tools like the max-flow-between-hubs function.

Regardless of one’s perception of the different robustness objective functions, it is interesting to note that it was observed in earlier research, e.g. *van Leeuwen (2017)*, that the ATG tool preferred system topologies with redundant supply lines to vital users when hurt-state-percolation and `n_connections` were the applied opposing objective functions. Increasing overall system reconfigurability with hub-hub connections was not used as a robustness measure. This begs the question whether the max-flow-between-hubs robustness objective function “misses the point” with its focus on hub-hub connections. But the number of specified end users has in earlier research always been one, which is believed to be the reason that hurt-state-percolation (in combination with `n_connections`) prefers redundancy in supply lines over hub-hub connections. It is hypothesized here that the two robustness objective functions converge; i.e. show similar system topologies on the Pareto front, when the number of vital end users is increased. To test this hypothesis both the max-flow-between-hubs and the hurt-state-percolation robustness objective functions are used and compared in this paper for the case study.

Several other robustness objective functions have been implemented, but will not be discussed here as they are considered less applicable, performing poorly either in the fidelity of the generated system topologies or in the required input and calculation time.

3. Case study

With the ATG tool recapitulated and the different available objective functions discussed the case study will be introduced and discussed in this section. In the next section system topologies will be automatically generated for the case study, which will help test the hypothesis concerning the system objective functions formulated in the previous section. Note that the system topologies that are shown in this section are handmade and not generated by the ATG tool.

3.1. Ocean-going Patrol Vessel

An Ocean-going Patrol Vessel is a relatively small warship, typically designed for hostile environments that are considered to be “low in the violence spectrum”. As such they are typically well equipped for anti-drugs and anti-piracy missions and/or (sea) border control, but unfit for enemy engagement in an actual war. Still, the lifetime of these vessels is such that one cannot assume that these ships will never see an actual war environment. As a result, a fictional scenario in which the ship and its systems are extensively re-designed and engineered for a more violent environment can be thought of. This fictional scenario is the background of the present paper and case study.

Duchateau (2018) presented the OPV lay-out and a single network topology for a small number of its “distributed ship service systems”. This single network topology is subsequently automatically routed many times over through spaces inside the ship’s envelope using a k-shortest path algorithm. While doing so constraints coming from e.g. the type of space and / or bulkhead location are taken into account. For each routing the hurt-state-percolation objective function is used to determine the vulnerability of that routing to one or more random hits. Repeating the process of routing and vulnerability assessment is achieved by integrating the algorithms with NSGA-II “in an attempt to find a Pareto-set of solutions minimising both overall routing configuration length and the distributed system vulnerability”. The paper as such demonstrates the possibility to better incorporate early stage system design in early stage ship design. However, automatic routing was done for a single system concept design (one network topology) in a single ship concept design (one lay-out of spaces). This may lead to sub-optimal solutions as a good routing will hardly mitigate the flaws of sub-optimal system or ship concept designs. Ultimately an integrated approach in which different system concept designs (from the ATG tool) are routed in different ways (from the routing tool) through different ship concept designs (from the packing tool) is envisaged.

3.2. 23-node case study system on board of OPV

Fig.4 shows the handmade 23-node case study system topology of *Duchateau (2018)*. Table I was reprinted from his paper and lists the system components (nodes) and their role, i.e. supplier, hub or user (where suppliers and users are converters), in the different considered (energy) distribution systems (edge types). The number of possible connections for the 23-node case study system is 71: 8 DG-SWB connections + 1 SWB-SWB connection (bidirectional) + 4 SWB-TR connections + ... and so on. The vast majority of these potential connections are supplier-to-hub (s-h) or hub-to-user (h-u) connections. In fact, there are only three (bi-directional) hub-to-hub (h-h) connections possible; one between the two switchboards, one between the two CW hubs and one between the two Computer rooms. *Duchateau (2018)* choose the 76mm Gun as the only vital end user reflecting a scenario where fighting power is considered the only vital function.

Fig.4: Graph of 23-node case study system

Table I: List of OPV system components and associated distribution systems.

System component	Distribution system in which system component is		
	user	hub	supplier
4 x Diesel-Generator set (DG1-4)	-	-	440V
2 x Main Switchboard (SWB aft & fwd)	-	440V	-
2 x Transformer (TR PS & SB)	440V	-	690V
2 x Electric Motor (EM PS & SB)	690V		
3 x Load Centre (LC1-3; aft, mid & fwd)	-	440V	-
2 x Chilled Water Plant (CWP aft & fwd)	440V	-	CW
2 x Chilled Water Main Pipe line (CW HUB aft & fwd)	-	CW	-
Sensor Mast (incl. radar)	440V; CW	-	S_data
2 x Server Room (Comp aft & fwd)	440V; CW	S_data	-
Command Centre (CIC)	440V; CW; S_data	-	W_data
2 x Gun (30mm & 76mm)	440V; CW; W_data	-	-

3.3. Necessity for scaling up the 23-node case study system to a 35-node case study system

In order to test the hypothesis of section 2.3 the 23-node case study system needs to be scaled up. Especially the number of hubs needs to be increased in order to raise the number of possible hub-hub connections. This will increase the potential for the max-flow-between-hubs objective function to improve system reconfigurability. The number of vital end users needs to be increased as well in order to see whether the two robustness functions indeed converge as was hypothesized.

It is interesting to see whether the propulsion system can be integrated in the ATG tool as well. First of all, because propulsion and manoeuvring capabilities can be considered vital for survivability, meaning that integration of more propulsion components presents a way of increasing the number of vital end users (e.g. propellers and steering machines). Furthermore, the components of propulsion systems typically are relatively large. Thus, a system designer wanting to apply the first principle dimension prediction design tool of *Stapersma (2015)* (or a different dimension prediction tool for that matter) needs to know which propulsion system components should be sized. Another reason to integrate the propulsion system here is that this is seldom done in comparable studies (also not in *de Vos (2018)*), while the propulsion system is, at this stage, just another energy distribution system (that is indeed vital to both the ship's mission capability and survivability).

Table II lists the system components that are added to the 23-node case study system in order to scale it up to a 35-node case study system that will be more fit for testing the hypothesis of section 2.3 and demonstrating the usefulness of the ATG tool. Fig.5 shows a handmade 35-node case study system topology. For sake of clarity not all potential connections are shown. The 35-node case study system has 126 potential connections. Still the vast majority of these are s-h and h-u connections, but now there is also more design freedom in h-h connections. E.g., the two switchboards have each been split in two separate segments. This will in practice always be the case when two DG-sets are providing power to a single switchboard: a bus breaker will be integrated in that switchboard. Typically, the bus breaker will be closed and the switchboard is operating as one hub. This is the reason for connecting the two segments of the two switchboards in Fig.4 as well (bi-directionally). During automatic topology generation system topologies may however be generated where these specific h-h connections do not exist, i.e. there are no bus breakers and there really are four separate switchboards. In such a case (4 hubs) the number of potential h-h connections in that specific hub layer is $n_h \cdot (n_h - 1) / 2 = 4 \cdot 3 / 2 = 6$. It can be seen that the propulsion system is indeed added more elaborately in the 35-node case study system (hybrid or CODELAD concept) including the steering machines (rudders). Both the rudders and the propellers will be defined as vital users, but redundant supply lines for the propellers implies each propeller being driven by two shafts, which is impractical to say the least. The redundant supply with the propulsion diesel engines as driving machines next to the electric motors of course is the crux of hybrid propulsion. Note that the propulsion diesel engines (same as the diesel

generators) are “stand-alone” in the sense that their fuel supply and cooling water & lube oil systems are omitted here. Further, the ATG tool will confront a system designer with an important question concerning the mechanical power distribution system, as it may generate system topologies where the gearboxes are connected by a cross-connect transmission. After all, to the tool these are just hubs (in a mechanical power distribution system). This will be shown in the next section, where system topologies are automatically generated for the 23-node and 35-node case study system case study system.

Table II: List of additional OPV system components and associated distribution systems.

System component	Distribution system in which system component is		
	user	hub	supplier
2 x Main Switchboard (extra; so total number of SWB will be 4)	-	440V	-
2 x Diesel Engines (DE PS & SB)	-	-	Mech
2 x Transmission Gearbox (GB PS & SB)	-	Mech	-
2 x Propellers (Prop PS & SB)	Mech	-	-
1 x Bridge	-	-	HC_data
2 x Steering Machines (Rudder PS & SB)	440V; HC_data	-	-
1 x Bow Thrusters	440V; HC_data	-	-

Fig.5: Graph of 35-node case study system. Note the added propulsion components and shaft connections (green) and the rudders and bow thruster.

4. Automatic Topology Generation for case study systems

Based on the previous sections and recommendations of the other, related publications; *van Leeuwen (2017)*, *Duchateau (2018)* and *de Vos (2018)*, the following questions are raised with respect to automatic topology generation for the case study systems:

1. How do the two robustness objective functions (max-flow-between-hubs and hurt-state-percolation) perform in terms of finding realistic system concept designs, i.e. which is most suited to the design problem at hand? Do the metrics indeed converge when the number of end users is increased?
2. Does the ATG tool succeed in supporting a system designer who aims to find system design requirements and promising system concept designs?

These questions are the main focus of this section in which the results of the ATG tool for the OPV case study are presented and analysed.

4.1. ATG for 23-node case study system

Fig.6 shows two generated design spaces and Pareto fronts for two runs with the ATG tool for the 23-node case study system: one with max-flow-between-hubs (left) and one with hurt-state-percolation (right) as robustness objective function (on the y-axis). The system claim objective function is in both cases $n_connections$ (on the x-axis), to which a constant number of components (23 in this case) is added. Max-flow-between-hubs is a normalised function with respect to the maximum flow that could occur per hub layer (multiplied by 100 per hub layer to mimic a percentage). A constant “hub density” multiplied by 100 is added. The mathematical function and algorithm itself is not very difficult, but the explanation and interpretation of the values is. A reader wishing to understand the function and its output is referred to *de Vos (2018)*. The output of the function is made negative as NSGA-II minimizes objective functions, while the idea behind the max flow function is that flow between hubs is maximised. Hurt-state-percolation calculates the chance that a number of vital end users do not receive the energy (or other supply) they require for operation, given a generated system topology and a pre-defined number of random hits. Note that the values on the y-axis can then best be interpreted as: the chance that energy cannot flow (percolate) towards pre-defined vital users when the system is hit (metric for system vulnerability). An elaborate explanation of this function can be found in *van Leeuwen (2017)*.

Fig.6: Design spaces for 23-node case study system with $n_connections$ as system claim objective function and max-flow-between-hubs (left) or hurt-state-percolation (right) as robustness objective functions.

Focussing on the “Pareto front” in Fig.6 (left), there are only four “optimal” system topologies when max-flow-between-hubs is the applied system robustness objective function. All other generated topologies score equal on max-flow-between-hubs but have more connections as can be seen from the “design space”. Every “dot” may represent multiple unique system topologies as different topologies may score equal on both objective functions. The difference in such a case is then in the supplier-hub (s-h) or hub-user (h-u) connections. The reason for the low number of optimal system topologies in the left-hand plot is simple: there are only three possible hub-hub (h-h) connections in the 23-node case study system (as explained before). Since the max-flow-between-hubs objective function only uses potential h-h connections to increase system reconfigurability, the design freedom for NSGA-II is very small in this case. A1, B1 and C1 are three of the four optimal system topologies on the Pareto front. These topologies are shown in the appendix. A1 has no h-h connections, B1 has two h-h connections (between the two SWB’s and the two CW hubs) and C1 has three h-h connections (also between Computer rooms). Note also that each of these optimal system topologies have a minimum amount of s-h and h-u connections to make sure the system is “connected”. This means no components or sub-networks are “loose”. This is the work of the earlier described repair function.

The right-hand plot, with hurt-state-percolation as system robustness objective function, shows a more variable design space. The number of generated system topologies is similar (10000), but the scores of generated system topologies on the objective functions used is more variable. System topologies A2, B2 and C2 were selected to be shown in the appendix. First compare system topology A2 to A1 to see that the minimum number of connections + components that is reached is slightly lower in the right-hand plot of Fig.6 than in the left-hand plot: 56 (A2) instead of 58 (A1). The reason for this is the earlier introduced vitality repair function that ensures that vital users have multiple (redundant) supply lines. The vitality repair function is turned off when hurt-state-percolation is the applied robustness objective function (right-hand plot) to give the ATG tool the freedom to decide whether redundant supply lines should be used. The vitality repair function should however be activated when max-flow-between-hubs is used (left-hand plot) as that objective function does not consider redundant supply lines as a robustness measure. With the 76mm Gun as the only vital user (like in *Duchateau (2018)*) the difference between topologies A2 and A1 then is exactly two (58-56), namely, a redundant 440V supply line and a redundant CW supply line. Indeed, A2 has almost no components with double supply lines and no hub-hub connections (the latter was also true for A1 of course) and therefore represents the least robust system concept design with the lowest number of connections (while the repair function does still ensure a connected system).

Both of these robustness measures, redundant supply lines and hub-hub connections, are indeed used by hurt-state-percolation to make systems more robust. This can be concluded from analysing the differences between the system topologies on the Pareto front. Comparing A2 to B2 one can see that seven additional connections were made going from A2 to B2; B2 is at 63 for number of connections + components. Six of these are h-u connections (the first ones made are an extra 440V and an extra CW supply line to the 76mm Gun), while one of them is a h-h connection between the two CW hubs. Furthermore, one can see that the Pareto front in Fig.5 makes a very sharp corner at system topology B2. Robustness still increases when system topologies have more connections than B2, but the increase is a lot less than adding (the correct) connections to system topologies with a lower number of connections than B2. It is to be expected that the Pareto front will become smoother when more vital end users are defined. It may then also become more interesting for the hurt-state-percolation objective function to increase the number of hub-hub connections. This can also be expected from analysing system topology C2, where two additional hub-hub connections are made (in comparison with B2): one between the switchboards and one between the Server rooms Comp aft & fwd. Thus, these connections are for the 23-node case study system the “best-of-the-rest”.

4.2 Topology generation for 35-node case study system

For the 35-node case study system the variety in system topologies increases compared to the 23-node case study system, Fig.7. Fig.7 (left) shows that with the 35-node case study system the design freedom has now also increased for the max-flow-between-hubs robustness objective function. The freedom and resulting variety in developed system topologies remains however inherently lower than for the hurt-state-percolation robustness function as more constraints are applied and the focus remains limited to hub-hub connections. Note that the maximum value of the y-axis has increased with 100; this is a consequence of a new hub layer being part of the system: the mechanical hubs (better known as gearboxes). Their contribution to the increased design freedom is limited however, since there are only two gearboxes and the only option for max-flow-between-hubs is to add a bi-directional connection between the gearboxes or not. Nevertheless, confronting a system designer with the option of having such a “cross-connect” transmission to increase system reconfigurability fits well with the intention of the ATG tool. The real increase in design freedom is caused by the increase in number of hubs in the 440V hub layer. There are now 4 hubs, which means there is now a possibility that generated system topologies have ring distributions in that hub layer. The max-flow-between-hubs objective function is designed to value such topologies and indeed system topology D1 (see appendix) has a full ring in the 440V hub layer. The only topologies that outperform D1 according to max-flow-between-hubs have the same full ring + additional connections between the hubs in the ring. Note that this in fact just increases the number of rings present in the 440V hub layer as can be seen from topology E1.

Fig.7: Design spaces for 35-node case study system with $n_connections$ as system claim objective function and max-flow-between-hubs (left) or hurt-state-percolation (right) as robustness objective functions. Compare with Fig. 6.

The Pareto front in the right-hand plot in Fig.7 is much smoother than in Fig.6, as expected. Note that for this run with hurt-state-percolation as robustness objective function nine vital end users were specified: the 76mm Gun, 30mm Gun, CIC, Sensor Mast, Bridge, both propellers and both steering machines (rudders). System topologies with hub-hub connections start to appear more frequently in the left (steep) end of the Pareto front in this case. One should however be careful to conclude that this is because hub-hub connections are now in general valued by hurt-state-percolation. It is also possible that the ATG tool is unsuccessful in finding approximately equally robust topologies with less (hub-hub) connections as the optimization with NSGA-II may not be perfect.

To understand this, it is important to note that the sharp corner in the Pareto front is still there, although now somewhat less sharp, at system topology D2 (shown in the appendix). When following the Pareto front system topologies from the least robust (lowest number of connections + components) to more robust (i.e. from left to right), D2 is the first topology for which all vital end users have redundant supply lines. As soon as that is the case, hub-hub connections become more or less meaningless when the pre-defined number of hits in the simulation is limited to one. The reason being that, with the redundant supply lines, the only way to knock out a vital user with a single hit is by hitting it directly. If the number of pre-defined hits would be two the sharp corner would be present in the Pareto front as well: at the first system topology that has three supply lines to all vital end users.

When comparing the steep-end Pareto front system topologies (i.e. left of D2) it is clear that especially the hub-hub connection between the CW hubs is often present, while hub-hub connections in the other hub layers “seem to appear and disappear randomly”. Hurt-state-percolation, in combination with $n_connections$, apparently has no or little use for these h-h connections, while it does for the h-h connection in the CW hub layer. The difference between the CW distribution system and the other distribution systems stems from the ratio between the number of vital users and the number of supplying hubs. In the CW network only one h-h connection adds redundancy in the supply path to five vital users (Sensor Mast, CIC, Bridge, two Guns). The other option, making five redundant supply lines, is more “costly” in terms of $n_connections$. At system topology D2 these redundant supply lines are there anyway and the h-h connection between the CW hubs loses its meaning, but before that point is reached (to the left of system topology D2) the CW h-h connection is deemed a very good robustness measure. The only reason this connection is still there in topology D2 is that NSGA-II was unable to optimise further and delete it from a topology that has so many redundant supply lines. Hurt state percolation in combination with $n_connections$ here “teaches” the user of the

ATG tool (and the main author of this paper...) that h-h connections are only good robustness measures when the ratio between the number of vital users and the number of supplying hubs (per energy type) is sufficiently high. This also means the earlier defined hypothesis of the two robustness objective functions converging is only true under the condition that the ratio N_{vu} / N_{hubs} per energy distribution system is sufficiently high.

Furthermore, it is clear that the main robustness measure that is preferred by hurt-state percolation in the other energy distribution systems (with a lower N_{vu} / N_{hubs} ratio) is to add redundant supply lines to vital end users. Only after the supply lines are there, hub-hub connections start to be preferred by hurt-state-percolation (to the right of D2) in these energy distribution systems as well. But by then they contribute very little to system robustness as they are in the mildly decreasing end of the Pareto front. System topology E2 is shown in the appendix and indeed contains all possible hub-hub connections. From the observation that redundant supply lines are “added” in the steep part of the Pareto front and hub-hub connections thereafter in case the hurt-state-percolation is the robustness objective function, it is concluded that the “non-negotiability” of this robustness measure when max-flow-between-hubs is the robustness objective function is a fair assumption (given a sufficiently low N_{vu} / N_{hubs} ratio – which typically is the case).

4.3 Topology generation for 35-node case study system with LC’s promoted to SWB’s

Finally, if the ratio between the number of vital end users and the number of supplying hubs is so important, an interesting question can be raised: why is it that the Load Centres are hierarchically lower than the switchboards and why can’t they be interconnected? They are performing a similar function as the SWB’s: a junction in the network where energy is gathered and distributed. When setting up the case study system the LC’s were placed lower in the hierarchy of the 440V network topology and interconnections between them were not allowed in order to mimic practical system designs. Indeed, such a “radial distribution” is found often in marine engineering practice, especially for smaller ships with lower voltage levels. The main reason for this hierarchical approach is probably that it enables application of overcurrent protection devices in the supply lines of the lower level LC’s (also known as distribution panels). In this way, only a small group of users attached to the local LC will experience power loss when a short circuit or overload occurs in that part of the system and the overcurrent protection as a result takes the local LC of the grid. The larger network is then left undisturbed. As such, the hierarchical design of “radial distribution” networks (really a combination of radial and tree distribution) in combination with overcurrent protection is an effective measure against total black-outs and so-called cascading failures as a consequence of internal or external perturbations. However, this hierarchical approach comes at the expense of reconfigurability options as it fixes the N_{vu} / N_{hubs} ratio (usually at a low value). Note that for the “real” 440V hubs (SWB’s) in the case study systems up till now there have only been five users: three LC’s and two transformers, none of which were specified as vital. Only users connected to the LC’s were specified as vital.

Completely connected hub layers with many rings, as would surely be preferred by the max-flow-between-hubs objective function may be preferred by the hurt-state-percolation function as well when the LC’s are “promoted” to the level of the SWB’s. The ATG tool can cope with such a “wild idea”: all that needs to be done is allowing bi-directional interconnections between the LC’s themselves and between the LC’s and SWB’s. This promotes the LC’s to 440V SWB’s, of which there are suddenly seven (4 former SWB’s + 3 former LC’s). This increases the N_{vu} / N_{hubs} ratio for the 440 V network from 0/4 to 7/7. Note however that the ratio still does not become as high as it is for the CW network (5/2) as the number of vital users is approximately equal while the number of 440V hubs is much higher (7) than the number of CW hubs (still 2).

Fig.8 shows the design space when the run of Fig.7 is re-done (only with hurt-state-percolation) with the Load Centres at the same level as the 440V switchboards. Note that the sharp corner is again present in the Pareto front; this time at $n_{connections} + n_{components} = 113$. Again, these topologies, and the topologies to the right of the corner, are the topologies where all vital users have redundant

supply lines. The increased availability of hub-hub connections in the 440V network is now used by hurt-state-percolation to improve robustness in the steep end of the Pareto front (to the left of the corner). System topology F, at the right-hand side of Fig.8, shows even a ring (SWB2.1 – SWB2.2 – LC1 – LC2 – SWB2.1) to which almost all vital end users are connected. This was observed in other topologies in the steep end of the Pareto front as well. This is considered sufficient proof that the two robustness functions indeed converge as long as the N_{vu} / N_{hubs} ratio is sufficiently high. It is also clear that the CW hub-hub connection is present in system topology F. Again, it is stressed that especially for this energy distribution system the N_{vu} / N_{hubs} ratio is favourable for hub-hub connections (cross-over) as robustness measure.

Fig.8: Design space (left) and generated system topology F (right) for 35-node case study system – Load Centres act as 440V hubs as well, together with switchboards.

The reader may observe the “propeller shafts” in system topology F. It is clear that this rather theoretical approach to distribution system design does not take into account specific details of the different energy distribution systems; like the fact that doubling mechanical connections is difficult and highly impractical (especially under water). For electric and hydraulic connections (cables and pipelines) this is somewhat easier, although doubling supply lines for these systems also means that some form of switching between or accumulation of the supply needs to take place inside the components. Here one should remember that the ATG tool is not necessarily meant to provide “the right answers”, i.e. feasible system concept designs, but rather answers that makes the designer aware of his/her preferences / biases. In the case of the propeller shafts it is clear that a designer immediately “fixes” the system topology by deleting the redundant shaft lines. Although it is interesting to note that the generated system topology is only highly impractical, not entirely impossible! With max-flow-between-hubs this strange design solution for the propulsion system would not have been generated by the way. That function is somewhat more of an engineering tool, taking some practical considerations better into account. The more important notion however is that the theoretical exercises above can be related to a classic discussion in marine engineering: radial vs. (zonal) ring distribution, see e.g. *Geertsma et al. (2009)*. In the more traditional design approaches (zonal) ring distribution is often mentioned as a more robust system topology because of its reconfigurability. The current approach cannot count as mathematical proof for this statement, but it is clear that the presented ATG tool and the focus on network design with hubs provides a much better foundation to deal with this (and other) important design question in network design. This is considered proof of the approach being able to support a system designer in finding the important system requirements and promising system concept designs.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The intention of this paper is to show the usefulness of the ATG tool as a designer support tool. Usefulness however is a tricky concept since, like with system robustness, a clear metric may be

lacking and “it is in the eye of the observer” that the usefulness can be found. At least the paper has sharpened the author’s awareness to avoid own biases and to keep an open mind with regards to the approach.

This paper focused on design space exploration for distributed systems on board ships and utilizes methods that have already been applied for ship concept design. The validity and effectiveness of design space exploration may be different for system design and ship design. The three general robustness measures as specified in section 2.3 are widely used and may make the approach less useful to system design. Still, it is shown that the ATG tool more or less confirms these measures using two very different robustness objective functions, of which one is in fact designed to be in line with the measures and practical system designs (max-flow-between-hubs) and the other (hurt-state-percolation) is less biased towards design practice (but still confirms the measures under certain conditions). It is even clear that these conditions and the tipping point between the discussed topological robustness measures may be investigated with the ATG tool. By doing so the ATG tool succeeds in providing a much better foundation to choose certain system topologies and better explains why they adhere to existing design rules concerning system robustness.

Clearly a system designer is confronted with important questions concerning system design requirements when using the ATG tool for design space exploration. A designer may also use the tool to select promising system concept designs from the automatically generated system topologies.

Finally, it is possible to treat energy distribution systems, their components and their connections as more or less equivalent in functionality and working principle in early design. This generic perspective on on-board distribution systems may sometimes be missed in practice as many systems are designed in later ship design stages by specialised companies or organisational units. Also, the interaction between the systems of different domains are integrated into one overall topology making the designer more aware of potentially inconsequent choices. The risks for sub-optimal integration of system designs with conventional design practices should not be underestimated.

Much is still to be learned about early stage on-board system design, both from applying the current ATG tool and from developing it further. Many ways forward can be envisaged, amongst which a further development of the system claim and system robustness objective functions (e.g. include capacity calculations). The presented approach may be unique as design space exploration in early stage on-board system design is rarely undertaken and the developed node and edge differentiation framework seems to work very well in enabling system design in an integrated manner. Interested readers are invited to follow future publications from the authors on this topic (of which the dissertation of the main author will be the first).

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References

- DE VOS, P. (2014), *On the application of network theory in naval engineering*, 12th Int. Naval Engineering Conf., Amsterdam
- DE VOS, P.; STAPERSMA, D. (2018), *Automatic topology generation for early design of on-board energy distribution systems*, Ocean Engineering J.
- DEB, K. (2001), *Multi-Objective Optimization Using Evolutionary Algorithms*, Wiley
- DEB, K.; PRATAP, A.; AGARWAL, S.; MEYARIVAN, T. (2002), *A fast and elitist multiobjective genetic algorithm: NSGA-II*, IEEE Trans. Evolutionary Computation 6(2), pp.182-197

DUCHATEAU, E.A.E. (2016), *Interactive Evolutionary Concept Exploration in Preliminary Ship Design*, PhD thesis Delft University of Technology

DUCHATEAU, E.A.E.; DE VOS, P.; VAN LEEUWEN, S. (2018), *Early stage routing of distributed ship service systems for vulnerability reduction*, 13th Int. Marine Design Conference, Helsinki

GEERTSMA, R.D.; WESTON, A.V.; DEVLIN, J.; WRIGHT, W. (2009), *Power system survivability – how can we deliver?*, 3rd Engine as a Weapon Conf., London

HABBEN JANSEN, A.C.; KANA, A.A.; HOPMAN, J.J. (2018), *A methodology for an operational vulnerability assessment for naval ships using a Markov model*, 13th Int. Marine Design Conf., Helsinki

STAPERSMA, D.; DE VOS, P. (2015), *Dimension prediction models of ship system components based on first principles*, 12th Int. Marine Design Conference, Tokyo

VAN LEEUWEN, S.P. (2017), *Estimating the vulnerability of ship distributed system topologies*, Master's thesis, Delft University of Technology

VAN OERS, B. (2011), *A Packing Approach for the Early Stage Design of Service Vessels*, PhD thesis, Delft University of Technology

Appendix

Generated system topologies of 23-node case study system: A1 (left) and A2 (right), ref. Fig.6

Generated system topologies of 23-node case study system: B1 (left) and B2 (right), ref. Fig.6

Generated system topologies of 23-node case study system: C1 (left) and C2 (right), ref. Fig.6

Generated system topology of 35-node case study system: D1, ref. Fig.7

Generated system topology of 35-node case study system: D2, ref. Fig.7

Generated system topology of 35-node case study system: E1, ref. Fig.7

Generated system topology of 35-node case study system: E2, ref. Fig.7

The Digital Twin throughout the Lifecycle

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Abstract

This paper presents the future possibilities of the digital twin in the Maritime Industry and the solutions to optimise the use throughout the lifecycle of a vessel. Especially in relation to Autonomous vessels the Digital Twin will play a crucial role in optimal performance of the vessel. The Maritime industry is fragmented and the original builder of the Digital Twin, the Shipyard, is in most cases not the Owner who is operating the vessel for a period of 20 to 30 years. Also the Class Societies are part of this value chain and should adapt their approval process and inspection process to serve the Digital Twin. A collaboration between the parties involved is absolute necessary and will introduce a new view on the Maritime industry and a new business models for the Shipyards.

1. Introduction

The marine industry must convert its existing fleets to more energy efficient, reliable and more environmentally friendly ships with better overall performance and lower total operating costs. This modernization of the fleets must begin immediately as existing fleets are aging at an alarming rate and a significant number of ship retirements are expected in the next two decades. Additionally, the future fleets must satisfy an ever changing set of operational requirements and new regulations. To cope with these challenges, the shipbuilding industry is experiencing a significant transformation as leading shipyards around the world strive to build more competitive ships with better performance, reliability and availability with the lowest total cost of ownership. The industry is embracing a digital transformation, truly a sea change in shipbuilding, that has successfully transformed other global industries under enormous market pressures like the automotive, aerospace, energy and now the shipbuilding industry. This digital transformation that integrates the complete shipbuilding enterprise including the key members of the supply chain, class societies and ship owners is poised to revolutionize shipbuilding operations by providing all employees, partners and the owners representatives immediate controlled access to 3D models in a single database (the Digital Twin) that is aligned with all ship requirements and synchronized with the latest changes and revisions. This transformation will provide everybody who is working on the project (un)restricted access to the knowledge that defines and controls the technical and physical definition of the of the vessel at any point in the development cycle and location in the in the shipyard with mobile digital devices that are now available. This will enable operational coordination and harmony that is crucial to building complex, advanced ships and offshore platforms and will enable shipyards to achieve major breakthroughs in total enterprise productivity. The impact of digital transformation is well established in other industries and now will enable shipbuilders across the globe to improve communication, data transfer, efficiency and productivity.

But who is the owner of the Digital Twin and Who is going to control the Digital twin throughout the lifecycle of the vessel?

2. History & Future

The trend to integrate major industry enterprises started in the 90's in the automotive and aerospace industries to improve collaboration between designers and engineers. These industries were seeking to improve product development efficiency by more tightly integrating computer-aided design systems with internally developed product data management systems. Concurrently the role and importance of partners and suppliers, many half a world away, were increasing dramatically. For the automotive giants, the challenge was to maintain the design integrity of many models with thousands of parts over the millions of units produced annually. For the aerospace industry, the challenge was to maintain the design integrity of a much fewer number of models, but every product delivered had hundreds of thousands of part numbers and many critical serialized parts requiring absolute traceability. Then much

more robust commercially developed product lifecycle management suites were introduced that dramatically improved enterprise development productivity and offered major OEMs the scalability to manage the most complex products and operations. These suites provided aerospace original equipment manufacturers an array of tightly integrated applications tied to a lifecycle management platform. Now OEM's had the crucial change and configuration management capabilities to manage workflows and improve collaboration among integrated product teams across the entire lifecycle from design and production and subsequently across a lifecycle that could last 20-30 years.

2.1. The 1980s

Computer-aided software debuts in the 1980s. The first generation of computer-aided software entered the world of ship development and offered designers and systems engineers 2D images of arrangements, systems and structures. Concurrently, computer-aided software engineering tools offered specific discipline tools to automate repetitive analyses: hydrostatic, hydrodynamic, stability, finite element analysis, etc. Each tool set offered teams the ability to improve their productivity and optimize their processes, but multi-discipline engineering and operational alignment were labor intensive and paper-based, and drawings were still the medium for transferring design intent to production teams and suppliers. These improvements in productivity in design and engineering did not preclude the need for large quality organizations to constantly check and recheck production plans and decisions with drawings, while substantial amounts of changes were being processed throughout the detailed design and production phases. Further challenging this already demanding environment were countries that wanted to build a modern fleet, and jointly produce them in a local shipyard to ensure homegrown companies could provide complete lifecycle repair and support, and enable their citizens to participate in the programs.

2.2. The 1990s

Providing more comprehensive solutions. In the 1990s, a new generation of software emerged with broader and more comprehensive solutions, and the first versions of commercially developed product data management (PDM) systems were implemented. The first PDM systems offered a more disciplined and automated solution to change and configuration management, which was exactly what the shipbuilding and aerospace industries needed as the scale and complexity of new designs was growing exponentially and there was no end in sight to the relentless flow of design changes. No longer was it reasonable to assume that this could be coordinated and synchronized across a major enterprise without the help of software to control and manage the process.

The 2D computer-aided design (CAD) systems gradually were replaced by 3D systems, which enabled the digital mockup (DMU) of complex ship models as well as the digital simulation of material flow and assembly processes throughout a shipyard. Digital simulations of existing shipyard workflows and processes produced double-digit percentage improvements in existing shipyards, and even greater improvements in new greenfield shipyards in which processes and workflows could be simulated and optimized before the shipyard was even built. There was some improvement in performance for shipbuilding programs that depended on this generation of new software technology, but there were also disappointing results; for instance, programs fell behind schedule, were over budget and did not always meet requirements and/or performance expectations. It was clear from lessons learned in other industries that for shipyards to achieve transformational results, the next generation of software technology for shipbuilding would have to be more than an information technology (IT) project. It would require the dedication and commitment of all levels of shipyard leadership.

As one executive put it, "Change is not easy and the last thing that engineers want to do is give up the tools that they know and love for something new and better." But change was a prerequisite for satisfying future requirements and budgets, and there were encouraging examples from other industries that were realizing significant breakthroughs in productivity with a new generation of software technology, process improvements and team training.

2.3. The 2000s

Taking a completely different approach to the way they vessels are design, develop, produced and operated. The digital shipyards have been enabled by a new generation of software technology that offers an open, scalable and modular portfolio that can be used to readily and rapidly transform an existing infrastructure to improve design and engineering productivity. Moreover, the new software continuously aligns design and engineering activities with specifications and requirements; ensures that embedded-systems-engineering functionality supports multi-physics analyses while maintaining the ship work breakdown structure systems (SWDBS) alignment, and captures and maintains the bill of materials (BOM) in a single master database record for each ship in a class from concept development through sea trials and delivery. This same software portfolio can also be used to enhance production, construction and sea trials productivity for shipbuilders as well as members of their supply chain. The result is a highly-integrated enterprise that is better aligned and more efficient and capable of producing vessels that are meeting the requirement, delivered on time and within budget, the holy grail of any shipbuilding program. This generation of digital shipyards has achieved substantial improvements in productivity with a far more versatile work force in which teams can design naval and commercial ships almost simultaneously, providing a single source of ship class and hull number knowledge/technical definition. Processes are digitally simulated, thereby optimizing performance and eliminating costly errors. In the 2000s, it is also worth mentioning examples of fleet in-service configuration management initiatives that were implemented to improve safety or service and support productivity. This trend is growing in importance as fleet owners and operators seek to reduce the cost of ownership of current and future fleets.

2.4. The 2010s

PLM comes aboard The emergence of product lifecycle management (PLM) portfolios that are tailored to the unique challenges of developing advanced ships are transforming the most advanced shipyards in the world so that future fleets are more affordable, sustainable and reliable. The productivity projections from these new portfolios are crucial for meeting the constraints of current budgets, plus the commissioning of each new ship can be linked to the decommissioning of an existing ship so that overall fleet readiness is not adversely affected. The most comprehensive PLM for shipbuilding also has a new array of computer-aided engineering (CAE) software technology that enables users to analyze and improve the acoustic signature of ships to satisfy crucial noise requirements, and composite software tools to suppress self-generated machinery noise. The next step in the evolution of shipbuilding IPDEs will be the extension of this digital platform to all partners, members of the supply chain and fleet support teams to maximize total enterprise productivity and reduce the total cost of ownership. This trend is already underway in some leading shipyards.

2.5. The 2020s

Tightening enterprise integration, the next generation of IPDE solutions will enable shipyards to more tightly integrate the complete enterprise with particular attention to the supply chain and service lifecycle management, both top priorities today. Strategic partners will continue to collaborate and share data through a highly secure private network with International Organization of Standardization (ISO) standards such as the JT™ data format to enable the building of 3D multi-CAD models. A cloud-based solution will offer the rest of the supply chain access to the information and data that they need from the master data file to be an efficient yet virtual member of the team. In a similar manner, service lifecycle management will be coordinated and managed by the lead shipyard or the overall service provider with supply chain members and fleet support staffs. Additionally, in-service lifecycle performance, such as mean-time-between failure, system-reliability metrics and related data will be carefully documented for all systems and components by class and hull number. As a result, future fleets can benefit from lessons learned and many systems will not need to be re-engineered for next generation designs.

This future however can only exist if the Digital Twin is acknowledged by all players in the Marine Industry. The Marine Industry today is still fragmented and it will be a big challenge to align it for future benefits.

3. The Digital Twin

3.1. Shipyards

Throughout the greater part of this decade, Shipyards have been on a steady course to bring production from the outdated, out-of-sync plants of the past and into the data-rich, streamlined and efficient future of the Digital Shipyard. The key to that transformation is in the data: creating a synchronized thread of digital information that connects even the most disparate global supply chains into a cohesive digital enterprise. Doing so creates a “single source of the truth” for the entire ecosystem, stretching from conception to production to service throughout the product lifecycle.

Think about how cloud computing has made it possible to update personal and professional information across different devices simultaneously. If you update a contact’s name in the directory on your phone, that update can automatically happen on a computer and tablet if they have compatible software that links to the “digital thread” on a remote server; so when you get back to your desk and look up that contact, you see the latest update.

This ties the entire life of a ship, from a designer's initial rough sketch to its last voyage at sea, to a single, traceable digital thread that is accessible to the farthest reaches of the supply chain. In that thread, every change, every update, every improvement or problem can be synched to each player in the ecosystem to guarantee that everyone is working off the most accurate and up-to-date information possible. This means no more costly rework resulting from out-of-sync designs; it means shorter production schedules, smarter maintenance and, inevitably, better performance. And finally, it means the industry can meet its sky-high demands on time and on budget. And when you follow the thread out to sea, where those initial build costs continue to grow throughout the life of this ship, we can start to understand the real power this digital thread is offering the Marine industry.

This is the power of the “single source of truth” or in other words the Digital Twin of the product. In theory this sounds fantastic and would help the major players in the Marine Industry to improve efficiency, quality and reduce the total cost of ownership. In real life we still have to go a long way before all parties involved are really cooperating and making the Digital Twin a success.

The marine Industry is still fragmented and cooperation is being executed on a level which is not high enough to touch the status of real partnership. This partnership is essential to come to an optimal performance where all parties can benefit from the power of the Digital Twin. The Marine industry has to re-invent herself and has to embrace a new way of working where partnership is the basis, mutual benefits the goal and the Digital Twin the engine to power innovation.

3.2. The Position of the Class Societies

The position of the class societies plays an important role in the story of the Digital Twin. They are the only supplier in the whole value chain who are involved from the early design stage to the decommissioning stage. We could say that they are the red line in the Product lifecycle of the vessel.

In the first stage of the life cycle they have the shipyard as a client (original contractor) but for the major part of the total lifecycle the owner or operator is the actual client of the class society. Or should we say that the class society is a service supplier to the owner? Over the past decades the class societies lost a part of their power dictating how a shipyard or owner should act or operate their vessel. Nowadays the major class societies are all member of IACS. This organization is a strong platform to discuss rules and regulations and introduce more uniform procedures but it is also a weakness. Due to the IACS agreements the owner can easily change class if they are not happy with the way they are treated!

Class and owner are stepping into a marriage for the total lifecycle of the vessel but sometimes they are ending up with a divorce. During this divorce the information has to be transferred from one class society to the other class society. This is regulated by IACS but not all class societies are working in the same way or are using the same software platform to control their procedures. It can also be the other way that the owner is selling the vessel to a third party where the class society remains. Also in that case, information has to change and probably different software platforms are being used. If you look at this complex world of information transfers it would be a lot easier if this is being supported by a standardized format which can be used throughout the lifecycle of the vessel. An exchangeable format which can be used by all classification societies, ship owners and operators and which is supported by the major CAD/PLM tools which are used by the shipyards. This is a complex matter but a necessity to optimize the information stream during the lifecycle of a vessel. The shipyard is the origin of the information stream. They build the 3D model for their production process and can convert this model into a Digital Twin which can be used throughout the lifecycle of the vessel.

Going back to the class societies, what are they doing right now and are they collaborating with each other to come to a standardized exchangeable format? The answer is No! Some are busy with developing a format like DNV GL; some are building their own software solution around a CAD tool like BV and CCS; and others are in the stage of defining their way forward. They are all working independently and are looking more to their own benefits than the benefits for the whole value chain. The time has come that the class societies have to hire a helicopter to fly above the marine Industry and start working on a collaboration to overcome this challenging problem. Without a proper file format, the Digital Twin in the marine Industry is still far away. The subject should be put on the IACS agenda because they can initiate a change.

A standardized file format will also open up the possibility to discuss 3D approval where the class information with regard to the approval process is directly uploaded in the Digital Twin. This is however not only a simple transfer of information but also a security issue which has to be addressed. Block chain technology can help to solve this problem and makes the transfer of information later on in the life cycle of the vessel much easier.

3.3 Owners & Operators

Fleet operators in all markets are facing numerous challenges including a growing number of competitors, rising material and labor costs, more demanding requirements such as sustainable shipping and the need to lower the overall operating costs without affecting availability. Owners and operators need to be more innovative and efficient to satisfy this growing list of challenges.

When the maintenance costs of a ship can be 60-70 % of the total lifecycle cost and fleet Owners and Operators are facing significant budget reductions, never before has lifecycle service and support been more important for fleet Owners. Thus both fleet Owners and shipyards are focused on building future fleets that are easier to operate and less expensive to service and support. In parallel they have to implement technology to more efficiently support existing fleets which can have extended service lives. PLM solutions provide shipyards and fleet operators a single source of truth which increases the accuracy and coordination throughout service operations and facilitates fleet upgrades, enhancements and alterations.

During the total lifecycle of the vessel, the Owner is the real user of the Digital Twin. It is a strange situation that the basis for this Digital Twin is being made during the building of the vessel and that the owner is paying for this 3D Model but is unable to use it because of IP rights from the shipyards. Of course, shipyards have to protect their IP rights but they also have to collaborate with the ship owner to furnish him with a Digital twin which he can use for operating and maintaining the vessel. As mentioned before, the Owner is also depending on the Class Society who also has its version of the Digital Twin in its system to control the certificates and the inspection information. So the Owner is the real user of the Digital Twin and can benefit the most out of it, but has no control over the information. This is a

strange situation and the Marine Industry has to work together to come to a solution where all parties involved in the value chain can benefit from the Digital Twin.

4. New Business Opportunities for Shipyards

Shipyards, and in some cases design houses, are the first owner and builder of the 3D model which can transform to a Digital Twin by adding relevant information with regard to the installed equipment and used materials. However, this Digital Twin also contains the production information to build the vessel. In some cases this information is protected by IP rights. With the access to this information you can easily make a copy of the vessel at any yard in the world. From the perspective of the Shipyard it is not strange that they want to protect their information to third parties like the Class Society and the Owners. However, they have to be more open to share their information to reduce the overall costs of building and operating a vessel. Class Societies are checking the work of the yard and equipment/material suppliers and build up their own model to validate calculations. On the other side, Owners are also building up their maintenance model with 2D data provided by the yard. The Shipyard owns the Digital Twin but is only supplying 2D information to the Class Society and the Owner. Isn't that strange in the digital world we are living in?

The shipyards have the key to a new business model in their hands but they have to unlock it themselves. Shipyards have to change their way of thinking and to transform from being a builder only to an OEM supplier. The information they own is valuable and can be used to optimize the performance of their product and to lower the total costs of ownership for the Owner. To unlock this potential, they have to start sharing the necessary information in the Digital Twin with the Owners and support them with the maintenance of the Digital Twin during the lifecycle of the vessel. In return the Owners can submit operational data to improve next-generation designs.

This way of thinking is new to the Maritime Industry because all parties involved are reluctant to share information. They are afraid that valuable information is shared with competitors and that they lose their competitiveness.

5. Autonomous Vessels

One of the most interesting and challenging trend is the roadmap towards autonomous vessels. The development of autonomous cars is all over the news. Big companies like Tesla, Uber and Google are all developing and testing the technology necessary to make this happen in the near future. So it looks like the car industry is ahead but this is not really the case. The first projects to build autonomous ships are being executed and the first vessel should be in operation along the coast of Norway by the end of 2018. The challenges of developing an autonomous vessel differ from autonomous cars or trucks. Traffic control offshore is less complex than the traffic control onshore but the international character of shipping makes it more difficult with regards to the rules and regulation and responsibilities when something is going wrong.

The remote areas where ships are sailing are also a point of attention. When there is a technical problem onboard the vessel it is not easy to repair it or to send people onboard. This means that autonomous vessels should be very reliable (redundant systems) and tested (simulation) during the building and commissioning of the vessel. Here, the Digital Twin can play a crucial and important role. With the help of a Digital Twin the design risks can be minimized and the vessel's systems can be thoroughly tested before actual commissioning is starting. All kinds of simulations can be done upfront, under different circumstances, to ensure safe performance of the ship systems later on when the vessel is in operation. During the operation, feedback from the vessel can be fed into the Digital Twin to optimize performance and to enable improvements. During operation the Digital twin is the backbone of the operator to manage the vessel from shore. He can combine real-time info from the vessel with the design data from the model to make analyses and to predict maintenance. Also when problems occur on board the vessel during operation, the Digital Twin can act as reliable source of information to solve the

problem. AR and VR technology in combination with the Digital Twin will give operators of autonomous vessels the tools to safely manage their assets.

6. Summary and Conclusions

The demand for complex, versatile and affordable ships has never been greater as fleet owners and operators around the world seek reasonably priced and reliable designs that satisfy their requirements. However, the cost and complexity of modern ships are not compatible with most budget projections. Thus, ship owners and operators are seeking technology solutions that will enable shipyards to build future fleets on budget and on time with the operational performance and lifecycle durability and availability to satisfy acceptable total cost of ownership goals. In the future, these benefits will be extended across the entire supply chain and drive down the total cost of ownership of future fleets.

PLM Software solution will enable future fleets to have more capabilities and perform better by facilitating innovative solutions throughout the lifecycle of the vessel, thereby reducing the time and cost of building the vessel and lowering the recurring costs. The latter is crucial as we transition to new generations of ship designers and shipyard production and sustainment specialists. At this point in history when fleet owners and operators have to “do more with less,” the shipbuilding industry is facing an inflection point and the path to improved performance is the next-generation of integrated digital shipbuilding enterprises.

To achieve this goal, the major players in the marine industry have to put their hands together and start collaborating on many aspects and they have to overcome their fear of sharing important and crucial information with each other. Establishing these partnerships is the key to success. Class Societies have to find a way to work more closely on the information transfer with the shipyard and come to an data transfer format which is supported by the shipyards and can be used by the ship owners. IACS can play an important role in this. The shipyards are the spider in the web and have to start sharing more information with the equipment suppliers and the ship owners. This to make the Digital Twin happen and to discover new business opportunities. The Owner benefits the most from this new collaboration, but has to provide operational data to the shipyard and class society to improve their services and feed innovation.

If this can be established the power of the Digital Twin can grow to its full potential.

Intelligent Design and Operation of Ship Energy Systems combining Big Data and AI

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Abstract

Digitalization and automation have been transforming the shipping industries. INTENS is an industry-wide joint effort dedicated to advancing and promoting the digital transformation in Finnish marine industries and beyond, with special focus on ship energy systems. By combining Big Data and Artificial Intelligence, it is able to holistically integrate ship energy systems at the component, system, ship and fleet levels, aiming to achieve intelligent and optimal design and operation of ship energy systems throughout their life cycles. Consequently, it can potentially change and disrupt the ways how the marine industries operate currently and pave the way to the future shipping.

1. Introduction

As a global effort into greenhouse gas emissions reduction, the introduction of International Maritime Organization's (IMO) energy efficiency measures (EEDI - Energy Efficiency Design Index, EEOI - Energy Efficiency Operational Indicator, SEEMP - Ship Energy Efficiency Management Plan, and ECA - Emission Control Areas) has stimulated the development and adoption of novel energy technologies, practices and innovations throughout ships' design, building and operation phases. However, despite the great efforts, if business goes as usual, a 50-250% increase in maritime CO₂ emissions from international maritime transport is projected by 2050 due to the expected future economic growth and transport demand increase, according to *IMO (2014)*. As the most recent action, IMO and its member states have adopted an initial strategy that envisages reducing the total annual GHG emissions from international shipping by at least 50% by 2050 compared to 2008.

Meanwhile, digitalization and automation have been transforming the shipping industries. Novel technologies and innovations are continuously gaining momentum in the marine domain and speeding up the mega-transition at a rapid pace. Major digital transformation trends, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data, Digital Twin, Internet of Things (IoT) and Cloud/Edge Computing, are already shaping the future of shipping. In the foreseeable future, the shipping industries will be radically different from what they are now, which poses both challenges and opportunities to the global marine cluster.

Owning the knowledge of cutting-edge digital technologies and expertise in the marine domain, Finland has all the necessary ingredients to pioneer the digital transformation of the marine sector globally. Profoundly, a group of industry-leading marine companies (such as *Wärtsilä (2017)*, *ABB (2017)* and *Rolls Royce (2017)*) are the global forerunners of marine industry digitalization. The project INTENS (Integrated Energy Solutions to Smart and Green Shipping) aims to integrate Big Data, AI, Digital Twin and Cloud Computing into the whole ship lifecycles and to strengthen the position of the Finnish marine industries. The consortium, consisting of nineteen partners from Finnish marine industries and research institutions, dedicates ten networked RDI projects (nine industrial projects and one public project) to advancing the digital transformation in Finnish marine industries and beyond, with special focus on ship energy systems, and to deepening the scientific and practical knowledge of smart and green shipping.

2. Research, Development and Innovation (RDI) Methodology

Novel technologies and innovative solutions have been widely applied to ship designing, building, retrofitting and operating processes, which, however, rarely resulted in expected energy efficiency increases and emissions reduction, especially under dynamic operating conditions and uncertainties. Meanwhile, modern ships are generating huge amount of data all the time during the operation. Given

the recent advancement of ICT technologies and data analytics, how to utilize and enrich the data collected from ships has been a normal routine for all people working in the marine cluster.

Thanks to its great potential and expected advantages, the Digital Twin concept has started gaining momentum and become more and more imperative to the business when the IoT starts emerging, and will continue playing a central role in industries’ digital transformation. Industrial leaders, such as *GE (2017)* and *IBM (2017)*, have been introducing Digital Twin in their businesses. Specifically, *DNV GL (2017)* has been promoting Digital Twin in marine industries as part of their digital asset ecosystem. Done properly, Digital Twin can bring IoT, Big Data, AI, VR/AR (virtual reality/augmented reality), Cloud/Edge Computing and dynamic simulation and optimization to one central place and communicate interactively with physical counterparts, which can potentially transform the industries and the whole society. However, there are still some challenges and questions to answer before digitally-twinning industries become real. To name a few:

- How can we build digital twins of components, devices and systems with tools and technologies at hand? Who will build the different digital twins?
- At which level do we need to develop different Digital Twins? Always at very detailed level?
- How can we integrate different digital twins to act as a seamless function, which is especially critical for shipping?
- How can we curate the huge amount of data for specific purpose? Is it all about data?
- How can we figure out the (known and unknown) unknowns from the knowns?

In INTENS, we adopt the Digital Twin concept as the main RDI methodology to study, develop and implement Digital Twins into the marine cluster, and to address the scientific and practical challenges hindering the wider utilization of the concept in the industries. Instead of identical twins of physical systems, we would rather build schematic twins with necessary details for desired purpose and focus more on developing the capacities of Digital Twin for

- perceiving, related to effectual Big Data handling and understanding of the systems and environment,
- learning, related to effective machine learning and data enrichment,
- thinking, related to reasoning and efficient optimization with cloud/edge computing, and
- acting, related to design, operation, maintenance, prognostics and diagnostics.

Fig.1: An illustrative diagram of the RDI methodology

As shown in Fig.1, the schematic twins (virtual models) of the case energy systems (including fleets, ships, systems and components) connect and run in parallel with their physical counterparts online or offline. Combined with AI and Big Data technologies, they learn and update themselves based on the available information, which includes multi-source data, generated by themselves or collected from the case systems or other sources (e.g. similar systems, environments, ...) in real time or in the past, and knowledge accumulated through the earlier experience during the long history of shipping. Thus, the roles of models have been redefined as

- information collector and carrier to collect and carry the information throughout their lifecycles,
- information enabler and transformer to enrich and transform the information to benefit the system design and operation, and
- information generator as large amount of information is generated when virtually running the models in parallel with their physical counterparts identically or for various scenario analyses.

Digital Twins are primarily built based on their physical counterparts. However, advanced digital design methods are commonly used in all engineering domains nowadays. The future twins will be digital by design before even having the physical counterparts. Different from identical twins that represent all the details of the physical counterparts, the schematic twins contain only necessary details and can be efficiently utilized for various purposes. There are three common approaches to build virtual models, namely physics-based (white-box) approach, data-driven (black-box) approach or the hybrid of two (grey-box approach). Physics-based first-principle models contain more details but need more prior information, which in theory needs to be identical to the physical systems. The data-driven models are built solely based on the data available but need large amount of high quality data to train before reaching an acceptable level of accuracy. The hybrid models are especially useful to represent the systems with only partially available information. In practice, the selection of the modelling approaches depends on the requirement of specific tasks and the available information.

Fig.2: A multi-layer platform for design, operation and maintenance of ship energy systems

Fig.2 gives a brief overview of how we develop and utilize the virtual models to identify proper scenarios, novel solutions and innovations for design, operation and maintenance of ship energy systems throughout their lifecycles. The core of the conceptual framework is the three-layer platform

built on top of an information (knowledge and data) base. The knowledge base includes various ship energy technologies, energy systems and their dynamic and/or data-driven models and libraries; the database includes measurement data, collected via ship onboard energy management systems (EMS) and on-site or lab experiments, and simulation data generated in the earlier work. The system-level ship energy flow simulation platform provides a multi-domain dynamic simulation environment where ship energy systems are modelled based on first principles and simulated under real operating conditions. Fig.3 shows one example of how to evaluate ship energy saving scenarios using the system-level dynamic energy flow simulation, where a combined shaft generator and waste heat recovery (WHR) system is implemented and optimized for optimal energy efficiency improvement of one case container ship. *Zou et al. (2014)* Big Data-centric operations, such as data handling, data-driven modelling and data analytics, are carried out on the AI-enabled information enrichment platform; and the ship energy system optimization platform is the multi-objective optimization layer that holistically generates and optimizes the design (new-build or retrofit), operation and maintenance scenarios of the energy systems in question. The virtual models can be connected to the corresponding energy systems on board or via satellite remotely, running in parallel as the schematic digital twins with the physical counterparts, in real time or offline, for exploring novel energy solutions and innovations, for business-critical decision-making, and for energy system condition monitoring, diagnosis and “measuring” critical sports via simulation, called equipment-free soft sensors.

Fig.3: A top-level diagram of the energy flow simulator with implemented energy saving scenarios

3. Multi-Level Framework

Building modern ships, especially large cruise ships, is of a collaborative nature due to their complexity and the involvement of large number of suppliers. However, in the current modus operandi, the same or similar operations still involve plenty of operation silos (ship design, build, operation, ship maintenance, supply, logistics, etc.). The limited collaborations and interactions between different silos result in the lack of systematic consideration and hence unnecessary inefficiency and waste of energy and resources, especially during the design and operation phases of ships. This becomes even more critical when the scale and the complexity of ship energy systems and shipping network increase. On the other hand, digital transformation will only gain full speed after a critical mass of players is involved.

In this paper, we propose a network-based multi-level collaboration framework, aiming to enable and encourage the industry-wide cooperation, information exchange and enrichment within the consortium during the project period and to the whole cluster afterwards. As shown in Fig.4, ship energy systems can be represented at multiple levels, with higher levels specifying the topology of the networks or ship energy plants and lower levels including more components with more detailed dynamic representation. It is not limited to four levels, however. For instance, on top of the fleet level, the framework can be expanded to the global shipping network level and even further extended to land-based energy and

logistics networks related to shipping. Different companies are grouped to corresponding levels according to their main businesses. The INTENS consortium covers the whole value chain of the marine cluster, vertically across all the component, system, ship, and fleet levels, which offers ideal opportunities to research and demonstrate how to enable industry-wide collaboration and information sharing. Done properly, this could benefit different players in the domain and ensure the developed solutions and innovations can be feasible and applicable to the whole cluster later on.

Fig.4: Illustration of the multi-level collaboration framework

Fig.4 shows the foundation of the multi-level collaboration framework is the aforementioned multi-layer conceptual energy system platform, which runs as an information fusion reactor to generate added value, optimized solutions and innovations for the involved partners from the information they shared. Specifically, each partner can design and optimize their products in a true marine environment and evaluate system performances with operating profiles from real operating conditions, not just with single “design points”. Furthermore, the partners work together to offer a better-integrated product portfolio to their customers. The advanced platform and its vast information base provide the collaboration framework with some unique features:

- Scalability – The energy systems of ships of different types, scales and complexities, can be systematically represented at one or more levels, with necessary details for specific purpose. At each level, the systems are shown as a network, and all levels together form an overall network.
- Flexibility – The energy systems can be modelled using physics-based, data-driven or hybrid approaches at one or more levels depending on requirements and information available. During the optimization process, different concepts or scenarios of design, operation and maintenance can be formed and evaluated at each level or across all the levels of the overall network.
- Interactivity – The energy systems have to be taken into consideration as an integrated one and the interactions between different subsystems are key to the systems’ performances. Huge data

communication not only happens at each level, but more importantly, across the different levels, which is one of the key features of the framework.

4. Application Cases

As an industry-wide collaborative consortium, INTENS aims to develop and implement various novel solutions and innovations in 15 practical application cases. Specifically, corresponding to the multi-level collaborative framework, the application cases are grouped into fleet, ship, system and component levels, respectively, although we do need to extend most of the cases across more than one level in practice. As listed in Table I, the RDI activities of all the application cases are further highlighted, especially with respect to the Digital Twin advancing efforts.

Table I: List of application cases and their RDI activities

Case group	Application case	RDI highlight
Fleet level	Global cargo fleets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Big Data driven collaborative voyage optimization - Advanced IoT utilization
	Regional fleets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning-aided ship operation and forecasting - Nature-inspired regional fleet operation optimization - System-level data mining
Ship level	Future cruise ships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lifecycle excellence through simulation - Cloud-based dynamic system optimization - Optimization as a service
	Hybrid ships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimal battery hybridization and integration - Poly generation concepts - Robust automation
	MS Silja Serenade	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learning-based ship operation optimization - Schematic Serenade twin
	MS Wasa Express	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste heat recovery
System level	Battery systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simulation-enabled system integration
	Hybrid engines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptive system parameter learning - Engine and battery system integration - Hybrid engine system twins
	Organic Rankine cycles (ORC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste to electricity - ORC system twins
	Waste heat recovery (WHR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste to energy - WHR system twins
Component level	Duel fuel engines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emissions reduction - Data-enriched fault diagnostics - Engine twins
	Heat exchangers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data-driven design optimization - Heat exchanger twins
	Novel catalysts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adaptive emissions reductions - Catalyst twins
	Silencers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simulation-based optimization
	Smart filters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI-enabled condition monitoring - Filter twins

5. Conclusions

As industry-wide collaborative effort, the INTENS projects aims to accelerate the digital transformation and to leap Digital Twin closer to reality in the marine industries, which could potentially change and disrupt the ways how the marine industries operate currently and pave the way to the future shipping.

By implementing Digital Twin into the marine industries, significant scientific breakthroughs, innovations and solutions are expected. Using the proposed multi-level collaborative framework, we can enable efficient technology transfer and intensive technical cooperation. The enhanced collaboration will largely benefit the marine industries and beyond, help the digital transformation of marine businesses, improve ship energy efficiency and help to achieve ambitious goal of GHG emissions reduction globally.

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References

- ABB (2017), *Remote Diagnostics services – Predicting by analyzing*, ABB Global Service, http://new.abb.com/docs/librariesprovider91/leaflets-brochures/rds/digital_level3_leaflet_web1.pdf
- DNV GL (2017), *Software inspired by a broader view – a leading provider of digital solutions*, DNV GL, pp.11-15
- GE Digital (2016), *The rise of Digital Twins*, <https://www.ge.com/digital/blog/rise-digital-twins>
- IBM (2017), *Digital Twin - IBM Watson Internet of Things*, <https://www.ibm.com/internet-of-things/resources/digital-twin>
- IMO (2014), *Third IMO Greenhouse Gas Study 2014*, Int. Maritime Org., London, pp.21
- ROLLS ROYCE (2017), *Rolls-Royce announces investment in Research & Development for Ship Intelligence*, <https://www.rolls-royce.com/media/press-releases/yr-2017/08-03-2017-rr-announces-investment-in-research.aspx>
- WÄRTSILÄ (2017), *Digital transformation, Finland 100 Future of the seas*, <https://www.wartsila.com/finland-100/digitalisation>
- ZOU, G.; KINNUNEN, A.; TERVO, K.; ORIVUORI, J.; VÄNSKÄ, K.; TAMMI, K. (2014), *Evaluate ship energy saving scenarios using multi-domain energy flow simulation*, 13th COMPIT Conf., Redworth, pp.408-417
- ZOU, G. (2017), *Ship energy efficiency technologies - now and the future*, VTT Technology (306), pp.120

Sea Traffic Management – The Route to the Future

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Abstract

The paper outlines how the Sea Traffic Management (STM) concept, is developing to fulfil the many aspects of digitizing an ecosystem. It discusses the importance of framing, the justification of an organisation or industry, and suggest that STM bring a new framing to the whole shipping industry – “share data and benefits”.

1. Introduction - The STM concept is born

A core shipping problem is a lack of means to share and communicate desired events and the times thereof due to problems in information exchange during sea passage. This has made sea transport an isolated and unique industry. Observe, almost 90% of world trade travels by sea. With today's technology, it is possible to increase efficiency by enabling sharing of critical data among stakeholders and at the same time increase safety and security. In the light of the data processing and connectivity efficiencies of digitization, sea transport can be more synchronized and transparent within the entire transportation system during an entire sea passage and its endpoints in port operations, *Haraldson (2015)*. Several initiatives for digitizing the maritime sector have been posited, both commercially and concept wise. Introducing digitization in the maritime sector will also bring opportunities for new business models and contracting models.

In 2009, the concept of Sea Traffic Management (STM), led by the Swedish Maritime Administration, started to take form in a EU-funded project (MONALISA). Then, STM aimed at enhanced safety by allowing ships to share their intentions and routes with shore side actors like VTS or Port Control. At the same time, ports were given the opportunity to receive real-time ETA data during the sea passage from departure berth to arrival berth. The need for standardisation and the potential of data sharing of voyage plan information, both spatial and temporal, past, present and intended was elaborated. Major logistical benefits were anticipated by sharing entire voyage plans and their contained data, instead of just the singularity of the ship. Sharing these data will also enhance safety and security aspects, enable completely new ways of monitoring, and manage sea traffic.

MONALISA was successful and paved the way for another project MONALISA 2.0, which extended STM to embrace safe, efficient, and environmentally sustainable sea transport, *Andersson and Ivehamar (2014)*, *Watson et al. (2015)*. To some extent, this project was inspired by the aviation sector's experiences and lessons from the SESAR program. During this effort, an IEC standard for voyage plans was developed and approved. During MONALISA 2.0, three operational concepts were coined; voyage management, flow management, and port collaborative decision making. Furthermore, the scope of STM was set as berth-to-berth. Consequently, in STM this scope was to include both a ship-centric and a port-centric view tied together with an overall voyage-centric view covering the berth-to-berth process including the port call processes at each end. This also meant that STM undertook the challenge of integrating different practices on a new level; operations at sea and within ports, which had not been previously integrated at scale. By looking at the whole voyage berth to berth and its different operations at the endpoints on a new level a number of previous efficiency-inhibiting problems could be overcome, *Lind et al. (2016)*. Efficiency cannot be pursued without taking into consideration both single and multiple instances of ship movements and a port's current conditions. Efficiency is tightly connected

to environmental sustainability, such as with green steaming, *Watson et al. (2015)*, whereby a ship arrives and is served at a port just-in-time providing foundations for re-evaluating existing contractual models (such as charter parties). STM also creates means to increase safety of navigation by means of shared situational awareness and new efficient ways to organize traffic in dense areas and/or at port visits. At its core, STM connects port efficiency, navigational safety, and sustainability, and creates opportunities to enhance the mode of transport on all levels. *Svedberg (2013)*, *Siwe et al. (2014)*, *Lind et al. (2014)*, *Haraldson (2015)*, *Siwe et al. (2015)*, *Lind et al. (2018a)* have described the basis of STM and the development.

2. Opening up for validation of the STM concept

In June 2015, the EU commission granted funding for one of the largest sea transport project ever lasting from 2015 to 2018. The purpose was to validate the STM concept emanating from MONALISA 2.0 and prepare for its scaled implementation in the maritime industry. As digitization was also knocking on the door in the maritime sector, this made the introduction of STM very relevant because it relies heavily on digital data sharing and connectivity, *IMO (2013)*. Thus, it was appropriate that 2017 was deemed as the year when digitization came to the maritime sector.

3. Revisiting the foundations of digitization of ecosystems: Systems of framing and capital conversion

As Sea Traffic Management addresses an ecosystem, it becomes relevant to re-visit the foundations of such phenomenon, *Adner (2006)*:

- All organizations and ecosystems are in the business of capital creation. (The different types of capital are: natural, economic, human, organisational, social, and symbolic capital.) Typically, they pursue economic capital creation, but some pay prime attention to other forms, such universities on human capital. A shipping company creates economic by using its ships (economic capital) to move products from export to importer
- Organizations can employ multiple combinations of systems of engagement, framing, inquiry, production, and record in their capital conversion repertoire. Shipping is a system of production because it follows routine practices in transporting goods. It also creates a system of record, as do all actors in the ecosystem.
- The goal of an organization or ecosystem is to create a competitive bundle of complementary capitals and capital conversion processes. Digitization is an opportunity to change the competitiveness of a capital bundle.

Table I shows these system types with examples from the shipping sector, *Watson and Seidel (2018)*.

Table I: Ecosystem types

Type	Intended focus	Example
Engagement	Collaboration and coordination	STM
Framing	The reason for behaving in particular ways	Shipping culture
Inquiry	Knowledge production	Data Analytics
Production	Products and services	Movement of goods
Record	Data	AIS, Time stamps

4. Some basic foundations of STM

STM has some key foundations. First, sea transport is a global phenomenon. This means that to extract the full efficiency gains of STM, there must be a high level of global adoption. Second, due to some culturally-determined drag on higher levels of collaboration, the introduction of digitization and greater connectivity to support higher levels of synchronization will challenge current practices and likely require a rewiring of systems of framing.

The STM concept aims at sustainability gains in systems of production, such as berth-to-berth times, to raise capital productivity, as well as providing stakeholders, external to the maritime sector, incentives to utilize shipping in their capital creation processes that require the movement of goods.

Standardized message formats need to be adopted among different stakeholders to enable capital conversion activities to seamlessly connect across organizations. Thus, general adoption of STM's Route Exchange Format (RTZ) and Port Call Message Format (PCMF) is essential, *Lind et al. (2018a)*. The Route Exchange Format provides both the geographical nature of the voyage and the schedule of the whole voyage including departure and arrival times. The port call message provides a basis for sharing intentions and outcomes (in the form of time stamps), such as when a berth is available and needed, associated to movements, services, and status of agreement processes. RTZ has the status of being accredited as an approved IEC standard and PCMF has the status of being proposed as IALA S-211 standard within the GI-registry, *Lind et al. (2018b)*.

The maritime sector is a distributed ecosystem with many competing and autonomous actors. This drives a need for establishing technical interfaces and operational procedures for episodic collaborations, and their facilitation becomes an important factor in enabling integrated systems of production, *Lind et al. (2018c)*. Hence, within the ecosystem there must be agreements of when, what, why, and how to share data. An important cornerstone of STM is that the information provider will control of which recipients (actors and/or cluster of actors) received shared data directly or indirectly.

Importantly, STM must also become concerned with facilitating the sharing of the systems of record for port call participants to provide a basis for port-level analytics (system of inquiry), as part of optimizing the ecosystem's performance. The same goes for providing a basis for optimization providers of voyage management services for voyage-level analytics. Without a holistic understanding of operations, neither a port nor a ship cannot achieve high levels of capital productivity. By the introduction of STM, a move is made from multiple systems of production for each player to an integrated system of production for sea transports berth-to-berth.

STM builds on three enablers, *Lind et al. (2018a)*:

- Voyage management with a focus on supporting a ship, shipping company or port to execute an efficient and safe sea passage berth-to-berth with for example reliable arrival times (estimated and desired) with high accuracy and in real time.
- Flow management with a concern for providing guidance to single or multiple ships in narrow and/or congested waters or waters with other constrains, temporary or permanent to achieve a safe and efficient passage.
- Port collaborative decision making with a focus on preparing and realizing port call operations for just-in-time operations and minimal turn-around time enabling that the port call process can be pursued with a high degree of predictability in its different events. It is important to achieve a high degree of predictability for the time of departure.

These concepts are bound holistically for STM and therefore interrelate in different ways, such as:

- Voyage management and port collaborative decision making interaction: port call synchronization is a common task to ensure that a ship arrives when a port is ready to serve it, as for instance, enabling the ship / shipping company to achieve an optimal speed profile for a voyage or to communicate port operational changes to upcoming operations on arrival.
- Port collaborative decision making and flow management interaction: port call coordination considering multiple ships' and ports' interfaces to a shore centre provider for enhanced situational awareness, safe passage, and for example, allocation of timeslots.
- Voyage management and flow management interaction: ships sharing voyage plans with shore centres to enable the provision of traffic synchronization and monitoring services by the combination of multiple data streams.

Besides these three operational enablers, STM also recommends a technical concept emphasizing interoperability. This digital infrastructure, SeaSWIM, address the need for identity management and service discovery across the industry.

Table II summarizes how STM address all the systems types mentioned in Table I.

Table II: How STM address ecosystem types, *Lind et al. (2018a)*

Type	How this is addressed in STM
Engagement	Technical and operational procedures for collaboration and coordination
Framing	STM is a new frame for raising the industry's efficiency and sustainability.
Inquiry	Foundation for optimization and safety services (such as route optimization, port call optimization, enhanced traffic monitoring and management of traffic flow) being established
Production	Integrated performance in sea transport berth-to-berth
Record	Essential records captured for optimization and integrated performance

5. Hold on to the vision for long-term gains

STM is a vision. It supersedes old frames that are no longer viable in the era of digital data processing and connectivity. Without new ways of thinking and acting, the industry will miss critical opportunities to raise its capital productivity and sustainability.

The realization of STM requires many actors' participation. Actors being part of the value chain need to ensure that their operations are pursued in an integrated manner and service providers need to be encouraged to provide holistic services. We will likely see movements by existing providers to develop proprietary solutions.

STM with its enabling concepts provides an arena for service innovation by providing means for third-party entrepreneurs to provide new services. As elaborated in this paper, common message formats is a first step towards global harmonization. Data sharing through collaboration is an important means for achieving enhanced ecosystem performance. STM provides an arena to develop capabilities towards a long-term vision where smaller pieces, such as a minimal set of state data, are shared in the beginning of paving the way for a system of records with enhanced state sharing, or fragmented routes are shared as a first step towards fully fledged route data sharing as the first step towards a more comprehensive data sharing system. We already see how third-party innovators enter the maritime sector to provide innovative services, as a contribution to capital conversion systems, based on data shared within the maritime sector.

The original data owner will control their data sharing. For example, a terminal operator might share time stamp data with actors within the port to support minimizing vessel turnaround, which should advantage the terminal operator. These data would not be shareable with others outside the port, unless permitted by the terminal operator.

STM provides new features for many actors, both for those responsible for the installed base, as well as for those desiring to become part of maritime ecosystem's service provisioning. Within the STM validation project, 300 ships, 5 shore centres, and 13 ports are engaged in validating STM. This is an important first step to encouraging continual investment in the industry. Up to this point, technical interfaces have been established as a part of the systems of production, such as interfaces and procedures for sharing voyage plans, as well as providing systems of records to support the distributed coordination of port call operations. Systems of inquiry have also been established with diverse analytic and optimization services.

We expect to see other initiatives based on the principles of STM that will enable more integration across the ecosystem. The vision of STM is much larger than the immediate actions that we see today.

There will likely be a balance between emergent vs. regulative standardization. A first step has been taken to elaborate on the necessary technical and operational standardization informed by industry practices.

6. Final words: STM changes the system of framing

A system of framing defines how an organization or industry justifies its role and establishes its mission. When Alfred Sloan took over GM in 1923, he set its frame as, “a car for every purse and purpose”, Sloan (1964), Henry Ford stayed with his earlier frame, “a car painted any color that he wants so long as it is black”, Ford and Crowther (1922), and within a few years GM eclipsed Ford in terms of annual sales. Accepting the STM frame means that each player in shipping industry needs to rethink its systems of engagement, production, record, and inquiry. In particular, it needs to review how it digitizes them and how it shares data within the ecosystem. We urge each member of the shipping industry to take such a review of the impact of digitization on its framing of its purpose, and how digitization affects each of its fundamental systems. STM proposes a holistic frame of sea transport for the multitude of members of the ecosystem. The framing for STM is set as “sharing data and benefits”.

Ford was lucky, its failure to reframe was not fatal, but it never regained market leadership in automotive sales. Can you be so fortunate?

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References

ADNER, R. (2006) *Match your innovation strategy to your innovation ecosystem*, Harvard Business Review

ANDERSSON, P.; IVEHAMMAR, P. (2014), *Economic Impacts - Cost Benefit Analysis of Implementing Dynamic Route Planning at Sea*, MONALISA Project Bureau, Norrköping

FORD, H.; CROWTHER, S.; (1922), *My life and work*, Garden City Publishing, p.72

HARALDSON, S. (2015), *Digitalization of sea transports – Enabling sustainable multi-modal transports*, 21st Americas Conf. Information Systems, Puerto Rico

IMO (2013), *A concept of sustainable maritime transportation system*, Int. Mar. Org., London
<http://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/HotTopics/SMD/Pages/default.aspx>

LIND, M.; KARLSSON, F.; WATSON, R.; BERGMANN, M.; HÄGG, M. (2018a), *Empowering the chain of operations in berth-to-berth sea transports by digitization*, Concept note #8, STM Validation project

LIND M.; BERGMANN M.; WATSON R.T.; HARALDSON S.; PARK J.; GIMENEZ J.; ANDERSON T.; VOORSPUIJ J. (2018b), *Towards unified port communications – From a project format to a global standard*, Concept note #9, STM Validation Project

LIND M.; BERGMANN M.; HARALDSON S.; WATSON R.T.; PARK J.; GIMENEZ J.; ANDERSON T. (2018c), *The skilled collaborator – The winners in the digitized maritime sector*, Concept note #2, STM Validation Project

LIND M.; BRÖDJE A.; WATSON R.T.; HARALDSON S.; HOLMBERG P-E.; HÄGG M. (2014), *Digital infrastructures for enabling sea traffic management*, 10th Int. Symp. ISIS, Hamburg

LIND, M.; HARALDSON, S.; KARLSSON, M.; WATSON, R.T. (2016) *Overcoming the inability to predict - A PortCDM future*, 10th IHMA Congress – Global Port & Marine Operations, Vancouver

SIWE, U.; LIND, M.; HÄGG, M.; DALÉN, A.; BRÖDJE, A.; WATSON, R.T.; HARALDSON, S.; HOLMBERG, P.-E. (2015), *Sea traffic management – Concepts and components*, COMPIT Conf., Ulrichshusen, pp.281-289

SIWE, U.; LIND, M.; SVEDBERG, U. (2014), *Sea traffic management - A concept creating the need for new maritime information standards and software solutions*, COMPIT Conf., Redworth, pp.257-263

SLOAN, A. (1964), *My years with general motors*, Crown Business, p.512

SVEDBERG, U. (2013), *Sharing of complex maritime information*, e-Navigation Underway Conf.

WATSON, R.T.; HOLM, H.; LIND, M. (2015), *Green steaming: A methodology for estimating carbon emissions avoided*, 36th Int. Conf. Information Systems, Fort Worth

WATSON, R.T.; SEIDEL, S. (2018), *From gesture to digitization: Representation and the evolution of social systems*, Working paper, University of Georgia, Athens

Fast Decoding of Automatic Identification Systems (AIS) Data

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Abstract

Decoding large AIS encoded data sets into clear text is time consuming. This paper details an approach on how to structure the innermost part of AIS decoding to increase performance. The method is compared to existing Open Source implementations, as well as to a straight forward example. The proposed approach can increase decoding performance 20-30 times compared to these.

1. Introduction

Automatic Identification System (AIS) is a maritime tracking system that allows ships to broadcast their position, current manoeuvres, and other information to receivers in their area, <https://www.itu.int/rec/R-REC-M.1371/en>. One important purpose with AIS is to facilitate improved on-board navigational safety by allowing the captain to access information about the ship's surroundings even when potential obstacles are obscured from sight or on-board sensors (e.g. radar).

AIS messages are broadcast from ships over VHF radio, and can be accessed by other ships, coastal receivers, and satellites. These receivers can be joined together in networks to cover large areas, such as a country's coast line. Aggregating data from such sources – either by subscription to streaming services (E.g. Swedish Maritime Administration, <http://www.sjofartsverket.se/ais>) or crowd-sourcing (<http://www.aishub.net>) – will over time result in large volumes of historical AIS data. When analysed, stored historical AIS data can provide valuable information, for instance about traffic patterns, *Smith et al. (2013)*, and trends in shipping operations, *Pallotta et al. (2013)*, or to measure compliance of nautical regulations, *Eide et al. (2007)*.

The broadcast format of AIS was designed to be carried on low bandwidth transmissions; the encoded format is therefore compact and suitable for efficient storage. Even though storage today is relatively cheap, the volume of AIS data that is generated is large and growing—as illustration, approximately 1.5GB of encoded AIS messages (AIS messages as NMEA sentences) are generated in Swedish territorial waters per day.

Analysing AIS data from a larger geographical area or time span has many of the characteristics of Big Data, *De Mauro et al. (2015)* – the volume of data poses challenges in terms of both storage and processing with standard tools.

While there are several Open Source libraries for decoding AIS data, they were not necessarily designed to efficiently handle large data volumes. Instead many of the freely available libraries are intended for decoding a live AIS data stream, in which case the data decoding rate is not the limiting factor on a modern computer.

In light of the challenges described above, the use case is to decode AIS messages in sub sets of interest, instead of storing all data decoded. While utilizing the compact nature of the encoded messages to minimize storage requirements, this approach calls for a highly optimized decoding algorithm to minimize the time spent on decoding.

In this paper, we focus on the innermost part of decoding AIS since it is time consuming and has a large impact of the overall running time, if optimized. More specifically, in this paper we show:

- How to structure the AIS data in memory, including an example in C (Section III)
- How to retrieve data fields, also including an example in C (Section III)

- That the above increase performance by a factor of 20-30 compared to a straight forward approach (Section IV)
- That the above increase performance by a factor of 19 and 34 compared to two existing Open Source libraries (Section IV)

2. Background and approach

Encoded AIS is received as NMEA 0183 sentences. The AIS data payload in each NMEA sentence consists of ASCII armoured six-bit bytes in network byte order (i.e., Big Endian), <http://catb.org/gpsd/AIVDM.html>. (Throughout this paper "six-bit bytes" refer to bytes where only six of the available eight bits can be used. Analogically, "eight-bit bytes" means all bits can be used.) That is, six bits are used for data and the bytes are sent in the reverse order compared to what is used on modern, Intel-based computers.

Decoding AIS consist of:

1. Removing the ASCII armour
2. Converting the resulting six-bit bytes
3. Extracting the fields of information.

To de-armour the data, every byte is subtracted by the value 48. (All values in this paragraph are decimal.) But, the 8 value interval from 88 to 95 (ASCII characters "X" to "_") are not allowed according to the standard, so in case a byte value is larger than 87, 56 is subtracted from that byte (i.e., $48 + 8$).

Conversion is the process of removing the unused bits (i.e., packing the six-bit bytes as eight-bit bytes). The converted bytes represent binary encoded fields of data, the smallest being a single bit and the largest several bytes.

Extracting a field requires, given a start bit and an end bit, to mask out the bits that represent a specific field and load it into a variable.

There exist 27 different types of messages, <https://www.itu.int/rec/R-REC-M.1371/en>, each with its own decoding scheme in terms of which bits mean what and of which data type. There is an IALA document that supposedly further defines technical aspects of messages and their content, *IALA (2001)*, but it is not publicly available, and the authors of this paper have not read it.

The approach to speeding up decoding consists of the following three parts:

- A. Use a lookup table for the de-armouring of each incoming byte
- B. Process several bytes at a time instead of copying over one bit at the time from the input bytes.
- C. Store the converted bytes in reverse order. That is, to put the first incoming byte at the end of the result buffer.

2.1. Version A

The straight forward approach shown below serves as an example of how to decode AIS data and retrieve the values of fields. It is straight forward in its imperative programming structure, solving each sub-task one at a time in order.

Fig.1 shows an example of how to remove the armouring by subtracting by one of the two constants, where the constant depends on the value of the input byte (detailed in 1).

```
char dearmored = b > 87 ? b - 56 : b - 48;
```

Fig.1: Example of dearmouring

After dearmouring, the string of six-bit bytes is converted into eight-bit bytes. Conversion is, in this version, done by copying every bit, one at a time, from the source string into a destination string. This using two position references, one for each string, Fig.2.

Fig.2: Dearmoured and converted bytes, including bit positions, in Version A. Converted 'Byte 1' stored at the lowest memory address

The data fields can be extracted after conversion. Each field use only a minimum of bits to store the data, with the desired precision. Few of the fields use even bytes for values and in most cases a field does not start nor end at the byte boundary, so shifting bits and masking is usually necessary.

As an example, in order to retrieve a field starting at bit 6 and ending at bit 13, then byte 1 (containing bits 6 and 7) needs to be shifted left 8 steps. Byte 2 (containing bits 8 to 15) is assigned as the low byte. The resulting two bytes then needs to be shifted right two steps, to remove bits 14 and 15, and masked to remove bits 0 to 5 (See Fig.1 for bit index). Fig.3 shows a straight-forward approach to convert a string of six-bit bytes.

```
static int convert_simple(char* input, int in_bytes, char* output, int
output_sz){
    for(int i = 0, j = 0; i < 6*in_bytes; i++, j++){
        // indices to input and output buffers
        int in_byte = i/6;
        int in_bit = i%6;
        int out_byte = i/8;
        int out_bit = i%8;

        // Get and de-armour the whole byte
        int v = input[in_byte];
        v = v > 88 ? v - 56 : v - 48;

        // Shift right to the current bit
        v = (v >> (5 - in_bit)) & 0x01;

        // Shift left to the right output location
        v = (v << (7 - out_bit));

        // Store the bit
        output[out_byte] |= v;
    }
    return 1;
}
```

Fig.3: Straight-forward approach to convert a string of six-bit bytes

The example below shows a straight-forward approach to retrieving values. A byte is loaded in the low end of the result. For each succeeding byte, the already loaded ones are shifted left. Finally, the result is shifted right if there are unused bits at the far right and then masked.

```

static int retrieve_field_simple(char* input, int startbit, int endbit)
{
    int startbyte = startbit/8;
    int nr_bytes = (endbit - startbit)/8 + 1;

    // Values are never more than 4 bytes
    int v = 0;

    for (int i = 0; i < nr_bytes; i++) {
        char b = input[startbyte + i];

        // Make room for the next byte
        v = v << 8;
        v |= b;
    }

    // Right shift when the field does not start at the boundary
    v = v >> (7 - endbit%8);

    // Clear bits left of the end
    v = v & ~(~(0ULL) << (endbit - startbit));

    return v;
}

```

Fig.4: Straight-forward approach to retrieving values

2.2. Version B

This section describes an alternative, faster approach to decoding, compared to the one outlined in 2.1. The approach has the same result, the difference in less branching (likely less CPU pipeline stalls) and handling larger chunks in each iteration. Dearmouring is done by a precalculated lookup table, which removes the branching instruction and the need to subtract. The storage need for the lookup table is only 256 bytes, which on modern computers fits in any of the caches.

Fig.5: Dearmoured and converted bytes, including bit positions, in Version B. Converted 'Byte 1' stored at the highest memory address

In Fig.2 the storage of converted bytes is reversed compared to Fig.1, such that the first dearmoured byte is stored at the highest memory address. The purpose is to remove logic from both the conversion and the retrieval of field values. When converting, 4 six-bit bytes are packed into 3 eight-bit bytes and then stored using a pointer. In each iteration, the pointer is moved and the next 4 six-bit bytes are packed.

```

static int convert_fast(char* input, int in_bytes, char* output, int
output_sz){
    // fast conversion
    for(int i = 0, j = output_sz - 3; i < in_bytes; i += 4, j -= 3){
        // Retrieve and de-armour 4 six-bit bytes
        char v1 = dearmour_table[input[i]];
        char v2 = dearmour_table[input[i+1]];
        char v3 = dearmour_table[input[i+2]];
        char v4 = dearmour_table[input[i+3]];
        // Pack them as 3 eight-bit bytes, stored in an int
        int v = (v1 << 18) | (v2 << 12) | (v3 << 6) | (v4);
        // Get a pointer into the output buffer
        int* o = (int*)(output + j);
        // Store the value at the pointer location
        *o |= v;
    }
    return 1;
}

```

Fig.6: Fast approach to convert a string of six-bit bytes

To retrieve a value a pointer to the byte containing the end bit is set. The pointer is dereferenced and the value stored in a variable. This without the need to left shift bytes, as needed in Version A. Lastly, if necessary, the value is shifted right and masked.

```

static int retrieve_field_fast(char* input, int input_sz, int startbit,
int endbit){
    int startbyte = (input_sz - 1) - startbit/8;
    int endbyte = (input_sz - 1) - endbit/8;
    // Pointer reference to byte that contains end bit
    int* p1 = (int*)&(input[endbyte]);
    // Contains end bit byte and 3 more bytes
    int v = *p1;
    // Right shift when the field does not start at the boundary
    v = v >> (7 - endbit%8);
    // Clear bits left of the end
    v = v & ~(~(0ULL) << (endbit - startbit));
    return v;
}

```

Fig.7: Fast approach to retrieving values

3. Analysis

In this section, version A (straight forward) is compared in complexity and assembly output against version B (optimised). Version B is also compared in running time performance against two commonly used Open Source libraries.

3.1. Complexity

The traditional big O analysis measures the complexity in terms of growth rate, which is the same in both versions. They both iterate the incoming bytes once, so big O is O(n). However, in practical use

the value of the preceding constant factor is also of interest since it is roughly a multiplier on the running time of a program. The factor can be estimated by counting the number of pseudo instructions; assignments, data retrievals and operations (add, subtract, etc.) performed in each version.

- Version A contains 23 pseudo instructions inside the conversion loop. The loop is performed $6*n$ times for n number of bytes. This gives a total of $133*n$ executed instructions.
- Version B contains 22 instructions inside the conversion loop, but it only iterates, in worst case $(n + 1)/4$ times. This gives $22/4 * (n + 1) \approx 5n + 5$ executed instructions.

The quotient of the number of pseudo instructions in each version is approximately 25, thus, in theory, 25 times the performance gain. This is not including the reduction when extracting the data fields, which will further add to the theoretical gain.

3.2. Assembly

When compiling the two versions with the GCC compiler, with full optimisation turned on (-O3), the generated assembly contains the following number of instructions for the conversion loop.

- Version A - 40 instructions
- Version B - 5 instructions

The retrieval function contains the following number of instructions:

- Version A - 13 instructions
- Version B - 3 instructions

The quotient of Version A divided by Version B is 8 for the conversion and approximately 4 for the retrieval. With a theoretical unpacking that constitutes of 1 conversion and 6 field retrievals the total number of pseudo instructions is:

- Version A - $40+6*13 = 118$
- Version B - $5+6*3 = 23$

The quotient would then be approximately 5, meaning 5 times the performance gain. Note that this is done using the GCC compiler. Other compilers might produce a different result.

The running time for three different decoding programs are shown in Fig.8. Version B is the method described in this paper, “TB Salling”, <https://github.com/tbsalling/aismessages>, is an Open Source Java library and “Schwehr”, <https://github.com/schwehr/libais>, is an Open Source Python library (inner loop in C++). All three programs decoded the same three datasets and output the same data. The data sets consisted of 100K, 1M and 10M AIS messages collected from AISHub, <http://www.aishub.net>. The output was AIS Message type 1, 2 and 3, and the fields:

- MMSI
- Message Type
- Longitude
- Latitude
- Course over ground
- Speed over ground

The lines in Fig.8 show a linear increase in computational time, although with a very different constant factor. The quotient between Version B and the other two libraries, based on the time it took to decode the largest dataset, are:

- Schwehr / Version B : $171/5 = 34$
- TBSalling / Version B : $95/5 = 19$

Fig.8: Computational time in seconds for three different AIS decoding libraries

4. Discussion

It was shown in this paper that it is possible to speed up the conversion and field retrieval by using the proposed layout of the bytes to decode. However, conversion and data retrieval are only one part of decoding AIS. Other parts, such as error checking the input, splitting it up, CRC-check and several other operations, also take time. In order to achieve really high performance, it is necessary to optimise all parts of the decoding, not only the ones described in this paper.

The comparison in IV is done between libraries written in three different languages. In the case of Fast Decode it has the advantage of being written in C, a language with a small overhead in terms of memory management and built in features. The source code is compiled with the GCC C compiler, so the program runs natively. GCC also has very good optimisation, which is seen in the assembly comparison in section IV.

The other two are written in Python and Java - languages with much more overhead than C. Both of them are executed using their Virtual Machines, which means that they do not run natively. Running in Virtual Machine is a disadvantage performance wise compared to C, but that does not account for all of the performance difference, *Prechelt (2003)* shown in section IV.

There are other open-source libraries but the ones in this comparison were chosen since they are frequently mentioned and used.

5. Conclusions and future work

It is possible to achieve a significant speed up when decoding AIS data, shown by comparison of two frequently used Open Source libraries and in a more general case, given that the current structure of such a library is similar to the straight forward approach (Version A). Decoding is a time-consuming effort when dealing with large sets of AIS data, even more so in the use case of repeatedly loading different subsets for analysis. The presented optimisation reduces that effort. Since the proposed optimisation is limited to the most internal part of decoding and the retrieval of fields, it is likely possible to easily implement it in existing AIS decoding software, such as the libraries used in the analysis, or other commercial software.

As stated in the discussion there are more aspects to consider when decoding AIS. By minimising the time spent in the inner loop then time spent in other parts becomes visible, such as tokenisation of the input and how to load and store AIS data into a relational database most efficiently.

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References

IALA (2001), *IALA technical clarifications to Recommendation ITU-R M.1371-1*, https://www.itu.int/dms_pubrec/itu-r/rec/m/R-REC-M.1371-1-200108-S!!PDF-E.pdf

DE MAURO, A.; GRECO, M.; GRIMALDI, M. (2015), *What is big data? A consensual definition and a review of key research topics*, AIP Conf. Vol. 1644, pp. 97-104

EIDE, M.S.; ENDRESEN, O.; BRETT, P.O.; ERVIK, J.L.; RØANG, K. (2007), *Intelligent ship traffic monitoring for oil spill prevention: Risk based decision support building on AIS*, Marine Pollution Bulletin 54, pp.145–148

PALLOTTA, G.; VESPE, M.; BRYAN, K. (2013), *Vessel Pattern Knowledge Discovery from AIS Data: A Framework for Anomaly Detection and Route Prediction*, Entropy 15/6, pp.2218-2245

PRECHELT, L. (2003), *Are scripting languages any good? A validation of Perl, Python, REXX, and Tcl against C, C++, and Java*, Advances in Computers 57, pp.205-270

SMITH, T.; O'KEEFFE, E.; ALDOUS, L.; AGNOLUCCI, P. (2013), *Assessment of Shipping's Efficiency Using Satellite AIS data*, Report UCL, London, https://www.theicct.org/sites/default/files/publications/UCL_ship_efficiency_forICCT_2013.pdf

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18th Conference on
Computer Applications and Information Technology in the Maritime Industries

COMPIT'19

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In Design, Production and Operation of Maritime Systems

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